

D3.21 Fifth Periodic Report on JRPs

WP3

Responsible Partner: Sciensano

Contributing partners: ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	69 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D3.21 Fifth Periodic Report on JRPs
WP and task	WP3
Leader	Sciensano
Other contributors	ANSES
Due month of the deliverable	M63
Actual submission month	M64
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 17-Apr-23
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU See updated Grant Agreement
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> WOA <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):.....</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

FIFTH PERIODIC REPORT ON JRPS

Contents

CONTENTS.....	3
1 INTRODUCTION.....	6
1.1 PROJECT DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES	6
1.2 PUBLICATIONS.....	7
1.3 IMPACT AND RELEVANCE OF THE RESEARCH PROJECTS	35
2 REPORTS OF THE JRP, YEAR 5	38
2.1 JRP12-R2-AMRSH5-FARMED	38
2.1.1 Consortium composition.....	38
2.1.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project	38
2.1.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	39
2.1.4 Project self-assessment	60
2.1.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	62
2.1.6 Publications and additional outputs.....	70
2.1.7 One Health impact	74
2.1.8 Data Management Plan	75
2.1.9 Future dissemination activities.....	75
2.2 JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	76
2.2.1 Consortium composition.....	76
2.2.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project	76
2.2.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	77
2.2.4 Project self-assessment	84
2.2.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	86
2.2.6 Publications and additional outputs.....	92
2.2.7 One Health impact	102
2.2.8 Data Management Plan	103
2.2.9 Future dissemination activities.....	103
2.3 JRP14-R2-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	105
2.3.1 Consortium composition.....	105
2.3.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project	105
2.3.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	106
2.3.4 Project self-assessment	115
2.3.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	117
2.3.6 Publications and additional outputs.....	132
2.3.7 One Health impact	135
2.3.8 Data Management Plan	136
2.3.9 Future dissemination activities.....	136
2.4 JRP15-R2-AMR2.1-FED-AMR.....	137
2.4.1 Consortium composition.....	137
2.4.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project	139
2.4.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	141
2.4.4 Project self-assessment	155
2.4.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	157
2.4.6 Publications and additional outputs.....	176
2.4.7 One Health impact	185
2.4.8 Data Management Plan	186
2.4.9 Future dissemination activities.....	187

2.5	JRP16-R2-ET2.2-TELE-VIR	188
2.5.1	Consortium composition.....	188
2.5.2	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	188
2.5.3	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	189
2.5.4	Project self-assessment	203
2.5.5	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	204
2.5.6	Publications and additional outputs.....	213
2.5.7	One Health impact	216
2.5.8	Data Management Plan	217
2.5.9	Future dissemination activities.....	217
2.6	JRP17-R2-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	218
2.6.1	Consortium composition.....	218
2.6.2	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	218
2.6.3	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	219
2.6.4	Project self-assessment	243
2.6.5	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	244
2.6.6	Publications and additional outputs.....	258
2.6.7	One Health impact	261
2.6.8	Data Management Plan	261
2.6.9	Future dissemination activities.....	262
2.7	JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEME.....	263
2.7.1	Consortium composition.....	263
2.7.2	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	264
2.7.3	Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	266
2.7.4	Project self-assessment	295
2.7.5	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	298
2.7.6	Publications and additional outputs.....	305
2.7.7	One Health impact	313
2.7.8	Data Management Plan	314
2.7.9	Future dissemination activities.....	314
2.8	JRP19-R2-ET1.1-PARADISE	315
2.8.1	Consortium composition.....	315
2.8.2	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	315
2.8.3	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	316
2.8.4	Project self-assessment	332
2.8.5	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	334
2.8.6	Publications and additional outputs.....	341
2.8.7	One Health impact	345
2.8.8	Data Management Plan	345
2.8.9	Future dissemination activities.....	345
2.9	JRP20-R2-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	346
2.9.1	Consortium composition.....	346
2.9.2	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	347
2.9.3	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes.....	348
2.9.4	Project self-assessment	367
2.9.5	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables	371
2.9.6	Publications and additional outputs.....	378
2.9.7	One Health impact	384
2.9.8	Data Management Plan	385
2.9.9	Future dissemination activities.....	385
2.10	JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE.....	386
2.10.1	Consortium composition	386
2.10.2	Summary of the work carried out in the Project	386
2.10.3	Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes	387
2.10.4	Project self-assessment.....	404
2.10.5	Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables.....	406
2.10.6	Publications and additional outputs	418

2.10.7	<i>One Health impact</i>	424
2.10.8	<i>Data Management Plan</i>	424
2.10.9	<i>Future dissemination activities</i>	424
2.11	JRP22-R2-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	426
2.11.1	<i>Consortium composition</i>	426
2.11.2	<i>Summary of the work carried out in the Project</i>	427
2.11.3	<i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	428
2.11.4	<i>Project self-assessment</i>	440
2.11.5	<i>Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables</i>	442
2.11.6	<i>Publications and additional outputs</i>	450
2.11.7	<i>One Health impact</i>	474
2.11.8	<i>Data Management Plan</i>	475
2.11.9	<i>Future dissemination activities</i>	475
2.12	JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS	476
2.12.1	<i>Consortium composition</i>	476
2.12.2	<i>Summary of the work carried out in the Project</i>	476
2.12.3	<i>Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	477
2.12.4	<i>Project self-assessment</i>	494
2.12.5	<i>Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables</i>	496
2.12.6	<i>Publications and additional outputs</i>	503
2.12.7	<i>One Health impact</i>	506
2.12.8	<i>Data Management Plan</i>	507
2.12.9	<i>Future dissemination activities</i>	507
2.13	JRP24-R2-FBZSH9-BEONE	508
2.13.1	<i>Consortium composition</i>	508
2.13.2	<i>Summary of the work carried out in the Project</i>	508
2.13.3	<i>Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	509
2.13.4	<i>Project self-assessment</i>	519
2.13.5	<i>Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables</i>	521
2.13.6	<i>Publications and additional outputs</i>	528
2.13.7	<i>One Health impact</i>	531
2.13.8	<i>Data Management Plan</i>	532
2.13.9	<i>Future dissemination activities</i>	533

FIFTH PERIODIC REPORT ON JRPS

1 Introduction

The actual document is complementary to the technical part of the One Health EJP Periodic Report, which describes all the activities within the seven work packages of the project. This JRP-specific document contains more details, and is composed of all final reports of the projects that have come to an end in 2022.

All publications and deliverables are available through the specific project pages on the One Health EJP website: <https://onehealthjep.eu/projects/>.

1.1 Project deliverables and milestones

An overview of the actual number of deliverables per project is given in the following table. Although all JRP have come to an end in 2022 and no further scientific activities were allowed in 2023, still some deliverables are missing. The Project Leaders gave various reasons, i.e.

- Despite the instructions, some work is still going on (but no reimbursement of expenses is allowed) (WORLD-COM).
- The Project Leader of FULL-FORCE confirmed that two protocols were not finalized due to the premature departure of a key scientist.
- One deliverable was still ongoing (FED-AMR). The project leader is following this point and has contacted the Work Package leader. Zenodo link will be provided as soon as possible.
- In some cases, the departure of a collaborator resulted in only a partial delivery (FED-AMR, TELE-Vir).
- The dissemination plan of the ADONIS project was not delivered separately, but recommendations to disseminate to EFSA and ECDC and to the scientific community are described in the final report.
- In PARADISE, the detection of the parasites by metagenomics approaches turned out to be unsuccessful with a metabarcoding platform and therefore, comparison with shotgun metagenomics was not possible. In addition, the identification of aptamers with the desired affinity was unsuccessful and therefore parasite enrichment experiments that should have led to a SOP and to inter-laboratory tests, could not be performed.
- IDEMBRU: Covid-19 has severely impacted the project. Several laboratories had to close, partners had to dedicate more than 80% of their time to testing for more than two thirds of the project. The BSL3 facility had to be closed for 6 months during 2022, which impaired characterization of new isolated strains and preparation of in vivo infections. Furthermore, the project encountered delays and loss of RNA-seq expert who started matrix development and data analysis. All of this led to delays or cancellation of some deliverables.

These justifications seem to be reasonable and therefore the limited delay and even cancellation of some deliverables does not jeopardise the global output of the One Health EJP.

PROJECT	DUE DELIVERABLES in Y5	DELIVERED in Y5	% DELIVERED	DELAYED
JRP12-FARMED	7	7	100%	0
JRP13-WORLDCOM	8	7	88%	1
JRP14-FULLFORCE	34	32	94%	2
JRP15-FED-AMR	33	32	97%	1
JRP16-TELE-Vir	16	15	94%	1
JRP17-IDEMBRU	23	21	91%	2
JRP18-MEME	25	25	100%	0
JRP19-PARADISE	20	16	80%	4
JRP20-DISCOVER	13	13	100%	0
JRP21-BIOPIGEE	29	29	100%	0
JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	15	15	100%	0
JRP23-ADONIS	17	16	94%	1
JRP24-BeONE	17	17	100%	0
TOTAL	257	245	95%	12

PROJECT	MILESTONES PLANNED in Y5	MILESTONES ACHIEVED in Y5	% ACHIEVED
JRP12-FARMED	17	17	100%
JRP13-WORLDCOM	16	12	75%
JRP14-FULLFORCE	25	25	100%
JRP15-FEDAMR	48	48	100%
JRP16-TELE-Vir	17	17	100%
JRP17-IDEMBRU	52	49	94%
JRP18-MEME	21	21	100%
JRP19-PARADISE	20	20	100%
JRP20-DISCOVER	25	24	96%
JRP21-BIOPIGEE	35	34	97%
JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	20	20	100%
JRP23-ADONIS	19	18	95%
JRP24-BeONE	31	31	100%
TOTAL	346	336	97%

1.2 Publications

In total there are 190 published JRP manuscripts (2 manuscripts in 2018, 12 manuscripts in 2019, 60 manuscripts in 2020, 48 manuscripts in 2021, 57 manuscripts in 2022 and 11 manuscripts in 2023). Round 1 projects are still publishing manuscripts (13 manuscripts in 2022 and 4 manuscripts in 2023). More than one and half a year after the end of the projects, round 1 projects still deliver publications and the same situation is expected to be the case for round 2 projects. Likely, the number of published manuscripts will continue to increase even after the end of the One Health EJP.

In addition to that, the One Health EJP Consortium has published 6 manuscripts concerning One Health initiatives, particularly showcasing the importance of multidisciplinary, cross-sector collaboration, within and across countries. These manuscripts are more strategic and focus on the outcomes of the One Health EJP initiatives that can be taken up by parties, also outside the actual consortium. These publications are listed below, after the JRP manuscripts.

These publications particularly showcase the importance of multidisciplinary, cross-sector collaboration, within and across countries.

From a practical point of view, the Project Leaders are well aware that all the manuscripts must be uploaded to Zenodo. Unfortunately, some Zenodo repository links may be missing in this report (and on the EU Participant Portal). The WP3 and Communications teams are following up on this issue and will ensure that the missing repository links will become available.

2018 – 2 JRP publications

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review. Møller FT, Mølbak K, Ethelberg S.

Eurosurveillance. 2018;23(24). doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2018.23.24.1700503

https://zenodo.org/record/3747633#XpCQ_sgZM0

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola* and Related Phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Brisse S.

Front Microbiol. 2018;9:3000. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660887#XkEm5mhKiUk>

2019 – 12 JRP publications

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Antimicrobial Usages and Antimicrobial Resistance in Commensal *Escherichia coli* From Veal Calves in France: Evolution During the Fattening Process.

Gay E, Bour M, Cazeau G, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2019;10:792. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.00792

https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#YAqc_uhKjcc

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: The shufflon of IncI1 plasmids is rearranged constantly during different growth conditions.

Brouwer MSM, Jurburg SD, Harders F, et al.

Plasmid. 2019;102:51-55. doi:10.1016/j.plasmid.2019.03.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730621#Xn3MyYhKi70>

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR: Attributable sources of community-acquired carriage of *Escherichia coli* containing β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes: a population-based modelling study. *The Lancet* Mughini-Gras L, Dorado-García A, van Duijkeren E, et al.

Planetary Health. 2019;3(8):e357-e369. doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(19)30130-5

<https://zenodo.org/record/3621285#Xjl8UGhKhPY>

JRP04-ET1-MADVIR: Field samplings of *Ixodes ricinus* ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus micro-focus in Northern Zealand, Denmark.

Petersen A, Rosenstjerne MW, Rasmussen M, et al.

Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases. 2019;10(5):1028-1032. doi:10.1016/j.ttbdis.2019.05.005

<https://zenodo.org/record/3634258#Xjl8d2hKhPY>

JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT: Point-of-Need DNA Testing for Detection of Foodborne Pathogenic Bacteria.

Vidic J, Vizzini P, Manzano M, et al.

Sensors. 2019;19(5):1100. doi:10.3390/s19051100

<https://zenodo.org/record/3935799#X6Ud-GhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: An outbreak of monophasic *Salmonella* Typhimurium associated with raw pork sausage and other pork products, Denmark 2018–19.

Helmuth IG, Espenhain L, Ethelberg S, et al.

Epidemiol Infect. 2019;147:e315. doi:10.1017/S0950268819002073

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249319#.X6UIWmhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi *Salmonella*-related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, clinical aspects, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs.

Garrido-Esteba M, Latasa P, Ordóñez-León GY, Martínez-Avilés M, de la Torre A, García-Comas L.

Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis. 2019;38(2):337-346. doi:10.1007/s10096-018-3433-1

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244788#.X6LhGYhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: *Salmonella* Surveillance Systems in Swine and Humans in Spain: A Review.

Martínez-Avilés M, Garrido-Esteba M, Álvarez J, de la Torre A.

Veterinary Sciences. 2019;6(1):20. doi:10.3390/vetsci6010020

<https://zenodo.org/record/3635293#.XjlyUGhKhPY>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Whole genome sequencing reveals resemblance between ESBL-producing and carbapenem resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates from Austrian rivers and clinical isolates from hospitals.

Lepuschitz S, Schill S, Stoeger A, et al.

Science of The Total Environment. 2019;662:227-235. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.179

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249232#.X6UhA2hKjcc>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Description of *Klebsiella africanensis* sp. nov., *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. tropicalensis subsp. nov. and *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. variicola subsp. nov.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Diallo TA, Criscuolo A, Brisse S.

Research in Microbiology. 2019;170(3):165-170. doi:10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660879#.XkEmO2hKiUk>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Description of *Klebsiella spallanzanii* sp. nov. and of *Klebsiella pasteurii* sp. nov.

Merla C, Rodrigues C, Passet V, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2019;10:2360. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.02360

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660875#.XkEICGhKiUk>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Outbreak of Yersiniabactin-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit:

Wisgrill L, Lepuschitz S, Blaschitz M, et al.

The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal. 2019;38(6):638-642.

doi:10.1097/INF.0000000000002258

<https://zenodo.org/record/3661013#.XkFq-OSWwj9>

2020 – 60 JRP publications

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART and JRP14-FULL-FORCE : Novel IncFII Plasmid Harboursing *Bla* NDM-4 in a Carbapenem-Resistant *Escherichia Coli* of Pig Origin, Italy.

Diaconu, E. L.; Carfora, V.; Alba, P.; Di Matteo, P.; Stravino, F.; Buccella, C.; Dell’Aira, E.; Onorati, R.; Sorbara, L.; Battisti, A.; Franco, A.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2020, 75 (12), 3475–3479

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa374>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4451840#.YAfPRNhKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Spill-Over from Public Health? First Detection of an OXA-48-Producing Escherichia Coli in a German Pig Farm.

Irrgang, A.; Pauly, N.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Grobbel, M.; Kaesbohrer, A.; Hammerl, J. A. *Microorganisms* 2020, 8 (6), 855.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8060855>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4447289#.YAWijthKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: First Detection of GES-5-Producing Escherichia Coli from Livestock—An Increasing Diversity of Carbapenemases Recognized from German Pig Production.

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Irrgang, A.; Tausch, S. H.; Pauly, N.; Grobbel, M.; Kaesbohrer, A.; Hammerl, J. A. *Microorganisms* 2020, 8 (10), 1593.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8101593>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4451836#.YAfzdhKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: ChromID® CARBA Agar Fails to Detect Carbapenem-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae With Slightly Reduced Susceptibility to Carbapenems.

Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Grobbel, M.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Käsbohrer, A.; Bisenius, S.; Fuchs, J.; Horlacher, S.; Lingstädt, H.; Mauermann, U.; Mitro, S.; Müller, M.; Rohrmann, S.; Schiffmann, A. P.; Stührenberg, B.; Zimmermann, P.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Irrgang, A. *Front. Microbiol.* 2020, 11, 1678.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.01678>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4447313#.YA7QnehKjcc>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Identification of a BlaVIM-1-Carrying IncA/C2 Multiresistance Plasmid in an Escherichia Coli Isolate Recovered from the German Food Chain.

Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Grobbel, M.; Käsbohrer, A.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Malorny, B.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Irrgang, A.

Microorganisms 2020, 9 (1), 29.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010029>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4451858#.YAfqINhKg2w>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries.

Mesa Varona, O.; Chaintarli, K.; Muller-Pebody, B.; Anjum, M. F.; Eckmanns, T.; Norström, M.; Boone, I.; Tenhagen, B.-A.

IDR 2020, Volume 13, 957–993.

<https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S237038>
<https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: blaCTX–M–1/IncI1-ly Plasmids Circulating in Escherichia coli From Norwegian Broiler Production Are Related, but Distinguishable.

Mo SS, Telke AA, Osei KO, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2020;11:333.

doi:10.3389/fmicb.2020.00333

<https://zenodo.org/record/3701226#.YAcqSehKjcc>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Temporal dynamics of the fecal microbiota in veal calves in a 6-month field trial.

Massot M, Haenni M, Nguyen TT, Madec J-Y, Mentré F, Denamur E.

anim microbiome. 2020;2(1):32.

doi:10.1186/s42523-020-00052-6

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAcfnuhKjcc>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: The importance of using whole genome sequencing and extended spectrum beta-lactamase selective media when monitoring antimicrobial resistance.

Duggett N, AbuOun M, Randall L, et al.

Sci Rep. 2020;10(1):19880.

doi:10.1038/s41598-020-76877-7

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAqkH-hKjcc>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization via multicopy plasmid encapsidation mediated by temperate phages.

Rodríguez-Rubio L, Serna C, Ares-Arroyo M, et al.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy. Published online July 28, 2020:dkaa311.

doi:10.1093/jac/dkaa311

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244116#.X6KBDjiWxMO>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries

Mesa Varona O, Chaintarli K, Muller-Pebody B, et al.

IDR. 2020;Volume 13:957-993.

doi:10.2147/IDR.S237038

<https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Stepwise evolution and convergent recombination underlie the global dissemination of carbapenemase-producing *Escherichia coli*.

Patiño-Navarrete R, Rosinski-Chupin I, Cabanel N, et al.

Genome Med. 2020;12(1):10.

doi:10.1186/s13073-019-0699-6

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Mobile Colistin Resistance Gene *Mcr-1* Detected on an *Incl1* Plasmid in *Escherichia Coli* from Meat.

Brouwer, M. S. M.; Goodman, R. N.; Kant, A.; Mevius, D.; Newire, E.; Roberts, A. P.; Veldman, K. T. *Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance* 2020, 23, 145–148.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2020.08.018>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4475507#.YQJhJTh7mVN>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Phenotypical Antimicrobial Resistance Data of Clinical and Non-Clinical *Escherichia Coli* from Poultry in Germany between 2014 and 2017.

Mesa-Varona, O.; Kaspar, H.; Grobbel, M.; Tenhagen, B.-A.

PLoS ONE 2020, 15 (12), e0243772.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243772>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Colistin-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae Isolated From Process Waters and Wastewater From German Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses.

Savin, M.; Bierbaum, G.; Blau, K.; Parcina, M.; Sib, E.; Smalla, K.; Schmithausen, R.; Heinemann, C.; Hammerl, J. A.; Kreyenschmidt, J.

Front. Microbiol. 2020, 11, 575391.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.575391>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4981351#.YP7O5Th7m9I>

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR: Analysis of COMPASS, a New Comprehensive Plasmid Database Revealed Prevalence of Multireplicon and Extensive Diversity of *IncF* Plasmids.

Douarre P-E, Mallet L, Radomski N, Felten A, Mistou M-Y.
Front Microbiol. 2020;11:483.
doi:10.3389/fmicb.2020.00483
<https://zenodo.org/record/3968418#.XyQSQTgUIM2>

JRP04-ET1-MADVIR: Novel enteric viruses in fatal enteritis of grey squirrels.
Dastjerdi A, Benfield C, Everest D, Stidworthy MF, Zell R.
Journal of General Virology. 2020;101(7):746-750.
doi:10.1099/jgv.0.001431
<https://zenodo.org/record/4249097#.X6kclGhKhM0>

JRP05-TOX-Detect: Advanced Methods for Detection of Bacillus Cereus and Its Pathogenic Factors.
Ramarao, N.; Tran, S.-L.; Marin, M.; Vidic, J.
Sensors 2020, 20 (9), 2667.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/s20092667>
<https://zenodo.org/record/3933055#.YVcVMJpBy70>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Modelling spread and surveillance of Mycobacterium avium subsp. paratuberculosis in the Swedish cattle trade network.
Rosendal T, Widgren S, Ståhl K, Frössling J.
Preventive Veterinary Medicine. 2020;183:105152.
doi:10.1016/j.prevetmed.2020.105152
<https://zenodo.org/record/4450338>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Using stochastic dynamic modelling to estimate the sensitivity of current and alternative surveillance program of Salmonella in conventional broiler production.
Apenteng OO, Arnold ME, Vigre H.
Sci Rep. 2020;10(1):19441.
doi:10.1038/s41598-020-76514-3
<https://zenodo.org/record/4271431#.X65ljTiWxPY>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Climatic and topographic tolerance limits of wild boar in Eurasia: implications for their expansion.
Bosch J, Iglesias I, Martínez M, De la Torre A.
GES. 2020;13(1):107-114.
doi:10.24057/2071-9388-2019-52
<https://zenodo.org/record/4244729#.X6LYN4hKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Identifying emerging trends in antimicrobial resistance using Salmonella surveillance data in poultry in Spain.
Alvarez J, Lopez G, Muellner P, et al.
Transbound Emerg Dis. 2020;67(1):250-262.
doi:10.1111/tbed.13346
<https://zenodo.org/record/3660026#.XvyQnGgzZM0>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Spatial Trends in Salmonella Infection in Pigs in Spain.
Teng KT, Martinez Avilés M, Ugarte-Ruiz M, et al.
Front Vet Sci. 2020;7:345.
doi:10.3389/fvets.2020.00345
https://zenodo.org/record/4244797#.X6Li_lhKjcc

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: First Report on the Finding of *Listeria monocytogenes* ST121 Strain in a Dolphin Brain.

Sévellec Y, Torresi M, Félix B, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(10):802.

doi:10.3390/pathogens9100802

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244051#.X6J4fziWxM1>

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Genetic Characterization of a *Listeria Monocytogenes* Serotype IVb Variant 1 Strain Isolated from Vegetal Matrix in Italy.

Torresi, M.; Orsini, M.; Acciari, V.; Centorotola, G.; Di Lollo, V.; Di Domenico, M.; Bianchi, D. M.; Ziba, M. W.; Tramuta, C.; Cammà, C.; Pomilio, F.

Microbiol Resour Announc 2020, 9 (33).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.00782-20>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5472980>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: Evaluation of a commercial exogenous internal process control for diagnostic RNA virus metagenomics from different animal clinical samples.

Van Borm S, Fu Q, Winand R, et al.

Journal of Virological Methods. 2020;283:113916.

doi:10.1016/j.jviromet.2020.113916

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244771#.X6Lc5ohKjcc>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: COVID-19 in health-care workers in three hospitals in the south of the Netherlands: a cross-sectional study.

Sikkema RS, Pas SD, Nieuwenhuijse DF, et al.

The Lancet Infectious Diseases. 2020;20(11):1273-1280.

doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30527-2

<https://zenodo.org/record/4457341#.YArXXOhKjcc>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: Rapid SARS-CoV-2 whole-genome sequencing and analysis for informed public health decision-making in the Netherlands.

The Dutch-COVID-19 response team, Oude Munnink BB, Nieuwenhuijse DF, et al.

Nat Med. 2020;26(9):1405-1410.

doi:10.1038/s41591-020-0997-y

<https://zenodo.org/record/4457379#.YArZ5ehKjcc>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: Increased viral read counts and metagenomic full genome characterization of porcine astrovirus 4 and Posavirus 1 in sows in a swine farm with unexplained neonatal piglet diarrhea.

Van Borm S, Vanneste K, Fu Q, et al.

Virus Genes. 2020;56(6):696-704.

doi:10.1007/s11262-020-01791-z

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244782#.X6LfzYhKjcc>

JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* isolated from carcasses of chickens slaughtered in Poland – a retrospective study.

Wieczorek K, Bocian Ł, Osek J.

Food Control. 2020;112:107159.

doi:10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107159

<https://zenodo.org/record/3676306>

JPR09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: Campylobacter in chicken – Critical parameters for international, multicentre evaluation of air sampling and detection methods.

Johannessen GS, Garofolo G, Di Serafino G, et al.

Food Microbiology. 2020;90:103455.

doi:10.1016/j.fm.2020.103455

<https://zenodo.org/record/3663545#.XkPEvGhKiUk>

JPR09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: MLST-based genetic relatedness of Campylobacter jejuni isolated from chickens and humans in Poland.

Wieczorek K, Wołkowicz T, Osek J, Biggs PJ, ed.

PLoS ONE. 2020;15(1):e0226238.

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0226238

<https://zenodo.org/record/3628110#.X6FsFjiWxPY>

JPR09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: Molecular Characterization and Antimicrobial Susceptibility of C. Jejuni Isolates from Italian Wild Bird Populations.

Marotta, F.; Janowicz, A.; Di Marcantonio, L.; Ercole, C.; Di Donato, G.; Garofolo, G.; Di Giannatale, E.

Pathogens 2020, 9 (4), 304.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9040304>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5564702#.YWV-g3duLnM>

JPR09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: A multi-center proposal for a fast screening tool in biosecured chicken flocks. Foodborne Campylobacter

Jeffrey Hoorfar, Ivana Koláčková, Gro S. Johannessen, Giuliano Garofolo, Francesca Marotta, Kinga Wieczorek, Jacek Osek, Mona Torp, Bjørn Spilberg, Camilla Sekse, Natasia Rebekka Thornval, Renáta Karpíšková

Applied and Environmental Microbiology, Vol.86, N°20

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01051-20>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244138#.YjHwmzapW3c>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: A multi-scale epidemic model of Salmonella infection with heterogeneous shedding. Labarthe S, Laroche B, Nguyen TNT, et al.

Calvez V, Grandmont C, Lochërbach E, Poignard C, Ribot M, Vauchelet N, eds. ESAIM:

ProcS. 2020;67:261-284.

doi:10.1051/proc/202067015

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxM0>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Reduction of Salmonella Typhimurium Cecal Colonisation and Improvement of Intestinal Health in Broilers Supplemented with Fermented Defatted ‘Alperujo’, an Olive Oil By-Product.

Rebollada-Merino A, Ugarte-Ruiz M, Hernández M, et al.

Animals. 2020;10(10):1931.

doi:10.3390/ani10101931

<https://zenodo.org/record/4114070>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Cost-effectiveness analysis of using probiotics, prebiotics, or synbiotics to control Campylobacter in broilers.

van Wagenberg CPA, van Horne PLM, van Asseldonk MAPM.

Poultry Science. 2020;99(8):4077-4084.

doi:10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Dietary supplementation with fermented defatted “alperujo” induces modifications of the intestinal mucosa and cecal microbiota of broiler chickens.

Rebollada-Merino A, Ugarte-Ruiz M, Hernández M, et al.

Poultry Science. Published online August 2020:S0032579120304843.

doi:10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015

<https://zenodo.org/record/4017817#.X6LRjYhKjcc>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Gut microbiota composition before infection determines the *Salmonella* super- and low-shedder phenotypes in chicken.

Kempf F, Menanteau P, Rychlik I, et al.

Microb Biotechnol. 2020;13(5):1611-1630.

doi:10.1111/1751-7915.13621

<https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Diversity of mucoid to non-mucoid switch among carbapenemase-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Chiarelli A, Cabanel N, Rosinski-Chupin I, et al.

BMC Microbiol. 2020;20(1):325.

doi:10.1186/s12866-020-02007-y

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456731#.YAAqiMOhKjcc>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Broad-Spectrum Cephalosporin-Resistant *Klebsiella* spp. Isolated from Diseased Horses in Austria.

Loncaric I, Cabal Rosel A, Szostak MP, et al.

Animals. 2020;10(2):332.

doi:10.3390/ani10020332

https://zenodo.org/record/3929408#.Xv8m_ygzZM0

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* carriage in low-income countries: antimicrobial resistance, genomic diversity and risk factors.

Huynh B-T, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, et al.

Gut Microbes. 2020;11(5):1287-1299.

doi:10.1080/19490976.2020.1748257

<https://zenodo.org/record/3929396#.Xv8lrSgzZM0>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: The ZKIR Assay, a Real-Time PCR Method for the Detection of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and Closely Related Species in Environmental Samples.

Barbier E, Rodrigues C, Depret G, et al.

Dudley EG, ed. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2020;86(7):e02711-19,

/aem/86/7/AEM.02711-19.atom.

doi:10.1128/AEM.02711-19

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730608#.Xn3Kk4hKi70>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Community-Acquired Infection Caused by the Uncommon Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ST66-K2 Lineage.

Rodrigues, C.; d’Humières, C.; Papin, G.; Passet, V.; Ruppé, E.; Brisse, S.

Microbial Genomics 2020, 6 (8).

<https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000419>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4436269#.YGLbQ68za70>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Jousset, A. B.; Bonnin, R. A.; Takissian, J.; Girlich, D.; Mihaila, L.; Cabanel, N.; Dortet, L.; Glaser, P.; Naas, T. Concomitant Carriage of KPC-Producing and Non-KPC-Producing *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* ST512 within a Single Patient.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2020, dkaa137.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa137>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6334276#.YiYSrujML2B>

JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir: An alternative workflow for molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 – escape from the NA extraction kit-shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020.

Fomsgaard AS, Rosenstjerne MW.

Eurosurveillance. 2020;25(14). doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.14.2000398

<https://zenodo.org/record/4247188#.X6QLjWhKjcc>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: Cystic Echinococcosis: Clinical, Immunological, and Biomolecular Evaluation of Patients from Sardinia (Italy).

Santucci C, Bonelli P, Peruzzi A, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(11):907. doi:10.3390/pathogens9110907

<https://zenodo.org/record/4159681>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: Comparison of Two DNA Extraction Methods and Two PCRs for Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the Stool Samples of Naturally Infected Red Foxes. Skrzypek K, Karamon J, Samorek-Pieróg M, et al.

Animals. 2020;10(12):2381. doi:10.3390/ani10122381

<https://zenodo.org/record/4384600>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level.

Santolamazza F, Santoro A, Possenti A, Cacciò SM, Casulli A.

Infection, Genetics and Evolution. 2020;85:104575. doi:10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575

<https://zenodo.org/record/4066416#.X6UQMWhKjcc>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: Bayesian Analysis of Three Methods for Diagnosis of Cystic Echinococcosis in Sheep. Bonelli P, Loi F, Cancedda MG, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(10):796. doi:10.3390/pathogens9100796

<https://zenodo.org/record/4061823#.X6PZl2hKjcc>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple *Echinococcus granulosus Sensu Stricto* Cysts in Single Hosts Reveal Different Patterns of Infection Events between Livestock and Humans.

M'rad S, Oudni-M'rad M, Bastid V, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(6):444. doi:10.3390/pathogens9060444

<https://zenodo.org/record/3894117#.XvyQ6ygzZM0>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis.

Casulli A. *The Lancet Global Health*. 2020;8(4):e470-e471. doi:10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730559#.Xn3FalhKi70>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: Species Detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* Complex by Novel Probe-Based Real-Time PCRs.

Maksimov P, Bergmann H, Wassermann M, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(10):791. doi:10.3390/pathogens9100791

<https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.X6PY3WhKjcc>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Molecular Characterization of *Giardia duodenalis* in Children and Adults Sampled in Algeria.

Belkessa S, Thomas-Lopez D, Houali K, Ghalmi F, Stensvold CR.

Microorganisms. 2020;9(1):54. doi:10.3390/microorganisms9010054

<https://zenodo.org/record/4422456#.YArbG-hKjcc>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Veterinary Students Have a Higher Risk of Contracting Cryptosporidiosis when Calves with High Fecal *Cryptosporidium* Loads Are Used for Fetotomy Exercises. Schaffner DW, ed.

Thomas-Lopez D, Müller L, Vestergaard LS, et al.

Appl Environ Microbiol. 2020;86(19):e01250-20, /aem/86/19/AEM.01250-20.atom.

doi:10.1128/AEM.01250-20

<https://zenodo.org/record/4129990#.X6PX8WhKjcc>

JRP21-FBZSH9-BEONE: Prediction of antimicrobial resistance in clinical *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates from whole-genome sequencing data.

Dahl LG, Joensen KG, Østerlund MT, Kiil K, Nielsen EM.

Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis. Published online September 24, 2020.

doi:10.1007/s10096-020-04043-y

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249355#.X6UnVWhKjcc>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Fluorescent Bead-Based Serological Detection of *Toxoplasma Gondii* Infection in Chickens.

Fabian BT, Hedar F, Koethe M, et al.

In Review; 2020. Accessed August 20, 2020. <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-34121/v1>

<https://zenodo.org/record/3974390#.X6PV0WhKjcc>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Isolation and genetic characterization of *Toxoplasma gondii* in Spanish sheep flocks. Fernández-Escobar M, Calero-Bernal R, Benavides J, et al.

Parasites Vectors. 2020;13(1):396. doi:10.1186/s13071-020-04275-z

<https://zenodo.org/record/3974417#.X6PWsWhKjcc>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Expression of *in Vivo* Biotinylated Recombinant Antigens SAG1 and SAG2A from *Toxoplasma Gondii* for Improved Seroepidemiological Bead-Based Multiplex Assays.

Klein S, Stern D, Seeber F.

In Review; 2020. Accessed August 20, 2020.

<https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-33963/v1>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4129949#.X6Ldr4hKjcc>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Isolation, Genotyping, and Mouse Virulence Characterization of *Toxoplasma Gondii* From Free Ranging Iberian Pigs.

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Regidor-Cerrillo, J.; Vallejo, R.; Benavides, J.; Collantes-Fernández, E.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.

Front. Vet. Sci. **2020**, *7*, 604782.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.604782>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516873#.YUg5qOxxe70>

2021 - 48 JRP publications

In 2021, 47 manuscripts were published by the JRP (17 by the first round JRP and 30 by the second round JRP). The manuscripts are mentioned below (authors, title, DOI and repository link). A list of all the One Health EJP manuscripts published since 2018 is available on the One Health EJP website:

<https://onehealthejp.eu/publications/>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Co-Occurrence of the Bla VIM-1 and Bla SHV-12 Genes on an IncHI2 Plasmid of an Escherichia Coli Isolate Recovered from German Livestock.

Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Schwarz, S.; Grobbel, M.; Meemken, D.; Malorny, B.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Käsbohrer, A.; Irrgang, A.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2021, 76 (2), 531–533.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa436>

https://zenodo.org/record/4451874#.YgU9vt_MLFU

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Isolation Procedure for CP E. Coli from Caeca Samples under Review towards an Increased Sensitivity.

Pauly, N.; Klaar, Y.; Skladnikiewicz-Ziemer, T.; Juraschek, K.; Grobbel, M.; Hammerl, J. A.; Hemmers, L.; Käsbohrer, A.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Irrgang, A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (5), 1105.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9051105>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4835626#.YVQo9ppBxM0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Horsing Around: Escherichia Coli ST1250 of Equine Origin Harboring Epidemic IncHI1/ST9 Plasmid with Bla CTX-M-1 and an Operon for Short-Chain Fructooligosaccharide Metabolism.

Valcek, A.; Sismova, P.; Nesporova, K.; Overballe-Petersen, S.; Bitar, I.; Jamborova, I.; Kant, A.; Hrabak, J.; Wagenaar, J. A.; Madec, J.-Y.; Damborg, P.; van Duijkeren, E.; Ewers, C.; Hordijk, J.; Hasman, H.; Brouwer, M. S. M.; Dolejska, M.

Antimicrob Agents Chemother 2021, 65 (5).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.02556-20>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5506463#.YUBKk50zaUk>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Clinically Relevant Escherichia Coli Isolates from Process Waters and Wastewater of Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses in Germany.

Savin, M.; Bierbaum, G.; Kreyenschmidt, J.; Schmithausen, R.; Sib, E.; Schmogger, S.; Käsbohrer, A.; Hammerl, J.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (4), 698.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040698>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4981248>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Comparison of Phenotypical Antimicrobial Resistance between Clinical and Non-Clinical E. Coli Isolates from Broilers, Turkeys and Calves in Four European Countries.

Mesa-Varona, O.; Mader, R.; Velasova, M.; Madec, J.-Y.; Granier, S. A.; Perrin-Guyomard, A.; Norstrom, M.; Kaspar, H.; Grobbel, M.; Jouy, E.; Anjum, M. F.; Tenhagen, B.-A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (4), 678.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040678>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4704208#.YKS6KKgzbY0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Phenotypic and Genotypic Properties of Fluoroquinolone-Resistant, Qnr-Carrying Escherichia Coli Isolated from the German Food Chain in 2017.

Juraschek, K.; Deneke, C.; Schmogger, S.; Grobbel, M.; Malorny, B.; Käsbohrer, A.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Hammerl, J. A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (6), 1308.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9061308>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Outcome of Different Sequencing and Assembly Approaches on the Detection of Plasmids and Localization of Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in Commensal Escherichia Coli. Juraschek, K.; Borowiak, M.; Tausch, S. H.; Malorny, B.; Käsbohrer, A.; Otani, S.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Deneke, C.; Hammerl, J. A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (3), 598.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9030598>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4964345>

JRP05 ET1-TOX-Detect: The Cytotoxic Potential of Bacillus Cereus Strains of Various Origins.

Glasset, B.; Sperry, M.; Dervyn, R.; Herbin, S.; Brisabois, A.; Ramarao, N.

Food Microbiology 2021, 98, 103759.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2021.103759>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516520#.YgUztzipW3c>

JRP05 ET1-TOX-Detect: DiagnoTop: A Computational Pipeline for Discriminating Bacterial Pathogens without Database Search.

Borges Lima, D.; Dupré, M.; Mariano Santos, M. D.; Carvalho, P. C.; Chamot-Rooke, J.

Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom. 2021, 32 (6), 1295–1299.

<https://doi.org/10.1021/jasms.1c00014>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516526#.YgUz1TipW3c>

JRP06 FBZ1-NOVA: One Health Glossary to Support Communication and Information Exchange between the Human Health, Animal Health and Food Safety Sectors.

Buschhardt, T.; Günther, T.; Skjerdal, T.; Torpdahl, M.; Gethmann, J.; Filippitzi, M.-E.; Maassen, C.; Jore, S.; Ellis-Iversen, J.; Filter, M.

One Health 2021, 13, 100263.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4769914#.YT9EEp0za70>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Chloride Resistance in Listeria Monocytogenes of Human, Food, and Environmental Origin.

Gelbicova, T.; Florianova, M.; Hluchanova, L.; Kalova, A.; Korena, K.; Strakova, N.; Karpiskova, R. Comparative Analysis of Genetic Determinants Encoding Cadmium, Arsenic, and Benzalkonium

Front. Microbiol. 2021, 11, 599882.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.599882>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456720#.YLDmBzhDtM0>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Exposure to Quaternary Ammonium Compounds Selects Resistance to Ciprofloxacin in Listeria Monocytogenes.

Guérin, A.; Bridier, A.; Le Grandois, P.; Sévellec, Y.; Palma, F.; Félix, B.; LISTADAPT Study Group; Roussel, S.; Soumet, C.

Pathogens 2021, 10 (2), 220.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020220>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5471681>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Draft Genome Sequences of Two Listeria Monocytogenes Strains Isolated from Invasive Snails (Arion Vulgaris) in Austria in 2019. 2021.

Pietzka A; Murer A; Lennkh A; Hauser K; Votsch; Springer B; Allerberger F; Ruppitch W.

American Society for Microbiology, 2021, Vol.10 N°21

<https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.00375-21>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5472856>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Comparative analysis of genetic determinants encoding cadmium, arsenic and benzalkonium chloride resistance in *Listeria monocytogenes* of human, food and environmental origin. Tereza Gelbicova, Martina Florianova, Lucie Hluchanova, Alžběta Kalova, Kristýna Korena, Nicol Strakova, Renáta Karpiskova

Front. Microbiol., 14 January 2021

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.599882>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456720#.YLDmBzhDtM0>

JRP08 FBZ2-METASTAVA: Detection of Norovirus Variant GII.4 Hong Kong in Asia and Europe, 2017–2019.

Chan, M. C.-W.; Roy, S.; Bonifacio, J.; Zhang, L.-Y.; Chhabra, P.; Chan, J. C. M.; Celma, C.; Igoy, M. A.; Lau, S.-L.; Mohammad, K. N.; Vinjé, J.; Vennema, H.; Breuer, J.; Koopmans, M.; de Graaf, M.; *Emerg. Infect. Dis.* 2021, 27 (1), 289–293.

<https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2701.203351>

https://zenodo.org/record/4556945#.YgU-E9_MLFU

JRP08 FBZ2-METASTAVA: Monitoring SARS-CoV-2 Circulation and Diversity through Community Wastewater Sequencing, the Netherlands and Belgium.

Izquierdo-Lara, R.; Elsinga, G.; Heijnen, L.; Munnink, B. B. O.; Schapendonk, C. M. E.; Nieuwenhuijse, D.; Kon, M.; Lu, L.; Aarestrup, F. M.; Lycett, S.; Medema, G.; Koopmans, M. P. G.; de Graaf, M. *Emerg. Infect. Dis.* 2021, 27 (5), 1405–1415.

<https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2705.204410>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4457357#.YP7XnTh7m9I>

JRP10 FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC: Effect of Biscuit Flour and Fermented Defatted “Alperujo” Co-Administration on Intestinal Mucosa Morphology and Productive Performance in Laying Hens.

Porras, N.; Rebollada-Merino, A.; Bárcena, C.; Mayoral-Alegre, F. J.; Lomillos, J. M.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A.

Animals 2021, 11 (4), 1075.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11041075>

https://zenodo.org/record/4736117#.Yiht_japVM0

JRP10 FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC: A Large Panel of Chicken Cells Are Invaded in Vivo by *Salmonella* Typhimurium Even When Depleted of All Known Invasion Factors.

Roche, S. M.; Holbert, S.; Le Vern, Y.; Rossignol, C.; Rossignol, A.; Velge, P.; Virlogeux-Payant, I.

Open Biol. 2021, 11 (11), 210117.

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsob.210117>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5707381#.Yicr-ejMJM0>

JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED: A Shotgun Metagenomics Approach to Detect and Characterize Unauthorized Genetically Modified Microorganisms in Microbial Fermentation Products.

Buytaers, F. E.; Fraiture, M.-A.; Berbers, B.; Vandermassen, E.; Hoffman, S.; Papazova, N.; Vanneste, K.; Marchal, K.; Roosens, N. H. C.; De Keersmaecker, S. C. J.

Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences 2021, 2, 100023.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochms.2021.100023>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5347021#.YS-kSY4zaM8>

JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Population Genomics and Antimicrobial Resistance Dynamics of *Escherichia Coli* in Wastewater and River Environments.

Delgado-Blas, J. F.; Ovejero, C. M.; David, S.; Montero, N.; Calero-Caceres, W.; Garcillan-Barcia, M. P.; de la Cruz, F.; Muniesa, M.; Aanensen, D. M.; Gonzalez-Zorn, B.

Commun Biol 2021, 4 (1), 457.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR>

JRP14 AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE: A Peek into the Plasmidome of Global Sewage.

Kirstahler, P.; Teudt, F.; Otani, S.; Aarestrup, F. M.; Pamp, S. J.

mSystems 2021, 6 (3).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/mSystems.00283-21>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5543288#.YZPKXmDMJM0>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: Draft Genome Sequence of a Multidrug-Resistant *Escherichia Coli* Sequence Type 1193 Pandemic Clone Isolated from Wastewater in Austria.

Cabal, A.; Peischl, N.; Rab, G.; Stöger, A.; Springer, B.; Sucher, J.; Allerberger, F.; Ruppitsch, W.

Microbiol Resour Announc 2021, 10 (37).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.00762-21>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5770120#.YeZ1rd8xl4F>

JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir: Escape from the NA Extraction Kit-Shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020.

Fomsgaard, A. S.; Rosenstjerne, M. W. An Alternative Workflow for Molecular Detection of SARS-CoV-2 – *Eurosurveillance* 2020, 25 (14)

<https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.14.2000398>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4247188#.X6QLjWhKjcc>

JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU: The Use of Flocked Swabs with a Protective Medium Increases the Recovery of Live *Brucella* Spp. and DNA Detection.

Freddi, L.; Djokic, V.; Petot-Bottin, F.; Girault, G.; Perrot, L.; Ferreira Vicente, A.; Ponsart, C.

Microbiol Spectr 2021, 9 (3), e00728-21.

<https://doi.org/10.1128/Spectrum.00728-21>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Identification of *Echinococcus Granulosus* Genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays. Bonelli, P.; Dei Giudici, S.; Peruzzo, A.; Mura, L.; Santucci, C.; Maestrale, C.; Masala, G.

Pathogens 2021, 10 (2), 125.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020125>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4471215#.YGLkiq8zZM0>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: New Global Targets for NTDs in the WHO Roadmap 2021–2030.

Casulli, A.

PLoS Negl Trop Dis 2021, 15 (5), e0009373.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009373>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4771738#.YKTFCqHOQgp>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Molecular Analysis Suggests That Namibian Cheetahs (*Acinonyx Jubatus*) Are Definitive Hosts of a so Far Undescribed *Besnoitia* Species.

Schaes, G.; Joeres, M.; Rachel, F.; Tuschy, M.; Czirják, G. Á.; Maksimov, P.; Conraths, F. J.; Wachter, B.

Parasites Vectors 2021, 14 (1), 201.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3>

https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YTDH7t_OOgo

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone.

Barth, T. F. E.; Casulli, A.

Pathogens 2021, 10 (10), 1326.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10101326>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5646982#.YicsOujMJMO>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Mining Public Metagenomes for Environmental Surveillance of Parasites: A Proof of Principle. *Front. Franssen, F. F. J.; Janse, I.; Janssen, D.; Caccio, S. M.; Vatta, P.; van der Giessen, J. W. B.; van Passel, M. W. J.*

Microbiol. 2021, 12, 622356.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.622356>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5494583>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Parasitic Intestinal Protists of Zoonotic Relevance Detected in Pigs by Metabarcoding and Real-Time PCR.

Stensvold, C. R.; Jirků-Pomajbíková, K.; Tams, K. W.; Jokelainen, P.; Berg, R. P. K. D.; Marving, E.; Petersen, R. F.; Andersen, L. O.; Angen, Ø.; Nielsen, H. V.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (6), 1189.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9061189>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4898752#.YTnBA50zaUk>

JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCOVeR: Monitoring of Antimicrobial Resistance to Aminoglycosides and Macrolides in *Campylobacter Coli* and *Campylobacter Jejuni* From Healthy Livestock in Spain (2002–2018).

Lopez-Chavarrias, V.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Barcena, C.; Olarra, A.; Garcia, M.; Saez, J. L.; de Frutos, C.; Serrano, T.; Perez, I.; Moreno, M. A.; Dominguez, L.; Alvarez, J.

Front. Microbiol. 2021, 12, 689262.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.689262>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5109549#.YUyflGzZM0>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Identification of Oocyst-Driven *Toxoplasma Gondii* Infections in Humans and Animals through Stage-Specific Serology—Current Status and Future Perspectives.

Álvarez García, G.; Davidson, R.; Jokelainen, P.; Klevar, S.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (11), 2346.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9112346>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5821931#.YdXABWCZOUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Zoonotic Pathogens in Wild Muskoxen (*Ovibos Moschatus*) and Domestic Sheep (*Ovis Aries*) from Greenland.

Berg, R. P. K. D.; Stensvold, C. R.; Jokelainen, P.; Grønlund, A. K.; Nielsen, H. V.; Kutz, S.; Kapel, C. M. O.

Vet Med Sci 2021, vms3.599.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.599>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516925#.YUhcMexxe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Expanding the Known Repertoire of C-Type Lectin Receptors Binding to *Toxoplasma Gondii* Oocysts Using a Modified High-Resolution Immunofluorescence Assay.

Fabian, B. T.; Lepenies, B.; Schares, G.; Dubey, J. P.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.

mSphere 2021, 6 (2).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/mSphere.01341-20>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4657064#.YGXUY68zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: In Vivo and in Vitro Models Show Unexpected Degrees of Virulence among *Toxoplasma Gondii* Type II and III Isolates from Sheep.

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Regidor-Cerrillo, J.; Vallejo, R.; Benavides, J.; Collantes-Fernández, E.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.

Vet Res 2021, 52 (1), 82.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00953-7>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516897#.YUg7QOxe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Identification of Molecular Biomarkers Associated with Disease Progression in the Testis of Bulls Infected with *Besnoitia Besnoiti*.

González-Barrio, D.; Diezma-Díaz, C.; Gutiérrez-Expósito, D.; Tabanera, E.; Jiménez-Meléndez, A.; Pizarro, M.; González-Huecas, M.; Ferre, I.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.; Álvarez-García, G.

Vet Res 2021, 52 (1), 106.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00974-2>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5812116#.YdVZo2jMKUK>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Changes in Serum Biomarkers of Inflammation in Bovine Besnoitiosis.

González-Barrio, D.; Huertas-López, A.; Diezma-Díaz, C.; Ferre, I.; Cerón, J. J.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.; Álvarez-García, G.

Parasites Vectors 2021, 14 (1), 488.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04991-0>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5812119#.YdVZe2jMKUK>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Veterinarians as a Risk Group for Zoonoses: Exposure, Knowledge and Protective Practices in Finland. Kinnunen, P. M.; Matomäki, A.; Verkola, M.; Heikinheimo, A.; Vapalahti, O.; Kallio-kokko, H.; Virtala, A.-M.; Jokelainen, P.

Safety and Health at Work 2021, S2093791121000871.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2021.10.008>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: The Disease Burden of Ocular Toxoplasmosis in Denmark in 2019: Estimates Based on Laboratory Testing of Ocular Samples and on Publicly Available Register Data.

Marstrand, J.; Kurtzhals, J. A. L.; Fuchs, H. J.; Nielsen, H. V.; Jokelainen, P. *Parasite Epidemiology and Control* 2021, 15, e00229.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parepi.2021.e00229>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5595613#.YXZegxpBy70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: A Longitudinal Study of *Toxoplasma Gondii* Seroconversion on Four Large Danish Sow Farms. Olsen, A.; Alban, L.; Denwood, M.; Houe, H.; Birk Jensen, T.; Vedel Nielsen, H. *Veterinary Parasitology* 2021, 295, 109460.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109460>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516957#.YUhCDexxe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: A Real-Time Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction for the Specific Detection of *Hammondia Hammondii* and Its Differentiation from *Toxoplasma Gondii*.

Schaes, G.; Globokar Vrhovec, M.; Tuschy, M.; Joeres, M.; Bärwald, A.; Koudela, B.; Dubey, J. P.; Maksimov, P.; Conraths, F. J.

Parasites Vectors 2021, 14 (1), 78.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04571-8>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647866#.YGNbWK8zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Molecular Methods for the Detection of *Toxoplasma Gondii* Oocysts in Fresh Produce: An Extensive Review.

Slana, I.; Bier, N.; Bartosova, B.; Marucci, G.; Possenti, A.; Mayer-Scholl, A.; Jokelainen, P.; Lalle, M.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (1), 167.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010167>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647840#.YGNQk68zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Comparison of Direct and Indirect *Toxoplasma Gondii* Detection and Genotyping in Game: Relationship and Challenges.

Stollberg, K. C.; Schares, G.; Mayer-Scholl, A.; Hrushetska, I.; Diescher, S.; Johne, A.; Richter, M. H.; Bier, N. S.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (8), 1663.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9081663>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516907#.YUg8qOxxe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Infection Prevention and Control Practices of Ambulatory Veterinarians: A Questionnaire Study in Finland.

Verkola, M.; Järvelä, T.; Järvinen, A.; Jokelainen, P.; Virtala, A.; Kinnunen, P. M.; Heikinheimo, A.

Vet Med Sci 2021, vms3.464.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.464>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647937#.YGNfea8zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Molecular Analysis Suggests That Namibian Cheetahs (*Acinonyx Jubatus*) Are Definitive Hosts of a so Far Undescribed *Besnoitia* Species.

Schares, G.; Joeres, M.; Rachel, F.; Tuschy, M.; Czirják, G. Á.; Maksimov, P.; Conraths, F. J.; Wachter, B.

Parasites Vectors 2021, 14 (1), 201.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YHg5Z-gzaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Experimental Infection with *Toxoplasma Gondii* in Broiler Chickens (*Gallus Domesticus*): Seroconversion, Tissue Cyst Distribution, and Prophylaxis.

Nedişan, M. E.; Györke, A.; Ştefănuţ, C. L.; Kalmár, Z.; Friss, Z.; Blaga, R.; Blaizot, A.; Toma-Naic, A.;

Mircean, V.; Schares, G.; Djurković-Djaković, O.; Klun, I.; Villena, I.; Cozma, V.

Parasitol Res 2021, 120 (2), 593–603.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-020-06984-x>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647895#.YGNbDT9JGUl>

JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS: Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Human Salmonellosis in the Netherlands.

Mughini-Gras, L.; Chanamé Pinedo, L.; Pijnacker, R.; van den Beld, M.; Wit, B.; Veldman, K.; Bosh, T.; Franz, E.

Epidemiol. Infect. 2021, 149, e254.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268821002557>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6090653#.Ygu1fzipW3d>

JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS: Coverage of the National Surveillance System for Human Salmonella Infections, Belgium, 2016-2020.

Van Goethem, N.; Van Den Bossche, A.; Ceysens, P.-J.; Lajot, A.; Coucke, W.; Vernelen, K.; Roosens, N.

H. C.; De Keersmaecker, S. C. J.; Van Cauteren, D.; Mattheus, W.

PLoS ONE 2021, 16 (8), e0256820.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6090759#.Ygu1jzipW3d>

2022 : 57 JRP publications

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Multicentre evaluation of a selective isolation protocol for detection of *mcr*-positive *E. coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in food-producing animals and meat.

Perrin-Guyomard, A., Granier, S.A., Slette-meås, J.S., Anjum, M., Randall, L., AbuOun, M., Pauly, N., Irrgang, A., Hammerl, J.A., Kjeldgaard, J.S., Hammerum, A., Franco, A., Skarzyńska, M., Kamińska, E., Wasyl, D., Dierikx, C., Börjesson, S., Geurts, Y., Haenni, M. and Veldman, K. (2022). *Letters in Applied Microbiology*. Early view.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/lam.13717>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: A European Multicenter Evaluation Study to Investigate the Performance on Commercially Available Selective Agar Plates for the Detection of Carbapenemase Producing Enterobacteriaceae.

Dierikx, C.; Börjesson, S.; Perrin-Guyomard, A.; Haenni, M.; Norström, M.; Divon, H. H.; Ilag, H. K.; Granier, S. A.; Hammerum, A.; Kjeldgaard, J. S.; Pauly, N.; Randall, L.; Anjum, M. F.; Smialowska, A.; Franco, A.; Veldman, K.; Slette-meås, J. S.

Journal of Microbiological Methods 2022, 193, 106418.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2022.106418>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Harmonisation of in-silico next-generation sequencing based methods for diagnostics and surveillance.

Nunez-Garcia, J., AbuOun, M., Storey, N., Brouwer, M. S., Delgado-Blas, J. F., Mo, S. S., Ellaby, N., Veldman, K. T., Haenni, M., Châtre, P., Madec, J. Y., Hammerl, J. A., Serna, C., Getino, M., La Ragione, R., Naas, T., Telke, A. A., Glaser, P., Sunde, M., Gonzalez-Zorn, B., Ellington, M. J. & Anjum, M. F. (2022). *Scientific Reports*. 12, 14372.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-16760-9>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: A Broad-Host-Range Plasmid Outbreak: Dynamics of IncL/M Plasmids Transferring Carbapenemase Genes.

Getino, M., López-Díaz, M., Ellaby, N., Clark, J., Ellington, M. J., La Ragione, R. M. (2022). *Antibiotics*. 11(11), 1641.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11111641>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Use of genomics to explore AMR persistence in an outdoor pig farm with low antimicrobial usage.

Storey, N., Cawthraw, S., Turner, O., Rambaldi, M., Lemma, F., Horton, R., Randall, L., Duggett, N. A., AbuOun, M., Martelli, F., & Anjum, M. F. (2022). *Microbial genomics*. 8(3), 000782.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000782>

JRP05-ET1-TOX-Detect: New Genetic Biomarkers to Differentiate Non-Pathogenic from Clinically Relevant *Bacillus Cereus* Strains.

Kavanaugh, D. W.; Glasset, B.; Dervyn, R.; Guérin, C.; Plancade, S.; Herbin, S.; Brisabois, A.; Nicolas, P.; Ramarao, N.

Clinical Microbiology and Infection 2022, 28 (1), 137.e1-137.e8.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2021.05.035>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5532833#.YVRb8JpBxM0>

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: A European-wide dataset to uncover adaptive traits of *Listeria monocytogenes* to diverse ecological niches.

Félix, B., Sevellec, Y., Palma, F. et al. (2022). *Science Data*. 9, 190.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01278-6>

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: FepR as a central genetic target in quaternary ammonium compounds (QAC)-adaptive process and cross-resistance to ciprofloxacin in *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Douarre, P. E., Sévellec, Y., Le Grandois, P., Soumet, C., Bridier, A., Roussel, S. (2022). *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 13, 864576.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.864576>

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: *Listeria monocytogenes*: Investigation of fitness in soil does not support the relevance of ecotypes.

Sévellec, Y., Ascencio, E., Douarre, P. E., Félix, B., Gal, L., Garmyn, D., Guillier, L., Piveteau, P., Roussel, S. (2022). *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 13, 917588.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.917588>

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Genomics elements located in the accessory repertoire drive the adaptation to biocides in *Listeria monocytogenes* strains from different ecological niches.

Palma, F., Radomski, N., Guérin, A., Sévellec, Y., Félix, B., Bridier, A., Soumet, C., Roussel, S., Guillier, L. (2022). *Food Microbiology*. 106, 103757.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2021.103757>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Super Shedding in Enteric Pathogens: A Review.

Kempf, F., La Ragione, R., Chirullo, B., Schouler, C., & Velge, P. (2022). *Microorganisms*. 10(11), 2101.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10112101>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: High Prevalence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in European Food Products: A Multicentric Study Comparing Culture and Molecular Detection Methods.

Rodrigues, C.; Hauser, K.; Cahill, N.; Ligowska-Marzęta, M.; Centorotola, G.; Cornacchia, A.; Garcia Fierro, R.; Haenni, M.; Nielsen, E. M.; Piveteau, P.; Barbier, E.; Morris, D.; Pomilio, F.; Brisse, S. *Microbiol Spectr* 2022, 10 (1), e02376-21.

<https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.02376-21>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6258025#.YiXWeOjML2A>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: A Longitudinal Survey of Antibiotic-Resistant Enterobacterales in the Irish Environment, 2019-2020.

Hooban, B., Fitzhenry, K., O'Connor, L., Miliotis, G., Joyce, A., Chueiri, A., Farrell, M. L., DeLappe, N., Tuohy, A., Cormican, M., & Morris, D. (2022). *The Science of the total environment*. 828, 154488. Advance online publication.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154488>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Genomic evolution of the globally disseminated multidrug-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* clonal group 147.

Rodrigues, C., Desai, S., Passet, V., Gajjar, D., & Brisse, S. (2022). *Microbial genomics*. 8(1), 000737.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000737>

JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED: Metagenomic Characterization of Multiple Genetically Modified *Bacillus* Contaminations in Commercial Microbial Fermentation Products.

D'aes, J., Fraiture, M-A., Bogaerts, B., De Keersmaecker, S. C. J., Roosens, N. H. C. J., Vanneste, K. (2022). *Life*. 12(12),1971.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/life12121971>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7566116#.Y9ALZHbMKM8>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Survey on Shedding of Selected Pathogenic, Zoonotic or Antimicrobial Resistant Bacteria by South American Camelids in Central Germany. B González-Santamarina; C Schnee; H Köhler; M Weber; U Methner; C Seyboldt; C Berens; C Menge.

Berliner und Münchener Tierärztliche Wochenschrift 2022, No. Berliner und Münchener Tierärztliche Wochenschrift 135, 1–16, 0–0.

<https://doi.org/10.2376/1439-0299-2021-21>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6642390>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Remarkable genomic diversity among *Escherichia* isolates recovered from healthy chickens.

Thomson, N. M., Gilroy, R., Getino, M., Foster-Nyarko, E., van Vliet, A. H. M., La Ragione, R. M. & Pallen, M. J. (2022). *Peer J.* 10, e12935.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.12935>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6759944>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM : Comparative Genomic Analysis of Antimicrobial-Resistant *Escherichia coli* from South American Camelids in Central Germany.

González-Santamarina, B., Weber, M., Menge, C., Berens, C. (2022). *Microorganisms.* 10(9), 1697.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10091697>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7327073>

JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Genomic Analysis of a *mcr-9.1*-Harbouring IncHI2-ST1 Plasmid from *Enterobacter ludwigii* Isolated in Fish Farming.

Manageiro, V., Salgueiro, V., Rosado, T., Bandarra, N. M., Ferreira, E., Smith, T., Dias, E., Caniça, M. (2022). *Antibiotics.* 11(9), 1232.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11091232>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7096620#.YymkZ3bMJPY>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Portable Differential Detection of CTX-M ESBL Gene Variants, blaCTX-M-1 and blaCTX-M-15, from *Escherichia coli* Isolates and Animal Fecal Samples Using Loop-Primer Endonuclease Cleavage Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification.

Higgins, O., Chueiri, A., O'Connor, L., Lahiff, S., Burke, L. P., Morris, D., Pfeifer, N. M., González Santamarina, B., Berens, C., Menge, C., Caniça, M., Manageiro, V., Kisand, V., Hassan, M. M., Gardner, B., van Vliet, A. H. M., La Ragione, R. M., Gonzalez-Zorn, B. & Smith, T. J. (2022). *Microbiology Spectrum.* e03316-22.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.03316-22>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7440937>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Dissemination Routes of Carbapenem and Pan-Aminoglycoside Resistance Mechanisms in Hospital and Urban Wastewater Canalizations of Ghana. Delgado-Blas, J. F.; Valenzuela Agüi, C.; Marin Rodriguez, E.; Serna, C.; Montero, N.; Saba, C. K. S.; Gonzalez-Zorn, B.

mSystems 2022, 7 (1), e01019-21.

<https://doi.org/10.1128/msystems.01019-21>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6619655#.YqBvbOxBy59>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: JMM Profile: Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification (LAMP): For the Rapid Detection of Nucleic Acid Targets in Resource-Limited Settings. Hassan, M. M.; Grist, L. F.; Poirier, A. C.; La Ragione, R. M.

Journal of Medical Microbiology 2022, 71 (5).

<https://doi.org/10.1099/jmm.0.001522>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6618240>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: The Prevalence, Counts, and MLST Genotypes of *Campylobacter* in Poultry Meat and Genomic Comparison with Clinical Isolates. Tedersoo, T.; Roasto, M.; Mäesaar, M.; Kisand, V.; Ivanova, M.; Meremäe, K.
Poultry Science 2022, 101 (4), 101703.
<https://zenodo.org/record/6642459>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Antibiotic Resistance in *Campylobacter* Spp. Isolated from Broiler Chicken Meat and Human Patients in Estonia. Tedersoo, T.; Roasto, M.; Mäesaar, M.; Häkkinen, L.; Kisand, V.; Ivanova, M.; Valli, M. H.; Meremäe, K.
Microorganisms 2022, 10 (5), 1067.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10051067>.
<https://zenodo.org/record/6642526>

JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM : Genomic Screening of Antimicrobial Resistance Markers in UK and US *Campylobacter* Isolates Highlights Stability of Resistance over an 18-Year Period. van Vliet, A. H. M.; Thakur, S.; Prada, J. M.; Mehat, J. W.; La Ragione, R. M.
Antimicrob Agents Chemother 2022, 66 (5), e01687-21.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.01687-21>.
<https://zenodo.org/record/6618202>

JRP14 AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE: Detection of an IMI-2 carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacter asburiae* at a Swedish feed mill.
Börjesson, S., Brouwer, M. S. M., Östlund, E., Eriksson, J., Elving, J., Lindsjö, O. K. and Engblom, L. I. (2022). *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 13, 993454.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.993454>
<https://zenodo.org/record/7244094>

JRP14 AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE: Global Distribution and Diversity of Prevalent Sewage Water Plasmidomes.
mSystems. 2022 Oct 26;7(5):e0019122.
Doi: 10.1128/msystems.00191-22.
<https://zenodo.org/record/7319669>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: Assessment of the Transmission Dynamics of *Clostridioides Difficile* in a Farm Environment Reveals the Presence of a New Toxigenic Strain Connected to Swine Production. Alves, F.; Nunes, A.; Castro, R.; Sequeira, A.; Moreira, O.; Matias, R.; Rodrigues, J. C.; Silveira, L.; Gomes, J. P.; Oleastro, M.
Front. Microbiol. 2022, 13, 858310.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.858310>.
<https://zenodo.org/record/6857162#.Yyh-SXZByUk>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: Characterizing Antimicrobial Resistance in Clinically Relevant Bacteria Isolated at the Human/Animal/Environment Interface Using Whole-Genome Sequencing in Austria.
Journal International Journal of Molecular Sciences.
Doi: 10.3390/ijms231911276
<https://zenodo.org/record/7446455#.Y5xQ-FGZND8>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: Airborne spores' dissemination of a swine associated *Clostridioides difficile* clone.
Alves, F., Cano, M., Brondani, G., Nunes, A., & Oleastro, M. (2022). *Anaerobe*. 78, 102651.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anaerobe.2022.102651>
<https://zenodo.org/record/7446535#.Y5xSj1GZND8>

JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir: Improvement of Field-Deployable Metagenomic Virus Detection by a Simple Pretreatment Method; preprint; Fomsgaard, A. S.; Rasmussen, M.; Spiess, K.; Fomsgaard, A.; Belsham, G. J.; Fonager, J.

Infectious Diseases (except HIV/AIDS), 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.31.21268552>.

JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir : Epizootic Haemorrhagic Disease Virus Serotype 8 in Tunisia, 2021.

Sghaier, S.; Sailleau, C.; Marcacci, M.; Thabet, S.; Curini, V.; Ben Hassine, T.; Teodori, L.; Portanti, O.; Hammami, S.; Jurisic, L.; Spedicato, M.; Postic, L.; Gazani, I.; Ben Osman, R.; Zientara, S.; Bréard, E.; Calistri, P.; Richt, J. A.; Holmes, E. C.; Savini, G.; Di Giallonardo, F.; Lorusso, A.

Viruses 2022, 15 (1), 16.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/v15010016>

JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU: The Retrospective on Atypical Brucella Species Leads to Novel Definitions. Occhialini, A.; Hofreuter, D.; Ufermann, C.-M.; Al Dahouk, S.; Köhler, S.

Microorganisms 2022, 10 (4), 813.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10040813>.

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Unveiling the incidences and trends of the neglected zoonosis cystic echinococcosis in Europe: a systematic review from the MEmE project.

Casulli A, Abela-Ridder B, Petrone D, Fabiani M, Bobić B, Carmena D, Šoba B, Zerem E, Gargaté MJ, Kuzmanovska G, Calomfirescu C, Rainova I, Sotiraki S, Lungu V, Dezsényi B, Herrador Z, Karamon J, Maksimov P, Oksanen A, Millon L, Sviben M, Shkjezi R, Gjoni V, Akshija I, Saarma U, Torgerson P, Šnábel V, Antolová D, Muhovic D, Besim H, Chereau F, Belhassen García M, Chappuis F, Gloor S, Stoeckle M, Müllhaupt B, Manno V, Santoro A, Santolamazza F. (2022). *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 22 Nov 2022, S1473-3099(22)00638-7.

DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(22\)00638-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(22)00638-7)

<https://zenodo.org/record/7351658#.Y342P33MJQJ>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Cystic echinococcosis in northern Tanzania: a pilot study in Maasai livestock-keeping communities.

Tamarozzi, F., Kibona, T., de Glanville, W.A., Mappi, T., Adonikamu, E., Salewi, A., Misso, K., Maro, V., Casulli, A., Santoro, A., Santolamazza, F., Mmbaga, B. T. & Cleaveland, S. (2022). *Parasites & Vectors*. 15(1), 396.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-022-05518-x>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7342315#.Y3uSx33MKgo>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Comparison and evaluation of analytic and diagnostic performances of four commercial kits for the detection of antibodies against *Echinococcus granulosus* and *multilocularis* in human sera.

Peruzzu, A., Mastrandrea, S., Fancellu, A., Bonelli, P., Muehlethaler, K., Masala, G., Santucci, C. (2022). *Comparative Immunology, Microbiology and Infectious Diseases*. 86, 101816.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cimid.2022.101816>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7355608#.Y39kMH3MKgo>

JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE: Species and Genotypes Belonging to *Echinococcus Granulosus Sensu Lato* Complex Causing Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Europe (2000–2021): A Systematic Review. Casulli, A.; Massolo, A.; Saarma, U.; Umhang, G.; Santolamazza, F.; Santoro, A.

Parasites Vectors 2022, 15 (1), 109.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-022-05197-8>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6521887#.YnPkVtNBygo>

JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE: Insights into Human Cystic Echinococcosis in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq: Characteristics and Molecular Identification of Cysts. Issa, A. R.; Arif, S. H.; Mohammed, A. A.; Santolamazza, F.; Santoro, A.; Mero, W. M. S.; Casulli, A.

Pathogens 2022, 11 (4), 408.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11040408>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6521840#.YnPhktNBygo>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: A Retrospective Cohort Study on Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province (Pakistan) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records.

Khan, H.; Casulli, A.; Harandi, M. F.; Afzal, M. S.; Saqib, M. A. N.; Ahmed, H.

Pathogens 2022, 11 (2), 194.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11020194>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6091472#.YiXX5ejML2A>

JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE: Chromosome-Scale Echinococcus Granulosus (Genotype G1) Genome Reveals the Eg95 Gene Family and Conservation of the EG95-Vaccine Molecule. Korhonen, P. K.; Kinkar, L.; Young, N. D.; Cai, H.; Lightowers, M. W.; Gauci, C.; Jabbar, A.; Chang, B. C. H.; Wang, T.; Hofmann, A.; Koehler, A. V.; Li, J.; Li, J.; Wang, D.; Yin, J.; Yang, H.; Jenkins, D. J.; Saarma, U.; Laurimäe, T.; Rostami-Nejad, M.; Irshadullah, M.; Mirhendi, H.; Sharbatkhori, M.; Ponce-Gordo, F.; Simsek, S.; Casulli, A.; Zait, H.; Atoyhan, H.; de la Rue, M. L.; Romig, T.; Wassermann, M.; Aghayan, S. A.; Gevorgyan, H.; Yang, B.; Gasser, R. B.

Commun Biol 2022, 5 (1), 199.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-03125-1>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6521878#.YnPjSdNBygo>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Amplicon-Based next-Generation Sequencing of Eukaryotic Nuclear Ribosomal Genes (Metabarcoding) for the Detection of Single-Celled Parasites in Human Faecal Samples.

Chihi, A.; O'Brien Andersen, L.; Aoun, K.; Bouratbine, A.; Stensvold, C. R.

Parasite Epidemiology and Control 2022, 17, e00242.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parepi.2022.e00242>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7091766#.Y49CkLTMKUK>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: An Outbreak of Cryptosporidiosis Associated with Drinking Water in North-Eastern Italy,

Franceschelli Armando; Bonadonna Lucia; Cacciò Simone Mario; Sannella Anna Rosa; Cintori Christian; Gargiulo Raffaele; Coccia Anna Maria; Paradiso Rosa; Iaconelli Marcello; Briancesco Rossella; Tripodi Alberto.

August 2019: Microbiological and Environmental Investigations. 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7043272>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/7043272#.YysQ6nZBxM0>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Extensive Testing of a Multi-Locus Sequence Typing Scheme for *Giardia Duodenalis* Assemblage A Confirms Its Good Discriminatory Power.

Klotz, C.; Sannella, A. R.; Weisz, F.; Chaudhry, U.; Sroka, J.; Tůmová, P.; Nohýnková, E.; Ignatius, R.; Aebischer, T.; Betson, M.; Troell, K.; Cacciò, S. M.

Parasites Vectors 2022, 15 (1), 489.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-022-05615-x>.

[10.5281/zenodo.7525061](https://zenodo.org/record/7525061)

JRP20-FBZSH3-DiSCoVeR: A Statistical Modelling Approach for Source Attribution Meta-analysis of Sporadic Infection with Foodborne Pathogens. Mughini-Gras, L.; Benincà, E.; McDonald, S. A.; Jong, A.; Chardon, J.; Evers, E.; Bonačić Marinović, A. A.
Zoonoses and Public Health 2022, zph.12937.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12937>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6365098#.Ynkcy-hBxwQ>

JRP20-FBZSH3-DiSCoVeR: Multidirectional Dynamic Model for the Spread of Extended-Spectrum- β -Lactamase-Producing Escherichia Coli in the Netherlands.

de Freitas Costa, E.; Hagenaars, T. J.; Dame-Korevaar, A.; Brouwer, M. S. M.; de Vos, C. J.

Microbial Risk Analysis 2022, 22, 100230.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2022.100230>

JRP20-FBZSH3-DiSCoVeR and JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS-: Sources and Trends of Human Salmonellosis in Europe, 2015–2019: An Analysis of Outbreak Data.

Chanamé Pinedo, L.; Mughini-Gras, L.; Franz, E.; Hald, T.; Pires, S. M.

International Journal of Food Microbiology 2022, 379, 109850.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2022.109850>

JRP20-FBZSH3-DiSCoVeR: Comparison of Approaches for Source Attribution of ESBL-Producing Escherichia Coli in Germany.

Perestrelo, S.; Correia Carreira, G.; Valentin, L.; Fischer, J.; Pfeifer, Y.; Werner, G.; Schmiedel, J.; Falgenhauer, L.; Imirzalioglu, C.; Chakraborty, T.; Käsbohrer, A.

PLoS ONE 2022, 17 (7), e0271317.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0271317>

JRP20-FBZSH3-DiSCoVeR and JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS: Pathogenic Escherichia Coli, Salmonella Spp. and Campylobacter Spp. in Two Natural Conservation Centers of Wildlife in Portugal: Genotypic and Phenotypic Characterization.

Pista, A.; Silveira, L.; Ribeiro, S.; Fontes, M.; Castro, R.; Coelho, A.; Furtado, R.; Lopes, T.; Maia, C.; Mixão, V.; Borges, V.; Sá, A.; Soeiro, V.; Correia, C. B.; Gomes, J. P.; Saraiva, M.; Oleastro, M.; Batista, R.

Microorganisms 2022, 10 (11), 2132.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10112132>

JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE: Complex Network Analysis to Understand Trading Partnership in French Swine Production. Hammami, P.; Widgren, S.; Grosbois, V.; Apolloni, A.; Rose, N.; Andraud, M.

PLoS ONE 2022, 17 (4), e0266457.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0266457>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6458445#.YnkKehBxwQ>

JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE: What Is a Biosecurity Measure? A Definition Proposal for Animal Production and Linked Processing Operations.

Huber, N.; Andraud, M.; Sassu, E. L.; Prigge, C.; Zoche-Golob, V.; Käsbohrer, A.; D'Angelantonio, D.; Viltrop, A.; Żmudzki, J.; Jones, H.; Smith, R. P.; Tobias, T.; Burow, E.

One Health 2022, 15, 100433.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2022.100433>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7143533>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Contamination of Soil, Water, Fresh Produce, and Bivalve Mollusks with Toxoplasma Gondii Oocysts: A Systematic Review. López Ureña, N. M.; Chaudhry, U.; Calero Bernal, R.;

Cano Alsua, S.; Messina, D.; Evangelista, F.; Betson, M.; Lalle, M.; Jokelainen, P.; Ortega Mora, L. M.; Álvarez García, G.

Microorganisms 2022, 10 (3), 517.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10030517>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6351110#.YnkeCehBxwQ>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: *Toxoplasma Gondii* Genetic Diversity in Mediterranean Dolphins.

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Giorda, F.; Mattioda, V.; Audino, T.; Di Nocera, F.; Lucifora, G.; Varello, K.; Grattarola, C.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.; Casalone, C.; Calero-Bernal, R.

Pathogens 2022, 11 (8), 909. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11080909>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Unifying Virulence Evaluation in *Toxoplasma Gondii*: A Timely Task.

Calero-Bernal, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Katzer, F.; Su, C.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.

Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol. 2022, 12, 868727. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2022.868727>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: *Toxoplasma Gondii* Genotyping: A Closer Look Into Europe.

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Schares, G.; Maksimov, P.; Joeres, M.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.; Calero-Bernal, R.

Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol. 2022, 12, 842595. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2022.842595>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Comparative Performance of Five Recombinant and Chimeric Antigens in a Time-Resolved Fluorescence Immunoassay for Detection of *Toxoplasma Gondii* Infection in Cats.

Huertas-López, A.; Contreras Rojo, M.; Sukhumavasi, W.; Martínez-Subiela, S.; Álvarez-García, G.; López-Ureña, N. M.; Cerón, J. J.; Martínez-Carrasco, C.

Veterinary Parasitology 2022, 304, 109703. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2022.109703>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Detection of Anti-*Neospora Caninum* Antibodies in Sheep's Full-Cream Milk by a Time-Resolved Fluorescence Immunoassay.

Huertas-López, A.; Sánchez-Sánchez, R.; Diezma-Díaz, C.; Álvarez-García, G.; Martínez-Carrasco, C.; Martínez-Subiela, S.; Cerón, J. J.

Veterinary Parasitology 2022, 301, 109641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109641>

JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS: Genomic Characterization of Multidrug-Resistant *Salmonella* Serovar Kentucky ST198 Isolated in Poultry Flocks in Spain (2011–2017).

Samper-Cativiela, C.; Diéguez-Roda, B.; Trigo da Roza, F.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Enekave, E.; Lim, S.; Hernández, M.; Abad, D.; Collado, S.; Sáez, J. L.; de Frutos, C.; Agüero, M.; Moreno, M. Á.; Escudero, J. A.; Álvarez, J.

Microbial Genomics 2022, 8 (3).

<https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000773>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7082555>

JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS: Changing Epidemiology of *Salmonella* Enteritidis Human Infections in the Netherlands and Belgium, 2006 to 2019: A Registry-Based Population Study.

Chanamé Pinedo, L.; Franz, E.; van den Beld, M.; Van Goethem, N.; Mattheus, W.; Veldman, K.; Bosch, T.; Mughini-Gras, L.; Pijnacker, R.

Eurosurveillance 2022, 27 (38).

<https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.38.2101174>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/7303720>

2023 : 11 JRP publications

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR : The Heat Is On: Modelling the Persistence of ESBL-Producing *E. coli* in Blue Mussels under Meal Preparation.

Kausrud, K., Skjerdal, T., Johannessen, G. S., Ilag, H. K., Norström, M. (2022). *Foods*. 12(1), 14.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390%2Ffoods12010014>

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR : Estimating the likelihood of ESBL-producing *E. coli* carriage in slaughter-aged pigs following bacterial introduction onto a farm: A multiscale risk assessment.

McCarthy, C., Viel, A., Gavin, C., Sanders, P., Simons, R. R. L. (2022). *Microbial Risk Analysis*. 20, 100185.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2021.100185>

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR : Transmission routes of antibiotic resistant bacteria: a systematic review.

Godijk, N. G., Bootsma, M. C. J., Bonten, M. J. M. (2022). *BMC Infectious Disease*. 22(1), 482.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186%2Fs12879-022-07360-z>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Inflammatory Responses Induced by the Monophasic Variant of *Salmonella Typhimurium* in Pigs Play a Role in the High Shedder Phenotype and Fecal Microbiota Composition.

Kempf, F., Cordonni, G., Chaussé, A. M., Drumo, R., Brown, H., Horton, D. L., Paboeuf, F., Denis, M., Velge, P., La Ragione, R., & Kerouanton, A. (2023). *mSystems*. e0085222. Advance online publication.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1128/msystems.00852-22>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: Mapping the Evidence of the Effects of Environmental Factors on the Prevalence of Antibiotic Resistance in the Non-Built Environment: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map. *Environment International* 2023, 171, 107707.

Gardner, B.; Betson, M.; Cabal Rosel, A.; Caniça, M.; Chambers, M. A.; Contadini, F. M.; Gonzalez Villeta, L. C.; Hassan, M. M.; La Ragione, R. M.; de Menezes, A.; Messina, D.; Nichols, G.; Olivença, D. V.; Phalkey, R.; Prada, J. M.; Ruppitsch, W.; Santorelli, L. A.; Selemetas, N.; Tharmakulasingam, M.; M. van Vliet, A. H.; Woegerbauer, M.; Deza-Cruz, I.; Lo Iacono, G.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107707>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/7446911#.Y6G50nbMJD8>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: Molecular Epidemiology of *Clostridioides Difficile* in Companion Animals: Genetic Overlap with Human Strains and Public Health Concerns.

Alves, F.; Castro, R.; Pinto, M.; Nunes, A.; Pomba, C.; Oliveira, M.; Silveira, L.; Gomes, J. P.; Oleastro, M. *Front. Public Health* 2023, 10, 1070258.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.1070258>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/7528151#.Y7-bHbMJD8>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: *Clostridioides Difficile* in South American Camelids in Germany: First Insights into Molecular and Genetic Characteristics and Antimicrobial Resistance. *Antibiotics* 2023, 12 (1), 86.

Dost, I.; Abdel-Glil, M.; Schmooch, G.; Menge, C.; Berens, C.; González-Santamarina, B.; Wiegand, E.; Neubauer, H.; Schwarz, S.; Seyboldt, C.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics12010086>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7550849#.Y9Dmvv6ZND8>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Inflammatory Responses Induced by the Monophasic Variant of *Salmonella Typhimurium* in Pigs Play a Role in the High Shedder Phenotype and Fecal Microbiota Composition.

Kempf, F., Cordonni, G., Chaussé, A. M., Drumo, R., Brown, H., Horton, D. L., Paboeuf, F., Denis, M., Velge, P., La Ragione, R., & Kerouanton, A. (2023). *mSystems*. e0085222. Advance online publication.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1128/msystems.00852-22>

JRP20-FBZSH3-DiSCoVeR and JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS:- Genotypic and Phenotypic Characterization of Pathogenic *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp.*, and *Campylobacter spp.*, in Free-Living Birds in Mainland Portugal.

Batista, R., Saraiva, M., Lopes, T., Silveira, L., Coelho, A., Furtado, R., Castro, R., Correia, C. B., Rodrigues, D., Henriques, P., Lóio, S., Soeiro, V., da Costa P. M., Oleastro, M., Pista, A. (2023). *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 20(1), 223.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20010223>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Prevalence and Molecular Characterization of Toxoplasma Gondii in Different Types of Poultry in Greece, Associated Risk Factors and Co-Existence with Eimeria Spp.

Andreopoulou, M.; Schares, G.; Koethe, M.; Chaligiannis, I.; Maksimov, P.; Joeres, M.; Cardron, G.; Goroll, T.; Sotiraki, S.; Dauschies, A.; Bangoura, B.

Parasitol Res 2023, 122 (1), 97–111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-022-07701-6>

OHEJP : 6 publications

The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), 2018–2022: an exemplary One Health initiative. Brown, HL., Passey, JL., Getino, M., Pursley, I., Basu, P., Horton, DL., La Ragione, RM. (2020). *Journal of Medical Microbiology*, pp 1-3.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1099/jmm.0.001228>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5541709#.ZBBYyJHMJM0>

Participation in One Health Networks and Involvement in the COVID-19 Pandemic Response: A Global Study.

Streichert, L. C.; Sepe, L. P.; Jokelainen, P.; Stroud, C. M.; Berezowski, J.; Del Rio Vilas, V. J.

Front. Public Health 2022, 10, 830893.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.830893>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6255721#.YiXYeujML2A>

Search term “One Health” remains of limited use to identify relevant scientific publications: Denmark as a case study.

Benedetti, G., Jokelainen, P., & Ethelberg, S. (2022). *Frontiers in Public Health*. 10, 938460.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.938460>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6951259#.Y9kxzHDMJM2>

One Health collaboration with and among EU Agencies – Bridging research and policy.

Bronzwaer, S., Catchpole, M., de Coen, W., Dingwall, Z., Fabbri, K., Foltz, C., Ganzleben, C., van Gorcom, R., Humphreys, A., Jokelainen, P., Liebana, E., Rizzi, V., Url, B. (2022). *One Health*. 15, 100464.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2022.100464>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7354026#.Y9kyDnDMJM1>

OHEJP: A governance and coordination perspective – Sweden’s and Italy’s approaches to implementing One Health.

Humboldt-Dachroeden, Sarah. (2022). *SSM- Qualitative Research in Health*. 2, 100198.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100198>

EPI-Net One Health reporting guideline for antimicrobial consumption and resistance surveillance data: a Delphi approach.

Rajendran, N. B., Arieti, F., Mena-Benítez, C. A., Galia, L., Tebon, M., Alvarez, J., Gladstone, B. P., Collineau, L., De Angelis, G., Duro, R., Gaze, W., Göpel, S., Kanj, S. S., Käsbohrer, A., Limmathurotsakul, D., de Abechucu, E. L., Mazzolini, E., Mutters, N., T., Pezzani, M. D., Presterl, E., Renk, H., Rodríguez-Baño, J., Săndulescu, O., Scali, F., Skov, R., Velavan, T. P., Vuong, C., Tacconelli, E., Adegnika, A. A., Avery, L., Bonten, M., Cassini, A., Chauvin, C., Compri, M., Damborg, P., De Greeff, S., Del Toro, M. D., Filter, M., Franklin, A., Gonzalez-Zorn, B., Grave, K., Hocquet, D., Hoelzle, L. E., Kalanxhi, E.,

Laxminarayan, R., Leibovici, L., Malhotra-Kumar, S., Mendelson, M., Paul, M., Muñoz Madero, C., Murri, R., Piddock, L. J. V., Ruesen, C., Sanguinetti, M., Schilling, T., Schrijver, R., Schwaber, M. J., Scudeller, L., Torumkuney, D., Van Boeckel, T., Vanderhaeghen, W., Voss, A., Wozniak, T. (2022). *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe*. 2022, 100563.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanepe.2022.100563>.

1.3 Impact and relevance of the research projects

In the final reports, project leaders were requested to expand on the expected One Health impact that their project may have for any national and international stakeholders active in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, AMR and/or emerging threats. Among others, the following expectancies were mentioned:

- FARMED: aimed to harness long-read sequencing to allow scientists and stakeholders to detect pathogens and AMR within a variety of matrices, used throughout the One Health EJP consortium. In addition, several partners are in close contact with the stakeholders such as EFSA, ECDC, WHO via their reference laboratory tasks or working group memberships (e.g. European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL)) for *E. coli* at ISS, involved in the activities of the steering committee for the development of a joint EFSA-ECDC database for molecular typing data collection and coordinating the activities of an Inter EURLs working group on Next Generation Sequencing.
- WORLDCOM: the consortium have developed new harmonised methodologies and protocols for on-site rapid and sensitive detection of AMR using LAMP. It has been presented at national level in Ireland to the National Interdepartmental AMR Consultative Committee (with membership from government Departments of Health and Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine - DAFM).
- FULL-FORCE: the project brought together 17 institutes from 10 countries, all devoted to plasmid-based surveillance. It has provided data (such as the identified IncZ plasmids among human, but not animal *E. coli*) that will help convincing the national stakeholders of the need for continuous, structural investment in sequence-based surveillance technologies. For the international stakeholders (ECDC, EFSA), this project shows the added value of incorporating surveillance of mobile genetic elements in current programs.
- FED-AMR: has contributed to improve the methods and knowledge in environmental exDNA research and its role in AMR transmission, to collect and analyse large amounts of data and metadata from an agricultural environment, which outcomes have been presented to stakeholders and to underline the importance of the role of exDNA as a source of diverse antimicrobial resistances in the environment. The results obtained show how essential it is to track the spread of specific ARGs geographically and over time, identify new ARGs and support preventive measures and interventions against AMR pathogens.
- TELE-Vir: the project acknowledge strongly the OneHealth initiative that animals and humans are interdependent by presenting a biosurveillance POI toolbox for unbiased detection (metagenomics) of RNA- and DNA viruses in different sample materials from many species. The POI toolbox can be envisioned to be of interest for stakeholders in countries with low laboratory infrastructure and with a high biodiversity. For instance, INSA (human health sector) has already established contact with the “equivalent” institute from the Animal Health sector (INIHAV) in Portugal to introduce the TELEVIR toolbox, showing the direct application of the TELEVIR outputs in an OneHealth perspective. In addition, INSA strict collaboration with countries of Portuguese official language, namely African countries (e.g., NIH from Guinea-Bissau is already using the tool opens goods perspective that the POI toolbox can contribute to virus surveillance in the future.

- IDEMBRU : within the project, a first proficiency test has been organised for sequencing data. This applied exercise will help establishing standardised quality of genomic analyses within the reference laboratories. Moreover, several new complementary bacteriology analyses have been developed to separate core from non-core strains, and prepared one of the most complete MALDI-TOF spectral databases to identify core, non-core *Brucellae spp.* and *Ochrobactrum spp.*, that will greatly shorten the diagnostic time and responses to Brucella outbreaks. Moreover, specific virulence- and bio-markers were identified that, in combination with cellular infection results (cytokine and RNA profiles) will be the basis of zoonotic potential characterisation not only for Brucella, but also genetically similar species (*Francisella spp.* for example). During the IDEMBRU project, the collaboration with PADI Web platform for epidemic surveillance started on early warning systems for Brucella outbreaks in European countries.
- MEME : MEME impacted on animal health, public health and food safety sectors. Beneficiaries of scientific outputs of MEME were EU reference labs, international organizations (ECDC, EFSA, OIE, WHO, FAO) and all decision makers. The project has provided a set of molecular tools, epidemiological risk assessments and quantitative epidemiological models for the detection, surveillance and control of these parasitic infectious diseases in Europe and beyond.
- PARADISE : the use of genomics in epidemiology and surveillance of pathogens has been a major focus at the EU level in recent years, with EFSA/ECDC promoting several initiatives, mostly on bacteria. The important advances made by PARADISE at both the wet- and dry-lab level will contribute to a wider use of WGS and metagenomics. Complementarities with other projects within and beyond the OHEJP have resulted in the sharing of bioinformatics approaches for genome comparison (TOXOSOURCES) and has helped to identify strategies and challenges for implementation of molecular methods for *Cryptosporidium* (HARMONY-CAP). Interactions and networking with the *Cryptosporidium* Reference Unit, Public Health Wales, allowed continuous exchange of information on molecular typing schemes and their appropriate integration to public health surveillance.
- DISCoVeR: The project has collected comprehensive and standardised datasets for the target pathogens (Salmonella, Campylobacter, STEC, and ESBL and made the phenotypic and metadata open accessible. It has filled knowledge and data gaps regarding potential sources of foodborne zoonoses by including available data on non-livestock reservoirs and non-food sources. The project has critically assessed and improved existing source attribution models and developed new phenotypic and genomic based models for pathogen and antimicrobial resistance for attribution. It has applied the attribution approaches to quantify the contributions of animal reservoirs, including wildlife and companion animals, food and environmental sources, and compared and discussed the results across methods. The approaches and models developed in this project serve as proof of concept for other zoonoses and foodborne diseases.
- BIOPIGEE: the project aimed at identifying effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control hepatitis E virus (HEV) and Salmonella occurrence in European pig farming. The comprehensive literature reviews, field and experimental studies, expert opinion surveys and risk modelling which had been done provide a valuable knowledge base for international stakeholders involved in the domain of zoonoses. The outcomes include guidance for farmers, veterinarians, consultants and slaughterhouses in European countries in form of illustrative flyers and web content to inform stakeholders, incl. collaborating farm education centres. The material should provide reliable and cost-efficient guidance on the reduction of Salmonella and HEV spread in animals and humans (through occupational exposure) which add important information for monitoring and regulation in order to advance One Health. Regional and national authorities could pick up the material produced, translate them into their regional

language(s) and use them. It is also possible to develop the material further or adapt it to the local needs.

- TOXOSOURCES : the project contributed substantially to training of the next generations of One Health researchers. There are several examples of impact at national level. For example, a risk profile of foodborne parasites was compiled by the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration. In the Netherlands, the results were communicated with the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport which provided co-funding for TOXOSOURCES as well as to the preceding QMRA work. An example of impact at global level is that TOXOSOURCES project leader was invited to contribute to FAO Guidelines for surveillance of *Toxoplasma gondii*/toxoplasmosis in livestock. The developed and harmonized methods were applied to samples from humans, animals, and environment, and are implemented in laboratories across sectors, across Europe. The results of TOXOSOURCES will have substantial positive One Health impact at national, European and global levels. The results can inform actions that will improve food safety throughout the food chain: from improving infection prevention and control at farm level to lower prevalence in animals to risk mitigation in the production and processing of fresh produce, processing of meat into various products and preparing food in homes and restaurants. The evidence-based actions will improve not only human health, but also health and welfare of the animals raised for meat production or fed meat as part of their diets, as the infection can cause clinical disease also in animal hosts.
- ADONIS : The major outcome of this project is the conclusion that, since it showed increasing incidence in some countries and increased number of outbreaks at the EU level, more efforts should be undertaken to control Salmonella in the EU. Subsequently, the project has determined that the most relevant anchor points to achieve this point to the level of poultry health and production. This makes the problem of Salmonella a true One Health issue. Lowering the incidence and reducing the number of outbreaks can only be achieved by a joint effort between public health, veterinary health, and food safety domains. On the public health side the project has highlighted the importance of maintaining and improving a good functioning Salmonella surveillance system at the public health level with state-of-the-art (WGS) typing of isolates in order to efficiently detect clusters/outbreaks. The sharing of this typing data internationally and in a One Health setting is of the utmost importance to tackle cross-border events and to identify (potential) sources as quick as possible in order to prevent outgrowth of clusters/outbreaks.
- BeONE : the BeONE project resulted in tools and outputs that are expected to i) contribute to the capacitation of EU laboratories to carry out routine surveillance integrating both genomic and epidemiological data, ii) launch new research lines to improve FWD (food and waterborne diseases) genomic epidemiology, and iii) facilitate data sharing and comparability among EU countries, international organisations, and/or other stakeholders involved in FWD prevention and control. Fully aligned with the One Health concept, BeONE may ultimately promote an enhanced interoperability at multi-country and intersectoral levels towards an evidence-informed public health policy- and decision-making.

2 Reports of the JRP, Year 5

2.1 JRP12-R2-AMRSH5-FARMED

2.1.1 Consortium composition

Role	Name	Institute, Country
Project Leader	Manal AbuOun	21, APHA, UK
Deputy Project Leader	Michael Brouwer Sigrid De Keersmaecker	31, WBVR, NL 4, Sciensano, BE
WP1 Leader	Sigrid De Keersmaecker	4, Sciensano, BE
WP1 co-Leader	Josephine Grützke	9, BfR, GE
WP2 Leader	Saria Otani	12, DTU, DK
WP2 co-Leader	Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn	17, UCM, Spain
WP3 Leader	Michael Brouwer	31, WBVR, NL
WP3 co-Leader	Soren Persson	27, SSI, DK
WP4 Leader	Manal AbuOun	21, APHA, UK
WP4 co-Leader	Michael Brouwer	31, WBVR, NL

2.1.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Advances in sequencing technologies and bioinformatics have enabled easier detection of genetic material. FARMED has allowed EU institutes to assess the feasibility, and implementation, of long-read metagenome and resistome sequencing, to provide investigators with the early detection of pathogens to apply the most appropriate control measures. FARMED members have given presentations at various scientific meetings and engaged with stakeholders as well as peer-reviewed publications.

Primarily a wet laboratory-based project, FARMED project was severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic due to staff resources at many institutes being diverted to COVID-19 activities as well as significant delays in receiving consumables required for the project. Despite this, we progressed the FARMED objectives.

WP1 (Assess feasibility of Long-read metagenome sequencing on exemplar matrices. Investigate the use of Hi-C metagenomics). Initially we identified and compared commercially available DNA extraction kits using simple and complex matrix samples (range covering the One Health spectrum) spiked with in-house or commercially available routinely identified bacterial species (mock communities). An integral step in sequencing is the ability to extract DNA from samples, which is of suitable quality, quantity, and purity, however the methods employed were dependent on the sample matrices. Based on the obtained results, the feasibility of using long-read sequencing for species and AMR identification in different sample matrices in a diagnostic setting (i.e., pathogens present at relatively high load) was demonstrated. Hi-C sequencing was explored as a tool to define the context of AMR genes (e.g., linkage of plasmid to its host in metagenomics samples). Using a mock community, an assignment of AMR genes to species was possible with an accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity of >90%. However, the application of Hi-C sequencing is not yet standardised and far away from routine or field settings, both at wet lab and dry lab level.

WP2 aimed to develop Bioinformatics tools to analyse the sequencing data and define the characteristics within the sample. Since the inception of FARMED, DTU had further developed KMA (k-mer alignment and thus was the preferred analysis tool. KMA and ResFinder (<https://cge.food.dtu.dk/services/ResFinder/>) are ready-to-use to call for antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes from the sequencing data. Although KMA is a fast tool to process sequence data in real-time, the output required improvement to simplify and direct the user to the reliable results, for which we developed a suggested list of parameters, aiming to aid users in considering the confidence of presence of bacterial species within a sample.

WP3 concentrated on the Implementation of on-site protocols for long-read metagenomic DNA sequencing, including isolation of DNA from sample matrices, long-read sequencing, and bioinformatics analysis, conducted 'outside' of traditional laboratory setting. A review of the available literature identified several factors that were required and included four definitions of on-site sequencing with access to variable facilities such as internet connection, power for equipment and access to cold storage. Although this was not possible for all institutes, several were able to perform the required steps in the field/on-site or on-site simulation, with varying success. There are now kits on the market enabling on-site DNA isolation which have been tested by the FARMED consortium with variable success. However, currently the restricting barrier to accomplish full 'on-site' long-read metagenomics, including resistome analysis, is the sequencing as this requires several hours to achieve the desired depth of sequencing and analysis steps, requiring sufficient computational power and time.

FARMED has shown that long-read metagenomics is feasible for analysis of a variety of sample matrices, applicable to range of stakeholders, but still requires both wet-laboratory standardisation and bioinformatics automation to ensure confidence and accurate comparison of results between laboratories. For its full on-site application, some identified limitations should be addressed through further maturation of the technology.

2.1.3 Work carried out in the JRP/IIP. scientific results and integrative outcomes

The aim of FARMED was to assess the feasibility of long-read metagenomics to characterise the metagenome and identify pathogen and AMR within various One Health samples matrices used in both the human, animal, and environment surveillance and research. FARMED was divided into three linked scientific work packages (WP1) assess long-read metagenomics within laboratory, (WP2) bioinformatics analysis tools to identify bacteria within the microbiome and (3) develop protocols for on-site long-read metagenomics.

WP1 - Assess feasibility of Long-read metagenome sequencing on exemplar matrices. Investigate the use of Hi-C metagenomics.

WP1 was led by Sciensano and BfR, with contributions from all members of the consortium.

JRP12-WP1-T1-Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'defined' microbial community.

Although all the consortium had experience with short read metagenomics and long-read sequencing of pure isolates, only four had experiences of long-read metagenomics. A survey of the consortium identified the different methods and experiences of institutes with both short- and long-read sequencing technologies, highlighting the different matrices from a variety of human, animal, and environmental sources examined, DNA extraction methods, and bioinformatics tools used to detect bacterial species and/or AMR. An integral part step in any sequencing is the ability to extract and isolate DNA from samples, which is of suitable quality, quantity, and purity. Without this long-read metagenomes could yield bias results as well as inability to collocate bacteria or plasmids to AMR genes. WP1 started by assessing the DNA extraction methods currently used within the consortium,

using either pond water or water buffalo faeces samples, spiked with 6 bacterial species at different concentrations (table 1), as well as un-spiked control samples. The two different sample matrices, water buffalo faeces (complex matrix) and pond water (simple matrix) were chosen as they were the most common sample matrices used by the consortium. BfR prepared a defined microbial community (DMC), consisting of four Gram-negative isolates and two Gram-positive isolates with known complete genome sequences and different AMR profiles (table 1). Two differently composed communities, either with a fixed concentration of 10^5 CFU/ml or with a range from 10^3 to 10^7 CFU/ml were used to spike the two matrices. The matrices were screened for *Salmonella*, and ESBL and/ or Carbapenemase producing Enterobacteriaceae as well as by PCR for isolates harbouring the *mcr-1* to *mcr-9* genes to ensure they were negative and suitable for the DMC analysis. The integrity of DNA present was preserved, within the defined mock community and the matrices themselves, samples were prepared with the commercial nucleic acid preservation solution DNA/RNA Shield (Zymo Research).

Table 1 – The concentration of bacteria used to spike complex and simple matrices (DMC).

Bacteria	Control	Fixed Concentration DMC (CFU/ml)	Mixed Concentration DMC (CFU/ml)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	0	10 ⁵	10 ³
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	0	10 ⁵	10 ³
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0	10 ⁵	10 ⁵
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	0	10 ⁵	10 ⁵
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	0	10 ⁵	10 ⁷
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	0	10 ⁵	10 ⁷

Each partner used the DNA extraction protocols (mainly commercially available kits) already used/present in their laboratories, which include bead beating, enzymatic lysis or a mixture of to extract DNA. The concentration of DNA extracted by the various methods ranged from 1 to 60 ng/μl of DNA, with satisfactory 260/280 ratio (1.6-1.8). The range of DNA fragment sizes (3-50kb) also varied between the methods. The project partners used the same long-read sequencing kits (ONT Ligation sequencing kit (SQK-LSK109) and native barcoding Expansion) in order to obtain comparable sequencing results between the consortium. DNA was sequenced with Illumina short-read (these varied between the consortium) and ONT-MinION (Flow Cell R9) long-read sequencing technologies, aiming to achieve ~5Gbp per sample.

An evaluation of the short (Illumina) and long (ONT) read sequencing of a defined mock community (DMC) consisting of 6 species (four Gram-negative isolates and two Gram-positive isolates) with known complete genome sequences and different AMR profiles, spiked into water buffalo faeces or pond water at different concentrations, was performed. Analysis showed that long-read sequencing using ONT technology was able to identify some of the bacterial species contained in the DMC, but not all, which appeared to be dependent on the DNA extraction method used. Comparison of the microbial profiles, from short and long read data, found different clustering depending on the database used (SILVA/16S or complete genomes). Illumina data clustered by institute when using the 16S SILVA database, whereas when the FARMED_db (complete genomes) was used, the samples clustered based on sample type rather than by institute or DNA method. For MinION data using the FARMED_db, the clustering was less clear where the samples from different institutes generally separated according to either blank (FB) or mixed concentration (FM) sample type. Analysis of the AMR content was less impacted by institute or DNA extraction method. The differences observed in the bacterial composition of samples was likely due to the depth of sequencing undertaken as well as DNA extraction method. It is encouraging that although there was variation in the sequencing, most were able to identify the spiked bacterial species in the DMC samples.

Three commercially available DNA extraction kits which showed the greatest promise were selected for further scrutiny, where at least two institutes would use each DNA extraction kit, using real-life 'simple' (WP1-T2) and 'complex' (WP1-T3) matrices of choice for the respective institutes. To enable comparison between institutes and determine the detection limits, a commercially available mock community (ZymoBIOMICS Gut Microbiome Standard, GMS, CAT no D6331), was used to achieve a consistent output between different users and allow comparison of methods between partners in the consortium, which will be discussed in WP1-T2 and WP-1-T3.

It is important to understand the impact of chosen methodology, such as the different extraction methods, sequencing library preparations, sequence base-calling, as well as the data analysis method, will have on the results obtained. Sciensano compared the output of different sequence coverages (i.e. 1 or 3 samples pooled on a MinION flow cell) to retrieve the expected species and AMR genes. A

lot of information was lost due to improper demultiplexing when pooling 3 samples on a MinION flow cell, which was corrected by sequencing only one sample per flow cell, that identified previously missing species, as well as increased the number of AMR genes detected. APHA has compared and evaluated the choice of sequencing library preparation kit (slower ligation library kit vs faster rapid library kit) as well as the basecalling (fast vs high accuracy) approach, both can be time-consuming stages thereby impacting timely delivery of results. The ligation library kit and the high accuracy (HAC) base-calling identified more species compared to the rapid library kit and the fast basecalling. However, the ligation kit failed to detect several DMC species which could be down to either the inappropriate size selection step used during library preparation or the choice of KMA parameter thresholds, which required optimisation and evaluation (WP2-T1). If the focus of the investigation is to identify pathogens or bacterial species harbouring AMR genes of interest rather than the exploration of all microbiomes species then the faster and less labour intensive Rapid kit may be a suitable option. A consideration must therefore be made between sequencing costs and depth of coverage required to detect pathogens or to characterise the metagenome.

PacBio's long-read sequencing technology relies on circular consensus sequencing (CCS) with the promise to produce >10kb high-fidelity long (HiFi) reads for metagenome profiling and assembly. PacBio recommends 4 samples per flow cell to assemble metagenomes from a sample. At BfR, in parallel to short-read Illumina and long-read ONT sequencing, the previously described samples of the DMC spiked into water buffalo faeces were sequenced using the PacBio technology. Analyses of the fixed and mixed samples could successfully identify reads of all six members of the DMC as well as the water buffalo matrix. However, due to the low number of reads, different assembly programmes were unable to assemble the spiked bacteria from the metagenomes. Due to the unexpected large extent of required optimisation of the PacBio laboratory as well as the bioinformatics workflow in combination with the inability to multiplex samples in larger number and the resulting high cost of PacBio sequencing per sample, it was decided to focus on the more efficient ONT methodology. Furthermore, the high requirement of input DNA concentrations as well a lengthy library preparation time of two days underlined that PacBio does not serve as a suitable long-read alternative, since the quality of its data output did not compensate for the additional workload needed or the higher costs in respect of metagenomic demands.

JRP12-WP1-T2- Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'simple' sample matrices.

Simple matrices were defined as matrices with low level of bacterial contamination, for example river and irrigation water. DNA extraction from these matrices would usually require pre-processing to concentrate the bacterial population into a smaller workable volume, which may introduce complications such as sample viscosity as well as alteration of bacterial composition through loss of specific genera.

ISS: The Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit for DNA extraction (Zymo Research) was tested on three different matrices relevant for Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*: flour, lettuce and sprout spent irrigation water. For the first two matrices this DNA extraction method proved difficult to apply and thus were not analysed further. In detail, flour was difficult to mix in a small amount of liquid used in the first steps of the extraction and only 665 ng in total were obtained (concentration 13.3 ng/μl) when extracting DNA from 200 mg of floor spiked with 75 μl of GMS, which was not enough for MinION sequencing. Similarly, lettuce was used to try to extract DNA from the contaminating flora, including the spiked GMS, but only 725 ng (concentration 14.5 ng/μl) were obtained in total when starting from 200 mg of sample spiked with 75 μl of GMS, which was not enough for MinION sequencing. For this reason, it was concluded that such kit was not the best solution for extracting DNA from contaminating microflora from flour and vegetal samples. No other attempts were made on such matrices.

On the other hand, several attempts were made for extracting DNA from sprouts spent irrigation water, because it is one of the matrices mentioned in Reg. (EU) 209/2013, laying down microbiological

criteria for testing the contamination of sprouts with Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*. The use of a filtration step was excluded, due to the viscosity of the matrix. Using the same DNA extraction kit: starting from 200 µl of sample only allowed to obtain total 11 ng of DNA extracted; thus concentration of the water samples was applied (5000 rpm for 30 minutes) in the following tests performed without the spiking with GMS. In detail, when concentrating 25 ml of sample a total of 210 ng was obtained (concentration 6 ng/µl), while 385 ng (concentration 11 ng/µl) when concentrating 50 ml of water and 1750 ng (concentration 50 ng/µl) when concentrating 200 ml of water, which was sufficient for MinION sequencing. The GMS and sprout spent irrigation water spiked with GMS samples were MinION sequenced using the native ligation barcoding genomic kit (SQK-LSK109) kit, with barcoding kit (EXP-NBD114), to prepare the libraries, and sequenced on a flowcell (FLO-MIN106 R.9.4.1) for total 21 hours and 21 minutes. Preliminary analyses identified low number of reads: 5,942 reads from clean GMS and 6,946 reads from spiked water, for 58.8 Mb and 62.7 Mb totally sequenced, respectively (Read length N50 were 19kb and 23kb, respectively). The data were analysed on ARIES (<https://w3.iss.it/site/aries/>), a webserver developed at ISS for NGS data analysis. The reads were trimmed with Porechop with default parameters and then mapped with KMA tool against a precompiled database of bacterial sequences (<ftp://ftp.cbs.dtu.dk/public/CGE/databases/KmerFinder/20200420>). Despite the low number of reads, the results showed that the sequence obtained from the pure GMS sample contained all the expected species present in the original sample with relative abundance higher than 1.5%. In the sequence obtained from the water sample spiked with GMS, only the species present in the pure GMS sample with relative abundance higher than 6% could be retrieved. Nevertheless, the number of reads classified as the detected species ranged only between 85 (for *Bifidobacterium adolescentis*) and 1328 (for *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*) (mean 389.5) for the clean GMS sample and between 5 (for *Fusobacterium nucleatum*) and 249 (for *Roseburia hominis*) (mean 51) for the spiked water sample. This task has allowed ISS to develop our understanding of what other bacteria may be present in such matrices.

UCM: UCM analysed water from the Manzanares river, a river that flows through the metropolitan area of Madrid, being the samples taken specifically on a spot prior to the entrance of the river course in the centre of the city. To extract the genomic DNA of the microbial community present in the water sample, a previous step of enrichment of the sample was needed, and two different approaches were tested, centrifugation and filtration. A first attempt of centrifugation of 100 ml of water at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes was carried out, but the gDNA yield obtained using the Quick-DNA HMW MagBead Kit (Zymo Research) was too low to perform ONT MinION sequencing (less than 50 ng overall). Centrifugation of approximately 800 ml of water was performed and enough gDNA concentrations for ONT MinION sequencing were obtained using this method (concentrations ranging between 1000 and 1500 ng). Multiplexed (duplex) sequencing including pure GMS and sample spiked with GMS was tried, but a dramatic loss of sequencing pores occurred in the first hours of the run, rendering a sequencing run with low number of reads (54798 reads/296 Mb in total, 21233 reads/119 Mb belonging to GMS sample and 21795 reads/115 Mb belonging to SPIKED sample). The amount of data was low, but the quality and length of the reads was acceptable, being overall enough for subsequent analysis.

To assess what was the problem with the ONT MinION run, purity of the samples pointed out as a probable cause of the rapid pore loss. Quality of the different gDNA extractions performed was assessed, giving A260/A280 and A260/A230 purity ratios very inconsistent, sometimes higher, and sometimes lower than the required standards, being very rarely suitable for sequencing. Therefore, we went back to the centrifugation method making some changes suggested by other members of the FARMED project. We increased the centrifugation time to 3 hours and the amount of water to 300 ml, and with these modifications we were able to obtain adequate concentrations for ONT MinION sequencing (always more than 1500 ng). In addition, the purity of these samples was more consistent and in a range that was suitable for sequencing (values between 1.8 and 2.0 for both ratios). The same sequencing strategy was carried out and with these new pure samples we were able to have a run of 72 hours without errors and producing a normal amount of data (5631726 reads/19.8 Gb in total,

2298080 reads/6.8 Gb belonging to GMS sample and 2618223 reads/10.3 Gb belonging to SPIKED sample) with an acceptable read length (~3.5Kb) and a good read quality (~10.2).

KMA was used for the detection of the species present in the Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) in the data obtained in the two sequencing runs performed. In the first run, the number of pores sequencing highly decreased in the first hours of the run, producing a limited amount of data to work with. KMA was able to detect even the species of the GMS with a relative abundance of 0.01% in the PURE GMS sample. However, this detection is based on a low number of reads mapped to the reference genome of the species and with other metrics being below of the criteria to truly considered that species as present in the community investigated. On the other hand, in the GMS SPIKED sample we were not able to retrieve the species at a relative abundance of 0.01%, our limit was marked at the species with a relative abundance of 1.5%. This is most likely caused by the dilution of the GMS in the simple matrix, which lowers even more the relative abundance of the species. In addition, the number of reads classified as the different species were low overall, but even so KMA was able to detect them, which shows the great detection capacity that the tool has. The second sequencing run worked without problems for 37 hours, which was translated in a good amount of data of a relatively good quality. Contrarily as what was expected, the limit of detection in the PURE GMS sample was still at the species with a relative abundance of 0.01%, but now the number of reads and the rest of metrics support strongly the presence of the species on the community analysed. These results were repeated in the GMS SPIKED sample, with lower but equal results in terms of supporting evidence of the presence of the different species. With respect to AMR, KMA detected only 5 of the 7 ARGs were detected. The gene in *S. enterica* (with a relative abundance of 0.01%) was not detected despite the trace of bacteria identified in the taxonomic analysis. We need to consider the fact that the ONT MinION flowcell was multiplexed with both samples (Duplex), so maybe if a single sample was loaded the sequencing depth could be enough to detect the species of the GMS with lower relative abundances. In terms of the microbial community present in the river water sample, we were able to identify bacteria commonly detected in water samples, like species from the genera *Microcystitis*, *Aurantimicrobium* or *Limnohabitans*. Since the database used was a small representation of bacteria to be taken on-site, there might be more species known and even unknown in our samples, that can be only retrieved with other databases or other approaches. These data support the idea that metagenomic long-read sequencing from simple matrixes is feasible, but special attention needs to be taken in the purity of the samples, because the enrichment method used might affect the quality of the gDNA to a point that the sequencing can easily fail. The selection of the database is also key to be able to detect specific bacteria in these less well studied environments.

JRP12-WP1-T3- Assess feasibility/perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'complex' sample matrices.

Complex matrices were defined as matrices with high level of background material as well potentially high and diverse levels of bacteria, for example faeces, food, environmental (e.g. dust), milk, waste water, boot swabs.

APHA: had access to the REHAB project's metagenome samples (AbuOun et. al. 2020, <https://www.microbiologyresearch.org/content/journal/mgen/10.1099/mgen.0.000630>), faecal samples recovered from pig and cattle, which had previously been extracted with the MOBIO PowerSoil DNA isolation kit and sequenced using Illumina. Spiked (ZymoBIOMICS Gut Microbiome Standard added to the sample) and none-spiked faecal samples were processed with GenFind v3 (Beckman) and PureLink (Invitrogen) kits using modified protocols followed by long-read sequencing. It was observed that GenFind v3 yielded higher DNA concentrations compared to PureLink whether extracting from pure ZymoBIOMICS standard (75ul) or faecal material (200mg). Interestingly, spiked samples yielded even higher DNA concentrations compared to none-spiked samples. Samples were originally sequenced using Rapid barcoding kit (SQK-RBK004) and multiplexed (6 samples on a flow cell). This multiplexing and rapid library preparation approach has previously yielded enough sequence data for identification of spiked species in DMC samples using KMA pipeline and thus was used again

when spiking faecal samples (from REHAB project) with gut-microbiome standards from Zymo. The obtained data was used for KMA parameter testing and optimisation which were carried out in collaboration with Sciensano and BfR. However, the generated sequence coverage was not sufficient to test other metagenome analysis approaches, particularly for metagenome assembly approaches. Because of this the DNA extractions from REHAB samples (pig and cattle faeces) were subsequently **re-done** using GenFind V3 kit with the lysis performed using lysozyme and metapolyzyme. The library preparation was then carried out using the Ligation sequencing gDNA kit (SQK-LSK109) with barcodes from Native barcoding expansion kit (EXP-NBD114). Additionally, only two samples were sequenced per MinION flow cell (R9.4).

The sequenced data together with available short-read data were processed using the KMA pipeline (WP2-T1). Alpha diversity analysis (the Simpson diversity index, Shannon diversity index and Chao1 richness estimate) was performed using the diversity function in the vegan package in R. The abundance and diversity of identified taxa (genera) in both cattle and pig samples were found to differ by the NGS approach used (short-read vs long-read). Choice of the extraction method could also have influenced the diversity among samples; however, this was not directly tested and thus the influence of DNA isolation approaches is unknown. At the taxonomy level, higher microbial diversity and richness was observed among cattle and pig samples sequenced on Illumina system (short-read). The diversity and richness among remaining samples, although obtained using different lysis enzymes, but sequenced on MinION system, remained highly similar. At the AMR level, all cattle samples appeared to have similar or close diversity and richness values regardless of the NGS approach. However, in pig samples the higher diversity again appears to be among samples processed on Illumina compared to samples processed using MinION. Genus and AMR gene abundance was then analysed using principal coordinate analyses (PCoA). There was a clear batch separation of samples from those sequenced on Illumina to those sequenced on MinION. Interestingly, the MinION samples further separated by animal (pig and cattle) whereas such separation was not observed in Illumina samples. Dominant AMR classes across all samples were beta-lactam, macrolide, and tetracycline. As observed in diversity analysis, there was high variation in identified bacterial taxa, which appeared to be due to the NGS approach used and the animal. Further work is underway to understand these differences.

BfR: Through the German National Reference Laboratories for *Salmonella* as well as for *Escherichia coli*, the sequencing unit of the BfR was provided with two complex sample matrices with bacterial contamination: ground up insect (cricket) powder and sesame paste (tahini) naturally contaminated with *Bacillus* and/or *Salmonella*. Ground cricket powder was chosen as it is a novel food in terms of Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 and gaining importance as an alternative food source as insect-based foods are gaining importance as an alternative for future world nutrition. The selection of contaminated tahini matrix was triggered by an ongoing international outbreak with several *Salmonella* serovars included, where Tahini samples were either positive or negative for *Salmonella*, while the insect powder was either *Bacillus* positive and *Salmonella* negative or *vice versa*. In all these cases, the complex sample matrices had been analysed microbiologically and contamination levels had been determined. From 200 mg of these samples, DNA was extracted utilising the established ZymoBionics HMW DNA Kit. The ground insect powder yielded low DNA concentrations, potentially due to high salt concentrations and storage conditions. Despite their high fat content, the tahini samples yielded sufficient DNA concentrations for ONT sequencing. Thus, in total four complex matrix samples were sequenced using ONT technology: *Salmonella*-contaminated tahini, uncontaminated tahini, *Bacillus*-positive cricket powder and *Salmonella*-positive cricket powder. The two tahini samples were multiplexed with the *Salmonella*-contaminated cricket sample and sequenced using the ONT native barcoding kit (SQK-LSK109). The *Bacillus*-positive cricket sample was multiplexed separately with other isolate samples and sequenced at an earlier date using the ONT rapid kit (SQK-RBK004). The ONT rapid kit has a shorter laboratory workflow and relies on a single step to cleave DNA and attach barcodes, while the native barcoding kit consists of a lengthier protocol relying on ligation, which can produce better yields.

Nevertheless, analyses of sequencing data from the *Bacillus*-contaminated insect sample correctly identified the *Bacillus* contamination and further analyses were able to assemble contigs (flye), assign a *Bacillus* clade and identify AMR genes. On the other hand, the sequencing of the *Salmonella*-contaminated tahini and insect samples only yielded a small number of four or zero *Salmonella* reads, respectively. In the case of the *Salmonella*-positive tahini sample, four *Salmonella* reads were classified, but they could neither be assembled nor assigned to a certain serovar. This discrepancy between *Salmonella*- and *Bacillus*-contamination could potentially be due to the different levels of contamination, which was supposed to be very low for the *Salmonella* positive tahini sample. As had been established microbiologically, the *Bacillus* contamination in the insect sample was around 6.4×10^5 CFU/g, while the *Salmonella* contamination of the tahini sample was estimated to be much lower, since the *Enterobacteriaceae* contamination was determined to be at 2.9×10^1 CFU/ml. Nevertheless, in the sequencing results of both, the *Salmonella*-contaminated tahini sample and the negative tahini sample, the complex plant matrix, *Sesamum indicum*, was identified correctly.

These same samples were also sequenced using short-read Illumina technology. Comparisons with the long-read sequencing data of these samples shows that the percentage of classified long-read sequencing reads (<10% unclassified) far exceeded the percentage of classified short-read sequencing reads (65-70% unclassified), although the higher percentage of classified reads in the long-read data didn't always translate to more bacteria reads. Moreover, the complex matrix *Sesamum indicum* was more readily identified in both of the long-read sequenced tahini samples compared to short-read data and at least four *Salmonella* reads could be classified in the long-read data of the contaminated tahini sample compared to no *Salmonella* reads in corresponding short-read data. Lastly, the *Bacillus* spike in the insect sample could not be readily identified by short-read sequencing as reads belonging to the *Bacillus* genus only made up 1% of the total number of reads, while for the long-read sample the *Bacillus cereus* reads (the species confirmed microbiologically) made up 50% of all the classified reads.

Overall, we could establish that ONT sequencing has the ability to correctly identify bacterial contamination in complex sample matrices, even in matrices with challenging properties such as high fat or salt contents. Even utilising ONT's rapid library preparation workflow (SQK-RBK004) enabled the assembly of bacterial contigs, assignment of clades and AMR identification. However, the levels of bacterial contamination are still a crucial factor. For the matrices analysed here, long-read technology proved superior at identifying the selected bacterial contaminants in comparison to the short-read sequencing approach.

DTU: As part of DTU projects (Global Sewage (<https://www.globalsurveillance.eu/projects/global-surveillance-of-antimicrobial-resistance>) and Veterinærforlig III (<https://www.foedevarestyrelsen.dk/Leksikon/Sider/Gennemf%C3%B8relse-af-Veterin%C3%A6rforlig.aspx>)), both pig faeces and sewage were available to be included in this task. Pig faeces and sewage were sequenced on GridION platform (ONT), with and without the standardised mock community (ZymoBIOMICS Gut Microbiome Standard D6331). As well as the standardised mock community on its own. The DNA was extracted using Quick-DNA HMW MagBead kit (Zymo), and Ligation Sequencing Kit SQK-LSK109 and Native Barcoding Expansion (PCR-free) EXP-NBD104 kits (ONT) were used for library preparation and sample multiplexing. Seven Gbp in 4.8 M reads were sequenced, with 3 kb N50 and 56 kb as the longest read. The output was then mapped to our manually curated Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification), and to ResFinder database for AMR predictions. All spiked bacterial species were identified in DTU's initial analyses. Approximately 60% of the spiked bacterial species abundances were consistent with the artificial inputs of the added bacterial abundance in the mock community in the metagenomic samples in this initial analysis by DTU.

SCIENSANO: Sciensano worked with two different complex matrices. First, Sciensano performed shotgun metagenomics experiments using chicken faeces as 'complex' sample matrix. A Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) was spiked either in PBS (PURE sample) or in chicken faeces (SPIKED sample). Chicken faeces were also analysed unspiked (BLANK sample) to have an idea of the natural

microflora. DNA was extracted from the 3 samples (PURE, SPIKED and BLANK) using the Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit from ZymoResearch (selected in WP1-T1) and yielded enough (1.6 - 5.6 µg) of pure long fragment DNA (30 - 60 kb), meeting the requirement for Nanopore sequencing with the ligation prep (min 1 µg). The samples were sequenced with Nanopore (one sample per flowcell) as well as with Illumina (one sample per run) for comparison purpose. Except for the PURE sample for which a new DNA extraction was needed, the same samples were also used for multiplex Nanopore sequencing with 3 samples per one flowcell. All sequencing runs produced high amount of genomic data suitable for bioinformatics analysis (see WP2.T1). Nevertheless, it can be noticed that few bases (12.3%) were lost because not properly demultiplexed (unclassified or misclassified) by Guppy with the Nanopore multiplexed run. After evaluation of the sequencing statistics, the hypothesis was made that the lost reads belonged to SPIKED sample and could result from a matrix effect. Using KMA, all species with relative abundance higher than 0.001 % could be detected in the PURE sample sequenced in singleplex, and higher than 0.01% in triplex as well as Illumina. In SPIKED samples, *Bifidobacterium adolescentis* and the species with relative abundance 0.1% or below could not be detected, independently of the sequencing method or the multiplexing level. Overall, species were better detected with Nanopore singleplex than with Nanopore triplex or Illumina, attesting the feasibility of using this technology for metagenomics analysis. Nevertheless, the accuracy and sensitivity of the sequencing were greatly influenced by experimental settings. This was shown in a comparison, made by Sciensano using the detection criteria (see WP2-T1), of the KMA output data from APHA, BfR, Sciensano, SSI and WBVR. These 5 institutes performed similar experiments with GMS analysed pure or spiked in complex matrix, but using different sequencing multiplexing levels (1plex, 3plex, 4plex, 5plex and 6plex), run time (24h, 48h and 72h) library preparation methods (rapid or ligation kit) and DNA extraction kits (Quick-DNA HMW MagBead kit, ZymoResearch or GenFind V3, Beckman). The different combination of experimental settings were sorted from "ideal settings" (i.e. singleplex, 72h, ligation kit and Quick-DNA HMW MagBeat kit) to "cost-time efficient settings" (i.e. 6plex, 24h, rapid kit and GenFind V3 kit). It appeared that, the more the experimental settings go from ideal to cost-time efficient, the more the detection accuracy and sensitivity decreased, both being not anymore comparable to Illumina sequencing.

Secondly, Sciensano performed the analysis of the complex feed additive matrix using shotgun metagenomics. Feed additives (e.g., vitamins) are often produced using genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs) to replace chemical synthesis methods, as this is more practical and requires fewer resources. The presence of a GMMs or its DNA, often harbouring AMR genes, in microbial fermentation products is prohibited by European regulations. If no isolate of the GMM can be obtained, a metagenomics approach is the only way to demonstrate the presence of a GMM in a microbial fermentation product, with characterisation based on detection of AMR genes and vectors, species and unnatural associations in the GMM genome. We based the evaluation of the feasibility of this new approach on the investigation of a previously analysed sample containing a GMM *Bacillus subtilis* (rapid alert to the competent authorities (EU): RASFF 2014.1249) overproducing vitamin B2 (riboflavin), isolated and fully characterised at that time. The method was applied to a sample positive for some qPCR markers but for which no isolate could be obtained. The short and long-read sequencing technologies were compared for their performances, including the newly released Flongle, as a smaller and cost-effective alternative. The analysis was finalised, and the results published in Buytaers et al. 2021 (Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences, Volume 2, 30 July 2021, 100023). Altogether, our method allowed to predict the presence of a GMM in the sample, based on the simultaneous detection of AMR genes or vectors in species previously described as common GMM producers, and the encounter of unnatural associations in the genome. This open approach can be applied to other GMM used to produce fermentation products like food enzymes. This was done in a next phase, whereby combining short- and long-read metagenomic sequencing, several *Bacillus* contaminations were detected in multiple food enzyme samples: *B. velezensis*, *B. licheniformis* and *B. amyloliquefaciens*; of which the latter two constitute unviable organisms that could not be cultivated. Furthermore, the three transgenic constructs could be fully characterised. Lastly, these contaminations were carrying a

considerable load of AMR genes, representing a potential public health risk. These results have been published: <https://doi.org/10.3390/life12121971>.

SSI: Two different clinical diarrheagenic faecal samples (A and B) both culture-negative for conventional gastrointestinal pathogens, were used for the spiking experiment and analysed as native samples or spiked with GMS, in addition to being lysed by either lysozyme or bead-beating, prior to GenFind DNA extraction. Average DNA yield and total no of bp for lysozyme and bead-beating were 3051/2300 ng and 1,410,563,822/2,058,714,719, respectively. Generally, longer reads were observed from lysis with bead-beating. Based on species identification of GMS species in spiked clinical samples, detection limits of both lysis procedures were approximately 0.1-1% relative abundance. The Gram-positive species *C. difficile* was only detected in samples lysed by bead-beating, indicating that this procedure is superior with respect to Gram-positive bacteria.

Clinical sample A was found to contain 61/55% relative abundance of *Klebsiella oxytoca* reads by bead-beating and lysozyme lysis, respectively. This opportunistic pathogen (antibiotic associated diarrhoea) is not part of the conventional diagnostics and could therefore be associated with the clinical presentation. Further analysis found significant numbers of reads related to β -lactamase resistance gene *bla_{oxy}* (ResFinder) and plasmid IncFIB (PlasmidFinder), both previously identified in *Klebsiella oxytoca* (Paskova et al. (2018), PMID: 30042758). The clinical sample B did not contain any pathogenic species, but an abnormal high amount of *E. coli*, i.e., 60/65% relative abundance for bead-beating and lysozyme lysis, respectively. Reads were analysed by VirulenceFinder, but did not retrieve any *E. coli* virulence genes, so the observed imbalance of high amount of *E. coli*, may be attributed to post diarrhoea and/or prior antibiotic treatment. ResFinder analysis identified resistance genes towards aminoglycosides, β -lactamases, trimethoprim, macrolide, sulphonamide, tetracycline and aminoglycoside along with read originating from plasmids IncFIA, IncFIB, IncFII and repUS2, where Inc-plasmids are well known of carrying many of the detected resistance genes found by ResFinder.

WBVR performed a comparative analysis of the various sample preparation kits from Oxford Nanopore technologies, based on two DNA isolation kits, the Beckman Genfind V3 DNA and the Purelink Genomic DNA mini kit. DNA was isolated from veal calf faecal samples that were not spiked. The Ligation sequencing kit, the PCR-barcoding kit, the Rapid sequencing kit, and the Field sequencing kit were tested with the same input DNA samples and scores for number of reads per 2-hour sequence runs, mean quality score and read length were compared, as well as their potential usage in field conditions. The Ligation and PCR Barcoding kits resulted in high numbers of reads, well above 500,000 with a high average quality (>10) but a relatively low read length below 1000 bp on average. Furthermore, the kits were scored low for their usability in field conditions due to their dependence on lab equipment. The Field sequencing kit had an average number of ~10,000 reads and a lower average quality of approximately 7. However, this kit produced the longest reads and is most usable under field conditions. The Rapid sequencing kit was considered the most promising option, although the number of reads was relatively low and comparable to the field sequencing kit at ~10,000 reads per sample, the quality of the reads was on average 9-10. Furthermore, while the kit requires some more handling of the sample than the Field sequencing kit, it is more usable for on-site preparation than the other kits as it allows the user to measure multiplexed samples which is considered essential.

To assess the usability of on-site sequence results for the detection of pathogens and AMR, results from 6 faecal samples of (2 veal calves, 2 broiler chickens, 2 pigs) from the EU AMR-monitoring were measured via Nanopore sequencing at WBVR. DNA was extracted using the Purelink Genomic DNA mini-kit and sequence libraries were prepared using the Rapid sequencing kit. Culturing results showed MRSA to be present in 2 of the 6 samples while by sequencing *Staphylococcus aureus* could be detected in both, and one additional sample. However, the *mecA* gene could not be detected in any of these samples. *Campylobacter* was cultured from 5 of the 6 samples, while only in 4 of these, this bacterium was also detected using sequencing. *E. coli* were cultured non-selectively from all 6 samples, while selective culturing for ESBL *E. coli* was positive in 3 of these samples. In contrast, *E. coli* was detected in the sequencing results of all samples, but ESBL genes could not be detected in any of these. As a

preliminary conclusion, while the individual bacteria were detected well from all faecal samples, the expected AMR-genes could not be detected using the current set-up.

Samples of mastitis milk, spiked with mastitis pathogens *E. coli*, *S. aureus* or *S. uberis*, were analysed at WBVR. DNA from the samples was isolated with the PDQeX system for testing on-site conditions. DNA was prepared for sequencing using the Rapid sequencing kit. In all three spiked samples, the respective pathogens could be detected along with further parts of the microbiota that is expected in raw milk. Furthermore, part of the expected AMR genes that were present in the bacteria with which the bacteria were spiked could also be detected, along with AMR genes that were present in the milk microbiota. Further testing of non-spiked clinical mastitis milk is planned.

IZSAM spiked GMS into “boot-socks” which are elastic cotton tubes pulled over the boots and termed 'socks' worn underneath the shoes plastic to collect faecal droppings in poultry houses. Sampling with boot swabs is simple, safe, cost-effective, and a user-friendly environmental method for assessment of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* prevalence in poultry flocks. DNA was extracted by Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit from ZymoResearch from three samples: pure GMS, boot-socks spiked with GMS, and unspiked boot-socks as a blank. Good yield (> 1 µg DNA /50 µl) and DNA integrity (fragment length 25 Kb; DIN 8.3) were obtained for pure GMS. Higher length (50 Kb) was obtained for boot-socks, both spiked and unspiked, despite DNA recovery was lower. DNA from pure GMS and boot-socks were sequenced by MinION using ligation kit and Native barcoding exp 1-12 following the native barcoding genomic DNA protocol on a R9.4.1 flowcell in a single multiplex sequencing run for 72h. The critical point was the length of time to perform the high accuracy basecalling (more than 10 days). Details of the sequencing results will be discussed in WP2-T1. The total throughput obtained after 72h sequencing was 18.7 Gb, after filtering 17.1 Gb, most of this was obtained for the pure GMS (11 Gb), while only 3.3 Gb by the spiked boot-sock and 2.8 Gb the blank boot-sock. Discrepancies on the number of reads and the N50 reflects these unbalanced results from the different barcodes according to the input DNA. Pure GMS and spiked boot-socks were analysed through KMA using the proposed parameters. Apart from the species *Veillonella rogosae*, *Prevotella corporis*, *Methanobrevibacter smithii*, *Candida albicans* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* which were not present in the old database, all the other GMS species were identified in both samples.

JRP12-WP1-T4- Perform Hi-C metagenomics

This task was undertaken in close collaboration by BfR and Sciensano

Hi-C metagenomic sequencing is relatively new technology that proximity ligation of DNA molecules to determine the genetic context of AMR genes and its linkage to the bacterial host chromosome. This approach fuses DNA in close structural proximity during the DNA isolation and library preparation, prior to short-read sequencing. This method aims to reveal information about the genetic context of AMR genes and their genomic location, i.e., extrachromosomal elements such as plasmids or linked to bacterial host chromosomes. Feasibility of this method was investigated using spiked samples and samples from the EFFORT project.

Figure 1: Overview of the Hi-C workflow (Lieberman-Aiden et al., 2009): Cross-linked DNA is fragmented with restriction enzymes. The resulting sticky-ends are repaired to blunt-ends and

junctions are marked with biotin. After ligation the DNA-fragments containing incorporated biotin are isolated by pulldown with streptavidin and DNA is prepared for high-throughput sequencing. The prepared Hi-C library is sequenced using a paired-end sequencing technology.

At the BfR an artificial community (MC, mock community) consisting of four different species with known ARG profile, as well as known genome and plasmid sequences was constructed from single isolates. A shotgun library and Hi-C libraries in duplicates with two different versions of the commercially available Proximo Hi-C (Microbe) Kit (Phase Genomics Inc, USA) were prepared and paired-end sequenced using the NexSeq 500 system (Illumina, USA). The resulting data were analysed with two different pipelines – the commercially available ProxiMeta pipeline and our own developed pipeline called Hiccap. The latter relies on a mapping-based approach and uses only the Hi-C dataset together with a species and AMR database. In summary, with both pipelines it was possible to link most of the AMR genes specifically to the species of the artificial community. The sensitivity and specificity of the Hiccap analysis can be adjusted by using different threshold parameters such as the selection of reference genomes in the species databases and the AMR gene coverage threshold. The deliverable provides detailed results on the feasibility of the Hi-C metagenomics.

As artificial communities are far from real samples concerning complexity, pathogen and AMR gene concentrations and contain high amounts of matrix signals, samples from the EFFORT project were used to test the methodology. These samples are derived from an in-vivo experiment where the transmission of an AMR plasmid from a *Salmonella* enterica serovar Corvallis strain was investigated in the gut of chicken livestock. DNA from the collected faeces samples from two different days of the experiment on which a transfer could be detected microbiologically were extracted and Hi-C and shotgun libraries were generated and sequenced using Illumina technology. Hi-C metagenomics was able to assign of ARGs to species with high a specificity, and sensitivity (>90%). We observed slightly better results using an in-house developed mapping-based pipeline (Hiccap) compared to the commercial assembly-based pipeline. However, the success of the method was dependent on the database and better results were obtained with close mapping references.

Another artificial community constructed by BFR (MC1), containing six different species with known reference genomes was used by Sciensano to construct a Hi-C library. This library was then sequenced on Illumina MiSeq, yielding a satisfactory amount of sequencing data after optimization of Miseq flowcell loading. The resulting Hi-C reads were analysed with the Phase Genomics Inc. ProxiMeta pipeline, and with the HiCEXplorer set of tools (Wolff *et. Al.* 2018, <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/46/W1/W11/5036837?login=false>). The results showed that it was feasible to link the plasmids in the mock community to their host strains, when using the reference sequences to map the Hi-C reads. Future work will involve verifying if ONT based assemblies can be used as shotgun libraries.

These results show that there might be a possibility for such scientific questions to omit the shotgun dataset in the future which represents a large cost factor. A limiting factor has been the analysis of sequencing data, with only a handful of pipelines available. Analysis can be performed on the ProxiMeta platform of Phase Genomics Inc. however due to large size of the data files and ftp server access restrictions an alternative open-source pipeline needed to be identified. For this purpose, recently published bioinformatics pipelines were identified: for example, the HAM-ART pipeline (<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1009776>) and the HiCBin pipeline (<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-022-02626-w>). As the development of the in-house Hiccap pipeline is ongoing, comparisons with these open-source pipelines is still under development. Nevertheless, these pipelines require a paired-end deep-sequenced shotgun library, thus considerably increasing the cost factor. On the other hand, the Hiccap pipeline aims to only rely on a paired-end deep sequenced Hi-C library, hence reducing the practical expenses for sequencing. Although, the analyses of Hi-C data are not yet standardized or established routine, by utilizing the in-house Hiccap pipeline it was shown that Hi-C metagenomic sequencing has the ability to identify the genomic identity of reads as well as assigning ARGs to species. With the further development of this Hiccap pipeline, there might even be

the future possibility of identifying reads' genomic identities and assigning ARGs to species without the need for a paired-end deep-sequenced shotgun library.

Although the analysis of Hi-C data is not yet standardized and far away from being routine, the advantage of Hi-C metagenomic sequencing of being able to link plasmids to their hosts in metagenomics samples might be an interesting research tool to be used, e.g., to further address the GMM characterisation issue.

WP2 - Bioinformatics tools to analyse the sequencing data and defining the characteristics within the sample.

WP2 was led by DTU and SSI, with significant contributions from other members of the consortium.

To enable sharing and storage of sequencing data between the consortium, which could remain private before being published, APHA and SCIENSANO researched the available options, as this facility was not provided by OHEJP. We anticipated that for each task comparison we would generate up to 120GB of MinION data and 192GB of Illumina data between the consortium. Three options were considered for sharing and storage of data (Google Cloud, Google Drive and ownCloud), each with advantages and disadvantages, the consortium decided to use ownCloud (<https://farmedejp12.owncloud.online/>). Data storage must be considered when engaging in metagenome studies due to the volume and size of sequencing data and analysis but also the databases used for metagenome analysis.

JRP12-WP2-T1- Development/adaptation of a pipeline that can predict species within sample/matrix

Due to the vast quantity of data generated by metagenome sequencing, it is essential to have a resource efficient analysis pipeline, whether performed within in laboratory or on-site. At the project proposal stage, the tools were developed to interrogate metagenome data use short-read sequencing data. When the project started, DTU had just launched the KMA (k-mer alignment) pipeline, which uses a novel mapping method to map raw reads as well as fasta files against a database (Clausen et. al. 2018, <https://bmcbioinformatics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12859-018-2336-6>). The KMA command line based pipeline can be implemented and used for bacterial community and AMR assignments from long-read as well as short-read sequences, and was considered for the standard workflow for FARMED data analysis, and is freely available at <https://bitbucket.org/genomicpidemiology/kma>.

To ensure consistency of initial results, DTU performed preliminary KMA analysis using their manually curated Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification) and the entire DMC dataset of raw short (Illumina) and long (Nanopore) read sequencing data generated by the consortium in WP1.1. The community analysis showed that the species richness of taxa varied between the FARMED consortium, while the diversity of identified bacterial taxa appeared to be consistent between samples. Using the SILVA database for KMA analysis, microbial community analyses showed that bacterial communities sequenced by the same institute were more similar, even if they were from different DMC faecal samples, compared to the same sample sequenced at another institute. This was observed using both sequencing platform outputs, Illumina and Oxford Nanopore, suggesting the differences were largely influenced by the different DNA extraction and library preparation practices used at each institute.

Institute_1	Sample type	DNA Method	<i>A. baumannii</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>V. cholerae</i>
In-1	FB	E	-	-	++	-	-	-
In-3	FB	E	-	+++	+++	-	-	+++
In-4	FB	M	-	++	++	-	-	-
In-5	FB	E	-	+++	-	-	++	++
In-6	FB	E	-	++	-	-	-	-
In-1	FF	E	-	-	+++	-	-	-
In-3	FF	E	-	+++	+++	+++	-	+++
In-4	FF	M	++	+++	+++	++	++	++
In-5	FF	E	++	+++	++	++	++	++
In-6	FF	E	++	+++	++	++	-	+
In-1	FM	E	-	-	-	-	-	-
In-3	FM	E	-	+++	+++	-	-	+++
In-4	FM	M	-	+++	++	++	-	+++
In-5	FM	E	-	+++	-	++	++	+++
In-6	FM	E	-	+++	-	-	++	+++
In-5	WB	E	+	+++	-	-	+	+
In-6	WB	E	-	++	-	-	+	+
In-5	WF	E	++	+++	++	+	+++	++
In-6	WF	E	++	+++	++	++	+++	++
In-5	WM	E	-	+++	-	+	++	+++
In-6	WM	E	-	+++	-	++	++	+++

Using the full genomes database, the spiked bacteria were detected from the Nanopore sequencing at a range of different number of reads between the different institutes. Bacteria spiked at 10^{-5} were identified in most institutes for the fixed (FF) concentration samples. However, the number of identified spikes species was less in the mixed concentration samples, where only *E. coli* spiked at 10^{-3} was identified in 2/5 institutes. In the case of the blank samples (FB/WB) we would expect to identify some of the spiked bacteria such as *E. coli* in the samples as these are part of the normal microbiome.

Table 2 – Number of ONT reads for DMC bacterial spiked species

FB = faecal matrix, not spiked (blank); FF = faecal matrix spiked with fixed concentration DMC; FM = faecal matrix spiked with mixed concentration DMC; WB = water matrix, not spiked (blank); WF = water matrix spiked with fixed concentration DMC; WM = water matrix spiked with mixed concentration DMC; E = enzymatic extraction method; M = bead-beating extraction method

No of reads					
0	-	1-10	+	11-100	++
				>100	+++

Sciensano analysed the sequencing data generated from the different experiments with the UNSPIKED, PURE and SPIKED sample (see Task WP1-T3), using KMA and the Custom-2 parameters (see 12M-Report-Y4). One issue first addressed raised was the choice of reference database. Several databases were tested for analysis metagenomics data:

- gmstd_db: a database containing only the genomes of the different bacterial strains present in the GMS and provided by ZymoResearch
- gmstdFP_db: the same database as gmstd_db but containing in addition 60 genomes belonging to closely related species that could potentially be detected as false positives.
- DTU_db: the database previously used for KMA analyses of the DMC samples. This database contains only complete reference genomes. All GMS species are represented in this database except *Veillonella rogosae*, *Prevotella corporis* and *Methanobrevibacter smithii*
- newDTU_db: a new extended database provided by DTU and containing a mix of complete genomes and contig/scaffold sequences. All GMS species are represented in this database except *Veillonella rogosae*.
- FARMED_db: the DTU_db to which was appended complete genomes belonging to *Methanobrevibacter smithii*, and contigs/scaffolds lists belonging to *Veillonella rogosae* and *Prevotella corporis*.

Comparison of the databases gmstd_db, DTU_db and newDTU_db was performed with the PURE sample. The results showed that the composition of the database (i.e. complete genomes vs. contigs/scaffold) has an impact on the KMA results and their interpretation. When performing the analysis using the gmstd_db and DTU_db, composed only of full genomes, all the reads belonging to a species usually mapped to a best hit present in the database, resulting in high mapping scores (depth, template identity and template coverage) making the result interpretation straightforward for non-expert users. On the contrary, the same analysis with newDTU_db, composed of a mix of complete genomes and contigs/scaffolds, resulted in the spread of the reads which mapped to different contigs with various mapping scores, making the interpretation more complex. Additionally, it was observed that short contigs are more prone to obtain high mapping scores because of their length, but this can

be misleading and inaccurate for taxonomic identification, as only a part of the genome is attributed to a species. Moreover, more false positives were reported when using the newDTU_db in comparison with the DTU_db. Considering all of this, a database containing mainly complete genomes, and contigs/scaffold only if complete genomes are not available, is recommended. Consequently, for the analysis of the UNSPIKED, PURE and SPIEKD samples, a new database called FARMED_db was created. This FARMED_db is actually composed of the DTU_db to which was appended complete genomes belonging to *Methanobrevibacter smithii*, and contigs/scaffolds lists belonging to *Veillonella rogosae* and *Prevotella corporis* (because no complete genome was available on NCBI for these 2 species).

From the analysis of the PURE sample using the gmstd_db, gmstdFP_db and FARMED_db, the depth, template identity and template coverage values generated by KMA for each true positive and false positive species were compared to define detection threshold for species identifications. As with the Custom-2 parameters a lot of data is retrieved by KMA (see report 9M-Y5), the determination of detection criteria with confidence level was needed for proper interpretation. Additionally, to consider the presence of contigs in the database, the template length was included in the decision criteria to better reward the long reference templates (i.e., complete genomes). In total, 6 different levels of detection were proposed by Sciensano to help for data analysis. Depending on the level of detection, the taxonomic identification can be trusted, or requires a complementary analysis to confirm the result.

ISS: The tools needed for Nanopore data analysis were made available through ARIES Galaxy-based web-platform (<https://w3.iss.it/site/aries/>), curated at ISS, counting about 500 users worldwide. The subscription for using ARIES is free, granting easy access to bioinformatics pipelines to users without large experience in bioinformatics analysis. In detail, the Nanoplot and Porechop tools wrappers for Galaxy systems were already available on Galaxy tool-shed and were imported on ARIES by ISS team and made available in the list of tools. KMA tool wrapper was also available in the Galaxy tool-shed, but corrections were needed in the wrapper before for importing the tool in ARIES. These were performed by ISS team and the tool made available in the list of tools.

JRP12-WP2-T2- Development/adaptation of a Resfinder-'like' pipeline for identification of AMR for long-read sequences

APHA KMA pipeline was used for the identification of AMR genes from short- and long-read sequence data. However, because the AMR genes could not be easily linked to the species they originate from, a custom workflow has been devised. This workflow involves assembling MinION generated data using Flye (with the -meta parameter) into contigs which are then classified using Kaiju (taxonomy) and Abricate (AMR). The long contigs were able to find links between species and AMR, which could be extended to establish links with plasmids. This approach offers the advantage to provide more complete genomes/plasmid where long read sequencing alone might struggle.

DTU: Like WP2-T1, KMA and ResFinder (<https://cge.food.dtu.dk/services/ResFinder/>) are ready-to-use to identify AMR genes from the long-read sequencing data. Unlike bacterial species identification using various reference databases, ResFinder AMR database provides a comprehensive collection of AMR genes that are currently sufficient. Both KMA and ResFinder are freely available online to be used on and offline.

SCIENSANO analysed the sequencing data generated from the different experiments with the UNSPIKED, PURE and SPIEKED sample (see Task WP1-T3), using KMA and the Custom-2 parameters (see 12M-Report-Y4). Five out of the seven AMR genes included in GMS could be correctly detected in the PURE and SPIEKED samples. One additional AMR gene was detected in the PURE sample sequenced in Nanopore singleplex. The missing AMR genes belong to low abundant species which were also not detected during KMA taxonomic identification. Although the result interpretation of KMA output for AMR genes detection is more straightforward than for taxonomic identification, because of the shorter length of the reference templates (i.e., AMR genes), 2 decision criteria were elaborated to help non-expert users.

Furthermore, for the detected AMR genes, they could be linked to their host species, using a 2 step KMA analysis. In brief, this 2-step analysis consisted into extracting from the KMA output files, the reads identified as belonging to a given species during a first KMA analysis for taxonomic identification (with FARMED_db) and performing a second KMA analysis with these reads as input but this time with the ResFinder database. As such, if AMR genes are found on reads previously identified at the taxonomic level, the link between the two can be established. Also, for the genetically modified microorganisms in the food enzymes samples, the AMR genes could be linked to their host chromosome or plasmid.

JRP12-WP2-T3- Benchmarking of tools with spiked samples in WP2

APHA compared two other metagenomics tools/workflows to KMA. The Epi2Me Labs (<https://labs.epi2me.io/wfindex/>), from ONT offers an analysis workflow for long-read metagenome samples. The Epi2Me wf-metagenomics workflow is a cloud-based Nextflow workflow which offers Kraken2 and Minimap2 approaches to carry out taxonomic classification of metagenome samples. Pure GMS sample sequence data was processed using the wf-metagenomics workflow using a Kraken database of capped size (PlusPF-8 – <https://benlangmead.github.io/aws-indexes/k2>). In total, 10/15 GMS species were identified by the wf-metagenomics workflow. Of the missing 5 species:

- two GMS species (*Veillonella rogosae* and *Prevotella corporis*) were not in the PlusPF-8 database, however other species from the same genera were present and identified
- three GMS species were some of the lowest abundant species - *Akkermansia muciniphila* (1.5%), *Enterococcus faecalis* (0.001%) and *Clostridium perfringens* (0.0001%).

This tool has recently been updated and is currently planned to be used to analyse the REHAB metagenomic samples. The advantages of Epi2Me workflows are that is easy to use for non-bioinformaticians as the workflows are available which include all the steps needed for both taxonomy and the output is provided in html format and the entire set up is via a GUI, which is very useful for inexperienced users and makes analysis implementation easy and quick which do not require significant computation resources and is time efficient.

Kaiju is a tool used for taxonomic classification of metagenomic data, which uses a protein rather than sequence database, achieving a higher sensitivity compared with methods based on nucleotide comparison (<https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms11257>). To improve classification of MiniION data, long-read data was assembled prior to classification using Kaiju (see WP2-T2 for details), which increased the N50 from ~1.4kb to 7.5kb. Compared to the bacterial classification of the raw data, assembling the long read data decreased the percentage of unclassified reads from ~69% (64-74%) to ~31% (11-51%). Host (pig and/or cattle) or plant DNA were not removed from the dataset, which likely was included in a portion of these unclassified reads, which are not present in the RefSeq database (to be confirmed). As well as bacterial reads, a small percentage (0.2 – 2.8%) of reads were assigned to viruses.

Sample bacterial community compositions were compared at the phyla level, which showed the number of phyla were higher in Kaiju and Epi2me outputs, which reflects the database used. These approaches produced similar microbial profiles at the phyla level, although there were differences in the less abundant phyla. As expected, due to KMA using a much smaller database than Kaiju or Epi2Me, KMA only identifies the most dominant microbial community members. Therefore, depending on the purpose of metagenomic analysis, a combination of raw and assembled data might need to be considered to ensure the least amount of data is lost and a true representation of the sample to be obtained.

DTU compared their output from the faecal and sewage water samples with and without the GMS mock community (from WP2 T1) by mapping the sequences to bacterial databases using two different aligners/mappers (KMA and KRAKEN). The assigned bacterial species were similar and comparable with no major difference between KMA and KRAKEN, where the same abundant bacteria dominated both outputs (from KMA and KRAKEN). The difference was mainly the computational time: mapping

and alignment jobs were, however, completed more quickly when using KMA. In addition, KRAKEN output isn't optimal for direct interpretation of the data as it requires more data handling, after the analyses, compared to KMA. Not to mention that KRAKEN is restricted to a single bacterial reference database to be used without options to include other customised databases. Neither the ability for KRAKEN to identify AMR genes.

JRP12-WP2-T4- Test protocols on-site

This task was amalgamated with JRP12-WP3-T4 as both were aimed to test the feasibility of performing long-read metagenome sequencing on-site, which would include all steps from DNA extraction, library preparation, long-read sequencing, and subsequent data analysis.

WP3 - Implementation of on-site protocols for long-read metagenomic DNA sequencing

WP3 was led by DTU and SSI, with contributions from all members of the consortium.

JRP12-WP3-T1- Literature search & Harmonisation of on-site DNA isolation

WVBR and APHA designed and shared a questionnaire within the consortium to survey the DNA extraction, DNA short- (isolates and metagenomes) and long-read sequencing methods, as well as which matrices/samples were used by each institute. The bioinformatics analysis methods were also surveyed. All institutes contributed to this methods survey that was collated by WBVR.

A report on the available literature for on-site DNA extraction and long-read metagenome sequencing produced and uploaded Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557>. In summary, an overview of different DNA isolation techniques from literature was included. From literature it became obvious that 'on-site' is not a well-defined concept and a framework was given to define different levels of available facilities for on-site measurements. Parameters concerning the quality, quantity, and purity of the extracted DNA for different methods were discussed, as well as the specific requirements for Nanopore sequencing. Based on the literature search and experience from the various partners in FARMED, several further methods were described for further investigation during the lifetime of FARMED.

JRP12-WP3-T2- Investigation of on-site equipment for DNA extraction and sequencing (original title: Investigate the use of Voltrax)

The Voltrax (from ONT) was expected to be able to perform the metagenome DNA extraction as well as the library preparation, which could directly be loaded onto the MinION for sequencing. However, currently the Voltrax is only able to prepare the DNA sequencing library, which is still valuable for on-site metagenome sequencing. However, until recently (early 2022) there were problems with delivery of Voltrax versions and kits, which caused a delay to FARMED. WBVR and Sciensano tested and compared the Voltrax to other sequencing library preparation methods in terms of suitability for on-site use and yield per library per time unit.

DTU has only tested BentoLab (<https://bento.bio/devices/>) device for DNA extractions using Quick-DNA HMW MagBead Kit (D6060, Zymo Research) on-site. DTU also assessed both library preparation protocols for ONT long-read sequencing (Rapid Sequencing Kit SQK-RAD004 and Ligation kit LSK-109) in the field, and both kits resulted in similar library outputs and qualities to our in-lab preparations.

SCIENSANO tested the original Voltrax device (V1) on lambda control DNA, and on a DNA extract from a pure microbial mock community. The lambda library produced by Voltrax resulted in a good sequencing run on an ONT flongle flowcell. However, subsequent libraries resulted in very low sequencing yields. After replacing the Voltrax V1 with the Voltrax V2b, the new version of the device was able to produce a library from a chicken fecal sample spiked with the zymo Gut Microbiome Standard, resulting in a satisfactory sequencing run (N50 ~8kb (on-site DNA extraction protocol, Voltrax) compared to ~4kb on-site DNA extraction protocol, rapid sequencing kit and 14kb lab based

DNA extraction combined with rapid sequencing kit) compared to other methods (lab-based DNA extraction, ligation, and rapid library preparation).

WBVR has used several versions, VolTrax, VolTrax V2 and VolTrax V2b. For all versions, the cartridges in which the reactions are performed remain faulty for unknown reasons. This reduces usability in the field as the unreliability would mean that several spare cartridges would need to be taken into the field. Nonetheless, several runs were performed successfully, and the quality is comparable to the Rapid sequencing kit, which uses similar chemistry. As the time needed for the preparation of the sequencing libraries is comparable between these methods, currently the added value of the VolTrax system is limited.

JRP12-WP3-T3- Assess DNA isolation methods for suitability, test on matrices (faeces, blood, dust, (environmental), milk)

APHA trialled the PDQeX system, using the manufacturer's protocol, to extract DNA from pig, cattle faecal and poultry caecal samples spiked with either pure isolates *E. coli* and MRSA or the GMS, followed by MinION sequencing (rapid library preparation) or Illumina sequencing. In partnership with the manufacturer, a new prototype of the extraction tubes, changing sample input amounts and extraction conditions, appear to have increased DNA yield for pig and cattle samples, although this still not optimal (~10 ng/μl). promising DNA yield were achieved from poultry samples (~70ng/μl). While it appears long DNA fragments can be obtained (>12kb on 1% agarose gel) the recovered DNA yields from metagenomic samples using the PDQeX system do not meet the criteria for long-read sequencing, and appeared to destroy the flow cells due to protein contamination. Several attempts were made to remove this contamination and improve the DNA quality, using a combination of magnetic beads, heating, and alcohol washes with variable success. MinION sequencing produced a greater percentage of the genome coverage and mean species identity for selected pathogens found within faecal sample. Interestingly however, the frequency of species identified was greater in Illumina compared to MinION nanopore. Also, MinION offered the opportunity to link AMR genes to bacterial species as well as plasmids previously isolated from the same faecal samples. Work is underway to standardise this method to achieve consistent sequencing outputs.

SCIENSANO developed a protocol for on-site DNA extraction based on the Claremont Bio DNAexpress kit (Claremont Biosolutions), tested on chicken faeces matrices. This kit uses portable bead-beating tubes which includes an electric motor. After bead beating, a series of operations involving syringes, a silica-based DNA-binding column, and some buffers, purified DNA is obtained. However, further analyses showed that the obtained DNA extracts were of insufficient quality to construct nanopore sequencing libraries. This was addressed by purifying the extracts, yielding improved, although still unsatisfactory results. Finally, after replacing the Silica column purification process with a magnetic bead-based process (Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit, Zymo Research) using a BentoLab 'portable' lab that would allow extraction on-site, the obtained DNA extracts were of sufficient quality, yielding sequencing throughput comparable to that of laboratory-based DNA extraction methods.

WBVR has tested the USEB method by Wageningen University and the Ionic liquid method described in literature(<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-50246-5>). Both methods have been used successfully at WBVR to perform pathogen detection via amplification methods (LAMP and PCR). Both methods could only produce up to ~10 ng of DNA which was not of sufficient quality for library preparation. While Ampure DNA capture could be used to improve quality and concentration of the samples, the added steps were decided to be inconvenient for on-site isolation, losing the added value over commercially available kits.

IZSAM: Based on the previous experience on the use of ligation kit + high accuracy basecalling IZSAM proposed a new *fast* protocol to work on-site. It was the first attempt such protocol has been tested in lab. In detail, stool samples collected from poultry have been artificially contaminated with *Campylobacter* cultures at different concentration: 2×10^6 CFU/200 mg, 2×10^4 CFU/200 mg, 2×10^2 CFU/200 mg and 20 CFU/200 mg. The estimated copy number per sequencing reaction were 2×10^4 ,

2×10^2 , 2 and 0.2, respectively. Some critical points emerged from this experiment caused by the poor repeatability of the read number produced per run as well as the *Campylobacter* read count not strictly correspondent to the initial load, although the background microbiota were comparable. Finally, the mean read length observed in the different sequencing runs was generally low (less than 1Kb) with just few long reads higher than 10Kb. On the other hand, the whole protocol fits the purpose of use in the field, it is fast and only minimal instruments are required. The fast basecalling coupled with the use of flongle flowcells allows a real-time monitoring of the reaction, but still requires improvement.

JRP12-WP3-T4- Test protocol on-site

DTU tested the on-site sequencing and data analyses pipeline in the field (as preliminary trials) in February and March 2022. Samples from soil and faeces, with an addition of single bacterial isolate from a hospital, were collected in fields. DNA extractions were done using Quick-DNA HMW MagBead Kit (D6060, Zymo Research) on BentoLab device for DNA extraction and library preparation (<https://bento.bio/devices/>) with external portable power supply. Libraries were prepared using two protocols: Rapid Sequencing Kit SQK-RAD004 on BentoLab. All raw outputs (Fast5) were basecalled using an in-house built GPU-based laptop with Guppy-basecaller pipeline and high accuracy basecalling option. All resulting Fastq files were fed into KMA (after previous KMA performance assessment in WP2-T1, T2 and T3 in previous reports) for bacterial taxa and AMR identifications. From the faecal sample, approximately 65000 reads were assigned to 275 bacterial species and 12 AMR genes. As a control, *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterium was added to the faecal sample (100 μ l of 10^8 cells/mL) and *S. aureus* species was one of the abundant bacterial taxa in the microbiome analyses from the tested faeces.

SCIENSANO could test the 'on-site' sequencing protocol physically in the lab but using only equipment that would be feasible to use on-site (semi on-site sequencing). Using the DNA prepared from chicken faeces with the 'on-site' DNA extraction protocol, combined with the Voltrax library preparation and ONT sequencing, sufficient sequencing data could be obtained for further analyses. The data analysis was performed in the laboratory using the KMA tool (which would be feasible on-site, cfr DTU work). The results of these analyses demonstrated that the 'on-site' DNA extraction performed comparable to laboratory-based sequencing in terms of sequencing throughput. Furthermore, the on-site method showed less bias against gram-positive bacteria, whereas read N50 was lower. However, the lower read lengths did not inhibit resistance gene profiling, as the results were close to those of laboratory-based methods.

WBVR has had most success with the analysis of mastitis pathogens from milk of dairy cattle, an on-site demonstration will be carried out at 'Aeres hogeschool', a farming school with dairy cattle in the Netherlands. Milk samples of dairy cows suspected of mastitis have been collected in October 2022, and stored at -20 °C. In December, these samples will be sent to the diagnostic service of the Animal Health service Deventer but will also be tested by on-site methods from WBVR. It is planned to isolate DNA for LAMP analysis using the Ionic liquid method and DNA for Nanopore sequencing using PDQeX isolation. The aim is to have a diagnosis within 8 hours (before the next milking slot), where LAMP provides only a potential bacterial pathogen at very low cost, while Nanopore sequencing also provides an overview of resident AMR genes. The current gold standard in mastitis diagnostics through bacterial culturing of milk samples takes several days.

IZSAM selected poultry farms for the on-site experiment. The aim was to combine the standard sample collection protocol (bootsocks), normally coupled with culture methods for *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*, with a metagenomic approach for the detection of pathogens, faeces/environment microbiota and AMR genes. Controls were prepared in a pre-starting session collecting poultry meconium (chickens less than ten days) by using bootsocks. Absence of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* was proven by culture methods (ISO 10272/2017 and ISO 6579/2017), thus positive control was made spiking 108 cells of both pathogens into the "negative" bootsocks diluted with nuclease free water in a proportion of 1:10 and homogenised for DNA extraction using the E.Z.N.A.® Stool DNA Kit (Omega

Bio-tek). The same protocol was used on-site for the bootsocks collected in 6 different farms after 45 days housing. DNA concentration ranged from 3 to 10.6 ng/μl (50 μl), DNA Integrity (DIN) >6 (6 – 6.7) and average size of 26 Kb (24.7 – 27.8 Kb). Genomic libraries were prepared using Rapid Barcoding kit (SQK-RBK110.96) but only single sample per sequencing run were used on Flongle flow cells. Samples were sequenced for 4 hours, using basecalling, and monitored in real time by using Epi2me software and then analysed by KMA in the lab. The output (total bp produced) was generally lower than the expected cause the low input DNA, the rapid protocol (less efficient than others i.e. ligation kit), and the short time set for sequencing. Despite this, sequencing by MinION allowed to detect the presence of *Campylobacter* in all 6 bootsocks, data confirmed by culture, PCR and KMA analysis. Conversely, *Salmonella* was recognised by ‘whats in my pot’ workflow available through Epi2Me but presence of the pathogen was not confirmed by PCR or culture, and only a small number of reads (1 or 2) were retrieved by KMA analysis in 3/6 bootsocks tested.

In summary, ‘on-site’ long read metagenomics is feasible however there are several considerations which must be considered before the method is employed more widely

- DNA extraction method employed must be suitable for the sample matrix and achieve sufficient concentration of DNA .
- For library preparation, either VolTRaX or the rapid barcoding kit is recommended.
- Ideally only sequence one sample per flow cell to ensure depth of sequence data.
- The Mk1c or GPU laptop for the sequencing and basecalling.
- The time required to achieve depth of sequence data (~24-72 hours).

WP4 - Project management, coordination, and training workshop.

WP4 was led by DTU and SSI, with contributions from all members of the consortium.

JRP12-WP4-T1- Annual physical project meetings

Although physical meetings were planned from the outset of FARMED, our first was meant to be in March 2020, we were only able to physically meet at the end of the project in September 2022, at DTU campus. However, to overcome the travel restrictions across Europe caused by the COVID pandemic, we moved to online meeting through the course of the project and ensured the maximum number of participants could attend.

The first physical day meeting was arranged for 19th March but had to be postponed due to the start of COVID-19 and travel restrictions across Europe. Online meetings were held in May 2020 where initial discussions and plans were decided for the first FARMED task (WP1.1). The consortium had provisionally planned to meet in October 2020; however, travel bans/restrictions were still in place due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Finally, the face-to-face daylong meeting was held online on the 29th of October 2020, via go-to-meeting (hosted by SCIENSANO), which discussed in detail the activities carried out within the work packages.

In October 2020, Giusy Sannino (MicroGEM) Paul Butler (FORENTEQ LIMITED) presented a portable automated extraction system PDQeX, showing its capability to extract high quality DNA from various sample matrices, which is applicable to the FARMED project; participants were enthusiastic about its potential and resulted in two institutes taking up this machine.

The first face to face FARMED meeting eventually took place in September 2022 at DTU campus in Denmark, which also included some member attending virtually. The two-day meeting allowed the group to share and discuss their FARMED project results as well as offered the opportunity for a live demonstration of on-site DNA extraction tools.

JRP12-WP4-T2- Teleconferences will be organised every 3 months, between partners

The FARMED consortium held several teleconferences to discuss various aspects of project progress as well as forums to share experiences and results at various stages of the project. Example of virtual meeting held during FARMED project

JRP12-WP4-T3- Training dissemination of developed protocols

DTU held an online hands-on training session (6th November 2020) on the use of the KMA pipeline to analyse the data generated from the DMC samples (task WP1.1). The session provided an introduction and hands-on experience in installation requirements/steps, parameter set-up and troubleshooting. This training session allowed all collaborators to analyse their data using KMA producing .mapstat and .res files, which were shared with DTU to perform the initial comparisons in WP1-T1.

JRP12-WP4-T4- Annual reports

All FARMED 9M and 12M reports were submitted in full and on time.

2.1.4 Project self-assessment

Despite initial delays due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which severely impacted progress, the FARMED project has successfully tested and shown that long-read metagenomics using the Oxford Nanopore technology MinION system for pathogen and AMR detection is feasible. However, we quickly identified several caveats that would currently limit the usability of this technology for on-site surveillance or monitoring such as those performed across the EU like the yearly AMR monitoring:

- (1) The DNA extraction step which is integral to achieving DNA of suitable quality, quantity, and purity for long-read sequencing, can vary between sample matrices, extraction methods as well as users.
- (2) cost required to ensure an appropriate depth of sequencing is achieved to enable identification of pathogens of interest. We found that only 1 sample per sequencing run, prepared using the ligation method (which is time consuming), using high accuracy base calling gave the best overall characterisation of the sample.
- (3) bioinformatics methods and parameters need further standardisation, likely based on sample matrices, taking into consideration of the purpose of the long-read metagenomics. The reference databases used to analyse long-read metagenome sequence data have a crucial influence, as well as the parameters used to identify and quantitate the bacterial genera within metagenomic samples.

It must be noted that the technology is relatively new, and we fully expect future improvements to come as new versions of the sequencing kits and flowcells were released during FARMED, and as was evident seeing ONT move fast to accelerate development of processes for rapid COVID testing. Also, as scientist we are somewhat dependent on commercial technological developments. It quickly became apparent at the start of FARMED that included evaluating VolTRaX (WP3), which was promoted for DNA extraction and library preparation, this instrument was fully available. However, VolTRaX V2, which was released towards the end of the FARMED project, was only able to perform the library preparation and therefore the project was reliant on finding suitable alternatives for on-site DNA extraction. FARMED identified a handful of methods/kits suitable DNA extractions, which showed variable success; however further optimisations would be necessary to enable more widespread use.

The output of FARMED enabled further development of long-read metagenomics within the participating institutes as well as lead to further new and old collaborations between scientists.

Overall, all work packages achieved their aims:

- WP1: The feasibility of long-read metagenomics for pathogen and AMR detection was demonstrated for simple and complex matrices, covering the spectrum of the One Health context. However, the abundance of the species has a large impact on the success of detection.
- WP2: KMA, combined with Resfinder, were selected as the preferred bioinformatics tools to analyse the sequencing data, and defining the characteristics within the sample. A suggested list of parameters, aiming to aid users in considering the confidence of presence of bacterial species within sample was developed. The applied database is a crucial factor in the analysis.
- WP3: Different approaches were taken by institutes to enable on-site long-read metagenomics, where limitations were identified as well as some success was shown.

The FARMED project has enabled nine laboratories to develop their expertise in long-read sequencing approaches and provided a valuable platform on which to further develop and improve long-read metagenomics, with the aim to make long-read metagenomics a standard method in microbiology.

2.1.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
12	D-JRP12-1.1	Report on an initial assessment of long-read sequencing for metagenome (community and AMR) analysis (defined community, spiked and real simple and complex matrices) and comparison to current short-read standard.	M53	M60	Delayed due to the optimisation of analysis methods. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429361	8. Application of available methods.
12	D-JRP12-1.2	Report on the feasibility of using Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.	M52	M60	Confidential until results are published. Delayed as one institute has been delayed in their analysis (due to delivery problems) for this report. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433351	8. Application of available methods.
12	D-JRP12-2.1	Optimised long-read sequence bioinformatics tool for the analysis of microbial communities made publicly available.	M58	M60	Deliverables D-JRP12-2.1 and D-JRP12-2.2, were combined due to their similar outputs.	2, 3, 4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
					https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258	
12	D-JRP12-2.2	Optimised long-read sequence bioinformatics tool for analysis of the resistome made publicly available.	M58	M60	Deliverables D-JRP12-2.1 and D-JRP12-2.2, were combined due to their similar outputs. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433258	2, 3, 4
12	D-JRP12-3.1	Review on current scientific literature and overview of commercially available methods for on-site DNA isolation.	M36	M40	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557	8. Summary of available methods, not publication.
12	D-JRP12-3.2	Protocol for use of Voltrax on-site for extraction and library preparation from clinical, veterinary and environmental samples, suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing.	M56	M60	Issues with the Voltrax offered by the Oxford Nanopore Technologies. Additional time is needed for methods to be optimised for on-site long-read metagenomics, by multiple institutes. D-JRP12-3.2, D-JRP12-3.3 and D-JRP12-3.4 were combined as all three deliverables are connected and would not be undertaken separately. These will	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
					appear as appendices for deliverable D-JRP12-WP3.5.	
12	D-JRP12-3.3	Protocol for on-site extraction of high-quality DNA from clinical, veterinary, and environmental samples, suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing.	M60	M60	D-JRP12-3.2, D-JRP12-3.3 and D-JRP12-3.4 were combined as all three deliverables are connected and would not be undertaken separately. These will appear as appendices for deliverable D-JRP12-WP3.5.	2
12	D-JRP12-3.4	Detailed method for on-site long-read sequencing of sample matrix.	M60	M60	D-JRP12-3.2, D-JRP12-3.3 and D-JRP12-3.4 were combined as all three deliverables are connected and would not be undertaken separately. These will appear as appendices for deliverable D-JRP12-WP3.5.	2
12	D-JRP12-WP3.5	Report on initial findings of on-site diagnostic tests and IT solutions for human clinical, veterinary and environmental samples for early warning of emerging resistant pathogens.	M60	M60	Deliverable D-JRP12-WP3.5. contains D-JRP12-3.2, D-JRP12-3.3 and D-JRP12-3.4 as appendices. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433281	2
12	D-JRP12-4.1	Annual communication to stakeholders and OH EJP	M48, M60	M60	Y4 annual report was submitted in January 2022.	8. Sharing and communication

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		coordinators			Y5 9 month report submitted in September 2022.	for application of methods.

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
12	M-JRP16-01	Review on current scientific literature and overview of commercially available methods for on-site DNA isolation presented to FARMED consortium.	M36	Yes		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557
12	M-JRP12-02	Assessment of long-read sequencing for resolving a 'defined' microbial community and their AMR genes, using current DNA extraction methods; and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard.	M52	Yes	M59	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).
12	M-JRP12-03	Assessment of long-read sequencing on spiked metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M53	Yes	M59	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).
12	M-JRP12-04	Protocols for on-site high quality DNA extraction using Voltrax and library preparation ready for testing on-site	M54	Yes	M59	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above). The milestone has changed from Voltrax for DNA extraction to other methods for DNA extraction
12	M-JRP12-05	Assessment of long-read sequencing for 'simple' metagenome samples, using	M50	Yes	M59	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
		current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.				
12	M-JRP12-06	Assessment of the feasibility of Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.	M51	Yes	M59	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).
12	M-JRP16-07	Protocols for extraction of high-quality DNA (using different methods than Voltrax) from clinical, veterinary and environmental samples (simple and complex), suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing distributed amongst FARMED consortium for testing.	M58	Yes	M59	No single protocol could be identified as this depends on the matrix.
12	M-JRP12-08	Assessment of long-read sequencing for 'complex' metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M52	Yes	M59	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).
12	M-JRP12-09	Development/adaptation of a pipeline that can predict species within sample/matrix	M51	Yes	M58	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments and therefore limited data to develop their analysis.

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
12	M-JRP12-10	Finalised protocol for on-site long-read sequencing of sample matrix distributed amongst FARMED consortium for testing.	M53	Yes	M59	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above). No single protocol could be identified as this depends on the matrix.
12	M-JRP12-11	Development/adaptation of a Resfinder-'like' pipeline for the identification of AMR from long-read sequences	M55	Yes	M57	This has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments and therefore limited data to develop their analysis.
12	M-JRP16-12	Hands-on laboratory and bioinformatics workshop organised at DTU and SSI	M59	Yes	M35	The was not deemed necessary as all institutes were able to undertake Long-read metagenomics using their prefer matrices. An online workshop hosted by DTU was undertaken in the first year of FARMED which enabled and trained participating institutes to perform the KMA analysis.
12	M-JRP12-13	Benchmarking of bioinformatics tools developed in WP2 with metagenomic sequences gained from T1.1, T1.2 and T1.3	M57	Yes	M59	
12	M-JRP16-14	Test the bioinformatics tools that were benchmarked and developed in WP2 on a laptop that is on-site (outside of laboratory conditions)	M60	Yes	M59	
12	M-JRP16-15	DNA extraction, library preparation and long-read sequencing tested on-site (outside of laboratory conditions)	M58	Yes	M59	
12	M-JRP16-16	Voltrax DNA extraction, Voltrax library preparation and long-read sequencing	M58	Yes	M59	

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
		tested on-site (outside of laboratory conditions)				
12	M-JRP16-17	Complete workflow of DNA extraction (with or without Voltrax), library preparation (with or without Voltrax), long-read sequencing and bioinformatics analysis tested on-site for early warning of emerging resistant pathogens.	M60	Yes	M60	

2.1.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>A shotgun metagenomics approach to detect and characterize unauthorized genetically modified microorganisms in microbial fermentation products</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/5347021#.YS-kSY4zaM8</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochms.2021.10002</p> <p>Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences</p>		Yes, partial	No	Yes, (0 euros)
<p>Metagenomic characterization of multiple genetically modified <i>Bacillus</i> contaminations in commercial microbial fermentation products</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3390/life12121971</p> <p>Life</p>		Yes	No	Yes
<p>Tentative title: Comparison of 6 DNA extraction methods for isolation of high yield of High Molecular Weight DNA suitable for metagenomics Nanopore sequencing</p>	Under preparation	Yes		
<p>Tentative title: Optimization and evaluation of a workflow for metagenomics analysis in complex matrix using Nanopore sequencing and KMA tool</p>	Under preparation	Yes		
<p>Tentative title: Development and optimisation of a potential on-site nanopore sequencing protocol</p>	Under preparation	Yes		

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Tentative title: metagenomic comparison of UK farms harbouring AMR bacteria	Under preparation	Yes		

Additional output

- Oral presentation Sigrid De Keersmaecker 'JRP12 : FARMED : Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests' presented at 'OneHealthEJP@Sciensano' theme day on November 27th 2020.
- Poster of project "FARMED: Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests" presented at the One Health EJP Meeting, held in virtually in Prague 27-29th May 2020.
- Oral presentation Sigrid De Keersmaecker 'JRP12 : FARMED : Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests' presented at 'OneHealthEJP@Sciensano' theme day on November 19th 2021.
- Poster of project "FARMED: Long-read metagenomic sequencing workflow for the identification of pathogens/AMR on-site" presented at the One Health EJP Meeting, hosted in Copenhagen and online between 9-11th June 2021.
- Oral presentation Buytaers FE & De Keersmaecker SCJ - Strain-level shotgun metagenomics for the detection and characterization of bacterial foodborne contaminants in the context of outbreak investigation and EU regulatory enforcement. at the One Health EJP Dissemination Workshop on Metagenomics, held 27th October 2021.
- Oral presentation Otani, S – Can metagenomics replace the current *E. coli* based monitoring of AMR in livestock, food samples and environment? at the One Health EJP Dissemination Workshop on Metagenomics, held 27th October 2021.
- Poster presentation: Gand Mathieu* (Sciensano), Buytaers Florence* (Sciensano), Bloemen Bram (Sciensano), Saltykova Assia (Sciensano), Denayer Sarah (Sciensano), Verhaegen Bavo (Sciensano), Mattheus Wesley (Sciensano), Piérard Denis (UZBrussels), Bogaerts Bert (Sciensano), Marchal Kathleen (UGhent), **the FARMED consortium (One Health European Joint Programme)**, Roosens Nancy (Sciensano), Vanneste Kevin (Sciensano), De Keersmaecker Sigrid C.J. (Sciensano) (* equal contribution). Shotgun metagenomics as a ONE Health tool for better protecting human health. ONE Conference 2022 (organized by EFSA). Brussels, Belgium. 21-24/06/2022.
- Poster presentation: Indre Navickaite, Thomas Wilkes, Manal AbuOun (APHA). FARMED: Long-read metagenomic sequencing. One Health EJP Annual scientific meeting April 2022.
- Poster presentation: Josephine Grützke, Jens-Andre Hammerl, Jennie Fischer, Lee Julia Bartsch, Burkhard Malorny and Carlus Deneke (BfR). Application of proximity ligation to link antibiotic resistance genes and species using metagenomics. 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases. Lisbon, Portugal. April 23-26 2022.
- Oral Presentation: Bosco R. Matamoros, Carlos Serna, Gabriel Moyano, Emilia Wedel, Natalia Montero, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. Metagenomic sequencing analysis of the effects of apramycin on the poultry gut microbiome. One Health EJP Annual scientific meeting April 2022.
- Poster presentation: Bosco R. Matamoros, Carlos Serna, Gabriel Moyano, Emilia Wedel, Mario Pulido-Vadillo, Natalia Montero, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. Metagenomic analysis reveals that apramycin use restructures the resistome and favours interbacterial spread of *aac(3)-IV* gene. 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases. Lisbon, Portugal. April 23-26 2022.
- Oral Presentation: Saria Otani. Antimicrobial Resistance and Bacterial Pathogen detections in Microbiomes. Ministry of Food and Agriculture in Denmark. June 2022

- Poster presentation: Quillan Dijkstra, Arie Kant, Teresita de Jesus Bello Gonzalez, Frank Harders, Kees Veldman, Michael Brouwer (WBVR) Implementation of Multi-Locus Sequence Typing based on Nanopore Single Molecule Real-Time sequencing. KNVM Spring meeting The Netherlands, April 2022.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Two presentations at the One Health EJP Dissemination Workshop on Metagenomics, held 27th October 2021.

- Buytaers FE & De Keersmaecker SCJ - Strain-level shotgun metagenomics for the detection and characterization of bacterial foodborne contaminants in the context of outbreak investigation and EU regulatory enforcement.
- Otani, S – Can metagenomics replace the current *E. coli*-based monitoring of AMR in livestock, food samples and environment?

Linked to these presentations, a [report](#) has been disseminated by the WP5 Science to Policy Translation of the One Health EJP. This report can be used for communication purposes.

The two publications on using metagenomics for the characterization of GMM could be of large interest to EFSA. The outcomes have already been communicated to the national authorities and to ENGL-GMO (European Network of GMO Laboratories), as these publications demonstrate how GMM can be characterized if no isolates can be obtained. In this case, metagenomics is the only way that would allow to do so.

In addition, the methodology offers potential for new strategies in monitoring programmes within the context of AMR surveillance or clinical diagnostics (before patients are admitted to intense care). The deliverables on WP1 and WP2 could be of interest to EFSA and ECDC to inspire them when considering future surveillance programmes. In line with this, the national competent authorities and European reference laboratories/centres involved in AMR and pathogen surveillance could also benefit from this. As the technology is also of interest in other fields (see below), other stakeholders, not immediately involved in AMR and pathogen surveillance, might be interested (e.g., EMA).

The on-site work (summarised in deliverable WP3) could be of interest to national organisations involved in veterinary or clinical diagnostics to further develop on-site metagenomics analyses demonstrated in FARMED. As this technology is already used at international level within crisis context in less developed countries (e.g., Ebola), also organisations that are involved there could take benefit from the lessons learnt, to improve future on-site diagnostics.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Long read metagenomic sequencing is a technology which offers many advantages in all One Health sectors, however, due to the caveats identified and the requirement to further refine the long-read metagenomics process for both laboratory and on-site application, the approach has not been routinely implemented in all FARMED partner institutes yet. As the technology is improved, it will certainly have a place in situations where information about the bacteria (or viruses, which were not investigated within FARMED) would aid surveillance and disease diagnosis.

Sciensano, as NRL-GMO and part of the European ENGL (European Network of GMO Laboratories), has contacts with the competent authorities at national (FAVV/AFSCA) and EU level, regarding the

notification of the presence of GMM in microbial fermentation products. For some of these investigations, the long-read metagenomics approach is being used. Sciensano is also member of the ENGL working group on “Sequencing strategies for the traceability of GMOs - methods and related quality aspects” and of the ENGL working group on “Detection of genetically modified microorganisms in food and feed”, where the use of metagenomics for the identification and characterization of GMM in food/feed is being discussed.

In addition, the methodology is being used (or planned to be used) in other research projects for the detection and linking of AMR genes to host species, for foodborne outbreak investigation (as asked for by EFSA in a recent opinion paper: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/5898>) but also for other application fields such as for human/animal microbiome analyses, environmental monitoring for emergency preparedness and quality control of medicinal products and vaccines. Once successful, this can lead to future routine implementation of the methodology in specific tasks of monitoring/surveillance/control activities of institutes reporting to stakeholders as ECDC, EFSA, EMA and national authorities.

2.1.7 One Health impact

Long-read sequencing and metagenomics has the potential to offer scientists and stakeholders the opportunity to detect and characterise the genomic potential of bacteria and the metagenome, in many fields of science such as bacterial/viral/fungal pathogens, genetic mechanisms of AMR and from metagenomics, understanding what constitutes a healthy microbiome and use this knowledge to assess an unhealthy microbiome. With this knowledge, appropriate intervention strategies can be devised to halt or prevent further adverse outcomes, such as the use of antimicrobial agents which may lead to antimicrobial resistance. Currently EFSA/ECDC/VMD (UK) require information on a variety of microorganism in a range of matrices, such as the AMR monitoring undertaken yearly in Europe. FARMED aimed to harness long-read sequencing to allow scientists and stakeholders to detect pathogens and AMR within a variety of matrices, used throughout the One Health EJP consortium. We had success, with this relatively new technology in a laboratory setting and variable success with implementing this technology for on-site applications. However, with time this technology will improve allowing it to become the first choice for characterising One Health matrices.

When the technology further matures, the on-site application will have a large impact on antimicrobial treatment as human and veterinary clinicians can determine or revise their treatment much more quickly. Rather than waiting days for the results of culture-based laboratory tests, within several hours the pathogens and AMR-genes present in a sample will allow clinicians to make an informed decision based on metagenomics.

On-site metagenomic sequencing also has great future value for monitoring of AMR in environmental samples. The on-site application will simplify the logistical challenges that environmental sampling is faced with, and short-read metagenomics is already becoming a standard measurement for (waste) water analysis in point-prevalence studies due to its detection of all AMR-genes, independent from microbiological culturing.

Several members of the FARMED consortium were involved in other OHEJP projects. In particular the Full-Force JRP is relevant as it also utilised long-read sequencing to characterise mobile genetic elements which are associated with driving AMR in commensal and pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae.

In addition, several partners are in close contact with the stakeholders such as EFSA, ECDC, WHO via their reference laboratory tasks or working group memberships (e.g. European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL) for *E. coli* at ISS, involved in the activities of the steering committee for the development of a joint EFSA-ECDC database for molecular typing data collection and coordinating the activities of an Inter EURLs working group on Next Generation Sequencing; AMR EURL and certified WHO lab at DTU; Sciensano, as NRL-GMO and also part of the European ENGL (European Network of

GMO Laboratories), member of the ENGL working group on “Sequencing strategies for the traceability of GMOs - methods and related quality aspects” and of the ENGL working group on “Detection of genetically modified microorganisms in food and feed”). The involvement of FARMED partners in these reference laboratories and working groups will ensure proper dissemination of the FARMED results and its potential for future monitoring/surveillance to the stakeholders.

2.1.8 Data Management Plan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7335391>

2.1.9 Future dissemination activities

As listed above, several publications are still being prepared based on the results of FARMED. Dissemination of those publications by OHEJP through social media will help to further spread the impact of these results and will be requested when these manuscripts have been accepted.

On-site sequence demonstrations based on the protocols that were developed in FARMED are planned for early 2023. Also, for these activities, further impact can be generated when OHEJP aids in the dissemination on social media.

2.2 JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM

2.2.1 Consortium composition

Project Coordinators: Prof. Terry Smith and Dr. Arnoud van Vliet

Work-Package Leaders:

Work-Package 1: *Generation of up to date sequence information for selected pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes*

W-P Leader: Prof. Bruno González Zorn, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM

WP Deputy Leader: Prof. Veljo Kisand, University of Tartu

Work-Package 2: *Assay development*

WP Leader: Prof. Terry Smith, National University of Ireland Galway

WP Deputy Leader: Prof. Roberto La Ragione and Dr. Arnoud van Vliet, University of Surrey

Work-Package 3: *Development of Lateral Flow Diagnostics Detection and Mobile Communication system*

WP Leader: Prof. Roberto La Ragione and Dr. Arnoud van Vliet, University of Surrey

WP Deputy Leader: Prof. Terry Smith, National University of Ireland Galway

Work-Package 4: *Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed*

WP Leader: Prof. Christian Menge, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut

WP Deputy Leader: Prof. Manuela Caniça, National Institute of Health Dr. Ricardo Jorge (INSA)

Work-Package 5: *Project Management*

WP Leader: Prof. Terry Smith, National University of Ireland Galway

WP Deputy Leader: Dr. Arnoud van Vliet, University of Surrey

2.2.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The One Health EJP WORLDCOM project aimed to develop diagnostic tools linked with mobile referencing technology for the detection of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in zoonotic bacterial pathogens. Resulting technologies would enable rapid on-site AMR and pathogen detection from animal and human populations, and the environment, facilitating early investigation of emerging resistances and the development of machine-learning algorithms for AMR detection and prediction.

Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) and carbapenemase enzymes produced by Enterobacteriaceae confer resistance to beta-lactam antimicrobials presenting a major public health concern. A genomic approach was used to analyse publicly available sequences of relevant pathogens (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., *Salmonella* spp. and *Acinetobacter* spp.) for circulating antibiotic resistance genes (ESBL, carbapenemase and mobile colistin resistance genes). Based on this information, targeted de novo sequencing and phenotypic characterisation of bacterial pathogens from human, animal and environmental origin was performed among partners, resulting in the

generation of an in-house database (with a total of 685 isolates) for use in assay development. Biomarker genes associated with highly prevalent ESBLs (CTX-M), carbapenemases (OXA, KPC and NDM) and colistin resistance (MCR-1) were selected as AMR diagnostic targets. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (using LEC-LAMP and LAMP) was selected as the in vitro amplification technology for detection of these targets due to its speed, specificity and robustness, as well as its ease of application in the field, including on-farm and / or in remote settings.

Additionally, OXA-48, OXA-23, KPC, VIM, MCR-1 and MCR-9 AMR biomarkers were targeted using real-time singleplex LAMP assays. The assays were developed, optimised and validated against a wide range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial isolates to confirm sensitivity and specificity using both fluorescent and colorimetric detection. The assays were further developed and implemented to successfully detect AMR biomarkers from environmental water and pig faecal samples within less than an hour. Additionally, a smartphone app has been developed to provide automated detection for LAMP diagnostic tests. The smartphone app automatically analyses captured images of colorimetric LAMP assays to facilitate field testing.

Closely-related CTX-M biomarkers, preferentially associated with animal (CTX-M-1) and human (CTX-M-15) infection, were targeted with an internally controlled multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage (LEC)-LAMP assay enabling differential point-mutation detection. Assay validation using (i) isolates from animal, human or environmental sources and also (ii) DNA isolated directly from animal and environmental samples demonstrated rapid detection (10-20 min), complete analytical specificity, and single-digit genome copy sensitivity. Development of a portable workstation incorporating the LEC-LAMP assay with a rapid DNA extraction protocol and validation for on-site application was completed with a research article relating to this work accepted for publication with *Microbiology Spectrum*. This is the first report of portable nucleic acid diagnostics applied to differential detection of CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15, providing novel transferable diagnostic technology for improved epidemiological surveillance. Additionally, a duplex LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of closely related OXA variants, OXA-48 and OXA-181/232, was also developed and validated.

2.2.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP: 1 Generation of up to date sequence information for selected pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes

WP1-T1- Analysis of publically available sequences for antimicrobial resistance genes associated with *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *E. coli*

At the UoS, all known *bla* antimicrobial resistance genes present in *Salmonella*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* and *Acinetobacter* genomes were extracted from the NCBI Pathogens database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogens/isolates#/search/>). For the initial phase of this work package, the focus was on ESBL-related AMR genes in zoonotic bacterial pathogens. However, as these genes are absent from *Campylobacter*, it was not included in these studies. All types and subtypes of Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBLs) and plasmid-mediated colistin resistance genes were analysed for their frequency among genomes from *E. coli* (n=105,165), *Salmonella* (n= 270,559), *Klebsiella* (n=24,799) and *Acinetobacter* (n=8,039). High frequency resistance gene subtypes were highlighted for further sequence analysis to illustrate geographic distribution and geographic-specific single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). The prevalence of ESBL subtypes in bacterial pathogens and a sequence database of the selected alleles have been published on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4019839) and forms part of a manuscript that has been submitted for publication. This task has been completed.

WP1-T2- Targeted and whole genome de novo sequencing of phenotypically characterised isolates from various settings

NUIG generated genomic nucleotide sequence data from Illumina sequencing of locally isolated *E. coli* containing CTX-M alleles from environmental samples and provided this sequence data to a WORLDCOM AMR gene database for use in assay development. This data included nucleotide sequence information for CTX-M-1 (n=2), CTX-M-4 (n=4), CTX-M-9 (n=1), CTX-M-15 (n=24), CTX-M-27 (n=5) and CTX-M-65 (n=1) *E. coli* isolates.

During July 2021, a OHEJP Short Term Mission (STM) was undertaken by Liam Burke (NUIG) who travelled to WORLDCOM partner UCM to train in Nanopore sequencing and hybrid sequence analysis for plasmid characterization. This STM resulted in the generation of Nanopore sequence data for a collection of 41 carbapenemase producing (*bla*_{KPC-2}, *bla*_{NDM-5} and *bla*_{OXA-48}) *Enterobacteriaceae* isolates. All strains were first isolated during 2018-2020 in Galway from natural water environments (rivers, estuaries, and sea), hospital and municipal wastewaters, the hospital environment and hospital patients. Complete Nanopore data and hybrid assemblies are now available for all strains with annotation and analysis of carbapenemase plasmids and CPE genomes still ongoing. A manuscript is in preparation.

At UCM, a total of 443 isolates were sequenced using a MiSeq Illumina platform (n = 443, 100%) and MinION device (n = 25, 5.64%). Among the total, 433 corresponded to *E. coli* strains from different sources (110 from human, 144 from swine, 136 from broilers and 43 from aquatic environments) from Spain and 10 corresponded to *Citrobacter werkmanii* strains from hospital wastewater samples from Tamale (Ghana). An *in silico* analysis of acquired antimicrobial resistance genes was performed, showing the presence of CTX-M genes (*bla*_{CTX-M-55}, *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CTX-M-14}, *bla*_{CTX-M-27} and *bla*_{CTX-M-98}, sorted by frequency), carbapenemase genes (*bla*_{NDM-1}) and mobile colistin-mediated resistance genes (*mcr-1.1*). Human strains were from patients with urinary tract infection (UTI) and *E. coli* clonal group ST131 was the most frequent (17.2%). Within this clonal group we identified the presence of CTX-M genes (*bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CTX-M-14}, *bla*_{CTX-M-27}), while in the remaining sequence types (STs) we identified different ESBL genes (*bla*_{TEM-1}, *bla*_{SHV-102}, *bla*_{OXA-1}). Isolates of animal origin (swine and broilers) belonged to a wide variety of STs. In most of them, the *bla*_{TEM-1} gene was identified (61.4%) and the co-production of CTX-M genes (*bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CTX-M-14}) and *mcr-1* was uncommon, occurring in five isolates. Regarding the strains from aquatic environments (river and wastewater, n = 43) from Spain, all wastewater isolates (n = 25) showed a common high-level resistance to β -lactam compounds, including third generation cephalosporins. This could be attributed to the presence of *bla*_{CTX-M-55} and *bla*_{CMY-2}. Furthermore, 17 wastewater strains showed *bla*_{CTX-M-55} and *mcr-1.1* co-production, while the presence of *bla*_{CTX-M} or *mcr* genes was not observed in the river samples. Additionally, 10 *C. werkmanii* isolates were collected from hospital wastewater samples from Tamale (Ghana). All *C. werkmanii* isolates shared a common multidrug resistance profile, showing resistance to β -lactams and carbapenems. This phenotypic profile of resistance was a consequence of the *bla*_{NDM-1}, *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CMY-159-like} and *bla*_{OXA-1} genes. These results have been published in Communications Biology (DOI: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x) and mSystems (DOI: 0.1128/msystems.01019-21) and uploaded to the Zenodo repository.

At FLI, 143 *E. coli* strains, which had been isolated during a longitudinal sampling approach from four different pig farms in Thuringia, and which were resistant to 3rd generation cephalosporins in antimicrobial susceptibility testing and had also previously been assayed with the CTX-M-1/-15 specific LEC-LAMP assay developed at NUIG (see [JRP13-WP2-T1](#)), were short-read whole genome sequenced and analysed for their β -lactamase genes. Three sequences did not allow allele distinction due to incomplete gene assembly. Two strains which tested negative in the LEC-LAMP assay were identified as non-responsive *bla*_{CTX-M-27} alleles. 87 strains were identified as encoding *bla*_{CTX-M-1}. A further 51 strains with a *bla*_{CTX-M-15}-positive LEC-LAMP signal were classified as containing *bla*_{CTX-M-15} and five, also with a *bla*_{CTX-M-15}-positive LEC-LAMP signal, as containing *bla*_{CTX-M-55} confirming that the assay does not

distinguish between the SNP variant alleles CTX-M-15 and CTX-M-55. The large number of field isolates and the results obtained from sequencing and the LEC-LAMP assay validate the LEC-LAMP assay as specific. We additionally short-read sequenced 22 *E. coli* strains with an ESBL-phenotype that had been isolated from alpacas and llamas. Among the encoded β -lactamases, 16 encoded a *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, two a *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, two a *bla*_{CTX-M-27}, one a *bla*_{CTX-M-65} and two a *bla*_{CMY-2} allele. Of these, nine strains with a *bla*_{CTX-M-1} allele and two strains with a *bla*_{CTX-M-15} were tested and scored positive. The presence of a *bla*_{CMY-2} allele in one strain did not interfere with detection of the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} allele also present in this strain. Strains with a *bla*_{CTX-M-27} or a *bla*_{CTX-M-65} allele were negative in the assay, adding to the specificity validation. Additionally, nine ceftiofur-resistant isolates, identified as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* or *K. michiganensis*, were long-read sequenced to identify their β -lactamase genes and extend assay validation beyond testing *E. coli* strains. Six strains contained a *bla*_{CTX-M-15} and three a *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene. The sequencing data confirmed the results from the LEC-LAMP assay performed in parallel. This further validates the LEC-LAMP assay. One *bla*_{CTX-M-15} positive strain was also scored as *bla*_{CTX-M-1} positive in the sequence analysis with the Resfinder database (v 4.1; <https://cge.food.dtu.dk/services/ResFinder/>), but as negative in the LEC-LAMP assay. Detailed sequence analysis revealed a SNP at the tandem SNP position determining differentiation between the CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15 alleles. This SNP encoded an adenine, distinguishing it from both *bla*_{CTX-M-1} with a guanine and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} with a thymine at this position. This once more demonstrates the discriminatory power and, thus, the specificity of the LEC-LAMP assay. None of the *E. coli* or *Klebsiella* strains that were sequenced contained resistance genes either encoding a *mcr* allele mediating mobile colistin resistance, or a β -lactamase gene encoding a carbapenemase. Phenotypic resistance profiles and whole-genome sequencing data analysis from the strains isolated from alpacas and llamas have been published in two manuscripts (Berl Münch Tierärztl Wochenschr, 2022, 135:1–16; Microorganisms, 2022, 10:1697) which have been uploaded to the Zenodo repository. Manuscripts describing the isolation of *E. coli* strains from the pig farms, their antimicrobial resistance profiles, the LEC-LAMP results and the analysis of the whole-genome-sequencing are in preparation and will be submitted in 2023.

In addition, in total 434 *E. coli*, 103 *Salmonella spp.*, 88 *Campylobacter spp.* and 1 *Vibrio vulnificus* isolates were *de novo* sequenced and draft genomes assembled at UT. These isolates originated from various settings including hospitals, farms, food and environmental samples. The bioinformatic analysis of these genomes included annotation and prediction of the genes (i.e. ARM genes), and *in silico* assignment of MLSTs. A long read sequencing protocol using Oxford Nanopore technology was developed and tested for closing draft genomes using *de novo* assembled *E. coli* genomes and MRSA isolates from previous isolate collections, the results thereof were presented at ASM 2022 (poster). Two scientific peer reviewed publications about *de novo* WGS of *Campylobacter spp.* have been published and one Genome Announcement about clinical *Vibrio vulnificus* has been released. UCM and UT have led the generation of a sequence database (WORLDCOM_db), with the support of the UoS, with the aim of sharing among the WORLDCOM partners a resource of the relevant pathogens sequenced and characterized during the progress of WP1-T2. The dataset comprises 685 isolates sequenced isolates provided by UCM, NUIG and INSA with further sequences to be added by FLI. The isolates corresponded mostly with *E. coli* (n = 508), *K. pneumoniae* (n = 156), *A. baumannii* (n = 11) and *C. werkmanii* (n = 10) from various sources (human, animal and environmental). Metadata was included with information regarding the date of isolation, location, host, sample type, sequencing platform and the presence of ESBL, carbapenem and mobile colistin-mediated resistance genes. 20.4% of the isolates carried CTX-M genes (predominantly CTX-M-15), 13.8% carried KPC-3 gene (mainly in *K. pneumoniae* strains) and 4.6% carried NDM genes. The Microrreact web application has been used to host this database providing interactive data visualizations (maps, graphs, timelines). The web link to the whole dataset will be provided to WORLDCOM partners and public access will be restricted, allowing WORLDCOM partners to further explore and download the dataset.

At INSA, the whole genome sequencing of several Gram-negative isolates originated from various settings (human, animal, and food) was performed using Illumina technology. Genomes were *de novo* assembled using the INNUca pipeline and Prokka was applied to annotate the assemblies.

Bioinformatics tools and databases were used to investigate the presence of antimicrobial resistance genes, virulence factors, plasmids, mobile genetic elements, and pathogenicity.

Among the total of strains sequenced, around 150 strains (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterobacter cloacae* complex, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Providencia stuartii*, and *Proteus vulgaris*), were collected in Portuguese hospitals since 2014, and referred to INSA as NDM-producers. After *de novo* assembling, the phylogenetic inference was performed with chewBBACA pipeline, using the core genome MultiLocus Sequence Typing (cgMLST) schema. The evolutionary relationship was accessed by Minimum spanning trees (MST) using PHYLOViZ. The results obtained demonstrated the diversity of genetic structures associated with *bla*_{NDM-type} gene, including: (i) host bacterial specie; (ii) plasmid types and associated mobile genetic elements; (iii) *bla*_{NDM} variants; and (iv) coproduction of *bla*_{CTX-M-type}. A manuscript is in preparation and will be submitted in 2023.

For aquaculture, a total of 66 Gram-negative strains (belonging to *Aeromonadaceae*, *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Hafniaceae*, *Morganellaceae*, *Pseudomonadaceae*, *Shewanellaceae*, *Vibrionaceae*, and *Yersiniaceae* families) were selected for genomic characterization. More than 140 different genes were identified in the resistome of seabream and bivalve molluscs, encompassing genes associated with β -lactams, tetracyclines, aminoglycosides, quinolones, sulphonamides, trimethoprim, phenicols, macrolides and fosfomycin resistance. Disinfectant- and heavy metals-resistance genes were also found. Seventy-three percent of the strains analysed were considered pathogenic to humans. The manuscript is in preparation and will be submitted in 2023. In addition, an article was already published reporting the the resistome, virulome and mobilome of an MCR-9-producing *Enterobacter ludwigii* isolated in a fish from aquaculture (Antibiotics, 2022, 11, 1232. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11091232>). The results obtained highlighted that antibiotic resistance in aquaculture is spreading through food, the environment, and humans, which places this research in a One Health context

Furthermore, INSA performed a comparative genomic analysis of *mcr*-type-harbouring plasmids originating from clinical settings, food-producing animals, and vegetable samples in Portugal. Two incompatibility groups of *mcr-1*-type-harboring plasmids were detected: IncX4 and IncHI2. The IncHI2 group was found in the three different reservoirs: two unrelated MCR-1.1-producing *E. coli* isolates from vegetables and human, associated with *in silico* resistance to colistin, beta-lactams, sulphonamides, tetracycline and phenicol and one MCR-1.1-producing *S. 4,[5],12:i:-* from bovine meat, only associated with colistin resistance. IncX4 plasmids harboured *mcr-1.1* (two clinical *K. pneumoniae*) and *mcr-1.9* (two *E. coli* collected from swine) associated with multiple resistance elements including *bla*_{KPC-3}, *bla*_{CTX-M-type}, *fosA*-type, *oqxAB*-like, *dfrA14*-like, and *aac(6')Ib-cr*-like, in various combinations. Globally, the variability and content of the genetic environment of the *mcr*-type genes detected, suggests a high ability of these genes to mobilize and spread. The manuscript is in preparation and will be submitted in 2023.

WP1-T3- Development of machine learning algorithms for the prediction of anti-microbial resistance. (University of Surrey, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM)

At the UoS, machine learning algorithm studies have been undertaken to develop algorithms for automating LAMP detection, reducing human biases and the need for expertise to analyse the results. Thus, algorithms have been developed in collaboration with WP2-T1, specifically for the automated detection of AMR genes based on fluorescence and colorimetric LAMP assay image data. For the fluorescence-based detection, amplification and annealing data series were used as the input for a multi-modal neural network model trained using logistic regression. This model was trained and tested using a total of 56 samples, and leave-one-out cross validation estimated a test accuracy of ~ 98 %. With respect to colorimetric-based detection, images of tested samples (e.g. targeting *mcr-1* and *bla*_{KPC} genes) were used to train a nearest centroid classifier algorithm to automatically identify colour changes. The images for the samples were pre-processed using colour-based thresholding and contour edge detection to extract representative features for the algorithm. Moreover, a hierarchical clustering

technique, agglomerative clustering, has been introduced to provide robustness against background noise. This algorithm has been successfully validated using noisy image data and has since been ported into an Android smartphone app for on-site applications. This work has been published on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173>) and will be part of a future publication that is currently in preparation.

WP2: Assay Development

WP2-T1- Development and performance evaluation of singleplex isothermal amplification assays for selected AMR gene targets

NUIG completed the design and development of singleplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage - loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assays for the detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, using existing genomic sequence data from *E. coli* isolates collected and processed by NUIG. Sequence alignment analysis was used to identify single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) differences between both variants, which were then used to develop variant specific LEC-LAMP assays for differential target detection. A separate LEC-LAMP assay for the detection of an internal amplification control (IAC) was also developed. Complete analytical specificity for each assay was established. Analytical sensitivity testing for each assay demonstrated rapid low limits-of-detection with 10 genome copies detected in under 20 min. These assays were used in WP2 Task 3 to develop an internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay. NUIG also completed the design and development of a singleplex LEC-LAMP assay for the specific detection of the closely related OXA variants, *bla*_{OXA-48-}, *bla*_{OXA-181} and *bla*_{OXA-232}. Assay evaluation demonstrated complete analytical specificity and fast low-level detection of 10 genome copies in under 20 min.

At the UoS, *mcr-1*, *mcr-9*, *bla*_{OXA-48}, *bla*_{OXA-23}, *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{KPC} gene sequences were extracted from genomes listed in the NCBI Pathogens database to represent all gene alleles. This showed the conserved regions across the different alleles of each gene subtypes and the homology across the selected subtypes. Conserved regions among the sequences were used to design LAMP primer sets for the selected AMR biomarkers using both LAMP Designer 1.15 and Primer Explorer V5. Following optimisation, all LAMP assays were able to successfully detect target AMR genes within less than 10 mins. The detection limit demonstrated a successful detection of 0.0625 pg of DNA.

WP2-T2- Evaluation and selection of sample preparation methods for use with laboratory on-site tests

NUIG completed the development and evaluation of a rapid sample preparation protocol, a 15 min Chelex/heat lysis DNA extraction method, for on-site DNA extraction from animal faecal samples. Validation of this method was carried out using porcine faecal samples supplied by FLI. These samples were previously collected and confirmed positive for CTX-M-1 by selecting cultures from Gassner agar plates containing 4 µg/ml Ceftiofur, followed by bacterial DNA extraction and PCR using *bla*_{CTX-M-1}-family-specific primers with Sanger-sequencing. Samples contained varying amounts of coliform strains resistant to Ceftiofur, ranging from 25-100%. 200 mg of each sample was processed using the rapid sample preparation protocol, followed by LEC-LAMP testing. All samples successfully tested positive for CTX-M-1 in under 20 min. Application of this method was included in a recently accepted for publication with Microbiology Spectrum.

The team at the UoS developed a rapid, sensitive and culture-independent sample preparation method for environmental water samples. The method involved centrifugation of the water samples to precipitate the bacterial content followed by resuspension in extraction buffer and heat shock treatment for bacterial lysis. The method is rapid (30 min). To validate the method, spiked water samples were extracted and then subjected to LAMP where successful amplification was achieved within one hour. The assays demonstrated a detection limit of 10 cfu/mL (as confirmed by culture).

The application of the method with LAMP detection is part of a manuscript that has been submitted for peer review.

WP2-T3- Development and performance evaluation of multiplex assays for pathogens and resistance genes

NUIG completed the development and evaluation of an internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}. The internally controlled LEC-LAMP assay contains fluorescently labelled primer/probes specific to each target: FAM for *bla*_{CTX-M-1}; HEX for *bla*_{CTX-M-15}; and Cy5 for the IAC. The LEC-LAMP assay demonstrated complete analytical specificity and differential detection of both variants when tested with environmental *E. coli* isolates collected from Ireland and animal *E. coli* isolates from Central Germany: CTX-M-1 (n=15); CTX-M-15 (n=37); and other CTX-Ms (n=12). The LEC-LAMP assay also demonstrated low-level detection for each variant at 10 genome copies per reaction in approximately 20 min. NUIG has submitted a manuscript relating to this work to Microbiology Spectrum which has been accepted for publication. NUIG also completed the development of a duplex LEC-LAMP assay for the specific differential detection of the closely related OXA variants, *bla*_{OXA-48} and *bla*_{OXA-181/232}. Assay evaluation demonstrated complete analytical specificity and fast low-level detection of 10 genome copies in under 20 min.

At the UoS, the team further developed the LAMP assays into a multiplex detection system on the same assay strip. The 8-tube strip contains a reaction for the respective AMR biomarkers; thus, the test can simultaneously detect the six biomarkers along with positive and negative controls. This approach is being used in combination with the SmartApp application for pathogen/AMR detection in pig faeces samples.

WP3: Development of Lateral Flow Diagnostics Detection and Mobile Communication system

WP3-T1- Development of lateral flow diagnostics for AMR detection

The development of lateral flow diagnostics at the UoS was found to be redundant due to the excellent performance of both fluorescent and colorimetric detection assays that have been developed. Therefore, the team expanded on the AMR LAMP panel to include an additional plasmid mediated colistin resistance marker (*mcr-9*) due to the high prevalence in *Salmonella* spp. and in some reported *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* spp strains. The assay has demonstrated promising performance and will be further validated using additional *mcr-9* positive isolates.

WP3-T2- Development of mobile technology for communication of on-site results

At the UoS, a Smartapp for the Android platform has been developed to automatically analyse captured images from colorimetric LAMP assays performed outside, process captured images and upload their results to a cloud-hosted database. This deliverable aimed to transfer the machine learning outputs of WP1-T3 (i.e., deliverable D-JRP13-1.2) as applied to a mobile Smartapp for this purpose. This code was written in Python using the 'Kivy' package to develop software for the Android platform and tested on a mobile Samsung S10 device. This code has been uploaded to an online repository for version control purposes.

Further validation for assessing the efficiency of the Smartapp for detecting outdoor LAMP images is currently ongoing. These include our validated singleplex AMR LAMP assays and the *mcr-9* LAMP assay from spiked and un-spiked pig faecal samples. The beta testing demonstrated successful detection of positive (yellow tubes) and negative (pink tubes) in laboratory and outdoors settings. This work has been published on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173>) and will be part of a future publication that is currently in preparation.

WP4: Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed

WP4-T1- Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests for detection of pathogens and resistance genes

At FLI, the multiplex LEC-LAMP assay has so far been tested on 240 *E. coli* and nine *Klebsiella* spp. strains, which had been previously isolated from porcine and South American camelid faecal samples and which were resistant to Ceftiofur, as demonstrated by antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Of these, 162 were positive for *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and 83 for *bla*_{CTX-M-15/55}. The remaining four negative strains contain sequence-verified *bla*_{CTX-M-27} and *bla*_{CTX-M-65} alleles. Six ceftiofur-resistant *Klebsiella* spp. strains were shown to be *bla*_{CTX-M-15} positive, by both whole-genome-sequencing and by LEC-LAMP assay. The remaining three *Klebsiella* spp. strains were positive for the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} allele, as confirmed by LEC-LAMP assay and whole-genome-sequencing. Additionally, FLI has collected composite faecal samples from different age groups (sows, suckling pigs, weaners, early, middle, late finishers) from nine conventional pig farms with the help of the local pig health service. They were plated and counts of total *E. coli* and ceftiofur-resistant *E. coli* were determined to obtain both the total number and the relative proportion of ceftiofur-resistant isolates. For each sample with growth on agar plates containing ceftiofur, colonies were isolated and checked for the identity of the β -lactamase gene. So far, alleles for CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15 have been detected using the LEC-LAMP assay. DNA from the faecal material will be isolated directly following the protocol developed by NUIG to analyse sensitivity and specificity of the LEC-LAMP assay. As we did not identify any samples or isolates which were positive for a mobile colistin resistance gene or a carbapenemase, because these are infrequent in porcine, bovine and camelid samples from Germany, we were not able to provide isolates for target validation and feasibility testing nor to have any samples for on-site testing at FLI.

At INSA, the protocol developed by NUIG to analyse the sensitivity and specificity of the LEC-LAMP assay was tested and evaluated in CTX-M-producing bacteria recovered from clinical, animal (aquaculture), environmental and human samples.

NUIG developed a mobile diagnostics workstation incorporating the previously developed Chelex/heat based rapid DNA extraction protocol with the CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay and validated its application for on-site use in agricultural or environmental settings. Previously confirmed CTX-M-1 positive porcine faecal samples provided by FLI and UT were used to validate this portable diagnostic workstation. Application and validation of this workstation was included in a manuscript recently accepted for publication with Microbiology Spectrum. Recently, additional on-site validation testing of the portable diagnostics workstation incorporating the CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP with rapid DNA extraction protocol was carried out using bovine faecal samples. All bovine samples (n=50) were collected from multiple agricultural farm settings in Galway, Ireland.

WP4-T2- Generation of information for dissemination

Development and validation of the CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay in combination with the rapid DNA extraction protocol and portable diagnostics workstation has led to the generation of a research article entitled, "Portable differential detection of CTX-M ESBL gene variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, from *Escherichia coli* isolates and animal faecal samples using loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification", which has been submitted for publication with Microbiology Spectrum. This protocol developed for performing the LEC-LAMP assay was distributed to FLI and to INSA for testing samples and strains isolated at FLI and INSA, respectively. Its functionality and specificity were validated at FLI by testing on 249 *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* spp. strains; sequencing results obtained from 174 strains were consistent with the results obtained using the LEC-LAMP assay. Validation of the CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay at INSA was carried out with bacterial strains isolated from samples obtained from different reservoirs, and results were confirmed by other methods, such as multiplex PCR and WGS.

All publications of this project using LEC LAMP and LAMP technology will bear fruit in the scientific community, including the EURL, which, due to the technology's success and feasibility, will use it in future and, consequently, also validate it.

WP5: Project Management

WP5-T1 - Project Management (M25-M60)

A project management team, comprising Principal Investigators / Project Leaders from each of the project partners, was established at the outset of the project (January 2020). The management team provided direction and support to ensure the success of the project throughout the 3 year period of the project (Jan 2020 - Dec. 2022).

As a result of the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020, subsequent WorldCOM consortium meetings took place via Zoom meetings, beginning in March 2020. Regular virtual (ZOOM) consortium meetings were held throughout the project, and WorldCOM consortium virtual annual review meetings were held in 2020 and 2021.

In April 2022, WORLDCOM consortium members attended the OHEJP ASM meeting, presenting the work of the consortium to colleagues and stakeholders at various fora. The consortium members who attended the meeting also met to review progress to date. The consortium also hosted a very successful virtual workshop during the ASM entitled "**One Health EJP ASM Satellite Workshop: Diagnostics workshop; mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications**" which was held on April 14th 2022.

A WORLDCOM consortium final annual review meeting will be held in December 2022.

WP5-T2 - Preparation of a data management plan

A WORLDCOM DMP based on the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP was developed according to guidance provided by the OHEJP WP4 team in their D4.7 Guidelines for Data Management Plan implementation. The DMP was submitted (deliverable D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.2) and is available on the DMP group of the OHEJP website. WORLDCOM DMP leader Liam Burke attended online training on August 5th 2020 for the new OHEJP online data management platform CDP. A data management guide and DMP Excel template for WORLDCOM has been prepared for task leaders to help them comply with the DMP. Liam Burke will update the CDP application with details of WORLDCOM data throughout the project, with information provided to him by task leaders on their datasets using the Excel template. The OHEJP WP4 team reviewed and approved WORLDCOM's online DMP in December 2020.

The WORLDCOM DMP received positive feedback from the DMP Committee team (July 2021 and March 2022). It was noted that the WORLDCOM DMP was well developed, with a good understanding about how to use the template. Reviewers' individual comments for improvement were implemented in the online tool. The online DMP was updated again on 14th June 2022, and in November 2022 with all available project metadata. The final version of the DMP, containing links to manuscripts currently under review for publication, will be published, extracted and added to Zenodo before the project ends in December 2022.

Conference proceedings and selected reports, prepared within the consortium, were made publicly available.

2.2.4 Project self-assessment

The key objectives of the WORLDCOM project and consortium include the following topics. All objectives were successfully accomplished, with one exception as outlined below:

1. *“to develop new tools for early (real-time) detection of anti-microbial resistant pathogens in humans and animals”*

This objective was successfully achieved, through the design and development of novel LEC-LAMP and LAMP molecular diagnostics assays for the specific and real-time detection of key antimicrobial resistance genes in the laboratory and on-site (on-farm and at other remote locations). The design and development of novel AMR diagnostic tests using LEC-LAMP and LAMP technology, and their application using a portable diagnostics workstation for use in the field, and the development and use of a Smartapp algorithm will greatly facilitate field detection, reporting of results, and their transfer to central cloud storage.

Successful accomplishment of this objective will enable the application of the assays developed by the WORLDCOM consortium, and other LEC-LAMP and LAMP assays to be applied in the field for AMR markers associated with human and animal infection. The application of these real-time portable assays will enable new insights into the prevalence and transmission of AMR between environment, animals and humans.

2. *“To develop new diagnostic tools for AMR in humans and animals, in particular on-site tests”*

This objective was successfully achieved, with LEC-LAMP and LAMP tests developed for pathogens and resistance genes formatted for use on-site (e.g. pen-side/ bed-side; remote locations), using a portable diagnostics workstation and/or a Smartapp. The tests are suitable for use with animal and human faecal material and recreational, drinking and irrigation water samples.

3. *“To support the use of IT solutions in developing tools for diagnosing resistant infections in human and animal populations”*

In this project, the aim was to develop two IT solutions. The first IT solution, the development of mobile technology to enable communication of the results obtained on-site/pen-side with reference laboratories was successfully accomplished. The second objective, to develop and train novel machine learning algorithms for the prediction and detection of antimicrobial resistance from genomes of clinically relevant bacterial species was not achieved.

4. *“To ensure that the development of new tools will be compatible with the work and mandate of EU wide systems and organizations in these areas”*

Once the initial validation of the LAMP tests is complete, ring trials will be set up with EU laboratories undertaking statutory testing. The researchers from WORLDCOM will also liaise with EFSA and national standard organisations to ensure the tests meet the required standards.

Taken together, the ability to rapidly design and validate LEC-LAMP and LAMP assays to detect antimicrobial resistance genes (AMR) coupled with the protocols established for sample processing, signal detection and result reporting indicates that the monitoring and reporting system implemented here can be easily and flexibly adapted to regional prevalences of AMR genes and their risk for causing health issues in the different target populations. The easy to implement protocols will also allow transfer to LMIC countries to close gaps in the surveillance of pathogens and AMR.

2.2.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
13	D-JRP13-1.1	Generation of a sequence database comprising publically available and newly generated sequences for <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> and <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. and resistance genes CTX-M-15, NDM-5, KPC-2, OXA-48 and MCR-1.	M33	M33	Shared on relevant WORLDCOM OHEJP website section and with all consortium members during development. public at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4019840	3
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-1.2	Novel machine learning algorithms for the prediction and detection of AMR from genomic sequences.	M56	M56	Deliverable document uploaded on WORLDCOM section of OHEJP website and is part of the 1-page abstract made public on Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173..	2, 4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-2.1	Multiplex real-time isothermal assays for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes which will be suitable for use in laboratory and optimised further in WP3 into a format suitable for on-site use	M43	M43	Report on deliverable uploaded to ZENODO: Public at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5912015	1
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP3.1	On-site testing using Smartphone App for collection of data and transmission of test results to reference laboratory	M57	M57	1-page abstract made public on Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173 Deliverable document uploaded on WORLDCOM section of OHEJP website.	1
413	D-JPR13-AMR2.1-WP4.1	Feasibility testing of on-site tests for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes complete	M60	M60	Laboratory feasibility testing has been undertaken on LAMP assays demonstrating the application of the assays in the field.	1, 2, 4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
					ZENODO reference –Higgins et al. 2022 Publication ?	
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-WP4.2	Novel algorithms for prediction of antimicrobial resistance	M60	M60	This work is ongoing.	1, 3
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-WP4.3	Protocols and SOPs prepared and available for dissemination	M60	M60	ALL	2
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-5.1	Kick-off meeting organised	M26	M25	Brief report on KOM uploaded to ZENODO: Public via https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5464662	Other - Project management
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-5.2	DMP reviewed	M33	M33	The OHEJP WP4 team reviewed and approved WORLDCOM's online DMP in the CDP tool in December 2020.	3
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-5.3	Organisation of project review meetings	M33	M33	WORLDCOM consortium review meetings held in September 2020, September 2021, and December 2022	Other – project management

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-5.4	Final 12 month technical and financial reports prepared for Year 3 Year 4 Report submitted in M	M38 M50	M38 M50	Both technical and financial reports have been uploaded to Zenodo and can be accessed at: Public at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499692	Other – project management

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-01	Generation of sequence information for pathogens and resistance genes of interest.	M30	M42	Deliverable 1: Prevalence of ESBL subtypes in bacterial pathogens and a sequence database of selected alleles, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4019839

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-02	Transfer of relevant sequence information for development and training of novel machine learning algorithms.	M56	M56	Deliverable made public on Zenodo : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-03	Singleplex assays for the detection of pathogens including <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> and <i>E. coli</i> and CTX-M-15, KPC-2, NDM-5, OXA-48 and MCR-1 genes	M39	M39	Achieved and is part of a manuscript accepted for publication.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-04	Sample preparation methods evaluated	M39	M39	Achieved and is part of a manuscript submitted for publication.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-05	Organisation of kick-off meeting	M26	M25	Brief report on KOM uploaded to ZENODO: Public via https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5464662
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-06	Preparation of technical and financial reports for submission	M38	M38	Technical reports have been uploaded to Zenodo and can be accessed at: Public at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499692

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-07	Performance testing of lateral flow detection completed	M48	M48	Lateral flow was not pursued due to the excellent performance of both the fluorescent and colorimetric assays.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-08	Smartphone App for curation of assay results developed	M48	M48	Achieved and will be part of a manuscript to be submitted for publication.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-09	Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests underway	M60	M60	Ongoing at FLI and NUIG; Feasibility testing has already been performed and has already been accepted for publication. Further testing will be part of a manuscript to be submitted for publication.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-10	Feasibility testing of novel algorithm underway	M60	M60	Currently undergoing at UoS.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-11	Project review meetings organised	M36	M33, M45 and M60	Annual WORLDCOM consortium review meetings held in September 2020, September 2021, and December 2022.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-12	Technical and financial reports prepared	M60	M60	Technical and financial reports have been prepared and submitted for Year 3 and Year 4. T=Year 5 report preparation in progress.
13	M-JPR AMR2.1-13	Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tested underway	M60	M60	Ongoing at FLI and NUIG; Feasibility testing has already been performed and has already

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
					been accepted for publication. Further testing will be part of a manuscript.
13	M-JPR AMR2.1-14	Feasibility testing of novel algorithms underway	M60	M60	Currently undergoing at UoS.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-15	Generation of technical and financial reports	M60	M60	Year 3 and 4 reports submitted and Year 5 report I progress.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-16	Dissemination of outputs from project to OneHealth and publicly	M60	M60	Dissemination of outputs from the WORLDCOM project via publications, social media and other outlets and fora has been achieved. Dissemination is continuing and will be ongoing beyond Month 60.

2.2.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance dynamics of Escherichia coli in wastewater and river environments.	Published	YES		YES (2680 euros)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Delgado-Blas JF, Ovejero CM, David S, Montero N, Calero-Caceres W, Garcillan-Barcia MP, de la Cruz F, Muniesa M, Aanensen DM, Gonzalez-Zorn B. Commun Biol. 2021 Apr 12;4(1):457.</p> <p>DOI: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR</p>				
<p>Genomic Screening of Antimicrobial Resistance Markers in UK and US Campylobacter Isolates Highlights Stability of Resistance over an 18-Year Period.</p> <p>van Vliet AHM, Thakur S, Prada JM, Mehat JW, La Ragione RM.</p> <p>Antimicrob Agents Chemother. 2022 May 17;66(5):e0168721. DOI: 10.1128/aac.01687-21</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6618202</p>	Published	YES		YES (2430 euros)
<p>Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP): for mobile rapid detection of nucleic acid targets.</p> <p>Hassan, M.M., Grist, L.F., Poirier, A.C. & La Ragione, R.M.</p> <p>Journal of Medical Microbiology 2022 May 71(5):001522.</p> <p>DOI: 10.1099/jmm.0.001522.</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6618240</p>	Published	YES		YES (no specific gold OA cost due to Publish & Read agreement between publisher/society and university)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Survey on shedding of selected pathogenic, zoonotic or antimicrobial resistant bacteria by South American camelids in Central Germany.</p> <p>González-Santamarina, B., Schnee, C., Köhler, H., Weber, M., Methner, U., Seyboldt, C., Berens, C. & Menge, C.</p> <p>Berliner und Münchener Tierärztliche Wochenschrift 2022, 135:1–16</p> <p>DOI: 10.2376/1439-0299-2021-21</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6642390</p>	Published	YES		YES (1130.50 euros)
<p>The Prevalence, Counts and MLST Genotypes of Campylobacter in Poultry Meat and Genomic Comparison with Clinical Isolates.</p> <p>Tedersoo T, Roasto M, Mäesaar M, Kisand V, Ivanova M, Meremäe K. Poult Sci. Published online 2022:101703.</p> <p>doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2022.101703</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6642459</p>	Published	YES		YES (1740 euros)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Antibiotic Resistance in <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. Isolated from Broiler Chicken Meat and Human Patients in Estonia.</p> <p>Tedersoo T, Roasto M, Mäesaar M, Häkkinen L, Kisand V, Ivanova M, Valli MH, Meremäe K.</p> <p>Microorganisms. 2022;10(5):1067.</p> <p>doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10051067</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6642526</p>	Published	YES		YES (1623 euros)
<p>Dissemination Routes of Carbapenem and Pan-Aminoglycoside Resistance Mechanisms in Hospital and Urban Wastewater Canalizations of Ghana.</p> <p>Delgado-Blas JF, Valenzuela Agüi C, Marin Rodriguez C, Serna C, Montero N, Saba CKS, Gonzalez-Zorn B.</p> <p>mSystems. 2022 Feb 22;7(1):e0101921. doi: 10.1128/msystems.01019-21</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6619655#.YqBvbOxBy59</p>	Published	YES		YES (2830 euros)
<p>Genomic Analysis of a <i>mcr-9.1</i>-Harbouring IncHI2-ST1 Plasmid from <i>Enterobacter ludwigii</i> isolated in Fish Farming.</p>	Published	YES		Yes (no cost to the WORLDCOM project)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Manageiro V, Salgueiro V, Rosado T, Bandarra NM, Ferreira E, Smith T, Dias E, Caniça M. <i>Antibiotics</i> 2022, 11, 1232. https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11091232</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/7096620#.YymkZ3bMJPY</p>				
<p>Comparative Genomic Analysis of Antimicrobial-Resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> from South American Camelids in Central Germany.</p> <p>González-Santamarina B, Weber M, Menge C, Berens C. <i>Microorganisms</i>. 2022, 10:1697. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms10091697. https://zenodo.org/record/7327073</p>	Published	YES		YES (1449 Euros)
<p>Portable differential detection of CTX-M ESBL gene variants, <i>bla</i>_{CTX-M-1} and <i>bla</i>_{CTX-M-15}, from <i>Escherichia coli</i> isolates and animal faecal samples using loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification. Owen Higgins, Alexandra Chueiri, Louise O'Connor, Sinéad Lahiff, Liam Burke, Dearbháile Morris, Nicola Pfeifer, Belén Santamarina, Christian Berens, Christian Menge,</p>	Published	YES		\$1,800 > €1,700 if you're an ASM member. I am if necessary.

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Manuela Caniça, Vera Manageiro, Veljo Kisand, Marwa Hassan, Brian Gardner, Arnoud van Vliet, Roberto La Ragione, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn, and Terry Smith. Microbiology Spectrum 2022.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.03316-22</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/7440937</p>				
<p>Rapid culture-independent loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) detection of antimicrobial resistance markers from environmental water samples. Marwa M Hassan, Arnoud H. M. van Vliet, Owen Higgins, Liam P. Burke, Alexandra Chueiri, Louise O'Connor, Dearbháile Morris, Terry Smith and Roberto M. La Ragione.</p>	<p>Minor revisions for Microbial Biotechnology Journal</p>	<p>Yes</p>		
<p>On-site SmartApp and loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) detection of antimicrobial resistance from pig faeces</p> <p>Marwa M. Hassan, Brian Gardner, Arnoud H. M. van Vliet, Owen Higgins, Liam P. Burke, Alexandra Chueiri, Louise O'Connor, Dearbháile Morris, Terry Smith and Roberto M. La Ragione.</p>	<p>In preparation</p>	<p>Yes</p>		
<p>Flouroquinolone- or cephalosporin-resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> persist in Thuringian pigsties. Pfeifer N, Wiegand E, Barth SA, Berens C, Menge C, manuscript in preparation</p>	<p>Planned for publication in 2023</p>	<p>Yes</p>		

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Multiresistance is frequently observed in fluoroquinolone- or cephalosporin-resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> isolated in Thuringian pigsties. Pfeifer N, Barth SA, Higgins O, Chueiri A, O'Connor L, Smith T, Berens C, Menge C, manuscript in preparation	Planned for publication in 2023	Yes		
Persistent fluoroquinolone- or cephalosporin-resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> strains in Thuringian pigsties belong to lineages of globally disseminated high-risk clones, Pfeifer N, Weber M, Barth SA, Menge C, Berens C, manuscript in preparation	Planned for publication in 2023	Yes		
Exploring the resistome, virulome and mobilome of Gram-Negative bacteria isolated from farmed fish and bivalve mollusks. INSA team.	In preparation	Yes		YES (2400 Euros)
Diversity of genetic structures associated with <i>bla</i> _{NDM-type} gene and coproduction with <i>bla</i> _{CTX-M-type} genes. The role of LEC-LAMP method in the detection of the CTX-M-1/15 determinants. INSA team.	In preparation	Yes		
Comparative genomic analysis of <i>mcr</i> -type-harboring plasmids originating from clinical settings, food-producing animals, and vegetable samples in Portugal. INSA team.	In preparation	Yes		

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Decrypting the diversity of microbiome in aquaculture. Doctoral thesis. Vanessa Salgueiro.	To be defended in 2023	Yes		
Analysis of AMR patterns in <i>E. coli</i> in the 21st century. UoS with partners.	In preparation	Yes		
Analysis of AMR patterns in <i>Salmonella enterica</i> in the 21st century. UoS with partners.	In preparation	Yes		

Additional output

Posters and presentations

- Automated detection of AMR target genes using loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP). Presented by Brian Gardner (UoS) to the OHEJP ASM 2021. Selected as an e-Poster presentation.
- Rapid detection and discrimination of closely related Enterobacteriaceae CTX-M group 1 variants, blaCTX-M-1 and blaCTX-M-15, using an internally controlled multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay. Presented by Owen Higgins (NUIG) at the 2021 Microbiology Society conference, the OHEJP 2021 ASM, and the ECCMID 2021 conference.
- Development of LAMP assays for the detection of key AMR targets in animal faeces and water samples. Presented by Marwa Hassan (UoS) at the 2021 Microbiology Society conference.
- Rapid LAMP detection of key AMR targets for use as bed-side and/or pen-side diagnostics. Presented by Marwa Hassan (UoS) at the 2021 OHEJP 2021 ASM.
- Dynamics of quinolone- and cephalosporin-resistant *Escherichia coli* carriage along the production chain in Thuringian pigsties. Presented by Nicola Pfeifer (FLI) at the OHEJP 2021 ASM.
- Whole-genome sequencing of phenotypically characterized isolates from various setting. Presented by Vera Manageiro (INSA) at the OHEJP ASM 2021, 9th-11th June 2021 (e-Poster).
- Rapid and culture-independent LAMP detection of key AMR markers from environmental water samples. Hassan, M.M., Vliet, A.H.M. van, Higgins, O., Burke, L., O'Connor, L., Morris, D., Smith, T. & La Ragione, R.M. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- Rapid real-time differential detection of OXA-48-like variants using loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification. Owen Higgins, Louise O'Connor, Marwa M. Hassan, Brian Gardner, Liam Burke, Dearbhaile Morris, Arnoud H. M. van Vliet, Roberto M. La Ragione and Terry Smith. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- Comparative genomic analysis of multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* from South American camelids in Central Germany. Bélen González Santamarina, Michael Weber, Christian Menge and Christian Berens. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- HYBRID ASSEMBLY OF NANOPORE AND ILLUMINA READS – solving fragmented de novo assembly of resistant bacterial genomes. Peeter Laas, Age Brauer, Mado Remm, Tanel Tenson, Veljo Kisand . One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- Characterisation of OXA-48 plasmids in a diverse range of clinical and environmental Enterobacterales isolates from an urban location in Ireland. Mark Maguire, Carlos Serna Bernaldo, Natalia Montero Serra, Louise O'Connor, Niamh Cahill, Brigid Hooban, Kelly Fitzhenry, Aoife Joyce, Georgios Miliotis, Niall DeLappe, Genevieve Devane, Martin Cormican, Simone C Coughlan, Dearbháile Morris, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn and Liam P. Burke. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, Orvieto Italy and online.
- Genomic and resistance diversity of *Escherichia coli* from hospital inpatients and outpatients with urinary tract infection in Spain. Carlos Serna, Jose F. Delgado-Blas, Bosco R. Matamoros, Natalia Montero, Mario Pulido-Vadillo, F. Javier Fernandez-Favieres, Maria Garcia-Castillo, Rafael Cantón, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases 2022. Lisbon, Portugal.

- Oral presentation (R. La Ragione) – ECVM – Bari 2022 - Development of rapid diagnostics for the detection of pathogens and AMR
- Oral presentation (R. La Ragione) – ESGVM – Online - The application of LAMP technology for PoC diagnostics in veterinary practice.
- Oral presentations (R. M. La Ragione) on the development and use of Rapid diagnostic – MEVMA 2021, OHEJP conference 2022
- Antimicrobial Resistance and One Health. Bruno González Zorn. 5th International Caparica Conference in Antibiotic Resistance 2022, 05th – 08th September 2022, Caparica, Portugal.
- Comparative genomic analysis of multidrug-resistant Escherichia coli from South American camelids in Central Germany. Bélen González Santamarina, Michael Weber, Christian Menge, Christian Berens. Zoonoses 2022 - International Symposium on Zoonoses Research, 05.-07.10.2022, Berlin.
- Oral presentation (Marwa M. Hassan) – Rapid and culture-independent LAMP detection of AMR, the School of Veterinary Medicine Research Symposium, University of Surrey, 2022, 07.2022.
- Oral presentation (Marwa M. Hassan) - The applications of LAMP diagnostics for the detection of targeted AMR biomarkers, the Ryan Institute Centre for One Health Annual Conference 2022, 3.11.2022 – online.Oral Presentation (Arnoud H M van Vliet) - WORLDCOM: development of new tools for real-time detection of zoonotic bacteria and antimicrobial resistance, OHEJP Final School, 7 December 2022 (online)
- One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Diagnostic Workshop 2022: Mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications [<https://onehealthjep.eu/asm-satellite-workshop-2022/>].
- The workshop was hosted by the University of Surrey, led by Dr. Marwa M. Hassan (LEO) with Dr. Owen Higgins (NUIG) as deputy lead. The online workshop showcased the research that is currently undergoing in the field and illustrated a guidance to designing diagnostics for One Health applications. The workshop was very well attended with almost 100 registered participants and highly perceived with a satisfaction of 93% for the workshop in general and 91% for the hands-on practical component (about 25 participants).

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

We have developed One Health diagnostic techniques that can be utilised and implemented for testing on farm and from contaminated water sources. We have developed rapid and sensitive detection techniques that can identify key antimicrobial resistance markers to aid AMR screening, in the field, including in remote areas. A publication has been accepted, reporting the detection of specific AMR markers (CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15) using a portable diagnostics workstation developed for application in the field, and successfully tested using newly developed AMR assays, demonstrating the applications of rapid AMR diagnostic tests on-farm and in other remote locations. Additionally, we have developed a Smartapp algorithm to facilitate off-site detection, reporting of results and transfer to central cloud storage. The detection of AMR markers from animal faeces and from contaminated water samples has been submitted for publication and is currently under review. We have also contributed to a Journal of Medical Microbiology LAMP profile to feature the diagnostic technology, including its design and applications. Additionally, we led the organisation of the 2022 One Health EJP ASM Satellite Diagnostic Workshop as part of the OHEJP ASM showcasing the research that is currently ongoing in the area of

One Health diagnostics and providing guidance on designing diagnostics for One Health applications. The Smartapp detection of AMR markers from pig faeces samples will be also prepared as a manuscript for publication. Field application of the rapid assays developed within WORLDCOM by consortium members are ongoing. Application of rapid portable AMR molecular diagnostic tests will allow new insights in the transmission and prevalence of AMR alleles, currently indistinguishable, and can be expanded to new AMR targets and variants.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

The WORLDCOM project has been presented at national level in Ireland to the National Interdepartmental AMR Consultative Committee (with membership from government Departments of Health and Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine - DAFM). This committee are tasked with developing and implementing Ireland's 2nd National One Health Action plan on Antimicrobial Resistance 2021-2025 (iNAP2). Strategic Objective 5 of iNAP2 is to promote research and sustainable investment in new medicines, diagnostic tools, vaccines and other interventions. Completion of the WORLDCOM project has been identified as a strategic action under this objective, and project updates are communicated during committee meetings.

Recently, Prof. Dearbhaile Morris presented on WORLDCOM and other relevant projects at the "Building One Health Action under iNAP2" meeting co-hosted by DAFM, the Department of Health and the EPA, Dublin, June 23rd 2022.

Additionally, Prof. Bruno González Zorn presented different projects, including WORLDCOM, at the summer course "One Health Response and Antibiotic Resistance: New Approaches, New PRAN in Spain", July 20th 2022. This course included the Ministries of Health and Agriculture and the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products (AEMPS) involved in the new National Plan against Resistance to Antibiotics (PRAN). A strategic line of PRAN action is the control of antimicrobial resistance and the development of alternative prevention measures, including rapid diagnostic tests, which matches aims of the WORLDCOM project from a One Health perspective (including animal and human populations, as well as the environment). This will facilitate early investigation of emerging resistance and assist the prescriber in making decisions about the need for antibiotic treatment.

FLI has presented the WORLDCOM project internally to the GIZ, the German organisation for international cooperation, which is part of the Federal Ministry of Economic Growth and Development, in the context of their Global Programme for Pandemic Prevention and Response, One Health. Interest in the technology and its applicability, especially in countries with low and middle income, was voiced with a possible presentation in the context of an international lecture series on "Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) in international cooperation" in the future.

2.2.7 One Health impact

- The WORLDCOM consortium have developed new harmonised methodologies and protocols for on-site rapid and sensitive detection of AMR using LAMP. Some of the sample preparation methods and indeed the LAMP assays themselves or the experience gained in setting them up may be useful for One Health surveillance of AMR in resource-poor field settings.
- The project has also contributed to the harmonisation amongst partners of methods for sequencing and analysis of whole genome sequencing data, and generated a One Health database of resistant bacteria genomes which contributes to the knowledge base.

- The WORLDCOM project has been presented at national level in Ireland to the National Interdepartmental AMR Consultative Committee (with membership from government Departments of Health and Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine - DAFM). This committee are tasked with developing and implementing Ireland's 2nd National One Health Action plan on Antimicrobial Resistance 2021-2025 (iNAP2). Strategic Objective 5 of iNAP2 is to promote research and sustainable investment in new medicines, diagnostic tools, vaccines and other interventions. Completion of the WORLDCOM project has been identified as a strategic action under this objective, and project updates are communicated during committee meetings. Recently, Prof. Dearbhaile Morris presented on WORLDCOM and other relevant projects at the "Building One Health Action under iNAP2" meeting co-hosted by DAFM, the Department of Health and the EPA, Dublin, June 23rd 2022. Additionally, Prof. Bruno González Zorn presented different projects, including WORLDCOM, at the summer course "One Health Response and Antibiotic Resistance: New Approaches, New PRAN in Spain", , July 20th 2022. This course included the Ministries of Health and Agriculture and the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products (AEMPS) involved in the new National Plan against Resistance to Antibiotics (PRAN). A strategic line of PRAN action is the control of antimicrobial resistance and the development of alternative prevention measures, including rapid diagnostic tests, which matches aims of the WORLDCOM project from a One Health perspective (including animal and human populations, as well as the environment). This will facilitate early investigation of emerging resistance and assist the prescriber in making decisions about the need for antibiotic treatment. FLI has presented the WORLDCOM project internally to the GIZ, the German organisation for international cooperation, which is part of the Federal Ministry of Economic Growth and Development, in the context of their Global Programme for Pandemic Prevention and Response, One Health. Interest in the technology and its applicability, especially in countries with low and middle income, was voiced with a possible presentation in the context of an international lecture series on "Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) in international cooperation" in the future.
- The WORLDCOM project has facilitated a network to be built between the six OHEJP partners involved. Several partners have already begun to collaborate on new projects. For example University of Galway and UCM are collaborating on a Med-Vet-Net association short term mission in 2023 to investigate the One Health dissemination of aminoglycoside resistance plasmids in multidrug resistant Enterobacterales.

2.2.8 Data Management Plan

The DMP has been updated on the CDP tool with all currently available metadata for the project datasets. Six datasets are detailed in manuscripts that are soon to be published, and official referencing is not yet available. Zenodo links for these articles will be generated when their DOIs are available, added to the CDP tool and the data made public. The final DMP will then be extracted from the CDP tool and uploaded to Zenodo before the end of the project.

2.2.9 Future dissemination activities

Outputs from the WORLDCOM consortium will continue to be disseminated in 2023, through a variety of mechanisms, including:

- Peer-review publications;
- Conference Proceedings;
- Oral and Poster presentations at conferences;

- Workshops as well as other engagements and interactions with industry and other national and European stakeholder organisations and groups e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, and others.

2.3 JRP14-R2-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE

2.3.1 Consortium composition

The Full Force consortium was composed out of :

Principal Investigator	Pieter-Jan Ceyskens	Sciensano (BEL)
WP leaders	Henrik Hasman	SSI (DK)
	Muna Anjum	APHA (UK)
	Saria Otani	DTU (DK)
	Benoit Doublet	INRAE (FR)
	Stefan Widgren	PHAS (SW)
Task Leaders	Mike Brouwer	WUR (NL)
	Joost Hordijk	RIVM (NL)
	Laura Villa	ISS (IT)
	Marta Rozwandowicz	RIVM (NL)
	Jannice Schau Slette-meås	NVI (NO)
	Kristina Rizzardi	PHAS (SW)

In the course of this project, in total 53 scientists collaborated in the execution of the various WPs.

2.3.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

We are witnessing a rapid shift from microbiological to DNA-based surveillance of infectious diseases. Spurred by large European investments in hardware during the COVID-19 pandemic, national bodies and hospitals have become very proficient in DNA sequencing to (e.g.) rapidly identify virus variants. Across the EU, governments are now trying to harness these competencies, and to expand genomics-based surveillance to other infectious diseases for outbreak detection and transmission studies. However, when it comes to the **surveillance of antimicrobial resistance (AMR)** in bacteria, important technical challenges remain.

In surveillance of bacterial infections, the current methodology of EFSA, ECDC and NRCs is to compare them by their chromosomal genes. The reason is mostly technical, as the most widespread sequencing machines produce short-read data which can be easily mapped to these chromosomal regions. This is problematic for AMR with as many genes responsible for resistance located on mobile genetic elements outside the chromosome, like plasmids. Therefore, **our current surveillance systems fail to** (i) **Define** plasmid types, (ii) **Detect** and monitor emergent high-risk plasmids that contain multiple resistance genes, (iii) **Identify** ‘plasmid outbreaks’ in health-care or other settings, whereby linked cases of disease result from the spread of single plasmid in clonally diverse host cells, and (iv) **Determine** how AMR plasmids transmit across complex one-health landscapes, and the associated risks to human and animal health.

The goal of the Full Force project was to supply 17 EU partners with a **technological toolbox and hands-on training to perform plasmid sequencing**, and to apply this knowledge on existing bacterial collections. Over the course of the project, we were able to:

1. Deliver the consortium wet lab protocols on how to generate long-read sequencing data.

Construct and benchmark a common and open source bioinformatic pipeline, termed the Full Force Plasmid Assembler (FFPA). This allows harmonization of bioinformatic skills needed for plasmid sequencing.

2. Apply this methodology on a wide variety of study cases, focusing on:
 - a. Identification of the *K. pneumoniae* plasmidome, in the context of carbapenem resistance
 - b. The pESI megaplasmid, causing AMR in *Salmonella Infantis* throughout Europe
 - c. The discovery of a new type on IncZ plasmids
 - d. Variations in ESBL plasmids in *E. coli* isolated from horses
 - e. Expanding the mining from metagenomics datasets
 - f. Transmission of AMR in isolates among broilers.

Currently we have published 4 peer-review articles, while nine others are being drafted. However, the most important result of the Full Force is that it enabled harmonization of plasmid sequencing capacity across 17 public health and veterinary institutes. It provided an unprecedented amount of open access data on fully sequenced bacterial strains, which can be used in follow-up studies. It prepared our public health institutes for an 'AMR surveillance 2.0' based on plasmid data, and by doing so, it paved the way for detailed surveillance of AMR transmission in the next decade.

2.3.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Implementation of long-read sequencing

Lead: Henrik Hasman, SSI, DK

In task 1.1, through negotiations led by RIVM (NL), a consensus protocol (JRP-WP1.D3) for long-read sequencing was elaborated, based on the rapid library generation protocol from Oxford Nanopore. In short, it was decided to stick closely to each partner's routine methodology for DNA extraction, but add DNA/RNA shield (Zymo™) to preserve the integrity of the genomic DNA.

In task 1.2 and in an effort lead by Søren Overballe-Petersen, Henrik Hasman (SSI) and involving multiple members of their team, the Full Force Plasmid Assembler (FFPA v1.0) was created. This python script joins best-in-field tools to trim and QC short en long sequence reads (qcat, Trimmomatic), enables species identification through Kraken en performs either Nanopore and hybrid assemblies through Unicycler.

While this script works very well, it has been caught up by advancing technology and improving read quality of miniON flowcells. Therefore, a second version of FFPA (v1.2) was created, which is Flye-based (Figure 1). In laymen’s terms, the first version of FFPA used short Illumina™ reads to assemble

Figure 3. SNPs difference between various assemblies of E. coli bFR001 sequence data by EU public health institutes.

contigs, and long read to bridge these. Our new assembler uses the long reads to assemble the contigs, and the short reads only for polishing.

The great advantage of this package is that it can be locally installed in each institute, and enables harmonized plasmid assembly by non-expert scientist. This is of immense importance,

Figure 2. Two-day workshop on long-read sequencing and assembly of plasmids.

given the difficulties in recruiting dedicated bioinformaticians, and difficulties in

retaining training staff. The package was presented to all consortium members during a two-day training session organised by SSI.

Next, in Task 1.3, a proficiency test was prepared and shared with all the sequencing partners of the Full Force consortium. Here, each institution’s proficiency in SMRT sequencing of ESBL plasmids was to be submitted to the Full Force Owncloud repository and then compared to a set of specific reference material, in a process organised and coordinated by SSI. Due to the Covid-19 situation, not all project partners were able to deliver their sequencing results before the deadline (last data received May 2022), but initial work to prepare the final version of the reference material was carried out regardless of the partly missing data. The actual test material was discussed within the Full Force partners at the workshop in 2020 and after the workshop and it was decided to include 5 *Escherichia coli* strains from BfR (GER) as reference strains, since they had already been sequenced using Illumina, MinION and PacBIO technologies. However, a thorough retrospective assessment of these sequencing data revealed that the quality of the MiniON and PacBIO sequencing data was too low to actually produce definitive reference sequences for the benchmarking exercise. Therefore, at second round of PacBIO sequencing of the five test strains was initiated in March 2022 to deliver a high-quality benchmark

plasmid dataset. Unfortunately, these data did not lead to a definitive result and the benchmarking plasmids are now being manually assessed to produce the final benchmarking sequences before the end of the year. Based on

Figure 3. SNPs difference between various assemblies of E. coli bFR001 sequence data by EU public health institutes.

the first benchmarking plasmid (PT1 GoldStandard), some discrepancies between the data delivered

PART I		
Time	Monday	Tuesday
9.15 - 9.30	Logging in and Welcome	Welcome back
9.30 - 10.00	Introduction to FULL-FORCE	Finding the relevant data the FFPA results
10.00 - 11.00	Short presentation by all groups	Tips'n tricks for improving assembly quality + hand polishing
11.00 - 11.45	Presentation of wet-lab protocols (RIVM)	The proficiency test + Data sharing
11.45 - 12.30	Presentation of ONT - news and technical questions	The way forward in the Full Force project - Are we ready?
12.30 - 13.30	Lunch	Lunch
13.30 - 15.30	Introduction to FFPA and running the pipeline by yourself	Setting up Google cloud and installing FFPA (optional)

PART II		
Time	TBD	
9.15 - 9.30	Welcome back	
9.30 - 10.00	Introduction to the individual programs in FFPA	
10.00 - 11.00	Digging into the individual programs of FFPA part 1	
11.00 - 11.45	Digging into the individual programs of FFPA part 2	
11.45 - 12.30	Programs for handling miniON data	
12.30 - 13.30	Lunch	
13.30 - 14.30	Drylab - Running manual assembly in UniCycler	
14.30 - 14.45	Coffee	
14.45 - 16.00	Discussing optimization of FFPA to v2.0	

by the partners are seen (Figure 3) and the nature of these discrepancies will be analyzed and discussed at the final project meeting in December 2022 in Stockholm).

WP2. Case Studies

Lead: Muna Anjum, APHA, UK

In WP2, the acquired toolbox was applied in the (re-)sequencing of AMR strains from various research and surveillance projects, including EU projects such as EFFORT, COMPARE, ENGAGE and ARDIG, as well as national and EU surveillance activities for which short read sequences are available. By reconstructing full-length plasmids and chromosomes, new insights into transmission and evolution and AMR were pursued.

Task 2.1 The pESI megaplasmid in *Salmonella Infantis*

ISS (Laura Villa) coordinated a teleconference among task participants, in which it was decided to focus on the pESI virulence plasmid (Figure 4) of *S. Infantis* from animal and human origin. All task participants completed a metadata sheet, with epidemiological and microbiological data and 233 samples were selected from 1999 to 2020 for short-read sequencing. The selection of the 233 *S. Infantis* isolates by the task participants is based on maximal diversity in selection (year/source), assuring a distribution of isolates between human, animal and food origin and focusing on the presence pESI markers: SMX-TET-SUL resistance (NAL/CIP), and/or the presence of

IncFIB(pN55391), *tet(A)*, *sul1* and *dfrA14*. Eighty-seven *S. Infantis* isolates were sequenced from human and 146 isolates from animal, food and feed. WGS has been completed by M36 and sequences data have been shared on OwnCloud. Genomic analysis revealed that 39, 13 and 165 of 233 isolates carried *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *bla*_{CTX-M-65} and *tet(A)* gene, respectively. The *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-65} genes have been identified mainly in Italy, Belgium, and the Netherlands.

WGS analysis and characterization of the *S. Infantis* isolates was completed by July 2021, using different approaches. In depth characterization was carried out by using Resfinder and PlasmidFinder (database updated June 2021) to identify the resistance genes and plasmids replicons, respectively. Comparison of the genomes was performed by using Mash and SNPs analysis (reference: LN649235.1). In the SNPs tree, 8 clusters have been identified but no clear clusterization based on country or source was observed. In particular, *bla*_{CTX-M-1}-positive pESI plasmids were found in three clusters (I-II and IV), while pESI plasmids harbouring *bla*_{CTX-M-65} genes were all located in one distinct cluster (VII). Moreover, the *bla*_{TEM} gene was detected only in cluster V and cluster VII included only pESI negative isolates (Figure 5). Mash tree shows less variability, for the presence of a large and homologous plasmid (avg 300 kb).

It was decided that 55 isolates were chosen to be sequenced with Nanopore technology from 7 countries, using these criteria: 1) representative isolates for each country and source within each cluster identified in SPNs tree; 2) isolates showing identical or very closely related clusterization for SNPs analysis (indicating very homologous chromosomal content), but with different clusterization with Mash analysis. All task participants completed long-read sequencing of isolates by July 2022.

Figure 4. Genome map of the *S. Infantis* pESI megaplasmid.

Hybrid WGS analysis was carried out using Full Force Plasmid Assembler pipeline created by T1.2 of this project, and generated completed pESI-like plasmid sequences. In different pESI plasmid types

there were a clear association between *dfrA1 - bla_{CTX-M-1}* genes and *dfrA14 - ant(3'')-Ia - bla_{CTX-M-65}* genes. pESI-like plasmids carrying the *bla_{CTX-M-65}* gene were located in a well-defined cluster almost of human origin and they present a wide range of resistance genes conferring resistance to aminoglycosides, florfenicol, tetracycline and sulfamethoxazole. As previously reported (Alba et al., 2020), *bla_{CTX-M-65}*-positive pESI-like plasmids seem not to be related to the European *S. Infantis* population in the food chain and our findings confirm there is no evidence that are circulating in food-animal productions in EU countries. Importantly, this work showed that various pESI-like plasmids are associated with various reservoirs, showing that “*S. Infantis*” should not be generalized in current surveillance schemes.

Task 2.2 The plasmidome of Klebsiella pneumoniae

Through organised teleconferences, participants from Italy, France, Norway, Denmark, Sweden, The Netherlands and Portugal deemed that isolates with proposed high variation in genetic context as most

interesting to study. A pre-study using short-read sequences of *K. pneumoniae* isolates from the above-mentioned countries was performed by Antoni Hendrickx and his group at RIVM, to get an overview of the genetic diversity of strains isolated in Europe. Based on the results focus was set on genetically diverse isolates from three specific ST groups, ST15, ST147 and ST307, selected because they showed a high genetic diversity, were clinically relevant, represented a one-health perspective and contained several AMR resistance genes of interest.

A total of 328 isolates were sequenced and a hybrid assembly was performed using MinION long-read and Illumina short-read data, a total of 1574 plasmids were identified of which 1157 (74%) fully circularized. Preliminary analysis of the genetic relatedness of the circularised plasmids is shown in the figure 5. The plasmidome tree was generated using a k-mer based phylogenetic approach and clustered the plasmids well within their relative Inc-types. Further analysis of how each plasmid cluster was shared between isolates showed that although a majority of plasmids were shared regardless of isolate ST, there were clusters that were only shared by ST15 and ST147. Overall, these STs showed a greater genetic variability on the chromosome level as well, compared to ST307. These findings indicate that, for a reason yet to be determined, isolates belonging to ST307 are mainly adopting vertical gene transfer rather than horizontal as appears to be the case for ST15 and ST147, resulting in a less diverse genetic background for ST307.

Figure 5. Plasmidome tree of circularised plasmids, presence of Inc-types are depicted in blue and carbapenemase genes in red. An inset shows how plasmids within a cluster are shared in relation to a circular phylogenetic tree generated using only chromosomal sequences.

The results indicate that this study will greatly impact our understanding of how horizontal gene transfer affects the dissemination of carbapenemases and other highly relevant AMR genes in relation the genetic background of the plasmid backbone. Furthermore, there is a clear need to adapt AMR surveillance in Enterobacteriales to detect transmission events of relevant AMR plasmids. We have also observed several novel cases of plasmid evolution that particularly affect the dissemination potential of carbapenemases. From a one-health perspective, we can conclude that there are no boundaries between species, although isolates from animals are rarely carrying carbapenemases. Carbapenem resistance in *K. pneumoniae*, as also confirmed by this study, is mainly a human problem, and the focus for containing and reducing the burden of carbapenem resistance in *K. pneumoniae* should be on effective health hygiene measures and adequate use of carbapenems and third generation cephalosporins in human care. Although, given the lack of boundaries between human and animals, we cannot ignore the animal reservoir for spill over and further dissemination of resistance.

Task 2.3 Deciphering the IncB/O/K/Z group using long-read data

The main issue in the early phase of the project was the pre-classification of IncK/B/O/Z-positive plasmids by PlasmidFinder. To take this issue into account, the focus of the task was slightly extended by not only selecting isolates carrying CMY-2 on IncK plasmids, but also including isolates carrying other ESBL, AmpC or CPE's on plasmids only classified to the IncK/B/O/Z-group level. IncK plasmids carrying CMY-2 are of interest due to the association of CMY-2/IncK2 to poultry (Rozwandowicz et al). Broadening the focus to ESBL/AmpC/CPE on IncK/B/O/Z will allow to improve the classification of the plasmid group and to assess the evolutionary perspective of the plasmids within this group.

In this task, 410 *Escherichia coli* and *Shigella sonnei* isolates carrying an IncK/B/O/Z plasmid, from 10 European countries and Lebanon, were subjected to short read sequencing (Illumina). The isolates originated from humans (n=124), poultry (n=233), pigs (n=28), veal calves (n=19), dairy cattle (n=4) and the environment (n=2). The IncK/B/O/Z plasmids were further typed based on their RNAI and RNAII combined sequence and categorized into IncK1, IncK2, IncB/O and IncZ. IncZ plasmids were subclassified into IncZ1-7 based on their RNAI sequence (Moran et al) . Based on the classification, 78 IncZ and 59 IncK2 harbouring isolates were selected for long read sequencing (Nanopore).

Among the 410 isolates, IncZ was the most observed type within the IncK/B/O/Z plasmid group with 213 positive isolates (52%), followed by IncK2 (n=137; 33%), IncK1 (n=43; 10%) and IncB/O (n=17; 4%) (Figure 6).

Figure 7.: Phylogenetic tree of IncK/B/O/Z plasmids based on their combined sequence of RNAI and RNAII.

Figure 7: Phylogenetic tree of IncZ plasmids based on their RNAI sequence.

Based on RNAI, many IncZ plasmids could not yet be designated to a specific IncZ variant (IncZ1-7) (Figure 7). Classification of IncZ plasmids requires additional analysis and benchmarking. All animal sources only contained isolates from non-clinical samples and were labelled 'carriage isolates'. Human derived isolates were obtained from both carriage as well as clinical samples. IncZ was the most abundant plasmid type from the IncK/B/O/Z group among human derived isolates ($p < 0.05$). The occurrence of IncZ was also significantly higher in human clinical isolates compared to human carriage isolates ($p < 0.001$). Whether this has any biological significance cannot be determined yet.

Additionally, a phylogenetic analysis of IncK2 plasmids was performed. Although there was no obvious clustering based on the country or the origin of samples, there were three distinct clusters based on the plasmid sequence. Further analysis need to be performed to determine the basis of this differences. The high occurrence of IncZ plasmids in the current study was unexpected. It is hypothesized that this plasmid type has gone undetected in previous studies as IncZ plasmids are not detected by commonly used typing tools. Therefore the prevalence might have been underestimated. The significance of sequence-based variation within IncK2 plasmid group needs to be further examined. There is a need for better typing and surveillance of the IncK/B/O/Z plasmid group in order to determine their AMR-spreading potential.

Task 2.4 Plasmid epidemiology of ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae in horses.

Joost Hordijk and Marta Rozwandowicz (RIVM, NL) coordinated the group studying the epidemiology of plasmids in horses. Previous studies have shown a strong association of CTX-M-1 on *incH11* plasmids from horses (Dolejska et al, 2014; Valcek et al, 2021). Additionally, SHV-12 has been observed in association with MCR-9 in clinical samples from Sweden (Börjesson et al, 2020). To obtain a better insight in the distribution of these genes in European horses, these were the primary focus of this task. Nonetheless, *E. coli* isolates carrying other ESBL/AmpC's were also included to assess whether these could be relevant in transmission among horses as well. Additionally, potential determinants for co-selection will be taken into account. A previously described determinant for co-selection in horses is the presence of the *fos*-operon (Dolejska et al, 2014). The *fos*-operon encodes a fructooligosaccharide metabolic pathway, which may provide growth advantage for the bacterial host in sugar rich environments and thus act as a co-selector for resistance genes.

Figure 8: Mash tree from illumina data of the plasmidome of all isolates. Red bars indicate clusters of interest for Nanopore sequencing. 1: SHV-12 with IncI1 or IncX3, 2: CTX-M-1 with IncF, 3: SHV-12 with IncF, 4: CTX-M-1 with fos-operon, but no plasmid, 5: CTX-M-1 with IncN, 6: IncHI1 with CTX-M-1, -2, -14, -32 and SHV-12.

In this task, 264 *E. coli* isolates were available, submitted by 6 partners from France, Italy, Sweden and the Netherlands. The isolates were positive for CTX-M-1 (n=176), SHV-12 (n=29), CTX-M-2 (n=16), CTX-M-9 (n=4), CTX-M-14 (n=14), CTX-M-15 (n=13), CTX-M-32 (n=6), CTX-M-55 (n=1) and CMY-2 (n=5). A mash tree was constructed on the predicted plasmidome based on illumina reads. Six clusters were identified that harboured: isolates from multiple countries, contained CTXM-1 or SHV-12 which associated to the presence of a specific plasmid, or harboured a fos-operon that was not associated to IncHI1. This resulted in the following clusters (Figure 9): 1; SHV-12 combined with IncI1 and IncX3, 2; CTX-M-1 combined with IncF, 3; SHV-12 combined with IncF, 4; CTX-M-1 with a fos-operon, but no plasmid, 5; CTX-M-1 combined with IncN ,and 6; IncHI1 with CTX-M-1, -2, -14, -32 and SHV-12. In total 101 isolates were selected for Nanopore sequencing.

Although the data is currently still being processed and completed, preliminary analysis indicate that the fos-operon, which has been strongly associated with IncHI1 plasmids in horses, is also located on the chromosome, IncHI2 and IncF plasmids of multiple isolates from different countries.

Among the IncN plasmids, some plasmids show a high similarity.

The findings described above need be confirmed, expanded and the significance needs to be further examined.

Task 2.5 Benchmarking open access tools

One of the goals of the task was to investigate/benchmark relevant publicly available and in-house developed tools for mobile genetic element (MGE) typing. The agreement was to focus on plasmids since this is in line with the objective of the project. A questionnaire was sent to all partners in the consortium to determine which tools were used for detection of AMR genes, and plasmid detection and characterization. This list, together with a search for relevant publications in the PubMed database was used to get an overview of available tools. The results of the systematic search in PubMed was manually curated and tools were included if they met the following criteria:

- could be run on the command line with fasta-files as input
- tools and databases were updated regularly
- identified plasmid replicons and/or AMR genes

A total of five plasmid characterization tools and three AMR characterization tools were included. Each participating institution were assigned one or more tools to test. All institutions were instructed to use a specific version of both the tool(s) and database(s) they tested.

Institute	AMR tool (database)	Plasmid prediction tools (database)	
NVI	ResFinder	PlasmidFinder	mob-suite
INRAE	ResFinder	PlasmidFinder	
IZSLT	ResFinder	PlasmidFinder	
ANSES	AMRFinder plus	mob-suite	
Sciensano	ABRicate (AMRFinder plus)		
UU	AMRFinder plus	RFplasmid	Platon
PIWET	ABRicate (Resfinder, NCBI)	ABRicate (PlasmidFinder db)	Platon
INSA	ABRicate (Resfinder, AMRFinder plus)	ABRicate (PlasmidFinder db)	
APHA	ABRicate (AMRFinder plus)	RFplasmid	

A search in GenBank was performed to include all complete *E. coli* genomes where ONT MinION/GridION sequences were available for download. In total, 31 complete genomes with corresponding long read sequences were identified. The ONT sequences were assembled using the FULL_FORCE plasmid assembler (FFPA). Of the 31 genomes, nine were excluded due to poor assembly quality. Thus, all tools were tested using 22 complete *E. coli* genomes from GenBank and their corresponding FFPA assemblies. Each partner entered their results into a template file and uploaded to OwnCloud together with their raw data outcome. The processing of the results are ongoing between the NVI as task lead and APHA.

WP3. Applications in Metagenomics

Lead: Saria Otaki, DTU, DK

The development of culture-independent methods to detect, quantify and identify bacterial plasmids carrying antimicrobial resistance genes is greatly encouraged for future surveillance efforts. Here, we describe our work on (i) enhanced mining of existing metagenomics data, including those from the EFFORT and COMPARE projects, and correlate this to AMR-gene abundance, and (ii) development of diagnostic tools for direct identification of MGE/plasmid identifications from various sample types.

Task 3.1 MGE Analyses in metagenomics datasets

We constructed a database of MGEs detection from single isolates and metagenomics datasets. In research performed by Markus H K Johansson (DTU, DK), this databases was established and consists of ~4450 MGE sequences that originate from ~1050 different species. They contain several types of mobile elements:

- Insertion sequences (ISs) are among the smallest types of iMGEs. They are often composed of a transposase gene flanked by two inverted repeats (IRs). They are notable for their ability to modulate gene expression and promote mobility by forming composite transposons (ComTns), translocatable units (TUs) and in the case of elements from the IS26 family pseudo-composite transposons (PCTs).
- Unit transposons (Tns) are generally flanked by IRs and carry a transposase gene. They usually carry a resolvase gene, accessory genes and/or additional iMGEs. Miniature Inverted Repeats (MITEs) are non-autonomous ISs or Tns that have undergone deletions in their core genes but have retained the IR and can form ComTn-like structures.
- Integrative Conjugative Elements (ICEs), Cis-Mobilizable Elements (CIMEs) and Integrative Mobilizable Elements (IMEs) are larger iMGEs capable of conjugation. They can either conjugate independently or be co-mobilized by conjugation of other elements. These elements carry many accessory genes and other MGEs.

This work provides the groundwork for implementation of bioinformatics pipelines for quantification of MGE in metagenomics datasets, and in determining the presence and abundance of MGEs in public and *de novo* generated metagenomics datasets.

Task 3.2 Culture-Independent methods for plasmid identification

DTU lead efforts to establish a protocol to extract plasmid sequences from complex biomes (*e.g.*, sewage and faeces). The protocol allows plasmid DNA isolations, degrades linear gDNA and enriches circular elements in metagenomics samples. In short, plasmid DNA isolation was performed on individual sewage pellets (420 mg) using Plasmid Purification Mini Kit (Qiagen, Cat No./ID: 12123) following the manufacturer's instruction with the following modifications: protein precipitation with P3 buffer mixture was incubated on ice for 20 minutes, elution buffer QF and EB buffer were preheated at 65°C prior applications, and the DNA pellet washing step was done using ice-cold 70% ethanol after isopropanol precipitation. LyseBlue dye for cell lysis indication was added, and all buffer volumes were adjusted to sewage pellet weight. The plasmid DNA pellet was dissolved in 25 µl EB buffer for 1 hour at room temperature. Linear chromosomal DNA was reduced by Plasmid-Safe ATP-Dependent DNase (Epicentre, USA) treatment for 24 hours at 37°C. The DNase was inactivated at 70°C for 30 minutes. Circular DNA was enriched using phi29 DNA polymerase (New England Biolabs, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions, similar to as previously described.

To validate the methodology, ARGs, and predicted bacterial host genera, were investigated to understand sewage plasmidome dynamics. Combined with ongoing efforts of the Global Sewage Project, a total of 24 sewage samples yielded 58,429 circular elements carried genes encoding plasmid-related features. A single (yet diverse) cluster of 520 predicted *Acinetobacter* plasmids was predominant among the European sewage water. Our results suggested a prevalence of plasmid-backbone gene combinations over others. This could be related to selected bacterial genera that act as bacterial hosts. These combinations also mirrored the geographical locations of the sewage samples. Our functional domain network analysis identified three groups of plasmids. However, these backbone domains were not exclusive to any given group, and *Acinetobacter* was the dominant host genus among the theta-replicating plasmids, which contained a reservoir of the macrolide resistance gene pair *msr(E)* and *mph(E)*. Macrolide resistance genes were the most common in the sewage plasmidomes and were found in the largest number of unique plasmids. While *msr(E)* and *mph(E)* were limited to *Acinetobacter*, *erm(B)* was disseminated among a range of Firmicutes plasmids, including *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus*, highlighting a potential reservoir of antibiotic resistance for these pathogens from around the globe.

WP4. Modeling

Lead: Stefan Widgren, SVA, SW

The final objectives were to address: i) gaps in quantitative knowledge on the spread of pAMR which will be essential to direct future focused research, ii) insight in the uncertainty around the effect of measures reducing pAMR prevalence in the food production chains, and iii) identification of key elements in the production chains to mitigate the risk of human exposure.

Task 4.1 Design for a model for AMR transmission

As first task, parameterisation and design of a transmission spread model of pAMR in the simulation framework SimInf has been performed. Estimating model parameters from observed data is a major challenge in stochastic modelling. However, it is a necessary and critical step to evaluate a model's explanatory power. Parameterization is preferably conducted within a Bayesian framework. In this task, functionality to perform Approximate Bayesian computation (ABC) was developed and added to the SimInf R package. ABC is a simulation-based computational approach for parameterisation of complex problems, for example, in epidemiology (McKinley et al., 2018). The SimInf software is open

source, and the new ABC functionality is publicly available as planned. The most recent stable version of SimInf is available from the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) at <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=SimInf>. The development version is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/stewid/SimInf>.

For studying transmission of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* in Dutch broiler production chain, we developed two different types of transmission models in SimInf that described the observed time-related decline in prevalence during a production round: one with time-dependent decline in susceptibility and one with partial immunity to phylogenetic groups. Both models incorporated the environmental contamination effect between production rounds and within flocks. The parameter values, including transmission rate and recovery rate, were estimated by using the newly added ABC functionality in SimInf. This modelling work was conducted as a Master thesis by Furusawa (2022) at the Utrecht University. Work is ongoing to write a manuscript and submit a publication based on that work.

Task 4.2 Design for a model for AMR transmission

Secondly, we applied the above models to broiler production chain and further added the effect of mixing eggs and chicks from different origins and adjusted the size of a flock and the number of farms to the Dutch situation. Both models were able to describe the observed dynamics within and between the production stages equally well and estimate the outcome of interventions quantitatively. Both indicated that improving farm management to eliminate the bacteria from the environment was the most effective intervention, which made the influence of the intervention on the outcomes robust. According to our models, chicken meat consumption was not a major risk factor for human carriage of the bacteria.

2.3.4 Project self-assessment

Like any research project which kicked off in January 2020, the project planning has been hit hard by the Covid-19 pandemic. Due to restrictions imposed by all EU governments, suspension of research activities during lockdown and reorientation of many consortium members towards Covid-19 surveillance, many Full Force activities were postponed for at least six months. The basis of this project was supposed to be an on-site, three day workshop on plasmid sequencing, held at the State Serum Institute (SSI, DK), followed by a proficiency test to analyse each partner's capacity to perform SMRT sequencing. It goes without saying that all this has caused significant delays in deliverables and milestones, with the most important result being that most data of the case studies has not yet been published thus far. Nevertheless, as silver lining, the Covid pandemic also led to a massive investment in genome-based surveillance and minION-related hardware, through national and European funding like HERA.

With this in mind, the Full Force project definitely has had a great role in the roll-out of long-read sequencing in the participating institutes. More specifically, we (1) delivered protocols on how to generate long-read sequencing data, (2) constructed and benchmarked a common and open source bioinformatic pipeline to harmonize bioinformatic skills needed for plasmid sequencing, and (3) applied this knowledge on various study cases which are described in this document, generating sufficient data for at least five more papers to be submitted in 2023.

During the project, great differences in commitment were observed between the various partners. For example, BfR was very much absent from all meeting and discussions due to absence of the point of contact. Likewise, Fernando Esperon left his job in INIA (SP), leaving our consortium without a replacement and even the official redraw of this institute from the project. On the other side of the spectrum, both RIVM and PHAS stepped up, and even expanded the project beyond the set targets (e.g., in the work on IncZ plasmids and enabling open access data). This is a general weakness of the OHEJP setup, in that insufficient funds are available to recruit dedicated scientist on the project.

Instead, with 17 partners, we had to rely on available expertise and people, making it hard to enforce deadlines.

Approaching the end of the project, three important things remain. First, all generated data will be published, an effort led by PHAS. Second, at least eight (!) manuscripts still need to be published (see case studies and section 7). And finally, we need to convince EU bodies of the added value of plasmid sequencing for an 'AMR surveillance 2.0'. This was during the Closure meeting in Stockholm on December 5th, and will be done on many informal occasions afterwards. During the closure meeting, both ECDC and EFSA emphasized their interest in plasmid surveillance, and the added value of the Full Force project in capacity building. With this technology, more detailed case definitions will be possible in the near future. The broad implementation will require further roll-out in all member states. Lastly, and probably the most lasting outcome of this project is that it brought together scientist which are in love with plasmids, and who are spending many hours unravelling them. I have no doubt that this bond will last far beyond the end of the Full Force project.

2.3.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential , the Zenodo reference, other comments	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP14-0.D1	FULL FORCE Kickoff/Progress meeting report	M27	M27	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4275887	8
14	D-JRP14-0.D2	12 month report OHEJP Full Force	M36	M42	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4896736	8
14	D-JRP14-0.D3	Data sharing in Full Force - recorded webinar	M27	M27	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4277545	3
14	D-JRP14-WP0.D4	Full force annual meeting report	M48	M48	Public; https://zenodo.org/deposit/5793860	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential , the Zenodo reference, other comments	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP19-WP0.D5	Financial and activity report Y4	M48	M48	Public; https://zenodo.org/deposit/5793868	8
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D1	Teleconference to assess required protocols and infrastructure	M25	M26	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/3733393	8
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D2	Teleconference to discuss proposed protocols and infrastructure (follow-up)	M26	M26	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/3759335	8
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D3	Completion of final protocol for SMRT sequencing	M27	M34	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4277521	2
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D4	Invitation to workshop delivered to all participating institutions	M28	M27	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/3693741	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential , the Zenodo reference, other comments	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D5	Completion of workshop organization plan including selection of course material	M29	M35	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4290698	8
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D6	Selection of proficiency test data	M32	M35	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4290707	8
14	D-JRP14-1.D7	Delivery of analysis results of proficiency test by partners to SSI	M39	M42	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4896743	8
14	D-JRP14-2.D1	Submission of sequence- and metadata of longitudinal samples at ENA hub	M33	M42	Public ; https://zenodo.org/record/4905398	8
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D2	Submission of sequence- and metadata of cross-sectional samples at ENA hub	M58	M59	Merged with D-JRP19-WP2.D7 (see below)	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
14	D-JRP14-2.D3	Submission of sequence- and metadata of K. pneumoniae samples at ENA hub	M33	M42	Public ; https://zenodo.org/record/4896755	8
14	D-JRP14-2.D4	D-JRP14-WP2.4	M33	M42	Public ; https://zenodo.org/record/4896772	8
14	D-JRP14-2.D5	Submission of sequence- and metadata of horse-related samples at ENA hub	M33	M42	Public ; https://zenodo.org/record/4896789	8
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D6	List of relevant publicly available and in-house developed tools.	M58	>M60	Merged with D-JRP14-WP2.D12/D18, a single benchmark article will be prepared in 2023	5
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D7	Submission of long-read sequencing data of longitudinal samples to ENA hub	M50	M59	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/7323905	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D8	Submission of long-read sequencing data of cross-sectional samples to ENA hub	M50	M50	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/6602217	5
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D9	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>S. Infantis</i> and <i>S. Kentucky</i> to ENA hub	M50	M50	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/6602367	5
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D10	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> samples to ENA hub	M54	M59	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7319716	5
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D11	Submission of long-read sequencing data AMR horse samples to ENA hub	M50	M50	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/6602379	5
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D12	Report on MGE tool testing for MGE characterization using full-length genomes	M58	>M60	Merged with D-JRP14-WP2.D6/D18, a single benchmark article will be prepared in 2023	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential , the Zenodo reference, other comments	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D13	Paper on plasmid dissemination and evolution from longitudinal studies.	M54	>M60	See publication plan	
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D14	Paper on plasmid dissemination and evolution from cross-sectional studies.	M54	>M60	See publication plan	
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D15	Paper on the role of MGEs on in the EU wide dissemination of K. pneumoniae	M54	>M60	See publication plan	
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D16	Paper on the epidemiology of plasmids in AMR in horses	M54	>M60	See publication plan	
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D17	Paper on the role of MGEs on the spread of Salmonella Infantis and S. Kentucky across reservoirs	M54	>M60	See publication plan	
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D18	Recommendation of publically available tools for MGE analysis	M54	>M60	Merged with D-JRP14-WP2.D12/D18, a single benchmark article will be prepared in 2023	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential , the Zenodo reference, other comments	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP14-3.D1	Database construction tailored at MGEs	M36	M36	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4305711	3
14	D-JRP14-3.D2	Protocol for plasmid DNA extraction from environmental samples	M34	M42	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4896791	2
14	D-JRP14-3.D3	Publication of the validated method for plasmid DNA extraction on environmental samples.	M40	M42	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4896722	1
14	D-JRP14-WP3.D4	Report on the comparison of available pipelines for metagenome analyses	M58	>M60	Merged with D-JRP14-WP2.D6, a single benchmark article will be prepared in Y5	5
14	D-JRP19-WP3.D5	Protocols for real time PCR detection of up to 32 ARGs in singleplex format.	M48	-	Due to the departure of task leader Fernando Esperon (INIA, SP) from the Full Force consortium, this task has not been completed.	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 3) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
14	D-JRP19-WP3.D6	Report on the abundance and associations of species, AMR and MGE	M54		Public; https://zenodo.org/record/7319669	
14	D-JRP19-WP3.D7	White paper on the performance of MINion sequencing for direct identification of AMR genes in field samples	M54	-	Due to the departure of task leader Fernando Esperon (INIA, SP) from the Full Force consortium, this task has not been completed.	
14	D-JRP14-4.D1	First collection of type-materials (MGEs and strains) to be shared between involved partners	M30	M42	10.5281/zenodo.44896802	3
14	D-JRP14-WP4.D2	Refine additional collection of type-materials (MGEs and strains) to be shared between involved partners	M42	M42	Strain collection described in same deliverable report 10.5281/zenodo.44896802	3
14	D-JRP14-WP4.D3	Set-up of protocols for measuring plasmid persistence in complex microbiota and small-scale testing	M46	M43	Protocol described in same deliverable 10.5281/zenodo.44896802	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP19-WP4.D4	Report on conjugative transfer and maintenance of IncHI1-CTX-M plasmids in different E. coli genetic backgrounds	M54	>M60	Will be merged with D-JRP19-WP2.D16 in a single report	
14	D-JRP19-WP4.D5	Report on comparative analysis of horizontal transfer efficiency of different plasmid Inc groups carrying mcr genes	M54	>M60	Will be merged with D-JRP19-WP2.D13 in a single report	
14	D-JRP19-WP4.D6	Report on specific plasmid-host associations of pKpQIL plasmids and transposition of blaKPC transposon unit in KPC-producing K. pneumoniae strains	M54	>M60	Will be merged with D-JRP19-WP2.D15 in a single report	
14	D-JRP19-WP4.D7	Report on host range capacity of pESI plasmid from S. Infantis and provided fitness advantages	M54	>M60	Will be merged with D-JRP19-WP2.D17 in a single report	
14	D-JRP19-WP4.D8	Report on mechanisms of persistence of different AMR plasmids in diverse faecal and sewage bacterial communities	M54	M59	Public ; https://zenodo.org/record/7319669	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential , the Zenodo reference, other comments	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP14-W5.D1	Source code of the implementation of a SimInf model designed for pAMR transmission.	M34	M36	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/4305750	1
14	D-JRP14-WP5.D2	A report on quantification of horizontal vs. vertical transmission of AMR	M39	M57	Public https://zenodo.org/record/4925761	1
14	D-JRP14-WP5.D3	A report on using ABC methodology for parameter inference of a SimInf model designed for pAMR.	M50	M59	Public; https://zenodo.org/record/7319681	5
14	D-JRP19-WP5.D4	A report on human AMR exposure based on SimInf and sQMRA calculations	M54	>M60	See publication plan	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
14	M-JRP14-M1	Creation of specific data hubs in ENA AMR hub	M27	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M2	A teleconference or physical meeting on horizontal vs. vertical AMR transmission	M27	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M3	Selection of MGEs and host strains to be studied in T4.2	M28	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M4	A teleconference or physical meeting on input/output relationship between SimInf and sQMRA	M29	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M5	Publication of first version of data management plan	M30	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M6	3-days workshop on SMRT sequencing event	M30	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M7	Shipment of proficiency test data and strains	M32	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M8	Sharing of protocols, recipient- and host-strains, molecular tools	M33	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
14	M-JRP14-M9	An implementation of a SimInf model designed for pAMR transmission to be studied in T5.1	M33	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M10	Final selection of longitudinal samples for SMRT sequencing	M34	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M11	Final selection of cross-sectional samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M12	Final selection of K. pneumoniae samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M13	Final selection of S. enterica Infantis and Kentucky samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M14	Final selection of horse-related samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M15	Analysis of proficiency test data by all partners	M46	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
14	M-JRP14-M16	Individual reports of proficiency test sent to partners	M48	No	>M60
14	M-JRP14-M17	Successful adaptation of plasmid purification protocol to field samples	M36	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M18	Selection of additional MGEs and host strains based on first outcomes of WPs-2 and -3.	M40	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M19	Successful implementation of SMRT sequencing of field samples	M42	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M20	A parameterised SimInf model designed for pAMR transmission to be studied in T5.2	M42	Yes	
14	JRP14-M21	Construction of Isogenic CIPR S. Kentucky ST198 strains carrying different SG11-related elements	M45	No	Change of scope – focus on the pESI plasmid epidemiology of Salmonella Infantis

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
14	M-JRP14-M22	Transfer frequency data of representative IncHI1-CTX-M1 plasmids	M52	No	Change of scope – no conjugations planned for IncHI plasmids so far. No impact on other tasks.
14	M-JRP14-M23	Data on conjugative transfer of pESI plasmid from <i>S. Infantis</i> to other <i>Salmonella</i> serovars and other microbial species	M52	No	Change of scope – no conjugations planned for pESI plasmids so far. No impact on other tasks.
14	M-JRP14-M24	Finalised hybrid assemblies of longitudinal samples	M54	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M25	Finalised hybrid assemblies of cross-sectional samples	M54	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M26	Finalised hybrid assemblies of <i>S. Infantis</i> and <i>S. Kentucky</i> isolates	M50	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M27	Finalised hybrid assemblies of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> isolates	M53	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M28	Finalised hybrid assemblies of AMR horse samples	M50	Yes	
14	M-JRP14-M29	Transfer frequency data of mcr plasmids of different incompatibility groups	M52	No	Change of scope – no conjugations planned for mcr plasmids. No impact on other tasks.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
14	M-JRP19-M30	Data on the role of short-chain fructooligosaccharide metabolism in InChI1 plasmid maintenance	M54	Yes	
14	M-JRP19-M31	Data on plasmid-encoded fitness advantages of pESI to the host bacteria	M54	No	Change in scope: no fitness experiments planned due to departure of task leader in T4.3. . No impact on other tasks.

2.3.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Diaconu EL, Carfora V, Alba P, Di Matteo P, Stravino F, Buccella C, Dell'Aira E, Onorati R, Sorbara L, Battisti A, Franco A. Novel IncFII plasmid harbouring bla_NDM-4 in a carbapenem-resistant Escherichia coli of pig origin, Italy. J Antimicrob Chemother. 2020 Dec 1;75(12):3475-3479. doi: 10.1093/jac/dkaa374.</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/4451840#.YZPKcWDMJM0</p>		YES		YES (processing charges unknown)
<p>Kirstahler P, Teudt F, Otani S, Aarestrup FM, Pamp SJ. A Peek into the Plasmidome of Global Sewage. mSystems. 2021 May 26:e0028321.</p> <p>doi: 10.1128/mSystems.00283-21</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/5543288#.YZPKXmDMJM0</p>		YES		YES (processing charges unknown)
<p>Teudt F, Otani S, Aarestrup FM. Global Distribution and Diversity of Prevalent Sewage Water Plasmidomes. mSystems. 2022 Oct 26;7(5):e0019122. doi: 10.1128/msystems.00191-22.</p>		YES		YES (processing charges unknown)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://zenodo.org/record/7319669				
<p>Börjesson S, Brouwer MSM, Östlund E, Eriksson J, Elving J, Karlsson Lindsjö O, Engblom LI. Detection of an IMI-2 carbapenemase-producing <i>Enterobacter asburiae</i> at a Swedish feed mill. <i>Front Microbiol.</i> 2022 Oct 21;13:993454. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2022.993454</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/7244094</p>		YES		YES (3000 € approx..)
<i>An inter-lab comparison using ONT MinION for characterization of antimicrobial resistance genes and plasmids.</i>	Under preparation			3500€ (NVI, jannice.schau-sletteameas@vetinst.no)
<i>Plasmids without borders: An insight into the plasmidome and accessory genome K. pneumoniae in Europe.</i>	Under preparation			3500€ (PHAS, kristina.rizzardi@folkhalsomyndigheten.se)
<i>The variation of the Salmonella Infantis pESI plasmids in a One Health setting</i>	Under preparation			3500€ (Laura Villa, ISS)
<i>The Full Force Plasmid Assembler (FFPA) for harmonized plasmid assembly for improved AMR surveillance</i>	Under preparation			3500€ (Henrik Hasman, SSI)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<i>IncHI2 plasmids are responsible for SHV-2 carriage in E. coli samples isolated from horses</i>	Under preparation			3500€ (Joost Hordijk, RIVM)
Long-read sequencing identified novel IncZ—type plasmid in routine surveillance samples.	Under preparation			3500€ (Joost Hordijk, RIVM)
Increased understanding of the sufflon region of IncI1 plasmids using complete plasmid sequencing	Under preparation			3500€ (Mike Brouwer, WUR)
Transmission models of ESBL-producing Escherichia coli in Dutch broiler production chain	Under preparation			1500€ (Stefan Widgren, SVA)

Additional output

Apart from the deliverables listed above, two poster presentations featuring data of the Full Force project have been submitted/performed :

- Minori Furusawa et al. (2022). Transmission models of ESBL-producing *E. coli* in the broiler production chain. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6581036>. Presented at the society for Veterinary Epidemiology and Preventive Medicine (SVEPM) conference March 23-25 in Belfast.
- M. Rozwandowicz et al. (2022). Occurrence and diversity of IncZ plasmids. Plasmid Biology Conference, Toulouse, 2022.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

- The Full Force Plasmid Assembler (FFPA) is a software which can be readily implemented in public health and veterinary labs (as well as in clinical labs), and will provide standardization in plasmid assembly and interpretation in the context of plasmid outbreaks.
- Applications of the work in metagenomics could directly be implemented in waste water-surveillance of AMR, which has come very much to alive upon the Covid pandemic.
- Our modelling efforts suggested that thorough cleaning and disinfection between production rounds in broiler farms can reduce ESBL-producing *E. coli*, which might be of interest in those involved in veterinary Infection Prevention and Control actions.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Current surveillances has been organised based on what we can measure, not necessarily what we want to measure. The evolution from MLST to cgMLST enabled great improvements in genome-based surveillance of outbreaks, but are ill suited to track plasmid and AMR dissemination. Therefore, we have invited EFSA and ECDC to our Closure meeting in Stockholm, to discuss how advances in long-read sequencing and plasmid dissemination can be incorporated into future surveillance systems.

2.3.7 One Health impact

The transmission of AMR is mediated by mobile genetic elements. However, even our most advanced genome-based surveillance systems fail to detect and monitor high-risk plasmids across species and sectors. In the Full Force project, we supplied 17 EU partners with a **technological toolbox and hands-on training to perform plasmid sequencing**, and showed the added value of this is diverse case studies. The impact of this project is the following:

- For the international stakeholders (ECDC, EFSA), this project shows the added value of incorporating surveillance of mobile genetic elements in current programs. For example (Case 2.1), we show that there are distinct, sector-specific types of pESI plasmids associated with *Salmonella Infantis* isolates. Therefore, we invite these supranational bodies to include plasmid surveillance into their current monitoring of AMR in Europe. A meeting will these organisations was held in Stockholm, on December 5th2022. During this meeting, both

stakeholders emphasized their interest in plasmid surveillance, and the added value of the Full Force project in capacity building. With this technology, more detailed case definitions will be possible in the future. The broad implementation will require further roll-out in all member states.

- National stakeholders should recognize the need for continuous, structural investment in sequence-based surveillance technologies. Although the cost for long-read sequencing is comparable to current methodologies, underlying investments include sufficient GPU/CPU power and data storage capacities. Many of the Full Force consortium members are NRL in their country, and therefore in direct contact with their competent authority. Data provided in the various case studies (e.g. the identified IncZ plasmids among human, but not animal *E. coli*) will help them in convincing them of the added value of the technology.
- This project brought together 17 institutes from 10 countries, which are all devoted to plasmid-based surveillance. Most of the in total 53 scientist who participated in the research did not know each other at the start of the project. Through online and (thankfully) offline meetings, many new relationships were started. Moreover, the concept trainer-trainee which was introduced during the SMRT workshop organised by SSI strongly improved personal interactions between colleagues with similar functions in other countries. At the time of writing this report, this already resulted in a scientific publication which was not foreseen at the conception of the project¹, with at least two more to come.
- We did not have interactions with the industrial sector.

2.3.8 Data Management Plan

We plan a coordinated effort to submit all sequence data to ENA. A Full Force ENA project will be created, with all case study data (WP2) under various umbrella projects. Each institute has a data manager for the full force data. The CDP was updated in December 12th, and uploaded to Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/record/7428640>).

2.3.9 Future dissemination activities

Every time a novel publication will be out (see scheme in Section 7, nine papers being drafted), we will contact the PMT to announce it via their social media channels.

¹ Börjesson S, Brouwer MSM, Östlund E, Eriksson J, Elving J, Karlsson Lindsjö O, Engblom LI. Detection of an IMI-2 carbapenemase-producing *Enterobacter asburiae* at a Swedish feed mill. *Front Microbiol.* 2022 Oct 21;13:993454.

2.4 JRP15-R2-AMR2.1-FED-AMR

2.4.1 Consortium composition

Project Lead: Werner Ruppitsch,

Deputy Project lead and

Scientific Manager: Manuela Caniça

Administrative Manager: Karin Rainer

JRP15-	Title	Leader	deputy
WP1	Project Management and Communication	Ruppitsch	Cabal Rosel
WP1 T1	Scientific Management		
WP1-T1.1	Coordination of sampling, laboratory experiments and building a database, QM		
WP1-T1.2	Webinars (WP1.4 in Annex Deliverables) bimonthly in proposal (start proposal M25, Annexes M30)		
WP1-T1.3	Project Meetings		
WP1-T2	Administrative Management Consortium agreement, Monitoring of scientific progress, risk mitigation measures		
WP1-T3	Data and protocol management plan (T3) - not as pressing (email from OHJEP)		
WP2	Field experiments: Determination of the naturally occurring ARG background load and microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments	Caniça	Cabal Rosel
WP2-T1	Assemble list of sampling compartments and points. Determination of test areas representative for the European regions (North, West, East, South).		
WP2-T2	Establish common protocol for sampling and data analyses to facilitate comparability of the results between European test areas (North, West, East, South) and local sampling locations		
WP2-T3	Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in selected test environments, compare between ecosystems, characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media		
WP2-T3.1	Shotgun sequencing and bioinformatic analyses of AMR genes and MGEs		
WP2-T3.2	Gene enrichment with gene capture probes		
WP2-T4	Quantification of clinically relevant ARG tested by qPCR and or qPCR arrays		
WP2-T5	Identify naturally transformable bacterial species in tested compartments (NGS)		
WP2-T6	Asses clonal/lineage diversity in selected ARB species		

WP2-T7	Isolation and assessment of the quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in tested environments, seq. Comparison		
WP3	Elucidating the role of <i>Clostridium difficile</i> as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and its linkage between human and non-human (zoonotic) reservoirs	Oleastro	Persson
WP3-T1	Epidemiological survey of zoonotic ribotypes across participant countries		
WP3-T2	WGS and AMR characterization of human and non-human <i>C. difficile</i> isolates		
WP3-T3	Evaluation of the extent of genetic overlap between human and non-human <i>C. difficile</i> lineages		
WP3-T4	<i>C. difficile</i> / AMR dissemination between the human, animal and the environment: pig farm as a proof of concept		
WP4	Determination of the selection pressures in the tested compartments of human, animal and environmental ecosystems	Brandtner	Gajda/Gbylik-Sikorska
WP4-T1	Selection of essential antimicrobials to be quantified in the tested compartments (published antibiotic consumption data, farmers' questionnaire, personal experience, expert interviews (veterinarians))		
WP4-T2	Water: Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in aqueous matrices (water)		
WP4-T3	Manure: Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in manure		
WP4-T4	Faeces: Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in faeces		
WP4-T5	Soil: Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in soil		
WP4-T6	Quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil		
WP4-T7	Measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples gathered across participants countries		
WP 5	Identification of environmental conditions modulating transformation frequencies in soil microcosms and an in vitro porcine gut model (poGutMo) (laboratory studies)	Chambers	La Ragione
WP5-T1	Establish basement levels of HGT in the model organism (<i>E. coli</i>) arising from transformation in the poGutMo		
WP5-T1.1	Ability of <i>E. coli</i> to acquire AMR to serve as a donor DNA		
WP5-T1.2	Determine the optimal growth parameter for cultivating <i>E. coli</i> strains within the gut model		

WP5-T1.3	Rates of transformation calculated by taking samples from the gut model and plating on agar plates supplemented with the appropriate antibiotics		
WP5-T1.4	DNA transfer rates via bacterial conjugation will be calculated using the endpoint method		
WP5-T2	Evaluate conditions that drive HGT and the emergence of AMR via transformation (WP 4 & 6 will suggest drivers)		
WP5-T2.1	Iterative evaluation of candidate drivers (antibiotic, herbicide, cation) of HGT evaluated in the gut model - round 1		
WP5-T2.2	Iterative evaluation of candidate drivers (antibiotic, herbicide, cation) of HGT evaluated in the gut model – round 2		
WP5-T2.3	Conjugation-mediated HGT between the clostridial donor and recipient strains within the gut model determined		
WP5-T3	Effect of different environmental conditions on the expression of competence genes in <i>E. coli</i> determined using soil microcosms		
WP 6	Probabilistic and mechanistic models of the links between antimicrobial usage in animals, AMR in the environment, and the risks for public health.	Lo Iacono	Chambers
WP6-T1	Build a probabilistic mathematical model of the emergence of AMR in target bacteria and the relative contribution of transformation and conjugation to ARG acquisition (afterwards: Factors influencing the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment)		
WP6-T1.1	Data integration, Annotation and Association Analysis (afterwards: Systematic review: environmental factors associated with AMR)		
WP6-T1.2	Data integration, annotation and association analysis Y4		
WP6-T1.3	Data integration, annotation and association analysis Y5		
WP6-T2	Develop mechanistic models to address key questions regarding the spatio-temporal changes observed in microbiological communities		
WP6-T2.1	Modelling microbial communities		
WP6-T2.2	Modelling microbial communities II		

2.4.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

FED-AMR project aimed to understand the role of free extracellular DNA (exDNA) in dissemination of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) over ecosystem boundaries along the food/feed chain in one-year crop growing season. As transformation is an important driver for genetic plasticity of bacterial genes and genomes and natural transformation does not require physical contact between donor and recipient bacteria we hypothesized that this may facilitate antibiotic resistance genes (ARG) crossing ecosystem barriers and invading new habitats compared to HGT by conjugation.

The WP1 aims were met and were mainly based on project coordination, including scientific and administrative management, organization of regular activities, facilitation of cooperation between the WPs and integration of their outputs and results.

WP2 aimed to quantify and assess microbial and AMR diversity with next generation sequencing (metagenomics) in different compartments of food production chain, during one-year-crop growing season. In particular we were interested in studying the role of extracellular DNA in the dissemination of AMR genes. We had 476 samples from six European countries (Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Ireland, Portugal, United Kingdom), distributed in four EU regions from up to eleven compartments along the food/feed chain. Both extracellular free DNA (exDNA) and total DNA were subjected to 16S rDNA sequence-based microbial profiling to measure the bacterial diversity. The Phyla in exDNA are dominated by Proteobacteria and Firmicutes. The principal component analysis suggests a separation between three groups of compartments: 1) soil 2) crops, feeds and drinking water 3) farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure and wastewater, which may show e.g. a smaller shifting between the microorganisms found globally in the compartments of these three groups. No significant differences were detected between soil amended with manure and without it, which may be due to an history of exposure to manure in the preceding years. ExDNA and total DNA were also subjected to target enrichment (equivalent to gene capture) to characterize and quantify ARGs in the different compartments. The analysis started with samples obtained from the wild animal compartment where we detected ARG conferring resistance to about 30 antibiotic classes, where β -lactams, tetracyclines, aminoglycosides and fluoroquinolones were the most prevalent. In the same compartment, we identified e.g. 11 ARG-types conferring resistance to fluoroquinolones. As for the competent bacteria the highest loads were observed in feed (exDNA), groundwater (total DNA) and field drainage (total DNA). We can conclude that bacteria known to be able to take up extracellular DNA are present in all environmental compartments and may serve as receptors for ARGs that are harboured on free exDNA. We also characterized genetically (WGS-based typing) and phenotypically (antimicrobial susceptibility testing) more than 500 cultivable bacteria. In all countries, isolates retrieved from wastewater, pig manure and pigs were those carrying more ARGs, including extended-spectrum beta-lactamases, but also ARGs associated to antimicrobials used usually in animal husbandry such as aminoglycosides, tetracyclines or sulfonamides. However, AMR data in our study (including those from metagenomics) are not thought to be a direct result of antimicrobial drug use, because 'globally' there is no direct linkage of AMR (associated with the antibiotics from the classes identified in WP4) across the various compartments and countries, therefore, there will be other risk factors (to be identified yet, if achievable).

WP3 aimed at elucidating the role of *Clostridioides difficile* as a pathogen/ARGs transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and the genetic overlap between human and non-human zoonotic reservoirs. At the farm level, dominant clones in environmental compartments associated with pig production were identified, suggesting a transmission chain between compartments involving these animals. The results contributed to unveil the role played by animal and environmental reservoirs within the *C. difficile* epidemiology. The studies assessing genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages at different One Health settings support the zoonotic relevance of *C. difficile* and its presence in novel reservoirs.

In WP4 we aimed at determining the selection pressures (antimicrobials, elements and herbicides) for antimicrobial resistance in environmental ecosystems (soil, water, faeces, manure, plants, feeds). We analysed samples collected by WP2. The highest concentrations of antimicrobials were detected in manure and faeces and are likely to select bacteria resistant to these compounds. The results of WP4 will be used for an impact evaluation of the analysed substances on the prevalence and quantities of ARGs encoded on extracellular DNA in exposed bacterial populations residing in the tested environmental compartments.

In WP5 we successfully established and optimised (pH, temperature, flow rates and volumes) an in vitro model of the pig large intestine using pig faeces and conditions to represent the natural complex

microbial community of the gut. We demonstrated sufficient growth and maintenance of an E. coli J53 strain to serve as a recipient of exDNA to study the impact of antibiotics and/or trace elements on the efficiency of natural transformation within the gut. Also, a soil microcosm setting was created using non-manured agricultural soil and *Acinetobacter baylyi* ADP1 as receptor of extracellular DNA. The results showed a repression of the mRNA levels of two competence genes (*comA* and *dprA*) during the first 6 hours after spiking if the microcosm was incubated at 35°C compared to 20°C. These results indicate that elevated environmental temperatures may diminish the ability of naturally competent soil bacteria to take up extracellular DNA and may reduce AMR spread by bacterial transformation.

WP6 focused on generating a protocol for a systematic review on factors influencing the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment and on formulating and validating a mathematical model for the dynamics of microbial communities. The protocol was registered in a public repository and accepted in Dec/2022 and published in Jan/2023 in an international journal (*Environment International*: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107707>). With respect to the task on modelling microbial communities, we have formulated a new model and validated it with in-silico data purposely developed.

FED-AMR has a societal, policy and economic impact, as well as scientific impact through cross-sector communication of data contributing to the advancement of science. This project used the true concept of One Health, namely with an important environmental component (farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure, air of pig barns, feeds, crops, soil, water).

2.4.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Project Management and Communication

WP1-T1 Scientific Management (M25-M60)

The scientific manager (SM) Manuela Caniça and the project leader (PL) Werner Ruppitsch as well as their deputy Adriana Cabal Rosel have worked continuously to ensure the scientific soundness of the project. Budget and strategy changes (i.e. Ares genetics involvement) were discussed and voted by the FED-AMR Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) and Advisory Board (AB) members in 2021 (Y4). The scientific management has worked closely with the administrative management team consisting of Karin Rainer (project manager, PM), Krista Rathhammer (deputy PM) and Nadine Peischl (project administrator).

WP1-T1-ST1.2 Webinar forum and Skype meetings for instant scientific interactions (M29-M60)

Regular scientific and administrative exchange between the project partners was facilitated and encouraged through consistently scheduled monthly online meetings. These TCs included a short update of all WPs and plenary discussions as well as administrative input. Minutes of these meetings were shared with the project partners for approval. A definitive version incorporating all suggestions received was distributed via email and published on the internal workspace on the website (<https://fed-amr.ages.at>) hosted by AGES. In addition, regular online meetings were done between members of one or more WPs, in order to discuss strategies, overarching tasks and to exchange knowledge. Such meetings last the whole duration of the project. Furthermore, webinar forums were established for which recognized experts were invited to give talks on scientific topics of relevance to the project consortium.

WP1-T1-ST1.3: Project Meetings (M25-M52)

The kick-off meeting of this project was held face-to-face at the AGES facilities in Vienna in Y3. The second consortium meeting had to be postponed to April 2022 (Y5) due to the travel restrictions. This meeting took place at INSA for two full days, on the 21st and 22nd of April 2022, in a hybrid format (24

in-person participants) and with the option of joining online (12 participants). All six WPs made an update on the data already achieved, followed by discussion, namely with the aim of clarifying questions about several scientific issues, reorienting the analysis of these data, and talking about respective publications. Each WP leader was responsible for organizing and coordinating the work during the time allocated to the respective WP, ensuring the involvement of all participants. At the end, the next steps were discussed both in plenary and WP-dedicated sessions. Particular attention was given to the outputs and the importance of leaving a scientific legacy available and useful to the scientific community, stakeholders and policy makers in the field of the project: AMR spread. Between the 1st and 2nd meeting there was an interim meeting online, in December 2021, where an overview of all work already performed was presented by each WP leader and colleagues. The project closing meeting was held online in December (Y5) in order to honour the projects budget requirements.

WP1-T2: Administrative Management (M25-M60)

The coordination of joint activities in the frame of the FED-AMR project mainly coordinated by AGES. Additionally, each partner appointed an Administrative Representative who was in direct contact with the AGES Administrative Manager (AM), Karin Rainer. The administrative team at AGES and the Scientific Manager (SM) defined a risk management strategy for the project. The overarching risk management strategy initiated in year 3 of the project and was put in place by the AM and the SM, in consultation with the FED-AMR Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) to ensure that adverse situations were properly handled along the course of the project, which was being highlighted in the Data Management Plan.

WP1-T3: Data and Protocol Management (M25-M58)

A first version of the Data and Protocol Management Plan was already delivered on M34. In year 4, the DMP was updated in the new OHEJP data management platform CDP, regarding details of FED-AMR data throughout the project, with information provided to the leader and deputy leader, by task leaders on their datasets. In addition, a metadata file was generated for all samples collected in WP2. This file facilitated the introduction of metadata in the CPD platform and data analysis. The final version of the DMP will be delivered by end February 2023 upon agreement with the OHEJP coordination team and will be uploaded to Zenodo.

WP2: Field experiments: Determination of the naturally occurring ARG background load and microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments (M25-M60)

Overall, WP2 aimed to answer four main questions: which ARGs and how many of them are present in each compartment, and which and how many bacteria are present in the compartments. The tasks below have been answering these questions through a large amount of results obtained derived from the sequencing (16S, gene enrichment, WGS).

WP2-T1: Assemble list of sampling compartments and points. Determination of test areas representative for the European regions (North, West, East, South) (M25-M30)

In this task, the countries involved in the WP2 sampling elaborated first a list of sampling compartments and points. Sample collectors integrated four EU regions: East (Czech Republic, Poland), West (Austria, Ireland and Great Britain), North (Estonia and Norway), and South (Portugal). In addition, a sample timeline by collectors, a sample distribution list, and the transportation and conservation requirements for the samples was generated by WP2. Unique identifiers by compartment and time point were given to all samples. The outcome of this task is summarized in D-JRP15- FED-AMR-WP2.1 and the corresponding annexes.

WP2-T2: Establish common protocol for sampling and data analyses to facilitate comparability of the results between European test areas (North, West, East, South) and local sampling locations (M25-M33)

In this task, common protocols for the collection of different sample types, their processing and cultivation, DNA extraction (extracellular and total), antimicrobial susceptibility testing, whole genome sequencing and metagenomics sequence analysis, were generated by WP2. They supported the harmonization of testing procedures and enhanced comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe. The outcome of this task is also summarized in D-JRP15- FED-AMR-WP2.1 and the corresponding annexes.

WP2-T3- Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in the selected test environments (metagenomics). Compare microbial and ARG diversity between ecosystems and over ecosystem boundaries. Characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media (M27-M54)

The WP2 « analysis team » finalised the statistical analysis on the 16S rDNA microbial profiling data. The whole genome sequencing-based analysis of all consortium isolates is also finished, as well as the susceptibility testing. Results derived from these analysis were presented at several international conferences. At the moment, the group continues to distribute the analysed data in different possible manuscripts in accordance with the objectives. This task is finished.

Regarding the characterization of cultivable bacteria by WGS-based typing, more than 300 animal and environmental bacterial isolates belonging to clinically-relevant species, such as *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *S. enterica*, *S. aureus*, *E. faecium* and *E. faecalis* were obtained after sample cultivation by the six participating countries. Also, nearly 200 strains belonging to other bacterial species, mostly environmental, were gathered by the partners. The first 300 strains were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility and paired-end sequenced was carried out on Illumina devices at each institute. Afterwards, raw genome sequences (FASTQ) were forwarded to 2-AGES for genome assembly, species re-identification, species-specific assessment of the genetic relatedness by core genome MLST using publicly available schemes, extraction of the sequence types of the classical MLSTs, and extraction of ARGs and virulence genes using CARD and VFDB databases, respectively. Afterwards, the assemblies (FASTA) were shared with 33-NVI for further analyses. The Mobile Element Finder was used to identify mobile genetic elements (MGE). Also, an in-house pipeline (Ellipsis (<https://github.com/NorwegianVeterinaryInstitute/Ellipsis>)) was used for detection of plasmid replicons and for re-extraction of ARGs and VGs in all FASTA files; ARGs were determined using ResFinder, virulence genes using VirulenceFinder, and plasmid replicons using PlasmidFinder and mob-suite. The analysis of associations between ARGs and the compartments and countries in which the respective strains was isolated was performed. The identified MGE will provide more information about the possible dissemination via horizontal gene transfer of ARGs and VGs between clones of the same or different species, countries and compartments.

cgMLST-based analysis showed intra-country isolate clusters of the same species, but no multi-country cluster was detected. However, for several strains, the same ST was detected in more than one country, especially among the *E. coli* isolates. In all countries, isolates retrieved from wastewater, pig manure and pigs were those carrying more ARGs, including extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL), but also ARGs associated to antimicrobials usually used in animal husbandry such as aminoglycosides, tetracyclines or sulfonamides.

Two manuscripts have been already published on phenotypical and WGS-based characterization of 89 environmental bacteria from Austria belonging to clinically-relevant species. As for Portugal, ARG in isolates from the *Enterobacter cloacae* complex related with non-susceptibility to β -lactams, quinolones, fosfomycin and macrolides as well as several MGEs were identified. Phylogenetic analysis identified two main clusters with closely related strains from different compartments. Almost all

isolates were non-susceptible to colistin and resistant to at least one carbapenem due to carbapenemase production, and were obtained from three compartments (river water, sludge, and effluent from a stabilization pond). These results were presented at ECCMID 2022 and were part of an MSc thesis defended and published in 2022. Results from the WGS-based characterization and the phenotypical tests carried out by Czech Republic, UK, Estonia, Ireland and Portugal (other species different from *E. cloacae*) are also ready and we have given potential titles with the future manuscripts that will be drafted with those results.

WP2-T3-ST1- Shotgun sequencing and bioinformatic analyses of AMR genes and MGEs (M37-M58)

The FED-AMR partners agreed on the evaluation and comparison of ARGs using a novel methodology based on gene capture probes (equivalent to gene enrichment, see subtask WP2-T3.2 for more information). This methodology allowed us to analyse the ARGs and MGEs, and dispense with both conventional shotgun metagenomics (this subtask) and qPCR (task WP2-T4) for the collected samples. So, this subtask does no longer exist in a methodological point of view, but the aim persisted, and results came from WP2-T3.ST2.

WP2-T3-ST2- Gene enrichment with gene capture probes (M31-M48)

To ensure that target enrichment could be used instead of PCR and conventional shotgun metagenomics to analyze all the exDNA and/or total DNA obtained from the WP2 samples, we conducted a small pilot experiment comparing the results obtained for a pair of samples with shotgun metagenomics and target enrichment. As target enrichment showed superiority in detecting more ARGs, especially in the exDNA, the FED-AMR Supervisory Board agreed on the increased sensitivity and novelty of the use of target enrichment exclusively as a better approach to detect and quantify ARGs in the different compartments and EU countries.

Afterwards we performed the DNA extraction (exDNA and/or total DNA) and quality control of all samples within WP2 that were further enriched and sequenced. Results involved the generation of two large datasets grouping all the ARGs obtained in each of the samples by marker class and mechanism of resistance. These two large datasets included two different approaches to analyse gene enrichment data: 1) the one offered by the company ARES Genetics and 2) the one described by Lanza *et al.* (2015). WP2 considered the second approach as the best option, since it had been previously published and showing the benefit. Intensive data cleaning had been carried out in both cases, for both 16S and AMR data. Regarding AMR, we encountered some irregularities in the results provided by Ares Genetics (that did metagenomics for all the consortium) as did not contain the annotation of the information in the final format for a direct analysis, so it took more time (e.g. the ARG names, particularly regarding their classification into different AMR groups, which necessitated a manual revision of the ARGs names and classification). Statistical analyses have been completed using several R packages by the “analysis team”. These include evaluation of the ARGs diversity, among others, in each of the samples, DNA types (extracellular vs. total), compartments and countries. The correlation between all WP2 and other WPs results needs to be completed. In parallel, we are drafting a first paper including the wildlife results for both exDNA and total DNA from samples collected in Austria, Ireland and Portugal, which can also be considered a martyr document from where we will be able to correct and fine-tune the analysis and writing of the papers on the other compartments, related to metagenomics.

WP2-T4 Quantification of clinically relevant ARG tested by qPCR and or qPCR arrays (M34 – 43)

As explained in the 12M report of Year 3, the detection of ARG through qPCRs was eliminated from the project. The Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) contributed to this decision-making process. However, the quantification of relevant ARGs in the analysed compartments was performed, inferring from the number or reads that cover each detected ARG.

WP2-T5- Identify naturally transformable bacterial species in the tested compartments (NGS) (M42-M56)

To identify naturally transformable bacteria in the compartments tested, a query database containing bacterial species proven to be able to take up extracellular DNA under naturally occurring environmental conditions was generated. For this purpose, a literature search for naturally competent bacteria covering the years from 1994 to 2021 was performed using defined search strings, with PubMed and SCOPUS as reference databases. Only hits describing the development of competence in bacteria under physiological conditions were eligible for entering the query database. The bacterial species names retrieved from literature were annotated and the appropriate phylogenetic levels were allocated according to the taxonomic classification system as laid down in SILVA 138.1. For the annotation and classification of 16S NGS data generated in the frame of the project the same version of SILVA database was employed. The resulting collection of observed bacterial species in FED-AMR samples was used as the searched database. This search database was checked for the presence of bacteria sampled in the query database using the level “genus” as qualifier. The research questions were: 1. Are naturally transformable bacteria present in FED-AMR isolates? 2. If yes, in which compartments? 3. Which competent bacteria are to be found in these compartments?

The query database contained 171 entries (= bacterial species) with empirically obtained evidence for their natural transformability. The searched database contained the 16S sequence information of 488 samples and 5763 different bacterial species. Naturally transformable bacteria were identified in almost all samples (except for a sample from soil and from a farmer – both of exDNA as sample type), in all sample types and environmental compartments. The overall most prevalent taxons encountered in FED-AMR samples were *Pseudomonads* and *Sphingomonads*. *Lactobacilli* were found in a significantly lower number of samples, but showed highly abundant genus-specific sequence reads. Samples from wildlife (exDNA), farmers (ex/total DNA) and crops (ex/total DNA) carried the lowest abundance of competent bacteria. The highest loads with competent bacteria could be observed in feed (exDNA), groundwater (total DNA) and field drainage (total DNA). We can conclude that bacteria known to be able to take up extracellular DNA are present in all environmental compartments and may serve as receptor for ARG encoded on free exDNA.

The detailed statistical evaluation of the obtained results focus on country-specific comparisons and the comparison with *in silico* alignment studies based upon comEC homologies.

WP2-T6- Assess clonal/lineage diversity in selected ARB species (M43-M52)

In the original task WP2-T6, phylogenetic trees using 16S amplicon sequencing and the shotgun sequencing data were intended. However, since the number of samples that the consortium analysed was significantly higher than the initially planned, the methodological approach was modified and no phylogenetic analysis was done using the raw data (FASTQ). See deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6 for additional information.

Really, as well as the resistome referred above, the microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments from all partners was evaluated by characterising all 16S V1-V9 regions through 16S rRNA metagenomics and target gene enrichment. Thus, after cleaning up the data, all OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) with no reads, and correcting some errors we ended up with 573646 OTUs in 476 samples. We then proceeded to create a Phyloseq (R package) object using the available data in the literature (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013).

We divided the samples into 11 compartments: Crop – crops harvested in the agricultural fields; Feed – proceed feeds for animal consumption; Farmers – faeces samples from farmers; Pigs_Barn – faeces from farm pigs; Manure – faeces of pigs and other organic material used to fertilize the soil; Wild_animals – faeces samples of wild animals like deal, hares, but also sheep and goat; Soil_Fs_Ms_Ctrl_Bline – soil samples from forests, meadows and agricultural fields before being cultivated or fertilized; Soil_field_noMan – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized without the

use of manure; Soil_field_Man – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized with of manure; water_DRG – water samples from drainage, river and ground water; water_WTP – water samples from waste treatment plants.

Overall, water_DRG is the only compartment exclusively with samples that did not pass the quality control. If we separate the data sample type we will have 232 samples and 1725 genera for extracellular DNA samples and 223 samples and 1810 genera in total DNA samples. Phyla in extracellular and total DNA samples, are dominated by *Proteobacteria* and *Firmicutes*. Most of the Phyla are present in both extracellular and total DNA samples. *Acidobacteriota*, *Chloflexi* and *Gemmatimonadota* have higher reads in soil samples while *Bacteroidota* and *Firmicutes* have higher reads in farmers, pigs, manure and wild animals samples. Concerning alpha diversity, we explored the data with and without rarefaction (a procedure commonly used in microbial diversity analysis, but which may lead to loss of data). Our samples present high variability in the number of reads: 16 to the sample with least reads and 939820 for the sample with most reads. 72449 and 90698 for median and mean respectfully. Pielou's evenness index does not seem to be greatly affected by the total number of reads in each sample, both Chao1 and Shannon are. According to the rarefaction curves we identified that most of the samples approach the asymptote, which signalled that sampling depth was enough to capture the diversity in the sampled populations. The compartments that are significantly different from each other in terms of alpha diversity were determined both in the extracellular and total DNA samples. Most of the compartments were significantly different. From a total of 55 possible comparisons between compartments, we have 42 agreements extracellular and total DNA samples when rarefication was used and 45 agreements when rarefication was not used. This suggest that there are some punctual differences concerning alpha diversity between the extracellular and total DNA. Note that soil samples from forests, meadows, controls and baselines are significantly different than the other soil samples in extracellular DNA, but not in total DNA. In both types of samples, soil with and without manure did not present significant differences, which may be due to a history of exposure to manure in the preceding years (ARG "memory effect").

To perform ordination analysis we used CLR (centered log ratio) transformation that allowed us to use Aitchison distance. In both extracellular and total DNA samples PC1 separate soil samples from everything else, PC2 and PC3 separate the other compartments. The first three principal components explain 41.6%, 8.9% and 4.0% of the data variability in extracellular DNA samples and 45.2%, 7.3% and 5.3% in total DNA samples. PC2 and PC3 will separate crops, feeds and water samples from farmers, pigs and manure, with wild animals samples bridging these two clusters. We used multiple differential abundance methods to help ensure robust biological interpretations and we choose ALCOM-BC, ALDEx2 and the Wilcoxon test with CLR transformation. For the remaining compartments, the conclusions are not yet clear.

Regarding OUT's in both extracellular and total DNA samples, the compartments are divided into two main groups that separate the soil samples from everything else, as in the ordination analysis. The remaining samples are further divided into two groups: one with the mammals, another with the crops, feeds and water_DRG. Water_WTP and manure seem not to cluster with any other compartment. Concerning the separation for the OUT's we see that there are separations, which are common to the extracellular and total DNA and others that are specific. In both types of samples, we note large OUT's clusters exclusive from soil, others that are exclusive from manure and others exclusive for water_WTP. Following the group order in the dendrogram for the OUT's in the total DNA samples, we have a first cluster shared by mammals and manure, another that is shared by mammals, water_WTP, manure and soil samples. These are followed by a cluster shared by every compartment. For other clusters it is difficult to assign a characteristic. The total DNA samples seem to have a cluster that is shared by wild_animals, crops, feeds and soil samples that is not as evident in the extracellular DNA heatmap.

Overall, the data suggest: A) Separation between three groups: 1) soil; 2) crops, feeds and drinking water; 3) farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure and waste water. B) No significant difference was

detected between soil in fields with and without manure. C) Differences were detected between extracellular and total DNA samples in: farmers, feeds and soil. D) Very few samples of water that also did not pass quality control. This preliminary analysis may show a smaller shifting between the microorganisms found globally in the compartments of these three groups, suggesting, however, a greater (or more complex?: need to deepen the analysis further) interplay between the microorganisms of the compartments that correspond to farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure and wastewater.

WP2-T7- Isolate and assess quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in the tested environments. Sequence comparisons (M34-M52)

The extracted extracellular free DNA from all the collected samples was used according to the generated protocols based on previous literature available. Gene enrichment was performed as described in WP2-T3.

We first evaluated the quality of the extracted total and extracellular free DNA. Qubit measurements of double stranded DNA were done for all the samples. Further quality assessments of the samples were done as explained in D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6. In addition, we removed from the analysis all those genes with a coverage below 0.5. For a total of 475 samples 7252 different ARGs were detected.

Most samples presented good amount of Transcripts Per Kilobase Million (TPMs). Only 21 out of 475 had an insufficient number of reads. TPMs in the samples by country were analysed. Overall, the number of TPMs for the exDNA was similar to that of the total DNA and the ARGs with the highest TPM sums corresponded to the tetracycline ARG *tetW*, which was present in 343 samples, and mutations in ribosomal subunits. As for the number of ARGs in each compartment, there was variations among compartments, DNA type and countries.

After this overview on ARGs quantity and diversity the more complex statistical analyses is clarifying the differences between compartments, countries and DNA type regarding ARGs, their antibiotic class and resistance mechanism.

All ARG results provided by Ares Genetics were analyzed and grouped according to AMR mechanisms, as follows: antibiotic inactivation, target alteration (replacement and alteration), target protection and efflux impermeability; in the group called 'others' we have mainly resistance genes to heavy metals and biocides, as well as virulence genes (adherence, motility, chemotaxis, etc). The first specific analysis on ARG concerns the wildlife compartment; we found that the ARGs obtained in samples from this compartment confer resistance to about 30 antibiotic classes, where the most prevalent were mainly the following classes (in descending order): β -lactams, tetracyclines, aminoglycosides and fluoroquinolones. Among β -lactams the prevalent resistance mechanism was the β -lactamase production [mostly class A β -lactamases, including ESBLs (e.g. encoded by *bla_{CfXA}*), class C, namely PMA β (plasmid-mediated AmpC β -lactamases; e.g. encoded by *bla_{CMY}*, *bla_{ACT}*, *bla_{ACC}*, *bla_{MIR}*, *bla_{DHA}*, *bla_{ADC}*), and class D β -lactamases, such as carbapenemases (e.g. encoded by *bla_{OXA}*-types)]. In the same compartment, we identified genes encoding resistance to aminoglycosides through the action of aminoglycoside phosphotransferase (e.g. *aph(2'')-IIa*, *aph(3')-Ia*, *aph(3'')-Ib*), and 11 ARG-types conferring resistance to fluoroquinolones, which included episomal (such as *qnrB*, *qnrD*, *qnrE*) and chromosomal (*oqxA*, *gyrA*, *gyrB*) mutated gene variants. We also identified resistance to heavy metals, such as (more prevalent in descending order) to copper, mercury, tellurium, arsenic, nickel-cobalt, chromium and silver.

AMR data in our study (including those from metagenomics) are not thought to be a direct result of antimicrobial drug use, because 'globally' there is no direct linkage of AMR across the various compartments and countries associated with the antibiotics from the classes identified in WP4, therefore, there will be other risk factors.

Comparison of microbial and antimicrobial resistance gene diversity across ecosystems and along ecosystem boundaries, as well as discussion of results are included in the manuscripts under preparation (see Chapter 7).

WP3 Elucidating the role of *Clostridioides difficile* as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and its linkage between human and non-human zoonotic reservoirs

WP3- T1 Epidemiological survey of zoonotic ribotypes across participant countries

WP3 participants aimed at investigating the epidemiology of zoonotic *C. difficile* through the identification of zoonotic types of *C. difficile* across the WP3 partner countries by generating an epidemiological survey of zoonotic ribotypes (RTs). Based on this survey, a database was constructed comprising of genomic data (WGS reads) and associated metadata on potential zoonotic toxigenic *C. difficile* isolates from various sources (human, animal and environment). Metadata included demographic and epidemiological data, as well as strain type (namely RT), toxin profile and AMR profile, when available. Discrimination between zoonotic and non-zoonotic types was based on *C. difficile* RTs and other genetic markers described in the literature. In addition, participating partners started sampling campaigns in order to enrich the collection of *C. difficile* isolates available from different sources, more specifically from diverse animal, environmental and food sources (FED-AMR isolates). Harmonized protocols for *C. difficile* isolation from samples of animal, environment and food origin were developed and used by WP3 partners, for the several sampling campaigns.

WP3-T2 WGS and AMR characterization of human and non-human *C. difficile* isolates

A dataset of *C. difficile* isolates from zoonotic RTs (RT002, RT033, RT078 and RT049) covering different origins was selected from existing strain collections of WP3 and external partners as well as the FED-AMR isolates. The phenotypic (AMR) and genomic characterization (toxin profile, RT, WGS) was performed for the collection isolates not previously characterized and for all the FED-AMR isolates.

WP3-T3 Evaluation of the extent of genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages

The changing epidemiology of *C. difficile* reflects a well-established and intricate intercommunity transmission network. With rising numbers of reported community-acquired infections, research should focus on the role of alternative reservoirs. Within WP3-T3, several studies were conducted with that purpose. 1) A study aiming to evaluate the role of companion animals as possible reservoirs for human cases of infection was carried out, involving 335 faecal samples from dogs and 140 samples from cats in Portugal (INSA), collected during 2021 and 2022. The phylogenetic analysis revealed close genetic overlap between animal and human isolates involving main RTs present in both species (RT106 and RT014/RT020), supporting the possibility of clonal interspecies transmission or a shared environmental contamination source. Pets' isolates presented high rates of AMR to antibiotics that are important for human therapy: clindamycin (27.9%), metronidazole (17.1%) and moxifloxacin (12.4%). The study showed that companion animals could be reservoirs of toxigenic and antimicrobial resistant human-associated *C. difficile* isolates or vice-versa. Additionally, this study contributed important data on the genetic proximity between *C. difficile* isolates from humans and companion animals. This could help to clarify the role of animal reservoirs in the establishment of community associated transmission networks and alert for potential public health risk (one poster in the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022; one manuscript submitted to *Frontiers in Public Health*, in review). 2) Another study targeted pig isolates vs human isolates in Denmark (SSI): the phylogenetic analysis revealed close genetic overlap between pig and human isolates within two clusters (RT078, RT066), indicating either direct transmission or a shared intermediate reservoir. The antimicrobial resistance gene (ARG) profile within each human/veterinary cluster confirmed similarity and relevant AMR carriage. This study showed that food chain animals could serve as reservoirs of toxigenic and antimicrobial resistant human-associated *C. difficile* isolates (one poster at ECCMID (Lisbon 2022); one manuscript in preparation). 3) Similarly,

a study on *C. difficile* in New World Camelids, performed on 43 alpaca-/llama-husbandries in Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt and Thuringia in 2019 (Germany, FLI) showed a positivity rate of 16% (7/43) at farm-level; different RTs and toxin profiles were found, including the hypervirulent, zoonotic ribotype RT078. This study showed that New World Camelids are potential reservoirs for *C. difficile* and represent a previously unknown factor for zoonotic transmission in the One Health (OH) context (manuscript in preparation). From this study, a genomic analysis to assess genetic overlap between isolates from RT002 from different sources (human, food/environment, animals, including New Camelids) is being undertaken (one manuscript is scheduled). 4) Lastly, a study focused on food was performed (Germany, BfR), whose goal was to investigate strawberries from self-picking fields, since these often lead to the consumption of unwashed fruit directly on the field, posing a potential risk for *C. difficile* infection. The ratio of samples with *C. difficile* was low (2%). The only detected isolate from a self-picking field belonged to non-toxigenic RT051 that is not commonly associated with human CDI. Overall, the risk of *C. difficile* infection via consumption of unwashed strawberries appears to be low but not impossible (1 poster at the One Conference 2022).

While performing this task, a MGE database for *C. difficile* (MGE-Database for *C. difficile*) was constructed for the identification of transposons, plasmids and phages (FLI) in WGS data; this MGE database was tested and validated by WP3 partners.

Overall, these studies supported the high zoonotic importance of *C. difficile* (RT078, RT106, RT014/020, RT002) and its presence in novel reservoirs, and showed genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages at different OH settings.

WP3-T4. *C. difficile* / AMR dissemination between the human, animal and the environment: pig farm as a proof of concept

In order to assess *C. difficile*/AMR dissemination between humans, animals and the environment, studies were conducted on samples from four countries (two HOALs from Portugal and Austria, one agricultural facility from Estonia, single compartments from Ireland). The results obtained allowed to perform a classification of pig farm compartments according to their role in the epidemiology of *C. difficile*, which was identified in all the following ecosystems: pig barn (faeces), manure (pig), wild animals, soil (agricultural fields), river water, ground water, wastewater treatment plant and air. In addition, in each HOAL, a different *C. difficile* RT (RT033, RT078 and RT049, respectively) was dominant, reflecting well-established transmission chains and a resilient source. The presence of those clones in compartments associated with the pig production unit suggests a transmission chain involving these animals and contributes to unveil the role played by animal and environmental reservoirs in *C. difficile* epidemiology.

The results obtained from the HOAL in Portugal (INSA) are a good example of these events. The study aimed to establish a *C. difficile* transmission network involving all the OH components using a pig farm as a proof-of-concept, as well as to assess the diversity of potential zoonotic types and to unveil genomic features of dominant clones. From 188 studied samples, a predominant clone of RT033 was found in samples from all compartments connected to the pig production unit, with core-genome SNV-based analysis supporting a clonal transmission between them (mean distance of 0.1 ± 0.1 core-SNVs). The phylogenetic positioning of this clone was clearly distinct from the classical RT033 cluster, being the first report of a toxigenic RT033 clone. This clone displayed a unique combination of genetic elements that may contribute to host tropism, environmental dissemination and maintenance. We are currently performing a study focused on this novel RT033 clone with zoonotic potential, involving genomic diversity assessment and relevant phenotype assessment (germination, sporulation, biofilms and toxins production) (one manuscript in preparation). Lastly, two large-scale genomic studies are ongoing to assess genetic overlap between isolates from different sources (human, food/environment, and animals), targeting the dominant clones RT078 (HOAL from Austria) and RT049 (agricultural facility from Estonia) (two manuscripts are scheduled).

Overall, the results obtained from the three HOALs/agricultural facility showed the presence of dominant clones in compartments associated with the pig production unit and suggest a transmission chain involving these animals. They contributed to unveil the role played by animal and environmental reservoirs within the *C. difficile* epidemiology. Scientific outputs from this task: two scientific papers with peer-review (doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2022.858310, doi: 10.1016/j.anaerobe.2022.102651) and two posters (OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021).

WP4 Determination of the selection pressures in the tested compartments of human, animal and environmental ecosystems (M25-M50)

WP4-T1- Selection of essential antimicrobials to be quantified in the tested compartments (published antibiotic consumption data, farmers' questionnaire, personal experience, expert interviews (veterinarians) (M25-M30)

This task was finished in M30 and the corresponding deliverable (D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP4.1) was uploaded into the members area of the OHEJP website; this deliverable contains three protocols as annexes on the quantification of antibiotics, elements and herbicides in the different compartments.

Four antimicrobial classes to be tested in the compartments were selected: tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides, trimethoprim and fluoroquinolones (task JRP15-WP4-T1) in accordance with the ARGs [*tet(M)*, *tet(W)*, *tet(Z)*, *sul1*, *sul2*, *sul3*, *erm*-like genes, PMQR-encoding genes] that were investigated in the environment (faeces, manure, agricultural soil, drainage, surface and ground-water; see WP2). We focused on antibiotics from these groups that were marked as the most important according to published antibiotic consumption data and EFSA report on antibiotic residues in live animals and food. They were included in the analytical method by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC/MSMS) performed by 34-PIWET (WP4-T2 to WP4-T5). The chosen herbicides glufosinate and glyphosate, as well as its degradation product aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA), 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) are among the most often used herbicides in agriculture. Quantification of these substances (Task WP4-T6) was performed by an AGES associated sister company (UBA Vienna). Heavy metals and trace elements were chosen among those that are triggering co-selection and that have been used in co-selection studies: Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Hg, Co, Pb, Zn. The samples were analysed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP/MS) carried out by 23-UoS (Task WP4-T7).

WP4-T2-Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in aqueous matrices (water) (M31-M50)

29 antibiotics are in the analytical scope of the LC-MSMS method used in WP4-T2, T3, T4 and T5: 4 tetracyclines, 7 sulphonamides, 10 fluoroquinolones, 7 macrolides and trimethoprim. 72 samples were analysed and in 10 samples antibiotics from 4 antimicrobial classes (macrolides, tetracyclines, fluoroquinolones and sulphonamides) were detected: azithromycin, oxytetracycline, enrofloxacin and sulfadimidine).

WP4-T3- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in manure (M31-M50)

Results of 22 manure samples are available. Antibiotics from 2 antimicrobial classes (fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines) were detected in 12 samples (maximum values are 41 µg/kg marbofloxacin, 69 µg/kg enrofloxacin and ciprofloxacin; 124 µg/kg oxytetracycline; 768 µg/kg doxycycline). The concentrations of all five antibiotics exceeded the minimum selective concentrations. This indicated that under the given circumstances the detected antimicrobials were likely to select bacteria resistant to these compounds.

WP4-T4- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in faeces (M35-M50)

24 samples were analysed. Antibiotics from 2 antimicrobial classes (fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines) were detected in 2 samples (maximum values are 265 µg/kg enrofloxacin; 1250 µg/kg oxytetracycline; 3440 µg/kg doxycycline). The concentrations of all 3 antibiotics exceeded the minimum selective concentrations. This indicated that under the given circumstances the detected antimicrobials were likely to select bacteria resistant to these compounds.

WP4-T5- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in soil (M31-M50)

In this task, 118 samples were analysed. The tetracycline doxycycline was detected in 8 samples (6.8 %) in the range between 9 µg/kg and 20 µg/kg. The highest concentration could be detected at the minimum selective concentration.

WP4-T6- Quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil (M31-M50)

The following substances were in the analytical scope of the LC-MSMS method: Glyphosate and its more stable degradation product AMPA (Aminomethylphosphonic acid), Glufosinate, 2,4-D (2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid), Metolachlor ESA the degradation product of Metolachlor, Bentazon and the degradation products of Metazachlor (Metazachlor ESA and Metazachlor OA).

Analytical results: 114 soil samples: herbicides were detected in 66 samples (58 %) (maximum values are 200 µg/kg AMPA and 74 µg/kg glyphosate); 30 water samples: herbicides were detected in 26 samples (86.7 %) (maximum values are 4.3 µg/L AMPA and 0.7 µg/L Metolachlor ESA); 7 manure samples: herbicides were detected in 6 samples (maximum values are 91 µg/kg AMPA and 41 µg/kg glyphosate).

The observed glyphosate levels in the tested compartments were below the MICs and sub-inhibitory concentrations as analysed for *Salmonella* sp strains. It is likely that the observed glyphosate concentrations (wet weight) do not select for resistant bacteria or perturb bacterial populations.

WP4-T7 Measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples gathered across participant countries

Samples of water (77), soils (98), crops and animal feeds (56), manure and faeces from wild animals and farm pigs (43) were received at the University of Surrey, Department of Chemistry from members of the consortium (namely Austria, Estonia, Czech Republic, Republic of Ireland, United Kingdom and Portugal), for the subsequent determination of trace elements. The key elements considered for analysis were chromium (Cr), cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), mercury (Hg) and lead (Pb). These analytes were selected on the basis of their toxicity or their nutritional/physiological importance. In addition to these key elements, analyses were also completed and data are available for vanadium (V), manganese (Mn), iron (Fe), arsenic (As), selenium (Se), strontium (Sr), molybdenum (Mo), cadmium (Cd), antimony (Sb) and barium (Ba).

The analysis of water samples was completed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS, Agilent 7800) after filtration and acidification. The concentration profiles for all partners showed similar trends, with Zn showing the highest concentration in all areas when comparing the 8 key elements. Only samples from Czech Republic, Republic of Ireland and Portugal presented measurable concentrations of Hg (limit of detection 0.13 ng/mL). Samples from wastewater plants showed the highest concentrations for all elements, presenting as well as a clear seasonal trend over the period of sampling.

The bioavailable fraction of elements was determined from the soils samples. For this purpose, the soils were homogenised with 0.43 mol/L acetic acids and the extracts were analysed by ICP-MS after filtration. The concentration profiles varied largely amongst the consortium partners, due to the

differences in the geochemical makeup of the soil. In general terms, Zn presented the highest concentrations amongst the 8 key elements and the highest variability (ca. 2 to 9 $\mu\text{g/g}$), followed by Ni (approx. 1.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and Cu (0.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$). The concentrations of Cd and Hg were below the limit of detection (0.002 $\mu\text{g/g}$ Cd and 0.005 $\mu\text{g/g}$ Hg), but the presence of Pb and Cr was measurable in all samples.

The elemental composition of crops and animal feed ranged in very wide intervals and no clear geographical differences were observed when considering the concentration of the 8 key elements. Iron (Fe) presented the highest concentration of all elements analysed (max concentration 600 mg/kg), but when considering the 8 key elements, Zn again presented the highest concentration values, ranging from 150 to 10 mg/kg, followed by Cu from 2 to 50 mg/kg.

The profiles of all the elements in the manure and faeces were almost identical for all samples, indicating that the concentrations of these considered elements may be controlled by homeostatic processes. The highest concentrations observed were for Fe, followed by Mn and Zn. Measurable concentration of Cd and Pb were recorded for all samples, and the lowest measured values were for Cd.

WP5: Identification of environmental conditions modulating transformation frequencies in soil microcosms and an in vitro porcine gut model (poGutMo) (laboratory studies) (M32-M60)

WP5-T1 Establish basemnt levels of HGT in the model organism (*E. coli*) arising from transformation in the poGutMo

We first determined suitable *E. coli* strains with which to demonstrate ARG transmission arising from transformation. For this we used an *E. coli* J53 strain that was sensitive to rifampicin, but resistant to sodium azide. This served as the recipient (reporter strain) of transformation with exDNA encoding Rif, whilst the DNA amplicons encoding rifampicin resistance and bacterial DNA lysates from other *E. coli* strains served as sources of AMR encoding exDNA.

An important aspect of the poGutMo was that it would represent faithfully the bacterial abundance and diversity of the natural host. To determine this, DNA has been extracted from independent pig gut model experiments and submitted for 16S rRNA sequencing. Analysis is on-going to confirm whether bacterial abundance and diversity is being maintained within the model.

Optimal growth parameters for cultivating *E. coli* in the gut model were established in terms of primary bacterial inoculum concentration, time of inoculation, pH and flow rate. Once these conditions were established, we conducted experiments to establish the baseline efficiency of transformation using Rif^R-encoding DNA. We demonstrated successful transformation from 24 hours in the gut model. Further experiments are currently undergoing to demonstrate transformation with bacterial DNA lysate and plasmids as an additional source of exDNA.

Practical challenges were encountered in maintaining sufficient *E. coli* J53 recipient bacteria to be able to detect the low numbers of transformation events that may be occurring. We addressed this through co-incubation of the recipient strain with bacterial faeces before using this material to seed the gut model.

WP5-T2 Evaluate conditions that drive HGT and the emergence of AMR via transformation

As described later in the project self-assessment section, we encountered substantial technical difficulties in delivering T1 that meant it was no longer possible to achieve our ambition in T2 of evaluating environmental conditions that drive HGT and the emergence of AMR via transformation

(WP4 & WP6 were intended to suggest such drivers, such as antibiotic, herbicide, cation). The hope was that we would evaluate these iteratively in the model. However, it took too long to establish a baseline of natural transformation in the model under T1 and there was insufficient time left to introduce antibiotics or different cation concentrations in the gut model and evaluate their effect on transformation efficiency. However, we did conduct trace element analysis on the faecal content of the gut model in anticipation that we might manipulate the concentration of cations in the model to evaluate their impact upon transformation efficiency. The analysis demonstrated the lack of detectable antibiotics residues in the collected pig faeces and manure samples while variable concentrations of trace elements were detected.

In a similar way, the challenges we faced in T1 meant that we were unable to generate data in sufficient time to feed into the iterative *in silico* modelling we had envisaged in WP6.

WP5-T3 Effect of different environmental conditions on the expression of competence genes in *A. baylyi* determined using soil microcosms

A soil microcosm setting was created by utilizing non-manured agricultural soil. Heat exposure was chosen as the environmental parameter to be analysed, thus, soil samples were incubated at 35°C and at 20°C. The soil samples were spiked with the naturally transformable bacterium *Acinetobacter baylyi* ADP1 in order to track the expression of two competence genes: *dprA* and *comA*. DprA is an exclusively transformation-specific ssDNA binding protein which is essential for recruiting the recombinase *recA* to bind intruding ssDNA during transformation. ComA is a competence factor forming a transmembrane tunnel, which is required for DNA uptake. RNA was isolated from samples collected at 4 different sampling timepoints: Prior to incubation and spiking with *A. baylyi* (tinitial), immediately after spiking (tspike), six hours and 24 hours after spiking. The obtained RNA was analysed using RT-qPCR to quantify the expression of the 16S rRNA reference gene and the two transformation/competence-specific targets: *dprA* and *comA*. The delta delta Ct method was utilized for relative quantification. A 30 (*comA*)- to 40 (*dprA*)-fold decrease in target gene expression was noticeable in the *A. baylyi* spiked soils incubated up to 6 hours at 35°C in comparison to the control. However, this competence gene repression vanished after 24h and the expression-levels of the 35°C and 20°C soil samples converged. Preliminary results show that within a time window of 6 hours, expression of *A. baylyi* specific competence genes can be repressed due to heat exposure. This effect is time restrained as the mRNA-levels of *dprA* and *comA* are similar after 24h at either temperature. This observation indicates that uptake of free extracellular DNA by naturally competent soil bacteria might be reduced at elevated environmental temperatures. This experiment is currently fine-tuned and additional reference genes are tested. This experiment will be repeated under improved conditions and an additional timepoint (3 hours after heat incubation) will be added to obtain more information about competence gene expression levels.

*Figure 1 Temperature-dependent expression of competence-specific genes *dprA* and *comA* in relation to 16S rRNA using the Delta Delta Ct method. Sampling timepoints were tinitial (before spiking with *A. baylyi*), *tspike* (immediately after spiking with *A. baylyi*), 6h and 24h after spiking with *A. baylyi* and at two different temperatures (35°C and 20°C).*

WP6- Probabilistic and mechanistic models of the links between antimicrobial usage in animals, AMR in the environment, and the risks for public health.

WP6-T1 Factors influencing the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment (PRIOR name: Build a probabilistic mathematical model of the emergence of AMR in target bacteria and the relative contribution of transformation and conjugation to ARG acquisition) (M32-M60)

This task refers to the systematic evidence map “Factors associated with the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment from a One Health perspective: Protocol for a systematic evidence map” (doi: 10.17605/OSF.IO/A8GV6). The protocol successfully passed a very stringent editorial review, requiring a resubmission of the manuscript based on editors’ feedback. The manuscript was sent out for review. Following a request of major modifications, a revised manuscript was re-submitted to the journal. The manuscript was accepted in Dec/2022, published Jan/2023. As requested by the journal, the protocol is extremely detailed; a Qualtrics online form has already been prepared for data extraction. Most of the questions are in closed form reducing the risk of ambiguity. This will render the process more efficient and analysis simpler. Thus most of the work is already done.

WP6-T1-ST1 Data Integration, Annotation and Association Analysis (afterwards: Systematic review: environmental factors associated with AMR) (M32-M60)

Because of personnel departure at UoS two tasks (WP6-T2.1 “Modelling microbial communities” and WP6-T2.2 “Modelling microbial communities II”) have been merged to result in one combined paper.

WP6-T2 Develop mechanistic models to address key questions regarding the spatio-temporal changes observed in microbiological communities (M34-M60)

This task refers to the development and validation of a model that dynamically tracks changes in microbial communities to address specific questions. The plan is to focus on the impact of external fluctuations and/or impact of rare species on the dynamics of the community. The final decision on the specific research question will be made once the model is fully validated. At the moment we are continuing working on the model to improve the numerical code. The model can successfully infer the parameters (growth rate, interaction, mortality) of an independent agent based model which mimics microbial five different taxonomic units and the rest of the communities is treated as whole. We are aiming to increase the number of taxonomic units that the model can discriminate to make the model more impactful.

WP6-T2. ST1 - Modelling microbial communities (M34-M60)

This task refers to the development and validation of a model that dynamically tracks changes in microbial communities to address specific questions. The plan is to focus on the impact of external fluctuations and/or impact of rare species on the dynamics of the community. The final decision on the specific research question will be made once the model is fully validated. At the moment, we are continuing working on the model to improve the numerical code. The model can successfully infer the parameters (growth rate, interaction, mortality) of an independent agent based model which mimics microbial five different taxonomic units and the rest of the communities is treated as whole. We are aiming to increase the number of taxonomic units that the model can discriminate to make the model more impactful.

2.4.4 Project self-assessment

In general, the project objectives as laid out in the project proposal have been met. However, as the very ambitious goals we set at the beginning of this project were not sufficiently reflected in the working plan and the budget of the project proposal, adaptations on the methodological side and regarding the time frame were necessary, being all the sole responsibility of the respective WP leaders (except for the decision to eliminate the qPCR method and its replacement in WP2, which was discussed with the partners within WP2 and with the consortium, and approved by them and by the SSB). Additional costs arose partially due to increased administrative difficulties during the pandemic, as well as from enhanced analytic pathways. Most of the delays in the FED-AMR project were either a direct (closed laboratories, reduced staff availability, ...) or indirect (i.e. supply chain issues, late sampling, ...) consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic, as our project started in early 2020 (year3).

In WP2, the prior limited knowledge on free exDNA posed consequently diverse methodological challenges, such as the generation and validation of novel protocols for extraction of this DNA fraction. Despite the low exDNA concentrations obtained for some of the samples, the quality of the sequencing data exceeded our expectation. There is nevertheless room for improvement in the future with respect to the exDNA extraction protocols. Indeed, the time planned in the project proposal for the development of these protocols, specific to each of the compartments, was not realistic enough. Regarding target enrichment, this new approach has undoubtedly been the method that has allowed us to obtain harmonized AMR data for all participating countries in shorter time and with better results than with the initially chosen qPCR approach. Although there are still questions to be answered, we consider that all the initial objectives for this WP have been met. We have generated a unique dataset containing comprehensive information, from exDNA and tDNA, on microbial biodiversity (16S rDNA) and ARGs present in different compartments along the food/feed chain and in one-year crop growing season. Up to our knowledge, there are no studies integrating so many compartments that use target enrichment to detect ARGs in exDNA. The large datasets obtained here together with the associated metadata make our results a unique resource that will be available to other researchers and from which further studies can be performed.

In WP3, zoonotic vs anthropogenic antimicrobial resistance (AMR) transmission was studied with *Clostridioides difficile* as a model organism in WP3. At farm level, dominant clones in environmental compartments associated with the pig production unit were identified, suggesting a transmission chain involving these animals. These results contributed to unveil the role played by animal and environmental reservoirs within the *C. difficile* epidemiology. The studies assessing genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages at different OH settings support the high zoonotic importance of *C. difficile* and its presence in novel reservoirs.

In WP4 we aimed at determining the selection pressures (antimicrobials, elements and herbicides) for antimicrobial resistance in environmental ecosystems. The highest concentrations of antimicrobials were detected in manure and faeces and are likely to select bacteria resistant to these compounds. The results of WP4 will be used for an impact evaluation of the analysed substances on the prevalence and quantities of ARGs encoded on extracellular DNA in exposed bacterial populations residing in the tested environmental compartments.

WP5 encountered substantial technical difficulties that could not have been anticipated at the outset of the project. These were exacerbated by delays with the laboratory work due to COVID-19. The financial resources available proved inadequate to conduct the full range and scope of objectives originally envisaged. As such, in Y5 the whole WP was re-focussed on demonstrating that the pig gut model could serve as a representative model of the *in vivo* large intestine in terms of the bacterial microbiota. The model conditions were optimized to establish whether natural transformation could be detected with sufficient sensitivity to likely detect what was expected to be a low-efficiency event. This refocus meant it was no longer possible to consider conjugation using *C. difficile* in the model. This was not a major consideration since the focus of this project was on natural transformation, and

conjugation was only included in this WP as a comparator of the efficiency of conjugation versus transformation. More disappointingly, the technical challenges we faced meant that we could not achieve our ambition of evaluating environmental conditions that drive HGT and the emergence of AMR via transformation. The hope was that we would evaluate these iteratively in the model. However, without first being able to establish a reliable baseline of natural transformation in the model we had nothing against which to compare. This was always going to be an ambitious program of work. Lessons learnt include the need for more time and resource to establish the model. However, we have been successful in establishing an experimental in vitro pig gut model that can form the basis of future studies. The soil microcosm suffered similar issues due to COVID-related delays of laboratory reagents, changes in and lack of personnel, establishing a new laboratory method and resources to carry out this work package. Nonetheless, a soil microcosm pilot study was successfully conducted and functioned as a basis to identify heat as an environmental parameter that could repress the expression of competence genes in the naturally transformable bacterium *A. baylyi*. Temperature-levels that were non-lethal for the soil bacterium could temporarily repress the expression of certain competence factors, and hence, the ability to take-up free extracellular DNA and recombine it with the bacterial genomic DNA. Due to time- and staff-limitations we could not test the effect of additional parameters (e.g. antibiotics, herbicides, heavy metals, etc.) on competence gene expression. However, continuation of the work is secured and will build up on the already obtained results and experience. An RNA-Seq platform will be implemented to gain more insight on competence gene expression on *A. baylyi* and bacterial population levels.

In WP6, the main tasks were: 1) completion of the protocol for a systematic evidence map; and 2) completion of a model to dynamically track changes in microbial communities to address specific questions (e.g. impact of external fluctuations and/or impact of rare species on the dynamics of the community). The work on the systematic evidence map has required a longer time than anticipated. This is perhaps not surprising considering the scientific quality standards of the journal 'Environment International', to which we submitted our manuscript. Following a first pre-submission enquire, we have had multiple meetings with the editors of Environment International. Although they have been supportive, they have provided an in-depth and rigorous critique which required extensive revisions. As expected, the departure of Dr Gardner (he is working on the project only part-time, for a few hours a week) has had a large impact on the project. To mitigate this, we asked Dr Deza Cruz to step in and he has largely contributed to developing and finalising the protocol. For the modelling part, we had to revisit our objectives because of Dr Gardner's departure. Initially our plan was to assess the impact of external perturbation on microbial communities and the impact of rare species. We are still interested in these two questions, but at the moment it is difficult to anticipate and fully assess the performance and computational cost (e.g. the required time to complete the task) of the numerical code. Thus, we reserve to make a final decision after the model is validated and the computational cost estimated.

2.4.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.1	Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) installed. Local administrative representatives nominated (T1, T2)	M25	M25	Confidential (contains e-mail addresses of the members of the consortium) OHEJP: available Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5081685	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.2	Unified sampling and experimental protocols (T1.1.)	M33	M33	Public OHEJP : available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5081689	2
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.3	Data and protocol management plan (T3)	M34	M34	Public OHEJP : available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078099	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.4	Webinars (T1.2.)	M31	M31	Public OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5081710	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.5	Annual project report	M38	M38	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078024	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.6	Interim project report (T1.3.)	M52	M52	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057286	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR- WP1.7	Final project report (T1.3.)	M59	M60	Public Zenodo (draft version) https://zenodo.org/record/7585559#.Y9j1o4SZMQ8 Zenodo (final version) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7763690	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR- WP2.1	List of sampling compartments, points and European test areas and harmonized protocols in alignment with EFFORT project protocols available in data repository (T2.1, T2.2)	M33	M33	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5081756	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.2	Preliminary data collection on ARG prevalence and ARG background load in the compartments analysed so far (T2.4)	M37	M37	Public OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078064	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.3	Annual report Y3 (WP2)	M39	M38	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078149	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.4	Determination of naturally transformable bacteria in tested environmental compartments (T2.5)	M56	M60	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7446361	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.5	Shotgun sequencing: ARG diversity in tested environmental compartments (T2.3.1)	M46	M46	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726732	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6	16S metagenomics results: Microbial biodiversity and phylogenetic	M54	M56	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057188	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		relationships of ARBs over ecosystem boundaries (T2.3, T2.6)				
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.7	Quantity and stability of free extracellular DNA observed in environmental compartments tested so far (T2.7)	M56	M60	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7547822	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.8	Annual report for Y4 (WP2)	M49	M49	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057332	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.9	ARG dynamics in an agricultural testing area: Response of ARG concentrations according to different fertilisation techniques and crops over an annual growth period (WP2)	M58	M60	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7740360	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMRWP2.10	Final report on WP2 and draft version of peer-reviewed publication (WP2)	M58	M60	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7585276 Annex: https://zenodo.org/record/7588364#.Y9j1hoSZMQ8	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15–FED-AMR-WP3.1	Database of zoonotic <i>Clostridium difficile</i> isolates across participant countries (task 3.1)	M36	M36	Public OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078164	3
15	D-JRP15–FED-AMR-WP3.2	Overview of genetic overlap between human and non-human <i>C. difficile</i> isolates (task 3.2 and task 3.3)	M60	M60	Public OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472663	
15	D-JRP15–FED-AMR-WP3.3	Classification of pig farm compartments according to their role in the epidemiology of <i>C. difficile</i> (task 3.4).	M60		Public OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472732	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP4.1	Standardize protocols for sampling and testing of environmental samples	M30	M30	Public OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5482759	2
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.2	Quantitative results of antibiotics in water	M50	M50	Public. Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396025	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.3	Quantitative results of antibiotics in manure	M50	M50	Public. Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396070	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.4	Quantitative results of antibiotics in faeces	M50	M50	Public. Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396112	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.5	Quantitative results of antibiotics in soil	M50	M50	Public. Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396145	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.6	Quantitative results of herbicides in environmental samples	M50	M50	Public. Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396160	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.7	Quantitative results of trace elements in environmental samples	M53	M53	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057243	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.1	<i>E. coli</i> strains demonstrated to be suitable for transformation	M38	M38	Deliverable was made public, but elements of the data included in the deliverable may be embargoed or kept confidential, in line with the OHEJP guidelines. Zenodo: deliverable description https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5121159	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.2	Optimal growth parameters for cultivating <i>E.</i>	M57	M60	Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7759902	10

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		<i>coli</i> and transformation pilot experiments using AMR-encoding DNA are tested				
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.11	First results from soil microcosm experiments on effects of environmental conditions on transformation	M60		Pilot experiments have been performed. RNA isolation from soil samples has been established. RT Taqman qPCR systems for competence and reference genes have been designed and are available. Delays were due to bottlenecks in availability of laboratory staff. First results were delivered along with final summary of results and combined with D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP5.13 Since competence genes and their expression are essential for transformation, we used the results for both deliverables, since WP5.13 is only an in-depth topic for WP5.11.	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP5.13	Results of the soil microcosm experiments regarding environmental effects on competence gene expression	M58	M59	Please see “D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.11” Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7547851	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.1	Main code for the mathematical modelling made available in public repository (e.g. GitHub) with associated documentation (which can be used as “Material and Method” section of the forthcoming publications).	M30	M37	This is now a protocol for systematic review (not a code for mathematical modelling). Confidential until publication or registration of the protocol for the systematic review, except for FED-AMR or other One-Health EJP members. Zenodo: deliverable description https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139307 Following a request of major modifications, a revised manuscript was submitted to the journal. We are now waiting for the decision.	3
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP6.2	Findings presented at one international conference and one national conference.	M54	M57	We presented our results at two international conferences (ASM 2021 and One Conference 2022). See output section for more information. Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7341753	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.3	Update of codes and documentations in public repository (e.g. GitHub).	M36	M43	Confidential until full validation of the code or publication (except for FED-AMR or other One Health EJP members). Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7341773	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.4	Submission/publication of 1/2 paper(s) on how resilience of microbial communities depends on external environmental drivers and richness and diversity of the community.	M60	M60	Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/7547834#.Y8pfdnbMLEY DOI of paper: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107707	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5	Main code for the mathematical modelling made available in public repository (e.g. GitHub) with associated documentation (which can be used as “Material and Method” section of the forthcoming publications).	M57	M60	In the previous document this deliverable appeared as D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.3, not D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5. Both deliverables are similar, 6.5 now is just an update on the code but the deliverable titles were switched. This deliverable relates to WP6 task 2, 'Modelling microbial communities', and describes prototype code written in Python, along with associated documentation, uploaded to the University of Surrey's online repository GitLab for version control purposes. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7456214 We are continuing with this task, specifically to improve the Python code to make it more efficient. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7456214	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
					https://osf.io/a8gv6/	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-01	Kick off meeting	M26	M26	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-02	Database repository active	M27	M27	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-03	Webinar forums started	M30	M30	The consortium initiated the scientific exchange via online teleconferences and formally installed regular webinars by M31.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-04	Interim meeting	M48	M52	Had to be moved online and scheduled for convenience, date was decided in the TCs and through an online meeting on Zoom.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-05	Final meeting (T1.3.)	M60	M60	Online meeting
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-07	List of sampling compartments, points and European test areas available. Harmonized protocols for sample collection + transportation, DNA extraction, qPCR, metagenomics, shotgun sequencing,	M26	M33	The list of sampling compartments, points and European test areas have been defined. Harmonized protocols for sample collection and transportation and DNA extraction protocols are already available for all project members. Protocols for WGS, metagenomics, gene capture and bioinformatics were developed.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		gene capture and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of sequence data available. Alignment with EFFORT project protocols (T2.1, T2.2)			
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-08	Start of annual field study (i.e. sampling campaign, sample collection) (T2.3)	M27	M30	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-09	Start of DNA isolations and cultivation of ARB strains (immediately after reception of the first environmental samples) (T2.3, T2.7)	M27	M28	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-10	Start of performing qPCRs (T2.4)	M28	Not applicable	qPCR were replaced by Ares genetics services
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-11	Start collecting data for annual report (WP2)	M34	M34	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-12	Starting preparations for	M35	M38	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		gene capture probe approach (T2.3.2)			
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-13	Finishing annual report (WP2)	M36	M37	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-14	Starting preparations for shotgun sequencing (T2.3.1)	M37	Not applicable	Shotgun Metagenomics was replaced for target enrichment (see Task 2.3.1).
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-15	Stop: field sampling campaign (T2.3), DNA isolations (T2.7)	M40	M43	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-16	Starting 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates. Batch format (T2.3)	M40	M43	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-17	Start: Determination of naturally transformable bacteria (T2.5)	M41	M43	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-18	Finalizing ARG qPCRs (T2.4)	M42	Not applicable	qPCRs were replaced by target enrichment
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-19	Finalizing determination of transformable bacteria (T2.5)	M56	M60	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-20	Start: Assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6)	M43	M45	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-21	Finalizing 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates (T2.3)	M52	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-22	Finalizing assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6)	M52	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-23	Finalizing shot gun sequencing and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of NGS data (T2.3.1, T3.2.2, T2.3)	M53	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-24	Delivery of final annual report on WP2 + draft version of peer reviewed paper (WP2)	M54	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-25	Completed database with zoonotic types	M36	M36	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-26	Complete WGS on all included isolates	M46	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-27	Complete AMR profiles on all included isolates	M59	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-28	Genetic overlap-analysis human vs. non-human	M60	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-29	Identification of transmission network as described above	M60	M60	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-30	Starting the selection of essential antimicrobials to be quantified in the tested compartments	M25	M27	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-31	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in aqueous matrices	M27	M31	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-32	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in manure	M31	M31	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-33	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in faeces	M29	M35	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-34	Starting the analysis of antimicrobials in soil	M31	M35	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-35	Starting the quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil	M31	M40	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-36	Starting the measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples	M27	M48	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-37	Bacterial strains supplied to UoS	M25	M34	Bacterial strains have been supplied to UoS and used successfully.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-38	Porcine gut model set up using faecal samples obtained through WP2, samples stored for trace element analysis (WP4) – experiments can start	M44	M45	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-39	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace	M41	M45	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		element analysis (WP4)			
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-40	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M52	M52	
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-41	Antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals most likely to drive HGT through transformation supplied to UoS.	M57	M57	Antibiotics and transposable elements analysis results has been supplied to WP5.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-42	DNA sent for whole-genome sequencing	M55	M55	Bacterial isolates have been sent to WP2 for WGS and results have been received.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-43	Sub-strains of E. coli with appropriate antibiotic resistances made and chromosomal DNA and lysates prepared	M55	M55	Rifampicin resistant E. coli strain has been generated and appropriate nucleic acid preparations have been made.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-44	Porcine gut model set up using faecal samples obtained through WP2, samples stored for	M51	M51	All samples are stored for trace element analysis.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		trace element analysis (WP4) – experiments can start			
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-47	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M50	M50	All samples are stored for trace element analysis
15	M-JRP15-FEDAMR-52	Deliver results from soil microcosm experiments to WP6 leader for final modelling	M52	M60	This will depend on results from soil microcosm experiments. In addition, due to the departure of Dr Gardner we need to reassess feasibility of this milestone.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-53	Literature review on concept of resilience and modelling in microbial communities.	M27	M28	Mainly done at the beginning of the project, which led to the type of modelling proposed here (Lotka-Volterra system and agent-based models). We keep constantly monitoring the literature to be updated with the state-of-the-art.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-54	Identification of relevant available data. Formulation and implementation of the model for the microbiological community within-host. Conditioned to data availability, potential extension of the model to	M30	M30	We found that a dataset particularly suitable to our type of model is the one provided by Stein et al. which used cecal content data in (https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003388). We also developed our own agent-based models to validate the model.

JRP/JI P Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		natural environment (e.g. soil).			
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-56	Literature review on fluctuating ecological systems and gut model approach.	M45	M45	The review of the literature is an ongoing task to ensure we are updated with the state of the art.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-59	Application of the model to address specific questions and dissemination of findings in peer-reviewed publications and conferences.	M50	60	Partially achieved: the mathematical model has been presented in the OHEJP conference and Brian in continuing work on this milestone.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-62	Finding presented at one international conference and one national conference	M54	M54	The mathematical model has been presented in OHEJP conferences.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-64	Finishing annual report (WP2)	M48	(M60)	Since the FED-AMR project was extended till December 2022, the WP2 annual report for the Y5 be delivered at the end of the project.

2.4.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Draft Genome Sequence of a Multidrug-Resistant <i>Escherichia coli</i> Sequence Type 1193 Pandemic Clone Isolated from Wastewater in Austria. Microbiology Resource Announcements DOI: 10.1128/MRA.00762-21 https://zenodo.org/record/5770120#.YeZ1rd8xl4F	published	Yes	No	1,050.00 \$ 929.38 €
Assessment of the Transmission Dynamics of <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> in a Farm Environment Reveals the Presence of a New Toxigenic Strain Connected to Swine Production. Frontiers in Microbiology DOI: 10.3389/fmicb.2022.858310 https://zenodo.org/record/6857162#.Yyh-SXZByUk	published	Yes	No	2,950.00 \$ 2,750.00 €
Characterizing Antimicrobial Resistance in Clinically Relevant Bacteria Isolated at the Human/Animal/Environment Interface Using Whole-Genome Sequencing in Austria. Journal International Journal of Molecular Sciences. Doi: 10.3390/ijms231911276 https://zenodo.org/record/7446455#.Y5xQ-FGZND8	published	Yes	No	2,173.86 €
Airborne spores' dissemination of a swine associated <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> clone. <i>Anaerobe</i> . DOI: 10.1016/j.anaerobe.2022.102651 https://zenodo.org/record/7446535#.Y5xSj1GZND8	published	Yes	No	free of charge

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Gardner, Brian; Betson, Martha; Cabal Rosel, Adriana; Caniça, Manuela; Chambers, Mark; Contadini, Francesca M.; Gonzales Villeta, Laura C.; Hassan, Marwa M.; La Ragione, Roberto; De Menezes, Alexandre; Messina, Davde; Nichols, Gordon; Olivenca, Daniel V.; Phalkey, Revati; Prada, Joaquin M.; Ruppitsch, Werner; Santorelli, Lorenzo A.; Selemetas, Nick; Tharmakulasingam, Mukunthan; van Vliet, Arnoud H. M.; Wögerbauer, Markus; Deza-Cruz, Iñaki; Lo Iacono, Gianni (2022) Factors associated with the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment from a One Health perspective: Protocol for a systematic evidence map. Environment International. DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2022.107707 https://zenodo.org/record/7446911#.Y6G50nbMJD8</p>	published	Yes	No	
<p>Alves F, Castro R, Pinto M, Nunes A, Pomba C, Moreira O, Silveira L, Gomes JP and Oleastro M (2022) Molecular epidemiology of <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> in companion animals: genetic overlap with human strains and public health concerns. Frontiers in Public Health. DOI: 10.3389/fpubh.2022.1070258 https://zenodo.org/record/7528151#.Y7- bHbMJD8</p>	published	Yes	No	3,100 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Coelho, Rodrigo. Characterization of Antibiotic Resistance in Strains Isolated from Different Environmental Reservoirs [Caracterização da Resistência aos Antibióticos em estirpes isoladas de diferentes reservatórios ambientais]. Master thesis, 2022. http://hdl.handle.net/10451/53801 https://zenodo.org/record/7584902#.ZBsoqISZMQ8	published	Yes	No	Free of charge.
Ines Dost, Mostafa Abdel-Gliil, Gernot Schmoock, Christian Menge, Christian Berens, Belén González Santamarina, Elisabeth Wiegand, Heinrich Neubauer, Stefan Schwarz, Christian Seyboldt. <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> in South American camelids in Germany: First insights into molecular and genetic characteristics and antimicrobial resistances. Antibiotics. DOI: 10.3390/antibiotics12010086 https://zenodo.org/record/7550849#.Y9DmVV6ZND8	published	Yes	No	
Microbial composition and ARGs diversity in wild mammals of Portugal, Austria and Ireland (WP2).	under preparation			
Assessing the microbial composition and ARGs diversity in Europe in different compartments along the feed/food chain (WP2).	under preparation			
Tackling the dissemination of ARGs between compartments of the feed/food chain with target enrichment (WP2).	under preparation			

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Prevalence of naturally competent bacteria in European Agroecosystems (and their relevance in AMR dissemination) (WP2).	under preparation			
Correlation analysis reveals strong association of free extracellular ARGs with certain trace elements in environmental compartments of the food/feed chain (WP2)	under preparation			
Alves F, Nunes A, Castro R, Serrano M, Bolt C, Persson S, Maurischat S, Gomes JP, Henriques AO and Oleastro M. Genomic diversity, sporulation, germination and biofilm phenotypes of <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> ribotype 033 from different One Health settings (WP3).	under preparation			
Semeh Bejaoui, Jesper Nielsen, Monica Oleastro, Christian Seyboldt, Sven Maurischat, Adriana Cabal Rosel, Christelle Mazuet, Dorte Frees and Søren Persson (+NN to be determined later). <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> (ST11). Time resolved phylogeny and genetic overlap between human and non-human isolates across Europe (WP3).	under preparation			
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i> RT002 epidemiology and zoonotic potential". Authors involved would be FLI staff and WP3 Partners (WP3).	under preparation			
Maurischat, S., Seyboldt, C., Scholtzek, A., Tenson, T. Transmission and Persistence of <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> within agricultural settings and the environment (WP3).	under preparation			
Changes in the metal bioavailability and content of antimicrobial and herbicide agents as a result of application of manure to agricultural soils (WP4)	under preparation			

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
The development of a chemostat pig gut model for maintaining the microbiome composition and investigating the transfer of AMR (WP5).	under preparation			

Additional output

WP1

Oral presentations

- Werner Ruppitsch. “FED-AMR: The role of free extracellular DNA in dissemination of antimicrobial resistance over ecosystem boundaries along the food/feed chain (One Health EJP)”, One Conference, 21st-24th June, 2022, Brussels, Belgium.
- Werner Ruppitsch. Dissemination workshop on preparedness 2022 organized by OHEJP-WP5 on the topic AMR movement over ecosystem boundaries. 25th March 2022 (online).
- Manuela Caniça. FED-AMR: The role of free extracellular DNA in dissemination of antimicrobial resistance over ecosystem boundaries along the food/feed chain. 22th November, 2022, POC Meeting, Stockholm, Sweden.

WP2

Poster presentations

- Abstract in ECCMID 2021 (e-poster): Antimicrobial resistance and genetic relatedness of environmental bacteria across the animal-human-wildlife interface in Austria (WP2, 2-AGES) <https://zenodo.org/record/5499916#.YTs2z-dCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (e-poster): Diversity of bacterial communities and genes encoding AMR in different environmental compartments along the food/feed chain (WP2, 36-INSA) <https://zenodo.org/record/4916135#.YTsqrudCR4E>
- D. Olivença; A. Cabal; T. Tenson; M. Hassan; V. Manageiro; E. Dias; T. Rosado; V. Kõiv; V. Kisand; G. Rab; J. Jeremejeva; K. Telling; K. Arbo; M. Chambers; R. Laragione; E. Voit; Z. Drahošová; M. Kořínková; M. Woegerbauer; W. Ruppitsch; M. Caniça; A. de Menezes 2022. “Microbial and antimicrobial resistance gene diversity in extracellular and total DNA across rural ecosystem barriers in Europe”; OHEJP ASM 2022, Orvieto, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6857015>
- A Cabal Rosel; N. Peischl, B. Daza, A Stöger, G Rab; K Rathhammer; F Allerberger; M Wögerbauer, W Ruppitsch. 2022. “Antimicrobial resistance and genetic relatedness of environmental bacteria across the animal-human-wildlife interface in Austria”; ECCMID 2022, Lisbon, Portugal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6641985>
- V Manageiro, R Coelho, T Rosado, P Vieira, L Reis, R Matias, J Rodrigues, C Menezes, E Ferreira, A Sequeira, O Moreira, E Dias, M Caniça. 2022. Resistome, mobilome and virulome analysis of Enterobacter cloacae complex strains isolated from the water environment. ECCMID 2022, Lisbon, Portugal

- Olivença D; Cabal A; Tenson T; Hassan M; Manageiro V; Dias E; Rosado T; Kõiv V; Kisand V; Rab G; Jeremejeva J; Telling K; Arbo K; Chambers M; Laragione R; Voit E; Drahošová Z; Kořínková M; Woegerbauer M; Ruppitsch W; Caniça M; de Menezes 2022. Microbial and antimicrobial resistance gene diversity in extracellular and total dna across rural ecosystem barriers in Europe, ECCMID 2022, Lisbon, Portugal, <https://zenodo.org/record/6857015#.Y6G9SXbMJD8>
- A de Menezes, M Caniça, S Ciutti, L Griffin, A Haigh, AC Rosel, W Ruppitsch. 2022. Antibiotic resistance and AMR gene seasonality patterns in fallow deer (*Dama dama*) with different levels of human interaction: a case study of Ireland. Annual Conference of the UK-Ireland Microbiological Society, Belfast, UK (Oral communication).

WP3

Poster presentations

- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (e-poster): Dissemination of antimicrobial resistant *Clostridium difficile* RT078/ST11 in Austria across the human-animal-wildlife interface (WP3, 2-AGES) <https://zenodo.org/record/4915872#.YTsrnOdCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (e-poster): Zoonotic spread of multi-resistant *C. difficile* (WP3, 13-SSI) <https://zenodo.org/record/4915901#.YTsqSodCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (e-poster): Diversity and Dynamics of *Clostridioides difficile* in a farm environment PT (WP3, 36-INSA). <https://zenodo.org/record/4916135#.YT10-dCR4EF>. Alves; R. Castro; M. Pinto; M. Oliveira; C. Pomba; M. Oleastro 2022. “*Clostridioides difficile* in companion animals, a One Health concern?” One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, Orvieto, Italy.2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6641860>
- “Potential for the zoonotic spread of multi-resistant *Clostridioides difficile* “ ECCMID 2022 <https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.6641860.svg>) resulted in the following article in the Guardian: “Pigs can pass deadly superbugs to people, study reveals”. <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2022/apr/24/pigs-can-pass-deadly-superbugs-to-people-study-reveals>
- Scholtzek; P. Witt; G. Raatz; A. Bhatte; S. Maurischat 2022. “Prevalence of *Clostridioides difficile* in strawberries from Germany”. One Conference 2022, Brussels, Belgium. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6856987>

WP4

Abstracts

- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (e-poster): FED-AMR: Determination of selection pressures for AMR in environmental samples (WP4) <https://zenodo.org/record/4916158#.YT1CudCR4E>
- Presentation by SZU in the Ekomonitor Seminar on Waste Analytics in 2021: English title: International project to map the potential for horizontal transfer of antibiotic resistance genes

across different ecosystems, original language: Czech.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5770033>

- WP4- poster presentation entitled “Analysis of antimicrobials in environmental samples as a part of determination of selection pressures for antimicrobial resistance” accepted at Euroresidue IX conference. OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916158>

WP5

Poster presentations

- M. M Hassan; M. Getino; J. Leng; M. Chambers; R. M. La Ragione. 2022. “Development of an in vitro pig gut model for evaluating factors driving antimicrobial resistance” ; OHEJP ASM 2022, Orvieto, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6642824>

WP6

Abstracts

- Abstract accepted to ONE – Health, Environment, Society – Conference , 21-24 June 2022. "Modelling the dynamics and long-term stability of perturbed gut microbiota" (WP6, 23-UoS) <https://zenodo.org/record/6860460#.Y6HAFxbMJD8>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (e-poster): Ecological modelling of microbial communities subject to perturbation (WP6, 23-UoS) <https://zenodo.org/record/4915941#.YTsqqs-dCR4E>
- B Gardner, M M Hassan, M Chambers, R M La Ragoine, G Lo Iacono, 2021. “Ecological modelling of microbial communities subject to perturbation”, ASM 2021, <https://zenodo.org/record/4915941#.YTsqqs-dCR4E>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915941>

Poster presentations

- B Gardner, L C Gonzalez Villeta; J Leng; M M. Hassan; M Chambers; R M La Ragione; G Lo Iacono. 2022. “Mechanistic modelling of microbial communities with insights from an in vitro pig gut model”, ASM 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6856915>
- B. Gardner; M. M. Hassan; M. Chambers; R. M. La Ragione; G. Lo Iacono 2022. “Modelling the dynamics and long-term stability of perturbed gut microbiota”, One Conference 2022, Brussels, Belgium. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6860460>

Cooperation other organizations and dissemination

- On April 6 2021 partner 2-AGES presented our project to MediPIET (Mediterranean and Black Sea Field Epidemiology Training Programme Network), at the Training of Trainers on One Health.
- In the context of WP2, we have established a small collaboration with the University of Delft for comparison of our different extracellular DNA extraction methodologies and further

analysis with target enrichment were performed for two water samples that University of Delft.

- Presentation of the FED-AMR project at the One Health Session, Project Review Module 2021 and facilitation at the Introductory course and Phylogeny Sessions 2021, as part of the ECDC Fellowship Program.
- EFSA was updated (in)directly on the progress of the FED-AMR project through a stakeholder that belongs to the FED-AMR Advisory Board (Beatriz Guerra).
- The protocol for the systematic evidence map has attract some media attention (Altmetric score 64). More details at <https://www.altmetric.com/details/140395101?src=bookmarklet>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

- Main code for the mathematical modelling is available in GitLab as private and can be shared upon request. Once the paper is finished, it will be publicly available in GitHub.
- FASTQ files from the 16S sequencing and the ARG profiling will be available on ENA for other researchers once the WP2 results are published. Due to the limited amount of studies on gene capture for AMR, our project provides valuable datasets that can be used by other researchers interested in using similar methodologies for deep characterisation of AMR gene diversity.
- New documents produced during FED-AMR project, e.g. Protocols, are available for the scientific community.
- Risk Management Plan has been very well designed and is publicly available.

Outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

The HOALs, which correspond to real experimental laboratories, will be disseminated as an important model for in-depth studies that intend to continue to evaluate the spread of AMR.

In WP2 we have implemented the laboratory protocol related to the collection and phenotypic characterisation of clinically-relevant bacteria present in different environmental compartments. These were identified by the WHO for their relevance in terms of their resistance to last line antibiotics.

WP2 has developed important strategies for 16S and AMR metagenomic analysis, which will be disseminated to the scientific community through scientific publications.

Regarding WP3, we highlights the harmonization and dissemination of protocols for *C. difficile* collection and isolation in animal, food and environmental samples, and the development of a pipeline for identification of MGEs in *C. difficile* (ClosTyper). All these tools are already in use by WP3 partners and were or will be disseminated externally through scientific publications.

In WP4 selection pressures (antimicrobials, elements and herbicides) for antimicrobial resistance in environmental ecosystems (soil, water, faeces, manure, plants, feeds) were determined. Most of the samples showed low or usual concentrations of the analysed substances, but in some samples (soil, faeces and manure) antibiotics from 2 antimicrobial classes (fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines) were detected at or above the minimum selective concentrations for bacteria. The results will be used for an impact evaluation of antimicrobials, elements and herbicides on the prevalence and quantities of ARGs encoded on extracellular DNA in the tested environmental compartments.

There is a close liaison of AGES, and other institutes participating in the FED-AMR project, with ministry policy makers; they are informed and sensitized to the issue of AMR in a One Health context, namely through the this project.

2.4.7 One Health impact

Antimicrobial resistance gene (ARG) pollution is a global threat to the environment and a public health issue. Risk evaluation of pathogens, ARGs as well as mobile genetic elements (MGEs) in diverse environments and matrixes are mainly based on total DNA (tDNA) data. The role of extracellular (ex) DNA is still neglected in most environmental studies. In general, the FED-AMR project contributed:

- to improve the methods and knowledge in environmental exDNA research and its role in AMR transmission.
- to collect and analyse large amounts of data and metadata from an agricultural environment, which outcomes have been presented to stakeholders.
- to underline the importance of the role of exDNA as a source of diverse antimicrobial resistances in the environment, trough the results of the FED-AMR project, which, in combination with the extremely long persistence and its important role as a structural component of biofilms, might represent a serious future public health threat that is currently neglected.
- to still perform data analysis with the metadata produced and to combine all data i.e. exDNA, tDNA, pesticides, antibiotics, heavy metals, microbiomes, as well as to identify clinically relevant bacterial species, which may help to elucidate the transfer and development of resistances in microbial communities in an agricultural environment.
- to have identified new potential sources of emerging resistant microorganisms along the feed/food chain with a focus on the environment and wildlife as a typically neglected component of One Health.
- to confirm that *C. difficile* can spread clonally across the different compartments (animal and environment); the compartments soil and wastewater showed greater diversity in terms of *C. difficile* ribotypes, while fecal and manure samples indicating the dominant strain; this suggests a unidirectional spreading out of the animal compartments into the environment, while the soil and wastewater compartments seem to act as a reservoir for different input pathways beyond the animal compartments. Of particular interest is the possibility that *C. difficile* is transferred back to animal compartments via groundwater and surface water. The introduction of antibiotics or other substances that promote the development of antimicrobial resistance in *C. difficile* into any of the compartments can have an impact on the other compartments.
- to demonstrate the genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages at different One Health settings, supporting the high zoonotic importance of this human pathogen.
- to develop new ongoing projects such as HERA NGS II, funded by the EU Commission, which will incorporate and strengthen the knowledge acquired in this project.
- to understand the need to further improve any new method and new technologies, dynamically, despite the promising results we may have, as in the case of the FED-AMR.; therefore, with FED-AMR further research is essential before implementation into regional/ national surveillance systems.
- to a private company working on machine learning for detection of AMR from WGS data and a university institute working with exDNA, with whom a collaboration was established and further scientific exchanges in regards exDNA can occur in the future.
- to networking and communication between partners and reference laboratories from different backgrounds, sectors and countries, leading to new knowledge (such as at the level of the design of new protocols, or the implementation of new pipelines, or still for analyzing data in the interface of genomics and informatics).

Overall, we can still underline:

The Scientific impact of FED-AMR:

Cross-sector communication of data contributing to the advancement of science, namely e.g.:

- By a study capitalized on advancements in **high-throughput sequencing methods** and **analytical tools**, as it provides the large scalability necessary to investigate bacterial communities, in a way to explore and mapping AMR in exDNA, either in human, animal, and environmental settings, and in several sample matrices.
- By sampling campaigns that provided basic information for **establishing ARG monitoring in environmental compartments**, which is recommended by EFSA and has the potential to become compulsory for EU MS.
- By using the true concept of One Health, namely with an **important environmental component** (farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure, air of pig barns, feeds, crops, soil, water).

The societal, policy-making and economic impact of FED-AMR:

- Impactful research that **adds value** to a European, national and international level.
- Decisive **for assessing** the potential of exDNA to serve as a **high-risk source** of resistance determinants in agricultural soils and along the food/feed chain.
- Impact on **strategies to improve and/or upgrade** wastewater treatment plants, as it is decisive for WWTP engineers to know if they have to design devices that only kill bacteria or if strategies to eliminate bacterial DNA from the waste streams would have to be applied.
- As reliable and accurate surveillance is fundamental to characterize the risk of AMR in a given region, the results obtained **show how essential it is to track the spread of specific ARGs** geographically and over time, identify new ARGs and support preventive measures and interventions against AMR pathogens.
- Through a systematic evidence map, we will gather and collate data to inform future research, policy-relevant systematic review questions, and future funding strategies, concerning risk mitigation for antibiotic resistance emerging in the environment. As such, we expect that the evidence map will be relevant to e.g. WHO, ECDC and other EU agency, and national public health agencies. We expect that the evidence will contribute to the current debate about the role of environmental fluctuations always occurring in nature on the emergence and dynamics of antimicrobial resistance.

2.4.8 Data Management Plan

A first version of the Data and Protocol Management Plan was already delivered on M34. In year 4, the DMP was updated in the new OHEJP data management platform CDP, with details of FED-AMR data throughout the project, with information provided to the leader and deputy leader by task leaders on their datasets. In addition, the task leader and deputy leader generated a metadata file for all samples collected in WP2. This file facilitated the introduction of metadata in the CPD platform and data analysis. The final version of the DMP will be delivered by the end of April 2023 upon agreement with the OHEJP coordination team and will be uploaded to Zenodo.

2.4.9 Future dissemination activities

The main stakeholders we identified are policy makers, the scientific community (e.g. through publications), as well as students and the general public (e.g. farmers); dissemination to the wider public was not in the foreground or scope of this project, so it is a world to explore.

The presentation of scientific findings for specific target groups would be an added-value to help combat the problem of antibiotic resistance was promoted.

2.5 JRP16-R2-ET2.2-TELE-Vir

2.5.1 Consortium composition

Project leaders:

Anders Fomsgaard (SSI) - MD DMSc Professor, Chief of Virus Research & Development, Statens Serum Institut (SSI)

Katja Spiess (SSI) - Senior Scientist, Statens Serum Institut (SSI)

Deputy project leader:

Jovita Fernández-Pinero - Senior Scientist, Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA)

Project coordinator:

Katja Spiess (SSI)

WP1 leader:

Katja Spiess (SSI), co-leader: Miguel Angel Jiménez-Clavero - Senior Scientist Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA)

WP2 leader:

Vítor Borges - National Institute of Health Portugal, Department of Infectious Diseases (INSA), co-leader: Daniel Horton - Professor School of Veterinary Medicine, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Surrey. (UoS)

WP3 leader:

Katja Spiess (SSI), co-leader: Jovita Fernández-Pinero (INIA)

WP4 leader:

Morten Rasmussen (SSI) - Senior Scientist, Statens Serum Institut (SSI), co-leader: Katja Spiess (SSI)

2.5.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

It is crucial to address new emerging virus threats and to better control virus outbreaks. The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and the reoccurrence of emerging high virus pathogens, as for example Ebola- and West Nile virus, highlighted the importance of rapid diagnostics and improved methods to detect viruses, as early detection can assist interventive measures in order to avoid intensive outbreaks. Therefore, novel advanced virus detection methods are warranted to be prepared for future pandemics and next dangerous pathogen identification.

In the TELE-Vir project, we developed a point of incidence (POI) toolbox, for metagenomic virus detection in the field that will contribute to the identification of known viruses as well as of emerging virus threats. Metagenomic next generation sequencing (mNGS) has the ability to identify pathogens in as hypothesis-free manner compared to targeted strategies (Fomsgaard et al., J. Clin. Virol. Plus, 2(4), 100120 (2022)). This is of advantage to conventional diagnostic tests, since different pathogens can produce similar symptoms, which makes it difficult to choose for a specific (targeted) test. Moreover, our POI toolbox includes methods that can be transferred into a field setting to detect any kind of virus, in animals and humans, even in geographical areas without available laboratory infrastructure.

In work package (WP) 3 we established a **POI protocol** that includes sample pre-treatment, nucleic acids extraction, isothermal random amplification followed by non-targeted sequencing using the Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) system. It requires a minimum of laboratory equipment to be field employable and is relatively fast.

WP2 supported this approach by: 1) improving and adapting the “surveillance oriented” **INSaFLU-TELE-Vir** platform (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>) to handle sequence data (ONT, Illumina and Ion Torrent) of any virus (from reads to quality control, mutations detection, consensus generation, classification, alignments, genotype-phenotype” screening, phylogenetics, integrative phylogeographical and temporal analysis) and 2) by developing, benchmarking and implementing a novel pathogen detection module, from reads and quality control for the identification of both RNA and DNA viruses.

The POI toolbox was successfully tested in proof-of-concept studies by the TELE-Vir members (WP4), for example under different conditions in the field in Norway, South France and West Africa or by testing diverse sample material frozen and fresh material from *in vivo* laboratory studies to compare our POI protocol to well established detection methods. Sequencing data obtained from the partners performing the wet-lab activities were analysed with the INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform, as a complement to the multiple sample/virus tests performed during the tool development, benchmarking and final refinement.

We could detect a broad range of RNA as well as DNA viruses in different sample materials, proving a good symbiosis between the developed POI protocol and the INSaFLU- TELE-Vir platform, towards the deployment of a “start-to-end” framework that can potentiate strengthened timely metagenomics virus detection and routine genomics surveillance. The POI toolbox will be made publicly available and will be disseminated across national and international parties.

2.5.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Coordination and project management

WP1-T1- Coordination and project management

Project management and coordination of the project was proceeding according to the plan. The WP1 leaders organized regular meetings for the whole TELE-Vir consortium to guarantee the best outcome of the project. This is ongoing until December 2022.

WP1-T2- Data management

Data management plan (DMP) was submitted in the first year of the project (December 2020) and is updated during the project (last update until December 2022)

WP1-T3- Kick-off-meeting at IZSAM, Italy

The kick off meeting of the TELE-Vir project was held on January 21st – 22nd 2020 at the International Centre for Veterinary Training and Information "F. Gramenzi" (CIFIV) of Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell’Abruzzo e del Molise “G. Caporale” (Via G. Caporale, Teramo, Italy). All partners were present. This task is completed.

WP1-T4-1st TELE-Vir meeting online, organized by SSI

The first meeting of the TELE-Vir project was held on January 25th 2021 as an online meeting, due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. All partners were present. This task is completed.

WP1-T5-2nd TELE-Vir meeting at SSI, DK

The final annual meeting took place on the 23rd of June 2022 at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark. This task is completed

WP1-T6-Workshop in the use of the POI toolbox at SSI, DK

The workshop was organized by SSI and INSA and took place on the 23-24th of June 2022 in Copenhagen, Denmark. This task is completed

Figure 1 TELEVIR consortium met on the final annual meeting and the TELEVIR workshop to be trained for the proof of concept studies performed in WP4, where they used the POI toolbox incidences that was developed in WP2 & WP3.

WP2. Development of a bioinformatics toolkit for POI data analysis

WP2-T1- Survey and collection of databases for genotype-phenotype associations

A literature review was performed to identify coronavirus phenotypes of relevance to tropism, emergence, and clinical disease, and any data available for their prediction based on genotype. A summary was circulated to partner institutes and associated virologists, together with a survey. The aims of the survey were two-fold: (1) to obtain the views of virologists (potential end users of the POI toolbox) on coronavirus phenotype prediction and variant monitoring activities that they would like to see in a genomic surveillance toolkit; and (2) to obtain test datasets for further development of the POI toolbox. The results were reviewed and discussed in TELE-Vir internal meetings to help formulate the POI toolbox, and presented as a poster at the OHEJP ASM 2021.

As genotype-phenotype data were expanding rapidly, online databases (such as <https://sars2.cvr.gla.ac.uk/cog-uk> and <https://github.com/nodrogluap/pokay/tree/master/data>) were used to test and implement a novel mutation screening tool in the INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform (T3). Proof of concept has also been demonstrated for influenza A virus through a scoping review and construction of a comprehensive database of mutations with effect on phenotype (<https://zenodo.org/record/7455415#.Y5-QDXbP02w>). Naming and numbering conventions and a

rapidly developing field make this a complex but important exercise. Data include those from World Health Organisation antiviral susceptibility data for both avian and human influenza. This is important to demonstrate the wider potential of the tool for One Health approaches to emerging threats.

WP2-T2- Development of bioinformatics modules for third-generation sequencing analysis and pathogen identification

The implementation of metagenomic virus diagnostics and routine genomic surveillance can be particularly challenging due to the lack of bioinformatics tools and/or expertise to process and interpret next-generation sequencing (NGS) data. In order to start facing this challenge, INSA previously developed INSaFLU (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>) (Borges et al, 2018; <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-018-0555-0>), an open and user-oriented web-based bioinformatics platform for virus routine genomics surveillance. On behalf of the TELE-Vir project, and also as a response to COVID-19 pandemic and, later on, to a multi-country Monkeypox (MPXV) outbreak, the platform has been improved and adapted to better **accommodate the routine genome-based analyses of the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), influenza, MPXV and other viruses**. In summary, the main developments and achievements in T2 regarding routine genomic surveillance included:

- **Development, optimization and implementation of an automated pipeline for Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) data analysis**, from raw reads to quality analysis, consensus sequences generation/curation, mutation annotation, gene/protein/genome alignments, phylogenetic tree, metadata visualization, etc (complementing the existing pipeline for Illumina / Ion Torrent technologies).
- **Enrichment of the default reference database** with the publicly available reference genome sequence for SARS-CoV-2, MPXV and influenza;
- **Enrichment of the classification databases** with genetic markers for Human Betacoronaviruses and MPXV (complementing the existing database for rapid identification and classification of all influenza type and sub-type), and extension of this classification module to ONT data;
- **Extension of the software parameterization** (“Settings”) features, allowing users to configure key parameters for reads quality analysis, mapping and consensus generation, while making settings more flexible to handle distinct technologies and NGS data from multiple viruses.
- **Integration of novel features for automated curation of consensus sequences** (linked to T3), e.g., automatic insertion of undefined nucleotides (“N”) in low coverage regions, user-selected regions (e.g., error-prone regions) or sites where the mutation frequency is below the user-defined cut-off;
- **Integration of automatic SARS-CoV-2 Pango lineage** (<https://pangolin.cog-uk.io/>) **assignment** using Pangolin (<https://github.com/cov-lineages/pangolin>), as described by Rambaut and colleagues (Nat Microbiol; 5:1403-1407).
- **Integration of direct links to Nextclade** (<https://clades.nextstrain.org/>) for flexible SARS-CoV-2, seasonal influenza and MPXV consensus sequences analysis. This feature allows INSaFLU consensus sequences to be easily subjected to quality screening, clade classification, mutation exploration and other analyses available at the Nextclade framework.

In parallel, a brand new module for metagenomics (second- and third-generation sequencing) virus identification was developed in order to support both human and veterinary clinical practice and disease outbreak investigations. After reviewing the current state-of-the-art of the field of bioinformatics pipelines for metagenomic virus diagnostics, a modular pipeline was developed, incorporating the key steps of metagenomics taxonomic classification, namely: read quality control, viral enrichment/host-depletion, genome assembly, reads/contig classification and confirmatory reference-based remapping (Figure 2). Specifically, we tested software (such as Centrifuge, Diamond, Kaiju, Kraken2, KrakenUniq, BLAST, deSAMBA, Fastviromeexplorer, Clark) and databases (such as NCBI, RVDB, UniProt, Virosaurus) commonly used in clinical virology laboratories for metagenomics diagnostic using datasets (retrieved from literature or provided by TELE-Vir partners, namely on behalf of WP3 field studies) that have been well characterized by RT-PCR. This allowed us to benchmark the different workflows (i.e., test combinations of different components, reference databases and/or parameters) in order to finely explore how these different tools behave and, ultimately, to determine the best approach(es) to be implemented in the INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform. As expected, there is no “one-size-fits-all” approach that can detect all viruses, but a set of “well-performing” workflows that together can potentiate the detection of clinical relevant viruses. The implemented solution was precisely designed to allow users to easily run those complex workflows (covering the optimized combination of classification algorithms, databases, etc) simultaneously, and to report outputs in user-friendly visual solutions listing the most-likely suspected viruses, each accompanied by several robust and diagnostic-oriented metrics. This emphasis on the usefulness and accessibility of end-user reports serves to strengthen output interpretation and decision-making on the part of users. The integration of this new diagnosis-oriented “pathogen detection” module into the INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform is coupled with its inter-connectivity with the existing “surveillance-oriented” for an enhanced detection and monitoring of viral pathogens in an OneHealth perspective.

Figure 2 Simplified illustration of the main steps of the modular INSaFLU-TELEVIR bioinformatics pipeline for metagenomics virus diagnostics.

WP2-T3- Development of bioinformatics modules for sequence curation and phenotypic association

One of the objectives of the tool is to be able to characterize any viruses that are detected. Therefore a layer needed to be implemented is the screening of potential genotype-phenotype associations (where a genetic change is responsible for a change in the viruses pathogenicity, antigenicity or fitness). For this new module, a bioinformatics tool (“algn2pheno”) was developed (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/algn2pheno>; <https://pypi.org/project/algn2pheno/>), which takes amino acid/nucleotide alignments as input to detect and screen mutations against a database of known genotype-phenotype associations. Algn2pheno then generates a user-friendly overview of “phenotypes” predicted for each sequence. A pilot incorporation of the algn2pheno tool into the

INSaFLU platform has already been publicly released (<https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> and <https://github.com/INSaFLU/>). This functionality automatically screens SARS-CoV-2 Spike amino acid alignments in each SARS-CoV-2 project against two default databases: the COG-UK Antigenic mutations (<https://sars2.cvr.gla.ac.uk/cog-uk/>) and the Pokay Database (<https://github.com/nodrogluap/pokay/tree/master/data>). **Align2pheno then reports the full repertoire of Spike amino acid changes found in each sequence, flagging the presence of mutations of interest (and their potential impact on phenotype) included in those databases.** A standalone version of the `aln2pheno` tool was released and has already facilitated the selection of viruses in the COVRIN (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-covrin/>) project (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6784043>) showing the advantage of building bridges between ongoing One Health EJP activities to **enhance the identification of drivers for the emergence and spread of new pathogen threats and the generation of supportive data for risk assessment.** Additionally, we have investigated the feasibility of inferring biochemical and immunological properties of viruses detected at POI. In work aligned with JIP COVRIN, we have explored SARS-CoV-2 antigenic variation and its genetic determinants, using antigenic cartography analysis of published datasets as well as data received from partner SSI and the UK HSA. Antigenic distances between key SARS-CoV-2 variants have been measured using both rabbit sera in collaboration with SSI, and human vaccine sera for comparison with genetic data. We have also highlighted differences between species' responses, with implications for cross-species transmission, and between booster doses in humans, providing evidence to support public health advice (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41564-022-01163-3>).

WP2-T4- Development of bioinformatics modules for genomic and metadata integration towards enhanced surveillance

Another relevant layer of the platform update refers to the refinement/integration of (novel) functionalities for surveillance-oriented phylogenetics and geotemporal data navigation, fitting the needs of labs working in different sectors (Veterinary, Public health, etc.). In this context, INSaFLU was first upgraded to easily display metadata on existing phylogenetic trees using PhyloCanvas (<https://github.com/phylocanvas>) visual features to integrate epidemiological, clinical and/or pathogen genomic data. This INSaFLU potentiality was then substantially enhanced by the integration of Nextstrain (<https://nextstrain.org/>), allowing an **advanced exploration of phylogenomic data together with geotemporal data (or any other relevant metadata)**. Currently, INSaFLU allows running “generic” or virus-specific Nextstrain builds (seasonal Influenza, SARS-CoV-2 and Monkeypox), while providing flexibility to integrate sequences generated in the platform as well as external sequences (e.g., from GenBank or GISAID). Other functionalities for improved data navigation and interpretation were also implemented, such as the inclusion of novel interactive and dynamic panels for enhanced report of: i) all detected mutations (including information about genome position, nucleotide change, coverage evidence, frequency, impact at protein level, etc); ii) coverage (depth and breadth) per locus for all samples; iii) “`aln2pheno`” mutations potentially linked to known phenotypes (see WP2-T3). In interaction with the One Health EJP BeOne project (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-beone/>), work is ongoing to incorporate ReporTree (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>), which is a flexible pipeline that facilitates the detection of pathogen genetic clusters and their linkage with surveillance (clinical /epidemiological) metadata.

WP2-T5-development of a user and surveillance oriented web-based interface

In direct linkage with T2-T4 tasks, this task aimed at continuously optimizing the user interface for a broad audience, not only bioinformaticians, but also other scientists (e.g., virologists, epidemiologists) or decision makers with little computational background. This “front-end” work was complemented with the improvement of the “back-end” computational capacities and queue management in the online tool. The development and public distribution of a locally installable version (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/docker>) at beginning of the project was particularly relevant towards the ultimate deployment of a bioinformatics toolbox that also fits the needs for field studies and labs

working in different sectors (Veterinary, Public health, etc.). Altogether, **fully aligned with the OneHealth concept, the described INSaFLU functionality, versatility and user-friendliness can supply public health laboratories and researchers with start-to-end bioinformatics framework that can potentiate a strengthened and timely metagenomics virus detection and routine genomics surveillance.** INSaFLU updates were documented (<https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>) and uploaded to Github (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/>), being available in the online (<https://insaflu.insa.pt>) and locally installable (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/docker>) versions, with users, TELE-Vir partners and other stakeholders (e.g., ECDC) being notified of all novel features.

WP3. Development of a protocol for POI MiniON sequencing

In WP3 we developed the POI protocol for untargeted (metagenomics) detection of viruses. The protocol included the following working steps: 1) virus inactivation to be able to work with high pathogenic viruses, 2) pretreatment (host depletion), 3) nucleic acids extraction, 4) random amplification and 5) library preparation for MiniON sequencing.

WP3-T1- Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment Fast and easy field-deployable inactivation method for SARS-CoV-2 (and other viruses) using MPLB-buffer.

We tested if we can successfully inactivate RNA/DNA virus, before we performing the WP4 studies (proof of concept/field studies). This was necessary, as it is possible that diseased animals and humans are infected with highly pathogenic viruses. We further agreed in the TELE-Vir consortium, that we would use personal protective equipment during the proof of concept studies/field studies performed in WP4.

Previous studies have shown virus inactivation abilities, including Ebola Virus of the highly cytotoxic MagNA Pure Lysis Binding (MPLB) buffer used for nucleic acid extraction and purification (Rosenstierne et al. *Journal of clinical microbiology*. 2016 Oct;54(10):2521-9 ; Vinner and Fomsgaard, 2007. *Journal of virological methods*, 146(1-2), pp.401-404.).

Proof- of concept study 1 – virus inactivation

The virucidal activity of MagNA Pure Lysis Binding (MPLB) buffer used at the concentrations recommended by producer as well as at its lower concentrations was assessed against selected animal virus species (canine adenovirus type 2, canine coronavirus, myxoma virus) and human hepatitis A virus (HAV). Depending on the virus species, MPLB-buffer was able to efficiently inactivate all tested viruses even at lower than recommended buffer concentrations ranging from 15% to 30 %. Among the tested viruses the most resistant virus species to inactivation was HAV. The minimal buffer concentration required to inactivate the virus was 30%. Additionally, efficiency of AL and AVL lysis buffers in virus inactivation was also tested. Regardless the tested buffer type and applied temperature-time conditions, except myxoma virus a minimal 4 log reduction of the virus titres was observed.

Proof-of concept study 2 – virus inactivation

In this study, a protocol was developed to test the inactivation activity of two buffers: MPLB (Roche) and eNAT™ (Copan) against a bovine Beta-CoV (Bov-CoV strain 9WBL77). The eNAT buffer is a guanidine-thiocyanate-based medium that stabilises virus RNA and DNA. The Bov-CoV strain belongs to the same genus as SARS-CoV-2 but can be propagated in BSL2 structures and was therefore used as a model to validate virus inactivation using different inactivation buffers. The protocol is based on ultracentrifugation of the virus + buffer mixture to remove the toxic effect of the inactivation buffer on cell cultures. For the inactivation protocols using MPLB and eNAT buffers, a virus titre (10⁵ TCID₅₀/ml) and contact time (30min) were used. After 30 minutes of contact time, the three samples: 1- control virus (virus + MEM), 2- virus + MPLB and 3 -virus + eNAT were ultracentrifuged in a sucrose

cushion (100,000 g / 2 h) to remove the toxic supernatant. The pellets of samples 1, 2 and 3 were resuspended in the same volume of PBS and then titrated in HRT-18 cells.

Results. Titration in Hrt18 of the three samples (the non-inactivated virus sample as control and the two virus samples inactivated with MPLB and eNAT) demonstrated the inactivating power of both buffers. The results of the viral titration are: Sample 1 (virus control): 10^5 TCID₅₀/ml, sample 2 (MPLB): < 10 TCID₅₀/ml and sample 3 (eNAT): < 10 TCID₅₀/ml. In conclusion, the inactivating power of the MPLB and eNAT buffers against a beta-CoV under test conditions was highlighted.

Proof-of concept study 3 – virus inactivation

In this study, we show how 20 minutes of incubation in MPLB-buffer at room-temperature produce rapid inactivation of the SARS-CoV-2 using a modified published protocol by Rosenstierne et al (2016).

Two human SARS-CoV-2 isolates of 10^5 and 10^6 Tissue Culture Infectious Dose₅₀/ml were incubated 1:1 with MPLB-buffer or PBS (positive controls) for 20 minutes. The mixture was diluted to non-cytotoxic MPLB-buffer concentrations (determined empirically) and incubated on VeroE6 cells. We serially passaged supernatant from a 144h culture and measured active replicating virus at the 24h time-point with a SARS-CoV-2 E-gene RT-qPCR

Results. MPLB-buffer incubated SARS-CoV-2 samples were non-infectious in the 10^{-4} MPLB-buffer dilution, except three samples indicated by median Ct-value 39.8 (IQR=4.8) from the 10^5 TCID₅₀/ml stock. The control grew efficiently with median Ct-values 11.8 (IQR=1.8) for cells and 16.1 (IQR=1.8) for supernatant. The sub-genomic RT-qPCR for the 24h time-point showed no evidence for virus replication, including the three exceptive samples.

We showed that MPLB-buffer inhibits SARS-CoV-2 replication and inactivates next to the previous published Ebola virus, RNA and DNA from different species as human hepatitis A virus and canine corona virus, even at lower buffer concentration as recommended by the manufacture. With the MPLB buffer, we can facilitate POI-diagnosis and promote field research without risk of infection. Therefore, we implemented this step into our POI protocol and into the SOP for sample handling & pre-treatment (this SOP was described together with the protocol for NA purification (see next paragraph).

WP3-T2- Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample pre-treatment and NA purification

The proportion of viral genomes can be very small compared to the host-genomes and other nucleic acids in a given clinical sample. This “viral needle in the metagenomic haystack” can be troublesome. Therefore, we included a host depletion step with a DNase treatment step followed by filtration into the POI protocol. We tested clinical samples containing the RNA virus SARS-CoV2 and the DNA virus human papilloma virus (HPV), as well as mixed infected samples HPV with molluscum contagiosum virus (MCV). We demonstrated that DNase treatment together with a filtration step increased the proportion of SARS-CoV-2 sequenced reads > 500-fold compared to no pre-treatments. SARS-CoV-2 samples, tested positive previously by PCR, that had a CT below 33 achieved a high reference sequence cover (>56.6-100%) after only 180 minutes. We applied the same protocol for HPV, to access the detection ability of the POI protocol towards DNA viruses. HPV was detected in 7 out of 8 samples within 180 minutes of sequencing with almost full coverage (92.9- 100%) (Fomsgaard et al., *J. Clin. Virol. Plus*, 2(4), 100120 (2022).

The MPLB buffer proved to be highly efficient in inactivating DNA/RNA viruses (WP3-T1), but is also a standard buffer for nucleic acids (NA) extraction and purification. We used this buffer in a hand extraction method, where magnetic glass particles with bound RNA/DNA are captured by a small magnet. This field deployable method has been published previously (Rosenstierne et al. *JoVE*, (136), 2018). We tested successfully this NA extraction method on grown SARS-CoV-2 isolates and HPV samples and included it afterwards into our POI protocol (Fomsgaard et al., *J. Clin. Virol. Plus*, 2(4), 100120 (2022).

WP3-T3- Development and validation of a S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing (DNA & RNA)

In order to amplify the amount of viral components in a clinical sample without any targeted pathogen selection, we introduced a random amplification step in our POI protocol before library preparation. Here we used REPLI-G Cell WGA & WGA Kit from Qiagen, which allows parallel whole transcriptome amplification for RNA viruses and whole genome amplification for DNA viruses. Next, we tested different library preparation- as well as Oxford-Nanopore protocols.

Initial testing:

Porcine astroviruses

Well-characterized porcine fecal sample obtained from one of the SPF pig farms in Sweden, which contained infection with several porcine astrovirus (PoAstV) species, were tested. The samples were homogenized in TE buffer before DNase and filtration treatment. Total nucleic acids (TNA) were extracted using MagNA Pure LC Total Nucleic Acid Isolation Kit (Roche) according to the manufacturer's instructions. TNA were diluted in 100 µl of Elution Buffer and 10 µl containing magnetic glass particles (MGPs) were aliquoted for the REPLI-G Single Cell Kit (24) (Qiagen) whole transcriptome (WTA) amplification using. As PoAstV is an RNA virus, whole genome amplification was not performed. REPLI-g WTA included the following steps: cleanup, repair, reverse transcription, ligation and amplification. Rapid Barcoding kit SQK-RB004 from the Oxford Nanopore Technologies were used in library preparation according to the manufacturer's instructions and MinION sequencing. MGPs were not included in the library preparation. Data analysis showed that very few of the sequenced reads (less than 0,3%) were from Astroviruses but still several Astroviruses were detected by the method.

African swine fever

Two different protocols for MinION sequencing of African swine fever virus (ASFV) directly from positive samples were tested. After quality and quantity check of genomic DNA (gDNA) by Agilent tapestation and Qubit fluorometer, we used two different library preparation kits, Rapid Barcoding Kit 96 (SQK-RBK110.96) and a combination of Ligation Sequencing Kit (SQK-LSK110) and Native Barcoding Kit 24 (SQK-NBD112.24) for multiplexing samples. Rapid Barcoding Kit 96 (SQK-RBK110.96) is a PCR-free method that eliminate PCR bias and retains base modification information. This kit requires 50 ng of input DNA in a total volume of 9 ul per sample and takes less than 60 minutes. Ligation Sequencing Kit (SQK-LSK110) is optimized for throughput and long reads. The protocol includes DNA ends repair and dA-tailed using the NEBNext End Repair/dA-tailing module, and ligation of sequencing adapters onto the prepared ends. For this kit the input DNA is 1 ug in a total volume of 47 ul per sample and the protocol takes about 2 hours. After priming the flowcell R9.4.1 (FLO-MIN106), we loaded the pool libraries and operated onto MinKNOW software to set-up the run parameters. We selected 24 hours as run time and Fast basecalling as Basecall model for both libraries. After starting run, we launch Fastq WIMP analysis on EPI2ME platform for taxonomic classification of the reads. We could detect African swine fever following this protocol

Based on the initial testing and gaining experience we further developed the library preparation and sequencing strategy by testing the human papilloma virus (HPV) and molluscum contagiosum virus (MCV) (DNA virus) and SARS-CoV-2 (RNA virus) applying the following steps:

A multiplexed approach was tested, where 4 and 12 individual samples were multiplexed using the Rapid Barcoding Kit (SQK-RBK004, Oxford Nanopore Technology). The DNA concentrations of the samples were determined using a Qubit Fluorometer (Life Technologies) and used to normalize the input material for sequencing libraries, as our field employable spectrometer was still a prototype. The POI protocol together with the Rapid Barcoding Kit correctly detected SARS-COV-2 in nasopharyngeal swabs with CT-values below 33 and correctly typed HPV-types in samples containing multiple HPV types. This protocol also correctly detected co-infection of two different DNA viruses in the same sample (HPV and MCV) (Fomsgaard et al., *J. Clin. Virol. Plus*, 2(4), 100120 (2022).

For the final protocol a single sample approach using the Rapid Sequencing Kit (SQK-RAD004) was tested and validated. Individual clinical samples containing either SARS-CoV-2 or HPV was loaded on R9.4.1 flowcells and sequenced on the MinION device, with fast basecalling and a run length of up to 20 hours. The POI protocol together with the Rapid Sequencing Kit correctly detected expected library prepared viruses.

In WP3 we developed a POI protocol that contains virus inactivation, NA extraction, DNase pretreatment, random amplification, library preparation- and a sequencing protocol for metagenomics detection of RNA/DNA viruses. The steps of the POI protocol are described in the standard operation protocol (SOPs) for WP3 that were uploaded to Zenodo (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.5506815](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5506815); DOI [10.5281/zenodo.5506847](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5506847); DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7357506](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7357506)). For the proof of concept studies in WP3 we used the Rapid Sequencing Kit for RNA/DNA viruses detection, as it is field employable. In a potential outbreak situation, a sample can be taken from one human/animal with clinical signs or can be pooled if the clinical signs align and be successfully detected by our POI toolbox in the field.

WP4. Testing of the POI toolbox in the field

After successfully establishing the POI protocol (WP3) and the bioinformatics infrastructure (WP2), we tested our POI toolbox in proof of concept studies performed by nine TELE-Vir partners (WP4) that were supported by the bioinformatics team (WP2). One partner left the TELE-Vir project with the Y3 due to responsibilities during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic (Daniel Ruzek, VRI, Czech Republic), but the TELE-Vir partners agreed to compensate his work, by collecting and testing additional samples. The TELE-Vir-partners were trained how to use the POI toolbox (WP3) during the TELE-Vir-workshop in June 2022, SSI, Copenhagen.

In the proof of concept studies performed in WP4 we wanted to test a higher amount of samples as well as different sample materials. Therefore, we used in WP4 the Rapid Barcoding Kit SQK-RBK004 (Oxford Nanopore Technology), that also proved being successful for detecting SARS-CoV-2 and African Swine Fever Virus (see WP3-T3), as the Rapid Sequencing Kit is very expensive and not suitable for testing a larger amount of samples. A requirement for the Rapid Barcoding Kit is a quantification of RNA/DNA before library preparation. As this is challenging in the field we quantified the RNA/DNA with non-field employable devices, but also developed a field employable transilluminator and a visual and computer aided detection method (to be published).

Some of the TELE-Vir partners applied further changes to the POI protocol for example based on their existing laboratory structure. To be able to compare the results we categorized them in the table below:

Table 1 Classification of changes applied to the POI protocol

WP 4	
minor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • filter pore size changed • frozen sample material • Rapid Barcoding kit • use of a non-field-employable RNA/DNA quantification device (e.g. spectrometer)
major	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no or additional filtration steps • no pretreatment with DNase • extraction-, random amplification or- sequencing method changed

- additional purification steps after the random amplification step

We included into the table and graphs presented in WP4 only results that were generated following the POI protocol or applied only minor changes.

WP4 proof of concept studies performed by the TELE-Vir consortium (not all TELE-Vir partners contributed to the proof of concept studies, as described in the deliverables, some contributed only to the WP2 and WP3 development):

TELE-Vir partner - **ANSES**

TELE-Vir members : **D. Flores & L. Bigarré**

Aim: In order to identify viruses in sick fish, two studies were conducted on different models 1) Carp oedema poxvirus (CEV) and 2) Sturgeon mimiviruses

Samples: Study 1: swabs were obtained from gills of a carp during a mortality event in a lake in France. Study 2: tissues (gills) were obtained in a sturgeon farm strongly affected by mortalities two months before our visit.

Modifications POI protocol: YES - major modifications (table 1). Changes: pretreatment pore-size of filter (minor change) and different kit for NA extraction method (major change)

Conclusions: Expected DNA virus detected. One issue is the very low ratio *target/other DNA* (host, bacteria, phages, etc.) which is difficult to overcome to detect DNA viruses in fish.

TELE-Vir partner – **PIWET**

TELE-Vir members – **A. Rzeżutka & I. Kozyra & A. Kaupke**

Aim: Detection of aleutian mink disease virus (AMDV) and zoonotic hepatitis E virus (HEV) in wild boar

Samples: *Study 1:* swab samples of mink origin were collected from different farm environments. *Study 2:* an archive sample of wild boar organ homogenate was used

Modifications POI protocol: NO

Conclusion: Using the POI protocol AMDV was detected in three out of four tested samples. The presence of HEV was not confirmed. Failures in virus detection during sequencing could be due to degradation or inefficient amplification of viral DNA/RNA during WTA & WGA step.

TELE-Vir partner – **INIA**

TELE-Vir members – **Jovita Fernández-Pinero & Pilar Aguilera-Sepúlveda**

Aim: To evaluate the capacity of the POI toolbox for viral detection by testing experimentally infected animals and a human patient with neurological symptoms.

Samples: Feathers and oral swabs (freshly taken) from 5 infected partridges that showed moderate or mild symptoms compatible with a WNV infection and 1 human RNA sample (frozen material) with an unknown infection.

Modifications of POI protocol: Study 1: YES - minor modifications (table 1). Changes: RNA/DNA quantification device was used (Quantus). Study 2: YES - minor and major modifications (table 1). Minor changes: RNA/DNA quantification device was (Quantus) and Nanopore Rapid Barcoding kit were used. Major changes: different kit for NA extraction method (IndiSpin Pathogen Kit, INDICAL).

Conclusion: Expected virus were detected in the partridges (following POI protocol or alternative NA extraction protocol). None virus was detected for the human sample. One issue is the low ratio

target/other DNA (host, bacteria, phages, etc.). Quantification is an essential step, especially by following the Nanopore Rapid Barcoding kit in order to load the same amount of DNA/cDNA of the samples.

TELE-Vir partner – **IZLER**

TELE-Vir member – **Ana Moreno**

Aim of the field study was to test the POI protocol under different field scenarios collecting samples from wildlife and domestic animals.

Samples: Group 1. Turkeys with respiratory signs positive for avian metapneumovirus (aMPV): 20 tracheal swabs analyzed in 5 pools of 4 swabs.

Group 2- Nasal swabs from two cattle with slight nasal discharge but negative to bovine respiratory viruses.

Group 3- Mallard hunted: Cloacal swab positive for avian influenza A by real-time PCR.

Group 4- Homogenised lung of a pig with respiratory symptoms positive to influenza A (sw IAV H1N1).

Modifications POI protocol: NO

Methods: 5 samples (group 1) tested using a flow cell and the barcoding protocol. Two samples (group 2) and 1 sample (group 3) tested using the fast sequencing kit and a flow cell for each sample.

Modifications POI protocol: Yes – minor change

Methods: Group 4 tested using the POI Protocol but with an additional filtration step (0.22 µM filter) before DNase treatment.

Results: Fastq files were uploaded to the [INSaFLU-TELEVIR](#) platform. Group 1: aMPV was detected in WTA in pools 1 and 4 with Kaiju integrated in the INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform, but no read hits were recovered after re-mapping. Group 4: Pathogen characterization analysis using targeted re-mapping by the INSaFLU platform showed a SwIAV H1N1. Other porcine viruses were also detected in the WGA protocol such as TorqueTeno sus virus 1a and 1b, PPV7, PCV3 3 and porcine endogenous retrovirus. Group 3: the expected virus was not detected. Group 2: no viruses expected.

Conclusions: Small percentage of viral readings (<1%) obtained in all samples. High bacterial contamination could be expected, and for group 4 it was decided to filter the sample before DNase to eliminate bacterial DNA contamination. Thus, in clinical samples with high potential bacteria concentrations an additional filtration step should be included into the POI protocol.

TELE-Vir partner – **IZSAM**

TELE-Vir member – **Maurilia Marcacci**

Aim: Starting from September 2021, several outbreaks sustained by Epizootic hemorrhagic disease virus serotype 8 (EHDV-8) in cattle and deer have been described in Tunisia.

Samples: The field study was performed in Tunisia from 17th to 21st October 2022. During our mission, veterinary services reported the onset of Bluetongue-like clinical signs (which included fever, conjunctivitis, lacrimation, drooling, etc) in four cattle farms, two located in Grombalia district and two in Sidi Daoud village. A total of five whole blood samples were collected from animals showing clinical signs.

Modifications POI protocol: YES- minor modifications

Methods: We used POI protocol with some modifications. NA purification was performed without sample filtration as this virus is attached to the surface of the red blood cells. DNase incubation was carried out directly on purified RNA.

Results: The analysis performed by INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform assigned 11 reads for sample1, 543 reads for sample2, 80 reads for sample3, 86 reads for sample4 and 44 reads for sample5 to EHDV species.

Conclusion: The analysis successfully identified the viral species (EHDV) involved in the infection .

Swinepox virus lab study

Aim On September 2022, a domestic pig died in a pig farm in Abruzzi region, Italy. The piglet showed skin lesions consisting of multiple crusted pustules, suggestive for of poxvirus infection.

Sample Tissue sample with skin lesion. The proof of concept study was conducted in the IZSAM laboratories

Modifications of POI protocol: NO

Methods: After NA purification, we used DNA for library preparation by Nanopore Rapid Barcoding kit

Results: The analysis performed by INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform assigned 67 reads to Swinepox virus and 12 reads to Porcine parvovirus. Swinepox virus is compatible with the clinical lesions observed in that piglet while Porcine parvovirus is endemic in most swine herds.

Conclusion: In both studies the POI protocol combined with analysis performed by INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform identified viral species involved in clinical manifestations starting from different specimens (whole blood and tissue) collected from cattle and pig.

TELE-Vir partner – [UoS](#)

TELE-Vir members : **D. Horten & Guido Cordino**

Aim A study on found-dead wild animals in a Zoological collection in the UK

Samples, Oral and rectal swabs were taken from six different previously frozen animal carcasses.

Modifications of POI protocol: Yes – minor changes - samples were quantified using a nanodrop and field employable transilluminator and a visual and computer aided detection method

Conclusions human, bacteria (E.coli) and phages sequences were detected but no RNA viruses. The quantification indicated a probable high level of chemicals carry over (O.D. values above 2500 ng/ul).

TELE-Vir partner - [SSI](#)

TELE-Vir members : **M. Rasmussen & Anna S. Fomsgaard**

Aim: To screen animal species in Copenhagen Zoo for viruses.

Samples The samples were taken opportunistically from the enclosures and at the zoo's veterinarian clinic.

Modifications of POI protocol: YES - minor modifications. Change: Rapid Barcoding kit was used (minor change).

Conclusion: The POI protocol was easily installed at the location. Out of 53 samples from 17 species, the POI protocol detected virus in 18 samples from 10 species, however, the freshness of sample material seemed crucial for viral detection success. Frozen samples are not realistic in a field setting but a suggestion is to omit the DNase step for frozen samples.

TELE-Vir partner - [SVA](#)

TELE-Vir members: **Tobias Lilja, Mikhayil Hakhverdyan & Lihong Liu**

Aim: To screen poultry fecal samples, to identify porcine circovirus (PCV) in wild boar

Samples: Fecal samples from poultry, lung tissue from wild boar.

Modifications of POI protocol: YES – minor modifications (Table 1). 1). DNase pretreatment was followed homogenization and filtration steps; 2) Nanopore Rapid Barcoding kit was used.

Methods: After suspension of the fecal samples and homogenization of the tissue sample the POI protocol was followed. The Rapid Barcoding kit was used for library preparation.

Results: The poultry samples gave more than a million reads over 48 hours detecting DNA and RNA viruses.

Conclusions: PCV was not detected most likely for two reasons: 1) Low virus concentration and overrepresentation of host DNA; 2) A sharp decrease in the active pores of flow cell due to the so-called “branching” of DNA after 6 hours of sequencing. Instead, porcine parvovirus (PPV) was detected but it was not included in the aim of the study, which confirms the assumption that the POI protocol works well for samples where the virus concentration is high enough.

TELE-Vir partner - *NVI*

TELE-Vir member : *Øivind Øines*

Aim(s): a) To test fecal samples from birds for viruses in random environmental fecal samples to become familiarized with the POI toolbox, **b)** to test known positive samples for Newcastle Disease Virus with the POI protocol and finally **c)**, to apply the POI toolbox on samples with unknown aetiology.

Samples The samples were **a)** taken opportunistically from the environment, **b)** taken on dead birds by pathologist or other trained specialists as part of routine diagnostics at the pathology unit and **c)** on live animals in animal facilities.

Modifications of POI protocol: YES - minor modifications (table 1) for POC **a),b) & c)** . Changes: Larger filter pores (80µm) and Nanopore Rapid Barcoding kit was used (minor change) For **b)/c)** YES - major modifications as no initial DNA-se treatment was performed.

Conclusion: The POI protocol was in **a)** carried out in field-like conditions partly running PCR and sequence instrument on battery power, and slightly changed to accommodate for multiple samples. In **a)** a number of viral signals from environmental/feed sources was found. For **b)/c)** the POI protocol was performed in lab, and with samples from different sampels obtained from two outbreak cases; one set of samples from a known viral pathogen where qPCR results were available **b)**, and for samples in **c)** an unknown viral agent. In **b)** one of the samples were positive for the correct virus, but other samples that contained less viral load, had only some low level og viral signals in the results, indicating that the POI as it was carried out resulted in a low limit of detection (LOD) when compared to qPCR. For POC **c)** some relevant viral sequences have been identified in the data, which come from a relevant group of virus but this is currently being investigated (pending conclusion).

The POI toolbox worked in general well in our proof of concept studies in WP4 (see **table 2** below). Our POI toolbox is generated to react fast to virus outbreaks. Therefore, it is crucial to work with fresh sample material. Here we got the best results (see study from INIA and SSI). However, it was not possible to collect fresh sample material for example in mink farm that were affected during the pandemic. Moreover, some of the TELE-Vir partners will still need time to repeat the proof of concept studies to fully establish the POI protocol in their laboratories. TELE-Vir partner that already had experience in performing metagenomic sequencing, could apply succesfully the POI toolbox and offered to test samples in parallel from TELE-Vir partners with less experience to compare their results in the future. This was discussed and agreed on in our regular TELE-Vir meetings.

Table 2 Overview WP4 of the sample host, sample material, detection methods and results applying the POI toolbox

TELEVIR partner	Species - sample material (number of samples)	Virus (RNA/DNA virus) detected by target method (e.g. PCR/microarray)	Virus target detection method (if applicable)	Expected virus or virus hits detected by the TELEVIR POI toolbox (metagenomics detection)
PIWET (n=5)	1. mink - faecal swap -frozen (n=4)	1. Aleutian mink disease virus (AMDV)	1. PCR	1. YES (2/3 samples); YES* (1/2 samples)
	2. wild boar - liver-frozen (n=1)	2. Hepatitis E (swine) genotype 3 + Porcine circovirus 2 or 12a	2. microarray	2. YES (expected viruses 2/3);non expected viruses also detected
INIA (n=8)	1. red-legged partridge -feather fresh (n=6)	1. West Nile Virus (WNV) lineage 1 or 2	1. + 2. Real-time qPCR. - Virus detected (WNV-L1 or WNV-L2)	1. + 2. YES (7/7 samples)
	2. red-legged partridge -oral swap fresh (n=1)	2. West Nile Virus (WNV) lineage 1		
	3. human peripheral blood - plasma frozen (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	3. NO
IZLER (n=9)	1. turkey - tracheal swab (fresh) (n=5)	1. Avian pneumovirus (aMPV)	1.+2.+3. 4. PCR	1. YES* (1/3 samplest), NO (2/3 samples)
	2. cattle - nasal swab (fresh) (n=2)	2. neg PCR result		2. NO
	3. mallard -nasal swab (fresh) (n=1)	3.+ 4. Influenza A virus		3. NO
	4. pig- lung tissue (frozen) (n=1)			4. YES
IZAM (n=15)	1. cattle- whole blood (frozen) (n=10)	1. + 2. Epizootic haemorrhagic disease virus (EHDV)	1. PCR	1. + 2. + 3. YES (15/15 samples)
	2. cattle- whole blood (fresh) (n=4)		2. clincial signs	
	3. pig- skin lesion (frozen) (n=1)	3. Swinepox virus	3. clinical signs	
UoS (n=10)	1. rat- oral swab - frozen (n=2)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	1. + 2. NO
	2. pigeon- oral swab - frozen (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	
	3. rabbit- oral swab - frozen (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	
	4. blackbird-oral swab - frozen (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	
	5. rat- rectal swab - frozen (n=2)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	
	6. pigeon- rectal swab - frozen (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	
	7. rabbit- rectal swab - frozen (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	
	8. blackbird-rectal swab - frozen (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A	
SSI (n=53)	1. Asian Elephant - serum- frozen (n=2)	Elephant endotheliotropic herpesvirus (EEHV)-3/4 or EEHV-1	Real-time qPCR. Microarray - Virus detected (only EEHV-1 sample)	1. YES (EEHV-1) (1/2 samples)
	2. Asian Elephant - pericardial fluid- frozen (n=3)	EEHV-3/4	Real-time qPCR. Microarray - No virus detected	2. NO
	3. Asian Elephant -heart biopsi- frozen (n=2)	EEHV-1	Real-time qPCR. Microarray - Virus detected	3. YES (EEHV-1) (1/2 samples)
	4. Ball Python - full blood- frozen (n=2)	Adeno snake virus in 1/2	Real-time qPCR (1/2). Microarray - No virus detected.	4. NO
	5. Horse -nasal swab- fresh (n=4)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - No virus detected (3/4 analysed)	5. YES (3/4 samples)
	6. Crested Pidgeon - cloacal swab - fresh (n=2)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - No virus detected	6. NO
	7. Vari - anal swab - fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - No virus detected	7. NO
	8. Armur Leopad - feces - fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - No virus detected	8. NO
	9. Two-toed sloth - mouth and/or nasal swab- fresh (n=4)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - viruses detected (2/4)	9. YES (2/4 samples)
	10. Two-toed sloth -feces- fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - Viruses detected	10. YES
	11. Rock Wallaby -feces- fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - No virus detected	11. NO
	12. Hippopotamus -mouth swab- fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - No virus detected	12. NO
	13. Hippopotamus -feces- fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - No virus detected	13. NO
	14. Chimpanzee -mouth swap- fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	Microarray - Viruses detected	14. YES
	15. Gibbon -mouth swap- fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	15. NO
	16. Gibbon -fecal swab- fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	16. YES
	17. Hamaydrian baboon- fecal swap (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	17. YES
	18. Egyptian fruit bat - mouth swap- fresh (n=8)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	18. YES
	19. Egyptian fruit bat - serum- fresh (n=8)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	19. NO
	20. Egyptian fruit bat -urin swab- fresh (n=2)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	20. NO
	21. Goat -nasal swab- fresh (n=3)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	21. YES
	22. Pig -nasal swab - fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	22. YES
	23. Chicken -fecal swab - fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	23. YES
	24. Lama -fecal swab - fresh (n=1)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	24. NO
SVA (n=2)	1. Wild boar - lung- frozen (n=1)	Porcine circovirus (PCV)	Real-time qPCR/Illumina MiSeq	1. NO
	poultry -feces fresh (n=1)	Infectious bronchitis virus (IBV)	prior live vaccine	2. NO
NVI (n=44)	1. Seagulls/geese-fecal swabs-fresh (n=22) ct	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	N.A.	N.A. ^b
	2. Chicken/pidgeon-trachea swabs-fresh (n=7)	Avian paramyxovirus	1 Realtime PCR	N.A.
	3. Reindeer-genital/eye swabs-fresh (n=11)	Screening. Presence of virus unknown prior to POI protocol	2. Clinical signs	N.A.

YES = virus(es) detected (either expected or non-expected)

YES* = expected virus(es) detected in a intermediate step of the pipeline, but with a number of hits below the cut-off.

NO = no virus detected

^b sequences to be evaluated

2.5.4 Project self-assessment

We developed successfully in the TELE-Vir project a harmonized and standardized POI protocol for identification and characterization of emerging virus threats. We met all initial project objectives, but we got delayed in achieving our milestones and deliverables, due to the ongoing SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. The TELE-Vir-members are experts in the field of virology and their expertise and research was needed during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Moreover, most laboratories were closed to prioritize SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics in 2020/21 and reagents were running short, which also challenged the development of the TELE-Vir wet-lab activities. Regarding the bioinformatics component of the POI (WP2), it was also challenging to develop this work in the context of research field in continuous technological evolution (microbial genomics and metagenomics). In another perspective, the final platform functionalities also benefitted from the real-time software and data sharing at international level during the pandemic, leading to the integration of cutting-edge and state-of-the art bioinformatics features and resources. In summary, the TELE-VIR consortium could overcome these main challenges and we could establish the TELE-Vir POI toolbox, including a field-employable POI protocol for sample inactivation, nucleic acid extraction, random RNA/DNA amplification, NGS library preparation and Oxford next generation sequencing (WP3), and an open and user-oriented “start-to-end” bioinformatics framework for metagenomic virus detection and routine genomic surveillance (WP2). In our proof-of-concept studies we tested our POI toolbox and we could detect RNA/DNA viruses in different sample materials of different species. However, a disadvantage of applying an unbiased (metagenomics) virus detection can be a reduced sensitivity. Our POI toolbox is developed to detect virus infections in diseased animals and humans that have clinical signs. In this case, the virus load is normally high in these hosts, which will make it possible with our POI protocol to detect the virus. During the initial testing phase, we could detect SARS-CoV-2 virus with our POI protocol that we tested before by Real-time PCR with a CT below 33 (See WP3-T3). Similar results were reported during the proof of concept studies (WP4) by the TELE-Vir partner INIA that successfully detected with the POI protocol West-Nile virus in samples tested positive with a CT around 30. These results support evidence that in clinical sample material with a high virus load we can apply our POI toolbox (wet-lab protocol and bioinformatics platform) and not only to successfully detect viruses, but also to generate (near) complete viral genome sequences. The choice of the sample material might be critical for the success of applying the POI toolbox. It was of importance to work with fresh sample material stored in the MPLB buffer, as this buffer blocks enzyme activity and thereby degradation of the RNA and DNA within the sample. Moreover, TELE-Vir partners that had prior knowledge in metagenomics detection of viruses performed better in applying the POI protocol. Thus, the TELE-Vir POI toolbox (both wet- and dry-lab components) requires training. Indeed, it is a method with a protocol with multiple steps, which is sensitive to changes and the evaluation of the sequencing results requires knowledge. However, we propose that metagenomics detection of viruses is a future milestone for virus diagnostics and with our POI toolbox we establish the knowledge or deepened it in 10 EU laboratories. This knowledge can now be spread by a technology transfer and training in additional laboratories and countries and could be the ground stone for future advanced development of this POI toolbox in hand with ongoing development of new sequencing strategies, contributing to unbiased virus detection in biodiverse regions with low or no infrastructure.

2.5.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
16	D-JRP16-1.1	Kick-off meeting in Italy (IZSAM)	M25	M25	Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734134#.Xwbj0Sgza70 Milestone reached by M25 on time	1
16	D-JRP16-1.2	1st version of the DMP	M30	M30	Milestone reached by M30 on time	1
16	D-JRP16-WP1.3	1st TELE-Vir meeting (online)	M37	M37	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5506645#.YUSEcLgza70 Milestone reached by M37 on time	1
16	D-JRP16-WP1.4	2nd version of the DMP	M42	M46	Zenodo link – will be inserted until the end of 2022	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
16	D-JRP16-WP1.5	2 nd TELE-Vir meeting (Copenhagen, SSI)	M54	M54	The 2 nd TELE-Vir meeting took take place as planned see work plan- June 2022	1
16	D-JRP16-WP1.6	Workshop in the use of the POI-toolbox (Copenhagen, SSI)	M54	M54	The workshop took place as planned see work plan- June 2022	1
16	D-JRP16-WP2.1	Open-sourced bioinformatics platform that allows the user-friendly handling of high-throughput sequencing data (second and third generation) for detection and monitoring of viral emerging threats	M57	M60	Deliverable reached and published https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7443398	1, 2, 3, 4, 5
16	D-JRP16-3.1	1st version of a poi S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment	M36	M39	Deliverable reached and published https://zenodo.org/record/5506816#.YUSElbgza70	2
16	D-JRP16-3.2	1st version of a poi S.O.P for sample NA purification	M36	M39	Deliverable reached and published	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
					https://zenodo.org/record/5506848#.YUSFD7gza70	
16	D-JRP16-WP3.3	Final version of a poi S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing	M54-60	M58	Deliverable reached and published DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7357506	2
16	D-JRP16-WP3.4	Report on the validation of MinION sequencing mimicking the field scenario in lab conditions	M59	M60	Deliverable reached and published DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	2
	D-JRP16-WP4.1	Proof-of-concept performed (animal 1, syndrome 1, Sweden)- NVA	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1
	D-JRP16-WP4.2	Proof-of-concept performed (animal 2, syndrome 2, Poland) - PIWET	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
	D-JRP16-WP4.3	Proof-of-concept performed (salmonid, cardiopathies, France)-ANSES	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1
	D-JRP16-WP4.4	Proof-of-concept performed (cattle and equids, vector borne diseases, to be conducted in Africa)- IZSAM	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1
	D-JRP16-WP4.5	Proof-of-concept performed (animal 5, syndrome 5, Spain)- INIA	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1
	D-JRP16-WP4.6	Proof-of-concept performed (animal 6, syndrome 6, Czech Republic)	M60		This TELE-Vir partner left the project in year one of the project due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. His tasks were taken over by the other TELE-VIR partners.	1
	D-JRP16-WP4.7	Proof-of-concept performed (animal 7, syndrome 7, Italy)- IZLER	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
	D-JRP16-WP4.8	Proof-of-concept performed (animal 8, syndrome 8, Norway) - NVA	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1
	D-JRP16-WP4.9	Proof-of-concept performed (Human, syndrome, Denmark)- SSI	M60	M58-59	Proof of concept study performed. Deliverable achieved. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7467096	1

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify)

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
16	M-JRP16-01	Collected and curated databases for genotype-phenotype associations	M36	Yes	Initial database for CoV genotype phenotype associations complete. The rapidly developing available data for SARS-CoV-2 mean that this database will need to be continuously reviewed, throughout the remaining project time.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
16	M-JRP16-02	Software modules for third-generation sequencing data handling	M39	Yes	Modules for automate quality control and analysis of ONT data were developed and implemented.
16	M-JRP16-03	Software modules for viral rapid detection and classification	M59	M60	A modular bioinformatic pipeline for metagenomic virus diagnostics was developed. Work is ongoing to publicly release this new “pathogen detection” module into the INSaFLU-TELE-VIR platform, coupled with its inter-connectivity with the existing “surveillance-oriented” toolbox for an enhanced detection and monitoring of viral pathogens.
16	M-JRP16-04	Software module for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes (e.g., antigenicity, tropism, anti-viral drug resistance)	M54	Yes	A bioinformatics tool for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes was developed and released as standalone tool (https://github.com/insapathogenomics/align2pheno ; https://pypi.org/project/align2pheno/) and also integrated (pilot version) in the platform.
16	M-JRP16-05	Advertisement of the poi-toolbox workshop finished	M52	Yes	We send out the advertisement for the workshop to all TELE-Vir partners
16	M-JRP16-06	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and OHEJP participants in the POI protocol for MinION sequencing performed incl.	M52-54	Yes	Task completed – our plans could successfully be implemented at the workshop June 2022, SSI, Copenhagen

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		training materials, manuals & lectures and personal			
16	M-JRP#-07	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and OHEJP participants in the POI data analysis performed incl. training materials, manuals & lectures and personal	M52-54	Yes	Task completed – our plans could successfully be implemented at the workshop June 2022, SSI, Copenhagen
16	M-JRP16-08	Registration of participants for training in the POI-toolbox finished (max. 30 participants)	M52	Yes	24 TELE-Vir partners registered for the workshop
16	M-JRP16-09	Software module for locus- and genome-based comparative phylogenomics	M57	M59	Novel functionalities for better phylogenetic/metadata data navigation and interpretation were implemented in the beginning of the project. In M59, this feature was considerably strengthened by the release of a new module for advanced visualization and exploration of phylogenetic and genomic data together with temporal and geographical analysis
	M-JRP16-10	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (animal, syndrome, Sweden)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
	M-JRP16-11	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (animal, syndrome, Poland)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies
	M-JRP16-11	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (salmonid, cardiopathies, France)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies
	M-JRP16-12	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (cattle and equids, vector borne diseases, to be conducted in Africa)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies
	M-JRP16-13	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (animal, syndrome, Spain)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies
	M-JRP16-14	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (animal, syndrome, Czech Republic)	M58	no	This partner left the TELE-Vir consortium, but the other TELE-Vir partners compensated the work in the WP4 studies, by collecting more samples
	M-JRP16-15	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (animal, syndrome, Italy)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies
	M-JRP16-16	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (animal, syndrome, Norway)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
	M-JRP16-17	Selection of samples for the proof-of-concept (Human, syndrome, Denmark)	M58	yes	Sample where collected in time for the proof of concept studies

2.5.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
An alternative workflow for molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 – escape from the NA extraction kits shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020 https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.14.2000398 https://zenodo.org/record/4247188#.X6QLjWhKjcc		No		
Improvement of field deployable metagenomics virus detection by a simple pretreatment method DOI: doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.31.21268552		Yes		Yes, it is a new journal and have no publications fees yet
Phylogenomic characterization and signs of microevolution in the 2022 multi-country outbreak of monkeypox virus https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01907-y		Yes		Yes (but publication fee was not paid by TELE-Vir)
Epizootic Haemorrhagic Disease Virus Serotype 8 in Tunisia, 2021 Viruses 2022, 14, x. https://doi.org/10.3390 www.mdpi.com/journal/viruses		Yes		Yes (but publication fee was not paid by TELE-Vir)

Additional output

Posters

- Assessing coronavirus risks: feasibility of predicting traits of clinical and epidemiological relevance from sequence data. C. Bogaardt, V. Borges, J. P. Gomes, J. Isidro, J. M. Prada, D. L. Horton. Poster presentation, OHEJP Copenhagen June 9-11th 2021
- Pinheiro M, Pais RJ, Isidro J, Pinto M, Bogaardt C, Prada JM, Horton DL, Gomes JP, Borges V (2021) INSaFLU-TELE-Vir: an open web-based bioinformatics suite for influenza and SARS-CoV-2 genome-based surveillance. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 4:e68845. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.4.e68845>.
- Fast and easy field-deployable Sars-CoV-2 virus inactivation for downstream analysis. Anna S. Fomsgaard^{1,2}, Graham J. Belsham², Ria M. Lassaunière¹, Jannik Fonager¹, Katja Spiess¹ 1. Virus Research & Development Laboratory, Statens Serum Institute, Copenhagen, Denmark 2. Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. Poster presentation at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2021.
- Vítor Borges, Miguel Pinheiro, Ricardo J. Pais, Joana Isidro, Miguel Pinto, Carlijn Bogaardt, Joaquin M. Prada, Daniel L. Horton, João Paulo Gomes. INSaFLU-TELE-Vir: an open web-based bioinformatics suite for genome-based surveillance of influenza, SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens. ISIRV-WHO Virtual Conference, COVID-19, Influenza and RSV: Surveillance-Informed Prevention and Treatment, 19-21 October 2021 (**e-poster and recorded flash talk**)
- A simple sample pretreatment method for metagenomics virus detection in the field. Anna S Fomsgaard^{1,2}, Morten Rasmussen¹, Katja Spiess¹, Anders Fomsgaar¹, Graham J Belsham², Jannik Fonager¹. 1. Virus Research & Development Laboratory, Statens Serum Institute, Copenhagen, Denmark 2. Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. Poster presentation at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Orvieto, Italy, 2022.
- Kaupke A., Kwit E., Bigoraj E., Radko L., Rzeżutka A. Assessment of virus inactivation efficiency for selected guanidinium thiocyanate/hydrochloride lysis buffers commonly used in PCR diagnostics." One health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Orvieto, Italy, 11-13 April 2022
- Spiess K & TELE-Vir consortium, Point of incidence toolbox for emerging virus threats. One health EJP project leader meeting, Stockholm, 22 November 2022

LinkedIN

LinkedIN – OneHealth- the workshop organized for all TELEVIR partners in June 2022 has been published.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/h2020-one-health-ejp_ohejp-onehealth-strongertogether-activity-696926954644869121-f4vq?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

Presentations of the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform

The National Institute of Health (INSA) Dr Ricardo Jorge, Portugal, has presented the INSaFLU-TELEVIR open web-based bioinformatics suite for virus genome-based surveillance on behalf of several international initiatives and networks, e.g., ECDC COVID-19 Laboratory Networks Influenza, WHO Europe Laboratory Workshop. INSA also maintains several cooperative actions at national and international levels to enhance the capacity building of other national and international laboratories

(e.g., National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau) in pathogen genome-based surveillance. In this context, the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform was presented to/in:

broad audiences on behalf of:

- ECDC COVID-19 Laboratory Networks Influenza (20 May 2020)
- WHO Europe Laboratory Workshop (1 June 2020).
- ISIRV-WHO Virtual Conference, COVID-19, Influenza and RSV: Surveillance-Informed Prevention and Treatment, , ARPHA Conference, 2021 (19-21 October 2021)
- European Society for Clinical Virology (ESCV), 24th Annual Conference, Manchester, UK (9 Sep, 2022)
- European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Inf Diseases, Webinar (20 Sep, 2022)
- Mini symposium on Bioinformatics resources, tools and Research (BV-BRC and J. Craig Venter Institute) (15 Sep 2022)
- PROMISE RSV Laboratory Network (RSV-LabNet) (13 Dec 2022)
- MediLabSecure Webinar “Introduction to Metagenomics technologies” (14 Dec 2022)

Specific countries/reference laboratories (including training sessions):

- National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau (INASA), Guinea-Bissau (27 August 2021)
- Norwegian Veterinary Institute (Norway), Norway (19 April 2021)
- WITS-VIDA, South Africa (24 March 2022)
- NHS-UK, Scotland, UK (27 September 2022)
- Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIAV), Portugal (November 2022)
- Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA), Spain (7-18 November 2022), in cooperation with the EJP JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN project (Short-term mission)
- Multiple countries, on behalf of the ongoing ECDC mandate to “Support to Microbiology-related Activities and Capacity Building Focusing on Covid-19 and Influenza in the EU/EEA, the Western Balkans and Turkey. Laboratory Support, Training, and Standardisation”.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

It is important to be able to react fast to new virus outbreaks to prevent future pandemics. Knowledge is also warranted about hosts that can act as intermediate hosts, leading to potential zoonotic events, by a transmission of a virus from one host to a new host. We developed in the exploratory TELEVIR project a POI toolbox that contains a field deployable POI protocol to detect RNA & DNA viruses in biodiverse regions without existing infrastructure. The POI protocol is combined with the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform, which a free web-based (<https://insaflu.insa.pt>), but also locally installable (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/>), bioinformatics framework for “start-to-end” metagenomic virus detection and routine genomic surveillance analyses. The POI toolbox was tested in proof of concept studies, including field studies and we could successfully detect RNA/DNA viruses in different species. We will share our knowledge gained in the ten EU laboratories of the TELEVIR consortium with and interested stakeholders. For instance, specific training in the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform is being

planned in the frame of several national and international initiatives, in order to strengthen the capacity for genomic epidemiology and public health bioinformatics of key stakeholders, namely laboratories/countries conducting surveillance of emerging viral threats. One of the potential stakeholder is the EU project “Medilabsecure” (<https://www.medilabsecure.com/>) aiming to reinforce the preparedness and surveillance of relevant zoonotic pathogens in 22 beneficiary non-EU countries through a one health consortium. Human virology, animal virology, entomology, public health, veterinary services, and epidemiology sectors join their knowledge in specialized networks. CISA-INIA is leading the veterinary virology network, and it is planned the transfer of the POI toolbox produced by the TELEVIR project, which could be specifically useful tool for the human and animal virology components of Medilabsecure. In summary, these follow-up activities is of utmost relevance as we consider fast and unbiased detection of viruses will be the future golden standard for virus detection and pandemic preparedness.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

On behalf of the TELEVIR project, and also as a response to COVID-19 pandemic and, later on, the multi-country Monkeypox (MPXV) outbreak, the previously existing INSaFLU (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>) platform has been improved and adapted to better accommodate the routine genome-based analyses of the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), influenza, MPXV and other viruses. As a result, **the INSAFLU-TELEVIR bioinformatics framework has already been crucial for genomics surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/covid19/>; more than 43000 sequences analysed, as of November 2022), influenza (more than 600 sequences in 2020-2022), and, more recently, monkeypox (around 500 samples in 2022) in Portugal. The achieved INSaFLU-TELEVIR versatility and functionality has captured the attention of several stakeholders, such as ECDC (suggested tool for WGS analysis <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/novel-coronavirus/laboratory-support>). For instance, INSA is participating in a 4-year programme launched by ECDC to “Support Microbiology-related Activities and Capacity Building Focusing on Covid-19 and Influenza in the EU/EEA, the Western Balkans and Turkey” (AURORAE project).**

2.5.7 One Health impact

Human activities and stressed ecosystems have created new opportunities for diseases to emerge and spread. About 60% of emerging infectious diseases that are reported globally come from animals, both wild and domestic. Over 30 new human pathogens have been detected in the last three decades, 75% of which have originated in animals. Zoonotic transmission risks can be evaluated in biodiversity hotspots. Some of these areas are challenging with lacking infrastructure or long distance to high expertise laboratories. These challenges can prolong the detection and possible outbreak causing viruses, affecting human and animal health alongside economy on local and national scales. The consequences of a possible outbreak can be reduced if the viruses are detected before a spillover event into the human population, but also by gaining knowledge about viruses in animal populations that are in close contact to humans. The TELEVIR project acknowledge strongly the OneHealth initiative that animals and humans are interdependent by presenting a biosurveillance POI toolbox for unbiased detection (metagenomics) of RNA- and DNA viruses in different sample materials from many species. Our POI toolbox can be envisioned to be of interest for stakeholders in countries with low laboratory infrastructure and with a high biodiversity. As for example the EU project Medilabsecure (<https://www.medilabsecure.com/>) aiming to reinforce the preparedness and surveillance of relevant zoonotic pathogens in 22 beneficiary non-EU countries through a one health consortium. The transfer is planned of the POI toolbox to the animal/human virology labs in the beneficiary countries, which are located around the Mediterranean, Sahel and Black Sea regions. In this context, the INSaFLU-TELEVIR

platform has been recently presented to this network in a webinar organized by the Medilabsecure coordinators, which was followed by more than 90 people from all beneficiary regions. The open platform was highly appreciated by the participants, who mostly do not have the chance to acquire specific software for viral sequences analysis. Throughout the project, the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform captured the attention of the scientific community (leading to the considerably increase in the number of accounts created) and other stakeholders. For instance, INSA (human health sector) has already established contact with the “equivalent” institute from the Animal Health sector (INIAV) in Portugal to introduce the TELEVIR toolbox, showing the direct application of the TELEVIR outputs in an OneHealth perspective. In addition, INSA strict collaboration with countries of Portuguese official language, namely African countries (e.g., NIH from Guinea-Bissau is already using the tool opens goods perspective that the our POI toolbox can contribute to virus surveillance in the future, by sharing the knowledge not only within the TELEVIR consortium but also with further interested stakeholders at global level.

2.5.8 Data Management Plan

https://zenodo.org/record/7528642#.Y85J_XbMKUk

2.5.9 Future dissemination activities

Our main stakeholders are countries and European networks that are dependent on virus surveillance strategies that are non-targeted, field employable easily applicable for training people. We disseminated our POI toolbox that was developed by the TELEVIR consortium at OHEJP workshops and conferences, project leader meetings, but also on LinkedIn. We gained strong interest for the POI protocol by the outreach of the stakeholder MedilabSecure.

We were also engaged in several cooperative actions at national and international levels to enhance the capacity building in pathogen detection and genome-based surveillance. For instance, training in INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform is integrated in the 4-year programme launched by ECDC to “Support Microbiology-related Activities and Capacity Building Focusing on Covid-19 and Influenza in the EU/EEA, the Western Balkans and Turkey” (AURORAE project). The POI toolbox is ready to be shared now after successfully finishing the proof of concept studies in Y5. We will present the POI toolbox in upcoming project leader meetings in 2023. The project management team and the communication team can help to suggest potential stakeholders to the TELEVIR consortium and help to strengthen the collaboration with the Medilabsecure network.

2.6 JRP17-R2-ET2.2-IDEMBRU

2.6.1 Consortium composition

Project coordinator: Claire Ponsart – ANSES

Project co-coordinator: Vitomir Djokic - ANSES

WP	WP leader	WP deputy leader	Other involved partners
1	INIAV – AC Ferreira	NDRVMI– H Daskalov	ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, IZSAM
2	INSA – A Pelerito	BfR – S Al Dahouk	ANSES
3	APHA - R. Ashford	IZSAM – G. Garofolo	ANSES, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, WBVR
4	FLI – F Melzer	BfR – S Al Dahouk	ANSES, APHA, IZSAM, INIAV, INSA
5	WBVR – M van den Esker	Anses – L Freddi	APHA, BfR, FLI, IZSAM
6	IZSAM – F. De Massis	APHA – A. Whatmore	All partners involved
7	Anses – C Ponsart	INIAV – AC Ferreira	

2.6.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Zoonotic and highly infectious potential of core clade *Brucella* species is well described, whereas characteristics of newly discovered species, as well as their reservoirs just start to be explored. Project IDEMBRU aimed to develop a toolkit for diagnostics, characterization and assessment of the zoonotic potential of newly discovered strains, and identify unexplored wildlife and environmental reservoirs for classical *Brucella* species. Since IDEMBRU consortium consisted of EU, and national reference laboratories, project results had direct impact on surveillance and management of brucellosis.

The project strategically chose the samples from existing wildlife, environment and human collections to identify the presence of noncore clade *Brucella* sp. and new or emerging reservoirs for core clade species. Moreover, each partner dedicated newly isolated, unusual strains for genetic, phenotypic and zoonotic potential characterisations. The questionnaire was adapted for more than 1500 samples, to obtain relevant epidemiological data. The environmental bacteria *Ochrobactrum* sp. is genetically similar to *Brucella* sp. including opportunistic pathogens. Thus, a panel of isolated *Ochrobactrum* sp. strains was included into analyses. During this project, newly emerging *Brucella canis*, from core type species spread quickly in Europe, with a first human cases reported in 2022 in the Netherlands and in the UK. Since *B. canis* is not as well characterised as other highly pathogenic *Brucella* sp. *B. canis* isolation was done from clinical canine samples as well as those epidemiologically related, in France, Italy, Portugal and the UK. In Portugal human blood and tissue samples from selected professions at risk were analysed. The network of human diagnostic laboratories was created to reinforce surveillance systems for brucellosis outbreaks, especially regarding the atypical cases.

Within IDEMBRU, *B. canis* diagnostic methods were compared. The evaluation of DNA extraction methods from complex matrices - water, soil, animal-, and more specifically canine faeces. Specific primers for *Ochrobactrum* sp. were constructed for molecular diagnostics, and for the panel of *Brucella*

serologically cross-reacting bacteria using high-throughput microfluidics chip PCR. The first inter laboratory ring trial for whole genome sequencing was organised to standardise the quality of obtained sequences. Motility, agglutination, phage lysis, production of NAD on various substrates (BIOLOG™), growth capacity on 40 different nutrient deprived media were examined as addition to conventional phenotyping differentiation. Several sugars and specific growth media were chosen for differentiation between core and non-core *Brucella* species. The bacterial RNA-seq provided diverging datasets which highlighted that the method cannot be easily implemented. The existing MALDI-TOF spectral database was extended with the novel *Brucella* and several *Ochrobactrum* strains, which identified unique biomarkers. Core and non-core *Brucellae* including *Ochrobactrum* species demonstrated different levels of resistance to several antibiotics which can be used for their discrimination. The *in vitro* cell infections pipeline was developed, for the pathogenicity classification, employing the gene expression by RNA-seq and cytokine profiling of infected cells. Finally, two parts of the toolkit were prepared: for identification and characterisation of non-core *Brucella* isolates; for *B. canis* diagnostic and management of outbreaks; for diagnostic of core *Brucella* species in wildlife.

With OH EJP COHESIVE project, the *B. canis* presence and risks of infection for dogs and humans were evaluated. The White Paper was prepared, regarding current knowledge and recommendations for further necessary actions. For EFSA, an EREN communication was prepared with the similar topic.

The results of this project were presented at international Brucellosis symposiums, as well as annual OH EJP conference, and stakeholders' meetings. Four awareness-raising seminars on *B. canis* for European veterinary professionals and diagnostic laboratories were organised, with a great support and promotion by EFSA.

2.6.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Recording the situation of brucellosis in emergent wild and environmental reservoirs

Task WP1-T1: Mapping of existing data on emerging *Brucella* spp (M25-M36)

This task involved the mapping of existing data on emerging *Brucella* sp., and existing sample sets that could be included in the scope of IDEMBRU project. The list of the existing sample collections, and of existing atypical *Brucella* strains (D-JRP19-WP1.Del1) was created and shared among the partners within the consortium. Existing samples comprised *B. microti*-like, *B. pinnipedialis*, *B. ceti*, *B. suis* biovar 2, and *B. canis* isolates, sera and organs from several wild reservoirs.

Task WP1-T2: Sampling and analytical strategy according to previous epidemiological information from the different partners (M37-M50)

Within this task additional sampling was organised from emerging reservoirs, and the creation of a common database to share both epidemiological and analytical data. A large part of the interactions within the network were devoted to defining the best sampling strategy, taking into account both methodological requirements and epidemiological relevance. Additionally, it was decided to include the collection of samples for evaluation of the prevalence of *B. canis* infection in dogs, as this species started to emerge in different EU countries during the project, associated with two human cases reported in the Netherlands and in UK. Three biotopes, forest (n=1256), fresh water (n=22) and coastal region (n=274), were targeted. A total of 1552 animal samples (blood when possible, and tissues) from amphibians, dogs, foxes, marine mammals, reptiles, rodents, turtles, fish, molluscs, wild ruminants, jackals, bears and wild boars were sampled during the project.

An epidemiological questionnaire for sample collection, were prepared. The Epidemiological questionnaire include the date of sampling, geographic information (country, region and coordinates, sampling area/ total area), type of biotope and animal group (multispecies or single species place).

Task WP1-T3: Synthesis and analysis of epidemiological and phenotypic data in order to contribute to the toolkit with improved management of emerging outbreaks (M37-M58).

At the end of the WP1, we were able to identify the main target reservoirs of emerging *Brucella* sp. for surveillance and define the best sampling strategy. In accordance, a decision tree for diagnosis and identification of atypical *Brucellae* and *B. canis* outbreak was developed and will be included in the toolkit. The implemented SOPs in wp1-T2 were validated and are part of the proposed approach for the "Brucella canis - Diagnostic flowcharts for kennel outbreak confirmation and outbreak management" toolkit, and for "Atypical *Brucella* species identification toolkit".

WP2. Recording the situation of emerging brucellosis in human

Task WP2-T1- Mapping of existing data in order to establish the strains and/or biological samples from human populations suspected of Brucella infections

In Portugal, the network for laboratory surveillance of brucellosis caused by noncore clade species was created. The standardised epidemiological questionnaire, adapted from the one used in the INSA in order to safeguard the patients' privacy, was distributed to all members of the network. However, all strains at INSA and other network members belong to core clade *Brucella* species, mainly *B. melitensis* obtained after professional exposure, and their inclusion in the further analyses was not in the scope of this project. INSA contacted hospitals, private laboratories, General directorate of Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine and slaughterhouses of Setubal region, to obtain the biological samples from professionals at higher risk to acquiring brucellosis.

As a second step, from the human sera banks, INSA created the collection of additional human samples. This included sera from patients negative for smooth, core clade *Brucella* species, in order to test rough *B. ovis* antigens and possibly detect non-core *Brucella* exposure. The criteria for selection were fever, non-specific inflammatory symptoms and/or potential exposure to atypical *Brucella* sources already identified in the literature. The selection of sera was made, based on the occupational and environmental risks for humans. The selection takes into account exposure to dog kennels, exotic animals, forest workers, marine wildlife, anglers, and people living in the countryside, who could be more exposed to atypical *Brucella* or potential unknown reservoirs.

Task WP2-T2- Sampling and analytical strategy according to selected emerging reservoirs

Since the starting of the project, INSA received blood, cerebrospinal fluids, and biopsies from National Hospitals. Seven *Brucella melitensis* and one *Ochrobactrum intermedium* were isolated.

According to the analysis strategy, a first panel of 200 samples has been processed according to classical serological methods. Several samples (n=20) were chosen for further bacteriological culture and molecular detection based on the antibody titers, but so far, no non-core *Brucella* strain was isolated. The comparison was made between indirect RBT test, *B. ovis* antigen-based test and direct isolation and PCR results.

Task WP2-T3 - Synthesis and analysis of epidemiological data

In the absence of isolated strains and dedicated indirect diagnostic tools for humans, even for *B. canis*, the sources of seropositivity of human samples were traced using the epidemiological questionnaire to various classical sources of brucellosis already described in the literature. Moreover, no seropositivity was diagnosed in any of examined kennel owners. Consequently, neither the comparison between alternative serological tests nor between indirect and direct detection methods could be performed. Therefore, this task of projects, that heavily dependent on the presence of non-core

Brucella species and sensitivity and specificity of available diagnostic tools, could not be performed, nor the evaluation of these tests can be analysed.

WP3. Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

Task WP3-T1 Optimisation of methods for generating molecular typing data from complex samples

Task WP3-T1 PART 1: DNA extraction and bacterial culture from swabs

To date, few studies have evaluated methods for the optimal collection and processing of swab samples specifically for the detection of *Brucella* species, and compared them for either bacteriological culture or molecular methods (quantitative PCR). Consequently, work undertaken as part of WP3 aimed to (i) compare commercially available swab types for recovery of *B. abortus* (544), *B. melitensis* (16M), and *B. suis* (biovar 2 Thomsen) in bacterial culture and of DNA in quantitative PCR (qPCR); (ii) identify the optimal transportation conditions; and (iii) compare bacterial culture and qPCR for detection of *B. abortus*, *B. melitensis*, and *B. suis*. This study tested seven commercially available swabs with different tip materials. Swabs were spiked with known concentrations of each strain, and then either tested immediately or stored under different conditions (72 hours at +4°C or 72 hours at -20°C) prior to testing.

The survival of live bacteria on all swab types was significantly affected by the storage conditions (Figure 3.1.1A). The recovery rate of live bacteria from swabs treated immediately was significantly higher than that of swabs stored at +4°C or -20°C. Bacteria absorbed into swabs and stored for 3 days in the refrigerator exhibited an average 20% greater recovery than when frozen at -20°C. However, the qPCR detection of *Brucella* did not exhibit significant variation in quantification between storage conditions (Figure 3.1.1B).

Figure 3.1.1 Recovery rates of live bacteria by culture (A) and their DNA by qPCR (B) in *Brucella*-spiked swabs stored under different temperature conditions.

The only dry-swab for which recovery was not significantly worse than the control was the dry-flocked swab (S4). Conversely, the only wet swab tested (also flocked – S5) provided the best conditions for recovery of *Brucella*, with percentage recovery superior to that of the positive control (bacteria in 0.9% physiological solution). Broadly the same pattern of results was observed for qPCR detection from swabs (Figure 3.1.2B). The wet-flocked swab (S5) exhibited the highest rate of *Brucella* identification by qPCR, superior to that of the positive control, while only the two also flocked dry swabs (S4 and S7) were not significantly inferior to the positive control.

Figure 3.1.2 Recovery rates of live *Brucella* by bacterial culture (A) and their DNA by qPCR (B), from spiked swabs (treatment conditions combined). Recovery of live bacteria by culture and detection by qPCR were compared on seven swabs and a positive control (PC).

Task WP3-T1 PART II: DNA extraction from soils

Literature review indicated that the soil environment may play a role in the ecology of a number of recently described atypical *Brucella* species, such as *B. microti*. We compared the performance of various DNA extraction kits for soil samples, to enable more efficient detection of *Brucella* sp. by molecular methods (PCR). The performance of six commercially available extraction kits – specific for soil, was assessed on the basis of DNA yield and purity, as well as using *Brucella* genus-specific qPCR assays. As soils represent a highly complex and diverse matrix, we evaluated kit performance in three different dirt types, representative of physio-chemical properties: organic matter content, particulate matter content, and particle size distribution. The resulting DNA extracts were measured by spectrometry in order to estimate DNA recovery (ng/ μ L) and purity (260/280 and 260/230 ratios). The efficiency of extraction was evaluated using a pair of *Brucella* genus specific qPCR assays, targeting IS711 and bcsp31. Additionally, an exogenous internal positive control assay was included, amplifying a synthetic DNA target, in order to assess the presence of inhibitors in soil DNA extracts.

In DNA extracts from soil A (garden soil), only extraction kits 1 and 4 exhibited a significant negative correlation between *B. microti* DNA concentration and IS711 Ct values (Pearsons r ; $P < 0.05$). In soil B (sandy soil) DNA extracts produced with kits 1, 4 and 5 showed a negative correlation between DNA concentration and IS711 Ct values (Pearsons r ; $P < 0.05$). Significant differences were observed between DNA extraction kits in the Ct values obtained for a given number of genome equivalents added to soil samples. In most cases the lowest Ct values at a given concentration of *B. microti* DNA were observed in extracts generated using kit 1 (Figure 3.1.3). Exceptions to this pattern were observed in soil C (chalk loam), for which extracts from kits 5 and 6 generated slightly lower average Ct values at intermediate *B. microti* DNA dilutions.

Figure 3.1.3 Quantitative PCR results from soil samples spiked with varying concentrations of *B. microti*, targeting IS711. Figures A-C show results for soil types A-C. Dashed lines represent the thresholds routinely applied for defining positivity when testing culture material.

The percentage recovery by qPCR of *B. microti* DNA from soil extracts was calculated using standard curves of known input DNA amounts, and each eluate was expressed as a percentage of the amount added to soil samples prior to DNA extraction (Figure 3.1.4). In the case of IS711, only kits 1 and 6 generated recovery estimates for all replicate extractions, across *B. microti* concentrations and soil types. In the case of soil A, DNA extraction using kit 1 resulted in the highest mean recovery across all concentrations of added *Brucella* DNA (103%), followed by kit 5 with a mean recovery of 42% across all target concentrations, though in this case the variance between replicates was wide (coefficient of variation: 110%). In the case of soil B, kit 1 again exhibited the highest recovery (74%), followed by with kit 5 (44%). In soil C the average recovery levels demonstrated for kit 1 (24%) were marginally lower than those for kit 5 (28%).

Figure 3.1.4 Recovery of *B. microti* DNA by qPCR, from three soil types extracted using six different methods. Boxes represent the estimated percent recovery at each of three concentrations of experimentally added *B. microti* DNA, and are based on IS711 Ct values.

Task WP3-T2 Harmonisation and standardisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing

This task aimed to compare the performance of whole genome sequencing (WGS) procedures through ring trial in partner institutes, to ensure that comparable data could be generated. Five *Brucella* sp. strains were chosen for a panel to evaluate WGS methods applied by partner institutes. Strains were selected to incorporate phenotypically and/or genotypically diverse atypical species (*B. microti*, *B. inopinata* and *B. vulpis*), as well as representatives of genomically conserved “core” *Brucella* species of significance in wildlife populations (*B. suis* and *B. pinnipedialis*). All strains were cultured using

established methods described in WOHAT terrestrial manual. Results concerning the performance of library preparation and whole genome sequencing undertaken (e.g. quality metrics; number of reads etc.) were collated, to ensure comparability between institutes. Additionally, reference-based alignment and *de novo* assembly metrics were compared. Sequencing results returned by partner institutes were also compared with curated reference sequences available via publicly available genome databases (NCBI RefSeq) to benchmark results.

The number of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) identified by participants, relative to the selected reference strain, was largely comparable (Figure 3.2.1A). Both non-core species included exhibited a markedly higher number of SNPs than the three core *Brucella* species. All participating laboratories identified the largest number of SNPs relative to the reference genome in *B. vulpis* F60 (median number of SNPs identified: 55,725), similar to *B. inopinata* BO1 (median number of SNPs identified: 54,519). The numbers of SNPs identified by all laboratories were very highly correlated (Figure 3.2.1B).

Figure 3.2.1 Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) identified in five *Brucella* sp. strains sequenced by participating laboratories. Figure A shows the number of SNPs identified, relative to the selected reference genome (*Brucella melitensis* 16M^T). Figure B shows the correlation matrix between SNP numbers identified by participating laboratories.

Whilst there were some statistically significant differences between participants in *de novo* assembly statistics (e.g. N50), these were minor relative to differences observed between *Brucella* species (Figure 3.2.2). *B. vulpis* appeared to be an outlier in estimated genome length, relative to other strains, by all participants reporting that the substantially shorter contig-level assembled genome, compared to other strains (Figure 3.2.2A). Similarly, all participating laboratories reported that the estimated GC content of both *B. vulpis* and *B. inopinata* were markedly lower, and *B. microti* the highest estimated GC content than other sequenced strains (Figure 3.2.2B). Comparing these results to those for NCBI RefSeq or GenBank assemblies for the selected strains identified that the total assembly length for all strains was somewhat below that of the publicly available genome, except in the case of *B. inopinata* (Figure 3.2.2C). Comparison of estimated GC content with RefSeq/GenBank assemblies demonstrated that GC content of the assembled genomes was also lower.

Figure 3.2.2 Genome characteristics following *de novo* assembly of five *Brucella* sp. strains sequenced by participating laboratories. Figure A shows length of the assembled genomes and B shows estimated GC content (%). Figures C and D, respectively, show assembly length and GC content of the assembled genomes, relative to RefSeq/GenBank assemblies for the given strains.

A number of differences were observed between institutes in results of both sequencing performance and subsequent and bioinformatics analysis, because of the variety of protocols used. However, in all cases differences between laboratories had very minor impact on the conclusions which could be drawn, relative to differences between the strains themselves. The high degree of genetic divergence of atypical *Brucella* strains (both relative to core *Brucella* sp. and amongst non-core strains) emphasises the need to select appropriate reference genomes for reference-based mapping and variant calling analyses. Additionally, this work has also identified a need for improved reference genomes for a number of recently described *Brucella* strains.

Task WP3-T3 Adaptation of molecular typing methods

This task aimed to assess the extent to which widely used molecular typing assays (such as MLST and MLVA) accurately capture the diversity of the expanding group of atypical and non-core *Brucella* sp. We applied WGS to existing *Brucella* sp. strains and recent isolates, in order to generate *in silico* MLST, and whole genome SNP typing data. Additionally, *in silico* 16-locus MLVA profiles were retrieved, supported by conventional fragment analysis approaches where necessary. These data have been used to demonstrate that the available molecular typing methods continue to reliably characterise relationships within the expanding diversity of the genus (Figure 3.3.1B, Figure 3.3.1A), that can be used for characterisation of *Brucella* sp. strains (Figure 3.3.2).

Figure 3.3.1 Heatmaps showing divergence (number of base substitutions per site) amongst concatenated 9-locus MLST sequences for (A) MLST gene sequences for core *Brucella* species and (B) sequences from non-core *Brucella* species/strains.

Figure 3.3.2 Maximum likelihood phylogeny of currently described 9-locus MLST sequence types (STs, n=111), including 19 STs recorded from non-core species/strains (red diamonds).

A defining feature of the emerging group of “non-core” *Brucella* sp. strains is their greater degree of genomic diversity than core *Brucella* species, with a number of such strains incorporating genetic material from soil-dwelling organisms via horizontal gene transfer (HGT), which is un-common amongst core *Brucella* species. Additionally, the molecular typing of *Brucella canis* isolates from the

emerging canine brucellosis situation in the UK, Italy, France and elsewhere in Europe, applying molecular typing schemes (MLST) and WGS approaches such as SNP analysis and cgMLST was performed and correlated to epidemiological data. The molecular typing of strains isolated from the outbreak from an Italian kennel revealed that they all belong to the same cluster of cgMLST.

Under WP3-T3 we have additionally focused on generating improved genome assemblies for atypical and non-core strains, using MINion long-read sequencing data (generated on Oxford Nanopore MiniON platform), for subsequent extraction of molecular typing data. We have compared a various DNA extractions methods, deemed safe to be inactivated and used outside the BSL3 (required for handling core *Brucella* sp.) (Figure 3.3.3). We have also evaluated the impact on down-stream bioinformatic analyses by producing “hybrid” *de novo* genome assembly of atypical *Brucella* sp. strains, using both short- and long-read data

Figure 3.3.3 Comparison of (log) read lengths generated by MinION long-read sequencing of three *Brucella* species (A - C) using DNA extracted by four different methods (GenFind [blue]; Kingfisher [red]; PDQEx [green]; Qiagen [purple]).

Task WP3-T4 Integrative analysis of genomic and epidemiological data

In this task a comprehensive analysis of available molecular typing data for non-core *Brucella* sp. isolates was performed, with data from task 3. WGS data, from both short- and long-read sequencing approaches, for non-core *Brucella* sp. isolates was compared (Table 3.4.1)., including six new non-core *Brucella* sp. isolates, from Amazonian milk frogs (*Trachycephalus resinifictrix*) isolated in the UK. Since no novel non-core *Brucella* sp. were isolated during this project, epidemiological analyses of non-core *Brucella* sp. isolates in Europe across different emerging reservoirs was challenging. All 21 available WGS RefSeq genome assemblies as well as short-read data for a number of additional non-core *Brucella* sp. isolates from NCBI sequence databases has been incorporated into analyses. These data have been used to perform phylogenetic and clustering analyses of non-core isolates originating from a range of hosts, including fish, amphibians, rodents and humans.

Table 3.4.1 Non-core *Brucella* sp. strains from APHA strain collection sequenced for genomic analysis

Sample panel	n =	Illumina	MinION
Australian rodent strains* (2010)	10	Y	Y
Australian rodent strains* (1980s)	10	Y	Y
Existing UK amphibian strains	2	Y	Y

Newly isolated amphibian strains	6	Y	Y
Total	28		

* Assumed to be historical duplicates of the same strains

WP3-Other

WP4. Phenotypic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

WP4-T1 Phenotyping of emerging *Brucella* sp.

Task WP4-T1-ST1 Biotyping of emerging *Brucella* sp. isolated within the project

Conventional phenotyping of new emerging *Brucella* was performed. Conventional bacteriological methods were used, also applied for phenotyping of classical *Brucella* species, described in WOHAT terrestrial manual. These methods are Gram-staining, CO₂ – requirement, hemolysis, oxidase reaction, motility, catalase reaction, H₂S production, urease-reaction, Crystal violet staining, growth on basic fuchsin, growth on thionin, lysis by phages, and agglutination in monospecific sera (A, M, R). In order to obtain an indication of possible reactions in the routinely performed typing PCR's, these were also included in the studies for Task 1. We performed a *Brucella* BCSP31 PCR for genus identification, AMOS-PCR and the Bruce Ladder-PCR which allows to identify all core clade and recently described *Brucella* species.

Mostly there are no differences in typing results between the new emerging *Brucella* strains compared to the core clade *Brucella* species. However, all new emerging *Brucella* available at FLI were positive in the motility test. This property has not yet been demonstrated in any taxonomically classified *Brucella* species.

In addition, no agglutination reactions were observed with monospecific sera. There was also no agglutination reaction with a brucellosis (*B. abortus*, *B. melitensis*, *B. suis*) sera from confirmed positive animals.

Another remarkable result is that all *Brucella*-specific bacteriophages did not cause lysis of non-core strains. Thus, the latter three typing methods (motility, agglutination and phage lysis) can be applied as important conventional phenotyping differentiation methods between the core clade and new emerging *Brucella* sp. These methods are further used WP-6 for the toolbox.

Task WP4-T1-ST2 Electron microscopy of selected isolates/strains:

New emerging *Brucellae* isolated at FLI were characterized by their motility. Core clade species are immotile. This mobility is based on the functionally active flagella. To detect flagella, electron micrographs (negative contrast) pictures of various isolates (n=6) of non-core strains (frog isolates), *B. microti* reference strain and *B. melitensis* 16M (reference strain) were taken at FLI.

Sheathed flagella were detectable in all examined non-core *Brucella* isolates. A maximum of 1 polar arranged flagellum per bacterium was present, while the number of flagella in relation to the number of bacteria was different for the different isolates. The morphological structure of the flagella is as described previously (Al Dahouk et al., 2017).

New emerging brucella isolate 13RB5064 (magnitude 6,800x left, 9,300x middle and 49,000x right)

Non-core *Brucella* isolate 09RB8913 (magnitude 6,800x left, 4,800x middle and 18,500x right)

In *B. microti*, neither flagella nor it's fragments were detectable.

B. microti (magnitude 4,800x left, 9,300x middle and 49,000x right)

In *B. melitensis* (16M) - non-motile, only very isolated sheathed flagella were detectable as previously described (Ferooz & Letesson, 2010), but morphologically very different from the ones in non-core species.

Flagellum in *B. melitensis* (magnitude 4,800x left, 9,300x middle and 11,000x right)

From the present results, it can be concluded that the presence of functionally active flagella in new emerging *Brucella* sp. is a peculiarity leading to motility in this bacterial group not previously observed in core-clade species. Further research including genetic basis should be considered.

Task WP4-T1-ST3 Phenotyping of emerging *Brucella* sp. isolated during the project using the BfR *Brucella* MICRONAUT™

Goal of this subtask was to perform metabolic phenotyping of the novel *Brucella* isolates with the established *Brucella* BfR MICRONAUT™ system, as published previously by Al Dahouk et al. 2010. Unfortunately, the production of commercial MICRONAUT™ system has been discontinued during the first quarter of the IDEMBRU project. Hence, the Work package focused on the BIOLOG™ phenotype microarray system to characterize the metabolic properties of non-core clade *Brucella* species. The BIOLOG™ microarrays do not directly examine bacterial enzymatic activities and growth, but measure metabolic activity and consequently the NADH generation upon substrate utilization independent from growth [Bochner 2009] (Figure 1A). The BIOLOG™ phenotype microarray analysis compared the novel, core-clade *Brucella* species, *B. papionis* and *B. microti*, with the novel, non-core clade species, *B. vulpis* (Figure 1B and C). For the slow-growing isolates of *B. papionis* and *B. vulpis*, we observed distinct substrate utilization patterns (e.g. glucose, succinate, citrate, similar, while glutamate opposite catabolic activity). However, the BIOLOG™ analysis was not applicable for the highly metabolically active and fast-growing *B. microti*. We observed unspecific positive reactions in all 96-wells micro titer plate. Therefore, further modifications of the experimental settings, e.g. changes in the buffer compositions or of the redox-dye, are required to analyze fast-growing *Brucella* and *Ochrobactrum* sp. However, these comprehensive modifications within the commercial test system could not be established and implemented during the funding period.

Figure 1: BIOLOG™ phenotype microarray. Shown is the principle of determining the metabolic activity of bacterial cells (A) and the carbon sources in the PM1 MicroPlate™ tested for their ability to be utilized by *Brucella* (B.). Differences in the substrate utilization patterns of *B. papionis*, *B. vulpis* and *B. microti* are depicted (C). Colored boxes indicate negative and positive controls (dark blue and dark green) as well as a selected set of substrates (aquamarine, light green, yellow, red). F – formazan; TV – tetrazolium violet

The metabolic phenotyping of atypical *Brucella* species is a prerequisite for WP4-T4. To fulfill this task, we complemented our MICRONAUT™- and BIOLOG™-based metabolic comparison of clade and non-clade *Brucella* sp. with an alternative approach. We performed substrate utilization experiments in defined minimal medium supplemented with a single carbon or other energy source. This minimal medium was modified from publication of Plommet (1991) containing solely salts and vitamins, which did not significantly promote the growth of any tested *Brucella* strain. Subsequent bacterial growth was determined by measuring the optical density at 600 nm (OD600) after adding various single energy/carbon sources (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Alternative approach for phenotyping of *Brucella* sp. based on metabolic data. Growth kinetics of *Brucella* isolates in modified(*) Plommet minimal medium substituted with a single energy source to identify the maximum growth (maximum optical density at 600nm) of the respective isolates in the substrates of interest. Parts of this figure were created with Servier Medical Art, provided by Servier, licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 unported license.

A set of 40 substrates, including amino and organic acids, their respective derivatives as well as sugars or sugar alcohols, were individually tested for their growth promoting properties with typical, atypical *Brucella* sp., and *Ochrobactrum* strains (Table 1). This approach underlined the capacity of novel *Brucella* isolates to grow on single energy sources that distinguish them from classical *Brucella* sp. with their typically fastidious growth phenotype. The novel non-core *Brucella* sp. show a large utilization spectrum of carbohydrates and organic acids, with greatest diversity for amino acids and their derivatives. Strikingly, no strain of the classical *Brucella* species was able to proliferate with any of the used substrates under these restricted nutritional conditions. Similar growth characteristics showed *B. vulpis*. *Brucella* sp. NF2627 isolated from an Australian rodent showed a highly restricted substrate utilization pattern but was able to grow well on certain sugars, erythritol, pyruvate, lactate and the amino acids proline and lysine.

As demonstrated by our *Brucella* BfR MICRONAUT™ phenotyping assay, other non-core *Brucella* species as well as *O. anthropi* and *O. intermedium* in contrast to the core species make use of a wide array of substrates for their growth. Our analysis revealed a highly variable substrate utilization pattern by *B. microti* strains, supporting a previous study about the genetic and phenotypic diversity of this species [Al Dahouk et al. 2012]. Interestingly, some *B. microti* isolates could catabolize and grow on ectoine, previously described only for isolates from Pac-Man frog and *O. anthropi* [Soler-Lloréns et al. 2016].

	<i>O. intermedium</i>	<i>O. anthropi</i>	<i>B. inopinata</i> BO1	<i>B. inopinata</i> -like BO2	<i>B. sp. (frog isolates)</i>								<i>B. microti</i>				<i>B. sp. NF2627</i>	<i>B. vulpis</i> F60	<i>B. papionis</i> F9/08-00	<i>B. abortus</i> 544	<i>B. melitensis</i> 16M	<i>B. suis</i> 1330	<i>B. suis</i> 513	<i>B. canis</i> RM6/66
BfR-ID: BfR-BR-00_...	736	743	173	174	507	508	510	516	528	368	747	748	751	533	656	406	001	180	549	654	083			
C	Brucella broth																							
	Minimal medium																							
carbohydrates	Arabinose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Fructose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Fucose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Glucose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Maltose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Mannose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Rhamnose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Sucrose	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black			
sugar alcohols	Erythritol	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Glycerol	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Inositol	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Mannitol	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Sorbitol	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	organic acids & derivatives	Gluconic acid	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	
Adipic acid		Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Pyruvic acid		Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Lactic acid		Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Citric acid		Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
α-Ketoglutaric acid		Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Succinic acid		Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Fumaric acid		Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Malic acid	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black			
amino acids & derivatives	Ectoine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Alanine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Arginine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Asparagine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Aspartic acid	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Cysteine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Glutamic acid	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Glutamine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Glycine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Histidine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Isoleucine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Leucine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Lysine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Methionine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
	Proline	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black		
Serine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black			
Threonine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black			
Valine	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black			

Table 1: Substrate dependent growth of typical, atypical *Brucella* and *Ochrobactrum* sp. Growth (black) and no growth (white) is defined as $OD_{600} > 0.5$ and < 0.2 , respectively. Poor growth (grey) is defined as OD_{600} between 0.2 and 0.5. C – control media.

The analyzed *Brucella* isolates from frogs proliferated with an extended (relative to core *Brucella* sp.), but less diverse number of substrates compared to *B. microti*, most similar to the growth phenotypes of *B. inopinata* BO1 and *B. inopinata*-like BO2. Unexpectedly, not all frog isolates were able to catabolize rhamnose like *B. B13-0095* from a Pac-Man frog [Soler-Lloréns et al. 2016].

The *O. anthropi* and *O. intermedium* species were able to use most of the substrates and grew on 35 and 34 of the 40 tested substances, respectively. Our experimental setup identified several substrates that allowed the distinction between the *Ochrobactrum* and the non-core *Brucella* species, a feature that could potentially be used for diagnostics. Only *O. anthropi* and *O. intermedium* proliferated with citric acid, gluconic acid and mannitol as sole carbon and energy source in the defined minimal medium. In contrast, all tested non-core *Brucella* isolates were able to grow on adipic acid as sole carbon and energy source.

WP4-T2 Antibiotic resistance testing

Task WP4-T2-ST1 Antibiotic resistance testing of emerging *Brucella* sp. isolated during the project

In the course of the project, the microdilution plate system (Micronaut™, Merlin GmbH, Bornheim-Hersel, Germany) was established at four consortium laboratories. Nine different antibiotic dilutions of chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin, doxycyclin, gentamycin, levofloxacin, rifampicin, streptomycin, tetracyclin and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole are applied to their Micronaut-S plate. The protocol used is based on the publication of Tscherne et al., Adaptation of *B. melitensis* Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing to the ISO 20776 Standard and Validation of the Method. Microorganisms 2022, 10, 1470.

A total of 34 new emerging *Brucella* strains were compared with core-clade species, at four laboratories using the same protocol. The number of *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus* and *B. suis* isolates included was 129, 98 and 13, respectively. In addition, five *Ochrobactrum* isolates were examined.

We calculated the arithmetic mean and its standard deviation as well as the median for the MIC values of the different brucella species (groups).

		gentamycin	streptomycin	doxycyclin	tetracyclin	chloramphenicol	rifampicin	trimethoprim*	sulfamethoxazole*	ciprofloxacin	levamisol
frog (34)	arithmetic mean	0,479	1,971	0,221	0,214	1,771	3,057	1,700	32,300	0,375	0,379
frog	Stabwn	0,070	0,167	0,090	0,077	0,420	1,264	1,671	31,748	0,130	0,125
frog	Median	0,5000	2,0000	0,2500	0,2500	2,0000	4,0000	0,5000	9,5000	0,5000	0,5000
<i>B. melitensis</i> (129)	arithmetic mean	0,257	1,099	0,091	0,125	1,576	1,037	0,036	0,824	0,409	0,410
<i>B. melitensis</i>	Stabwn	0,059	1,456	0,054	0,031	1,140	0,704	0,052	1,880	0,145	0,146
<i>B. melitensis</i>	Median	0,2500	1,0000	0,0625	0,1250	1,0000	1,0000	0,0310	0,5930	0,5000	0,5000
<i>B. abortus</i> (98)	arithmetic mean	0,297	0,770	0,438	0,280	1,536	1,536	0,087	1,656	0,370	0,332
<i>B. abortus</i>	Stabwn	0,100	0,249	0,422	0,189	0,499	0,506	0,088	1,661	0,125	0,117
<i>B. abortus</i>	Median	0,2500	1,0000	0,2500	0,2500	2,0000	2,0000	0,0625	1,1870	0,2500	0,2500
<i>B. suis</i> (13)	arithmetic mean	0,212	0,365	0,031	0,072	1,222	0,769	0,065	1,245	0,302	0,292
<i>B. suis</i>	Stabwn	0,103	0,271	0,015	0,023	0,416	0,249	0,127	2,416	0,213	0,219
<i>B. suis</i>	Median	0,2500	0,2500	0,0310	0,0625	1,0000	1,0000	0,0310	0,5940	0,2500	0,2500
Ochrobactr. (5)	arithmetic mean	0,183	0,427	0,150	0,119	1,027	0,905	0,075	1,420	0,228	0,225
Ochrobactrum	Stabwn	0,068	0,290	0,161	0,086	0,572	0,603	0,032	0,603	0,059	0,059
Ochrobactrum	Median	0,2115	0,2706	0,0312	0,0721	1,0000	0,7692	0,0650	1,2447	0,2500	0,2500

* both antibiotics combined in one well

Task WP4-T2-ST2 Comparison of antibiotic resistance patterns and ECOFFs determination of emerging and classical *Brucella* species

Some of the project partner labs were also involved in the "Adaptation of *B. melitensis* Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing to the ISO 20776 Standard and Validation of the Method." (Tscherne et al. 2022). The number of studies and samples necessary to make a sound statement on ECOFFs exceeds the possibilities given in this project. For this reason, the results obtained were only evaluated in terms of their suitability for phenotyping.

Even if the total number of isolates tested does not allow statistically reliable statement, the differences in some antibiotics between the groups appear suitable for phenotyping. Thus, there are major differences between the *Brucella* groups compared on gentamycin, streptomycin, rifampicin, and the combination of trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole.

Trimethoprim-sulfmethoxazole (different scaling!)

These results should prompt the use of at least these antibiotics for future phenotyping analyses of new emerging *Brucella*, and are part of the WP-6 toolbox.

WP4-T3- RNA sequencing of a representative panel of classical and novel *Brucella* sp.

Task WP4-T3-ST1 Drafted RNA-seq protocols to identify regulatory differences between classical species and emerging *Brucella* sp.

We evaluated several RNA-seq kits for various *Brucella* species. Based on our experiments a suitable protocol has been developed. This protocol can be used for *Brucella* cultivation, RNA extraction, quality control, library preparation and sequencing. However, regarding the wet lab, laboratory specific optimization might be necessary.

Task WP4-T3-ST2 RNA sequences of a representative panel of classical and emerging *Brucella* sp.

Our pilot experiment addressed environmental conditions that emerging *Brucella* sp. might be exposed to. Overnight cultures of *B. vulpis* F60 and *B. microti* CCM4915 were used to inoculate Gerhardt's liquid minimal medium at pH7 and pH4.5 in triplicates. Growth phase dependent comparative RNA-seq-based transcriptome analysis was performed on samples that reached an OD600 >0.5. For transcript abundance determination and exploratory differential data analyses bioinformatics tools Kallisto and Sleuth were used, respectively. The complexity of the two species-related datasets were then reduced by means of a principal component analysis (PCA) and were illustrated with PCA plots (

Figure 3A and C). Furthermore, intra-species regulation was visualized with volcano plots for *B. vulpis* and *B. microti* (

Figure 3B and D). These volcano plots indicated that many transcripts were up- or down-regulated in response to acidic stress in both species.

The *B. vulpis* samples showed clear clustering according to their experimental conditions (i.e. pH7 vs. pH4.5) in PCA, with slightly more heterogeneity within the low pH replicates (RNA4, RNA5, RNA6), than neutral pH (RNA1, RNA2, RNA3) (

Figure 3A), with larger differences between clusters on principle component 1 (PC1) than on PC2. Thus, both clusters are more separated on the x-axis (PC1), than on the y-axis (PC2) (

Figure 3A). In contrast, PCA of the *B. microti* dataset was less conclusive (

Figure 3C), especially replicates of low pH with large variations among the technical replicates (

Figure 3C). This heterogeneity of low pH *B. microti* datasets made the discrimination of experimental conditions less clear than for the *B. vulpis* dataset.

These diverging datasets highlight that RNA-seq experiments cannot be easily implemented. Finally, the metabolic study in WP4-T1-ST3 required tremendous resources since well-established, commercially available assays were withdrawn from the market.

Figure 3: RNA-seq pilot experiment – atypical *Brucella* sp. during starvation and low pH. *Brucella vulpis*

F60 (A and B) and *Brucella microti* CCM4915 (C and D) were exposed to starvation (GMM) associated with neutral (pH7) and acidic (pH4.5) conditions. Technical replicates, with red and blue data points for pH7 and pH4.5, respectively, partially clustered in the principal component analyses of RNA-seq data (A and C). Differential gene expression with significantly up- and down-regulated genes (colored in red or orange) were found in both atypical *Brucella* sp. (B and D).

Task WP4-T3-ST3 Comparison of RNA sequences of selected clinical samples with 16S metagenomics to test viability of *Brucella* sp.

Since no new *Brucella* strain was isolated in WP-1 and WP-2 from clinical samples, we could not address this subtask.

Task WP4-T3-ST4 Integration of emerging *Brucella* MALDI-TOF MS spectra into the existing database

This subtask was highly dependent on cooperation and strain exchange among project partners to gather a variety of emerging species and their proteomic fingerprints. The FLI provided ten novel non-core *Brucella* isolates, for sequencing and MALDI-TOF MS analysis. Our in-house spectral library, predominantly consisting of core *Brucella* isolates, was extended by integrating the processed novel strains. For discriminatory power, we also integrated the spectra of *O. intermedium* and *O. anthropi*. The diversity within our extended spectral library is illustrated by the group spectra of all *Brucella* species with clusters of fragmented phenotypical groups (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Overview of our in-house MALDI-TOF MS spectral library after integration of the spectra of emerging *Brucella* species. Group spectra of species are marked with red and blue for typical and atypical phenotypes, respectively.

Species-specific biomarker peaks were identified for the novel species and isolates by comparison of all mass spectral patterns. Exemplary data are shown for the differentiation of *O. intermedium*, *O. anthropi* and *B. microti* (Figure 5 - Figure 7), showing clear divergence with more similarities among *Ochrobactrum* species than with *B. microti* (Figure 5A). The previously reported genus-specific peak [I] for *Brucella* was confirmed in our dataset (Figure 5B). In addition, a biomarker [II] that is absent in *O. anthropi* and *O. intermedium* but present in the *Brucella* genus – including all core and non-core species – was identified within the expanded dataset (Figure 5C).

Figure 5: Gel view of the group spectra of *B. microti*, *O. anthropi* and *O. intermedium* (A). Marked are the genus *Brucella*-specific peak [I] (B) and the peak [II] used for the differentiation of core/non-core *Brucella* from *Ochrobactrum* sp. (C). *B. microti* spectra are shown in aquamarine, and *Ochrobactrum* in black/grey (B and C).

Samples belonging to the *Ochrobactrum* genus revealed unique peaks [III-V; VI-VIII; IX-X] (Figure 6A-C). Discrimination of the two *Ochrobactrum* species within the extended *Brucella* genus was achieved with unique peaks [VI-VIII and IX-X] for *O. intermedium* and *O. anthropi*, respectively (Figure 6B and C).

Figure 6: Unique biomarkers for the discrimination of isolates belonging to the former genus *Ochrobactrum*. Peaks III-V can be found in both *Ochrobactrum* sp. (A), whereas discrimination to species level is achieved with peaks VI-VIII and IX-X for *O. intermedium* (B) and *O. anthropi* (C), respectively. *B. microti* spectra are shown in aquamarine, *Ochrobactrum* spectra are shown in black/grey.

In addition to the biomarkers for *Ochrobactrum* sp. (Figure 6), specific peaks for all novel *Brucella* species were identified. Exemplarily, biomarkers [XI-XIV] for the identification of *B. microti* isolates are shown (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Biomarker [XI-XIV] for the identification of *Brucella microti* (aquamarine). Black/grey spectra represent *Ochrobactrum* isolates.

In addition to the *Brucella* isolates collected within IDEMBRU, we integrated spectra from all novel *Brucella* sp. and several *O. intermedium* and *O. anthropi* isolates. A manuscript addressing the differentiation of novel and atypical *Brucella* with biomarker signals in mass spectral libraries is currently in progress. The MADLI-TOF MS data is under closure upon publication of this manuscript and will be provided to interested parties.

WP4-T4- Identification of diagnostically relevant regulatory processes by bioinformatics analysis of metabolic data (BfR *Brucella* MICRONAUT™) and RNA-seq data.

A new metabolic phenotyping approach has been designed and was implemented during the project to enable the generation of the metabolic data required for this subtask (compare WP4-T1-ST3). Due to a tremendous setback regarding RNA-seq know-how in our group, we were not able to complete this task appropriately.

WP5 Zoonotic potential and virulence

WP5-T1: Development of an in silico pipeline for preliminary assessment of overall virulence and zoonotic potential.

Task WP5-T1-ST1 Creation of *Brucella* genomes database from publicly available and emerging isolates

Creation of the database was slightly delayed as emerging isolates are still mostly lacking. Combining sets of online available genomes and in-house sequenced strains gave a test-set of 30 genomes that were used to examine differences between zoonotic and non-zoonotic species and robustness of tools to assembly quality.

Task WP5-T1-ST2 Selection of bioinformatics tools for identification and comparison of virulence factors

A literature search revealed a diverse array of tools to identify virulence genes in bacterial assemblies, of which a subset was selected as possible candidates (VFanalyzer, PathoFact, *Brucella*Base, PathogenFinder, and ABRicate), and only one widely used, namely VFDB (<http://www.mgc.ac.cn/VFs/main.htm>). However, because of the variabilities in the results and lack of sufficient data produced within WP-3 further assessment had to be taken only after finished sequencing ring trial. Due to changes in personnel within WP lead institution as well as unplanned leaves, this task had to be delayed for additional three months.

Task WP5-T1-ST3 Creation of an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes

We decided to make a pipeline on the basis of ABRicate tool. This package also includes the option to build a custom database. In this way we can add the genes that VFAnalyzer found extra and include 10 other potential *Brucella* sp. virulence genes selected in a recent publication on virulence factors in *B. melitensis* (Rabinowitz et al. 2021). Due to delays during the building of the database and the necessity to build our own database for the pipeline, this task was additionally delayed by approximately two months.

The SOP on running the BAT-VFDB, a data base of *Brucella* virulence genes, with ABRicate (already on Zenodo) was prepared.

Table with an overview of virulence genes present in BAT-VFDB and their use in discriminating between core and non-core Brucellae was prepared.

WP5-T2: Development of a macrophage based in vitro system for rapid assessment of zoonotic potential

Task WP5-T2-ST1 Assembly of macrophage cell lines collection derived from human and animals

The cell lines available in all participating laboratories, as well as bacterial strains were identified for harmonization experiments. Additionally, several cell lines were ordered and included in the harmonization experiments (e.g. DH82, HTR8-SVneo) and *Brucella* species were exchanged from ANSES to WBVR for the infection experiments.

Task WP5-T2-ST2 Set-up of protocols for in vitro infection models

For the development and harmonization of the *in vitro* infection protocol HeLa cell lines were chosen as human cell line and preferred choice for the testing the zoonotic potential. Six reference *Brucella* species with different zoonotic potential (categorized as 'non-zoonotic' 'rarely zoonotic' and 'highly zoonotic') were used in order to standardize the protocol and optimize parameters like MOI, time of incubation etc. Readout parameters included CFU counts and, qPCR to quantify the infection rate. Besides, IPMAs were performed to visualize the infections. To set up the protocol, it was decided to analyse cellular infection in the following post infection (PI) time points:

1. Two hours PI, to quantify the number of bacteria attached and infected cells;
2. Six hours PI, to determine the amplification curve of intracellular bacteria
3. 24 hours PI, to continue the growth curve and analyse the cellular reaction and damages inflicted
4. 48 hours PI, to analyse the cell death and final numbers of bacteria.

Task WP5-T2-ST3. Harmonization of analytical methods for investigation of pathogen – host-cell cross talk

First, it was determined that RT-qPCR was a less laborious and time demanding method to quantify infection compared to CFU counts. In order to relate CFU to Ct values, a calibration curves using a bcs31 as a target were made. The bcs31 PCR, a single-copy gene, was compared to the regular diagnostic IS711 target PCR. The IS711 element has varying copy numbers among different *Brucella*

species, making direct comparison difficult. Therefore, it was decided to use the bcsp31 PCR to enable direct comparison between species, and quantify infection by relating the Ct values from bcsp31 PCR to CFU counts. From the harmonization experiments it was decided to formulate the *in vitro* infection parameters (ST4) in the beginning of the infection (first 24 hrs)

Task WP5-T2-ST4. Formulation of *in vitro* infection parameters that will reflect zoonotic potential of a *Brucella* isolate

The goal was to find host cytokine and gene markers that give an indication of zoonotic potential in order to enable quick risk assessment. Cell lines were infected with *Brucella* species with different zoonotic potential, and samples were taken 1-2, 6 and 24 hrs post infection for cytokine assays, and fixed in Trizol after 6 and 24 hrs for RNA-seq experiments. For the analysis of cellular signalling and immune response regulation the panel of 13 cytokines was used. Briefly, after cells were infected with bacteria, at each time point (1-2h, 6h and 24h), supernatant was collected from each well individually. Supernatant was filtered through 0.2um syringe filters and treated with benzonase to remove both live bacteria and their DNA. Supernatant was then used to quantify the expression of 13 different cytokines, using Biolegend LegenPlex Multi-Analyte flow assay for human inflammation panel (BioLegen, San Diego, CA). As pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1, IFN- α , IFN- γ , MCP-1, IL-6, IL-8, IL-12, IL-17A, IL-18, IL-23, IL-33, and as anti-inflammatory TNF- α (through TNFR2 on epithelial cells such as HeLa) and IL-10 were analysed. Interestingly, the levels of IFN- γ did not show statistically significant differences compared to uninfected cells in all three time points, when THP1 or HeLa were infected with both benign *B. ovis* and *Ochrobactrum* strains, but concentrations of other pro-inflammatory cytokines were significantly increased. In the same time MCP-1 was not expressed in higher concentrations in HeLa cells until 6h pi, while IL-10 was significantly suppressed in all time points both in macrophages and epithelial cells. In the same time, since macrophages are effectors of the innate immune response, their reactivity towards pathogens was somewhat overexpressed in the culture of differentiated THP1 cells. Therefore, for further harmonisation of the protocol it was decided to use HeLa cells in which exact role of MCP-1, TNF- α and other cytokines can be traced.

For RNA-sequencing, RNA was extracted in the same experiment from the cellular fraction. mRNA gene expression was analysed based on poly-A enrichment of the isolated RNA. After preparing libraries, the RNA was sequenced using an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform. Differential expression analysis using the DESeq2 pipeline was performed, comparing gene expression in the host cell after infection with high vs mild vs low zoonotic *Brucella* species. This resulted in a table with possible RNA markers that reflect the zoonotic potential. In the future, a PCR-test can be developed based on these markers.

WP6. – Development of a toolkit for emerging brucellosis infections

Task WP6-T1 Assessment of currently available toolkits

Currently available toolkits have been assessed for other pathogens in order to identify strengths and weaknesses from previous experiences. Tools available at European Union level for early detection of, and response to, multi-country foodborne events (Epidemic Intelligence and Information System for food- and waterborne diseases (EPIS-FWD), Early Warning and Response System (EWRS) platform, Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) platform and the Food Chain-Lab tool) have been reviewed as existing approaches. After presented analyses, the leaders and deputies of all WPs have considered the WHO “Monkeypox Outbreak Toolbox” as the best reflecting the organization of a toolkit for emerging *Brucella* species, to fulfil the scope of the project. The resource has then taken into consideration for the development of the toolbox; it is available on the following web address:

<https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/monkeypox-outbreak-toolbox>

Task WP6-T2 Collaborative toolbox

The aim was to develop a collaborative toolbox comprising documents, guidelines, tracking system including emerging *Brucella* and flowcharts on outbreak investigations that may be needed for emerging Brucellosis outbreak investigations. Specific objectives have been:

- i) to describe the outbreak with a minimal dataset (case definition, spatiotemporal data, species etc.);
- ii) to define harmonized investigation strategies for emerging *Brucella* and reservoirs;
- iii) provide the tools and flowcharts necessary to properly characterise strains with an optimised and harmonised set of methods integrating classical phenotypic, genomic and proteomic approaches and assessment of behaviour in virulence models.

Given the recent emergence of *B. canis* infection in several EU Countries, and considering its zoonotic potential and the absence of diagnostic and management tools, the WP leaders and deputies decided to produce two complementary parts of the toolkit: one focusing on detection and characterisation of emerging *Brucella* species and/or reservoirs (the one already expected as project deliverable), and the second tailored specifically for *B. canis* identification and outbreak management.

The two operational toolboxes, each one tailored on the respective target *Brucella* clade, are composed of reference databases, harmonised protocols, guidance on interpretation, tracking systems, flowcharts on outbreak investigations. In both kits, the detection of the bacteria is emphasised with accurate descriptions of currently available detection methods (eg. RT-PCR, bacteriology), including new method such as MALDI-TOF, anti-bio resistance tests, growth on various new nutrient deprived media, motility or *in vitro* infection models- RNAseq and cytokine analyses. These new characterisation approaches include functional markers such as, virulence, resistance to antibiotics, and development of *in vitro* models. A regular SWOT analysis has been carried out by all WP contributors in order to better drive the toolbox assembling.

The resources of the different WPs have been integrated in the two final toolboxes to fulfil three major objectives:

- 1) the detection and investigation of the pathogens of interest from different sources, under various epidemiological contexts in terms of natural landscape, livestock demographics and wildlife in Europe;
- 2) the characterisation of emerging *Brucella* by identification of genomic and phenotypic variability via high throughput methods, such as NGS, molecular tests, proteomics, metabolomics;
- 3) the understanding of virulence and zoonotic potential through *in vitro* infection models.

The final toolkit will be available on the websites of the One Health EJP, ANSES and EFSA, both in integrative and interactive form.

Another component of the toolbox is the PADIweb project. The project built a fully automated information collection system, based on Google News and RSS alerts system for tracking and early warning system of targeted pathogens. According to the key words used, the system uses artificial intelligence to translate found news, and supervised learning approach to sort obtained in databases and present the news through maps and other information systems. Currently the PADIweb search engine is in testing phase for *B. canis*, while tracing of information for wildlife and environmental sources for non-core clade species needs additional refinements. The estimated time necessary to verify the system performances would be until the final toolkit submission. Furthermore, PADIweb data collection will be also available as an epidemiological tracking system for EU referent laboratory and EFSA.

WP7. Coordination, management and communication

During the three years of the project, project coordination assured regular monthly communication among partners, communication with OH EJP coordination, financial reporting as well as mediation among partners, MTAs organisation and exchanges of materials and necessary trainings. In the last year of the project, two two-day workshops had been organised in April and November. All partners participated with IDEMBRU scientific results on international Brucellosis conference, organised this year by IZSAM in Giulianova, Italy.

In the same time, coordination assured continuous communication with EFSA on the issue of emerging *B. canis*, epidemiology of non-core clade species and the need of raising awareness among exposed professionals, after first human cases around Europe. First three seminars were organised for veterinary and diagnostic laboratory professionals in France, one in collaboration with EFSA for European veterinarians and one for students and young professional in Italy.

Moreover, this year the White Paper on *B. canis* emergence and potential risks as well as risk management analysis was coordinated with COHESIVE. The document is in the submission phase.

Task WP7-Del1 and Del3 First draft and final data management plan

First draft of the data management plan was finished at the beginning of the second year of the project. Because of all the delays project had encountered and DMP platform not being ready, the first draft included all the documents necessary for the development of the project, with only several documents added later.

Task WP7-Del2 Creation of a data sharing common platform

Through Microsoft Office Cloud Sharing service SharePoint, ANSES provided access to all consortium members and dedicated storage for exchange of documents, and data. Because of the constant change in personnel in almost all members laboratories, cyber security had to be adapted and special attention was dedicated by ANSES informatics department to this issue.

Task WP7-Del4, Del5, Del6 – Reports of annual workshops exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders

Out of three annual workshops, two had to be held online during the pandemic, which probably hampered proper start of the project and progress in the directions all partners wanted. Furthermore, each partners institution in their respective countries was involved, to higher or lesser degree, in COVID testing for humans, animals and/or response groups, which additionally shortened time and personnel needed for IDEMBRU project. However, each time, exterior presenters, with special attention to stakeholders, were invited to give a talk on development of toolkits or pathogenesis investigations related to other, similar pathogens. So, during the three workshops, colleagues from EFSA, DG Santé, CIRAD, and CDC joined us and we had an opportunity to hear what their expectations would be from our project, so that our activities can be adapted accordingly.

Moreover, with EFSA close collaboration on *B. canis* awareness raising and distribution of current state of the art in diagnostics and epidemiology of canine brucellosis causes by this bacteria was strengthened, especially during the last year of the project.

Task WP7-Del7 –Implementation of a notification system including emerging and non-regulated Brucella.

With colleagues from CIRAD, it was decided to use their system PADIWEB as an online surveillance platform for early warning system for signs of brucellosis emergence in European Union. The PadiWeb uses AI technology to collect and analyse data from Google News platform, including multiple language sources and levels of relevance for collected parameters. Two different tracking systems have been

developed, one for non-core clade *Brucella* identification of clinical animal and human cases, and one for *B. canis* reporting and tracing, as well as early warning system for each EU country and region.

2.6.4 Project self-assessment

The IDEMBRU set ambitious tasks of investigating, on one hand epidemiological situation of non-core *Brucella* species within environment and wildlife across Europe, and on the other preparing the toolbox of laboratory diagnostic methods to analyse the zoonotic potential of these newly discovered strains. Several major roadblocks have been encountered that can be divided into two groups: organisational and scientific.

With COVID-19 pandemic the organisation of sample collections, field investigations as well as hiring personnel was difficult until the very end of the project. Furthermore, because of delayed maintenance during the pandemic, two partner laboratories suffered closures for three months each. In total 14 people left and joined the project within three years out of which three WP leaders or deputies. Most of the partners were also engaged in COVID testing for most of the two thirds of the project.

More than 1500 samples, of diverse complex matrices, from three distinct biotopes present in Europe have been tested. Several *Brucella* sp. or *Ochrobactrum* sp. strains have been isolated. This led to belief that contamination with non-zoonotic or potentially low zoonotic non-core *Brucellae* is not as high as previously supposed. However, the isolated strains were important to enrich and enlarge the existing collections and will contribute to further understanding of the diversity of *Brucella* and *Ochrobactrum* circulation and public health impacts. Moreover, the analysis of human samples for both *Brucella* or *Ochrobactrum* infections has led to a conclusion that the risks of brucellosis from those sources is very low or limited to particular species or biotopes. Nevertheless, current expansion of *B. canis* in European dogs, *B. microti* presence in breeding and wild frogs, *B. suis* infections of dairy herds as well as the latest cases of *B. melitensis* transmission from mounting goats to a dairy herd in France give contra arguments. The compelling evidence is the infection dose of *Brucella* genus that can be as low as 10 bacteria (not CFU!). Our project continued to prepare the laboratory methods for analysis of zoonotic potential using already existing strains. Unfortunately, time constraints as well as lack of trained personnel did not allow us to perform the *in vivo* infections, nor perform RNAseq analysis from bacteria under stress conditions. The amount of work needed, contributed to delays in majority of deliverables and running the experiments to the last possible minute. Isolation of new *Brucella* and *Ochrobactrum* strains only occurred in the last third of the project, therefore, already isolated strains were used to evaluate existing and develop new molecular practices for DNA isolation, purification, multiplex high throughput diagnostic, and discrimination within the genus as well as high quality sequencing. We organised the first proficiency test for sequencing data. This applied exercise helped to establish standardised quality of genomic analyses within the reference laboratories. Moreover, several new complementary bacteriology analyses have been developed to separate core from non-core strains, and prepared one of the most complete MALDI-TOF spectral databases to identify core, non-core *Brucellae* sp. and *Ochrobactrum*, that will greatly shorten the diagnostic time and responses to *Brucella* outbreaks. Moreover, specific virulence- and bio-markers were identified that, in combination with cellular infection results (cytokine and RNA profiles) will be the basis of zoonotic potential characterisation not only for *Brucella*, but also genetically similar species (*Francisella* sp. for example).

During the IDEMBRU project, the collaboration with PADI Web platform for epidemic surveillance started on early warning systems for *Brucella* outbreaks in European countries. With the emergence of *Brucella canis* in Europe, various actions were undertaken in order to raise awareness of this disease in dogs and owners, with the development of different communication tools including factsheet, webinars. All data gathered during this project will be regrouped the toolkit and will provide sources of information available, and implement developed surveillance strategies at EU level.

2.6.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
17	D-JRP17-WP1.Del1	Creation of a common database to share information about emerging <i>Brucella</i> and reservoirs among the consortium partners	M31	M33	Public: OHEJP_JRP17_IDEMBRU_Data_management_datasheet Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/4572555#.YUC5OzhDtN0	4
17	D-JRP17-WP1.Del2	Creation of animal and environmental samples collections (serum, tissues, strains, soil, water...) of emerging <i>Brucella</i> species and related reservoirs	M50	M48	OHEJP_JRP17_IDEMBRU_Data_management_datasheet Zenodo	1
17	D-JRP17-WP1.Del3	Development of a flowchart and related tools facilitating investigation and	M50	M59	Zenodo link: Development of flowcharts and related tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging Brucella	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		decision-making of emerging <i>Brucella</i> outbreaks			outbreaks	
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del1	Set-up of a human brucellosis network	M42	Achieved, Feb 2021	OHEJP JRP-17 IDEMBRU Work package 2 Deliverable 1 Zenodo Brucella canis workshop Zenodo	
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del2	Creation of human samples collections (serum, samples, strains) of emerging <i>Brucella</i> species and related environments	M50	M59	Even after extensive search through existing human sample collections, there was no evidence of undetected/ undiagnosed human cases infected with core- and non-core <i>Brucella</i> sp. Therefore, this task had no further meaning within this project and had to be cancelled.	
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del3	Development of a biobank and tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging <i>Brucella</i> outbreaks	M57	M59	Zenodo link: Development of a biobank and tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging <i>Brucella</i> outbreaks	
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del3	Molecular typing data from emerging <i>Brucella</i> isolates	M52	M54	Zenodo link: Molecular typing data from emerging <i>Brucella</i> isolates	
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del4	Rapid detection assay(s) for atypical strains using clade specific markers	M57	M60	Zenodo link: Rapid detection assay(s) for atypical strains using clade specific markers	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del1	Standard operating procedures for the extraction of <i>Brucella</i> DNA from complex matrices	M50		Zenodo link: Standard operating procedures for the extraction of <i>Brucella</i> DNA from complex matrices	
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del2	Harmonised whole genome sequencing and bioinformatic protocols	M48	Yes, M48	Zenodo link: Harmonised whole genome sequencing and bioinformatic protocols	
17	D-JRP17-WP4 Del1	Phenotyping scheme to differentiate emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp. from classical species	M48	M60	Zenodo link: Phenotyping scheme to differentiate emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp. from classical species	
17	D-JRP19-WP4 Del2	AMR testing protocol including proposals for ECOFFs for emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp		M60	Zenodo link: AMR testing protocol including proposals for ECOFFs for emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp	
17	D-JRP17-WP4.Del3	Drafted RNASeq protocols to identify regulatory differences between classical species and emerging <i>Brucella</i> strains	30		Zenodo link: Drafted RNASeq protocols to identify regulatory differences between classical species and emerging <i>Brucella</i> strains.	2
17	D-JRP17-WP4 Del4	Identification of diagnostically relevant regulatory processes	M59	M60	In the middle of the IDEMBRU project, the responsible employee left our lab, which resulted in a massive loss of key knowledge in RNA-seq and necessary bioinformatics analyses (brain drain). SOPs and	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
					bioinformatics pipelines could not be established before this change and without novel expertise. In addition, the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic negatively influenced the recruitment of new RNA specialists. Finally, the metabolic study in WP4-T1-ST3 required tremendous resources since well-established, commercially available assays were withdrawn from the market.	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del1	Bioinformatics pipeline for detection and classification of <i>Brucella</i> virulence factors in context of zoonotic potential	M54	M60	Zenodo link: Bioinformatics pipeline for detection and classification of <i>Brucella</i> virulence factors in context of zoonotic potential	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del2	Development of a reliable macrophage based <i>in vitro</i> system for rapid assessment of zoonotic potential	M54	M54	Zenodo link: Development of a reliable macrophage based <i>in vitro</i> system for rapid assessment of zoonotic potential.	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del3	<i>In vivo</i> infection model for emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp.	M54		Due to delays described above, this task cannot be delivered with the time line restrains. Therefore, the deliverable has to be cancelled. The <i>in vivo</i> model would be efficient method to evaluate the zoonotic potential of newly discovered strains and species of <i>Brucella</i> sp. especially for the laboratories that do not have cell culture facilities or knowhow. Unfortunately,	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
					the BSL-3 facility at ANSES had to be closed for a 6-month period during 2022, which impaired characterisation of new isolated strains and preparation of <i>in vivo</i> infections. However, the WP5.Del2 was adjusted to evaluate the zoonotic potential based on cellular stimulation and cell damages using <i>in vitro</i> models.	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del4	Development of a decision-tree as a tool to support decision-making concerning zoonotic potential of <i>Brucella</i> species	M59	M59	Due to all unforeseen delays, the laboratory experiments had to be ren and repeated until the last moment during the project. Unfortunately, the amount of obtained data is too large to be taken with ease and final interpretation of three different sources of data sets has to be finished later.	
17	D-JRP17-WP6.Del1	Review of toolkits for infectious diseases	M54	M59	Zenodo link: Review of toolkits for infectious diseases	
17	D-JRP17-WP6.Del2	Collaborative toolkit for emerging <i>Brucella</i> species and related reservoirs	M60	M60	Zenodo link: Collaborative toolkit for emerging <i>Brucella</i> species and related reservoirs	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del1	First draft of data management plan	M36	M40	Zenodo link: First draft of data management plan.	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del2	Creation of a data sharing common platform	M48	M48	Zenodo link: Creation of a data sharing common platform	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del3	Final draft of data management plan	M36	M40	Zenodo link: Final draft of data management plan	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories * (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del4	Report of the first annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	M40	M42	Public: One Health EJP_JRP17 WP7, Del4 Annual Workshop Report Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5389832#.YUC5fDhDtM1	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del5	Report of the 2nd annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	M55	M55	Zenodo link: Report of the 2nd annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del6	Report of the last annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	M57	M59	Zenodo link: Report of the last annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del7	Implementation of a notification system including emerging and non-regulated <i>Brucella</i>	M59	M60	The deliverable is in preparation and will be published on Zenodo as well as in scientific publication as soon as possible.	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M1	Mapping of existing human Brucella species (shared database)	28	Yes	
17	M-JRP17-M2	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders + deputy leaders on data management	M42	M34	
17	M-JRP17-M3	Definition of type of data generated for each WP and structure of the data sharing platform	M36	M34	
17	M-JRP17-M4	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders and deputy leaders	N/A	M34	
17	M-JRP17-M5	Creation of an epidemiological questionnaire	M37	M36	
17	M-JRP17-M6	Information on worldwide emerging Brucellae (shared database)	M34	M33	
17	M-JRP17-M7	Definition of sampling and testing protocols (molecular, bacteriology and serology)	M36	M42	
17	M-JRP17-M8	Definition of sampling and testing protocols (serology,	M38	M41	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		bacteriology and molecular biology)			
17	M-JRP17-M9	Drafted RNASeq protocols to identify regulatory differences between classical species and emerging Brucella strains	M40	M36	
17	M-JRP17-M10	Definition of the programme of the annual workshop	N/A	M36	
17	M-JRP17-M11	Organisation of accommodation and logistic aspects	N/A	N/A	
17	M-JRP17-M12	Implementation of first annual workshop	M38	M40	
17	M-JRP17-M13	Definition of criteria to be included in the notification system	34	M40	
17	M-JRP17-M14	Choice of the informatic system to implement the notification system	M38	M40	
17	M-JRP17-M15	Harmonisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing	M35	M48	
17	M-JRP17-M16	Optimised protocols for the extraction of Brucella DNA from complex matrices	M42		The WP3 leader (APHA) has experienced a number of delays to the completion of this deliverable, which relies to a significant degree on the distribution of strains to partner institutes. These arise from the on-

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
					going impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic at the work-package lead institute (APHA), as well as other local factors, such as staff availability. Therefore, the milestone was completed at M48.
17	M-JRP17-M17	Creation of Brucella genomes database from publicly available and emerging isolates (WP 2)	44	M44	
17	M-JRP17-M18	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders and deputy leaders	42	M42	
17	M-JRP17-M19	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging Brucella species	M59		A few strains have been isolated from any samples and project has to rely on existing collections. Secondly, the blood or sera is not the tissue usually collected from wildlife and is especially difficult to obtain outside the hunting season. Therefore, the scarcity of the available sera alone postponed this milestone. Secondly, the already the numbers of secondary antibodies or kits validated for wild animals is very low. With the ongoing pandemic situation, their availability is impeded and sometimes the waiting time is counted in months.
17	M-JRP17-M20	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging Brucella species	M59	M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M21	Selection of bioinformatics tools for identification and comparison of virulence factors	46	47	
17	M-JRP17-M22	Assembly of macrophage cell lines collection derived from human and animals	46	48	
17	M-JRP17-M23	Definition of the programme of the annual workshop	44	M49	
17	M-JRP17-M24	Creation of an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes	M57	M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M25	Development of in vitro infection protocol	48	49	
17	M-JRP17-M26	Organisation of accommodation and logistic aspects	46	49	
17	M-JRP17-M27	List of toolkits available from previous experience	M51	M51	
17	M-JRP17-M28	Literature reviewing	M47	Yes	
17	M-JRP17-M29	Integrative analysis of the infection situation in the emerging reservoirs	M59	M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M30	Integrative analysis of the infection situation in the emerging reservoirs	M59	M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M31	Experimental determination of infection gates	M50		Due to encountered delays this milestone cannot be completed. The in vivo model would be efficient and sustainable method to evaluate the zoonotic potential of newly discovered strains and species of Brucella sp. especially for the laboratories that do not have cell culture facilities or knowhow. However, the WP5.Del2 had to be adjusted to evaluate the zoonotic potential based on cellular stimulation in destruction in in vitro models.
17	M-JRP17-M32	Implementation of 2nd annual workshop	M50	M55	
17	M-JRP17-M33	Mailing list of people / institutes receiving notifications	M50	M52	
17	M-JRP17-M34	Develop and apply PCRs on high resolving SNPS to DNA extracted from relevant samples	M52	M54	
17	M-JRP17-M35	Complete molecular typing of emerging Brucella isolates	M59	M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M36	Harmonization of analytical methods for investigation of pathogen – host-cell cross talk.	M52	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M37	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders and deputy leaders	M53	Yes	
17	M-JRP17-M38	Epidemiological analysis of emerging Brucella isolates	M59	M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M39	Biotyping of emerging Brucella sp. isolated within the project	M59	60	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M60
17	M-JRP17-M40	Electron microscopy of selected isolates/strains	M59	M60	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59 + 1 (lab was closed)
17	M-JRP17-M41	Phenotyping of emerging Brucella sp. isolated during the project using the BfR Brucella MICRONAUT™	M52	No	Due to discontinued production of MICRONAUT plates, this milestone cannot be completed and was replaced by creation of MALDI-TOF specific library.
17	M-JRP17-M42	Antibiotic resistance of emerging Brucella sp. isolated during the project	M59	M60	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M60
17	M-JRP17-M43	RNA sequences of a representative panel of classical and emerging Brucella sp.	M59	No	Due to encountered delays and loss of RNA-seq expert who started matric development and data analysis, this deliverable cannot be completed within this WP. Currently suitable tests are being performed within WP5 to compensate this deliverable.
17	M-JRP17-M44	Comparison of RNA sequences of selected clinical samples with 16S	M59	No	Due to encountered delays and loss of RNA-seq expert who started matric development and data analysis, this deliverable cannot be completed within this WP. Currently suitable

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		metagenomics to test viability of Brucella sp.			tests are being performed within WP5 to compensate this deliverable.
17	M-JRP17-M45	Formulation of in vitro infection parameters that will reflect zoonotic potential of a Brucella isolate.	M54	M54	
17	M-JRP17-M46	Definition of the programme of the annual workshop	M49	M50	
17	M-JRP17-M47	Comparison of antibiotic resistance patterns and ECOFFs determination of emerging and classical Brucella species	M59	Yes	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M48	Harmonize in silico, in vitro and in vivo results	M59	No	Since in vivo infections cannot be performed, in silico and in vitro results will be compared
17	M-JRP17-M49	Testing algorithms for WGS and proteome	M50	M50	
17	M-JRP17-M50	Harmonised procedures from IDEMBRU WPs	M50	M50	
17	M-JRP17-M51	Availability of reference database	M50	M60	
17	M-JRP17-M52	Organisation of accommodation and logistic aspects	M56	M59	Workshop organised for M59
17	M-JRP17-M53	Description of infection pathodynamic using molecular and histological	M52	No	Since in vivo infections cannot be performed, this milestone cannot be finished. This milestone is one of the crucial

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		approaches in experimental animals			points to understand the host-New Brucella strain interaction and levels of pathogenicity. However, the results of final toolkit will be reduced to qualitative values – pathogenic or not; zoonotic or not.
17	M-JRP17-M54	Finalize and benchmark the decision tree	M59	M60	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M60
17	M-JRP17-M55	Implementation of 3rd annual workshop	M59	M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M56	Integration of emerging Brucella MALDI ToF MS spectra in the existing peptide profile databases	M59	M60	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M60
17	M-JRP17-M57	Identification of diagnostically relevant regulatory processes by bioinformatics analysis of metabolic data (BfR Brucella MICRONAUT™) and RNASeq data	M59	NO	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59

2.6.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
The use of flocked swab with protective media increases the recovery of live <i>Brucella</i> sp. and DNA detection. <i>Microbiol Spectr.</i> 2021 Dec 22;9(3):e0072821. DOI : 10.1128/Spectrum.00728-21. Epub 2021 Nov 17.	Published	Yes		
The Retrospective on Atypical <i>Brucella</i> Species Leads to Novel Definitions. <i>Microorganisms.</i> 2022 Apr 14;10(4):813. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms10040813.	Published	Yes		
First Isolation of <i>Brucella canis</i> from a breeding kennel in Italy. 2021 <i>Veterinaria Italiana</i> , 57(3). https://doi.org/10.12834/VetIt.2497.15848.1	Published	Yes		Yes (0 €)
Canine brucellosis due to <i>Brucella canis</i> : description of the disease and control measures. (2022) <i>Veterinaria Italiana</i> , 58(1), 5-23. https://doi.org/10.12834/VetIt.2561.16874.1	Published	Yes		Yes (0 €)
Insights into <i>Brucella canis</i> infection in dogs in Portugal - to submit to a National journal.	Under preparation			
Brucellosis in Portugal: a One Health problem - to submit to a National journal.	Under preparation			
Genomic diversity of <i>Brucella neotomae</i> and its zoonotic potential	Submitted (EID)	Yes	TBC	TBC

Additional output

EFSA EREN note on *Brucella canis*: Emergence of canine brucellosis due to infection with *Brucella canis* in different European countries. PONSART C, DE MASSIS F, FERREIRA AC, KOETS A, LAHTI E, MC GIVEN J, SACCHINI F, WHATMORE AM, GIRAULT G, FREDDI L, FERREIRA VICENTE A AND DJOKIC V

EFSA EREN presentation on *Brucella canis*: Emergence of canine brucellosis due to infection with *Brucella canis* in different European countries. Ponsart C - 27th EMERGING RISKS EXCHANGE NETWORK MEETING (EREN), Vienna, 11-12 May 2022, <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/27th-emerging-risks-exchange-network-meeting-minutes.pdf>

Seminar on *Brucella canis*. This workshop provided an overview of current situation about canine brucellosis in Europe, to discuss about the main existing information gaps, and to point out the challenges still pending in properly addressing the disease. 19 September 2022 Residential event: Kursaal venue in Giulianova (Teramo) and Cisco Webex Platform too.

Brucellosis 2022 International Research Conference (Teramo, September 2022) poster presentations acknowledging OHEJP (IDEMBRU) funding:

Roland Ashford, Lavicie Arais, Henny Omosigbo, Jodie Withall, Adrian Whatmore, Amanda Dainty, John McGiven (Poster) Evaluation of DNA extraction methods for long-read whole genome sequencing of atypical *Brucella* sp. isolates

Jodie Withall, Amanda Dainty, Lavicie Arais, Ann Thomasson, Stephanie Hay, Alberto Rodriguez Barbon, Andrew Routh, John McGiven, Adrian Whatmore, Roland Ashford (Poster) The isolation of atypical *Brucella* species from captive Amazon milk frogs (*Trachycephalus resinifictrix*)

Brucellosis 2022 International Research Conference (Teramo, September 2022) presentations acknowledging OHEJP (IDEMBRU) funding:

Teixeira C., Cavaco Gonçalves S., Alves M., Borges P., Ferreira A.C. (Oral presentation). "Insights into the seroprevalence of *Brucella canis* infection in dogs in Portugal".

Ferreira A.C., Pascoal P., Pereira M., Cavaco Gonçalves S., R. Dias (Poster). PORIFERA - Core-genome-based analytical pipeline for prediction of new markers to rapid identification of emerging *Brucella* species.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

OHEJP Roundtable of One Health EJP JRPs on the 11th of April 2022 at OHEJPASM2022 presentation: Identification of emerging *Brucella* species: new threats for human and animals IDEMBRU. Ponsart C

Online guidelines for canine brucellosis (ANSES Website, French). [Présentation PowerPoint \(anses.fr\)](https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/attachment/2022-04-11-Brucella%20canis-01.pdf)

Online seminar for French veterinary practitioners on *B. canis* awareness raising - <https://vimeo.com/733219390> . Ponsart C

Online seminar for French diagnostic laboratories on *B. canis* awareness raising and diagnostic

specificities - <https://vimeo.com/732133799>

EU European Union Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis - 15th Workshop of the EU Brucellosis National Reference Laboratories Giulianova, Italy – September 14-15, 2022:

- Emerging *Brucella* species: update of the IDEMBRU project. Djokic V
- First *Brucella canis* human case in the NL. Koets A.

OH EJP COHESIVE and IDEMBRU Workshop on *Brucella canis* as an emerging threat in Europe – current situation, risk assessment and perspectives

V. Djokic, L. Michelet, G. Girault, A. Lecu, L. Freddi, A. Ferreira Vicente, L. Perrot, L. Laboutiere, ML. Boschioli, C. Ponsart. Molecular detection and differentiation within brucellaceae family in urban and rural wildlife. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online (poster).

V. Djokic, G. Girault, L. Freddi, L. Perrot, L. Laboutiere, A. Ferreira Vicente, M. Ribeiro, F. Petot-Bottin, C. Ponsart. *Brucella* spp and *Ochrobactrum* spp DNA in French foxes, wild boars and deer. 73rd Annual Brucellosis Research Conference, December 4-5, 2021, Chicago (USA)

A. Ferreira-Vicente, V. Djokic, M. Ribeiro, F. Petot-Bottin, L. Perrot, L. Laboutiere, L. Freddi, G. Girault, C. Ponsart, Comparison of five serological methods in non-infected, suspect, exposed and brucellosis infected dogs: impacts on diagnostics strategies. 73rd Annual Brucellosis Research Conference, December 4-5, 2021, Chicago (USA)

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

EFSA EREN note on *Brucella canis*: Emergence of canine brucellosis due to infection with *Brucella canis* in different European countries. PONSART C, DE MASSIS F, FERREIRA AC, KOETS A, LAHTI E, MC GIVEN J, SACCHINI F, WHATMORE AM, GIRAULT G, FREDDI L, FERREIRA VICENTE A AND DJOKIC V

EFSA EREN presentation on *Brucella canis*: Emergence of canine brucellosis due to infection with *Brucella canis* in different European countries. Ponsart C - 27th EMERGING RISKS EXCHANGE NETWORK MEETING (EREN), Vienna, 11-12 May 2022, <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/27th-emerging-risks-exchange-network-meeting-minutes.pdf>

Ponsart, C., F. De Massis, A.C. Ferreira, A. Koets, E. Lahti, J. Mc Given, F. Sacchini, A.M. Whatmore, G. Girault, L. Freddi, A. Ferreira Vicente, V. Djokic. 2022. Online presentation to ZMD network meeting on the « Emergence of canine brucellosis in different European countries », EFSA, 13 October 2022.

2.6.7 One Health impact

The IDEMBRU project evaluated the presence of *Brucella* sp. in the environment, wildlife, domestic animals and humans (One Health approach). The project concentrated on new, so far undescribed species from the *Brucella* genus, their relation to close relative and plant root commensal *Ochrobactrum* group, but also on identification of a new reservoirs for already known, highly zoonotic species from this genus. In majority of EU countries, brucellosis has been eradicated. However, southern as well as EU neighbouring countries are still endemic, which goes to show that there are still unknown reservoirs for these zoonotic bacteria. Moreover, emergence of *B. canis* in Europe shows that although the surveillance systems in place are effective, many information lack regarding even biology of *Brucella*-host relation, like the impact of wild canids, omnivores or wild ruminants in the spread of this disease. Our project aimed to choose the most appropriate tools and devise effective diagnostic schemes for the comprehensive surveillance of brucellosis in EU. Usually, when diagnostic laboratories receive samples for brucellosis diagnostics, at least some clinical symptoms evocative of the disease caused by enough number of bacteria are present. The One Health approach allowed the consortium to devise and improve the diagnostic methods for low contamination samples (low concentration of bacteria in the large volume of sample), which is of utmost importance when searching for contaminated environment or reservoir species. At the end of the project, the contact with CIRAD regarding the use of AI through PADI Web portal was established and tracing of specific indicators, showing in google news for all European countries is being developed to create early warning system for brucellosis outbreaks.

Further, IDEMBRU project aimed to evaluate zoonotic potential of newly discovered *Brucella* species, by developing new phenotypic, molecular and *in vitro* characterisation methods. We compared growth on various nutrient deprived media, antibiotic resistance, motility, protein profiles, whole genome differences, specific SNPs, MLVA and HRM profiles, as well as their relation with host cells in *in vitro* conditions of highly-, non-zoonotic species, and unknown newly isolated strains. Several developed methods can be used for rapid and reliable characterisation of new *Brucella* strains zoonotic potential. This will reinforce the identification of highly zoonotic strains and management of brucellosis outbreaks. Furthermore, it will help evaluate risks for animal and public health when dealing with new, emerging *Brucella* species, such as *B. canis* or *B. amazoniensis* for example. These methods will be incorporated in the characterisation protocols of national reference laboratories for Brucellosis as well as EU referent laboratory.

The project already received interest from EFSA regarding the diagnostic, characterisation and management of emerging *Brucella* species. Furthermore, CIRAD will include PADI Web surveillance in their panel and the same system will be available through EFSA, ANSES and LRUE brucellosis websites.

This project helped reinforce relations among partners, establish collaborations on specific topics, such as phenotyping, MALDI-TOF MS analyses, and *in vitro* assays development. The work on certain topics will be further developed as parts of future projects in which, majority of the consortium will continue to participate. Furthermore, surveillance of wildlife reservoirs is already being prepared as a project proposal in combination with other bacterial pathogens. The project also helped reinforce competences and proficiency of Bulgarian National referent laboratory for brucellosis, which will significantly improve diagnostics and surveillance of this disease in the east of the EU, where situation is mainly unknown.

2.6.8 Data Management Plan

Not yet available. The DMP will be uploaded to Zenodo and link provided before the end of the One Health EJP (September 2023).

2.6.9 Future dissemination activities

Several scientific papers are still in preparation (majority of them). Upon acceptance and publication by chosen peer reviewed journals, these publications will be publicly available through Zenodo platform.

The impact of the IDEMBRU project will extend through validated SOPs as well that will find their purpose in national reference laboratories for Brucellosis. All SOPs will be made available on European Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis website.

The final product of IDEMBRU project is a comprehensive toolkit. This set of documents, instructions, SOPs and further guidelines will be made available through OH EJP IDEMBRU web site, as well as ANSES and EFSA websites.

2.7 JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE

2.7.1 Consortium composition

MEmE project coordinator:

A. Casulli (ISS)

Deputy coordinators:

G. Umhang (ANSES) and P. Maksimov (FLI)

Work packages leaders:

WP1: SAMPLING STRATEGY: J. Karamon (PIWET)

WP2: VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS: G. Umhang, F. Boue (ANSES)

WP3: DEVELOPMENT of NEW TOOLS AND PRODUCTION of EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DATA. P. Maksimov (FLI)

WP4: TRAINING, DISSEMINATION and PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES. A. Casulli (ISS)

WP5: SCIENTIFIC and ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT. A. Casulli (ISS)

Consortium (funded partners):

Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS), Italy (Coordinator); [Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut \(FLI\)](#), Germany; [Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail \(ANSES\)](#), France; [National Institute for Public Health and the Environment \(RIVM\)](#), The Netherlands; [National Veterinary Research Institute in Pulawy \(PIWET\)](#), Poland; [Norwegian Veterinary Institute \(NVI\)](#), Norway; [Statens Serum Institut \(SSI\)](#), Denmark; [National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinary Research \(INIAV\)](#), Portugal; [Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge \(INSA\)](#), Portugal; [University of Tartu \(UT\)](#), Estonia; [Veterinary and Food Laboratory \(VFL\)](#), Estonia; [Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment \(BIOR\)](#), Latvia.

External partners:

[Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna \(IZSS\)](#), Italy; [Department of Agriculture, Food and The Marine \(CVRL\)](#), Ireland; [University of Naples "Federico II" \(UNF\)](#), Italy; [University of Hohenheim \(UH\)](#), Germany; [Institute of Parasitology \(IP\)](#), Switzerland; [Norwegian Polar Institute \(NPI\)](#), Norway; [Svalbard Dyresykehus AS \(SDAS\)](#), Norway; [University Islamabad \(COMSATS\)](#), Pakistan.

2.7.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

[MEmE](#) is an international multicentre collaborative project that aims to fill research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control and epidemiology of zoonotic parasites *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg sl), causing alveolar echinococcosis (AE) and cystic echinococcosis (CE), respectively.

MEmE achievements were:

- The production of SOPs for the sampling of different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts.
- The validation of the parasitological (SSCT) and molecular diagnostic (multiplex- and MC-RT-PCRs) procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- The development, validation and comparison of new molecular tools (comparison of DNA extraction and PCRs assays, novel probe-based qPCRs, PCR-RFLPs and multiplex PCR assays and NGS approach).
- Multicentre studies for the production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments: contamination of fresh vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg; prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces.
- Quantitative assessment on the impact of human CE in Europe by means of systematic review approach.
- Molecular and clinical epidemiology studies in selected geographical areas.
- Dissemination of project results at different levels (general public, scientific community, experts, health authorities and media).

MEmE impacted on animal health, public health and food safety sectors. Beneficiaries of scientific outputs of MEmE are EU reference labs, international organizations and all decision makers. **We provided a set of molecular tools, epidemiological risk assessments and quantitative epidemiological**

models for the detection, surveillance and control of these parasitic infectious diseases in Europe and beyond.

MEmE scientific papers currently published on peer-review journals:

1. [Unveiling the incidences and trends of cystic echinococcosis in Europe: a systematic review from the MEME project](#). *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2022.
2. [Cystic echinococcosis in northern Tanzania: a pilot study in Masaai livestock-keeping communities](#). *Parasit Vectors*. 2022.
3. [Species and genotypes belonging to *Echinococcus granulosus* s.l. complex causing human cystic echinococcosis in Europe \(2000-2021\): a systematic review approach](#). *Parasit Vectors*. 2022.
4. [Comparison and evaluation of analytic and diagnostic performances of four commercial kits for the detection of antibodies against *E. granulosus* and *multilocularis* in human sera](#). *Comp Immunol Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2022.
5. [Insights into Human Cystic Echinococcosis in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq: Characteristics and Molecular Identification of Cysts](#). *Pathogens*. 2022.
6. [Chromosome-scale *Echinococcus granulosus* \(genotype G1\) genome reveals the Eg95 gene family and conservation of the EG95-vaccine molecule](#). *Commun Biol*. 2022.
7. [A Retrospective Cohort Study on Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province \(Pakistan\) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records](#). *Pathogens*. 2022.
8. [Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone](#). *Pathogens*. 2021.
9. [New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030](#). *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2021.
10. [Identification of *Echinococcus granulosus* genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs genotyping assays](#). *Pathogens*. 2021.
11. [Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs \(*Acinonyx jubatus*\) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed *Besnoitia* species](#). *Parasit Vectors*. 2021.
12. [Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the stool samples of naturally infected red foxes](#). *Animals (Basel)*. 2020.
13. [Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia \(Italy\)](#). *Pathogens*. 2020.
14. [A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level](#). *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. 2020.
15. [Bayesian analysis of three methods for diagnosis of cystic echinococcosis in sheep](#). *Pathogens*. 2020.
16. [Species detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* complex by novel probe-based real-time PCRs](#). *Pathogens*. 2020.
17. [Microsatellite investigations of multiple *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans](#). *Pathogens*. 2020.
18. [Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis](#). *The Lancet Global Health*. 2020.

2.7.3 Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

Figure 1. Updated PERT chart with interconnections and domino effects between WPs and Tasks of MEmE. In red 2 tasks «discontinued» for COVID-19 pandemic and 9 «new» tasks/subtasks implemented in the project.

WP1. Sampling strategy

WP1 is aiming to generate *a priori* protocols (T1) and to collect samples (T2, T3) for their use in WP2 and WP3.

WP1-T1. Standard Operating Procedures for sampling in matrices.

The following Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) were generated to feed activities in WP1, WP2 and WP3:

- Sampling of faecal material in dog faeces collected from the environment (**WP1-T2**) and their processing for molecular analysis (**WP3-T7**).
- Sampling of Eg cysts from naturally infected sheep and pigs at abattoirs (**WP1-T2**) and their processing for molecular analyses (**WP2-T1, T2**).
- Sampling of faeces and small/large intestines from naturally infected foxes and experimentally infected foxes (**WP1-T2, T3**) and their processing for parasitological and molecular analyses (**WP2-T1, T2, T3** and **WP3-T2, T3**).
- Sampling of vegetables for human consumption (**WP1-T2**) and their processing for molecular analysis (**WP3-T6**).

- Validation of Magnetic Capture qPCR assay (**WP2-T3**).

WP1-T2. Matrices collection in the field from (wild and domestic) intermediate and definitive hosts.

The aim of this task was to collect different parasitic matrices from naturally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts for their use in **WP2** and **WP3**.

WP1-T3. Matrices collection from experimental animal models.

Ethical authorisation on "Experimental infection of carnivores with *Echinococcus multilocularis*" has been obtained for five years (Decree n° 21_105#33541 November 16 2021, APAFIS #33541-202110081648536 v11).

Figure 2. Samples collected by WP1-T2 and WP1-T3 that were used in WP2 and WP3. See Table 1 for details.

Type of samples	Number of samples
Wild and domestic animal material:	
intestines of red foxes from endemic areas	590
intestines of arctic foxes from endemic areas	381
intestines of raccoon dogs from endemic areas	100
intestines of red foxes from non-endemic areas	363
cysts from pigs' livers	210
cysts from sheep's livers	200
sibling voles	70
faecal samples from dogs	1,619
arctic fox faecal samples	380
samples of lettuce	1,120
samples of berries	412
Experimental animal material:	
Em eggs	5,000
foxes' faeces	50
microtubes of frozen protoscoleces	100

Table 1. Samples collected from wild and domestic animals (WP1-T2) and from experimental animal models (WP1-T3) to feed tasks in WP2 and WP3.

WP2. Validation of parasitological and molecular assays

WP2-T1. Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT. [Ms in preparation]

Among the 603 red and arctic fox intestines collected by five partners (NVI, PIWET, FLI, ANSES and BIOR), 568 were independently analysed for each of the four segments of intestines resulting in 139 positive samples. The highest sensitivity was obtained for the combination of segments S4-S2 (99.3%), S4-S1 (97.1%) and S4-S3 (97.8%). The protocol of validation for SSCT was also applied to racoon dogs from Poland and Latvia. Among 70 racoon dog intestines which were analysed, five were infected by Em. Data from naturally infected racoon dogs was combined with those from racoon dogs experimentally infected. The best combination of segments for racoon dogs was S4-S2 with a sensitivity of 100%, confirming that worms are mainly present in the posterior part as observed for foxes.

WP2-T2. Comparison of multiplex PCRs.

This task focused on the validation of two molecular assays widely used for the detection of *Echinococcus* spp. targeting mitochondrial and nuclear markers: Assay 1. Boubaker et al. (PLoS Negl Trop Dis, 2013). The assay was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors, resulting in the lack of six over 11 PCR targets needed for proper species identification. Thus, results were evaluated again under several modified conditions. Last, single primer pairs were tested independently to evaluate their performance and, when their working conditions were found proper, they were combined with other primer pairs to achieve a balanced amplification. In conclusion, lack of specific PCR bands or the appearance of aspecific PCR bands made it impossible to execute the multiplex PCR and to get simultaneously all the targeted markers amplified, neither with the original conditions nor with the modifications tried. Assay 2. Trachsel et al. (Parasitology, 2007). The multiplex-PCR was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors. Em amplicon showed the characteristic band (267 bp), *Taenia* spp. amplicon always showed a non-specific band (200 bp), and the amplicon of Eg was often weak. Mixed infections were excluded by the nature of the matrices used, therefore the results were evaluated again under several modified conditions. After several tests, the concentration of the primers was changed to an equimolar primer mix (0.2 μ M), which resulted in a correct identification of all species. Expanding the number of Em DNA tested (N=82) from different countries it was observed that 10 out of 82 samples showed the typical band of Em but also a light band typical of Eg (117 bp). In conclusion, this single-tube multiplex PCR has been proved to be a robust and reliable assay that can be used not only for the identification of taeniid eggs but extended to DNA extracted from different matrices.

WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay. [Ms in preparation]

Magnetic Capture techniques together with the appropriate PCR protocol offer a good diagnostic alternative to the conventional parasitological Sedimentation and Counting Technique (SCT), and Intestinal Scraping Technique (IST), which also allows the processing of significantly higher sample size. There was a delay with the milestone in this task when the lead was transferred from SVA (SVA withdrew from MEmE in 2021) to NVI in M37. Two magnetic capture DNA extraction protocols and accompanying training video were published on Zenodo as project restricted technical notes in M42 (DOIs: 10.5281/zenodo.4897969; 10.5281/zenodo.4746190; 10.5281/zenodo.4746181; 10.5281/zenodo.4746141). In addition to this two previously published realtime PCR protocols had SOPs developed for use within the project. Initially nine laboratories expressed an interest in learning the method but in the end only one attended training and a further four participated in the proficiency tests. Further information about training and proficiency test results are in WP4.

WP2-T3. New. Comparison of Magnetic Capture protocols for extraction and detection of Em DNA in feces of definitive hosts. [Ms in preparation]

To date, two protocols based on the magnetic capture principle have been published (Isaksson et al., 2014; Maas et al., 2016). The aim of this activity was to compare the performance of these two methods (Isaksson_MC_qPCR and Maas_MC_qPCR). The Isaksson_MC_qPCR showed a higher diagnostic sensitivity (88%) than Maas_MC_qPCR (73%) (Table 2). In the negative (as determined by IST examination) field samples, Isaksson_MC_qPCR detected two fecal samples as *E. multilocularis* positive. In the case of Maas_MC_qPCR all IST negative fecal samples were reported as negative. There were no differences between the protocols for the fecal samples in the IST category +++, but for the fecal samples in the IST categories ++, + and -, Isaksson_MC_qPCR detected a markedly higher proportion of positive samples than Maas_MC_qPCR method (Table 3).

Sample groups	Number of samples	Worm burden according to IST	Additional information
-group	29	Negative	-
+group	30	1-5 worms	27 faeces from foxes with patent <i>E. multilocularis</i> infections and for two samples the status was not assigned
++group	29	>5-50 worms	27 faeces from foxes with patent <i>E. multilocularis</i> infections and two samples from foxes with prepatent infections
+++group	20	>50-1,000 worms	19 faeces from foxes with patent <i>E. multilocularis</i> infections and one sample from a fox with prepatent infections
++++group	9	> 1,000 worms	all samples except one derived from animals with patent infections; for one fox, the status was not assigned

Table 2. Faecal samples from foxes naturally infected with *E. multilocularis* tested by Intestinal Scraping Technique (IST).

Sample groups	Isaksson_MC_qPCR	Maas_MC_qPCR
% of positive in ++++ group	100	100
% of positive in +++ group	95	90
% of positive in ++ group	100	79,3
% of positive in + group	70	50
% of positive in negative group	6,9	0
% Total diagnostic sensitivity	88	73

Table 3. Diagnostic sensitivity of the Isaksson_MC_qPCR and Maas_MC_qPCR.

WP3. Development validation of new tools and production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments

WP3-T1. New molecular markers for Em and Eg sl: from rapid diagnostics to source attribution. WP3-T1-ST1. New mitochondrial markers. [Ms in preparation]

Designing diagnostic tools for *Echinococcus* species requires detailed knowledge of range-wide genetic variation. Mitochondrial genome has been a genetic marker of choice for diagnostics, primarily due to its high copy number that facilitates analysis of *Echinococcus* samples even for partially degraded samples. To develop species and genotype specific diagnostic assays, we sequenced mitochondrial

genomes using a worldwide scale panel of different *E. granulosus* s.l. (Eg sl) and *E. multilocularis* (Em) species and genotypes. For genotypes Eg ss genotypes G1 and G3 we sequenced near-complete mitogenomes (11682 bp), leaving out repetitive non-coding sequences in the mitogenome (Kinkar et al., 2019) that are difficult to sequence. For other species and genotypes we sequenced complete genomes. During the working process, it became clear that the genetic variation of Eg sl is significantly higher compared to Em and requires more input from Eg sl, especially of genotype G1 that had very high genetic variability. Therefore, we changed the original strategy and included more Eg sl samples (N=392; from 25 countries) into the analysis, compared to Em (N=108; from 12 countries), keeping the total number of 500 samples as originally planned. The mitogenome variation of Eg ss, especially of G1, was very high. The overall haplotype diversity (Hd) index for genotype G1 was (Hd=0.992) and the nucleotide diversity was 0.00129. The huge variation of genotype G1 is illustrated in Figure 3. Other species and genotypes had significantly lower variation. Based on the genetic variability data of Eg sl and Em, we developed Toehold Exchange Probes for a reliable and rapid identification of all species and genotypes of Eg sl and Em. Testing these probes is in progress.

Figure 3. Worldwide phylogenetic network of *E. granulosus* s.s. (G1) samples based on near-complete mitogenome sequences. Colours represent distinct haplogroups.

WP3-T1-ST2. New microsatellite markers. [A] Published, B) Ms in preparation]

A) The objective of this study was to obtain a better understanding of CE infection in livestock and humans from very low and high endemic areas by studying the genetic diversity of *E. granulosus* s.s. at the intra-individual host level. EgSca6 and EgSca11 microsatellite profiles were studied in 93 sheep from France and Tunisia, and in 12 cattle and 31 children from Tunisia only, all presenting multiple CE cysts (2 to 10). Overall, 96% of sheep, 92% of cattle, and 48% of children had at least two cysts with different microsatellite profiles. Inversely, 35% of sheep, 17% of cattle, and 65% of children had at least two cysts with the same microsatellite profile. The genotyping results for the CE samples highlight high and similar genetic diversity in France and Tunisia, suggesting that the probability of being successively infected by CE of the same microsatellite profile was rare in both countries. Therefore, our results

suggest that in rare cases, several eggs of the same microsatellite profile, from two to seven in our data, can be ingested simultaneously in a single infection event and develop into several cysts in livestock and children. They also indicate that multiple infection events are frequent in livestock, even in a low endemic country such as France, and are less frequent but not negligible in children in a high endemic country such as Tunisia. Moreover, this is the first time that genetic evidence of secondary CE has been found.

Figure 4. Distribution of the number of hosts according to the number of cysts (A) and to the number of microsatellite profiles (B) per host species (sheep, cattle and humans) for the panel of *E. granulosus* s.s. samples from France and Tunisia, screened by EgSca6 and EgSca11 microsatellites.

B) The screening of the Eg genome resulted in the identification of 15 new microsatellites targets, which were evaluated for their polymorphism, reproducibility, limit of detection, quality of the electrophoretic profiles and their specificity. The 6 selected targets were coupled with EgSca6 microsatellite previously described in **A)** (Figure 4). The panel was composed of 7 microsatellites, 5 targets with trinucleotide motifs and 2 with tetranucleotide motifs.

Figure 5. Examples of the electrophoretic profiles obtained for one *E. granulosus* s.s. sample for three of the selected loci.

A total of 91 Eg ss DNA samples from North Africa (Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia) and Europe (Italy and Greece) were collected and tested with the 7 microsatellites revealing a very high discriminating power

with 90 different multilocus genotypes (Figure 5) due to identification of 10 to 48 alleles for each microsatellites. Using these five populations, a preliminary population study was realized. The genetic distance calculated using Bruvo's distance allows to distinguish cluster_1 composed by 21 samples from Greece, cluster_1 with 5 samples from Algeria but also one from Italy and Greece, cluster_3 with five samples from Greece one from Italy when the others samples grouped in different clusters with samples from different origins (Figure 6). The panel composed of the seven microsatellites targets is a relevant alternative to classical Sanger sequencing of whole or near-complete mitogenome in order to perform phylogenetic studies but also source attribution.

Figure 6. Minimum spanning network of the five Mediterranean populations of *E. granulosus s.s.* using Bruvo's distance calculated from data of the samples panel with the seven microsatellites selected.

WP3-T1-ST3. NGS-based method.

Mitogenome data can pose a means to track the source of infection. Human infections can nowadays (due to extensive travelling and migration) occur abroad and testing the origin of infection requires an effective method for testing. The very high variability of *E. granulosus s.s.* (*Eg ss*) at the mitogenome level, especially of genotype G1 that is the most prevalent genotype among humans (see **WP3-T8-ST1**), provides a possibility to perform source attribution analysis. During this project a method was developed that enables to sequence 96 mitogenomes in a single sequencing run, using short-read next generation sequencing (SR-NGS). Based on extensive knowledge of genetic variability of the genus *Echinococcus*, obtained from **WP3-T1-ST2**, we developed primers that enable PCR-amplification of the entire mitogenome in a single PCR. However, as the PCR amplification of the entire mitochondrial genome requires high-quality DNA, but in reality the DNA quality of parasite samples varies and often important samples are of low quality, we also developed primers that allow PCR amplification of the whole mitogenome in four fragments. The latter approach was proven to be significantly more efficient compared to the amplification of mitochondrial genome in one PCR, especially for *Eg ss* that contain repetitive non-coding sequences in the mitogenome (Kinkar et al., 2019). The four-primer approach was used to analyse 96 samples in a single SR-NGS run, which allows easy and cost-effective generation of highly accurate mitogenome sequences (the principal workflow is presented in Figure 7).

Workflow for *Echinococcus* mitogenome sequencing in 4 fragments

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the workflow for sequencing *Echinococcus* mitogenomes in four overlapping fragments, using short-read next generation sequencing.

WP3-T2. New molecular methods for the detection of *Em* and *Eg*

WP3-T2-ST1. New singleplex TaqMan qPCRs for detection and genotyping of *Eg* s1 and *Em*.

[Published] We established six TaqMan® probe-based qPCRs that can be used for the diagnosis of *E. multilocularis* and *E. granulosus* genotypes in five epidemiologically relevant species and subgroups, i.e. *E. granulosus* s.s. (G1 to G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* complex (G6 to G8 and G10) and a single genotype (G8) of the *E. canadensis* complex as a single-step genotyping technique. It also allows differentiating *E. granulosus* samples from other *Echinococcus* or *Taenia* species in samples derived from cystic or faecal material. The qPCRs show high efficiency (ranging between 99% and 106%), high analytical specificity (100%) and sensitivity (ranging between 0.6 and 1.4 copies/μl), when used with DNA obtained from cysts or from cloned PCR products. Therefore, they are suitable for a PCR-based diagnosis of cystic echinococcosis in intermediate hosts, including humans as aberrant intermediate hosts (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Fluorescence curves for developed TaqMan® qPCRs of serially diluted *Echinococcus* reference DNA samples. **A:** G1_3 qPCR: *E. granulosus* s.s., **B:** G4 qPCR: *E. equinus*, **C:** G5_10 qPCR: *E. ortleppi*, and **D:** G5_10 qPCR: *E. canadensis*. RFU: relative fluorescence units. Cq: quantification cycle.

WP3-T2-ST2. New. New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Eg s1 and Em. [Ms in preparation]

To parallelize the detection and typing of members of the Eg complex, two variants (EG1 and EG1) of a TaqMan® probe-based five-plex real-time qPCR assay were developed and validated. The first variant of these assays (EG1) can simultaneously detect and genotype *E. granulosus* s.s. (G1, G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), and the *E. canadensis* complex (G6 to G8 and G10) (Figure 9). The second variant of the test (EG2) is capable of detecting and distinguishing *E. granulosus* s.s. (G1, G3), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* (G8), and the remaining two members of the *E. canadensis* cluster (G6 and G10). For simultaneous diagnosis and genotyping of Eg complex and Em infections, further two variants of a TaqMan® probe-based multiplex real-time qPCR were developed and validated (EGM1 and EGM2). EGM1 multiplex assay is able efficiently to distinguish between *E. granulosus* s.s., *E. equinus*, *E. canadensis* (G6-10) and *E. multilocularis*. In the case of EGM2 multiplex assay the species *E. granulosus* s.s., *E. canadensis* (G8), *E. multilocularis* and *E. canadensis* (G6-10) can be simultaneously detected and genotyped. Into each TaqMan® probe-based multiplex real-time qPCR assay an internal control was included.

Figure 9. Fluorescence curves for developed EG1 TaqMan® qPCR (A) of serially diluted *Echinococcus* reference DNA samples. B: G1_3_qPCR: *E. granulosus s.s.*, C: G4_qPCR: *E. equinus*, D: G5_10_qPCR: *E. ortleppi*, and E: G5_10_qPCR: *E. canadensis*. RFU: relative fluorescence units. Cq: quantification cycle.

WP3-T2-ST3 New. New validated method to identify *Eg sl* at species level by PCR-RFLP and mPCR.

[Published] The zoonotic tapeworm *E. granulosus s.l.* (*Eg sl*) represents a species complex encompassing multiple causative agents of cystic echinococcosis, a neglected tropical disease affecting more than one million people in the world. At least eight genotypes, grouped in five species, are currently recognized within this species complex, and they differ in terms of relative public health impact. Here we present a molecular method that first identifies the common *E. granulosus s.s.* (*Eg ss*) (genotypes G1 and G3) based on a PCR-RFLP assay, and can further identify the remaining species based on a multiplex PCR assay. We demonstrate the applicability of the method to DNA extracted from parasitic cyst material of human and animal origin, preserved in ethanol or frozen. The method has been developed and validated at the European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites (EURLP), according to the ISO/IE 17025.

Figure 10. Flow chart with four phases of the method. Phase1: DNA extraction. Phase 2: PCR amplification of a 444 bp fragment of the mitochondrial gene COX1. Phase 3: RFLP assay, showing the AluI specific digestion pattern of *E. granulosus s.s.* (G1,G3). Phase 4: Multiplex PCR assay, showing the specific banding patterns for the G4-G10.

WP3-T2-ST4 New. Rapid molecular identification of *Em* and *Eg* *sl* tissue samples by a novel PCR-RFLP.

[Ms in preparation] We developed a PCR-RFLP approach that allows specific identification of *Em*, *Eg* *ss*, *E. ortleppi* and *E. canadensis* by differentiating them from the genus *Taenia*, *Hydatigera* and *Versteria*. After PCR amplification of parasitic cestode DNA, an enzymatic digestion (*Dde* I, *Hinf* I and *Bsa* I) of the PCR product (846 bp) resulted in specific RFLP profiles. The limit of detection was estimated 300 copies with 100% specificity from 73 tissue DNA samples previously diagnosed by sequencing as other *Taenidae* species. Concerning sensitivity, all DNA samples were correctly identified: 54 as *E. multilocularis* with four different strains (Europe, Asia, Arctic and Mongolia), 16 *E. canadensis*, 5 *E. ortleppi* and 13 *E. granulosus ss*. The robustness of the method was evaluated by testing variation of annealing or digestion temperature and concentrations of $MgCl_2$ or primers, resulting in a successful diagnostic method for *Em* and *Eg* *sl* tissue DNA.

Figure 11. RFLP profiles obtained for *E. multilocularis*, *E. canadensis*, *E. ortleppi*, *E. granulosus s.s.* and the genera *Taenia*, *Hydatigera* and *Versteria* tissue DNA samples.

WP3-T3. Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using Regions Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS.

Magnetic capturing of molecular targets captured in complex samples can be sensitive approach to remove contaminants and genetic material of no interest in complex matrixes. This method help identify targets that could render undetectable with traditional nucleic acid isolation approaches if present in low levels. Region Specific Extraction (RSE)-approaches allow more biomass to be processed compared with traditional DNA-protocols where typically only a fraction of the same input material can be processed. Testing the samples with sensitive qPCR methods can be a useful combination for surveillance work when screening for low abundant targets. The method of (Isaksson et al., 2014) is routinely used for the surveillance of *E. multilocularis* by some partners. To test if it was possible to employ NGS methods for detection and verification and characterisation of parasite positive samples prepared from magnetic capture methods, this task (ST1 and ST3) focussed to investigate if two different NGS platforms and different approaches to their use could allow successful characterisation and identification of samples from complex samples.

WP3-T3-ST1. Region Specific Extraction sequencing of samples on nanopore NGS platform.

The use of the nanopore sequence platform for the identification of Em and Eg from positive controls prepared using the existing magnetic capture method (Isaksson et al., 2014), was run directly on a nanopore flow-cell, but these samples failed to produce good sequence data from the nanopore sequence runs. Attempts to solve this by modification of RSE protocol and sample preparation steps, were carried out. Modification of the RSE protocol involved testing of new fishing probes and attempts to perform a variation of pre-amplification procedures to the RSE templates before sequencing, was done either by long PCR-tiling, random or targeted whole genome amplification techniques, where some showed great promise for clean parasite samples prepared via standard DNA-isolation procedures. This protocol failed for RSE prepared templates from fecal samples and it was not possible to identify the responsible factors preventing success.

Figure 12. Steps for nanopore sequencing of DNA from regular and magnetic capture DNA-samples from *Echinococcus* spp. that were explored in WP3-T3. Protocol worked for clean DNA allowing identification of samples, but shortcomings were encountered for the MC-DNA samples.

WP3-T3-ST2 New. Detection of the entire mitogenome of *Echinococcus multilocularis* by Region-Specific Extraction method and Illumina based Next-Generation Sequencing.

DNA was extracted and processed from Em worm and cyst material according to the Region-Specific-Extraction (RSE) method (Dapprich et al., 2016). By NGS-based RSE approach from this study, the mitogenome (~13kb) from Em could be successfully captured and amplified. To validate the success and the accuracy of this protocol, the mitogenome from the same Em isolates were also analysed by the whole genome Illumina-based NGS. With this RSE method, the entire mitogenome of Em could be extracted. The read depth coverage was sufficient (median coverage per isolate ≥ 122 reads) to detect existing SNPs with a high confidence. The comparison of mitogenomes extracted by RSE data with mitogenome data obtained by direct NGS of the whole DNAs showed that the accuracy of the RSE method is consistent. Processing of ten samples and analysis of their mitogenomes showed that the method is able to detect genetic variations between the samples. The number of SNPs varied between 63 and 70 among the isolates collected in Germany. The results from the present study suggest that both approaches can provide a less costly and less time-consuming alternative for parasite identification and characterisation than conventional methods, especially when compared to classical methods i.e. “PCR plus Sanger sequencing”, for clean parasite samples. This method provides a more precise and flexible possibility for discovery of new typing markers as well as efficient analysis of the micro-diversity within the Em population (Figures 13, 14).

Figure 13. Positions of SNPs in mitogenome, detected in the *E. multilocularis* field samples by the RSE-Illumina NGS method.

Figure 14. The number of detected SNPs in respective Mitogenomes in the field samples applying RSE-Illumina NGS method.

WP3-T4. Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma (Discontinued)

Task replaced with “Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE/AE” due to COVID-19.

WP3-T5. Assessment of newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques.

Since 30 years from the development of the first molecular techniques for the detection of *Echinococcus* DNA, the molecular diagnostic became essential. There are currently a lot of molecular assays to detect DNA of Em and Eg sl by different methods. In absence of reference methods, a comparison of the most used techniques and those developed in MEmE was realized in order to provide recommendations for the diagnosis. All methods were performed at least by two partners. Ten partners were participating to the six methods selected (Table 4) by testing one tissue panel and copro-DNA panel to evaluate the specificity and sensibility of the methods (Table 5). The Cest multiplex and the two PCR-RFLP methods had high specificity (>90%) and sensitivity (>90%) concerning tissue samples. Nevertheless, sensitivity of the Cest multiplex is much lower (76%) concerning copro-DNA in contrast to the very high values (93-100%) of the three real-time PCR assays. However the specificity for the two real-time PCR assays targeting Em was problematic for tissue samples (72-76%), mainly due to cross reactions with highly concentrated Eg sl DNA. Both sensitivity and specificity of the Eg sl

real-time multiplex PCR was satisfying (93%), independently of the type of DNA. The evaluation carried showed a homogeneity between laboratories for each technique. This allowed us to confirm that real-time PCR techniques is more suitable than other approaches for the analysis of copro-DNA. For tissue samples, the end-point PCR approach and the two RFLP PCRs are the recommended methods.

Type of assay	Name of the test	Reference	Targeted species	Laboratories involved in the evaluation
End point PCR	Multiplex Cest	Trachsel et al., 2007	Em, Eg sl, Taenia spp.	ISS, FLI, ANSES + INSA, BIOR, IZSS, UT, CVRL, UZ, PIWET
Real-time PCR	qPCR-Em	Knapp et al., 2016	Em	ANSES, FLI, PIWET
Real-time PCR	qPCR-Em MGB	Isaksson et al., 2014	Em	ANSES, FLI
Real-time PCR	qPCRs Eg sl	Maksimov et al., 2020 (WP3-T2-ST1)	Eg sl	ANSES, FLI
RFLP	Eg sl RFLP*	Santolamazza et al., 2020 (WP3-T2-ST3)	Eg sl	ISS, ANSES
RFLP	Em/Eg sl RFLP*	Anses in prep (WP3-T2-ST4)	Em, Eg sl	ISS, ANSES

Table 4. List of the methods selected and laboratory involved in the comparison. * Methods using only DNA from tissues.

Type of matrix	Class of species	Parasite species	N of samples
Tissue	Nematodes	<i>T. canis</i>	3
		<i>F. hepatica</i>	1
		<i>F. gigantica</i>	1
	Cestodes	<i>T. leonina</i>	5
		<i>A. incisa</i>	3
		<i>M. lineatus</i>	1
		<i>M. litteratus</i>	3
		<i>H. kamyai</i>	3
		<i>H. taeniaeformis</i>	3
		<i>T. krabbei</i>	3
		<i>T. hydatigena</i>	4
		<i>Em</i>	7
		<i>Eg ss, G1</i>	3
		<i>Eg ss, G3</i>	2
		<i>E. equinus</i>	2
		<i>E. ortleppi</i>	3
		<i>E. canadensis, G6</i>	3
		<i>E. canadensis, G7</i>	3
		<i>E. canadensis, G10</i>	1
Feces	Cestodes	<i>Em</i>	6
		Negative	2
		<i>Eg ss (+Taenia sp.)</i>	12

Table 5. List of the parasite species, number of samples, tissue and fecal DNA samples constituting the panel.

WP3-T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg.

WP3-T6-ST1. Contamination of lettuces. [Ms merging ST1 and ST2 in preparation]

A total of 1,120 lettuce samples but also 69 from other vegetables (mainly parsley, spinach and chard) were collected during the summers 2020-2021 from local markets, producers, kitchen gardens and supermarkets with around 50-100 samples collected by each partner which realized the first washing step of the filtration method. The sequential sieving and molecular detection were realized at the Anses to assure homogenous assays and the correct limit of detection which was estimated at 3 eggs in 95% of the cases and 2 and 1 eggs in 75% and 50% of the cases, respectively. The detection of Em and Eg sl was realized using specific real-time PCR (Knapp et al., 2016, Maksimov et al., 2020) (see **WP3-T2-ST1**) and by end-point PCR and sequencing for others Taenidae (Trachsel et al., 2007). When possible pools of two lettuces from the same origin were realized. Considering Em endemic areas, the proportion of Em positive lettuce samples was 1.1%, while it was 2.1% for Eg sl considering all areas (Table 6). Additionally, other Taenidae species were detected in 2.4% of the samples mainly *Hydatigera* sp. and *T. hydatigena*. This is the largest epidemiological study ever conducted on the contamination of lettuces by Em and Eg. Such study will contribute in the understanding of foodborne transmission of these parasites.

Figure 15. Geographical distribution of the positive *E. multilocularis*, *E. granulosus* s.l. and other *Taenia* spp. samples detected in the lettuces from selected countries. Only the number of lettuce samples with at least one positive sample for Em or Eg sl was reported.

	N of samples	Em	Eg sl	Other taenidae sp.
France (Anses)	228	3	0	6 <i>Hydatigera</i> sp.
Portugal (Insa)	101	0	0	(1 <i>H. diminuta</i>)
Netherlands (RIVM)	6	0	0	0
Switzerland (UZH)	80	1	1 <i>E. canadensis</i>	2 <i>Hydatigera</i> sp.
Denmark (ISS)	50	2	0	(1 <i>Dilepis undula</i>)
Germany (UH)	63	0	0	1 <i>Hydatigera</i> sp.
(FLI)	11	0	0	0
Italy Rome (ISS)	80	0	1 <i>Eg ss</i>	1 <i>Hydatigera</i> sp.
Sardinia (IZS)	105	0	4 <i>Eg ss</i>	3 <i>Hydatigera</i> sp., 1 <i>T. multiceps</i> 1 <i>Taenia</i> sp.
Naples (UN)	46	0	3 <i>Eg ss</i>	0
Latvia (BIOR)	62	1	1 <i>E. canadensis</i>	1 <i>Hydatigera</i> sp. (1 <i>Atriotaeonia incisa</i>)
Poland (PIWET)	74	0	0	0
Norway (VETINST)	39	0	0	1 <i>T. serialis</i> or <i>T. krabbei</i>
Pakistan (COMSTAT)	100	2	3 <i>Eg ss</i> 1 <i>E. canadensis</i>	5 <i>T. saginata</i> , 1 <i>Hydatigera</i> sp. 3 <i>T. hydatigena</i>
Tunisie (UM)	75	0	9 <i>Eg ss</i>	3 <i>T. hydatigena</i>
Total	1,120	9	23	28
Proportion detected:	/	1%*	2.1%	2.9%

Table 6. Detection of DNA from *E. multilocularis*, *E. granulosus* s.l. and other *Taenidae* species from lettuces from kitchen garden, local markets and supermarkets from different countries. * calculated using only samples from known endemic countries for *Em*. Cestode species other than *Taenidae* were indicated between brackets.

WP3-T6-ST2 New. Contamination of berries. [Ms merging ST1 and ST2 in preparation]

A new subtask on the detection of *Echinococcus* spp. eggs in berries (mainly concerning strawberries and blueberries) was inserted. The filtration method was validated on strawberries with 95% probability of detection of 3 eggs in 200g sample (88% for both 1 and 2 eggs). In 2022, 12 partners (including external partners Finland and Tunisia) have collected 20 to 30 samples per country trying to prioritize local markets and completed by supermarkets if needed. In total, 412 berries samples were collected (Table 7). *Em* was detected in 6.9% of strawberries and 7.8% of blueberries from all known endemic countries, with higher proportions for the two Baltic countries (Figure 16). *Eg ss* was detected in 1.3% of strawberries and 1% of blueberries for European countries, with very high proportion (81.3%) in strawberries from Tunisia. No case of *Em* and *Eg sl* were obtained from the others types of berries. In Europe, the proportion of contamination in strawberries and blueberries was similar for *Em* and for *Eg sl* but seems more important for *Em* comparing to lettuces. Others cestode species were detected in six cases. This is the largest epidemiological study ever conducted on the contamination of berries by *Em* and *Eg*. Such study will contribute in the understanding of foodborne transmission of these parasites.

	Strawberries	Blueberries	Raspberry	Blackberries	other berries		Total N
France (Anses)	0/54	1 Em/31					85
Netherlands (RIVM)	1 Em/8	1 Em/6	0/3	0/3	0/4 redcurrant	0/1 white currant	25
Switzerland (UZH)	1 Em/10	0/7	0/6	0/6	0/1 redcurrant		30
Denmark (SSI)	1 Em/30 +1 <i>Hydatigera</i> <i>sp.</i>						30
Latvia (BIOR)	4 Em/30 +1 <i>T. serialis</i>	4 Em + 1 Eg ss/30 +1 <i>M. melesi</i>					60
Estonia (UT)	5 Em/30						30
Poland (PIWET)	1 Eg ss/13	0/3	0/5	0/4	0/4 blueberry bushes	0/1 canadian saskatoon berry	30
Italy-Sardinia (IZS)	1 Eg ss/34 +2 <i>Hydatigera</i> <i>sp.</i>						34
Portugal (INIAV)	1 Eg ss/17	0/15	0/15				47
Finland (FFA)	0/10	0/8	0/2		0/2 black currant	0/3 red cranberry	25
Tunisie (UM)	13 Eg ss/16 +1 <i>T. hydatigena</i>						16
Total N	252	100	31	13	16		412
Em proportion*	Em: 6.9%	Em: 7.8%					
Eg sl proportion	Eg ss: 6.3%	Eg ss: 1%					

Table 7. Detection of DNA from *Em*, *Eg sl* and other cestode species from berries obtained from the wild, kitchen gardens, local markets and supermarkets from different countries. * *Em* proportion was calculated including samples from known endemic countries.

Figure 16. Geographical distribution of the positive *E. multilocularis*, *E. granulosus* ss samples detected in strawberries and blueberries from selected countries. Only the number of berry samples with at least one positive sample for Em or Eg ss was reported.

WP3-T6-ST3 New. Dispersion of Em/Eg eggs in the soil.

A new subtask was inserted to assess the dispersion of Em eggs in the soil. One fox faecal sample containing 10,000 eggs obtained by experimental infection (**WP1-T3**) was deposited in the centre of a 2x2 m naive outside soil plot. Four months after, 400 surface (0-1 cm) soil samples, homogenously distributed, were collected and analysed by flotation to concentrate the eggs before DNA extraction and detection by real-time PCR (Knapp et al. 2016). Flotation of the remaining faecal sample identified 378 eggs, giving an estimated soil dispersion of 87% of the eggs (9,622 out of 10,000). The DNA of the eggs was detected in 37.8% of the soil samples (151 out of 400) that were distributed in all directions but mainly in the direction of the prevailing wind (Figure 17). The dispersion of eggs have reached the maximum distance of 1 to 1.4 m from centre to each border or each corner, respectively. According to Ct values of the real-time PCR, the detection was mainly done from one egg (92%) obtained after the flotation. Moreover, in the centre of the plot (12 squares of 10x10 cm), eggs were detected at depth of 1-3 cm. These data will be useful to understand the dispersion of Em eggs especially in kitchen gardens, which may result in the contamination of vegetables.

Figure 17. Spatial distribution of *Em* eggs on the surface and in depth (level -1 and -2) after four months dispersion from a fecal sample containing 10,000 eggs on a native soil plot (2x2 m).

WP3-T7. Prevalence of *Em/Eg* in dogs (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas.

Totally, 1,619 samples of dog faeces were collected in 7 European areas (France, Poland, Denmark, Italy, Estonia, Latvia and Norway) in 2020-2022. All samples were examined with mPCR (Trachsel et al., 2007): 0.2% were positive for *Em*, 1.4% for *Eg s.l.* and 4.0% for *Taenia*. *Em* was found in Poland (0.7%), *Eg* in Italy (10.3%) and Poland (0.2%) (Figure 18). Sequencing of samples confirmed the *Echinococcus* species and identify 6 *Taenia* species and *Mesocestoides* sp. Some samples were examined with an additional qPCR methods for *Em* (Knapp et al., 2016; N=839) and qPCR for *Eg s.l.* (Maksimov et al., 2020; see WP3-T2-ST1; N=1,169). Three samples were positive to *Em*, and 19 to *Eg ss* (G1, G3). All these samples were positive also in mPCR. Moreover, questionnaires (N=1,492) were delivered to the owners of the dogs analysed. A summary of the results on the potential risk factors selected from the questionnaires was presented in Figure 19. Even if dogs were little prevalent for *Em*, they pose a risk for the transmission due to their close contact with humans.

Figure 18. Prevalence of *Echinococcus* spp. and *Taenia* spp. in dogs (N=1,619) in selected European areas.

Figure 19. Summary of selected results based on questionnaire (N=1,492) delivered to dogs' owners.

WP3-T8. Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires (Discontinued)

Task replaced with "Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE/AE" due to COVID-19.

WP3-T8 New. Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE/AE.

WP3-T8-ST1 New. Species/genotypes of E. granulosus s.l. causing human CE in Europe (2000-2021).

[Published] This systematic review aimed to fill a gap of knowledge by providing a quantitative measure of molecularly identified species and genotypes belonging to *E. granulosus s.l.* causing human CE in Europe during the period 2000-2021. From a total of 1,643 scientific papers, 51 records were included in the SR. The main inclusion criterion for this study was the molecular confirmation of Eg at the genotype/species level as a causative agent of human CE cases in selected European countries. Relevant data were obtained from 29 out of 39 eligible European countries. This SR identified 599 human molecularly confirmed echinococcal cysts: 460 (76.8%) identified as *E. granulosus s.s.*, 130 (21.7%) as *E. canadensis* cluster (G6/7 and G10), 7 (1.2%) as *E. ortleppi* (G5), and 2 as *E. vogeli* (0.3%). Three geographical hotspots of human CE caused by different species of the Eg complex were identified: (1) *E. granulosus s.s.* in Southern and South-eastern Europe (European-Mediterranean and Balkan countries); (2) *E. canadensis* (G6/7) in Central and Eastern Europe; (3) *E. ortleppi* in Central and Western Europe. This SR also identified data gaps that prevented a better definition of the

geographical distribution of the Eg species complex in Europe: western Balkan countries, part of Central Europe and Baltic countries.

Figure 20. Approximate geographical distribution of species and genotypes of *E. granulosus* s.l. infecting humans (N=597) in Europe during 2000-2021. Prevalences of species and genotypes are reported in red.

WP3-T8-ST2 New. Unveiling the impact of human CE in Europe (1997-2021). [Published]

Although human CE is a notifiable parasitic infectious disease in most European countries, in practice it is largely under-reported by national health systems. To fill this gap, we extracted data on the number, incidence, and trend of human cases in Europe through a systematic review approach, using both the scientific and grey literature and accounting for the period of publication from 1997 to 2021. The highest number of possible human cases at the national level was calculated from various data sources to generate a descriptive model of human CE in Europe. We identified 64,745 human CE cases from 40 European countries. The mean annual incidence from 1997 to 2020 throughout Europe was 0.64 cases per 100,000 people and in EU member states was 0.50/100,000. Bulgaria, Italy, Romania and Spain accounted for 67,4% (n=43,653) of the total CE cases. National hospital records were available only from eight European countries, in which 83,432 hospitalizations were recorded. An average of 2,101 (range 1,801-2,360) and 1,716 (range 1,519-1,897) new CE cases per year were recorded at European countries and EU level during 2017–2019, respectively, before the COVID–19 pandemic compromised the notification of CE cases. An estimate of 1,756 (95% prediction intervals 1,072 to >5,323) and 1361 (95% PI 903 to >3,823) new CE cases per year are expected in 2023 at European countries and EU level, respectively, based on predicted time trend analysis during 1997-2019. CE deaths were recorded in 16 countries (40%) in a total of 895 cases during the considered period, corresponding to a hospitalized case fatality rate of 1-39%. Based on incidence rates and trends detected in this study, the current epicentre of cystic echinococcosis in Europe is in the south-eastern European countries, whereas historical endemic European Mediterranean countries have recorded a decrease in the number of cases over the time.

Figure 21. Number of documented human CE cases (N=64,745) in Europe at the national level during 1997-2021.

Figure 22. Time-trend analysis of the number of human CE cases at the country level (observed cases and predicted cases for the years 2020-2024).

WP3-T8-ST3 New. Human source attribution of cerebral cystic echinococcosis (CCE) by molecular approach and its quantitative assessment in the literature. [Ms in preparation]

This activity focuses on the first source attribution based on molecular methods of a rare case of cerebral CE (CCE) in a child from Roman countryside. In 2019, a 6-year-old boy living in Roman countryside underwent a left frontal-parietal craniotomy and microsurgical removal of an echinococcal lesion. Cyst sample was collected together with 12 cyst samples, belonging to sheep from the same farm owned by the child's family (farm A), as well as from randomly collected from slaughtered sheep raised in a different farm (farm B) located in the same province. All 13 cyst samples were identified as *E. granulosus* s.s. with an RFLP method (Santolamazza et al., 2020) and DNA was used as template for the amplification of the partial mitochondrial genes COX1, NAD5, NAD2 and NAD1 (Kim et al., 2017; Kinkar et al., 2018). Concatenated sequences (2368 bp) were aligned and analysed to generate a TCS network. Results showed a clear genetic relationship between the child's cyst and the cysts belonging to the sheep of his own family's farm (farm A) (Figure 23), in particular two sheep cyst sequences were identical to those of the child, thus supporting the hypothesis of a direct transmission within the family farm. A literature search was also conducted on 6 databases with Boolean terms for the clinical and epidemiological quantification of CCE at global level. The search identified 1,776 relevant articles which were selected by title and abstract. This SR identified 2,235 cases of human CCE of which 80.75% were primary cases, while 19.25% were secondary cases. Of 1,576 cases for which data was available, single CCE was detected in 83.82% of cases and multiple CCE in 16.18%. Of 1,471 cases for which data on age was present, 56.76% were ≤ 18 years, while 43.24 were > 18 years. Of 1,709 CCE cases for which data on sex was present, 56.76% were males and 43.24% were females. Cyst rupture occurred in 12.26% (N=274) of the total documented CCE cases, while recurrence in 9.71% (N=217), permanent disability in 7.79% (N=174), while death occurred in 6.22% (N=139). Considering all clinical centres reporting any localization of CE, CCE occurred in 1.87% (166/8,881) of these cases, while excluding cohorts of children from these clinical series, CCE occurred in 1.43% (113/7,879).

Figure 23. Haplotype network of the concatenated sequences of the genes COX1, NAD5, NAD2 and NAD1 from 13 samples of *E. granulosus* including child cyst (green), sheep cysts from farm A (orange) and sheep cysts from farm B (pink), and five reference sequences from France, Spain, Turkey (G3), Albania and Italy (G1).

WP3-T8-ST4 New. Molecular and clinical epidemiology studies in selected geographical areas.

A) Human CE in the Kurdistan region, Iraq: characteristics and molecular identification.

Published] From 2019 to 2021, 64 echinococcal cysts were surgically removed from 62 patients in Azadi and Vajeen reference Hospitals at Duhok city, Duhok governorate (Kurdistan region, Iraq). The results confirmed the liver as the most common anatomical site of CE with 72.58% of the cases, followed by the lungs in 19.35%, while 66.13% of CE cases were females. The highest rate of infections occurred in the age class 21–30 (27.42%). High rates of CE were reported among patients living in rural areas and housewives, which were 54.84% and 43.55% of the CE patients, respectively. The fertility of echinococcal cysts was 82.81%, and the viability of fertile protoscoleces was 70.53%. Cysts were staged with ultrasound according to the WHO-IWGE classification as 32.8% CE1, 32.8% CE2, 7.8% CE3a, 9.4% CE3b, 15.6% CE4 and 1.6% CE5. Molecular analyses using mitochondrial NAD5 gene showed that all analyzed samples (n=59) belonged to the genotypes G1 or G3 of *E. granulosus* s.s., thus, confirming sheep–dog–human transmission in the Kurdistan region, Iraq. No statistically significant correlation was found between the genotypes G1–G3 of *E. granulosus* s.s. and variables, such as the fertility, location and cyst stage classification. Based on the present findings, it is necessary to implement monitoring and control programs in sheep and dog populations to decrease the odds of human infections. Public health education campaigns are required to be implemented at the community level to reduce the risk of acquiring CE in humans in the Kurdistan region, Iraq.

B) A Retrospective cohort study on human CE in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province (Pakistan) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records. [Published]

Human CE is a worldwide-distributed parasitic zoonotic disease, which represents a threat for both human and animals. The current study aimed at estimating the prevalence of human CE in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) province of Pakistan. Clinical records from four major hospitals in this region were reviewed for CE human cases during the period of 2006–2021. Out of 251 (0.00071%) CE patients identified during the considered period, 142 (56.6%) were females, and 109 (43.4%) were males. The highest number of CE cases was recorded in the 21–30 (27.9%) age group, followed by 31–40 (23.1%) and 41–50 (16.3%). Most of the CE patients in KPK province were members of the Afghani ethnic group (17.1%); secondarily, they were Pakistani (6.4%), while for 76.5% ethnicity data were not available. The liver (41%) and the lungs (4.8%) were the most infected organs identified among CE patients in KPK province. The present study identified CE as a significant public health problem in KPK province, and the current findings demonstrated a constant endemicity of CE during the last 15 years.

C) CE: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia (Italy).

[Published] *E. granulosus* s.s., associated with G1 and G3 genotypes, is endemic with high prevalence in the Mediterranean basin. The parasite's life cycle comprises definitive hosts (canids) and intermediate hosts (ruminants) and can occasionally involve humans. The main aim of this research was to confirm the diagnosis of 13 patients suspected of CE who presented different complications and needed the surgical removal of the cysts. We also wanted to understand and clarify more the diagnosis of CE in humans. For this purpose, the patients first underwent cyst evaluation by ultrasound (US), immunological analysis, and then total pericystectomy, followed by parasitological, histopathological, and molecular biology examinations of the cysts. US stadiated one CE1, one CE2, eight CE3b, one CE4, and two CE5; immunology evidenced nine positives; histopathology confirmed 11 CE cysts, of which 8 fertile presenting protoscoleces were identified as *E. granulosus* s.s. by molecular biology, genotyped as three G1 and four G3 by neighbor-joining (NJ) phylogenetic tree. In conclusion, the results showed that 11 patients were affected by *E. granulosus* s.s. G1 or G3, and 2 cystic neoformations were of non-parasitic origin.

D) Identification of *E. granulosus* genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays (Italy). [Published]

Different *E. granulosus* s.l. genotypes exhibit great diversity in their life cycle, host selectivity and pathogenicity. For this reason, the study of genetic variation within *Echinococcus* species is of importance for their epidemiological implication. We employed two SNP genotyping technologies to distinguish G1 and G3 *E. granulosus* s.s. genotypes. The genotypes of DNA samples (N=28) extracted

from hydatid cysts of different animal species were identified by amplification and sequencing of a fragment of the mitochondrial *nad5* gene. Two SYBR green and three TaqMan real time PCR assays were developed for targeting of three *nad5* informative positions (SNP758, 1123, and 1380) known to be able to discriminate G1 from G3. Genotyping by SYBR Green PCR based on cycle threshold (Ct) with melting temperature (T_m) analysis and performed on SNP1123 and SNP1380 failed to identify one DNA sample. TaqMan assays for SNP758, 1123 and 1380 effectively confirmed genotype identification obtained by Sanger sequencing. Our results demonstrated that the combination of the three Taqman assays developed in this study represents a valuable and cost effective tool alternative to DNA sequencing for *E. granulosus s.s.* genotyping.

E) CE in northern Tanzania: a pilot study in Maasai livestock-keeping communities. [Published]

The aim of this study was to estimate the prevalence of human abdominal CE and the prevalence and species/genotypes of *E. granulosus s.l.* in livestock in Maasai communities. Human CE was diagnosed by abdominal ultrasound in five villages in the Longido and Ngorongoro Districts in northern Tanzania. Infection in ruminants was evaluated through inspection in local abattoirs, followed by molecular identification of one cyst per animal, using PCR-RFLP and mPCR (see **WP3-T2-ST3**). Ultrasound was performed on 823 volunteers (N=352 in two villages in Longido District, and N=471 in three villages of Ngorongoro). Hepatic CE cases were diagnosed only in Ngorongoro (N=6; 1.3%), of which three had active cysts. Village-level prevalence of CE ranged between 0 and 2.4%. Of the 697 ruminants inspected, 34.4% had parasitic cysts. Molecular identification was achieved for 140 of the 219 (63.9%) cysts sampled. *E. granulosus s.l.* and *T. hydatigena/Cysticercus tenuicollis* were identified in 51.4% and 48.6%, respectively, of livestock cysts. *E. granulosus s.l.* was identified in livestock from both Longido (35.3% of 116 genotyped cysts) and Ngorongoro (91.2% of 34 genotyped cysts). Of the total of 72 *E. granulosus s.l.* cysts identified in livestock, 87.5% were *E. granulosus s.s.* (G1–G3), 9.7% were *E. ortleppi* (G5) and one cyst was *E. canadensis* (G6-10). The three active human cysts, which were removed surgically, were G1–G3. Multiple species/genotypes of *E. granulosus s.l.* are circulating in Maasai communities of northern Tanzania.

F) Bayesian Analysis of Three Methods for Diagnosis of CE in Sheep (Italy). [Published]

This study assessed the performances of three post-mortem laboratory methods in the diagnosis of ovine CE. In the absence of a single and accurate test as a gold standard, the results of multiple analytical tests can be combined to estimate diagnostic performance based on a Bayesian statistical approach. For this purpose, livers (N=77), and lungs (N=79) were sampled from adult sheep and examined using gross pathology, histopathology and molecular analyses. Data from the three diagnostic methods were analyzed using a Bayesian latent class analysis model to evaluate their diagnostic accuracy in terms of sensitivity (Se), specificity (Sp), positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV). The gross pathology examination revealed excellent diagnostic capabilities in diagnosing ovine CE with an Se of 99.7 (96.7–99.8), Sp of 97.5 (90.3–99.8), PPV of 97.6 (90.5–100), and NPV of 99.7 (96.5–100).

G) Comparison and evaluation of analytic and diagnostic performances of four commercial kits for the detection of antibodies of *E. granulosus* and *E. multilocularis* in human sera (Italy). [Published]

The aim of our study was to evaluate and compare four commercial diagnostic kits, based on the detection of IgG antibodies against *E. granulosus* and *E. multilocularis*. The study was performed on a total of 259 sera: the positive (N=74) and the negative (N=185) group. The following analytic and diagnostic performances of the four kits were evaluated: operator skills, specificity, sensitivity, repeatability, reproducibility, accuracy, positive and negative predictive values. Based on the parameters evaluated, all four tests demonstrated excellent quality and proved to be reliable diagnostic tools to support the clinical evaluation of human patients suspected of having CE. The four commercial assays, in our hands, presented altogether, a range of performances from good to excellent, being immunoblotting (IB) the most reliable, used as gold standard, followed by the immunochromatographic test (ICT) and finally the two enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISAs).

H) Morphological characteristics of AE and CE lesions in human liver and bone (Germany). [Published]

CE and AE are neglected infectious diseases epidemiologically and are clinically vastly different with distinct microscopic features. Because of the rareness of these zoonotic diseases, pathologists have limited diagnostic experience in the analysis of the lesions caused by *Echinococcus* tapeworms. In this study we describe the main microscopic features to be considered to characterize these lesions: laminated layer, central necrosis, growth pattern, and delineation from adjacent tissue. Moreover, immunohistology using monoclonal antibodies is of great diagnostic help in reaching a definitive diagnosis by identifying the laminated body and small particles of *E. multilocularis* (spems) and small particles of *E. granulosus* (spegs).

I) Chromosome-scale *Echinococcus granulosus* (genotype G1) genome reveals the Eg95 gene family and conservation of the EG95-vaccine molecule (multicountry). [Published]

The development of a vaccine (called EG95) has been the most notable translational advance in the fight against this disease in animals. However, almost nothing is known about the genomic organisation/location of the family of genes encoding EG95 and related molecules, the extent of their conservation or their functions. The lack of a complete reference genome for *E. granulosus* genotype G1 has been a major obstacle to addressing these areas. Here, we assembled a chromosomal-scale genome for this genotype by scaffolding to a high quality genome for the congener *E. multilocularis*, localised Eg95 gene family members in this genome, and evaluated the conservation of the EG95 vaccine molecule. These results have marked implications for future explorations of aspects such as developmentally-regulated gene transcription/expression (using replicate samples) for all *E. granulosus* stages; structural and functional roles of non-coding genome regions; molecular 'cross-talk' between oncosphere and the immune system; and defining the precise function(s) of EG95.

L) Intestinal zoonotic parasites in dogs and foxes in an *Em* endemic area in Limburg (Netherlands).

The aim is to study the northern dispersal of *Em* from the endemic region in the southern province Limburg, where the prevalence in foxes increased from 1998 to 2013 from 13% to 59% in the province. In the study, 113 fecal droppings were collected in the field in both the endemic *Em* region and more northern and tested with the MC-PCR (Maas et al., 2016). Species identification was done on outer appearance of the dropping, and by using a molecular approach. Only 2 fox droppings originating from the endemic control area were tested positive (22%). The 37 fecal fox droppings from the study area were negative. The other droppings were from unknown or other origin. In addition dogs from the province in Limburg were included in the study and a questionnaire (same of WP3-T7) was distributed to owners and vets. A selection of dogs, preying on rodents were tested negative for *Em*. Although 65% of the hunting dogs were dewormed, the majority of dogs hunting on rodents were not dewormed more than 4 times a year. In conclusion there was no evidence of northern spread of *Em* in foxes from the endemic area, and no dogs were tested positive for *Em*. Although the sample size from the study area was limited.

WP4. Training, dissemination and proficiency testing schemes

WP4-T1. Trainings.

This WP focused on establishing the most effective methods for training scientists from institutions participating to MEmE in the parasitological and molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, physical training opportunities were restricted for large periods. For this reason, an online training video was made for "Magnetic capture of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples: DNA extraction with manual washing steps" (see WP2-T3). It can be viewed online at: <https://www.youtube.com/embed/hdo3mE8oMKE?rel=0>. In addition to this a training session in the magnetic capture method was carried out in July 2022 once travel was possible

again. In addition to this digital support was offered to laboratories implementing the magnetic capture method and a physical training session carried out in July 2022 once travel was possible again.

Due to COVID-19 pandemic non-participation to physical events the training for the newly developed qPCRs was organized and conducted on the remote basis on “New singleplex TaqMan qPCRs for detection and genotyping of Eg sl and Em” (see **WP3-T2-ST1**). A total of 8 participant institutions (ISS, PIWET, ANSES, NVI, SSI, OIE Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis, BIOR and INIAV) have registered for this remote training. In order to establish and learn the TaqMan qPCRs for the detection of Echinococcus spp. in the respective laboratories, primers and probe mixes along with the positive controls (cloned PCR products) were sent to each participant together with the appropriate protocols. All participants were supported in the process of establishment by means of Videoconferences and other communication tools. The TaqMan qPCR detection methods were successfully established in all participating institutes and thus the remote training was successfully completed.

WP4-T2. Dissemination of project results.

This task focused on establishing the most effective methods for disseminating project results at different levels. Due to COVID-19 pandemic non-participation to physical events partially prevent the dissemination, while it was done during online events (see participation to physical or online events) and publishing scientific papers for a wide scientific audience (see list of publications). Two papers in particular were focusing on the implementation of public health intervention for the surveillance and control of CE and AE:

[Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. Lancet Glob Health. 2020 Apr;8\(4\):e470-e471.](#)

[New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021-2030. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2021 May 13;15\(5\):e0009373.](#)

WP4-T3. Organization of selected PTs from WP2 and WP3.

A) A Proficiency Testing scheme (PT) on “**Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique (SSCT)**” for the detection of Em was launched in October 2021 (M46). Such PT involved 12 participants from MEmE and two additional European national reference laboratories out of MEmE. The participants have received five segments of intestines (three negative and two positive) in order to perform SSCT. A discordant result was obtained by two participants (one false negative and one false positive). These results can be considered as very encouraging as any laboratory realized SSCT in routine diagnostic intestinal analysis (excepting organizer Anses and Piwet) and many don’t even use intestinal diagnostic as a routine method for detection in definitive host.

B) and **C)** Additional PTs on “Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test” and “Harmonization of Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using RSE and NGS” were successfully conducted and completed during 2022. The PT on “Verification of *E. multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox faeces”, two protocols were developed. In the first two labs compared the performance of the Maas et al. 2016 method on naturally infected fox faeces with low to moderate levels of worm burden whilst in the second protocol four laboratories analysed sets of homogenised faecal samples spiked with either whole worms or worm segments. The laboratories then analysed these test panels using their preferred magnetic capture and PCR methods. Each laboratory tested the method with one of two magnetic capture protocols (MC1 Øines et al. 2014; MC2 Maas et al. 2016) and four different PCR protocols (Isaksson et al., 2014, Maas et al., 2016, Øines et al., 2014, in-house qPCR protocol). The two laboratories that carried out protocol 1 correctly identified 15 of the 30 positive samples and 9 of the 10 negative samples. The four laboratories that carried out the protocol 2 correctly identified 15 of the 16 negative samples and all but four of the positive samples (N=33). Two of the laboratories correctly identified all the samples in protocol 2, whereas the remaining two laboratories had either a false negative or both false negatives and a false positive in protocol 2. This work highlighted the importance

of carrying out in-house method verification, which was done at the two laboratories that correctly identified all their samples, but not at the two laboratories that reported false negatives/positive sample.

Figure 24. Results from the two different protocols used to for proficiency testing with different magnetic capture methods on both naturally infected red fox faecal samples (protocol 1), confirmed by IST of the intestines, and homogenised negative red fox faecal samples spiked with either whole worms or segments of *Echinococcus multilocularis* (protocol 2).

For the PT C) two laboratories participated in the PT on “Harmonization of Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using RSE and NGS”. Both correctly identified Em and Eg in samples of DNA extracted directly from parasite material (adult worms or metacestodes), however, it was concluded that further development of the protocols is needed to consistently identify Em and Eg in complex samples.

2.7.4 Project self-assessment

We are extremely satisfied of the scientific output generated by MEmE (see: 2. Summary of the work carried out in the Project) since we met the vast majority of the project deliverables. We believe that we have done more than planned and expected in the original proposal. See figure 1 with the updated *Pert chart* (in red 2 tasks discontinued by COVID-19 pandemic and 9 new tasks/subtasks implemented during the project).

In particular the following tasks were closed and remodulated due to COVID-19 impact (national lockdowns and overwhelmed clinical centres):

WP3-T8. Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires (discontinued) *

WP3-T4. Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma (discontinued) *

These new tasks, which have not been planned in the original proposal but were implemented during the 3-years project were:

WP2-T3. New. Comparison of Magnetic Capture protocols for the detection of Em in feces (FLI)

WP3-T2-ST2. New. New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Eg sl and Em (FLI)

WP3-T2-ST3. New. New validated method to identify Eg sl at species level by PCR-RFLP and mPCR (ISS)

WP3-T2-ST4. New. New molecular identification of Em/Eg sl tissue samples by novel PCR-RFLP (ANSES)

WP3-T3-ST2. New. Detection of the mitogenome of Em by RSE method and Illumina-NGS (FLI)

WP3-T6-ST2. New. Contamination of berries (ANSES)

WP3-T6-ST3. New. Dispersion of Em/Eg eggs in the soil (ANSES)

WP3-T8. New. Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE and AE (ISS)

WP3-T8-ST1. New. Species/genotypes of E. granulosus s.l. causing human CE in Europe (2000-21) (ISS)

WP3-T8-ST2. New. Unveiling the impact of human CE in Europe (1997-2021) (ISS)

WP3-T8-ST3. New. Human source attribution of cerebral CE and its quantitative assessment (ISS)

WP3-T8-ST4. (A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, L) New. Molecular epidemiology studies in selected geographical areas (ISS)

*** Rationale for discontinuing WP3-T8 and WP3-T4:**

WP3-T8. We encounter technical difficulties on the proteomic study from plasma (at ISS, Italy) of experimentally infected (and controlled) sheep in Portugal (at INIAV, Portugal). Because of COVID-19, we were late in obtaining ethics committee approval at INIAV. Afterwards, in November 2020 we made two attempts with parasite protoscoleces collected from sheep in Sardinia (IZSS, Italy) to infect foxes in Nancy, France (ANSES) where ethics committee approval was also obtained for foxes. Unfortunately, in January 2021 we did not obtain Eg worms from fox experimental model (neither at flotation of faecal samples nor at PCR examination). During February/August 2021, we mobilized the international community to provide Eg eggs from experimentally or naturally infected canids. We received positive feedback from Australia, Iraqi Kurdistan, Kazakhstan and China, willing to collect and subsequently provide eggs. National lockdowns and national restrictions due to COVID-19 affected such field collaborations since all these participants have retired. These eggs would have been used to infect sheep (animals are still housed in Portugal) and collect plasma for proteomic analyses searching for biomarkers of infection. We also discussed to modify ethical clearance at INIAV and try to infect sheep with Eg protoscoleces, instead of Eg egg. Since intraperitoneal injection of protoscoleces does not mimic natural infection, this may affect molecular pathways and therefore proteomic analysis outcome. Even if we had found another solution, we would not have been able to implement it before the end of MEmE because of the long time (at least 1 year) it takes for the parasite to develop in sheep.

WP3-T4. This study, coordinated by ISS, was planning a case-control study at hospital level by means of questionnaires for the study of human potential risk factors for CE and AE. In principle, the questionnaire should have involved cases of CE and AE versus control hospitalized patients due to other conditions. It was planned to involve in the study several clinical centres in Europe willing to participate. National lockdowns and national restrictions due to COVID-19 affected such collaborations

since it was not possible to obtain the ethical clearance from the centres which withdraw all from this collaboration.

2.7.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP1.1	SOPs for sampling in matrices shared within the Consortium	M28	M31	Public https://zenodo.org/record/4455196#.YAmIsxbSKgo	2
18	D-JRP18-WP1.2	Collection of samples in the field finalized	M36	M45	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499866#.YTsvmc_OMzk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP1.3	Collection of samples from experimental animal model finalized	M48	M52	Public https://zenodo.org/record/6203493#.YhOPW5bjK70	8
18	D-JRP18-WP2.1	Validation of SSCT	M36	M48	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499551#.YTr8sM_OMzk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP2.2	Validation of multiplex PCRs	M44	M49	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499864#.YdwvolnSKgo	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP2.3	Validation of Magnetic Capture Real-time PCR assay	M44	M45	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5500594#.YTusOaTOMzk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.1	New molecular markers	M58	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7361403#.Y4DEGX2ZObg	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.2	New multiplex TaqMan qPCR	M48	M48	Public https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.YdwY6FnSKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.3	New NGS method for the detection in complex samples	M60	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7437047#.Y5nYhn3MKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.4	Potential biomarkers for intermediate hosts plasma			Replaced by: D-JRP18-WP3.8 Quantitative assessment of the burden of human CE/AE	
18	D-JRP18-WP3.5	Assessment of newly developed methods against the existing	M58	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7362215#.Y4DtcX2ZObg	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.6	Contamination of vegetables by Em/Eg	M58	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7361764#.Y4DZPX2ZObg	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP3.7	Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog from selected geographical areas	M58	M60	Confidential https://zenodo.org/record/7448150#.Y57SuhXMJQQ	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.8	Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires			Replaced by: D-JRP18-WP3.8 Quantitative assessment of the burden of human CE/AE	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.8	Quantitative assessment of the burden of human CE/AE	M58	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7358066#.Y3-ZBH3MKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP4.1	Analysis and evaluation of training activities	M58	M60	Confidential https://zenodo.org/record/7361920	8
18	D-JRP18-WP4.2	Analysis and evaluation of PTs	M58	M60	Public, RSE-NGS: https://zenodo.org/record/7361169#.Y4DF632ZObg Public, SSCT: https://zenodo.org/record/5816663#.Y4DM5X2ZObg	8
18	D-JRP18-WP4.3	Final report of SSCT (PT scheme)	M48	M49	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5816663#.YdQlv1njLmE	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP4.3	Evaluation of different MC protocols for Em DNA in red foxes (PT scheme)	M60	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7456811#.Y6BZOH2ZObg	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.1	Data Management Plan (DMP)	M58	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7457924#.Y6BuYBXMkgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.2	Periodic technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M36	M45	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5413157#.YTH66d_OOgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.3	Periodic technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M48	M49	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5833427#.YdwWF1nSKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.4	Final technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M54	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7357984#.Y3-TfX3MKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.5	Kick-off annual meeting in Malzéville (France) by ANSES	M27	M28	Public https://zenodo.org/record/4455256#.YAmKvxbSKgo	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
18	D-JRP18-WP5.6	Interim annual meeting in Greifswald (Germany) by FLI	M49	M50	Public https://zenodo.org/record/6631959#.YqNbbuxBygo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.7	Final meeting in Rome (Italy) by ISS	M60	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7357898#.Y3-PH33MKgo	8

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
18	M-JRP18-01	Tasks and responsibility allocation	M25	Yes	Kick off meeting in France used for the allocation of the tasks and responsibilities
18	M-JRP18-02	Organization of Kick-off annual meeting by ANSES	M26	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-03	Ethics approvals for the use of animal model	M28	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-04	SOP for validation of SSCT	M30	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-05	SOP for validation of multiplex PCRs	M30	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-06	SOP for Validation of Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay	M41	Yes	Distributed along with verification material and ring test in M46.
18	M-JRP18-07	Protocols for New molecular methods, NGS included	M30	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-08	Protocol for proteomic analysis in animals plasma	M30	No	COVID19 disrupted this task. See WP3-T4. New tasks were replacing this.
18	M-JRP18-09	Protocol for contamination of vegetables by Em/Eg	M30	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
18	M-JRP18-10	Protocol for prevalence of Em/Eg in dog	M30	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-11	(Questionnaire scheme for potential human risk factors) Task replaced with literature search for "Quantitative assessment of the burden of human CE/AE".	M30	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-12	Interim evaluation of collection of samples in the field	M32	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-13	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M35	Yes	
22	M-JRP22-14	Organization of Training periods	M48	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-15	Interim evaluation of collection of samples from experimental animal model	M42	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-16	Selection of new/old methods to be compared	M44	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-17	Organization of interim annual meeting by FLI	M48	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-18	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M47	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
18	M-JRP18-19	Diagnostic performance of Participants to PTs	M58	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-20	Analysis and evaluation of dissemination activities	M58	Yes	
18	M-JRP18-21	Organization of Final meeting by ISS	M58	Yes	22-23 november 2022
18	M-JRP18-22	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M60	Yes	

2.7.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Green Open Access? embargo, release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Unveiling the incidences and trends of alveolar echinococcosis in Europe: a systematic review from the MEmE project.	Under preparation (ISS, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: 0 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Green Open Access? embargo, release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
A comparison of magnetic capture copro-PCR and sedimentation counting technique in arctic foxes from Svalbard.	Under preparation (NVI, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2000 €
A decade of monitoring Echinococcus multilocularis prevalence of in faecal samples from arctic foxes as well as targeted sampling of dogs and sibling voles from Svalbard.	Under preparation (NVI, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2000 €
Description of a panel of microsatellites for molecular epidemiology of E. granulosus sensu stricto	Under preparation (ANSES, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2000 €
Comparison between SSCT and two real-time coproPCR protocols for diagnostic of E. multilocularis in foxes	Under preparation (ANSES, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2000 €
Assessment of molecular diagnostic methods for detection of E. multilocularis and E. granulosus sensu lato	Under preparation (ANSES, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2000 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Green Open Access? embargo, release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Validation of SSCT as an intestinal diagnostic method of choice for the surveillance of <i>E. multilocularis</i> in foxes (and raccoon dogs) by a multicenter and proficiency test approach	Under preparation (ANSES, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2000 €
Contamination of lettuces and berries by <i>E. multilocularis</i> , <i>E. granulosus sensu lato</i> and others Taenidae species	Under preparation (ANSES, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2000 €
A multiplex TaqMan real-time PCRs for the detection and differentiation of <i>Echinococcus</i> species.	Under preparation (FLI, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2300 €
Comparison of different magnetic capture protocols and commercial automated methods for detection of <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> DNA in feces of definitive hosts.	Under preparation (FLI, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2300 €
Human source attribution of cerebral CE by molecular approach and its quantitative assessment in the literature	Under preparation (ISS, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2300 €
Multicentre study on prevalence of <i>Echinococcus</i> spp. in dogs in different regions of Europe	Under preparation (PIWET, 2023)	Will be		Expected cost: around 2300 €
Unveiling the incidences and trends of cystic echinococcosis in Europe: a systematic review from the MEmE project.	Published	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Green Open Access? embargo, release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1473309922006387?via%3Dihub https://zenodo.org/record/7351658#.Y342P33MJOQ				
Cystic echinococcosis in northern Tanzania: a pilot study in Maasai livestock-keeping communities. Parasit Vectors. https://parasitesandvectors.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13071-022-05518-x https://zenodo.org/record/7342315#.Y3uSx33MKgo	Published	YES		Yes, 0 €
Insights into Human Cystic Echinococcosis in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq: Characteristics and Molecular Identification of Cysts. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/11/4/408 https://zenodo.org/record/6521840#.YnPhktNBygo	Published	YES		Yes, 1983.77 €
Comparison and evaluation of analytic and diagnostic performances of four commercial kits for the detection of antibodies against E. granulosus and multilocularis in human sera. https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S014795712200073X?via%3Dihub https://zenodo.org/record/7355608#.Y39kMH3MKgo	Published	YES	Yes, 15 th April, 2023	No, 0 €
Species and genotypes belonging to Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato complex causing human cystic echinococcosis in Europe (2000-2021): a systematic review approach.	Published	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited editorial)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Green Open Access? embargo, release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://parasitesandvectors.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13071-022-05197-8 https://zenodo.org/record/6521887#.YnPkVtNBygo				
Chromosome-scale Echinococcus granulosus (genotype G1) genome reveals the Eg95 gene family and conservation of the EG95-vaccine molecule. https://www.nature.com/articles/s42003-022-03125-1 https://zenodo.org/record/6521878#.YnPjSdNBygo	Published	YES		Yes, 0 €
A Retrospective Cohort Study on Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province (Pakistan) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/11/2/194 https://zenodo.org/record/6091472#.Ygu6UJbSKgo	Published	YES		Yes, 1983.77 €
Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/10/10/1326 https://zenodo.org/record/5646982#.Ydr55ybSlzk	Published	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge)
New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009373 https://zenodo.org/record/4771738#.YKTFCqHOOgp	Published	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited editorial)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Green Open Access? embargo, release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia (Italy). https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9110907 https://zenodo.org/record/4159681	Published	YES		Yes, 1.389 €
Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed <i>Besnoitia</i> species. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YTDH7t_OOgo	Published	YES		Yes, 2.190 €
Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> in the stool samples of naturally infected red foxes. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10122381 https://zenodo.org/record/4384600	Published	YES		Yes, 1.481 €
Species detection within the <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> complex by novel probe based Real-Time PCRs. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100791 https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.X6PY3WhKjcc	Published	YES		Yes, 1.258,81 €
A validated method to identify <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> at species level. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575	Published	YES		Yes, 2.300 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Green Open Access? embargo, release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://zenodo.org/record/4066416#.X6UQMWhKjcc				
Identification of Echinococcus granulosus genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020125 https://zenodo.org/record/4471215#.YGLkiq8zZM0	Published	YES		Yes, 696,38 €
Bayesian analysis to evaluate three diagnostic methods for cystic echinococcosis in sheep. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100796 https://zenodo.org/record/4061823#.X6PZl2hKjcc	Published	YES		Yes, 1.389,79 €
Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9060444 https://zenodo.org/record/3894117#.XvyQ6ygzZM0	Published	YES		Yes, 654,56 €
Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8 https://zenodo.org/record/3730559#.Xn3FalhKi70	Published	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited comment)

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

MEmE main achievements were:

The production of SOPs for the sampling of different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts.

- The validation of the parasitological (SSCT) and molecular diagnostic (multiplex- and MC-RT-PCRs) procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- The development, validation and comparison of new molecular tools (comparison of DNA extraction and PCRs assays, novel probe-based qPCRs, PCR-RFLPs and multiplex PCR assays and NGS approach).
- Multicentre studies for the production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments: contamination of fresh vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg; prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces.
- Quantitative assessment on the impact of human CE in Europe by means of systematic review approach.
- Molecular and clinical epidemiology studies in selected geographical areas.
- Dissemination of project results at different levels (general public, scientific community, experts, health authorities and media).
- **MEmE impacted** on animal health, public health and food safety sectors. Beneficiaries of scientific outputs of MEmE were EU reference labs, international organizations and all decision makers. We provided a set of molecular tools, epidemiological risk assessments and quantitative epidemiological models for the detection, surveillance and control of these parasitic infectious diseases in Europe and beyond.
- It should also be remarked that **18 scientific papers were currently published** by MEmE project and **additional 12 papers** are in progress. Among all these publication, it should be highlighted the collaborative study published by **The Lancet Infectious Diseases** on November 23rd 2022, a quantitative research that aims to decrease the limit of uncertainty on the impact of human cystic echinococcosis in Europe (<https://authors.elsevier.com/a/1g7r15E-UoYvLp>).

Unveiling the incidences and trends of the neglected zoonosis cystic echinococcosis in Europe: a systematic review from the MEmE project

Adriano Casulli, Bernadette Abela-Ridder, Daniele Petrone, Massimo Fabiani, Branko Bobić, David Carmena, Barbara Šoba, Enver Zerem, Maria João Gargaté, Gordana Kuzmanovska, Cristian Calomfirescu, Iskra Rainova, Smaragda Sotiraki, Vera Lungu, Balázs Dezsényi, Zaida Herrador, Jacek Karamon, Pavlo Maksimov, Antti Oksanen, Laurence Millon, Mario Sviben, Renata Shkjezi, Valbona Gjoni, Ilir Akshija, Urmaz Saarma, Paul Torgerson, Viliam Šnábel, Daniela Antolová, Damir Muhovic, Hasan Besim, Fanny Chereau, Moncef Belhassen García, François Chappuis, Severin Gloor, Marcel Stoeckle, Beat Müllhaupt, Valerio Manno, Azzurra Santoro*, Federica Santolamazza*

The neglected zoonosis cystic echinococcosis affects mainly pastoral and rural communities in both low-income and upper-middle-income countries. In Europe, it should be regarded as an orphan and rare disease. Although human cystic echinococcosis is a notifiable parasitic infectious disease in most European countries, in practice it is largely under-reported by national health systems. To fill this gap, we extracted data on the number, incidence, and trend of human cases in Europe through a systematic review approach, using both the scientific and grey literature and accounting for the period of publication from 1997 to 2021. The highest number of possible human cases at the national level was calculated from various data sources to generate a descriptive model of human cystic echinococcosis in Europe. We identified 64745 human cystic echinococcosis cases from 40 European countries. The mean annual incidence from 1997 to 2020 throughout Europe was 0.64 cases per 100 000 people and in EU member states was 0.50 cases per 100 000 people. Based on incidence rates and trends detected in this study, the current epicentre of cystic echinococcosis in Europe is in the southeastern European countries, whereas historical endemic European Mediterranean countries have recorded a decrease in the number of cases over the time.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Collaborations were established with the following entities:

- The other parasitology-JRPs (OHEJP): **PARADISE** and **TOXOSOURCES**.
- The **European Reference Laboratory for Parasites** (EURLP).
- The **WHO Collaborating Centre WHO** Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis (in humans and animals).
- **PERITAS project** (molecular ePIdemiological studiEs on pathways of tRansmission and long lasTing cApacity building to prevent cyStic echinococcosis infection). 2018-2021. Funded by the EC under EULAC-Health.
- **ECHINO-SAFE-MED project** (New sustainable tools and innovative actions to control cystic ECHINOcoccosis in sheep farms in the MEDiterranean area: improvement of diagnosis and SAFETy in response to climatic changes). PRIMA, Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area.

2.7.7 One Health impact

MEmE impacted on animal health, public health and food safety sectors. Beneficiaries of scientific outputs of MEmE were EU reference labs, international organizations (ECDC, EFSA, OIE, WHO, FAO) and all decision makers.

We provided a set of molecular tools, epidemiological risk assessments and quantitative epidemiological models for the detection, surveillance and control of these parasitic infectious diseases in Europe and beyond.

2.7.8 Data Management Plan

Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of data management during this project. It covers the life cycle of the data from collection to availability and long-term storage. MEmE DMP covers the relevant aspects of the many types of data that were collected and generated during the project. MEmE did its best to make the research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. Ethical considerations, GDPR, data security and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) were considered along the process. In addition to the components of the FAIR-principle, transparency and visibility were also emphasized.

2.7.9 Future dissemination activities

Main stakeholders of MEmE are the international agencies such as ECDC, EFSA, OIE, FAO and WHO. Main dissemination of MEmE are scientific papers and participation to international scientific meetings. The Project Management Team (PMT) and Communication Team can be of help updating MEmE webpage, creating brochure for the Project dissemination and disseminate relevant outcomes such as *The Lancet Infectious disease* paper (we are already in contact for all that).

2.8 JRP19-R2-ET1.1-PARADISE

2.8.1 Consortium composition

Project Leader : Simone M. Cacciò (ISS, Italy)

Deputy Project Leader : Karin Troell (SVA, Sweden)

Work Package Leaders and Co-Leaders :

WP1: Project Leader : Simone M. Cacciò (ISS, Italy), Karin Troell (SVA, Sweden)

WP2: Yannick Blanchard (ANSES), Simone M. Cacciò (ISS, Italy)

WP3: Karin Troell (SVA, Sweden), Christian Klotz (RKI, Germany)

WP4: Marco Lalle (ISS, Italy), Karin Troell (SVA, Sweden)

Gender balance : 60%/40%.

2.8.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Foodborne parasites (FBPs) are major contributors to the global burden of gastrointestinal disease. In Europe, protozoa of the genera *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* are particularly relevant, and have been associated with large outbreaks linked to contaminated water and food. Outbreak investigation and source attribution remain difficult, also due to the lack of standardized typing methods. The PARADISE project successfully delivered informative genotyping schemes derived from whole genome data and innovative enrichment strategies applicable to food matrices for the zoonotic pathogens *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*.

The essential achievements of the project are summarized below:

- **WP2:** A large sequencing effort resulted in the generation of about 130 whole genome sequences (WGS) from *C. parvum* (humans and ruminants), 50 WGS from *G. duodenalis* assemblage B (mostly from humans) and about 70 WGS from *G. duodenalis* assemblage A (humans and other mammals). Comparative genomic studies of this collection of European WGS is shedding light on the population structure, virulence and evolution of these parasites, and providing insights for future functional studies. Ongoing collaborations with European Union Reference Laboratories for bacterial and viral pathogens are helping to foster the use of WGS for parasitic pathogens. The applicability of metagenomics for the detection of parasites in various biological, water and food samples, was critically evaluated by in silico and experimental studies. The analyses show that efficient detection can also be achieved in the presence of excess background material of eukaryotic origin (e.g., a vegetable matrix), but that confirmation of the results obtained by k-mer or mapping procedure is essential to avoid false positives.
- **WP3:** New multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) schemes for both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* assemblage B have been designed and tested on hundreds of isolates from different hosts and different geographic origin. The schemes demonstrated a high discriminatory power and represent valuable tools for outbreak investigations and epidemiological studies. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are available and ring tests among Consortium partners showed efficient implementation of the typing schemes. Adoption of the two MLSTs by Reference

Laboratories will address the specific need for robust molecular typing methods recently highlighted by EFSA.

- **WP4:** A post-DNA extraction capture system for *Cryptosporidium*, based on probes targeting the 18S rDNA and the *gp60* genes, have been designed and extensively characterized, and demonstrated to have high sensitivity in interlaboratory studies. This technique will allow investigation of DNA extracts from samples from outbreaks of unknown aetiology.
- The pre-DNA enrichment strategies based on nanobody and aptamer technologies culminated in the selection of nanobodies with high specificity towards *Giardia* cysts. These reagents could be used on matrices (food, water) contaminated with low number of parasites, whose detection is relevant for risk assessment.

2.8.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Coordination and impact

PARADISE-WP1 managed the project and was responsible for tracking the progress and addressing the challenges that eventually emerged, and for integrating the results and achieve the objectives. This included preparation and submission of deliverables and reports, organization of project meetings and scientific communication. Adherence to H2020 rules, e.g., ethical aspects, IRP, dissemination and publication, was managed by WP1. Finally, PARADISE-WP1 was also responsible for the Data Management Plan of the project.

The COVID-19-pandemic had a negative impact on several project activities, particularly those related to laboratory work, due to lockdowns, reduced access to laboratories, the direct involvement of staff in the implementation of molecular diagnostic SARS-CoV2 assays and sequencing of SARS-CoV2 genomes. Therefore, rational changes in the experimental strategy were discussed and adopted. However, delays in reaching some project's Milestones and in submitting Deliverables have occurred. Organization of the planned short-term missions and technical workshops was impossible. Dissemination of the project's main outcomes was also negatively impacted, particularly during 2020. To cope with the challenges caused by the COVID-19-pandemic, the project applied for a 6-month extension until the end of the year 2022.

WP1-T1- Management, coordination and communication

The Kick-off Meeting (Y3) was held on February 10-11, 2020, at ISS, Rome, Italy. Due to restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the Y4 Annual Meeting was organized as an online event, using the Teams platform, on October 26, 2021. The Final meeting (Y5) was held on June 22-23, 2022, at SVA, Uppsala, Sweden. On March 2022, one partner (OKI, Hungary) decided to leave the project; this decision was communicated to ISS (project coordinator) and to OHEJP (Sciensano and ANSES).

The key elements for the management of the project included online meetings with PARADISE WP-Leaders and Co-Leaders, Consortium emails, use of the online group for sharing and storage of relevant documents (e.g., 9 and 12 month reports, deliverables).

Figure 1. Group picture at the Final meeting organized by SVA, Uppsala, Sweden, on June 22-23, 2022.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) was updated regularly (last update, September 2022), with outcomes made available following the FAIR principle. Dissemination of the main scientific outcomes was active, and included presentations to relevant audiences at national and international conferences, and scientific publications.

The PARADISE Consortium was highly motivated and the general atmosphere was positive and supportive. Most of the Milestones, Deliverables and Reports have been reached and submitted by their planned deadlines, or with slight delays, throughout the timeline of the project. Several collaborations with other projects and networks were established and strengthened.

WP2. NGS-based genomics and metagenomics

The PARADISE JRP19-WP2 had two main goals. The first was to generate new whole genome sequence (WGS) data from isolates of *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*, ensuring inclusion of isolates from different hosts and of different geographic origin (WP2-T1). The second was to perform experimental and in silico analyses to demonstrate that parasite sequences present in metagenomics datasets can be detected with high specificity, and to evaluate the limit of detection of different platforms and workflows (WP2-T2 and WP2-T3).

WP2-T1 NGS-based genome study of selected isolates of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

Application of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology to parasitic pathogens is limited by the lack of in vitro systems to grow and amplify the targets present in the original matrix (i.e., faeces, water and food samples). Moreover, ad-hoc analytical workflows for data analyses are not available. Despite these technical challenges, the project generated an unprecedented number of WGS for both *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*. Many partner institutes (ANSES, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PHA, PIWET, RKI, SSI and SVA) and associated partners (CRU and NMBU) contributed to the collection of faecal samples of human and animal origin. An ongoing collaboration with the Finnish Food Authority (Finland) and with the Charles University of Prague (Czech Republic) allowed production of additional WGS data. NGS experiments were performed based on Illumina technology (short reads, 2x150 paired ends), and scaled to achieve an average 50X coverage. A password protected cloud storage space, set up by SVA, allowed the upload and sharing of WGS data from the project, from collaborations and from public databases. New WGS data were made available at the NCBI database.

For *Cryptosporidium parvum*, WGS from 31 isolates of human and 64 isolates of animal origin, collected in 11 European countries, were obtained. The bioinformatics analyses were initially conducted at ISS and SVA, using a pipeline developed in the context of a previous European project (COMPARE), but

also through the design and implementation of specific scripts. This allowed the identification of genomic regions with high variability, representing candidate markers for the development of a new Multi-Locus Typing Scheme (MLST) (JRP19-WP3-T2). In parallel, a large genome comparative study, conducted in collaboration with the University of Pavia (Italy) and based on all WGS available to date, is exploring the population structure and evolution of the parasite, with a focus on recombination and admixture. Phylogenetic analyses based on genomic SNPs showed that the European isolates form three clusters (Figure 2), one of which comprises the isolates from known outbreaks or from focalized foci of infection (i.e., single farms).

Figure 2. Phylogenetic relationships among *C. parvum* isolates from Europe. Isolates from other continents (Asia, Africa and North America) are also included.

For *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B, most WGS (41) were obtained from human isolates, in line with the known host distribution of this pathogen, but eight animal isolates could also be included. NGS experiments were performed based on Illumina technology (short reads, 2x150 paired ends), and scaled to achieve an average 50X coverage. A password protected cloud storage space, set up by SVA, allowed the upload and sharing of WGS data from the project, from collaborations and from public databases. New WGS data were made available at the NCBI database. The bioinformatics analyses of WGS data were conducted by P-11 (RKI), where a specific pipeline was developed. This allowed the identification of genomic regions with high variability, needed in WP3-T2 as candidate markers for the development of a new Multi-Locus Sequence Typing (MLST) scheme. In parallel, an ongoing collaboration with the Charles University of Prague (Czech Republic) and the University of Melbourne (Australia) allowed generation of 70 WGS data for *G. duodenalis* assemblage A, a related pathogen of humans and other mammals. This included 66 isolates of human origin and 4 isolates of animal origin. Genome comparative studies of these two large WGS datasets are exploring the complex structure of the polyploid genome of *G. duodenalis*, with a focus on factors influencing virulence, host specificity and zoonotic potential.

WP2-T2- In silico analyses of metagenomes for detection of foodborne parasites (protozoa and helminths)

The first goal of this task was to demonstrate that parasite sequences present in complex metagenomics datasets can be detected with high specificity. To this end, publicly available shotgun metagenomes from different matrices were downloaded from the MG-RAST database, or from published data. It should be noted that different metagenomics experiments generated vastly different number of reads (from 10^5 to 10^8). These datasets were interrogated using k-mer analysis (Kraken) and/or the mapping (BWA aligner). The results of these analyses are detailed in D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.2.

As a proof of concept, we first queried 5557 metagenomes from MG-RAST using the 18S rDNA sequence of *Entamoeba gingivalis* and demonstrated the presence of this parasite in the only environment in which it should be found, namely the human oral cavity.

Next, we interrogated calf intestinal metagenomes for gastrointestinal parasites, and detected the presence of reads from the 18S rDNA of *Cryptosporidium* spp. We showed that this approach is not sufficient to identify the pathogen to the species level, due to high conservation of this locus (considering that the average length of the reads was 150 bp). Therefore, we tested the use of the complete *Cryptosporidium parvum* reference genome, of individual chromosomes or by the use of species-specific signature sequences. We showed that this led to the specific detection of *C. parvum*, although the sensitivity is reduced with signature sequences. This study has been published.

We also tested a case of particular interest, namely a very large metagenome dataset (2.5 billion reads) derived from romaine lettuce; the lettuce was a suspected vehicle of infection in an outbreak of human cryptosporidiosis. The presence of *C. parvum* was reported by the authors based on both PCR and shotgun metagenomics (mapping using BWA). However, when reanalysing the data by our pipeline, we found that no reads could be confirmed as *C. parvum* by blasting the reads against the non-redundant NCBI database (Table 1). This showed that the assignment of reads to a target, based on k-mer of BWA mapping procedure, could generate false positive results, likely due to high sequence similarity among eukaryotes (e.g., at the level of ribosomal genes). We argued that confirmation of the initial results using BLAST is essential.

Table 1. Analysis of three metagenomes (romaine lettuce) for the presence of *Cryptosporidium parvum*

Sample	N of reads passing QC (% of total)	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>C. parvum</i>	N of reads confirmed as <i>C. parvum</i> by BLAST
BV286	138729248 (35.9%)	3121	78	0
BV287	165350248 (46.0%)	2602	102	0
BV288	247707572 (54.6%)	465	100	0

The second goal was to evaluate the limit of detection, i.e., the sensitivity. To this end, a metagenome of plant origin (Arugula, MG-RAST mgm4448187.3) that did not contain *Cryptosporidium* or *Giardia* sequences was selected. This was spiked in silico with 2500 reads of *Cryptosporidium* or 625 reads of *Giardia*, which were obtained from WGS experiments conducted in WP2-T1. The unspiked

metagenome, the spiked metagenome and the spike reads alone were then analysed using Kraken as a phylogenetic identifier, and NCBI BLAST to confirm the identity of the reads. The results showed that 2092 reads were identified as *C. parvum*, of which 2067 were confirmed using NCBI BLAST (Table 2). For *Giardia*, 566 reads were identified as *G. duodenalis*, of which 380 were confirmed using NCBI BLAST (Table 3).

Table 2. Results of a simulation experiment in which 2500 *Cryptosporidium parvum* reads were spiked into the mgm4551355.3 metagenome.

Sample	N of reads passing QC (% of total)	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp.	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>C. parvum</i>	N of reads confirmed as <i>C. parvum</i> by BLAST
Unspiked metagenome	28253230 (98.9%)	481	15	0
Spiked metagenome	28255624 (98.9%)	2806	2092	2067
Reads only	2394 (95.8%)	2325	2077	2067

Table 3. Results of a simulation experiment in which 625 *Giardia duodenalis* reads were spiked into the mgm4551355.3 metagenome.

Sample	N of reads passing QC (% of total)	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>Giardia</i> spp.	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>G. intestinalis</i>	N of reads confirmed as <i>G. intestinalis</i> by BLAST
Unspiked metagenome	28253230 (98.9%)	153	121	0
Spiked metagenome	28253230 (98.9%)	597	565	380
Reads only	459 (73.4%)	443	443	379

WP2-T3- Experimental amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics for detection of foodborne parasites

The main objective of this task was to compare the limit of detection of two metagenomics approaches, namely a targeted amplicon-sequencing approach based on the 18S rDNA and untargeted shotgun sequencing. The amplicon-sequencing platform (metabarcoding) developed by P-13 (SSI) prior to the project, can amplify most food- and waterborne parasites, although the sensitivity of the assay does not surpass that of real-time PCR methods. The metabarcoding assay was known, however, to have low sensitivity in the detection of some eukaryotic pathogens, including microsporidia, *Giardia* and *Dientamoeba*. The aim within the PARADISE project was to address these issues and increase sensitivity for these particular organisms. Alternative primers targeting the ITS region of the ribosomal cluster were tested on reference DNAs, and a new universal primer pair was designed and evaluated in silico. Moreover, attempts were made to optimize master mix and PCR cycles, and index keys. Unfortunately, despite these efforts it was not possible to overcome the problem. Accordingly, application of the assay for the analysis of a mixed salad plant matrix spiked with different amounts (corresponding to 10, 50 and 100 oocysts) of *C. parvum*, *G. duodenalis* or *Toxoplasma gondii* resulted in detection of the latter pathogen only. This will indicate that the limit of detection is >100 oocysts

for both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*, and between 50-100 oocysts for *T. gondii*. The shotgun approach was applied to DNA from a plant matrix (baby spinach) spiked with serial dilution of DNA of *Cryptosporidium parvum* or *Giardia duodenalis*, mimicking different contamination levels. Illumina libraries (paired-ends, 2x150 bp) were sequenced to generate 25-90 million reads from each spike. The results show that the expected parasites were found in the samples (Tables 4) and 5. In this case, results indicate that the limit of detection is >100 oocysts for *C. parvum* but around 10 cysts for *G. duodenalis*. However, reads were also assigned to parasites also in the unspiked samples, often due to similarity in ribosomal sequences between eukaryotes, therefore generating false positives. We show that it is possible to test and correct this issue by BLAST analyses.

Table 4. Number of reads detected by Kraken as *Cryptosporidium parvum* and number of reads confirmed by BLAST in plant DNA samples spiked with different amounts of *C. parvum* DNA.

Sample	Plant DNA	<i>C. parvum</i> DNA	N of reads	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>C. parvum</i> (relative abundance)	N of reads confirmed by BLAST
CrMET1	1 µg	10 nanograms	13122427	24928 (1.9×10^{-3})	5.374
CrMET2	1 µg	1 nanogram	15080218	3453 (2.3×10^{-4})	634
CrMET3	1 µg	100 picograms	14589873	147 (1×10^{-5})	35
CrMET4	1 µg	10 picograms	12340667	38 (3×10^{-6})	1
CrMET5	1 µg	1 picogram	14314820	37 (2.5×10^{-6})	0
CrMET6	1 µg	No DNA	12086094	35 (2.8×10^{-6})	3

Table 5. Number of reads detected by Kraken as *Giardia duodenalis* and number of reads confirmed by BLAST in plant DNA samples spiked with different amounts of *G. duodenalis* DNA.

Sample	Plant DNA	<i>G. duodenalis</i> DNA	N of reads	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>G. duodenalis</i> (relative abundance)	N of reads confirmed by BLAST
GMET1	1 µg	10 nanograms	52965068	134267 (2.5×10^{-3})	75051
GMET2	1 µg	1 nanogram	57683432	13547 (2.3×10^{-4})	8758
GMET3	1 µg	100 picograms	69434672	1702 (2.4×10^{-5})	810
GMET4	1 µg	10 picograms	70465268	311 (4.4×10^{-6})	70
GMET5	1 µg	1 picogram	97788126	262 (2.7×10^{-6})	5
GMET6	1 µg	No DNA	47283320	106 (2.2×10^{-6})	1

WP3. Design, implementation and validation of multi-locus typing schemes

Historically, the scant knowledge of the genomes of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* has limited the opportunity for a rationale selection of genetic markers, and efforts have mostly focused on loci containing repetitive sequences (mini- and micro-satellites) and a few polymorphic genes. The limitations in the use of these types of markers are well recognized, and no standardized genotyping schemes are currently available. To address this, the PARADISE project aimed at developing new, informative and robustly tested typing schemes for these parasites.

WP3-T1- In silico selection of informative loci from comparative genomics data

The goal of this task was to explore the WGS data generated in WP2-T1 for the identification of regions of high genetic variability in both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (Assemblage B). The selection criteria used were that: (i) the variable regions should be located on different chromosomes or at a sufficient

physical distance within one chromosome to minimize genetic linkage; (ii) a high genetic variability across the isolates should be present; (iii) specificity for *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* assemblage B should be demonstrated in silico; and (iv) the candidates selected for *G. duodenalis* assemblage B should have a low level of Allelic Sequence Heterogeneity (ASH).

Figure 3 depicts the overall strategy used for the selection of regions with high genetic variability in *C. parvum*, which resulted from further implementation of a pipeline (EBI pipeline) developed during a previous project (COMPARE). The comparative analysis of 137 WGS revealed a modest level of overall genetic diversity, with a total of about 24000 SNPs identified. Regions with high genetic variability were identified by calculating the number of SNPs in each annotated coding sequence, and then in 500 bp windows. Candidates were further selected after calculation of the Simpson's diversity index and then checked for PCR primer design options. We also followed a second selection approach, using an ad-hoc script, in which we identified physical intervals across the chromosomes containing a predefined number of SNPs (e.g., 10). Next, intervals of approximately 500-700 bp were selected and ranked in terms of their information content. By these combined approaches, 28 candidates were retained. These were combined using a Python script into marker schemes, which were evaluated based on how well they maximised the number of groups they divided the samples into. Finally, 8 markers were selected for further testing (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1).

Figure 3. General workflow of the bioinformatic analyses used to select regions with high genetic variability in *Cryptosporidium parvum*

Figure 4 depicts the overall strategy used for the selection of regions with high genetic variability in *G. duodenalis* assemblage B. The comparative analysis of 18 WGS data revealed a much larger variability compared to *C. parvum*. The analytical workflow, developed by partner P-11 (RKI), was based on a pairwise whole genome alignment of the *G. duodenalis* assemblage B samples, which were then combined into a multiple sequence alignment (MSA). Based on the MSA, genomic regions with a minimum length of 1000 bp were selected based on the condition that they occur in all input genomes. Next, MSAs were inspected to evaluate whether the genetic variability in windows of 500-700 bp allowed to differentiate the genomes included in the analysis. Additionally, ASH in each MSA was determined by isolate-specific mapping to the original sequencing data and by assessing the nucleotide frequencies in the respective read alignments. This procedure resulted in the selection of 104 candidates that were further screened in WP3-T2. A detailed account of the procedure and results obtained has been provided in D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1.

Figure 4: General workflow of the bioinformatics analyses used to detect regions with high genetic variability in *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B genomes; ASH, allele sequence heterogeneity.

WP3-T2- Development of MLST schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

Starting from the selection in WP3-T1, candidates were first screened for the possibility to design in silico unique primers for single and nested PCR assays for either parasite. Next, the specificity and sensitivity of the different PCR assays was tested in expert laboratories, allowing a second screening. Finally, the PCR products from the selected assays were submitted for Sanger sequencing to determine the quality and reproducibility of the sequencing reactions.

At the end of the selection process, eight different *C. parvum* markers were retained (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2). The discriminatory power of this MLST scheme was then investigated on a large collection of samples, which were sent by different partner institutes and collaborators to either P-23 or P-41. In addition, P-13, P-27, P-11 and P-40 ran the MLST on samples collected within their countries. In total 457 samples were originally considered for the test panel. After initial screening to ensure they were *C. parvum*, 90 samples were excluded due to either bad quality or that they were another *Cryptosporidium* species. The test panel of samples used for the experimental part of the MLST study included 367 samples from 13 countries representing both animal and human samples. In addition, 136 samples were included where the sequences for the eight markers could be extracted from the whole genome sequences. Hence, the final test panel included a total of 503 samples (Table 6).

The results show that good quality sequences for all eight markers were generated for 377 (75%) samples at the first attempt. Most other samples had good quality sequences for six or seven of the markers, but were excluded from the final analysis. However, in a few cases the samples were run a second time on the missing markers to complete the MLST. In those cases, all markers could be amplified and generated good sequences. Work is ongoing to finalise the MLST typing results for this panel of samples and determine the discriminatory power of the *C. parvum* MLST typing scheme and compare this to *gp60* typing and a published MLVA scheme. An SOP for implementing the MLST for *C. parvum* has been produced and made available (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.3). A preliminary report about the population structure of *C. parvum* in Europe was also produced (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.4).

Sample origin	Samples for PCR and sequencing	MLST extracted from genome data	Complete MLST – all isolates	Complete MLST - human isolates	Complete MLST - animal isolates
China		1	1		1
Czech Republic	6		6		6
Denmark	53	9	56	23	33
Egypt		1	1		1
Finland		17	17	7	10
France	24	7	21		21
Germany	21	16	28	12	16
Hungary		11	11		11
Italy		27	27		27
Latvia	3				
Netherlands	26		15	15	
Norway	4	4	7		7
Poland	14	2	16		16
Portugal	13	1	12		12
Slovenia		6	6	6	
Spain		1	1	1	
Sweden	124	5	94	7	87
UK	51	28	55	44	11
USA	28		3		3
Total	367	136	377	115	262

Table 6. List of the *C. parvum* isolates used for testing the MLST scheme.

For *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B, seven markers were retained at the end of the selection process (Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2). In this case, an issue of concern was the presence of Allelic Sequence Heterogeneity (ASH) in the selected markers, and its impact on data analysis and interpretation. We applied the MLST scheme to European isolates from humans (n=121, mostly from returning travellers but also from an outbreak) and animals (n=8). Full information at the seven markers was obtained for 80 human and two animal isolates (64%). Sequence analysis confirmed that ASH is a hallmark of assemblage B isolates, and showed that 66 isolates had ASH affecting 0.1-2.7% nucleotide positions (i.e., 4-105 of the 3897 positions of the concatenated markers). Notably, 16 isolates showed no ASH.

As sequences with ASH are not suitable for classical phylogenetic analyses, relationships among isolates were visualized as a heat map based on SNPs, calculated according to the Clustal Omega algorithm. This showed a clear separation of the parasite population into two clusters (Figure 5). Cluster 1 comprised isolates with sequences with no or low ASH, and included 22 human and two animal isolates. Interestingly, the sequence of a cat isolate from Sweden was identical to that of an unrelated human case from Germany. Cluster 2 comprised 60 human isolates with significant levels of ASH. Strikingly, isolates from a documented assemblage B outbreak in Italy were found in cluster 2, but clearly formed a sub-cluster with significantly lower SNP variation compared to non-outbreak isolates from the same cluster. Based in these data, inferences about the population structure of *G. duodenalis* assemblage B were derived (Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.4). In conclusion, we argued that parameters to decide on relatedness of isolates based on SNPs will have to vary depending on subpopulation assignment.

Figure 5. Heatmap of single nucleotide variation between *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B isolates, showing the presence of two clusters separating isolates with no or low ASH content (cluster 1) from isolates with high ASH content (cluster 2). Isolates from an Italian outbreak form a sub-cluster within cluster 2.

We also characterized a collection of isolates from assemblage A, another genetic group of *G. duodenalis* that infects humans and other mammals. We genotyped 60 human-derived and 11 animal-derived isolates at the six markers included in a published MLST scheme, and identified five novel variants at five of the six markers. After inclusion of previously published genotyping data, we analysed a dataset of 146 isolates from Europe and other continents and showed the presence of 78 distinct MLSTs. Data analyses confirmed the presence of two subpopulations, one (AI) that comprised all animal and a few human isolates, while the second (AII) comprised human isolates only (Figure 6). This suggests that zoonotic transmission of assemblage A is uncommon. Unique MLSTs were identified in two outbreaks, indicating that the typing scheme is suitable for epidemiological investigations. The results of this study have been accepted for publication.

Figure 6. Maximum likelihood tree showing the presence of two main clusters, corresponding to *Giardia duodenalis* sub-assemblage AI and AII. Information on host, origin of infection and epidemiologically linked cases is shown.

WP3-T3-Interlaboratory comparison of typing schemes

The goal of this task was to verify the ability to apply the SOPs, identify the genetic variants (alleles) and define the multi-locus genotypes during a ring test (RT) in which 14 laboratories from 11 European countries participated. The technical workshop (training on MLST) planned to take place as part of WP3 could not be organized in person, and therefore two separate virtual trainings were conducted by RKI (for *G. duodenalis*) and ISS (for *C. parvum*) in April/May 2022 to illustrate the specific aims and sequence analysis workflow prior to the shipment of the RT samples. The SOPs and the reference allelic sequences identified at each marker were made available to the participants. The RT samples included five *G. duodenalis* DNAs, tested and provided by RKI, and five *C. parvum* DNAs, tested and provided by SVA/ISS. In addition to reporting the MLST (*C. parvum*) and the consensus sequences along with identification of the ASH positions (*G. duodenalis*) for each sample, the participants were instructed to upload the raw sequence files into the project's cloud space. The results of the RT confirmed that the SOPs were correctly used by the participating laboratories (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.5), and that the limited percentage of failure (<5%) in the correct assignment of sequences to alleles was attributable to the low quality of Sanger sequencing reactions (for both parasites), and to slight inconsistencies in the consensus sequences at ASH positions (for *G. duodenalis*). It can be concluded that the implementation of the MLST schemes was largely accomplished.

WP4-Parasite enrichment strategies

The objectives of WP4 were the development and evaluation by inter-laboratory comparison of: i) two pre-DNA extraction protocols based on two alternative affinity reagents, nanobodies (single-chain variable fragment antibodies) and aptamers (oligonucleotides that bind to a specific target molecule), and their application for magnetic capture of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in different matrices; ii) a protocol for post-DNA enrichment to concentrate parasite DNA based on hybridization of target-specific biotinylated probes.

WP4-T1- Development of pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

The single current ISO standard for *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium* detection in fresh produce is based on immunomagnetic separation (IMS) of (oo)cysts. This method requires expensive reagents and is limited in application. The aim of WP4-T1 was to develop strategies to improve the sensitivity of detection while delivering less expensive methods applicable to food matrices. Two approaches were attempted, nanobodies and aptamers.

Figure 7 depicts the overall strategy used for the selection of nanobodies. We first immunized two new world camelids with antigen extracts from *G. duodenalis* cysts or *C. parvum* oocysts, respectively. Immune sera of the animals were tested by ELISA and IFA to ensure sufficient antibody production, and thus reactive B cells, against the antigens. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated, RNA extracted and used for production of highly complex cDNA phage libraries of variable domains of heavy-chain only antibodies (VHH, or nanobodies). Subsequent screening of *G. duodenalis* library identified 24 VHH clones reacting against cyst antigens (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.2). The same procedure failed to identify candidates against the *C. parvum* oocysts wall, despite additional screening strategies were attempted, including the use of a crude oocyst extract and whole oocysts bound to magnetic beads. Possibly, the bio-penning processes were not efficient to enrich for VHH domains reacting against the oocyst wall.

Of the 24 VHH candidates for *G. duodenalis*, 10 were selected for further characterization based on the retrieved VHH sequence (e.g., omitting candidates with identical sequences). The 10 candidates were subcloned and expressed in *E. coli* and then affinity-purified for further testing and selection via immunofluorescence analysis, western blotting and ELISA. Briefly, immunofluorescence assays revealed assemblage-dependent binding pattern, and identified two candidates binding to the cyst wall of both assemblages A and B and five candidates binding to assemblage A cysts only. In order to test the robustness of nanobody staining, a small interlaboratory test was performed. Two nanobodies candidates, one recognizing both assemblages A and B (Nb19) and one recognizing only assemblage A (Nb4) cysts, were sent to 5 partners within the consortium. Participants were asked to perform immunofluorescence staining using appropriate in-house protocols and material. Promising results, showing positive binding of the selected candidates to the *G. duodenalis* cyst, were obtained also in the partner laboratories, although it was not possible to develop an appropriate enrichment protocol for *G. duodenalis* cysts based on nanobodies bound to immunomagnetic beads.

Figure 7. Workflow of the experimental strategy for the identification of specific nanobodies recognizing *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium* cysts/oocysts.

Figure 8 depicts the overall strategy used for the selection of aptamers. Aptamers are short (25 to 90 mer) single-stranded oligonucleotides (DNA or RNA) that are capable of selective binding to almost any target (including peptides or cells) with high affinity and specificity by folding into unique 3D structures. The main advantages compared to monoclonal antibodies include lower cost, reproducible synthesis, easy labelling with multiple reporters, and lack of need to use animals.

An ssDNA library (80 mer oligonucleotides with a randomized region of 40 nucleotides) was used for the SELEX (Systematic Evolution of Ligands by EXponential nucleotide enrichment) procedure, using as targets *G. duodenalis* H3 assemblage B cysts and *C. parvum* IOWA oocysts. Partner P-27 (ISS) focused on *G. duodenalis*, while partner P-1 (ANSESS) worked on both *G. duodenalis* and *C. parvum*. Due to the Covid-19 pandemics, the short-term mission planned to take place during Y3 for knowledge transfer on the Cell-SELEX technology could not be organized, and online meetings were used as a surrogate. P-27 accomplished 10 rounds of SELEX (five replicates for both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*), whereas P-1 accomplished 14 rounds of selection against *G. duodenalis* cysts on five biological replicates, after adaptation of the protocol originally planned. Enriched sequences were identified by high-throughput sequencing (HTS) and bioinformatics analyses (Patternity suite). Ten candidate aptamers each for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts, as well as five candidate aptamers for both parasites were identified by P-1 and 18 candidate aptamers for *G. duodenalis* cysts were identified by P-27 (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.1).

The 10 candidate aptamers for each parasite and the 5 pan-*Cryptosporidium/Giardia* from P-1 were synthesized as 5'-alexa488 tagged oligonucleotides, along with one non-enriched sequence as negative control. Flow cytometry and fluorescence microscopy were performed to assess aptamers binding, and this has revealed two *Giardia* aptamers (18G and 16G) and one pan aptamer (5CG) that showed reactivity by both confocal microscopy and flow cytometry.

The 18 candidate aptamers from P-27, together with the unselected library and two non-enriched sequencing as controls, were synthesized as 5'-biotin-TEG oligonucleotides. Several different assays, including aptamer-based indirect ELISA, flow cytometry and fluorescence microscopy, were performed to assess aptamer binding to *G. duodenalis* cysts (from both assemblages A and B) by using FITC or

HRP-conjugated Streptavidin to detect biotinylated aptamers. No specific reactivity of candidate aptamers could be demonstrated by indirect ELISA, whereas two candidate aptamers, ISS-N000 and ISS-N001, showed reactivity on *G. duodenalis* assemblage A cysts using flow cytometry (i.e., a shift of the fluorescence peak). Surprisingly, no reactivity was seen with assemblage B cysts, despite these having been used for Cell-SELEX. Finally, fluorescence microscopy revealed that aptamer ISS-N000, and to a minor extent ISS-N001, reacts with the inner content of the cyst, but not with the cyst wall surface.

In conclusion, aptamers showing specific binding to the surface of either *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* (oo)cyst wall could not be identified, and therefore conjugation with magnetic beads was not attempted. Although these aptamers are not suitable for magnetic bead coupling, they may be exploited for other purposes (e.g., anti-giardial drug delivery).

Figure 8. Workflow of the experimental strategy for the identification of aptamers recognizing the (oo)cyst wall surface of *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium*.

WP4-T2- Development of post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

Detection of parasites on food and in water is complicated by low levels of contamination, often resulting in under-detection. Likewise, detection of low numbers of *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in manure requires sensitive methods. A possible solution is the use of methods that concentrate specific target DNA. PARADISE has focused on the magnetic capture hybridization PCR method, or “DNA fishing”. Hybridization-based capture is a type of target enrichment that hybridizes biotinylated single-stranded DNA probes to complementary target DNA regions to pull down the targeted DNA of interest allowing amplification of the targeted DNA. The aim of PARADISE WP4-T2 was to develop capture probes directed against commonly used markers for *G. duodenalis* and *C. parvum* and newly developed markers identified in WP3.

As a result, a magnetic capture (MC) system for the *Cryptosporidium* 18S rDNA and gp60 loci was designed. The MC systems consist of capture probes and in the case of 18S rDNA also helper probes. Helper probes are used to allow dimerization between the probe and target DNA.

The MC systems were originally and independently developed by P-41 and P-30 (SVA and RIVM), and later the protocols were harmonized, and all sensitivity testing and validation was mirrored in both labs. The protocol has been optimized in relation to buffers, temperatures, probes (design, helper probes and concentration) as well as on incubation times and, very importantly for parasites, the lysis method. The various capture oligonucleotides were tested on clean, enumerated oocysts as well as on different volumes of faecal samples from cattle. The final protocol has been used for validation and

sensitivity testing. The protocol and the samples used for validation has been published in D-JRP19-WP4.8. Validation and sensitivity testing has been performed at both P-41 and P-30 with most samples identical in both labs.

For comparison, the extraction and amplification has been evaluated for the MC-PCR in parallel with a traditionally used stool-kit for the gp60 probe system. Using qPCR to measure efficiency of the two methods, it was observed that the MC system is approximately 100 times more sensitive.

A Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) was prepared and distributed to all partners involved in WP4 plus those that expressed interest during the PARADISE final meeting (June 2022). P-41 (SVA) offered to distribute samples and reagents for an interlaboratory comparison and to organize a training at SVA. Representatives from two institutes visited SVA during a two-day training in October 2022. The full protocol was demonstrated, and the SOP was discussed in detail. Five institutes participated in the interlaboratory comparison, and received four samples (1. undiluted *C. parvum* positive, 2. sample 1 diluted 1:10, 3. sample 1 diluted 1:100, 4. negative sample). All participants were asked to run the full protocol and report Ct values for all samples for both 18S, gp60 and the Competing Internal Amplification Control (CIAC). Results showed that the newly developed method and SOP works well in other laboratories, and that the sensitivity is in the same range as in the laboratories that developed the method. One institute reported negative results from most samples indicating that something did not work. However, this institute reported negative qPCR results for the CIAC, which indicates the error was likely in the last step, the qPCR rather than in the hybridization capture. The institute has been given the opportunity to rerun the qPCR (results not received at the time of submission of this report). All details and results from the interlaboratory comparison have been reported (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.4).

Due to delay in WP3, a result of lock-downs during the pandemic, the D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3 was written before the MLST probes had been designed. As a result, we report here these newly developed probes, for both the MLST schemes developed for *G. duodenalis* assemblage B and *C. parvum* in WP3 here. All newly developed probes (Tables 7 and 8) have been designed according to parameters outlined in D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3.

Gene (Marker)	Chromosome	Probe sequence
CPATCC_0001010	8	GGCTAAAATTACTAGAAAATAATATAATGGCCTAAC
CPATCC_0007000	7	TGAATCGTGCCCTTCACCCCAAGCC
CPATCC_0012400	6	GCGAGACAATCACATGGCTTGTCCACA
CPATCC_0021750	4	ACAACGGCAGAGTTTTACCAAGTGT
CPATCC_0024650	5	AGGTGGAAGCTTGGAATAAGGGAT
CPATCC_0028230	2	TTCTTCGTCCGGAGGACCAACTGGA
CPATCC_0031960	3	AGGGGAGATTAGGTTGTTGCGACGCTT
CPATCC_0039030	1	TGGCGAGTATTCTGCCGGCTTTAGA

Table 6. Capture probes designed for *Cryptosporidium parvum* MLST

Marker	Chromosome	Probe sequence
2	4	CACCATAAAGGGCTTGACGGAGAAGAGGATTGAGAT
7	3	GTCTACACGCGTGAGTGGTACGATTCTTCCTTACT
8	2	TTTGCAAAGCGATCTAAGCTTCTCTCCAACGTACT
10	5	GCGTGTGGTCACCTATGAAGGAGATGTTTTTGATCC
11	4	GGAGTCTGAGGGGTTGACCATTTCAAAGCAAACAAT
14	1	ACATATCTTGCATCTTTTTGATAGCTGCTCCGTGCC
20	5	TGCTATTAAGAAGTCCTTTTGTGGTTCTGGACGGGA

Table 7. Capture probes designed for *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B MLST

2.8.4 Project self-assessment

As a consortium, we consider the PARADISE project successful in creating or strengthening collaborations among partners, and it achieved most of its ambitious scientific goals. Major progress was achieved in advancing science towards all the goals set.

WP2: The aims of the task on genomics (WP2-T1) were reached and exceeded. We generated more than the anticipated number of WGS for both *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*. Although planned to end in M52, this was extended to M58, as additional samples were available for WGS. The experience gained highlights that pathogen purification is the critical step in the overall WGS process. In addition, the bioinformatics workflows have been expanded beyond what was originally planned to include analyses (e.g., multiplicity of infection, recombination) that address the specific epidemiology of the pathogens under consideration. Capacity building to stimulate the use of WGS by Reference Laboratories has started, e.g., by training activities on bioinformatics in collaboration with the inter-EURL working group on WGS.

The metagenomics work partially reached the intended goals. The in silico analyses (WP2-T2) focused on the analyses of published metagenomes and of simulated data, and critically assessed parameters influencing the specificity and sensitivity of detection of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*, in particular to avoid false positives in food sample matrices with low pathogen loads. We consider that this goal was achieved and that we have gained valuable insight to what measures need to be taken to avoid both false negatives and false positives, for example by the use of confirmatory steps (e.g., BLAST). Efforts to improve the sensitivity of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* detection using the metabarcoding assay were unsuccessful (WP2-T3), and therefore the comparison of its limit of detection with that of shotgun metagenomics was not possible.

WP3: All tasks were completed for both *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. The new MLST schemes have been designed (T1), developed and thoroughly evaluated (T2), the SOPs prepared and the interlaboratory tests performed (T3). These new, highly discriminatory tools will find application in outbreak investigation and may become official methods in European Reference Laboratories. In addition to the outlined work planned in the proposal we have also performed a large-scale comparison of the MLST developed for *C. parvum* with the commonly used subtyping marker as well as with a published multi-locus fragment subtyping scheme.

We also expanded the work on *Giardia* MLST. The work was originally planned to focus only on *G. duodenalis* assemblage B, but was successfully expanded to include a study on *G. duodenalis* assemblage A. This work, based on a published MLST scheme, has been accepted for publication.

WP4: The work on pre- and post-DNA enrichment strategies (T1 and T2) partially reached the intended goals. For the post-DNA enrichment strategy (T2), a highly sensitive capture method for

Cryptosporidium was developed and extensively tested, and a SOP is now available and tested in an interlaboratory comparison. New hybridization probes for all markers selected for the new MLST schemes for Giardia and Cryptosporidium have been designed.

The work on nanobodies allowed identification of reagents showing high affinity to Giardia cysts, but coupling of nanobodies to magnetic beads, and demonstration of their utility to capture the parasite present in complex matrices, could not be achieved. Consequently, the SOPs for magnetic capture (D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.7) based on aptamers and nanobodies were not prepared. A large body of work, based on both established and new (high throughput sequencing) techniques, was conducted to select aptamers with affinity to Cryptosporidium and Giardia, yet specific staining of the (oo)cyst wall was not demonstrated for any of the selected candidates.

2.8.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.1	Report of the kickoff meeting	M26	April 2020	Public OHEJP: available https://zenodo.org/record/4452807#.YAhQRDmg9dg	8, meeting report
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.2	Report of Annual meeting	M46	M57	Public OHEJP: available 10.5281/zenodo.7064005 https://zenodo.org/record/7064005	8, meeting report
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.3	Report of Final meeting	M54	M57	Public 10.5281/zenodo.7064023 https://zenodo.org/record/7064023	8, meeting report
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.1	Protocol for 18S rDNA-based amplicon sequencing for detection of relevant FBPs	M30	M37	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4478998	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.2	Report on the FBPs detected in metagenomics datasets by <i>in silico</i> analysis	M48	M59	Public OHEJP: available 10.5281/zenodo.7380290	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.3	Report on limit of detection of amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics	M50	M59	Public OHEJP: available 10.5281/zenodo.7380368	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.4	SOP for FBPs detection using amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics	M58	No	Comparison of the limit of detection of two platforms was not possible, therefore this deliverable could not be prepared	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1	Report on the <i>in silico</i> selection of highly polymorphic sequences in <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> genomes	M30	M36	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4452771	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2	Report on the identification of markers for MLST of <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M45		Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5494475	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.3	SOPs for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> MLST schemes	M57		Public 10.5281/zenodo.7064263 https://zenodo.org/record/7064263	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.4	Report on the genetic population structure of <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M58	M59	Public OHEJP: available 10.5281/zenodo.7300011 https://zenodo.org/record/7300011	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.5	Report of interlaboratory comparison of MLST schemes for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M58	M59	Public OHEJP: available 10.5281/zenodo.7300054 https://zenodo.org/record/7300054	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.6	SOP for MLST schemes for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M58		This deliverable is a duplicate of WP3.3 that was mistakenly included.	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.1	Report on the cloning and sequencing of aptamers specific for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M36	M45	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5495542	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.2	Report on the selection of highly affine nanobodies specific for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M36	M45	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5495560	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3	Report on the probes designed to targets developed in WP3 for <i>C.</i>	M44	M45	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5495592	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		<i>parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>				
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.4	Report of interlaboratory comparison of post-DNA extraction hybridization probe capture and MC-PCR for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M52	M59	Public OHEJP available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7398452	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.5	Report of interlaboratory comparison of nanobodies-based magnetic capture for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M52	No	This deliverable will not be prepared	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.6	Report of interlaboratory comparison of aptamer-based magnetic capture for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M52	No	This deliverable will not be prepared	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.7	SOP for magnetic (oo)cysts capture based on aptamers and or nanobodies	M54	No	This deliverable will not be prepared	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.8	SOP for magnetic DNA capture based on hybridization probes	M54	M59	Public OHEJP: available 10.5281/zenodo.7300076 https://zenodo.org/record/7300076	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-1	Kick-off Meeting (WP1)	M26	M26	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-2	Study visit (ISS-ANSES) for optimizing aptamer selection strategy	M28	No	Study visit impossible due to the COVID-19 epidemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-3	Key isolates of C. parvum collected	M30	M45	Field work impacted by the Covid pandemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-4	Key isolates of G. duodenalis collected	M30	M45	Field work impacted by the Covid pandemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-5	Referenced database of foodborne parasite genomes established	M30	M58	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-6	Pipeline for metagenome data analysis for FBPs optimized	M30	M58	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-7	First set of candidate markers for MLST development available	M30	Yes	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-8	Animal immunization and cDNA library of nanobody	M30	M36	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		sequences for <i>C. parvum</i> and for <i>G. duodenalis</i> completed			
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-9	Submission of genome sequences of <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> to public repository	M36	M60	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-10	Aptamers sequences selected	M36	M58	
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-11	Highly affine nanobodies selected	M36	M58	Achieved in part. Selection did work for <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> but not for <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i>
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-12	Pre-evaluation of probes directed towards markers commonly used for <i>C. parvum</i>	M36	M36	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-13	Pre-evaluation of probes directed towards markers commonly used for <i>G. duodenalis</i> .	M36	M36	
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-14	Annual meeting (WP1)	M42	M46	The Annual meeting was held, virtually, on the 26th October 2021, due to restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemics.
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-15	Technical Workshop on enrichment strategies (WP4)	M42	M58	Organization of the technical workshop not possible due to the Covid-19 pandemics. In October 2002, P-41 (SVA) organized a two-day training on the magnetic capture system for <i>Cryptosporidium</i> .

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-16	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>C. parvum</i> available	M42	M48	
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-17	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>G. duodenalis</i> available	M42	M48	
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-18	Technical Workshop for training on MLST (WP3)	M48	M52	Organization of the technical workshop not possible due to the Covid-19 pandemics. Two virtual workshops were organized in April-May 2022, before the ring tests.
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-19	Validation of marker for typability and resolution accomplished	M48	M54	Results of the interlaboratory test have been discussed at the final meeting (Uppsala, 22-23 June) and by direct contacts with the Consortium partners
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-20	Magnetic bead coupled nanobodies suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M48	No	Coupling of candidate nanobodies with affinity to <i>Giardia</i> cysts or <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts could not be attempted
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-21	Magnetic bead coupled aptamers suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M48	No	Aptamers with the desired binding properties towards <i>Cryptosporidium</i> and <i>Giardia</i> (oo)cysts have not been identified.
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-22	Hybridization probes tested for robustness and sensitivity available	M48	M59	
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-23	Final meeting (WP1)	M54	M54	

2.8.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Molecular Characterization of <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> in Children and Adults Sampled in Algeria https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010054 https://zenodo.org/record/4422456#.YArbG-hKjcc	Published	YES		Yes 2730.00 \$ =2437.96 €
Veterinary Students Have a Higher Risk of Contracting Cryptosporidiosis when Calves with High Fecal Cryptosporidium Loads Are Used for Fetotomy Exercises 10.1128/AEM.01250-20 https://zenodo.org/record/4129990#.X6PX8WhKjcc	Published	YES		Yes 1475.33 €
Parasitic Intestinal Protists of Zoonotic Relevance Detected in Pigs by Metabarcoding and Real-Time PCR. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-2607/9/6/1189 https://zenodo.org/record/4898752#.YTnBA50zaUk	Published	Yes		Yes Free of cost
Mining public metagenomes for environmental surveillance of parasites: a proof of principle. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.622356. https://zenodo.org/record/5494583	Published	Yes		Yes 1580.00 \$ =2176.47 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Amplicon-based next-generation sequencing of eukaryotic nuclear ribosomal genes (metabarcoding) for the detection of single-celled parasites in human faecal samples. doi: 10.1016/j.parepi.2022.e00242. https://zenodo.org/record/7091766#.Y49CkLTMKuk</p>	Published	Yes		Yes 1580 €
<p>An outbreak of cryptosporidiosis associated with drinking water in north-eastern Italy, August 2019: microbiological and environmental investigations. doi: 10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.35.2200038. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7043272 https://zenodo.org/record/7043272#.YysQ6nZBxM0</p>	Published	Yes		Yes Free of cost
<p>Extensive testing of a multi-locus sequence typing scheme for <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> Assemblage A confirms its good discriminatory power DOI : 10.1186/s13071-022-05615-x</p>	Accepted in Parasites&Vectors	Yes		Yes 2860,90 €)
<p>Highly contiguous genomes of human clinical isolates of <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> reveal assemblage and sub-assemblage specific presence-absence variation in protein-coding genes</p>	In revision (Microbial Genomes)	Yes		Yes (±3000 €)
<p>Molecular epidemiology of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> and <i>Giardia</i> in Danish calves</p>	Under preparation	Yes		
<p>Design, development and testing of a new Multi-Locus Sequence Typing scheme for the zoonotic pathogen <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i></p>	Under preparation	Yes		

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
How should <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> be typed? Insights from a comparison of MLST and MLVA schemes	Under preparation	Yes		
Design, development and testing of a new Multi-Locus Sequence Typing scheme for <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> assemblage B	Under preparation	Yes		
Genomic epidemiology of <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> in Europe: a complex picture	Under preparation	Yes		
Large-scale comparative genomics of <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> assemblage B	Under preparation	Yes		
Identification and characterization of <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> cyst wall specific nanobodies	Under preparation	Yes		
Development of a magnetic capture method for the sensitive detection of <i>Cryptosporidium</i> spp. DNA	Under preparation	Yes		
Detection and prevalence of <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> in Dutch dairy calves using a magnetic capture method	Under preparation	Yes		

Additional output

A summary of the outbreak investigation where One Health approaches of PARADISE were applied by partner 13 (SSI) has been published (in Danish) in the Danish Veterinary Journal (<https://ipaper.ipapercms.dk/fsek/dvt/2020/dvt102020/?Page=36>)

The same outbreak investigation served as the base for a case study prepared for One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module 2022 in collaboration with One Health EJP Joint Integrative Projects MATRIX and OH-Harmony-CAP, organised by SSI and DTU-FOOD.

A presentation on the metagenomics work in WP2 was given at the meeting of the Dutch Society for Parasitology on 26th of May, 2021 (NVP - Evenementen (parasitologie.nl))

Oral presentation about OHEJP projects with focus on parasites, at OHEJP Research Seminar at DTU-FOOD, Denmark, 15.6.2022. By Pikka Jokelainen, SSI.

Poster presentation at ICOPA2022: “CRYPTOSPORIDIUM PARVUM IN CALVES IN DENMARK: HIGH PREVALENCE AND FEW SUBTYPES” by Pikka Jokelainen, SSI.

Presentation of results WP4-T2 at the Veterinary Parasitology Workshop, Wageningen University, May 18, 2022: “Capture probe based detection method for Cryptosporidium spp. and it’s use to determine prevalence of zoonotic Cryptosporidium spp. in dairy calves”. By Kees van der Ark, RIVM.

Presentation of results WP2-T3 at the Veterinary Parasitology Workshop, Wageningen University, May 18, 2022: “Looking for Cryptosporidium in the (metagenomics) hay stack”. By Frits Franssen, RIVM.

Application of tool developed in WP4-T2 for the detection of Cryptosporidium in the National Livestock Surveillance in the Netherlands. Public report by RIVM (in Dutch) expected in Q4 2022.

Paradise and sources of parasites - where to find Cryptosporidium, Giardia and Toxoplasma and how to detect and characterise them”. 9 September 2022. Seminar for the Swedish Agencies including SVA. By Karin Troell, SVA.

“Enroute to PARADISE – are there any final challenges at the pearly gates?” 5-7 December 2022. OHEJP final school. By Karin Troell, SVA.

Poster presentations about the project at One Health EJP internal events.

“Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

NGS (Genomics and Metagenomics). In line with the project’s call, PARADISE has used NGS methodologies to achieve its goals. This has resulted in the **largest sequencing effort** ever made at the EU level, and has been paralleled by the refinement of analytical workflows for the analysis of complex data that took into account the specific biology of parasitic pathogens. **EFSA** and **ECDC** can have an interest towards this work, as it demonstrates full applicability of genomics and metagenomics approaches to detect and characterize these important foodborne pathogens.

Non-NGS (molecular tools). Again, in line with the project’s call, PARADISE has used non-NGS methodologies to achieve its goals. The new **Multi-Locus Typing Schemes** for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* offer improved discriminatory power compared to previous methods, and can be used by the **National Reference Laboratories for Parasites** across Europe to conduct, e.g., epidemiological investigation of outbreaks.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Application of tool developed in WP4-T2 for the detection of *Cryptosporidium* in the National Livestock Surveillance in the Netherlands. Public report by RIVM (in Dutch) <https://www.rivm.nl/publicaties/surveillance-zoonosen-in-melkvee-2021>, report number 2022-0080. Continued application at National Livestock surveillance if *Cryptosporidium* is a relevant pathogen.

The developed MLST procedures for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* with improved discriminatory power compared to previous methods have been implemented in several laboratories within the consortium.

2.8.7 One Health impact

Foodborne parasites have rarely been prioritized as model pathogens in the EU and many knowledge gaps need to be addressed before this will happen. In this context, the opportunity given by the OHEJP initiative, with support to three different projects, has been an essential step. Complementarities with other projects within and beyond the OHEJP have resulted in the sharing of bioinformatics approaches for genome comparison (TOXOSOURCES) and has helped to identify strategies and challenges for implementation of molecular methods for *Cryptosporidium* (HARMONY-CAP). Interactions and networking with the *Cryptosporidium* Reference Unit, Public Health Wales, allowed continuous exchange of information on molecular typing schemes and their appropriate integration to public health surveillance. In more general terms, the project largely helped to strengthen the scientific exchange between participating research laboratories, which will foreseeable foster the initiation of new research projects beyond the scope of the PARADISE project.

The use of genomics in epidemiology and surveillance of pathogens has been a major focus at the EU level in recent years, with EFSA/ECDC promoting several initiatives, mostly on bacteria. In this context, parasitic pathogens are lagging behind, but the important advances made by PARADISE at both the wet- and dry-lab level will contribute to a wider use of WGS and metagenomics. Capacity building is still needed, and the ongoing interaction with the inter-EURL working group on WGS will contribute to this (e.g., by training activities).

As the coordinator of PARADISE (P-27, ISS) is also in charge of the European Reference Laboratory for Parasites, communication of the outcome of the project to the network of National Reference Laboratories was facilitated. The methods developed during PARADISE may become official methods in the future, and their application will aid in surveillance and in outbreak investigations. Other members of the consortium work in public health/animal health agencies, therefore the methods developed by PARADISE could be introduced into diagnostic and surveillance pipelines/SOPs.

2.8.8 Data Management Plan

10.5281/zenodo.7476652

2.8.9 Future dissemination activities

The main stakeholders of PARADISE are the international agencies such as ECDC, EFSA, OIE, FAO and WHO. Main dissemination of the project are scientific papers and participation to international scientific meetings. The Project Management Team (PMT) and Communication Team can be of help updating the PARADISE webpage, creating brochure for the Project dissemination and disseminate relevant outcomes such as important scientific publications that are in preparation.

2.9 JRP20-R2-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR

2.9.1 Consortium composition

Project leader: Tine Hald (DTU)

Deputy project leader: Eelco Franz (RIVM)

WP1 Project coordination and administration: Tine Hald (DTU) and Eelco Franz (RIVM)

- Task 1 Project management: Tine Hald (DTU) and Eelco Franz (RIVM)
- Task 2 Mapping of existing knowledge gaps: Annemarie Kaesbohrer (BfR) and Tine Hald (DTU)
- Task 3 Data Management Plan: Tine Hald (DTU) and Marianne Chemaly (ANSES)

WP2 Data: Coordination of data collection: Marianne Chemaly (ANSES) and Robert Söderlund (SVA)

- Task 1 Mapping of existing data/database establishment: Tine Hald (DTU) and Eelco Franz (RIVM)
- Task 2 Data collection: Salmonella: Magdalena Zajac (PIWET) and Ângela Pista (INSA)
- Task 3 Data collection: Campylobacter: Eva Møller Nielsen (SSI) and Mónica Oleastro (INSA)
- Task 4 Data collection: STEC: Camilla Sekse (NVI) and Rosangela Tozzoli (ISS)
- Task 5 Data collection: AMR: Julio Álvarez Sanchez (VISAVET) and Kaye Burgess (Teagasc)

WP3 Methods: Assessment and improvement: Thomas Rosendal (SVA) and Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM)

- Task 1 Microbial subtyping: Thomas Rosendal (SVA) and Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM)
- Task 2 SA by phylogeny: Eva Møller Nielsen (SSI)
- Task 3 Infectious disease modelling: Thomas Rosendal (SVA)
- Task 4 Metagenomic-based SA: Ana Sofia Duarte (DTU) and Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM)
- Task 5 Meta-analysis of case-control studies: Axel Bonacic Marinovic (RIVM) and Sara Monteiro Pires (DTU)
- Task 6 Aggregation of outbreak data: Sara Monteiro Pires (DTU) and Gaia Scavia (ISS)
- Task 7 Risk-assessment based approached: Eric Evers (RIVM) and Annemarie Kaesbohrer (BfR)

WP4 Results: Presenting and comparing results per hazard: Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM) and Sara Monteiro Pires (DTU)

- Task 1 Results for Salmonella: Sara Monteiro Pires (DTU)
- Task 2 Results for Campylobacter: Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM)
- Task 3 Results for STEC: Gaia Scavia (ISS)
- Task 4 Results for AMR: Thomas Hagenaars (WBVR)

WP5 Conclusions and policy translation: Gaia Scavia (ISS) and Tine Hald (DTU)

- Task 1 Technical expert evaluation: Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM) and Thomas Rosendal (SVA)

- Task 2 Translating SA estimates into policy: Gaia Scavia (ISS) and Sara Monteiro Pires (DTU)
- Task 3 Final recommendations in a One Health frame: Tine Hald (DTU) and Gaia Scavia (ISS)

2.9.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The DiSCoVeR project brought together researchers and experts from different disciplines (microbiology, bioinformatics and epidemiology) and sectors (veterinary science, food safety, public health and environmental health) from 19 institutions in 13 European countries into a unique consortium to address the challenges of source attribution in an interdisciplinary manner. As there exist no gold standard for conducting source attribution, we took a comprehensive approach applying several different methodologies and models in a comparative fashion.

We started by mapping existing knowledge and data gaps and recommending new studies and/or methods needed to fill them. We mapped available data by creating data inventories for the DiSCoVeR target pathogens: *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC/STEC² and ESBL *E. coli*. Not all expected data became available for the project, as some partners met delays in collecting new data from non-livestock and non-food sources due to COVID-19. Still, we collected comprehensive datasets including data from a broad range of reservoirs and sources, including those that are not traditionally part of existing monitoring and surveillance activities, e.g. pets (incl. reptiles), wildlife, and environmental sources. For *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and STEC, a substantial part of the isolates in the collection were sequenced and these data formed the basis for the WGS-based source attribution approaches.

With regard to approaches and models for source attribution, work was focused on cataloguing, evaluating and advancing existing methods for source attribution. For *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, and STEC, several types of national and multi-country WGS-based attribution models were developed. Overall, the results were in agreement and in line with those found with the 'conventional' subtyping approaches (phenotypic and MLST based), which gives credibility to both the results and the different models. Findings were further supported by a systematic literature review and meta-analysis of case-control studies of sporadic *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* infections and an aggregated analysis of EU *Salmonella* outbreak data. Although the nuances and the level of attribution of these types of studies are different from the subtyping approaches, the results are comparable and dissimilarities can to a large extent be explained. Multi-country Comparative Exposure Assessments (CEA) of all target pathogens and AMR in pets was also performed. The output is the relative exposure of humans to the target pathogens due to in-/direct contact with cats or dogs, and the results reflected a high degree of uncertainty mainly because of data scarcity. In conclusion, WGS-based models have some clear advantages (e.g. higher predicting accuracy due to the increased discriminatory power), but they are also more resource demanding, and in some situations, phenotypic and/or epidemiological models may give results that are just as useful.

A mapping of the currently existing control programmes of the target pathogens and AMR in humans, animals and the environment at the EU and national level was conducted. This task was addressed by i) a scientific literature review, ii) a review of grey literature, and iii) a survey aimed at relevant national experts.

During the project, we have held two stakeholder meetings to get input and feedback from among others EFSA, ECDC, EURLs, and the EC. In the last meeting, we presented the project outcomes and discussed how the key findings including the attribution estimates may be translated into policy.

² For the purpose of this document both the abbreviations VTEC= Verocytotoxin-producing *E. coli* or STEC=Shiga toxin-producing *E.coli* are used. Both terms identify the same *E.coli* pathogroup and are largely used in the scientific literature. They differ only in consideration of the term used to identify the type of Toxin produced by *E.coli* belonging to this pathogroup (i.e., Verocytotoxin or Shiga toxin encoded by *vtx* or *stx* genes), which is responsible of the main clinical pictures attributable to VTEC/STEC infection in humans.

From a One Health perspective, the surveillance focus is still very much on livestock and food, whereas the environment, including e.g. wildlife, is only sporadically monitored resulting in data scarcity. The role of the environment and pets as sources for human infections, therefore, remains unclear and is complicated by bi-/multi-directional transmission, as also illustrated by one of our models. Still, the findings confirm that livestock populations are the main reservoirs for the target pathogens except for ESBL, where human-to-human transmission are more important. From a risk assessment point of view, particularly, *Salmonella* in pigs and pork and *Campylobacter* in broilers and chicken meat stand out as areas, where targeted future control and intervention could be implemented to reduce the burden of human infections significantly.

Other recommendations based on the work in DiSCoVeR include, but are not limited to, harmonizing sampling and reporting further, including an expansion of the existing minimum requirement for accompanying metadata and subtyping results, and promote capacity building on integrated surveillance, burden of disease, source attribution, risk assessment, and system thinking at country level.

2.9.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Project coordination and administration (M25-60)

WP1-T1- Project management (M25-60)

Since the start of the project, we have had two face-to-face meetings: A kick-off meeting hosted by DTU on February 10-12, 2020, and a final meeting hosted by ISS on November 16-18, 2022. We have also had nine web meetings for all partners and 16 web meetings for the project management team (PMT) consisting of all work package leaders, their deputies and task leaders. In addition, WP leaders and task leaders have held regular web-meetings to follow progress and present and discuss results.

A share-site hosted by DTU was set up early in project. Here project partners have shared documents and data, including minutes of meetings and the data inventories.

Partners also agreed on a Material Transfer Agreement (MTA), which was signed by all partners.

WP1-T2- Mapping of existing knowledge gaps (M25-28)

For the mapping of existing knowledge gaps, a systematic literature search by means of a rapid review was performed. Based on predefined search queries, publications relevant for source attribution of the bacterial species *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC and for antimicrobial resistant (AMR) bacteria (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E. coli*) were identified in the two databases Scopus and Web of Science. Each identified publication was tagged according to categories like the organisms and sources they considered or the methods they employed. Using the data of the tagged publications, knowledge maps were created, which show the number of publications found for each method-source combination for each of the above-mentioned foodborne pathogens and AMR. The methodology and results of this mapping together with suggestions how to fill the identified knowledge gaps assembled in a report and submitted as deliverable D-JRP FBZ-1-WP1.1. The results were also presented at the OHEJP ASM in Copenhagen June 9-11, 2021. A summary is uploaded at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/5825542#.YdcJyWjMKUK>

WP1-T3- Data Management Plan (DMP) (M25-60)

The first draft of the DMP was prepared in Nov 2020 and updated in January 2022. The data inventories describing the data and including metadata will be made available as Excel sheets at Zenodo. Partners have also agreed to make the WGS data open access through ENA by creating a so-called umbrella project. Currently, all sequence data are uploaded at sciencedata.dk in a password protected folder. Upload to ENA requires some organising, as some sequences that are included in DiSCoVeR already

are at ENA, whereas others are not. We are currently completing pathogen-specific lists with all sequence data used in DiSCoVeR including ENA accession numbers. First when we have a final list of accession numbers, can we ask for the creation of an umbrella project, which we can then make open access. A final update of the DMP will take place, when all the WGS data used in the project have been uploaded to ENA. This is a time consuming process, which is expected to be completed by February 2023.

WP2: Data: Coordination of data collection (M25-M50)

WP2-T1- Mapping of existing data/database est. (M25-36)

A data inventory form in Excel was adapted to each pathogen subgroup. The purpose of the inventory was to get a overview of strains and sequences available in order to pinpoint areas with limited data availability to i) direct further sampling, and ii) identify for which pathogens and models we could expect to have sufficient data for source attribution. The data inventories were filled-in by partners and hazard-specific web meetings were organized to present the data available and agree on further sampling of mainly non-animal food reservoirs and/or isolate characterization (mainly sequencing) and transmission to the other WPs for source attribution analysis. A short description and the hazard-specific data sheets have been uploaded to Zenodo as D-JRPFZ-1-WP2.6 along with the data inventory files (Excel), which hold all the data collected and used in the project, except for the actual sequence data as explained above.

For the description and selection of data for the final inventories, we developed a set of minimum metadata and formulated some general data recommendations including minimum sample sizes and sampling periods. To ensure data representativeness, recommendations for human data in addition included the requirement to distinguish between travel- and non-travel-related cases, as well as between outbreak- and non-outbreak-related cases. Likewise, animal and food isolates should preferably be from national surveillance/monitoring/control programmes or larger surveys, and it was recommended to avoid “clustered” data e.g. data on more isolates from the same farm or food batch, or clinical isolates from diseased animals.

The data inventories provided the basis for selection of appropriate datasets for source attribution for the target pathogens and attribution approaches (see WP4 description for the source attribution approaches selected for each organism). For each of the pathogens, a publication describing the collected data and resulting dataset is being prepared.

WGS data

Generally, the majority, but not all isolates included in the inventories, had been sequenced. Consequently, for each target pathogen there exist a data inventory with metadata and some phenotypic information, as described above, and a ‘sub-dataset’ for the WGS data including accession numbers.

For sharing WGS data among participants, we created a space on the data platform sciencedata.dk and made a plan for uploading data. A meeting to demonstrate the sciencedata platform was held May 27, 2021. All available sequence data were uploaded by end of September 2022.

For *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* sequences, partners have either uploaded i) raw sequence data, which were run through the FoodQC pipeline at DTU, or ii) assembled sequences, which were then required to adhere to a set of agreed quality criteria. For STEC, a pipeline was developed as part of the projects, which all partners contributing with STEC sequences have used. For ESBL *E. coli*, no sequences were included in the project. Some were available, but many were missing or not allowed to be shared. We, therefore, assessed that it was not worthwhile collecting those that were available.

WP2-T2- Data collection: Salmonella (M25-48)

Partners were requested to share available *Salmonella* serovar-level information on isolates from their collections found in human, food, animal, and environmental sources from their countries. It was agreed to collect data from a 10-year period (from 2010 to 2019) and cover the top-10 serovars per indicated sources. In the case of human isolates, data from travel and non-travel-associated *Salmonella* cases were also shared.

Phenotypic data on isolates were submitted by 11 public health and animal health institutes located in nine European countries (Table 1). The full dataset holds data from 278 different serovars (145,076 isolates). Among these serovars, 19 were reported as cause of human infections, and 18 were common to both human and non-human sources.

Table 1. Number of *Salmonella* isolates submitted to database by different countries and institutes

Country	Institute	Source				Total
		Animal	Environment	Food	Human	
Czech Republic	VRI	1,046	68	68	3,054	4,236
Denmark	DTU	2,310		1,536		3,846
	SSI				8,012	8,012
France	ANSES	15,538	19	68		15,625
Ireland	Teagasc	206			633	839
The Netherlands	RIVM	2,360	58	15,68	11,569	15,555
Poland	PIWET	3,524	68	895		4,487
Portugal	INIAV	1,490	55	1,432		2,977
	INSA	20	55	140	2,259	2,474
Spain	VISAVET	3,373	2	760		4,135
United Kingdom	APHA	82,890				82,890
Total		112,757	323	6,467	25,527	145,076

Salmonella WGS data

Based on the *Salmonella* serovars inventory and presumed availability of sequences, it was decided to focus on six serovars: Enteritidis, Typhimurium, monophasic Typhimurium, Infantis, Newport, and Derby. Partners were asked for uploading the sequences of at least 25 isolates for each serovar in each non-human source and 50 sequences for each serovar in the human source per partner (or all the available sequences, if less). Sequences from 2015-2019 were prioritized, and the genomes should be equally distributed over the years and randomly chosen among good-quality genomes. For the human sequences, only domestic and sporadic cases were included. For the non-human sequences, those from the animal sources were prioritized and obtaining sequences from the environment, pets, and wildlife were given high attention. Overall, 4,185 sequences were provided by 14 Institutes from 9 countries (Table 2).

Table 2. Number of sequences of six *Salmonella* serovars submitted by the partners

Institute	Derby	Enteritidis	Infantis	mTyphimurium	Newport	Typhimurium	total
Anses		74		98			172
APHA	71	61	23	133	119	181	588

DAFM Laboratories	4	1	16	9	0	15	45
DTU				102		108	210
INIAV	20	32	21	0	7	20	100
INSA	9	29	14	35	27	23	137
PIWet	95	384	121	92	139	166	997
RIVM	10	145	40	6	10	6	217
SSI				68		73	141
SVA	2			4		23	29
Teagasc				103		33	136
UKHSA	118	99	100	100	100	100	617
University Hospital Galway	2	238	25	123	33	124	545
VISAVET	14	177	13	22		25	251
total	345	1240	373	895	435	897	4185

WP2-T3- Data collection: Campylobacter (M25-48)

Eight countries contributed with *Campylobacter jejuni* (n=4686) and *coli* data (n=675). A total of 1977 *C. jejuni* isolates and 90 *C. coli* isolates from human were included. Of *C. jejuni* data representing sources, most were from animals (n=1989) followed by food (n=596) and environment (n=124). For *C. coli*, most data were from animals (n=313) followed by environment (n=223) and food (n=49). For all of these isolates, sequence information was also available.

All sequences were processed through the FoodQC pipeline and made available for the partners through the sciencedata.dk platform for further analysis. Bioinformatics extracted from the sequences include quality parameters, SNP, 7-loci MLST, cgMLST, wgMLST, Kmer and AMR genes. For results of the modelling work, see WP4.

WP2-T4- Data collection: STEC (M25-50)

In total, partners from 11 countries contributed with STEC data from different sources. For the isolate inventory, a total of 7552 STEC isolates were registered, 5801 human isolates and 1538 isolates from non-human sources. The majority of the human isolates are from 2010-2020, but a few from 2021 are included. For the non-human sources the isolates were samples from 1997 to 2021.

The inventory is based on a general catalogue for all species deployed in DiSCoVeR, but a few extra metadata columns were included specifically for STEC (for human cases: "Age group", "Disease" and for non-human isolates "Import"). In addition, we added O-group, H-type, presence of stx1 and/or stx2 and eae based on results from an analysis done per partner either by serotyping, PCR or WGS. Main sources groups included can be seen from Figure 1.

Figure 1. Number of STEC isolates included per source group.

The need for further sampling of other sources than food-producing animals has been highlighted throughout the project, and new screening and sampling have been performed for STEC with focus on pets, wildlife and environmental samples. However, due to COVID-19 some sampling was cancelled or delayed meaning that we did not obtain all the data from non-livestock, non-food sources as initially expected. Still, the data we did manage to collect represent one of the most comprehensive datasets for STEC available globally!

STEC WGS data

A total of 3570 STEC sequences was collected. Most of these were also included in the overall STEC inventory described above. A pipeline for harmonized WGS analysis was created by ISS and included assembly, serotype (O:H), 7-gene MLST, stx subtyping, virulotyping and screening for AMR genes as well as cgMLST. The result files were shared and data merged with the metadata. The assembly files were available for all partners in the project. After rigorous quality check, the final inventory consists of 3418 good quality sequences. All sequences had $\geq 80\%$ of loci covered based on the cgMLST scheme.

WP2-T5- Data collection: AMR (M25-48)

All *E. coli* ESBL strains recovered from livestock, pet, wildlife, zoo animal, human, food or environmental samples collected by partner institutions during the period 2013-20 and identified using antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) and/or detection of ESBL genes. No WGS data were collected. Overall, information on 10674 isolates was retrieved originating from Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal and Spain. The provided information included the isolate ID, year of isolation, institute, country of origin, source information (including source group, subgroup and sample type), whole genome sequence status, AMR typing (including method and minimal inhibitory concentration) and ESBL genes presence, though not all data was available for all isolates. The isolate data information represented the years 2013 and 2020, with 2016 being the year

with most isolates (n=2,278, 21%), followed by 2018 (n=1,708, 16%) and 2017 (n=1,593, 15%). The isolates were organized in seven source subgroups: livestock (n=9,445, 88%), human (n=711, 7%), environment (n=470, 4%), wild animals (n=103, 1%), pets (n=26, <1%), fruit/vegetables (n=7, <1%) and zoo animals (n=2, <1%). The majority of the isolates (~93%) had information on their AMR phenotypes (mostly based on MIC testing), and in a large proportion of the dataset the presence of ESBL genes was assessed using molecular methods (mostly PCR-testing). Approximately half of the isolates (51%) carried at least one blaCTX-M gene, 10% a blaTEM gene and 8% a blaSHV gene.

In addition, information about antimicrobial resistance genes (ARG) is available from the WGS data of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and STEC, but we have not had time within the project to explore ARG data for the purpose of source attribution.

WP3: Methods: Assessment/improvement (M25-54)

In this WP, monthly web meetings were held to discuss progress and preliminary results. These were terminated in May 2022, as activities progressively moved to WP4.

Deliverable (D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2) on evaluation of SA methods was completed and the report uploaded to Zenodo. In the report, the so-called TRACE framework was applied to evaluate the various models identified through a scoping review.

WP3-T1- Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on microbial subtyping (M25-54)

and

WP3-T2- Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on phylogenetic data (M25-54)

As it turned out, there was considerable overlap between the objectives and activities of T1 and T2, and we consequently merged the two tasks, which will therefore be reported collectively.

Models based on WGS data

A Danish dataset of *Campylobacter* sequences collected from humans, animals incl. pets, foods and environments from 2015-2017 has been used for model development. Data were processed through different bioinformatics pipelines to obtain 7-loci MLST, cgMLST, wgMLST, SNPs and Kmer data. All these genomic output data have been explored in different source attribution models using machine learning (ML) to identify any host-associated genetic (groups of) markers. The different models were assessed with regard to accuracy and number of human cases that they would be able to predict. The best method was applied to more recent data from Denmark (2019-2020) and to the full multi-country *Campylobacter* dataset (Table 3). A network approach using both cgMLST, wgMLST and SNP based data has also been applied (Wainaina et al., 2022). Based on the clusters identified by this method, a Bayesian model was subsequently applied.

Table 3. Results of the multi-country attribution model based on cgMLST data input and a machine-learning approach including genomes from 3,058 human and 3,692 animal, food and environmental samples.

Multi-country model

	Denmark	France	Ireland	Netherland	Poland	Portugal	Spain	Sweden		
Broiler_chickens	1034 33,87%	75 2,46%	159 5,21%	221 7,24%	72 2,36%	143 4,68%	152 4,98%	43 1,41%	1 899	62,20%
Cattle	204 6,68%	40 1,31%	34 1,11%	192 6,29%	-	-	47 1,54%	-	517	16,93%
Dogs	14 0,46%	11 0,36%	-	106 3,47%	-	11 0,36%	-	-	142	-
Ovine	-	-	-	102 3,34%	-	-	-	-	102	-
Turkeys	-	-	-	45 1,47%	-	17 0,56%	21 0,69%	-	83	2,72%
Pigs	8 0,26%	1 0,03%	-	23 0,75%	12 0,39%	5 0,16%	10 0,33%	-	59	1,93%
Layer_chicken	-	-	-	50 1,64%	-	-	-	-	50	-
Sewage_wastewater	-	-	-	23 0,75%	-	-	21 0,69%	-	44	1,44%
Cats	-	-	-	34 1,11%	-	-	-	-	34	-
Surface_freshwater	-	7 0,23%	-	-	-	19 0,62%	-	-	26	-
Wild_birds	-	5 0,16%	-	12 0,39%	-	-	-	6 0,20%	23	-
Production environment	21 0,69%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	21	-
Agricultural_water	-	-	-	20 0,66%	-	-	-	-	20	-
Ducks	15 0,49%	-	-	10 0,33%	-	-	-	-	15	-
Recreational_water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	-
Other_wild_mammals_not_ruminants	-	-	-	-	-	-	7 0,23%	-	7	0,23%
	1 296 42,46%	139 4,55%	193 6,32%	838 27,46%	84 2,75%	195 6,39%	258 8,45%	49 1,61%	3 052	100,00%

A comparison of source attribution methods using a sample of 280 *Campylobacter* isolates from human cases and animal/environmental sources in the Netherlands using STRUCTURE, BEAST and a Random Forest methods on core-genome SNPs, gene presence absence data and cgMLST data was conducted. The three methods show slightly different attribution estimates, with the Random Forest method showing a noticeable lower attribution to the environment using both genetic sources, cgMLST representing the core genome and gene presence absence representing the accessory genome. Although there is no golden standard, the output of each method was compared with the majority vote. In this dataset, it seems that STRUCTURE based on cgMLST data slightly outperforms the other methods as it most often agrees with the majority vote.

Similar modelling as described for *Campylobacter* is also being performed for *Salmonella* sequences i.e. applying cgMLST in STRUCTURE and different ML-models. The results of these analyses are reported in WP4.

On selected datasets of human and animal/food/environmental sequences of *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium* and its monophasic variants, *S. Infantis*, *S. Newport* and *S. Derby* from 5-9 countries depending on the serovar, a ML approach using random forest (RF) or Logitboost to perform source attribution was applied. Both cgMLST and wgMLST profiles were retrieved and used as model inputs (features) after imputing missing data. For all models, non-human sequences from 5-12 primary source categories (broilers, layers, cattle, sheep/goat, pigs, ducks, turkeys, horses/donkeys, dogs, cats, other pets, other poultry) were used for model training (90%) and testing (10%). Overall, the different modelling approaches agreed wrt the most important sources for each serovar (*S. Enteritidis*: layers, followed by broilers; *S. Typhimurium*: pigs; *S. Infantis*: broilers and pigs; *S. Newport*: Reptiles and cattle). The wgMLST approach generally resulted in a higher accuracy (better performance), which is believed to be due to its higher discriminatory power. This on the other hand also led to more human cases that the models could not attribute to any source i.e. more cases with unknown origin.

Deliverable D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.1 “Describe novel approaches for source attribution using microbial subtyping” summarises the different WGS-based approaches developed.

Models based on phenotypic data

For *Salmonella*, the Dutch frequency-matching model based on serovars only was applied to all the available data. Attributions were performed overall, per country and year for the top-5 serotypes that were common to all four countries, namely *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, the monophasic variant of *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis* and *S. Stanley*. A ‘moving sum’ of the source isolates over the years was used so that the attribution of human cases caused by a specific serotype in a given year was based on the source isolates of that specific year and the year before. For STEC, a Bayesian approach was applied using the distribution of O-serogroup and virulence genes as input data for a model for four countries.

Also for ESBL *E. coli*, a Bayesian model for German data was developed using the distribution of ESBL-genes, phylogenetic groups and resistance patterns as input. There were insufficient data to make a multi-country model. The results of these phenotypically-based models are briefly described under WP4.

WP3-T3- Evaluation of microbial subtyping source attribution by infectious disease modelling (M25-54)

In this task, a method for evaluating the quality of source attribution based on subtyping was developed. Three evolving bacterial metapopulations were simulated including active migration between the metapopulations over time using the BactMeta software (<https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty093>) with variable migration rates between 2 of the populations (A and B). Samples were drawn from these at variable sampling fractions according to a Dirichlet distribution to generate synthetic human case data where the sampling fractions represent the attribution fractions that a source attribution model estimates. The synthetic data was submitted to the asymmetric island model (<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1000203>) to predict the sampling fractions. The association between the migration rates between A and B and sum of the error between the observed and expected attribution fractions was estimated by linear regression and summarized in parallel Tukey boxplots. The results indicated that the predictions of the asymmetric island model had median error of approximately 2% and largely were not impacted by migration between metapopulations. However, where resultant degree of overlap between the metapopulations due to migration was considered, an increasing error was detected with increasing overlap between the populations. For each 1% increase in overlap, the error in the prediction increased by 4.5% ($P < 0.001$). This indicates that this model performed well in spite of potential unobservable migration of bacteria between animal population, but there may be a limit to its utility, if the pathogens in the animal populations become too uniform (i.e., moving towards a homogenous distribution of subtypes/clones). This work is presented as an R package to make it possible for others to test other candidate source attribution models here: <https://github.com/trosendal/sourceSim>.

WP3-T4- Assessing and developing approaches for source attribution of antimicrobial resistance based on metagenomics (M25-54)

A paper ([Duarte et al., 2021](#)) describing the metagenomics-based source attribution methodology was recently published by one of the partners (but related to another EU financed project). We were unfortunately not able to obtain relevant metagenomic data from the general human population to test the model adequacy in the source-attribution of AMR for non-occupationally exposed humans. Data from the Dutch population exist, but we were not allowed to use the data in the project.

Between February and May 2022, a Master student explored in detail the outcome of the study by Duarte et al. during an internship at DTU. Genomic antimicrobial resistance signatures for each reservoir, previously identified with a SIMPER analysis, were investigated including 1) the distribution of abundance of 15 signatures by reservoir; 2) Principal Component Analysis using the 15 signatures, to investigate sample clustering according to reservoir and how each genomic signature explained data variance; 3) All-Subsets Regression for each reservoir, to determine the best combination of variables (antimicrobial resistance genomic determinants) for an outcome (a reservoir category) - in this case, all 15 signatures were included in the best variable combinations. The results of these three steps confirmed that the 15 previously identified reservoir-specific resistome signatures largely contributed to distinguish between four animal reservoirs (broilers, pigs, calves and turkeys).

Next, the outcome of the previously performed SIMPER analysis was compared with a non-linear method, a random forest model, which allows attributing single resistomes to one of the four reservoirs. The same data from the study of Duarte et al. were used, including 479 samples of resistomes of four animal reservoirs, spanning relative abundance of 390 genes. Data were split into 80% training and 20% test, the model tuned with 300 trees, with 5 times 10-fold cross-validation. The

model had an accuracy of 0.97 (MCC), and most incorrect attributions were between broilers and turkeys.

The model performance was assessed in three different ways: 1) testing with shuffled outcomes – as expected, the performance of the model markedly decreased and the MCC value was negative, indicating that the original model was learning from the data; 2) testing with the 15 worst variables from the model (variables with the least predictive importance). Since there were 127 genes that the model considered as zero important, 15 random genes among those were selected to test the model. The model performance markedly decreased, indicating that feature importance was not random; 3) testing with 2 testing sets, one with the 15 SIMPER-determined resistome signatures, and another with the 15 most important features according to the random forest model. Although some overlap was observed between the two sets of 15 AMR determinants, that overlap was not total, indicating that different sets of reservoir-specific resistome signatures may be determined depending on the method applied. However, the results showed that model performance (MCC) achieved with resistome signatures, either those determined by SIMPER or by Random Forest, was always higher than that achieved with other sets of randomly selected AMR determinants.

Future step will be to investigate the specific importance of selected resistome signatures by simulating their reservoir-specific relative abundance in a random forest model. The intended outcome of this task is a methodology to determine and validate reservoir-specific resistome signatures to be used in AMR source-attribution.

Also in relation to this task, INIAV and DTU were granted a STM addressing the use of metagenomics for source tracking in aquaculture. The STM was conducted in February 2022, during which INIAV explored the use of the random forest approach to attribute the source of AMR found in aquaculture (sediment) samples (n=34) to different aquatic environments. The conclusion was that although the model appeared to predict the samples' origin quite well, considerable more samples from more sites are needed for an assessment of model performance.

WP3-T5- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on case-control study results (M25-48)

A systematic literature review of recently published (2011-2021) case-control studies of sporadic *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* infections has been conducted. The merging of the this new systematic review with previous reviews followed by an overall meta-analysis using Bayesian evidence synthesis methods is also done and results summarised under WP4.

A methodological paper “A statistical modelling approach for source attribution meta-analysis of sporadic infections with foodborne pathogens”, outlining the approach used in WP4 to combine attribution estimates from different sources, has been published.

WP3-T6- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on data from reported outbreak investigations (M25-48)

Milestone in M33 (M-JRPFZ-1-06): Methods for source attribution based on outbreak data evaluated was met. Outbreak data for this task was requested from EFSA, which released the data in M40. Modelling for *Salmonella* is completed and results are summarised in WP4.

WP3-T7- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on Risk-assessment (M25-45)

A review of existing comparative exposure assessment (CEA) models was completed in M38 (M-JRPFZ-1-18).

For the CEA approach, data for all DiSCoVeR partner countries are incomplete or non-existent. For a comparative exposure assessment to be “comparative”, it needs to include several sources or to be performed in different regions/countries, which would also be in line with the spirit of OHEJP projects.

It was therefore decided that a reasonable approach would be to perform an exposure assessment for a specific source for which we expected to find only few microbiological typing data, i.e., pets like dogs and cats. The pet-CEA were performed for all target pathogens in different countries that had available data. The resulting exposure estimates were compared between the countries, and it was investigated whether possible differences are also reflected in the attribution estimates obtained by the other methods. The models included available national data on the numbers of dogs and cats and the pathogen prevalences in dogs and cats received from partners. Results are summarised in WP4.

WP4. Results – Quantifying the contribution of various sources of foodborne zoonoses and AMR (M30-56)

In WP4, data collected in WP2 and the methods assessed/developed in WP3 are used to quantify the contributions of the main sources of the target pathogens. Results are presented per pathogen, attribution method, type of data and, when/if applicable, geographical region/country. The results of applied methods for each pathogen are compared in the light of data availability and robustness, underlying uncertainties, the point in the food production chain where source attribution takes place, and the usefulness of different methods to answer different One Health questions.

A plan for which models to apply for each pathogens was agreed upon at a meeting on February 15, 2021. At the same meeting, persons/groups responsible for data management and modelling, respectively, for each pathogen-model combination were identified.

As an activity of interest for all tasks within WP4 and in collaboration with WP2 and WP3, we worked together to define a minimum set of (meta)data to be collected to perform source attribution in a meaningful way. A document was prepared and shared with all partners. This document was integrated in the milestone M-JRP FBZ-1-07 (Format for results presentation (standard structure) for all pathogens and AMR).

WP4-T1- Salmonella source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-54)

The specific activities of this task are structured as follows:

1) Attributions based on **microbial subtyping**, which include frequency-based models based on phenotypic subtyping data and machine-learning approaches based on WGS data.

The frequency-based models are based on serotyping data and target four countries (the Netherlands, Portugal, Czech Republic and Denmark, as examples of respectively Western, Southern, Eastern and Northern Europe). Only for these countries were serotyping data from both human and source isolates covering the whole 10-year study period (from 2010 to 2019) available for the project. Overall, 14,009 non-outbreaks and non-travel-related human salmonellosis cases (i.e. the sporadic and domestic cases) from the four countries together over the whole 10-year time period were mainly attributed to pigs (26.5%, 95%CI 19.4-33.6%), followed by layers (22.2%, 95%CI 15.6-28.7%), broilers (14.6%, 95%CI 6.8-22.3%), cattle (12.9%, 95%CI 8.9-16.9%), vegetables (11.4%, 95%CI 2.4-20.3%), seafood (6.8%, 95%CI 4.1-9.4%), turkeys (2.5%, 95%CI 1.3-3.6%), the environment (1.8%, 95%CI 1.0-2.6%), sheep and goats (0.8%, 95%CI 0.5-1.2%), while the other sources accounted together for only 0.6% of cases. Due to the much larger number of cases from the Netherlands and Denmark, the aforementioned ranking of sources was mainly determined by the attributions of these two countries. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

The population-genetic model, STRUCTURE, was applied to cgMLST data. Data for six serovars were included in the analyses: 1) Enteritidis, 2) Typhimurium, 3) Typhimurium monophasic variant, 4) Infantis, 5) Derby and 6) Newport. A separate model for each serovar was built. Analyses were first performed overall and then stratified by the country, where the human cases occurred. This latter analysis included England and Wales, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Denmark, although not all these

countries had sequence data available for all six serovars. The source with the highest attributable percentage for each serovar was found as follows: *S. Enteritidis*: Laying hens/eggs (>50% of cases), *S. Typhimurium*: Pigs/pork (>60%), *S. Infantis*: Broilers (>60%), *S. Derby*: Pigs/pork and cattle/beef (around 60%), and *S. Newport*: Ruminants (>60%). Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

Different approaches were applied to a multi-country dataset for five serovars selected based on occurrence in humans and non-human sources. cgMLST derived from sequences (WGS) from 1,021 human cases and 2,527 animal, food and environmental samples were used as input to a machine learning model using the random forest algorithm. The overall results showed that more than 60% of *S. Enteritidis* cases can be attributed to the laying hen reservoir. For *S. Typhimurium* and its monophasic variants, more than 60% of human cases can be attributed to pigs/pork. For *S. Infantis*, more than half of the cases was linked to broilers/chicken meat and for *S. Derby* around 50% of cases were estimated to come from pigs/pork. Finally, reptiles (+/- 30% of cases) were estimated to be the most important source of *S. Newport* infections, although closely followed by the cattle reservoir. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

2) Analysis of **Salmonella outbreak data** based on national data reported to EFSA's outbreak database from 2015-2019. In total, data from 1,508 *Salmonella* outbreaks reported across 34 countries were provided. Of these 1,040 (69%) were caused by simple foods and 468 (31%) by 'unknown' sources. The most important source of human salmonellosis in EU was eggs, followed by pork. Regional, temporal and serotype-associated differences in the relative contributions of the different sources were observed with eggs being the dominant source in Eastern and Southern EU, pork gained more importance in Northern and Western EU. Salmonellosis outbreaks appeared also to have increased during the study period, particularly for *S. Enteritidis* outbreak in Eastern Europe. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

3) **Meta-analysis of case control data** was performed and updated a previous systematic review. A systematic review of articles published between 2011 and 2021 was performed using a standardized process to review literature and select relevant articles using the key-terms: *Salmonella* (salmonellosis), Case-control, Sporadic and Risk Factors. From 1464 identified references, four articles were deemed fit for data-extraction and were included in this review. Information on the frequency of mentioning and estimated odds ratios was collected. The extracted data were merged with data from a previous review and meta-analysis was conducted. The main transmission pathway of sporadic salmonellosis was estimated to be food preparation, accounting for 14.5% (95%CI 13.3%–15.5%) of cases, closely followed by food consumption (13.2%, 95%CI 12.0%–14.5%) and water consumption (14.6% 95%CI 13.2-16.1%). The overall 'food- and waterborne transmission route' accounted for about 53% of cases. Of the other (non-food or waterborne) transmission routes, contact with animals accounted for 14.7% (95%CI 13.6-16.3%), followed by the environment (5.7%, 95%CI 4.8-6.6%). Foreign travel (7.7%, 95%CI 6.6-8.7%) and predisposition (11.7%, 95%CI 10.4-13.2%) were also important, while occupational exposure accounted for 7.6% (95%CI 5.3-10.5%) of cases. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

4) **Exposure assessment** (pets only, but all target pathogens). The goal of this analysis was to estimate the relative exposure of humans to pathogenic and antimicrobial resistant bacteria due to (in)direct contact with cats or dogs, as compared between countries, using two approaches. The General Exposure Indicator, which is the ratio of the number of dogs or cats to the number of humans in a country, gives a relative, non-bacterium specific, quantitative exposure estimate, which showed clear variation and differences between countries. The Bacterium Exposure Indicator is the ratio of the number of bacterium-specific infected dogs or cats and the number of humans in a country, and this gives a relative, bacterium-specific, quantitative exposure estimate. The uncertainty introduced by the dog/cat prevalence data, and its availability, implies that only a limited number of differences between countries could be found for the Bacterium Exposure Indicator. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

Discussion and conclusions for the *Salmonella* results.

Findings confirmed already well-established links between sources and human infections

- “Surprises” included
 - the apparent importance of horses/donkeys for *S. Enteritidis* infections as found in the STRUCTURE model, which may be explained by data from these sources being primarily from clinical cases, and that the directionality of infections is unknown i.e., these animals may as well have been infected by humans
 - Some disagreement between model as to whether reptiles or ruminants were the most important reservoir for *S. Newport* infections. In general, though, a low attribution confidence for many human cases was observed, particularly for those allocated to ruminants.
- The most important source for sporadic cases is pigs and pork products, whereas for outbreak-related cases it is eggs and products thereof.
- In the meta-analysis, the ‘food- and waterborne transmission route’ accounted for around 53% of cases, with pork being the single most important food source. Contact with animals was estimated to stand for around 15% of cases.
- Prevalence data from pets (dogs and cats) are very scarce making it very hard to draw any conclusions based on the comparative exposure assessment. Based on the other approaches, dogs and cats appear to be of minor importance, but these results are also based on relatively few data compared to the number of samples from other sources like livestock and food.

WP4-T2- *Campylobacter* source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-54)

Like in the previous task, specific activities have been defined:

1) Attribution based on **microbial subtyping**, which include the machine-learning approaches and population genetic models (STRUCTURE) based on WGS data.

A machine-learning model applying cgMLST as input data was developed. The dataset consisted of 6,750 *Campylobacter jejuni* sequences from eight countries. Of these, 3058 were collected from human cases and 3692 from different animal, food and environmental sources. Separate national models and a multi-country model were developed. Not surprisingly, broilers/chicken meat came out as the most important source in all countries ranging from 34% of cases in the Netherlands to 81% in Denmark, followed by the cattle reservoir (range: 0% in Poland to 18% in the Netherlands and Spain). Overall results from the multi-country model is presented in Table 3 and discussed in detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.2.

The population-genetic model, STRUCTURE, was also applied to the *Campylobacter* cgMLST dataset. The results were very much in line with these from the ML-approach with attribution estimates for *C. jejuni* as follows: Broilers/chicken meat around 56%, the cattle reservoir 18%, the environment and pets each 8%. For *C. coli*, the estimates were: Broilers/chicken meat 63%, environment 10%, pigs 9%, turkeys 6% and wildlife 5%. Results are presented and discussed in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.2.

2) **Meta-analysis of case-control data** to update systematic reviews (please see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1). A systematic review of articles published between 2011 and 2021 was performed using a standardized process to review literature and select relevant articles using the key-terms: *Campylobacter* (campylobacteriosis), Case-control, Sporadic and Risk Factors. From 620 identified references, five articles were deemed fit for data-extraction and were included in this

review. Information on the frequency of mentioning and estimated odds ratios was collected. The extracted data were merged with data from a previous review and a meta-analysis was conducted. The main transmission pathway was estimated to be food consumption, accounting for 22.9% (95%CI 22.2%–23.6%) of cases, followed by food preparation (16.0%, 95%CI 15.5%–16.6%) and water consumption (9.7% 95%CI 8.9-10.5%). The overall ‘food- and waterborne transmission route’ accounted for about 53% of cases. Of the other (non-food or waterborne) transmission routes, the environment accounted for 15.1% (95%CI 14.4-15.9%), followed by contact with animals (8.9%, 95%CI 8.5-9.4%). Foreign travel (11.9%, 95%CI 10.9-12.9%) and predisposition (7.8%, 95%CI 7.3-8.4%) were also important, while occupational exposure and person-to-person transmission accounted for a minor proportion of cases (3.6%). Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.2.

3) **Exposure assessment** (pets only). Please, see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1. Results are presented and discussed in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.2.

An analysis of **outbreak data** was not included for *Campylobacter* because the scarcity of documented *Campylobacter* outbreaks would make such an analysis not very useful.

Discussion and conclusions for the *Campylobacter* results.

- All applied source attribution approaches confirmed broilers/chicken meat to be the most important source, although varying across countries and also depending on the amount of data available from other sources
- The role of the environment and other non-livestock sources, such as wild animals, seemed larger for *C. coli* compared to *C. jejuni*, but broilers were still the most important source across countries
- In the meta-analysis, the ‘food- and waterborne transmission route’ accounted for approximately 53% of cases, whereas overall meat consumption accounted for around 60% of food-related cases. Eating out was the most important risk behavior related to food consumption. Environmental transmission was estimated to account for 15% and contact with animals for 9%
- Prevalence data from pets (dogs and cats) are very scarce making it very hard to draw any conclusions based on the comparative exposure assessment. Still, the risk-based models confirmed some of the country-specific results from the other models e.g. that exposure from dogs was higher in the Netherlands than in Poland

WP4-T3- STEC source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-56)

Specific activities include:

1) Attribution based on **microbial subtyping**, which include frequency-based models based on phenotypic data (O-serogroups, virulence genes, etc.), machine-learning approaches based on WGS data, and population genetic models (STRUCTURE).

The data that fed the **frequency-matching source attribution model** consisted of 5,801 Shiga-toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC) human isolates and 1,751 non-human isolates (from animal, food or environmental samples) coming from 11 European countries collected between 1997 and 2021. The original Danish model was modified to include a total of four dimensions, to account for sampling year and country, as well as subtype and source, for each isolate to be attributed. The subtype was defined as the combination of O-serogroup, stx and eae. This was done for the more prevalent STEC serogroups namely O157 and O26, with the complete combination of the three genes. For other STEC isolates not belonging to these serogroups, we looked at the O-serogroup and at the presence/absence of stx2 only. We included in the analysis only those countries with STEC data covering both humans, animals, food and environment, i.e., Italy, Netherlands, Norway and the United Kingdom. We also considered

the animal/vegetable/environmental types (e.g., cattle, green leafy vegetables, surface water, etc.). The model attributed a total of 3,668 STEC isolates from human cases. Five-hundreds and eight human isolates were not attributable to any source because the combination of O-group and virulence genes were not found in any of the non-human sources. The majority of cases were attributed to cattle and ruminants in all the countries. Italy showed a more heterogeneous distribution of cases over all the sources, including some cases attributed to environmental sources. Results are presented and discussed in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.3.

For the **machine-learning approach** using random forest, we applied a total of 3,403 STEC genomes from across 11 countries (Denmark, UK, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Czech Republic, Ireland and the Netherlands) and encompassing 85 serotypes. Of the 3,403 sequences, 2,405 originated from human cases (from 6 countries: Denmark, UK, the Netherlands, Italy, Norway, Portugal) and 998 from different animal, food and environmental sources that were categorized in 10 different source groups. Results of the overall model indicated that the largest fraction of the human sequences were attributed to cattle (68.5%), followed by sheep and goats (16.5%), and deer (11%). However, the class predictions were based on the class with the highest probability, which on occasions was higher than several other class probabilities by only a small margin making such results less certain. The attribution estimates for the different sources of human STEC isolates by country are reported confirmed cattle as the most important source in each of the countries, and the ranking of the other sources largely followed the overall one as well. An exception can be seen for Denmark in which the second most important source appeared to be deer instead of sheep and goats. Attribution estimates were also broken down by age group, which again confirmed cattle as the first source in all age groups, but somewhat higher (around 80%) in the youngest age group (0-4 years) compared to the older groups (60-70%). The ranking of the other sources largely followed the overall one. Results are presented and discussed in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.3.

Within the subtyping approaches, we also applied cgMLST data in the population-genetic model, **STRUCTURE**, as for the *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*. The model was run overall and for each of the six countries reporting human data. As source data were sparse, we included all available for all the models meaning that human cases in one country could be allocated to a source originating from another country. Overall, the cattle reservoir came out as the most important source responsible for around 76.2% of cases. This was followed by “Other wild ruminants” (around 10.4%), where samples from reindeer comprised a considerable part. The model also gave a signal for “Wild boars”, particularly in Italy (8.4%). It should be stressed, however, that the credibility intervals around the estimates in general were quite large. Results are presented and discussed in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.3.

A pangenome analysis was also performed, which identified a series of genes associated with human or animal isolates, and within the latter groups with livestock and wild animals. These genes can be seen as indicators of host specificity and could be exploited in further source attribution analyses.

2) Analysis of data from **Meta-analysis of case-control studies** is extracted from recent work available through another project done by one of the partners (Mughini-Gras et al., 2018). The results are based on a single Dutch case-control study, where the estimates were further combined with estimates from an expert elicitation study. The results showed that the main transmission pathway of sporadic STEC was food preparation (37%), followed by travel (20%) and contact with animals (19%). Within the food consumption pathway, the risk factor with the highest attribution was consuming beef or lamb (65%), followed by pork (9%). For further details see D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.3.

3) **Analysis of outbreak data** is also not included, because there are already recent work available through another WHO-related project led by one of the partners (Pires et al., 2019). This global study provide estimates for the WHO European region that indicates “beef” and “vegetables and fruit” as the most important sources each contributing to around 30% of human cases.

4) **Exposure assessment** (pets only). (Please, see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1). Results are presented and discussed in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.3.

Discussion and conclusions for the STEC results.

- Both the subtyping modelling approaches and the meta-analysis of case-control studies confirmed the cattle reservoir including beef consumption as the most important source
- In children < 5 yr. cattle contributed to around 80% cases. In older age groups and adults, other ruminants gained relatively more importance ($\approx 20\%$)
- The role of the environment and other non-livestock sources, such as wild birds, only had a small impact, although other wild ruminants such as reindeer seems to contribute with around 10% of cases. Wild boars despite the few sequences also signalled some importance in e.g. Italy
- Prevalence data from pets (dogs and cats) are very scarce making it very hard to draw any conclusions based on the comparative exposure assessment, but there were no obvious differences between countries. As dogs and cats were not included in the other approaches, it was not possible to compare results

WP4-T4- AMR source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated (M30-56)

Specific activities include:

1) Attributions based on **microbial subtyping**, more specifically a frequency-based model of ESBL based on the distribution of AMR determinants was developed for German data (Perestrelo et al., 2022). The results highlighted person-to-person transmission as important source of ESBL-EC for humans themselves, and provided quantitative estimates for the contributions of several animal sources of ESBL-EC to humans. Similar results were obtained in the past in the Netherlands (Mughini Gras et al., 2019) as part of the OHEJP project RADAR. Generally consistent outcomes were obtained when exploring different ways to define the subtypes used in the models. The study also highlighted the need for harmonized laboratory protocols for typing of isolates from different sources. A multi-country ESBL-EC gene database is also made available for source attribution through the DiSCoVeR project as described in WP2. However, the present database poses challenges, as it is largely skewed towards non-human data, and country-specific datasets including both major animal/food categories and humans are only available in a very few countries. Conditional to further collection of relevant data, a multi-country attribution analysis may be achieved, at least for North-Western Europe. A summary of the results can be found in D-JRPFBZ-1-WP4.4.

2) A multidirectional dynamic risk model for ESBL-*E. coli* (EC) transmission between broiler flocks, broiler farmers, and the open community has been developed and was parameterized for the Netherlands. This model was used to describe the transmission of ESBL-EC within and between populations including modelling of the flock-to-human transmission via food consumption due to contamination at the slaughterhouse and/or during food preparation. The colonization of the open community could primarily be attributed to the open community itself (62%), followed by vegetable consumption (29.5%), and contact with farmers (8.5%). What-if analysis to explore the effect of interventions directed at different points in the food production chain on the ESBL-EC prevalence in the open community indicated that interventions aimed at reducing the spread of ESBL-EC at primary production level, i.e. within broiler flocks, were most effective. These results are published (de Freitas Costa et al. 2022) and summarised in D-JRPFBZ-1-WP4.4.

3) **Exposure assessment** (pets only). (Please, see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1). Results are presented and discussed in D-JRPFBZ-1-WP4.4.

Discussion and conclusions for the AMR/ESBL results.

- Overall, the studies highlighted the importance of human-to-human transmission as a source

of ESBL-EC (and possibly AMR in general), and provided attribution estimates for several animal sources

- A multi-country ESBL-EC database is provided, which with a relatively few additional human data could allow for a multi-country attribution model, at least for North-Western Europe
- The multi-directional model indicates that intra-species transmission contributed most to ESBL-EC prevalence in both humans and broilers
- This model can also be used to explore the effect of interventions in the livestock sector or food production, where interventions aimed at reducing within-flock prevalence in broiler farms appeared most effective
- Prevalence data from pets (dogs and cats) are very scarce making it very hard to draw any conclusions based on the comparative exposure assessment. Although, dogs and cats were found to contribute to the number of human ESBL cases in NL in other approaches, it is difficult to compare results

WP5: Conclusions and policy translation (M32-60)

WP5-T1- Technical expert evaluation (M41-57)

Based on the work and deliverables from WP1-4, we discussed and agreed on the following overall conclusions for the DiSCoVeR project:

- Quantifying the role of the environment, wildlife and pets as sources for human infections remains a challenge complicated by bi/multi-directional transmission and data scarcity. Some planned studies addressing these sources and reservoirs were cancelled or delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, whereas those performed in general only contributed with few data points making interpretation difficult.
- Despite this uncertainty, our findings clearly identify livestock populations as the main reservoirs for all target pathogens except for ESBL, where human-to-human transmission seems to be more important. From a risk assessment point of view, particularly, *Salmonella* in pigs and pork and *Campylobacter* in broilers and chicken meat stand out as the main sources, where targeted future control and intervention could be implemented to reduce the burden of human infections significantly.
- Although some discrepancies between model results were observed, most could be explained with differences in model assumptions, inputs and parametrisation, and the majority of the analyses pointed to the same direction in terms of main sources providing credibility to both the results and the model approaches used.
- Application of WGS-based data for attribution holds some clear advantages with regard to model specificity, but they are resource demanding and require specific technical expertise, time and computer capacity, and phenotypic and/or epidemiological models may, in some instances, provide results that are just as useful for the risk managers.
- Using metagenomics for AMR attribution is a very promising approach to an otherwise wicked challenge. However, it need to be explored how it works on resistomes obtained from the general population, which were unfortunately not available for the project.
- A collection of standardised datasets from several countries and time periods provide more robust results and makes it possible to observe trends that are otherwise difficult to see including effects of control and prevention efforts.

The above conclusions and final recommendations mentioned below (WP5-T3) are also presented deliverable D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.2 and D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.4, which have been combined to a single document aimed at stakeholders and decision makers. This report describes the DiSCoVeR project's main results, conclusions and recommendations. At the time of finishing this final report, the D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.2+WP5.4 was still not completed. Expected publication date is January 2023.

WP5-T2- Translating source attribution estimates into options for control policies (M33-58)

An online stakeholder workshop was held on January 22, 2021. Around 20 participants from EFSA, ECDC, EURLs, other relevant EJP projects, as well as DiSCoVeR WP-leads joined the meeting. A follow-up meeting, where we presented and discussed the projects results was held November 17th, 2022. Here invited stakeholders included ECDC, EFSA, EC SANTE, and the EURLs.

A Master student enrolled at DTU has in collaboration with ISS addressed the deliverable D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.1: Map of the current existing control programme and intervention strategies to mitigate the risk of transmission of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC, and antimicrobial resistance to human at the EU and national level. This task was addressed by i) a scientific literature review (completed), ii) a review of grey literature (completed), and iii) a survey aimed at relevant national experts (completed, being reviewed). The survey was distributed through the OHEJP network and EFSA's zoonosis network. DG SANTE and EFSA were informed about the survey and provided their endorsement as well as their help to distribute the survey. The MSc student handed in her thesis in June 2021 and an abstract was selected for oral presentation at the OHEJP ASM on June 9-11, 2021, in Copenhagen. A summary of the literature review and the overall results of the survey was submitted as deliverable D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.1 in M48.

At the final stakeholder meeting with participants from ECDC, EFSA, EC SANTE, and the EURLs and held on November 17th, 2022, we received important input from stakeholders and at the time of finalising this report, we were preparing deliverable D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.3, which will be comparing data available through ECDC and EFSA surveillance, data made available for DiSCoVeR, and 'ideal' data needed for source attribution. Expected publication date is January 2023.

WP5-T3- Final recommendations in a OH frame (M49-60)

The line of thinking behind One Health is by no means a new concept (Evans and Leighton, 2014). In fact it can be traced as far back as to the time of Aristotle, and the concept has during the last decade been defined by different organisations in slightly varied versions (see text box below). Recently, the major players i.e., the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the World Health Organization (WHO) agreed to a new operational definition of One Health proposed by their advisory panel consisting of members representing a broad range of disciplines in science and policy-related sectors. This new One Health definition states: "One Health is an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the **health of people, animals and ecosystems**. It recognizes the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and inter-dependent. The approach mobilizes **multiple sectors, disciplines and communities** at varying levels of society to work together to foster well-being and tackle threats to health and ecosystems, while addressing the collective need for clean water, energy and air, safe and nutritious food, taking action on climate change, and **contributing to sustainable development**". Importantly, "animals" include both domesticated species and wildlife, and the previously used term "environment" is now changed to ecosystem health, which also addresses biodiversity. One Health is, therefore, also to be concerned with the impact and consequences of anthropogenic activities such as climate change, deforestation, overharvesting and pollution.

Despite the clear definition and presumably good intentions, there seems still to be an unbalanced focus on human health and health of livestock i.e., animals with a clear economic value, when it comes

to One Health initiatives within foodborne diseases. Obviously human health and livestock have very central roles for foodborne diseases, as we could also conclude from our gap analysis, where we found that the vast majority of surveillance and control activities are still within these domains with very limited activity in other areas e.g., wildlife and the environment. However, as we have also shown, wildlife do play a role in disease transmission and sustainment of disease as reservoirs, even if they do not directly comprise a major source of human infections, which is also supported by other studies (Mughini-Gras et al., 2016; Mulder et al., 2020a; Mulder et al., 2020b). In addition, and because most samples are from livestock and foods hereof, the estimated importance of e.g., cattle as a reservoir for *Campylobacter* and STEC may to some extent reflect a proxy for some environmental contamination that is not directly monitored. For instance, we did find that when otherwise not well-monitored sources were included in the models (e.g., solipeds, wild ruminants, wild boars, fruit and vegetable, and reptiles), their relative importance as a source for human infections tended to be associated with the number of included samples. This was especially observed for the subtyping source attribution

DEFINITIONS OF ONE HEALTH

'One Health is the collaborative effort of multiple health science professions, together with their related disciplines and institutions – working locally, nationally, and globally – to attain optimal health for people, domestic animals, wildlife, plants, and our environment.'
One Health Commission

'A collaborative, international, cross-sectoral, multidisciplinary mechanism to address threats and reduce risks of detrimental infectious diseases at the animal-human-ecosystem interface.'
Food and Agriculture Organization

The **World Organisation for Animal Health**, while not specifically defining One Health, endorses the approach as 'a collaborative and all-encompassing way to address, when relevant, animal and public health globally. This collaboration should not be limited to only the international level, but must be translated as a new and fundamental paradigm at national levels'.

'One Health' is an integrated, unifying approach to balance and optimize the health of people, animals and the environment. The approach mobilizes multiple sectors, disciplines and communities at varying levels of society to work together. This way, new and better ideas are developed that address root causes and create long-term, sustainable solutions.

The World Health Organisation

The **One Health Initiative** considers One Health to be 'a worldwide strategy for expanding interdisciplinary collaborations and communications in all aspects of health care for humans, animals, and the environment'.

The **One Health Global Network** considers that the aim of One Health is to 'improve health and wellbeing through the prevention of risks and the mitigation of effects of crises that originate at the interface between humans, animals and their various environments'.

The **One Health Committee of the World Small Animal Veterinary Association** comments that 'One Health or One Medicine proposes the unification of the medical and veterinary professions with the establishment of collaborative ventures in clinical care, surveillance and control of cross-species disease, education, and research into disease pathogenesis, diagnosis, therapy and vaccination. The concept encompasses the human population, domestic animals and wildlife and the impact that environmental changes ('environmental health') such as global warming will have on these populations.'

*Adapted from
Gibbs (2014) | Veterinary Record | 85*

approaches, where a larger number of isolates/sequences generally resulted in more subtype diversity within a source, thereby increasing the probability of matches with subtypes found in humans. The observed results are therefore to some extent biased by the number of isolates available.

To address some of these issues and fill identified data and surveillance gaps, a strengthening of the One Health reporting of foodborne disease and zoonoses could be considered by increasing the focus on selected environmental reservoirs, and fruit and vegetables. However, traditional sampling of these sources for foodborne pathogens may not be very cost-effective. Several studies including some that are part of DiSCoVeR have collected many hundreds samples with only a few positive findings. Hence, development and application of "smarter" approaches are needed, for instance monitoring of relevant indicators, like the quality of drinking water is monitored for faecal contamination and not specific pathogens. Making use of infrastructure from other national or EU monitoring programs not related to food safety could also be an option to increase efficiency and potentially optimise resources.

We, therefore, propose to **increase transdisciplinary research collaboration** including e.g. experts working with wildlife conservation and environmental protection both at national and EU level. A first step would be to identify possible areas of synergy including (existing) monitoring of indicators of wildlife and environmental health that may also be of value for monitoring zoonoses and foodborne diseases. An example of a novel way of monitoring water, and fruit and vegetables could be metagenomics analyses looking for species-specific faecal contamination (Bernard et al., 2021). A call

for public participation in data collection (e.g. dog owners submitting dog-poo collecting bags, hunters sampling game, etc.) could also be explored.

Further research studies to understand the transmission pathways including the **directionality of transmission** are also needed for most of the foodborne pathogens and in particular for *Campylobacter*, STEC, and AMR in pathogens and commensals. The fact that we generally do not know the baseline of environmental contamination makes it very hard to interpret the findings done in limited studies and put the results in context to food safety and human and animal health in general. Studies on environmental contamination with *Campylobacter* in the Netherlands suggest that wild birds and poultry contributes significantly to the contamination of surface water, but their respective contributions vary with livestock densities (cattle and poultry) in the area, water type and season (Mughini-Gras et al., 2016; Mulder et al., 2020).

Integrated surveillance is a cornerstone in One Health and can provide the foundation for doing source attribution analyses to directly support public and veterinary health and not just as an ‘academic’ exercise. In Denmark, for instance, integrated surveillance of *Salmonella* has for many years been used to produce the ‘annual *Salmonella* source account’, which’s results support the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration in deciding on new or revised surveillance and intervention activities (Wegener et al., 2003; Anonymous, 2020). Integrated surveillance combined with burden of disease estimation, source attribution analyses, and risk assessment has previously been promoted as a powerful tool to prioritise effective prevention and control of zoonoses and foodborne disease (Havelaar et al., 2007). Burden of disease methodologies support a comparison and prioritisation between different diseases or risk factors by quantifying the burden using a common metric (DALYs). Source attribution analyses identify the most important sources and transmission routes of the diseases allowing for targeted intervention. Risk assessment helps identifying the best (combination of) options for intervention and can be combined with cost-effectiveness analyses. Finally, when intervention has been implemented, source attribution analyses can support an evaluation of the effect of intervention.

An integrated approach, however, requires new modes for collaboration that integrates frameworks and methods beyond traditional research, veterinary and public health disciplines and also involves relevant competent authorities, policy makers, industries, and other members of the community. To accomplish this, future training of the general workforce currently dealing with specific smaller and isolated parts of a One Health system must transcend individual disciplines to provide a deeper understanding of other disciplines and how these are connected to the One Health system in question. Based on the collaboration and research done in the DiSCoVeR project, we propose that transfer of the source attribution approaches and implementation of the results creates an opportunity to strengthen the **institutional capacity building** for One Health. Such capacity building activities should promote increased network-collaboration and training within integrated surveillance including source attribution approaches, burden of disease methodologies, and risk assessment. System thinking and mapping could also be an important part of such training by providing methodologies for thinking and applying knowledge holistically (Matthiessen et al., 2022). For many years, the dominating scientific approaches have relied on splitting complex issues into smaller pieces to understand them (Monat and Gannon, 2015). This “dissective” thinking has clear advantages, but also involves the risk to overlook potentially important associations between system components and missing out on opportunities to generate novel solutions to complex problems. Applying system thinking in a One Health context, therefore, makes a lot of sense and is increasingly being encouraged (Léger et al., 2018; Ruegg et al., 2018; Matthiessen et al., 2022).

Improved One Health surveillance should also be facilitated by **increased and easier data sharing** including an increased level of detail regarding the individual samples. As discovered in this project, the current minimum data required for member states (MS) to report are not sufficient for source attribution or any detailed analysis of trends. For example, many MS do not report serotyping or other subtyping information even, if the information exist.

Barriers for data sharing are many. Some are technical challenges associated with datasets becoming increasingly larger and more complex, but also several economic, legal, and political barriers make sharing health-related data difficult (Schwalbe et al., 2020). Ideally, all relevant data and information between human, food, animals, and environmental sectors should be shared. This may require a change in legislation making it mandatory to share certain types of data. Such additional data could also include results from the food industry's own check programmes. Obviously increased sharing of data and the level of data detail should be controlled by legislation and still be protective of both the individual and private entities by securing anonymity and circumvent apprehensions about confidentiality. However, anonymous data with a comprehensive set of specified metadata can still be of great value for surveillance and control.

Data owners also need to be assured that it is safe to share their data and there should be transparency about the use of the data. Policies for data sharing should be clearly formulated, so that concerns about inappropriate or out-of-context use of the data is circumvented to the extent possible. Data providers may also be worried about not receiving acknowledgement, or that others will use their data to gain scientific recognition.

Data sharing is also often hampered by lack of compatibility between databases and platforms. When many stakeholders from different sectors are to share data, the infrastructure need to accommodate easy sharing, preferably so that data only have to be reported in one place.

Shared **data should be FAIR** i.e., the data should meet the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (Wilkinson et al., 2016). As we discovered through our project, data that we could have made good use of were available, but not accessible either because the data owners did not have time to do the data extraction and anonymisation, or it would take too long to get the permissions to share the more raw data. The former reason lead to another important point about the **value of data sharing** – or put in another way: “what’s in it for me?” If those collecting and owning the data are not themselves in need of data from other sources, why should they use time and energy to share their data? This is a valid reason and may only be overcome by data-sharing policies requiring certain data to be shared.

The overall value of data sharing in the scientific community builds on the logic that data sharing encourages more connection and collaboration between researchers, which can result in important new findings within a field. Furthermore, it allows sharing of resources, which should increase efficiency of public funds invested in research, surveillance, and control. However, data sharing requires a great deal of effort, resources, and collaboration. Preparing data to be shared takes time and careful documentation. When data providers (e.g. diagnostic labs, microbiologists) and data users (e.g. epidemiologists, risk assessors) differs, the need for or prioritisation of data sharing may differ, thereby impeding data sharing.

It is becoming increasingly more common that scientific journals require that data used in a publication is shared openly. This is definitely a major step in the right direction as it is putting focus on data sharing. However, much of the data shared in this way is not the raw data actually collected or used in the study, but rather processed/aggregated data shared in specific formats and not easily combined with other data sources for use in for instance new research studies. An exception to this is the public archives for sharing sequence data e.g., the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). Here raw sequence data are shared in a standardised format with a minimum set of metadata, and although the accompanying metadata not always have sufficient detail or the interpretation can be ambiguous, the principle of a common repository with standardised data is commendable and should be extended to other types of data relevant for One Health surveillance.

2.9.4 Project self-assessment

In the DiSCoVeR project, we have collected comprehensive and standardised datasets for the target

pathogens (*Salmonella* (n=145,000 isolates; s=4,185 sequences), *Campylobacter* (n=5,361 isolates/sequences), STEC (n=7,552 isolates; s=3,418), and ESBL (n=10,674 isolates)) and made the phenotypic and metadata open accessible through Zenodo. The sequence data (WGS) will be available at ENA through an umbrella project.

We have filled knowledge and data gaps regarding potential sources of foodborne zoonoses by including available data on non-livestock reservoirs and non-food sources. We had expected more data from wildlife and the environment, but particularly because of COVID-19, some planned studies were either cancelled or delayed to an extent that the sampling results were not available for the modelling work.

We have critically assessed and improved existing source attribution models and developed new phenotypic and genomic based models for pathogen and antimicrobial resistance for attribution. We have applied the attribution approaches to quantify the contributions of animal reservoirs, including wildlife and companion animals, food and environmental sources, and we have compared and discussed the results across methods. In addition, we have proposed a method for evaluating the quality of source attribution based on subtyping to better understand the underlying mechanisms and improve the characterisation of the sources and transmission pathways implicated in the epidemiological cycles of the hazards.

We have provided recommendations on the translation of results from source attribution models in to actions, emphasising that *Salmonella* in pigs and pork and *Campylobacter* in broilers and chicken meat stand out as areas, where targeted future control and intervention could be implemented to reduce the burden of human infections significantly. We have also evaluated current surveillance and control activities in a One Health context and made recommendations for improvement by seeking out (further) collaboration and identifying possible surveillance synergies within the environmental/ecosystem pillar of One Health, as surveillance and research focus currently is very much oriented towards human health and food-producing animals. Finally, we have evaluated transfer of the source attribution approaches as an opportunity to strengthen the institutional capacity building for One Health by promoting increased network-collaboration and training within surveillance, source attribution approaches, burden of disease methodologies, and risk assessment activities.

The project partners agree that the DiSCoVeR project have made very good progress and achieved almost every aim and objective. Partners have worked towards common goals with very little 'silo' work. Most tasks have been completed through collaboration between many partners that have met regularly to discuss progress. Particularly, the collection and sharing of data have required intensive communication not only between partners, but also with external collaborators contributing with valuable data (e.g., the National Wildlife research institute in Spain (IREC) and the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA)).

The comparative application of several models/approaches has proved to be very insightful and can help decision making and priority setting. When results from different models converge, we get more 'confidence' in both the results (i.e. that the targeted sources are the right ones) and the approaches. In contrast, when results diverge, a critical appraisal is undertaken to investigate the extent to which the results are more the result of the data (e.g., imbalanced data) or the methods used (e.g., model assumptions), which often lead to recommendation on further research activities including additional data collection or model development.

Other important lessons learnt concern the data collection and sharing. Agreeing on and collecting standardised data across countries and domains was very time consuming. It required the signing of a Material and Data Transfer Agreement (MDTA) among all partners, as well as external collaborators, where the latter were identified later in the project requiring an amendment. Once data were collected from many different sources and providers, resources were used to sort and manage the data to make them ready for analyses. Making the DNA sequence data publicly available also turned out to be a very time-consuming task, as some sequences already were at ENA, meaning that they were not identified

as being part of the project, whereas others needed to be uploaded as part of the project. In order to associate all the sequences used in the project, a so-called umbrella project will be created at ENA. However, this can only be done, when all data owners have uploaded the remaining sequences and provided the ENA accession numbers.

This whole data management process evolved gradually during the project following the principle learning by doing. For future projects, it is highly recommended to have the data flow, management, and organisation sorted out as early as possible and communicated clearly to all data providers. In potential future projects and collaborations, it is also recommended to provide a standardised MDTA and data format, and a common database to share data for all EJP partners and projects.

References

- Anonymous, 2020. Annual Report on Zoonoses in Denmark 2019, National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark. <https://www.food.dtu.dk/english/publications/disease-causing-microorganisms/zoonosis-annual-reports>
- Bernard J. Phiri, David T. S. Hayman, Patrick J. Biggs, Nigel P. French & Juan C. Garcia-R (2021) Microbial diversity in water and animal faeces: a metagenomic analysis to assess public health risk, *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*, 48:3-4, 188-201, DOI: 10.1080/03014223.2020.1831556
- Duarte, A. S. R., Röder, T., Van Gompel, L., Petersen, T. N., Hansen, R. B., Hansen, I. M., ... Hald, T. (2021). Metagenomics-Based Approach to Source-Attribution of Antimicrobial Resistance Determinants - Identification of Reservoir Resistome Signatures. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 11, 601407. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.601407>
- Eduardo de Freitas Costa, Thomas J. Hagenaars, Anita Dame-Korevaar, Michael S.M. Brouwer, Clazien J. de Vos. Multidirectional dynamic model for the spread of extended-spectrum- β -lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli* in the Netherlands, *Microbial Risk Analysis*, Volume 22, 2022, 100230, ISSN 2352-3522, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2022.100230>.
- Evans BR, Leighton FA. A history of One Health. *Rev Sci Tech*. 2014 Aug;33(2):413-20. doi: 10.20506/rst.33.2.2298. PMID: 25707172.
- Havelaar, A. H., Braunig, J., Christiansen, K., Cornu, M., Hald, T., Mangen, M. J. J., ... Wahlstrom, H. (2007). Towards an integrated approach in supporting microbiological food safety decisions. *Zoonoses and Public Health*, 54(3-4), 103–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1863-2378.2007.01036.x>
- Léger A, Stärk KDC, Rushton J and Nielsen LR (2018) A One Health Evaluation of the University of Copenhagen Research Centre for Control of Antibiotic Resistance. *Front. Vet. Sci*. 5:194. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2018.00194
- Matthiessen, L. E., Hald, T., & Vigre, H. (2022). System Mapping of Antimicrobial Resistance to Combat a Rising Global Health Crisis. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 816943. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.816943>
- Monat JP, Gannon TF. What is systems thinking? A review of selected literature plus recommendations. *American Journal of Systems Science* 4, 11-26 (2015).
- Mughini-Gras, L., Penny, C., Ragimbeau, C., Schets, F. M., Blaak, H., Duim, B., ... van Pelt, W. (2016). Quantifying potential sources of surface water contamination with *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli*. *Water Research*, 101, 36–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.05.069>
- Mughini-Gras, L., et al., Attributable sources of community-acquired carriage of *Escherichia coli* containing beta-lactam antibiotic resistance genes: a population-based modelling study. *Lancet Planet Health*, 2019. 3(8): p. e357-e369.
- Mughini-Gras, L., et al., Attribution of human infections with Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) to livestock sources and identification of source-specific risk factors, The Netherlands (2010-2014). *Zoonoses Public Health*, 2018. 65(1): p. e8-e22.

Mulder, A. C., Franz, E., de Rijk, S., Versluis, M. A. J., Coipan, C., Buij, R., ... Mughini-Gras, L. (2020a). Tracing the animal sources of surface water contamination with *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli*. *Water Research*, 187, 116421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.116421>

Mulder, A. C., van de Kasstelee, J., Heederik, D., Pijnacker, R., Mughini-Gras, L., & Franz, E. (2020a). Spatial effects of livestock farming on human infections with shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* O157 in small but densely populated regions: the case of the Netherlands. *GeoHealth*, 4, e2020GH000276. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GH000276>

Pires SM, Majowicz S, Gill A, Devleeschauwer B. Global and regional source attribution of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* infections using analysis of outbreak surveillance data. *Epidemiol Infect.* 2019 Jan;147:e236. doi: 10.1017/S095026881900116X. PMID: 31364563; PMCID: PMC6625198.

Perestrelo, S., et al., Comparison of approaches for source attribution of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* in Germany. *PLoS One*, 2022. 17(7): p. e0271317. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0271317>

Rüegg SR, Nielsen LR, Buttigieg SC, Santa M, Aragrande M, Canali M, Ehlinger T, Chantziaras I, Boriani E, Radeski M, Bruce M, Queenan K and Häslér B (2018) A Systems Approach to Evaluate One Health Initiatives. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 5:23. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2018.00023

Schwalbe N, Wahl B, Song J and Lehtimäki S (2020). Data Sharing and Global Public Health: Defining What We Mean by Data. *Front. Digit. Health* 2:612339. doi: 10.3389/fdgth.2020.612339

Wegener HC, Hald T, Wong DL, Madsen M, Korsgaard H, Bager F, Gerner-Smidt P, Molbak K, 2003. Salmonella control programs in Denmark. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, July;9(7):774-80.

Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, Blomberg N, et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data*. 2016 Mar 15;3:160018. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18. Erratum in: *Sci Data*. 2019 Mar 19;6(1):6. PMID: 26978244; PMCID: PMC4792175.

2.9.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
20	D-JRP20-1.1	Mapping of knowledge gaps and recommendations for new data generation and method development	M28	M33	Uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5825542#.YdcJyWjMKUK	1/5
20	D-JRP20-1.2	Data Management Plan	M30	M35	The DMP can be found here	3
20	D-JRP20-2.5	Database/sharing platform solution established	M36	M42/M48	Confidential – only partners has access to the WGS data selected for the project. By the end of the project, all data used for peer-review papers will be uploaded to ENA. Some of the data used are already at ENA. A short document describing the data-sharing platform is uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5828337#.Ydh0XGjMKUK This deliverable was compiled in December 2021, but the data-sharing platform was available from June 2021.	5
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP2.6	Description of data generated for Salmonella, Campylobacter, Shigatoxin-	M48		Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5828412#.YdmekGjMKUK	3/5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		producing E. coli (STEC) and their AMR determinants				
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.1	Describe novel approaches for source attribution using microbial subtyping	M49	M51	https://zenodo.org/record/6365186#.Yq4ONHZByUk doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6365186	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2	Report on the critical and quantitative evaluation of existing and novel source attribution methods	M51	M51	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/6365057#.Yq4ONHZByUk doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6365057	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1	Salmonella source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method	M54	M55	Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7058181	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.2	Campylobacter source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated	M54	M56	Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7058216	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.3	STEC source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated	M56	M57	Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7396784	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.4	AMR source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated	M56	M56	Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7303549	2
20	D-JRP20-5.1	Map of the current existing control programme and intervention strategies to mitigate the risk of transmission of <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , STEC, and antimicrobial resistance to human at the EU and national level.	M42	M48	Public. Delayed due to COVID. https://zenodo.org/record/5812282#.YdhU42jMJPY	1
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP5.2	Document: Transmission pathways of <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , STEC, and antimicrobial resistance from animals, food, and environment to humans: One-Health characterisation of the source and components and options to inform control policies.	M57	M61	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7575742#.Y9ZqE3bMJJaR	7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
20	D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.3	Document: translation of the source attribution methodological approach to the One-Health context for surveillance of Salmonella, Campylobacter, STEC, and antimicrobial resistance: options, needs, prioritization.	M58	M61	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7576299#.Y9ZqVHbMJar	7
20	D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.4	Final conclusions and recommendations for the use of source attribution approach into One-health framework for surveillance and control of Salmonella, Campylobacter, STEC, and antimicrobial resistance	M60		This deliverable is merged with D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.2.	7

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
20	M-JRP20-01	Identification of Project Management Team	M25	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-02	First annual project meeting	M27	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-03	Completion of mapping of knowledge gaps and recommendations for new data generation and method development	M28	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-04	Identification of types of samples to investigate and for which species to include in the sampling	M29	Yes, M32	
20	M-JRP20-05	Framework for evaluation of Microbial subtyping methods	M33	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-06	Methods for source attribution based on outbreak data evaluated	M33	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-07	Format for results presentation (standard structure) for all pathogens and AMR	M33	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-08	Mapping of data available for Salmonella	M34	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-09	Mapping of data available for Campylobacter	M34	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
20	M-JRP20-10	Mapping of data available for STEC	M34	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-11	Mapping of data available for AMR	M34	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-12	Protocol for presentation of results for Salmonella, Campylobacter, STEC and AMR	M34	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-13	Framework for using phylogenetic data for source attribution	M51	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-14	Comparison of data and methods for each pathogen and AMR	M36	Yes, M38	
20	M-JRP20-15	Framework for using metagenomic data for attribution of antimicrobial resistant	M39	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-16	Results from evaluation of microbial subtyping methods using artificial data	M54	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-17	Description of method of source attribution using existing case-control	M42	Yes	
20	M-JRP20-18	Method for source attribution by risk assessment evaluated	M42	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
20	M-JRP20-19	Second annual project meeting hosted by ANSES	M41	No	Cancelled
20	M-JRP20-20	Completion of control programme and intervention strategies mapping	M41	Yes, M48	
20	M-JRP20-21	Update of Data Management Plan	M41	Yes, M49	
20	M-JRP20-22	Completion of data collection	M42	Yes	
20	M-JRPFZ-1-23	Completion of dataset for all species	M50	Yes	
20	M-JRPFZ-1-24	Third annual project meeting hosted by ISS	M57	Yes	
20	M-JRPFZ-1-25	Stakeholder Workshop	M57	Yes	
20	M-JRPFZ-1-26	Final update of Data Management Plan	M60		Delayed – awaiting upload of remaining sequence data to ENA. Expected completed by February 2023.

2.9.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
V. Lopez-Chavarrias, M. Ugarte-Ruiz, M. C. B. Asensio, A. Olarra, M. Garcia, J.L. Saez, C. De Frutos, T. Serrano, I. Perez, M.A. Moreno, L. Domínguez, J. Alvarez Monitoring of Antimicrobial Resistance to Aminoglycosides and Macrolides in <i>Campylobacter coli</i> and <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> from healthy livestock in Spain (2002-2018) doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.689262 https://zenodo.org/record/5109549#.YUyflgzZMO		Yes		Yes
Lapo Mughini-Gras, Elisa Benincà, Scott A. McDonald, Aarieke de Jong, Jurgen Chardon, Eric Evers, Axel A. Bonačić Marinović (2022). A statistical modelling approach for source attribution meta-analysis of sporadic infection with foodborne pathogens. https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12937 https://zenodo.org/record/6365098#.Ynkcy-hBxwQ		Yes		Yes
Pinedo, L. C., Mughini-Gras, L., Franz, E., Hald, T., & Pires, S. M. (2022). Sources and trends of human salmonellosis in Europe, 2015–2019: An analysis of outbreak data. <i>International Journal of Food Microbiology</i> , 379, 109850. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2022.109850		Yes		Yes
Eduardo de Freitas Costa, Thomas J. Hagenaars, Anita Dame-Korevaar, Michael S.M. Brouwer, Clazien J. de Vos. Multidirectional dynamic model for the spread of extended-		Yes		Yes

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
spectrum-β-lactamase-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> in the Netherlands, <i>Microbial Risk Analysis</i> , Volume 22, 2022, 100230, ISSN 2352-3522, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2022.100230 .				
Perestrelo, S., et al., Comparison of approaches for source attribution of ESBL-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> in Germany. <i>PLoS One</i> , 2022. 17(7): p. e0271317. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0271317		Yes		Yes
Pista A, Silveira L, Ribeiro S, Fontes M, Castro R, Coelho A, Furtado R, Lopes T, Maia C, Mixão V, Borges V, Sá A, Soeiro V, Correia CB, Gomes JP, Saraiva M, Oleastro M, Batista R. Pathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> spp. and <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. in Two Natural Conservation Centers of Wildlife in Portugal: Genotypic and Phenotypic Characterization. <i>Microorganisms</i> . 2022 Oct 27;10(11):2132. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms10112132		Yes		Yes
Batista R, Saraiva M, Lopes T, Silveira L, Coelho A, Furtado R, Castro R, Correia CB, Rodrigues D, Henriques P, Lóio S, Soeiro V, Costa PM, Oleastro M, Pista A. Genotypic and phenotypic characterization of pathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> spp. and <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., in free-living birds in mainland Portugal.	Submitted	Yes		Yes (1.200€; to be paid in 2023)

Additional output

Abstracts from the ASM One Health EJP 2021 and 2022:

- Sara Perestrelo, Guido Correia Carreira, Lars Valentin, Jennie Fischer, Yvonne Pfeifer, Guido Werner, Judith Schmiedel, Linda Falgenhauer, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "Source Attribution of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* in Germany" Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP 2021, 9-11 June, Denmark and online.
- Guido Correia Carreira, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "Mapping knowledge gaps of source attribution methods and sources for zoonoses and resistant bacteria using a rapid review approach". Oral presentation held at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Rebekka Sørensen, Tine Hald, Gaia Scavia, Michele Luca D'errico. "MAPPING THE CURRENT EXISTING HAZARDS' CONTROL PROGRAM AND STRATEGIES IN THE VARIOUS SECTORS AND TRACTS OF THE ANIMAL-ENVIRONMENTFOOD-HUMAN CHAIN IN EU". Oral presentation held at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Mónica Oleastro, Maria Leonor Lemos, Alexandra Nunes, Paulo Martins da Costa. "A PRELIMINARY STUDY OF *CAMPYLOBACTER* SPP. IN DOGS IN PORTUGAL – A ONE HEALTH PERSPECTIVE". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Ana Amaro, Célia Leão, Patrícia Themudo, Lurdes Clemente. "EMERGENCE OF MULTIDRUG RESISTANT *SALMONELLA* *INFANTIS* ST32 IN THE POULTRY INDUSTRY, PORTUGAL 2016-2020". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Leonor Silveira, Sofia Ribeiro, Iúri Lopes, Mariana Fontes, Rita Castro, Frederico Lemos, Angela Pista. "Prevalence and characterization of *Salmonella* spp. and pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in food-producing animals in Portugal". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645807>.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Rita Batista, Anabela Coelho, Rosália Furtado, Teresa Lopes, Isabel Moura, Margarida Saraiva, Carla Maia, Cristina Belo-Correia, Iuri Lopes, Leonor Silveira. "Prevalence and characterization of pathogenic *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in wild animals in mainland Portugal". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645848>.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iuri Lopes, Leonor Silveira. Phenotypic and Genotypic Characterization of *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in Pets, Portugal 2019-2020 – A ONE HEALTH Perspective. Poster presentation at ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, 11-13 April, Orvieto, Italy and online.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7341735>.
- Michele Luca D'Errico, Rebekka Aarlund Sørensen, Tine Hald, Gaia Scavia. Mapping control programmes to mitigate the risk of human exposure to *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC and antimicrobial resistance through animals, food and the environment: an experts' survey. Oral Communication at ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, 11-13 April, Orvieto,

Italy and online.

- Ornella Moro, Sara Pires, Camilla Sekse, Rosangela Tozzoli, Gaia Scavia, Lapo Mughini-Gras. Exploring Shiga Toxin-producing E. coli sources in European countries through classical attribution methods. Poster presented at ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, 11-13 April, Orvieto, Italy and online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645672>.
- Lopez-Chavarrias, Vicente, Wieczorek, Kinga, Osek, Jacek, Dieguez Roda, Bernabe, Torre Fuentes, Laura, Ugarte-Ruiz, Maria, Moreno, Miguel Angel, Dominguez, Lucas, & Alvarez, Julio. (2022). Epidemiological comparison of Campylobacter jejuni isolates from Poland and Spain combining MLST and antimicrobial resistance whole genome analyses. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6637353>
- GS. Johannessen, JK. Antony-Samy, CA. Bøe, EZ. Fiskebeck, K. Lagesen, K. Madslie, J. Våge, M. Økland, C. Sekse. Occurrence of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli in wild ruminants in Norway. Presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, April 11 – 13 in Orvieto, Italy and online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7399760>

Other abstracts:

- Sara Perestrelo, Guido Correia Carreira, Lars Valentin, Jennie Fischer, Yvonne Pfeifer, Guido Werner, Judith Schmiedel, Linda Falgenhauer, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "To which extend do humans and animals share the same reservoirs of ESBL producing Escherichia coli?" Poster presentation at the Junior Scientific Zoonosis Meeting 2021, 3-4 June, online.
- Célia Leão, Ana Amaro, Patrícia Themudo, Lurdes Clemente. Insights into pESI like megaplasmid of Salmonella Infantis ST32 spreading in the poultry industry. Poster presentation at the MICROBIOTEC 2021, 23-26 November.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iúri Lopes, Rita Castro, Leonor Silveira. Detection and characterization of Enteropathogenic Escherichia coli and Salmonella spp. in cats and dogs from a Lisbon area kennel - A ONE HEALTH perspective. Poster presentation at the XVII Congresso Internacional Veterinário 2021, 22-23 October, Santa Maria da Feira, Portugal.
- Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iuri Lopes, Leonor Silveira, Angela Pista. Colistin Resistance Genes in Escherichia coli and Salmonella spp. Isolates from Pets, Wild and Food-producing Animals in Portugal, 2019-2021. Poster presentation at the 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases 2022, 23-26 April, Lisbon, Portugal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645500>.
- Lopez-Chavarrias, Vicente, Dieguez Roda, Bernabe, Torre Fuentes, Laura, Ugarte-Ruiz, Maria, Saez, Jose Luis, Moreno, Miguel Angel, Dominguez, Lucas, & Alvarez, Julio. (ISVEE 2022, August 7-12 Halifax, Canada). Mapping antimicrobial resistance markers for aminoglycosides and macrolides in Campylobacter in Spanish livestock. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6637724>
- Skarżyńska M, Zając M, Lalak A, Kwit R, Pasim P, Skrzypiec E, Wojdat D, Koza W, Mikos-Wojewoda E, Skóra M, Wasyl D. Characterisation of Salmonella Typhimurium from domestic pigeons (Columba livia domestica). International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis (IS3), June 20-22, Saint-Malo.
- M. Zając, M. Skarżyńska, A. Śmiałowska-Węglińska, R. Kwit, K. Tłuścik, A. Bomba, E. Skrzypiec, D. Wojdat, W. Koza, A. Lalak, A. Giza, E. Iwan, D. Wasyl. The phylogeny structure and molecular characterization of monophasic Salmonella Typhimurium from unhuman sources

in Poland. International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis (I3S), June 20-22, Saint-Malo.

- Bonifait L., Baugé L., Thépault A., Payne A., Kérouanton A., Denis M., Rivoal K., Pozet F., Cesbron N., Nicolle P., Gibout O., Chenoufi N., Lequeux T., Zonderland J.-L., Chemaly M. 2022. Detection and characterization of Salmonella spp. in wildlife in France. Poster presentation at the International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis (I3S), June 20-22, Saint-Malo.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iuri Lopes, Leonor Silveira. Colistin resistance genes in Escherichia coli and Salmonella spp. in pets, wild and food-producing animals in Portugal. Oral communication. 1st Egas Moniz ONE HEALTH Symposium, 3 November, Monte da Caparica, Portugal.
- Jaromir Guzinski, Yue Tang, Eva Litrup Tine Hald, and Liljana Petrovska. Improved machine learning model for source attribution of Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhimurium and monophasic variants, using whole genome MLST loci. International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis (I3S), June 20-22, Saint-Malo.
- Costa E, Hagenaars T, Dame-Korevaar A, Brouwer M, Hesp A, De Vos C, 2022. Multidirectional dynamic model for the spread of Extended-Spectrum- β -lactamase-Producing E. coli in the Netherlands. Abstract book of the 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics, August 7-12, 2022, Halifax, Canada. Pp. 85.

Scientific reports:

- Eric Evers (RIVM, The Netherlands), Annemarie Käsbohrer (BfR, Germany). “Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on risk assessment”, OHEJP DISCoVer WP3-T7, milestone M-JRPFZ-1-18, 10 February 2021.
- Mayu Horie. “Application of Machine Learning in source attribution of foodborne bacteria”, MSc student research project report, Utrecht University, The Netherlands.
- Charlotte Onstwedder “Risk-factors for human Campylobacteriosis and Salmonellosis in Europe (2011-2021): a rapid review”, MSc student research project report, Utrecht University, The Netherlands.
- Teunis, Gijs “Salmonella source attribution using machine-learning” MSc student research project report, Utrecht University, The Netherlands.

Master theses:

- Bækken, M.S. Occurrence of Shiga-toxin producing Escherichia coli in minced meat and meat from pork in Norway (In Norwegian). MSc Thesis, May 2021, Norwegian Veterinary Institute in collaboration with the Norwegian University of Life Sciences (<https://nmbu.brage.unit.no/nmbu-xmlui/handle/11250/2826335?locale-attribute=en>).
- Brinch, M. L. [Development of a WGS-based source attribution model for Campylobacter](#). MSc Thesis, June 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.
- Sørensen, R. A. Mapping the currently existing hazards’ control programmes and strategies in the various sectors and tracts of the animal-environment-food-human chain in EU/EFTA/EEA. MSc Thesis, June 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.

- Wang, B. Development of a WGS-based source attribution model for Salmonella. MSc Thesis, September 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.
- Azevedo, M. Isolation and characterization of Campylobacter spp. from surface and recreational waters. Supervised by Mónica Oleastro (National Institute of health Dr Ricardo Jorge) and Mário Ramirez (Faculty of Medicine, University of Lisbon), MSc Thesis, in preparation, Portugal.

Related publications:

- Wainaina, L.; Merlotti, A.; Remondini, D.; Henri, C.; Hald, T.; Njage, P.M.K. Source Attribution of Human Campylobacteriosis Using Whole-Genome Sequencing Data and Network Analysis. Pathogens 2022, 11, 645. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11060645>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

In the DiSCoVeR project, we have collected **comprehensive and standardised datasets** for the target pathogens (*Salmonella* (n=145,000 isolates; s=4,185 sequences), *Campylobacter* (n=5,361 isolates/sequences), STEC (n=7,552 isolates; s=3,418), and ESBL (n=10,674 isolates)) and made the phenotypic and metadata open accessible through Zenodo. The sequence data (WGS) will be available at ENA through an umbrella project. We believe that these multi-country datasets compiled of isolate data and sequences from humans and various animal and food sources are quite unique and could be analysed by other methods and by other researchers to provide novel insights to the epidemiology of foodborne hazards in EU MS.

We have also made a critical and systematic assessment of existing source attribution models and developed new phenotypic and genomic-based attribution models for pathogen and antimicrobial resistance.

Based on the results, we have provided recommendations on the translation of results from source attribution models in to actions, emphasising that Salmonella in pigs and pork and Campylobacter in broilers and chicken meat stand out as areas, where targeted future control and intervention could be implemented to reduce the burden of human infections significantly. We have also evaluated current surveillance and control activities in a One Health context and made recommendations for improvement by seeking out (further) collaboration and identifying possible surveillance synergies within the environmental/ecosystem pillar of One Health, as surveillance and research focus currently is very much oriented towards human health and food-producing animals. Most of these recommendations are considered relevant for risk managers/decision makers such as ECDC and EFSA, national food, veterinary, and environmental authorities, and farmer and consumer organisations.

Finally, we have evaluated transfer of the source attribution approaches as an opportunity to strengthen the **institutional capacity building** for One Health by promoting increased network-collaboration and training within integrated surveillance, source attribution approaches, burden of disease methodologies, risk assessment, and system thinking.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

The purposes of the multidirectional dynamic risk model for ESBL-E. coli transmission between broiler flocks, broiler farmers, and the open community, and parameterized for the Netherlands, were

informed by discussions with representatives of the Dutch national authorities (Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality; Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority), and its results were discussed with them in Dec 2021 and discussion will continue in Feb 2023.

In Denmark, the WGS-based attribution models developed for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* are implemented as part of the surveillance programme to inform the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration about the effect of control and if there is need for any changes. This means that the surveillance data are applied to the models on a regular basis (every 2nd to 3rd year depending on data availability) and the results are published as part of the "[Annual Report on Zoonoses in Denmark](#)" and discussed with the authorities and the industry.

2.9.7 One Health impact

Direct and indirect impact the outcomes of your project may have for international stakeholders active in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, AMR and/or emerging threats (ECDC, EFSA, FAO, OIE, WHO-EU; EU reference laboratories, etc.)

- Approaches and models developed in this project serve as proof of concept for other zoonoses and foodborne diseases.
- Generally, surveillance data lack detail to be used for source attribution and detailed trend analysis limiting their usability.
- Making more use of baseline surveys at the EU level is a recommended approach for obtaining harmonised and comparable data that can be used for source attribution and for estimating the effect of intervention if done regularly within the same source/reservoir.
- Recommendations for harmonisation and standardisation of data including metadata such as standardised source categories and subtypes, as well as reporting all available subtyping data.
- Recommendation for an infrastructure for data reporting: Data sharing needs to be easy and data should ideally only be uploaded to one system that both data owners and users have access to at a level that they are individually cleared for.

Description of how regional or national authorities and stakeholders may implement and/or integrate any of the results from the project in their work:

- We have held two meetings for EU-level stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC, EC SANTE, EURLs), where we have received input on project progress (1st meeting) and presented and discussed our results (2nd meeting).
- Also several meetings with national authorities to disseminate the results have been held (IE, UK, DK, PT, IT, NL). In UK, meetings with all involved in EJP projects are held monthly

How did this project help building and strengthening the networking with other partners of the One Health EJP and beyond:

- IE: The Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) joining the project to also get the environment represented.
- ES: National Wildlife research institute – IREC
- IT: University of Milan, providing data from dogs and cats, and wild ruminants

- PT: National Veterinary Medical Institute, Oporto University, providing data on ESBL, Salmonella, and STEC. Use of metagenomics for AMR source tracing done in collaboration with the AquaRAM projet (AquaRAM - Antimicrobial Resistance Determinants in Aquaculture Environments ALG-01-0145-FEDER-028824) with partherns from FCIências.ID - Associação para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento de Ciências, Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA), and Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária, I.P. (INIAV).
- NO: Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), providing data on wildlife
- NL: the public health (RIVM) and veterinary (WBVR) institutes, together with the only Veterinary Faculty of the country, joined forces to generate and analyse data for the project.

2.9.8 Data Management Plan

The first draft of the DMP was prepared in November 2020 and updated in January 2022. The data inventories describing the data and including metadata are made available as Excel sheets at Zenodo. Partners have also agreed to make the WGS data open access through ENA by creating a so-called umbrella project. Currently, all sequence data are uploaded at sciencedata.dk in a password protected folder. Upload to ENA requires some organising, as some sequences that are included in DiSCoVeR already are at ENA, whereas others are not. We are currently completing pathogen-specific lists with all sequence data used in DiSCoVeR including ENA accession numbers. First when we have a final list of accession numbers, can we ask for the creation of an umbrella project, which we can then make open access. A final update of the DMP will take place, when all the WGS data used in the project have been uploaded to ENA. This is a time consuming process, which is expected to be completed by February 2023.

2.9.9 Future dissemination activities

The DiSCoVeR projects main stakeholders are the national competent authorities on food safety and public health, as well as EFSA and ECDC. During the project we have organised two stakeholder workshops inviting among others representatives from EFSA, ECDC, EC SANTÈ and the EU Reference laboratories for the targeted pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E. coli*, and AMR). The main purposes of the first workshop held in January 2021 was to give an overview of attribution models included by the project, discuss data requirements, availability, and accessibility, and the needs of the stakeholders in terms of results and input to the their work. In the second stakeholder meeting held in connection with the final project meeting in November 2022, project results were presented and discussed with the stakeholders. Focus were on future data requirements and translation of results into public health action. A summary of the results can be found in Deliverable 5.2 ([D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.2](#)).

In terms of help from the PMT regarding communication and dissemination, we have been discussing that it could be useful to take the main conclusions and recommendations from D5.2 and turn them into a 1-pager infographics that could be distributed to stakeholders and through SoMe. However, to do this properly, we think people trained within communication and desktop graphics should be involved. So, if the PMT can provide assistance with this, it would be highly appreciated.

2.10 JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE

2.10.1 Consortium composition

Project Leader: Elke Burow (BfR, DE), formerly Chris Kollas (formerly BfR, DE), Tamino Dubbert (BfR, DE)

WP1 Leader: Elke Burow (BfR, DE), formerly Chris Kollas (formerly BfR, DE), Tamino Dubbert (BfR, DE)

WP2 Leader: Richard Smith (APHA, UK), Elke Burow (BfR, DE)/occasionally Veit Zoche-Golob (formerly BfR, DE)

WP3 Leader: Wim van der Poel (WUR, NL), Live L. Nesse/Ane-Mohr Osland (NVI, NO)

WP4 Leader: Robin Simons (APHA, UK), Beate Conrady, formerly Pinior (formerly Vedmeduni Vienna, AT)

WP5 Leader: Elke Burow (BfR, DE), occasionally Veit Zoche-Golob (formerly BfR, DE)

WP6 Leader: Marie Sjölund (SVA, SE), Tamino Dubbert (BfR, DE), formerly Chris Kollas (formerly BfR, DE)

2.10.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The OHEJP BIOPIGEE project aimed at identifying effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control hepatitis E virus (HEV) and *Salmonella* occurrence in European pig farming. To achieve this, comprehensive literature reviews, field and experimental studies, expert opinion surveys and risk modelling have been used. The collated information was and continues to be disseminated to stakeholders (farmers, veterinarians, advisors) in illustrations, support tools and workshops.

During the field studies, farms and slaughterhouses were visited to look into the implementation of biosecurity measures and to take samples from pigs. The aim was to analyse associations between sample results and answers to questionnaires. For farms, a total of 264 questionnaires were received originating from nine European countries. A number of protective biosecurity measures could be identified. Additionally, data summaries were produced showing which biosecurity measures are used where at European pig farms. For slaughterhouses, the results from the questionnaire indicated that there were considerable differences between the slaughterhouses in implementation of best biosecurity practices throughout Europe. Although many biosecurity measures were in place, the results suggested areas of improvement. Either one should implement practices shown to be most effective (e.g. decontamination with hot water or steam vacuum treatment; bung sealing with plastic bag during evisceration; vertical scalding) or avoid practices shown to increase bacterial contamination of carcasses but are still used (e.g. pressure washing of carcasses at evisceration with cold water). The questionnaire was adjusted to be used as an assessment tool in European slaughterhouses.

During experimental studies the effectiveness of various disinfectants against the persistence of *Salmonella* in biofilms was studied and a HEV sampling method and infectivity test adapted for testing of HEVs in biofilm were developed. It was found that one needs at least 0.1% peracetic acid (PAA) for 10 minutes and at least 1% Glutaraldehyde (GA) for 30 minutes to successfully disinfect *Salmonella* in biofilm. For HEV, sampling with electrostatic dust collectors (EDCs) was studied. The developed sampling method is relatively easy to perform and can be executed in any laboratory without the need for sophisticated equipment. However further validation will be needed.

For modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures stochastic simulations on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures were performed and used to inform a cost-effectiveness analysis

model. The results of this analysis suggested that, assuming a 100% implementation rate, anal bunging at the slaughterhouse and organic acids in water or feed of weaner pigs on farm were the most cost-effective biosecurity measures for *Salmonella*, while none of the measures for HEV were considered cost-effective.

A literature review and meta-analysis to identify effective measures to control HEV, *Salmonella* and pathogenic *E. coli* in primary production had been performed. The measures were ranked according to their effect sizes in order to gain an impression of which measures might have the largest impact in practice.

Finally several online workshops were conducted with experts in the fields veterinary medicine, agriculture and meat industry in order to extract, inform about and discuss effectiveness of biosecurity measures and to rate country-specific biosecurity practices, as well as to exchange ideas on how to best disseminate the existent information and new information produced in BIOPIGEE.

Ideas about the content and presentation of material gathered in the BIOPIGEE project had been exchanged with a German farming education centre on how to set up the material to address farming pupils. This task is ongoing.

A guidance document is in preparation together with the publication of the findings taking into account the feedback received from stakeholders during the above-mentioned workshop.

Two tools have been developed. These are two checklist implemented as interactive Excel-Spreadsheet. The checklists are based on the benchmark system developed in the project. One checklist addresses the control of *Salmonella* on pig farms, the other deals with the control of HEV on pig farms.

Given the topics of the project and its outcomes, it may have the largest impact for EFSA. The outcomes include guidance for farmers, veterinarians, consultants and slaughterhouses in European countries in form of illustrative flyers and web content to inform stakeholders, incl. collaborating farm education centres. The material should provide reliable and cost-efficient guidance on the reduction of *Salmonella* and HEV spread in animals and humans (through occupational exposure) which add important information for monitoring and regulation in order to advance One Health.

2.10.3 Work carried out in the IRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

Note: In the following the running years of the project correspond to the running years of the OHEJP. That means that the first year of BIOPIGEE is 2020, which is the third year of the OHEJP. Therefore, the first year of BIOPIGEE is designated as “Y3” (i.e. year three of OHEJP). Correspondingly “Y4” and “Y5” correspond to the second and third year of BIOPIGEE.

WP1 Project coordination and integration of results

WP1-T1 Project management and meeting organisation

Y3 : The BIOPIGEE Kick-off meeting was organised and successfully conducted at BfR in Berlin/Germany on 29th-30th of January 2020. All participating organisations were represented, of these 41 BIOPIGEE members took part. Four quartely WP leader meetings were organised and held. The BIOPIGEE OHEJP website had been filled with content, participants were invited to join. All general, important and finalised documents had been uploaded to the page and status updates had been written. Shared documents had been set up and updated versions uploaded to the BfR cloud server. Links and passwords to open these documents were stored at the BIOPIGEE website. Thereby, data protection as well as access of only project people was ensured. Production of a BIOPIGEE flyer in WP6/ OHEJP Communication Team was supported with text modules and images.

Y4 : The BIOPIGEE Mid-term meeting took place - virtually due to the pandemic - on 2nd/3rd March 2021 (organised with APHA) where all WPs and Tasks presented their work, results, challenges and further plans which were discussed with the group. Four quarterly WP leader meetings and collaborations with other projects and institutions were arranged. An online glossary of relevant terms in BIOPIGEE had been developed between task groups in cooperation with the MATRIX project. Since several tasks of the project had been affected by the pandemic situation (farm visits, lab work, workshops), changes in the timeline of tasks and consequences for links between Tasks/WPs were coordinated. The Gantt chart and the list of due dates for deliverables and milestones were modified accordingly. In agreement with all project partners, despite budgetary consequences, a 6-month-extension of the project was requested (April '21) in order to enable fulfilment of planned tasks. The work plans of all WPs for Y5, 2022, had been modified together with WP-leaders taking a 6 months extension into consideration.

WP1-T1-ST1 Definition of biosecurity measure

A new subtask “Definition of ‘biosecurity measure’ across WPs/Tasks in BIOPIGEE” (WP1-T1-ST1- was later moved to WP5, as Task T0) was identified and initiated.

Y5 : Four quarterly meetings of the WP leaders had been arranged and held to discuss current issues. A collaboration with the HealthyLivestock project is ongoing and project outcomes had been exchanged and discussed, e.g. in workshop events. Some tasks are still being affected by the pandemic (farm visits, lab work, workshops) and changes in the schedule and organisation of tasks and consequences for links between Tasks/WPs had been coordinated. The Gantt Chart and the list of due dates for deliverables and milestones had been modified accordingly. The BIOPIGEE online glossary was updated and supplemented with the definition for “biosecurity measure” after its publication. The final meeting was organized by IZSAM (IT) and BfR (DE) and then successfully held in presence in Guilianova Italy on 6 and 7 October 2022. From 10 countries attended 36 participants of which 8 were participating online. Most participants were from the 14 partner institutions of the project. Two participants were invited, one from EFSA and one from CEVA (NL).

WP1-T2 Development of data management plan

Y3 : First, the elaboration of the data management plan was started. All WP-leaders were invited to fill the “old” xls-sheet regarding their data. Later, we were informed that the former tool DMPonline will not be supported by OHEJP any further and a search for a better tool is under way. The deadline for the first version of the DMP was delayed by the OHEJP-PMT. Hence, work on the DMP was put on hold until September 2020. Introduction to the new tool CDP for the DMP took place on September 9th 2020. Afterwards, we filled the DMP in CDP and are waiting for further instructions from OHEJP-PMT (was announced for January 2021).

Y4 : A draft of the data management plan (DMP) was developed with WP leaders and entered into the CDP-tool in 2020. From the CDP-tool, an excel sheet of the DMP was downloaded, uploaded to the BIOPIGEE website and transferred to a shared document hosted at the BfR-server. Updates made by WP leaders in the shared document in June, August, October and December 2021 were transferred to CDP.

New options to describe complex data in the DMP have become available as was informed in a training session by the DMP group in March 2021. In addition, contact information, keywords, description and file types were updated for each piece of data listed in the BIOPIGEE DMP as suggested by DMP group during 2021. The DMP will be updated repeatedly until the end of the project.

The DMP includes currently 21 different kinds of data, which are closely related to deliverables of the project. It is research data and methodologies, mainly related to pigs as focused in the project. Most of the data are intended to be published in scientific journals and are therefore confidential until publication. Location, where to find the data (e.g. website, Zenodo) is listed together with information whom to contact for each dataset (names, institutions and email addresses), which have a unique

identifier in the plan. There is little to consider for ethical aspects as data will be anonymised and no personal or identifiable data will be included. Data related keywords from ORION were selected on a drop down list in the CDP tool and are also used in the BIOPIGEE DMP. Thereby, the DMP takes into account the following aspects: data summary, making data findable, making data openly accessible, making data interoperable, increase data re-use (FAIR data principles), data dissemination, data security and ethical aspects.

Y5 : The data management plan was revised according to comments by the OHEJP WP4 DMP group at the beginning of 2022 and had been updated continuously both in a shared document in the project group and in the Lisam CDP tool. With the end of the project, the BIOPIGEE DMP comprises the description of 35 data items.

WP1-T3 Provision of project deliverables and reports

Y3 : First deliverables (questionnaire, flyer, data management plan, HEV infectivity assay) and the 9M report had been provided, via the private group and/or Zenodo.

Y4 : The publication plan for the project, arranged in a shared document, was modified to indicate the status of publications (intended, in work, submitted, accepted, published) for WP2 to WP5 and had been continuously managed. Here also references and links of finalised publications have been collated. Deliverables were continuously collected and distributed (uploaded to the private web-group and to Zenodo). Reporting was a repeated task. The annual work plan (AWP) for Y5 was amended together with the WP leaders, considering a 6-months-extension and was submitted to OHEJP coordination team (9th June 2021) and silently accepted (without any comments) by the OHEJP coordination. The 9M-report 2021 and the 12M report 2021 were prepared together with the WP leaders and delivered.

Y5 : The publication plan for the project, compiled in a shared document, had been modified to inform and exchange information about the status of publications and had been continuously managed. Deliverables had been continuously collected, checked and distributed (uploaded to the private web-group, to Zenodo and forwarded to OHEJP WP3/CommsTeam). The 9M report and the final report had been delivered.

WP2 Biosecurity effectiveness studies.

WP2-T1 Development of biosecurity protocol

Y3 : A biosecurity protocol for European pig farms was developed in order to assess the relevance of measures on the prevalence of Salmonella and hepatitis E virus. As first step, existing protocols from Europe and North America were assessed but, on evaluation, it was decided to design a new protocol specific to the needs of the project. Evidence from a literature review and expert opinions (scientists) was used to inform the content of this protocol. The biosecurity measures were reworded as questions (55 biosecurity questions for indoor, 56 for outdoor situation), and questions on general farm characteristics (10) and economic/performance factors were added.

WP2-T1-ST1 Transfer of the questionnaire into an electronic version

The questionnaire was transferred into an electronic survey tool and translated into the necessary languages of the countries participating in WP2-T2. An app for this survey was produced, set up on devices of interviewers in each of the participating countries and the function of the app and data transfer to a central server were tested, with support of WP1. This system enabled standardized data collection, and facilitated data income and evaluation.

WP2-T2 Application of the biosecurity protocol

Y3 : The developed biosecurity questionnaire was applied on pig farms in the participating countries. Farms were recruited and 59 farm visits took place in nine different countries. Incoming survey data

had been reported to the interviewers quarterly to check and prepare for later data evaluation. Pictures were taken of examples of good biosecurity practice, to add to the project documentation in work package 6.

The task was delayed due to different restrictions in EU member states related to worldwide pandemic of coronavirus disease COVID-19. NL decided not to collect fecal samples that they had planned in this task for *Salmonella* testing but instead will attempt to use results from routine meat juice sample surveillance to identify high and low risk farms. There were difficulties in all countries to visit farms and to take sample as initially planned. Although most countries started farm visits in autumn 2020, these continued to be disrupted by COVID-19 lockdowns, as well as African Swine Fever concerns, restricting access to farms and the willingness of farmers to allow access. Biosecurity data from 90 pig farms from a previous ANSES study was collected and aligned to questions within the biosecurity protocol to allow their usage in this study.

The sampling, laboratory testing and recruitment protocols were designed. Details of the HEV-testing methods were discussed between partner labs and participants of WP2-2 and WP2-T5 in order to harmonise methods as much as possible and to reach comparability of results that can also supplement the HEVnet database.

Y4 : Although COVID-19 restrictions had a large impact on the progress of the task, as of 1st December 2021, all of the planned farm visits (264) had taken place. Corresponding questionnaires had been uploaded onto the electronic data capture system from nine countries (DE, NL, CZ, PL, BG, UK, AT, IT, EE) with additional data provided by two other countries (SE and FR). Almost 4,000 samples were collected from field visits and tested for *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV). NL and EE used data from national *Salmonella* monitoring, or other sources of information, to help categorise their farms as being at higher or lower risk for these pathogens. Analysis had been completed to determine the significant associations between biosecurity measures and the risk category of each pathogen. Pictures were taken during farm visits to show case examples of good and bad biosecurity practice, to add to project documentation in work package 6.

Y5 : The analysis of the biosecurity questionnaire and HEV/*Salmonella* laboratory results was completed. Descriptive analysis of the data was carried out, with particular focus on presenting differences in biosecurity measures between farm types and participating countries/ regions. Multivariable risk factor analysis and principal component analysis have been completed to identify the most effective biosecurity measures in controlling *Salmonella* on European pig farms. These results have been shared with WP4 and WP5, so that cost-benefit analysis can be applied to the identified measures and the benchmark system can include the measures. To assess the potential effect of bias on the task 2 results, a number of sensitivity analyses were also completed, which confirmed the suitability of the multivariable risk factor model. Similar analyses have been completed for HEV . Publications are being drafted from these analyses. Additionally, a biosecurity dataset from the Republic of Ireland is being shared with the project team to allow a paper to be produced on the use of biosecurity on pig farms on almost 400 European farms in 11 countries.

WP2-T3 Slaughterhouse biosecurity practices

Y3 : This Task was planned to start at the beginning of Y4 but already started this year to collect existing national and local assessment protocols on biosecurity measures in slaughterhouses. A first virtual meeting took place in September 2020.

Y4 : An online survey was designed to collect information on best biosecurity practice in slaughterhouses. The survey took place in seven countries (DE, CZ, EE, IT, AT, UK and NL) with 32 responses. The survey included 20 questions organised into the sections general, transportation, lairage (waiting area at the slaughterhouse where arriving pigs are kept until slaughter), scalding, singeing, evisceration, carcass splitter, decontamination and chilling. The content was based on

information about biosecurity measures' effectiveness presented in peer-reviewed literature and on opinions from slaughterhouse experts within the partner institutes.

Sampling methods for visits to slaughterhouses were agreed within the team. Bacteriological samples were collected from three slaughterhouses, one in CZ and two in IT. The samples were collected along the slaughter line to help validate information on the effectiveness of biosecurity practices. The evidence from the studies had been collated into a report on the effectiveness of slaughterhouse biosecurity.

Y5 : The results from the slaughterhouse literature review, sampling visits and questionnaire survey that were collected from this study are being organised for two publications.

WP2-T4 Field studies

Y3 : The study plans for the three proposed studies were designed and the teams were in contact to assess synergies and harmonisation of techniques to improve comparison of potential findings. The overarching protocol was uploaded to the BIOPIGEE page and was thereby made accessible to the whole consortium.

Y4 : This task was largely affected by COVID-19 lockdowns in the participating countries. However, longitudinal studies were started in the UK. In NL, the research focus for this task was updated and refocused on internal biosecurity and spread of HEV between pens. A pilot study on four farms was completed, the results of which were analysed and informed the final study protocol (choice of farm and age groups to sample) for the longitudinal study. Unfortunately, recruitment in NL was delayed due to farmers withdrawing participation or being found to be HEV negative.

Y5 : In the UK, two longitudinal studies were completed to investigate the epidemiology of HEV, in particular with regards to the mixing of pigs and potential environmental reservoirs. The first trial was a two-stage breeder-finisher unit, and the second trial was a weaner-finisher unit, and both were visited four times to collect samples from a cohort of pigs, from entry onto the farm through to slaughter. The results suggested a wide range of environmental reservoirs and that earlier mixing of pigs effected the timing of the peak of prevalence in the cohort group.

In the Netherlands, two longitudinal field studies were carried out investigating the transmission rate of HEV between consecutive batches of finisher pigs in the same pens, and between pens within compartments. A secondary aim was to investigate whether PRRS pre- or co-infection influences the latent period, or the duration of infectious period of HEV in a pen of finisher pigs. Every pen was faecal sampled once a week, and serum samples were collected at the beginning and end of every batch to identify contingent HEV infection prior to the fattening stage, and seroconversion during the fattening phase. Between batches, pens were sampled post cleaning and disinfection. In the first farm, all pens were HEV negative, although boot socks of the first batch were positive in the last week prior to slaughter, demonstrating that HEV was still present on the farm and transmission was possible. On the other farm, all pens became positive, and the moment of infection in a pen was dependent on the compartment the pen is in, and presence of a positive adjacent pen. As the study is linked to a separate project, data collection is continuing beyond the end of the BIOPIGEE project and will be thoroughly analysed during the next year.

In Italy, ten farms were recruited for a study which aims to determine the effectiveness of cleaning and disinfection procedures on farms against *Salmonella* and HEV. *Enterobacteriaceae* were also enumerated to have an indication of residual faecal contamination. The study did not investigate individual cleaning regimens or disinfectant products. Samples were taken on four farms in April 2022. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the recent African Swine Fever outbreak in Italy it was not possible to recruit finisher farms as initially proposed, and therefore farrow-to-wean and weaning farms were recruited instead. Each farm was visited before and after cleaning and disinfection. All samples collected were negative for *Salmonella* and HEV; however, *Enterobacteriaceae* colony count ranged from negative to 10⁵ cfu/cm² (mL) and indicated suboptimal cleaning and disinfection in some of pens.

Three publications are planned to present the findings from these studies.

WP2-T5 Analysis of HEV prevalence and subtypes

Y5 : 266 HEV sequences from BIOPIGEE samples from seven countries were uploaded onto the HEVnet website along with relevant metadata on farm types, country of origin and biosecurity measures associated with HEV in WP2-T2. These have been used for sequence diversity analysis and assessments of association with diversity. The results will be presented in a publication.

WP3 Impact of disinfection on persistence of pathogens in biofilm

WP3-T1 Comparison of methods for testing the effect of disinfectants

Y3 : Discussion about and planning of methods and reference strains to be used by all participating laboratories had taken place.

Y4 : Parameters to compare methods for testing disinfectants effectivity were described. Reference strains to be used by all participating laboratories had been defined. Biofilm methods between labs had been compared. Methods to continue with in Task 2-ST2 had been defined. The deliverable WP3.7 “Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm” was produced and submitted in August 2021.

Y5 : This task had been finalized for using reference strains. Additional data are being produced using wildtype strains.

WP3-T2 Effect of disinfectants on biofilm-associated wild type Salmonella

Y3 : Method establishment started.

WP3-T2-ST1: Selection of wild type Salmonella isolates

Discussions about choice of the panel of Salmonella isolates, and finalisation of the method to be used to screen the isolates for biofilm forming abilities had taken place.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants

Labwork started with initial testing.

Y4 : Disinfectants and conditions and biofilm methods to be used had been defined. Wild type strains had been selected and sent to all participating laboratories.

WP3-T2-ST1: Selection of wild type Salmonella isolates

A panel of Salmonella isolated from UK pig farms had been screened for their biofilm abilities using two methodologies. From this panel, six biofilm-forming Salmonella isolates, from serovars Derby and Typhimurium, had been selected for the use in Task WP3-T2-ST2.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants

Each lab used the already locally established biofilm model for testing the effectiveness of disinfectants. Lab work started with initial testing.

Y5 : The panel on wildtype strains had been selected and shared with all partners. Disinfectant efficacy testing had been done.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants

The panel on wildtype strains had been selected and shared with all partners. Disinfectant efficacy testing had been finalized. The efficacy of two disinfectants (Glutaraldehyde and Peracetic acid) at various concentrations had been studied. The assessments were performed using three different biofilm models on wild- type strains selected in the previous sub-task.

Deliverable 3.19 had been submitted.

A Poster had been presented at Eurobiofilms 2022 (31.8.22-3.9.22, Mallorca, Spain) and a manuscript is in preparation.

WP3-T3 Study of HEV stability in relation to disinfection approaches

Y3 : Preparations were made to study the HEV stability in microfilms using appropriate HEV infectivity assays which partly had been developed in WP3-T3-ST1, and had been further implemented in Y4 (and Y5).

WP3-T3-ST1 Implementation of HEV infectivity assay for testing biofilms

A first version of the HEV infectivity assay had been completed. In this assay primary hepatocytes are isolated from liver tissue of (HEV free) piglets using a collagenase treatment. The obtained primary hepatocytes are aliquoted and stored at -180 Celsius until use. For the actual assay the hepatocytes are seeded onto plates and inoculated with different concentrations of HEV. First HEV replication plots had been established.

A second option for testing of HEV infectivity, precision-cut liver slices (PCLS) had been used. PCLS cuts had been directly transferred to an ice-cold organ preservation solution and inoculated with different concentrations of HEV and tested daily using qRT-PCR for increasing levels of HEV RNA. Single replication rounds had been observed but the method still needs optimisation.

Y4 : HEV stability in microfilms had been be studied using appropriate HEV infectivity assays which had been developed in WP3-T3-ST1, and had been further implemented in Y4 (and Y5).

WP3-T3-ST1 Adaptation and implementation of HEV infectivity assay for testing biofilms

The HEV infectivity assay was completed. In this assay, primary hepatocytes are isolated from liver tissue of (HEV free) piglets using a collagenase treatment. The obtained primary hepatocytes are aliquoted and stored at -180°C until use. For the actual assay, the hepatocytes are seeded onto plates and inoculated with different samples potentially contaminated with HEV. A second method for testing of HEV infectivity, precision-cut liver slices (PCLS) had been developed and had been used further for validation of the hepatocytes assay. Adaptations of the bioassay had been made in order to make it suitable for testing biofilms.

The deliverable WP3.6 “HEV infectivity assay is available” had been implemented further. It had been tested on field samples and had been further validated using other HEV bioassays.

The deliverable WP3.5 “Method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers” was completed.

The deliverable WP3.20 “HEV infectivity test adapted for testing of HEV in biofilms” was completed.

WP3-T3-ST2 HEV in Salmonella biofilms

We investigated whether there was a correlation between the presence of HEV and Salmonella in faecal samples of pigs. No significant correlation had been seen, however more samples need to be tested to obtain reliable outcomes. The method how to sample the environment/biofilms had been developed and tested. Electrostatic Dust Collectors (EDC) had been used to swab the environment/ biofilm. The virus had been eluated, which means adsorbed material was removed from the adsorbent, EDC, by means of a solvent (5ml of cell culture medium in this case) and tested for the presence of HEV with the use of real time PCR. In case of a positive result the sample will be grown in the HEV infectivity assay.

Y5 : Work on sub-taks ST2 and ST3 has been concluded.

WP3-T3-ST2 HEV in Salmonella biofilms

The deliverable WP3.14 “Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayer/biofilm” had been submitted.

WP3-T3-ST3 Field study of HEV and Salmonella co-occurrence at pig farms

On two different pig farms, environmental samples (291) were collected after the cleaning procedure. Samples were analysed for the presence of HEV and Salmonella in order to study if HEV may be more stable in Salmonella biofilms. Using electrostatic dust collectors, floors, walls, feed bowls and drink nipples were sampled. The wipes were processed in PBS and DNA and RNA were isolated using the pathogens kit of Zymo research. Isolates were tested for HEV and Salmonella by real-time PCR. In 171 out of the 291 samples, Salmonella DNA was detected (Ct between 29 and 38). In 15 out of the 291 samples, HEV RNA was detected of which 10 positives were in Salmonella positive samples and 5 positives in Salmonella negative samples. It was concluded that there was no significant correlation between the presence of Salmonella and HEV. An in-vitro study on Salmonella biofilms combined with an experimental HEV infection will not be conducted as this will have no added value.

WP4 Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures

Summary

In WP4 we developed models to simulate the transmission of HEV and Salmonella along the pig production chain and assessed the effectiveness of various biosecurity measures. These models were used to inform a cost-effectiveness analysis. The results suggested Anal bunting at the slaughterhouse and Organic acids in water or feed of weaner pigs on farm were the most cost-effective biosecurity measures for *Salmonella*, while none of the measures for HEV were considered cost-effective. In future, it might be worth considering the cost-effectiveness against multiple pathogens or whether targeting biosecurity measures to high-risk farms might improve the cost-effectiveness.

To simulate the transmission of HEV between farms and the prevalence in pigs sent to slaughter, a model combining complex network analysis and exponential random graph models was produced (Hammami, P. *et. al.* 2022). This model confirmed the topological stability of the network over time while highlighting the important roles of companies, types of farm, farm sizes, outdoor housing systems and batch-rearing systems. This model also investigated the effectiveness of some on-farm biosecurity measures, but found that the only factor that looked like it would have a big effect was a hypothetical measure that would reduce the prevalence of a concurrent immunomodulating virus.

This slaughter pig prevalence from the network model acted as an input to a quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA) for the slaughter to consumption phases of the pig production chain, which included modules to simulate human exposure via minced meat, liver pate and sliced liver (Wilkins, N., 2022). The QMRA output was an estimate of human HEV infection with and without biosecurity measures implemented, which informed the cost-effectiveness model. This model estimated that while HEV RNA is likely to be present in all products, only the sliced liver was likely to have sufficient infectious virus to cause human illness. For Salmonella, a pre-existing QMRA was used to simulate the impact of various biosecurity measures on human cases, to inform the cost-effectiveness analysis.

The cost-effectiveness model weighed the benefits of the estimated reduction of human cases and reduced pig prevalence against the cost of a 100% implementation rate of the biosecurity measure. Monetary values were ascribed to human salmonellosis/HEV cases by cost of illness analysis. Previously published values on the animal health impact due to *Salmonella* were assigned to pig cases. Unfortunately, lack of data did not allow the evaluation of the economic animal health impact due to HEV within the time frame of the project (see more on this and other issues encountered in WP in Section 2.10.4). Costs associated to the implementation of a biosecurity measure were evaluated

measure-specific and, if data allowed it, country-specific. The cost-effectiveness model was applied to the year 2019.

WP4-T1 Development of questionnaire on biosecurity costs

Y3 : A questionnaire with respect to health and performance data of pigs located in farms was developed which covers 24 questions. The questionnaire was delivered to the partners of WP2-T1, who used it during their empirical survey at the farm level. Questions about the costs of biosecurity were not included. The reason is that the costs of the selected biosecurity measures will be difficult and very time-consuming to answer for the farmers. Thus, the costs of the biosecurity measures will be estimated using usual country prices such as disinfection costs per litter and via monetary values from the scientific literature. This concluded WP4-T1.

WP4-T2 Stochastic simulations on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures

Y3 : Three online meetings were held to coordinate and harmonise the different tasks of 4.2 and 4.3 between the partners. In these meetings the adaption of currently available transmission models such as QMRA for Salmonella and SimInF model for HEV and/or Salmonella of the consortium partners had been discussed in order to analyse the impact of biosecurity and other mitigation measures (e.g. at the slaughterhouse) on prevalence reduction of the zoonotic pathogens. During the meetings, In- and Outputs of the models were discussed. Furthermore the data requirements for the planned transmission model were discussed. This included e.g. the type of transmission data, meta-data on the animal population like movements data of pigs, and necessary data inputs of the other WPs 2, 3 and 5 about the effectiveness of biosecurity measures and/or mitigation measures on the reduction of prevalence values.

WP4-T2-ST1 Data collection for the transmission models

Data requirements for the transmission model was discussed between the partners as well as the outputs of the single models considering different type and aggregation of input data from the other WPs. Additionally, the data requirements and their availability were discussed. The R codes of the available models were presented to each member involved in WP4. The latter procedure was necessary so that everyone has the same level of knowledge about the inner workings of the R codes and associated strength and limitation of the corresponding transmission models.

WP4-T2-ST2 Adaption of the models based on the available data

The simulation model is had been planned to run for three countries for which all data needed are available. The adoption of the models started e.g. incorporation of the effect of biosecurity measures on the spread within and between herds in the R Code.

Y4 :

WP4-T2-ST1 Data collection for the transmission models

The data collection phase for the network model was completed, but there were issues with obtaining pig movement data for some of the proposed case study countries. Data were obtained and successfully integrated into the model from France. Data were obtained from the UK, but due to data privacy issues, some data (e.g. information to identify individual farms) could not be shared. Considerable effort was put in to developing methods to allow geographical data to be used instead, but unfortunately this did not leave enough funding to fully integrate the UK data into the model and validate the results. The method is developed to allow this in the future, but the resource is unlikely to be available within BIOPIGEE. It was not possible to obtain movement data from Italy and while a potential source for similar data from Germany was identified, it was not possible to obtain the data in time.

Data collection for the QMRA continued and a number of potential gaps had been identified, particularly in relation to inactivation rates and dose-response for HEV, which we will look to resolve over the next year of the project.

Y5 : The baseline QMRA for HEV and *Salmonella* had been completed and validated. The models had been run for multiple biosecurity intervention measures. Some measures had been parametrised using prior data from published literature and some using the results of the longitudinal studies conducted in WP2. Unfortunately, due to data and resource issues it had not been possible to run the models for multiple countries, but this would be feasible in the future if sufficient data become available. This WP collaborated the colleagues developing the economic model in WP4-T4, to ensure the model outputs WP4-T2 were appropriate to act as inputs to the model in WP4-T4. For each measure, the output metric of probability of human illness was calculated. This was then compared against the baseline run to determine the effectiveness of the measure. Comparing the effectiveness between individual biosecurity measures allowed identifying which measures the model predicts to be most effective. These outputs then acted as inputs to the economic model. Deliverable WP4.17 was submitted.

WP4-T3 Merge of models into one QMRA

Y3 : Work just started at end of Y3.

Y4 :

WP4-T3-ST1 Different transmission models will be matched to one QMRA zoonotic pathogen model

Draft results of the farm-to-slaughter network transmission model with the French data had been produced, including simulations of some on-farm biosecurity interventions. This work is currently in publication process.

Despite delays due to staff resourcing, COVID-19 and outbreak response work related to avian influenza, work had done to adapt the previous Salmonella QMRA for HEV. This included developing methodology for consumption of liver as a route of human HEV infection and a methodology to simulate the inactivation of HEV during cooking of liver. Data collection had identified a number of potential gaps, particularly in relation to cross-contamination rates at the slaughterhouse, inactivation rates and dose-response for HEV.

Discussions had taken place to ensure successful integration of the network model with the QMRA at the slaughterhouse stage. A poster on this process had been presented at the 2021 OHEJP annual meeting.

Y5 : The outputs of the French network model developed by ANSES had been provided as inputs to the QMRA. This allowed for a full farm-to-consumption analysis to be done for these input data. Unfortunately, due to resource, data and logistic issues it was not possible to fully connect the models developed by different countries into one fully functional model. In particular, it proved problematic to obtain pig movement data and impossible to obtain permission to share that raw data with multiple countries in the time available for this project. As such, future use of the full model would rely on the individual institutes running their own sections.

WP4-T4 Economic model of biosecurity measures across Europe

Y4 : Work on this task had not started until M46 as the initial task leader, Beate Pinior/Conrady, left the project. A new member, Clara Bester took over this task in M47. Initial work concentrated on analysing the cost-related data collected within WP2 Task2 during the farm visits in several countries. Furthermore, a concept for the cost-benefit analysis had been developed taking into account outcomes from a literature review conducted within the COHESIVE project.

Y5 : Data from selected example countries had been collected for conducting the economic analysis by applying the concept of a Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA). Biosecurity measures for the analyses based

on the results from WP2-T2 and WP5-T2 had been selected in communication with BIOPIGEE team members from WP4-T2 and WP4-T3. The selected biosecurity measures had been individually evaluated by using the pathogen specific QMRAs. Unfortunately, due to technical and logistical issues, only one measure had been considered at a time. Costs for the selected biosecurity measures had been identified based on the initial definition of the measure in the original study from the literature, which evaluated the effect of the measure as well as consulting national guidelines and expert opinions. Additionally, cost-of-illness analysis were conducted for human salmonellosis cases as well as human HEV cases.

WP5 Benchmark of biosecurity practice

WP5-T0 Definition of biosecurity measure

Y3 – Y5: The new task “Definition of biosecurity measure” was moved from WP1 to WP5. The group developed a common understanding of ‘biosecurity measure’ across project tasks based on applied inclusion/exclusion criteria from five BIOPIGEE task groups and a literature scoping review including four scientific databases. The definition proposal was presented at the ONE-Health, Environment, society-2022 conference, and at BIOPIGEE online workshops. An article manuscript presenting and discussing the definition in detail has been published in 2022.

WP5-T1 Data integration from WP2-4 in catalogue of biosecurity measures

Y3 : With support of WP1, an online table (“BIOPIGEE: Biosecurity measures Salmonella and HEV”) was set up starting the WP5 catalogue of effective biosecurity measures for HEV and Salmonella prevalence. Data from WP2 to WP5, especially from a brief review in WP2-T1, were integrated into the catalogue. All BIOPIGEE participants were invited to supplement the BIOPIGEE catalogue of biosecurity measures. The catalogue had been updated continuously with identified biosecurity measures and estimates of their effectiveness. At the end of the project, this catalogue should represent a valuable resource for the project’s stakeholders working on food safety and the reduction of Salmonella and HEV in pork products.

Y4 : The catalogue of biosecurity measures to reduce HEV and/or Salmonella prevalence was revised to consider all relevant data from the project, to ensure consistent data and safe updates. Procedures for inputs and updates as well as backups were defined. Data was updated by the first results from WP5-T2 and WP5-T4. All BIOPIGEE participants were invited to supplement the BIOPIGEE catalogue of biosecurity measures. The catalogue had been updated continuously with identified biosecurity measures and estimates of their effectiveness.

Y5 : The BIOPIGEE catalogue of identified biosecurity measures had been filled with findings on effective measures to control HEV and *Salmonella* occurrence at different production stages in primary production and at slaughter as well as on expert opinion. This task lost the leader. The project leader asked task leaders to add their results to the catalogue organised in a shared document.

WP5-T2 Literature review/meta-analysis

Y3 : A systematic literature review about the effectiveness of biosecurity measures specifically against Salmonella and HEV in pigs farms had been nearly finished. The search question, terms, period, and in- and exclusion criteria had been defined in the group with the help of a shared online document. The articles found in literature databases had been evaluated and the extraction of the relevant data is expected to be finished in M36. Afterwards the data will be categorised and prepared for the meta-analysis. The meta-analyses will be performed for all biosecurity measures for which sufficient studies were published in order to estimate their effectiveness to reduce Salmonella- and HEV-prevalence in pig herds. As additional data, e.g. about the way of pathogen detection, productions stages and farm types, were extracted from the literature, stratified meta-analyses might be possible which will provide more targeted effect estimates. Besides providing information for the catalogue of biosecurity

measures (WP5-T1), the results of this task will be used in WP4 to parametrise the simulation models. Although it won't be possible to offer first estimates to WP4 at the end of M36, the data processing and meta-analyses had been done in close consultation with WP4 to support WP4 in defining dummy variables for the simulation based on preliminary results until estimates will be available. Thus, WP4 can advance in coding and testing their simulations and the time lost due to the delay in task WP5-T2 had been minimised.

This task had been delayed because some partners, who contributed intensively, were additionally charged with COVID-19 related tasks and had to leave the work group. This had been solved on a higher level, but delays occurred due shortage of personnel for 4 months at BfR after the initial project lead had left. Besides, technical issues around conference tools strained communication between partners until solutions had been found. Thanks to personnel reinforcement at BfR since November this task had been finalised with the help of the group, but with some delay. The task was anyway planned to be carried out in steps and to run until 2022.

In the review, we concentrated particularly on biosecurity measures included in the questionnaire in WP2-T1 and for which no references on proving evidence of effectiveness had been identified in WP2-T1. Therefore, knowledge gaps in information from WP2-T1 had been analysed.

Y4 : A first round of a systematic literature review about the effectiveness of biosecurity measures specifically against *Salmonella* and HEV in pigs farms had been finished with the help of 10 reviewers from 7 countries, who evaluated about 1650 articles found in literature databases and according to a harmonised scheme. Relevant data were extracted and estimates of the effectiveness of the identified biosecurity measures were summarised by meta-analyses. The risk of bias of the included articles was assessed. First effect estimates were offered to WP4 at the end of M38 and entered in the catalogue of biosecurity measures (WP5-T1).

In a second round the systematic literature and meta-analyses was then updated and expanded, including biosecurity measures to reduce the occurrence of pathogenic *E. coli* in pig herds. In this round, a total of 11 reviewers overall participated from 7 different countries. Tutorials on literature screening, data extraction and risk of bias analysis were held to instruct participants. In this updating turn, a software-based machine learning tool, ASReview was applied alongside the manual screening by reviewers, with thanks to the collaboration from the University of Utrecht. In total for the manual screening, 5130 article titles were initially included and 1185 abstracts were screened in duplicate. For ASReview, 4068 articles were uploaded onto the software and 536 abstracts were screened. After further full text screening, 82 articles moved to data extraction and finally risk of bias analysis, with a final sample of 54 papers deemed to have sufficient primary data to be extracted for the analysis. Data cleaning of the extracted estimates had continued by four partners throughout December and January. Work had been delayed due to a lack of staff at BfR and elsewhere to conduct the analysis of the extracted effect estimates.

Y5 : The literature review and meta-analysis to identify effective measures to control HEV, *Salmonella* and pathogenic *E. coli* in primary production had been finalised in a joint work between 6 partner countries/institutes. Finally, 35 articles met the inclusion criteria (4 on HEV, 29 on *Salmonella*, 2 on pathogenic *E. coli*). From these articles, 14 observations on measures related to HEV, 145 related to *Salmonella* and three related to pathogenic *E. coli* control were extracted. Most measures addressed biosecurity categories like Cleaning & Disinfection (42), Mixing of pigs (35) and FeedWaterBedding (24). The results were transferred to the biosecurity catalogue (WP5-T1).

A manuscript is currently being drafted to present the study and its results intended to be published in a scientific journal.

WP5-T3 Machine learning approaches

Y3 : This task had not started yet. However, it had been discussed to drop or change it in order to support the data analysis / imputation of missing values in task WP2-T2 because that task might need

additional time and/or finish the data acquisition with much less data than planned due to the COVID-19 -restrictions.

Y4 : This task had not started yet and conduction is unclear as the task leader left the project and replacement is unclear. Partly, the additional use of ASReview replaced this task.

Y5 : The prediction of effectiveness of specific biosecurity measures with the help of a machine learning approach and to inform the biosecurity catalogue appeared not useful anymore and had therefore been cancelled. Instead, we used the ASReview tool in WP5-T2 to automate and complement part of the comprehensive and thereby labour- and staff intensive literature review on global biosecurity practice.

WP5-T4 Expert panel to add estimations on effectiveness/ weights

Y3 : This task will build on and expand the expert panel set up and surveyed in WP2-T1 (scientists) to additionally incorporate knowledge of other stakeholders like practitioners, advisors, etc.. A list of types of experts to recruit had been compiled. A comprehensive discussion had taken place about which kinds of experts to invite and how to categorise them. This fruitful discussion showed that there are marked differences between the veterinary and consulting systems within the pig sectors of the different partner states. These differences in the systems considerably influence the understanding of the roles within the pig sector of different professions. A shared spreadsheet with predefined types of experts was created and a first selection of experts from several countries agreed to support the panel. Further experts had be contacted. The procedure of the expert interviews had started to be defined and the expert survey had been prepared. For this, the questions from the questionnaire of WP2-T2 needs to be reworded to statements and any possible need for translations had been identified between partners. Scoring categories for evaluating the responses of experts had been discussed and developed.

Y4 : The questionnaire about biosecurity measures in primary pig production, developed in WP2-T1 and applied on farms in WP2-T2, was adapted for an expert survey to assess the importance of biosecurity measures to reduce Salmonella and HEV occurrence in different pig production systems.

For this, questions were reworded to best practice statements, considering results from WP5-T2 literature review, and the initial expert panel from WP2-T1 (scientists) was expanded to additionally incorporate knowledge of other stakeholders like practitioners, advisors, etc.. We finally identified and agreed on the grouping of expertise and then recruited representatives from participating countries for the panel. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the interviews were carried out with an online questionnaire.

The experts were asked to:

- 1) Rate their own expertise for the pathogens HEV and Salmonella, for the husbandry systems and for biosecurity;
- 2) Select the setting(s) they wanted to answer questions for (settings: HEV*indoor keeping, HEV*outdoor keeping, Salmonella*indoor keeping, Salmonella*outdoor keeping);
- 3) Rank the effectiveness of eight biosecurity measure categories, scoring them between 1-80 based on their importance for pathogen prevention/control, and
- 4) within each category, score each specific measure, based on its relevance to control within each setting, between 1 (least relevant) and 5 (most relevant).

Responses from 46 experts (from PL, UK, DE, BG, AT, IT, SE, NL, BE, EE, NO) could be included in the analysis. The experts' answers to the questionnaire had been analysed.

Results indicated that, no biosecurity category stood out, with all category contributing to some extent. The experts confirmed the high importance of the majority of the biosecurity measures within the categories, nonetheless activities related to animal movement/mixing as well as cleaning/disinfection

practices were consistently ranked high for all settings. Additionally, gaps relating to outdoor farming and HEV in pigs were identified and should be targeted in future research.

A manuscript for this study is intended to be submitted to a scientific journal.

Y5 : A manuscript for the study on biosecurity measures prioritised by experts to control HEV and *Salmonella* in indoor and outdoor pig production has been prepared between authors from six countries and has been submitted to Porcine Health Management.

WP5-T5 Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity practice

Y5 : This task started in M51. Task group meetings took place (1-2 per month). The list of participants, the objective and subtasks were clarified and organised. At first, effective biosecurity measures were collated based on incoming data from the other tasks WP2-T2, WP5-T2, WP5-T4 (collected in the WP5-T1 catalogue). Only measure that met the BIOPIGEE definition of biosecurity measures (clarified in the additional BIOPIGEE task WP1-T1-ST1/WP5-T0) and which proved to be effective (based on former studies or on results from WP2-T2) were included in the benchmark list. The wording of the measures was prepared in agreement with reference information, task partners and in consultation with WP4-T4. The measures were grouped as in WP2, WP4 and WP5 and ordered by prioritisation of experts (panel). A benchmark system had been developed which addressed different production stages and pathogens. A traffic light system had been used and cut-offs were found in applying the benchmark checklist to example farms from WP2-T2 with the help of the collected survey data.

WP6 Dissemination

WP6-T1 Assembly and development of biosecurity information

Y3 : Collection of best biosecurity illustrations (pictures) during farm visits of WP2-T2 had been described in the Sampling protocol of WP2-T2. The task had been delayed due to the COVID-19 outbreak as farms could not be visited by some partners with subsequent delays in collection of illustrations.

WP6-T1-ST1 Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

A shared file at the BIOPIGEE website had been developed to list appropriate channels for dissemination in partner countries. Twenty-one web sites in six countries had been identified for dissemination.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

The start of this task had been postponed from M31 to M43 when effective biosecurity measures for slaughterhouses had been analysed in WP2-T3.

Y4 :

WP6-T1-ST1- Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

The list of web sites for dissemination had been revised and the original 21 web sites across six countries had been kept. The shared document had been made accessible to all partners via a link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website.

WP6-T1-ST2a Provision of information for farming schools and websites

Illustrations of examples for good biosecurity (pictures), to be used in this task, were collected in WP2. Pictures from different partner countries' farms had been assembled and uploaded to the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website. Ideas about the content of this material had been exchanged with an advisory service in Germany as well as at the online workshop between the BIOPIGEE project group and the T5.4 expert panel.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

A slaughterhouse biosecurity protocol/questionnaire has been developed and sent to slaughterhouses in seven countries (DE, CZ, EE, IT, AT, UK and NL).

The deliverable WP6.15 “Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided” had been completed in December 2021.

Y5 :

WP6-T1-ST1- Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

The list of web sites for dissemination had been revised and the original 21 web sites across six countries was kept.

WP6-T1-ST2a Provision of information for farming schools and websites

The material in the form of leaflets for farming schools consisting of information on the project itself, best biosecurity practices with pictures as illustrations had been prepared for dissemination by BIOPIGEE partners. Ideas about the content and presentation of this material had been exchanged with a German farming education centre on how to set up the material to address farming pupils.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

An online workshop on findings about effective biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* (and HEV) at slaughter of pigs was held on September 16th, 2022. A guidance document is in preparation together with the publication of the findings taking into account the feedback received from stakeholders during the above-mentioned workshop.

WP6-T2 A support tool for calculating cost effectiveness

Y5 : A tool had been implemented based on results from WP4-T4. It calculates an estimation of the cost-efficiency of biosecurity measures along the food chain.

The calculation tool is created in Excel, to allow users an easy access and evaluation of costs and benefits of selected biosecurity measures. The measures were identified through a literature review and meta-analysis conducted in WP5-T2. Results are searchable for four countries (Austria, France, Germany and United Kingdom). In WP4-T4 the cost-benefit analysis was conducted based on the comparison of an estimated current implementation rate of a biosecurity measure (WP2) against an assumed 100% application rate within a country. The figures incorporated into the calculation tool are the output from this cost-benefit analysis. All currently available results from WP4-T4 have been transferred into the calculation tool. The tool design allows additional data to be added at a later stage.

A prototype of the tool is established. After finalizing the output-design, the tool will be distributed via the BIOPIGEE website and the corresponding deliverable report.

WP6-T3 Organisation of a workshop-series

As a preliminary remark it must be stressed that plans for the workshop series had to be altered due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Instead of arranging the workshops in conjunction with relevant conferences, the first workshop was cancelled and replaced with smaller national or regional events for disseminating information on the project and to gather input from stakeholders. Stakeholders to invite had been identified for the expert panel (WP5)) and WP6 (workshops). The physical workshops were replaced with three online workshops. The first was held on 14 December 2021 to which the expert panel was invited and discussed preliminary results from the BIOPPIGEE project and provided input for work during the final year of the project. The second and third workshops were held on 14 and 16 September 2022. These two workshops targeted different audiences as the the second workshop addressed primary production while the third addressed biosecurity during slaughter. The latter two workshops were well attended with more than 100 registered participant per workshop.

Y3 :

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant experts

WP5 and WP6 together identified relevant experts and stakeholders to invite to the expert panel and workshop series, respectively. Interested parties were listed at the BIOPIGEE website.

WP6-T3-ST2 Identification of relevant conferences

Relevant conferences were listed in our publication plan (link to shared document at BIOPIGEE website had been provided) and recurrently revised. However, no workshops could be carried out in conjunction with a conference because of the pandemic and after lifting restrictions due to the pandemic, reluctance from the organising committee of the ESPHM conference to enable this. The ESPHM conference had been identified as the best option for the workshop as it attracts pig practitioners and the scientific community related to porcine health management, the timing in May 2022 and the location in Budapest, Hungary.

WP6-T3-ST3 Organisation of Workshop 1

The first workshop was cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic and replaced with regional or national events which has been carried out in Germany.

Y4 :

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

BIOPIGEE partners revised the list of stakeholders identified. For the second workshop, an expert panel, recruited for T5.4, was invited for a web-meeting to discuss BIOPIGEE results. National contact BIOPIGEE partners sent out the invitation to a total of 84 identified experts in eleven countries.

WP6-T3-ST2 Identification of relevant conferences

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, physical conferences were cancelled. Relevant conferences for hosting the third workshop in 2022 in conjunction with a conference, were listed in our publication list, options were discussed in the WP leader meeting in June and September 2021. The ESPHM was identified as a suitable conference for hosting a pre-congress workshop arranged by the BIOPIGEE consortium. The discussion continued in the beginning of 2022 but the plan was dropped as the ESPHM board did not allow for a pre-congress symposium at a suitable time preceding the conference despite quite far-reaching plans for a hybrid event.

WP6-T3-ST3 Organisation of Workshop 1

Due to the Covid pandemic, the first workshop was cancelled. National information events are planned instead. In Germany, participation in information days of and with animal health services took place to inform and discuss results from BIOPIGEE (25th Nov 2021). Here, contacts and exchange with a German consultancy service for biosecurity practice in pig farming and with a German training centre for farming apprenticeship were initiated. This exchange may be beneficial with testing and giving feedback when designing the information material in WP6-T1-ST2a and the support tool in WP6-T2.

WP6-T3-ST4 Organisation of Workshop 2

An online workshop was held on 14th December 2021. Listed experts for WP5-T4 were invited to this half-day-workshop where preliminary results from the BIOPIGEE project were presented and discussed. There were in total 62 participants from 11 countries, 35 project members and 27 externals. The panel was represented by 17 participants.

The presentations gave a good overview about first findings. Main points in the discussions were how we define and delimit biosecurity measures in pig production and what has been so far learned about transmission of HEV between pigs. Moreover, a focus of this workshop was the exchange of ideas

about how and where to disseminate outcome of the project to spread knowledge on best biosecurity practice in pig production.

Y5 :

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

For the workshops, stakeholder groups had previously been identified. These were invited by:

- 1) main contact persons at the partner institutes per country,
- 2) the OHEJP CommsTeam, and by
- 3) Task WP2-T3 (slaughterhouse panel).

WP6-T3-ST5 Organisation of final Workshops

The first onsite workshop at the beginning of the project was replaced by national dissemination events where findings and feedback could be exchanged. The events are described in the deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.3.

After one online workshop at which project findings were discussed with the WP5-T4 expert panel in December 2021 (deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.10), another two virtual workshops were planned for the end of the project. These two workshops were held in mid of September 2022; instead of one onsite workshop. The goal of the two workshops was to present and discuss findings on effective biosecurity measures in

- 1) primary production and
- 2) at slaughter,

each targeting a particular and still wide audience of stakeholders. The workshop for primary production (deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.26) included outcomes from WP2-T2 and WP2-T4 field studies, WP4-T4 economic modelling, WP5-T2 literature study and WP5-T4 expert survey. The second workshop (deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.28) addressed literature information and a guidance document on effective slaughterhouse measures and sample results from slaughterhouses in CZ and IT (outcome from Task WP2-T3). In both workshops the implementation of effective measures in respective operations have been discussed.

WP6-T4 Production of BIOPIGEE flyer

Y3 : WP6 (supported by WP1 and the OHEJP Communication Team) produced a BIOPIGEE flyer with brief information material about the project for handing out to farmers (WP2-T2), to external collaboration partners, at conferences, at workshops (WP6-T3) and when recruiting experts for the panel (WP5-T4).

WP6-T5 Press release

Y4 : A press release about activities in the project has been drafted between partners (DE, UK, AT, SE) and published at the beginning of 2021.

WP6-T6 Glossary of terms used in BIOPIGEE

Y4 : A glossary of terms used in BIOPIGEE has been developed between tasks and is hosted in the infrastructure of the OHEJP MATRIX project. The BIOPIGEE Glossary can be accessed via a link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website since 17th December 2021. In 2022, the definition of “biosecurity measure” was published and afterwards it was added to the glossary.

2.10.4 Project self-assessment

According to the proposal plan, effective biosecurity measures for the control of both Salmonella and HEV occurrence in the pig production (food) chain had been identified in the project and also disseminated to stakeholders.

In WP2, delays were encountered in recruiting and visiting farms, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and African Swine Fever presence in participating countries. The extension of the overall project helped us recruit close to the expected number of farms. Additionally, farm data was sourced from other studies as a backup plan and these will be used for an additional publication. The delays still impacted upon the ability to produce analytical results to inform the other workpackages in good time, which impacted slightly upon their use of the data. However, the WP managed to achieve all its aim and produced novel and robust datasets for epidemiological analysis.

WP4 encountered issues around sharing of sensitive pig movement data between countries, as such it was only possible to run the network model for France in the time available. This highlights a major issue around data availability across countries which hampers the development of models with EU wide applicability. In the future, consideration could be given as to whether models could be shared rather than the data. For Salmonella, we were able to produce results for Austria and the UK, giving us results for three countries overall, but not the countries suggested in the original proposal.

Another issue in WP4 identified was the difficulty in obtaining relevant outputs from the longitudinal studies. This issue was only identified at a late stage of the project, future studies should allow for earlier communication between WPs regarding the type and format of data outputs expected and data inputs required. These issues meant that, while results for multiple biosecurity measures identified in the other WPs were produced, for both HEV and Salmonella, we were unable to produce results for all of them.

Also in WP4 it was found that very little data were available to parameterise the HEV QMRA in terms of actual infectious virus, which is the relevant microbiological variable for predicting the probability of infection and hence the expected number of human cases. As there were significantly more data available concerning RNA copies, a methodology was developed which relied on 'conversion factors' between RNA copies and infectious virus. The nature of these conversion factors was subject to high uncertainty, hence this approach resulted in high uncertainty around the number of human cases. However, the human exposure, i.e. levels of HEV RNA consumed, and the relative difference in HEV cases between biosecurity measure were considered more robust.

Finally, WP4 encountered issues due to three other problems. Multiple experienced staff left the project, including the WP lead. Resources were diverted for long periods of time due to high priority work such as HPAI outbreaks. Lockdowns and movement restrictions due to COVID-19 prevented face-to-face meetings to facilitate discussion and sharing of results and also led to delays in other WP deliverables giving less time to incorporate results.

In WP6, the workshops were initially planned to be held in conjunction with conferences relevant to the project. This plan was discarded because of the COVID-19 pandemic and replaced with online workshops. Despite the deviation from the original plan, the workshops which did take place were considered successful with many attendees from many countries in Europe as well as participants from other parts of the world including Africa ensuring wide dissemination.

Overall, some modifications had to be made, mainly due to the pandemic but the objectives could still be addressed as planned. In BIOPIGEE, outdoor farming systems were considered. Although the sample of outdoor farms may be representative of current European production within the dataset, a larger sample size of outdoor farms would be needed to be included in the future to validate the measures for these farms. Besides, more knowledge on HEV and its control measures is needed. Comparison with ASF findings is desirable also with regard to supplementation of pathogen related check lists in

both ways. Finally, cost/economy information on measures is still scarce and important to increase for reliable calculations.

2.10.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
21	D-JRP21-WP1.2	First draft of data management plan finished	M30	M34 (website)	The DMP was uploaded to the project website and public in the CDP tool. It gets repeatedly updated in a shared document and changes transferred to CDP; OHEJP DMP group recommends to upload only the final DMP to Zenodo.	8
21	D-JRP21-WP1.4	Project report 1st year submitted	M36	M36	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/4361090	8 (reporting)
21	D-JRP21-WP1.13	Project report 2nd year submitted	M49	M49	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5930342	8
21	D-JRP21-WP1.19	Revised data management plan submitted	M60	M60	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7429754	8
21	D-JRP21-WP1.23	Final project report submitted	M60	M60	Going to be public under link https://zenodo.org/record/7429770	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
21	D-JRP21-WP2.1	Biosecurity protocol (addressing measures to control Salmonella and HEV) designed for data collection in the field	M28	M29 (44 zenodo)	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5336900	2
21	D-JRP21-WP2.8	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at slaughterhouses	M42	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5774876	4
21	D-JRP21-WP2.9	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at farm	M42	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5792859	4
21	D-JRP21-WP2.12	Produce report on evidence gathered by field studies	M54	M54	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6780124	8
21	D-JRP21-WP2.18	Report on correlation of biosecurity practice with HEV sequences to WP5 and 6, sequence analysis of hepatitis E to HEVnet	M57	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7267862	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP3.5	Method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers	M36	M42	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/4940091 ; was delayed due to COVID-19 pandemic and consequences	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.6	HEV infectivity assay available	M36	M36	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5242819	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.7	Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm	M40	M44	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5211242	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.14	Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers/biofilm	48	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7231931	
21	D-JRP21-WP3.19	Information on the effect of different disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm	M56	M56	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7023490	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.20	HEV infectivity test adapted for testing of HEVs in biofilm	M48	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5793040	1
21	D-JRP21-WP4.11	Model Output: Number of animal cases with and	M56	M56	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6974303	7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		without biosecurity measures				
21	D-JRP21-WP4.16	Economic calculation	M57	M57	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7085855	7
21	D-JRP21-WP4.17	Model output: Number of human cases with and without biosecurity measures	M57	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7180805	7
21	D-JRP21-WP5.21	Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity practice finished and forwarded to WP1 and WP6	M58	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7268326	4
21	D-JRP21-WP6.3	Workshop 1 completed		M56	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6974588 National events were visited for dissemination and exchange of thoughts with stakeholders (instead of organising one international onsite workshop at the beginning of the project which was cancelled due to the pandemic situation).	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP6.4	BIOPIGEE Flyer	M32	M32	Brief information when contacting potential new collaborators, experts for our panel, recruiting farmers, and as general dissemination to public) https://zenodo.org/record/4009015	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.10	Workshop 2 completed	M48	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5806257	
21	D-JRP21-WP6.15	Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided	M48	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5772529	2
21	D-JRP21-WP6.22	Provision of information on best biosecurity practice to farming schools	M58	M60	Going to be public under Zenodo link https://zenodo.org/record/7429810	6
21	D-JRP21-WP6.24	Project web-content developed	M60	M60	Going to be public under Zenodo link https://zenodo.org/record/7429783	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.25	A support tool (Excel) for calculation of cost effectiveness of preventive biosecurity measures developed	M60	M60	Going to be public under Zenodo link https://zenodo.org/record/7429826	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP6.26	Workshop 3 completed	M58	M58	Two online workshops held for dissemination of results on effective biosecurity measures in 1) primary production and 2) at slaughter in September 2022, public, https://zenodo.org/record/7259005	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.27	Provision of biosecurity protocol and of benchmark of biosecurity practice	M60	M59	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7351107	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.28	Workshop 4 completed	n.a. (additional workshop)	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7181040	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-01	Kick-off meeting successfully organised	M26	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-02	Questionnaire on biosecurity costs	M26	Yes, M27	Farm performance questions included. Biosecurity cost question excluded; data will be gathered from other sources.
21	M-JRP21-03	Relevant conferences for workshops to be held are identified	26	Yes (46)	Was delayed due to pandemic situation. It is planned to disseminate more findings in pre-conference-Workshop at the ESPHM on 11th March 2022
21	M-JRP21-04	Biosecurity protocol designed for Salmonella and HEV	M28	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-05	Relevant stakeholders identified	28	Yes (36)	Was postponed due to the current COVID-19 situation (no workshops took place yet); Instead of stakeholders, a list of experts for a panel in WP5-T4 has been expanded (online table, link in BIOPIGEE private webgroup). These experts were finally invited for an online workshop to be hold in December 2021.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-06	Appropriate websites or other online channels for dissemination identified	30	Yes	List of web sites is being filled in an online table (link in BIOPIGEE private webgroup); Content will be continuously updated throughout the project
21	M-JRP21-07	Workshop 1 completed	30	Yes (47)	WP-leader decision: The workshop was cancelled due to COVID-19-outbreak, instead national information events in 2021/22 are planned (in Germany, animal health services were informed about our findings and discussed with at their conference in Nov 2021)
21	M-JRP21-08	Design of field study protocols	M32	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-09	First part of meta-analysis finished	36	Yes (38)	A literature review and meta-analysis was carried out. Was delayed due to partners involved in covid-testing and missing personnel for 4 months at BfR
21	M-JRP21-10	Salmonella strains for testing are collected	M36	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-11	HEV infectivity assay available	M36	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-12	Mid-term meeting successfully organized	39	Yes	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-13	Application of protocols across countries	40	Yes (46)	Was delayed and sample size slightly reduced in a few countries due to pandemic situation and restrictions for visiting farms.
21	M-JRP21-14	Relevant stakeholders re-identified	36	Yes (41)	As stated for M-JRP21-05, an expert panel is addressed instead. This was re-identified in M41.
21	M-JRP21-15	Transmission model adaptation based on available data	45	yes	Completed. The baseline QMRA models for Salmonella and HEV have been completed utilizing relevant recent data.
21	M-JRP21-16	Test methods to be used in JRP21-WP3-T2-ST2 are selected	40	No (46)	Milestone completed. Each lab will use the already locally established biofilm testing method for WP3-T2-ST2.
21	M-JRP21-17	Produce summary of evidence of slaughterhouse biosecurity effectiveness	42	Yes (48)	Development of questionnaire took longer than planned (review of peer-reviewed papers; consideration of technique in all countries; common understanding of relevant biosecurity measures and formulation of questions; translations; implementation into survey tool; test runs; data protection issues). The questionnaire was prepared and the survey was carried out in summer 2021.
21	M-JRP21-18	Workshop 2 completed	40	Yes (48)	Was postponed to the second half of 2021, due to pandemic situation, changed to a

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
					virtual workshop with the expert panel from WP5-T4.
21	M-JRP21-19	Completion of farm visits and lab work	54	56	completed (NL continues with visits which can complement BIOPIGEE results)
21	M-JRP21-20	Application of appropriate economic methods based on available data	51	yes	Completed. Economic methods were selected for application. Working document is created, to be updated if methods have to be adjusted.
21	M-JRP21-21	Uploading of sequences to HEVnet	54	56	Completed
21	M-JRP21-22	Matching of different simulation model approaches to one	55	yes	Completed. The different models developed in WP4 have been developed to ensure that the relevant outputs of one model can act as inputs to another.
21	M-JRP21-23	Relevant disinfectants are tested against Salmonella in biofilm	56	yes	Completed
21	M-JRP21-24	Relevant disinfectants are tested against HEV in surface microlayers/biofilms	56	yes	A pilot study on HEV stability in relation to disinfectants has been executed
21	M-JRP21-25	Finalized data integration from WP2-4 into catalogue of biosecurity measures	59		ongoing, depends on delayed tasks; existing content has been used for other tasks

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-26	Finalized literature review/meta-analysis	50	53	finalised (was delayed because of change in staff), results are currently being written up in a manuscript by the task group
21	M-JRP21-27	Economic model for the assessments of profitability of biosecurity measures	57	57	finalised, parameters for economic assessment identified and model to calculate the profitability set up. Cost-benefit analysis was carried out with the available results from the QMRA.
21	M-JRP21-28	Predicted effectiveness of specific biosecurity measures from machine learning approach incorporated in catalogue	57	n.a.	cancelled, appeared not anymore useful and necessary for informing the biosecurity catalogue because other tasks (literature review, field studies) fed already the catalogue. Instead, ASReview was used in WP5-T2 to partly automate and complement the comprehensive literature search. Thereby, the following WP5-T5 benchmark task was well informed.
21	M-JRP21-29	Expert panel ranked biosecurity practice	51	yes	finalised, manuscript has been submitted
21	M-JRP21-30	Information on best biosecurity practice to farming schools ready to be provided	M58	Yes (M60)	nearly finalized, additional content was added to inform also about other project outcomes and aspects

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-31	Relevant stakeholders re-identified	M58	2022-07-05	Relevant stakeholders re-assessed for the invitation to the final workshops.
21	M-JRP21-32	Benchmark system for effectiveness/relevance of biosecurity practice finished	M58	Yes (M58)	completed
21	M-JRP21-33	Final meeting successfully organized	M58	Yes (M58)	completed
21	M-JRP21-34	The Excel support tool for cost effectiveness calculations distributed	M60	Yes (M60+)	As of end of M60 the tool is being tested for comprehensibility and user friendliness. Distribution will only start 2023.
21	M-JRP21-35	Workshop 3 and 4 completed	M58	Yes (M57)	completed
21	M-JRP21-36	Project web-content disseminated online	M60	Yes (M60)	Finalised, all outputs, respective DOIs and links are listed in the information material for complete access to project results. Distribution will start end of 2022.

2.10.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière: analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation, JRP conference/paper</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6091598</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6091598</p>	published	Yes	Yes	No
<p>Complex network analysis to understand trading partnership in French swine production, PlosOne</p> <p>DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0266457</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/6458445#.YnkdKehBxwQ</p>	published	Yes	No	Yes (about 1400 €)
<p>What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for animal production and linked processing operations</p> <p>DOI: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2022.100433</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/7143533</p>	published	Yes	No	Yes (about 2000 € without taxes)
<p>Prioritization of pig farm biosecurity for control of Salmonella and hepatitis E virus infections; results of a European Expert Opinion Elicitation</p>	submitted	Yes	TBC	TBC

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Effectiveness of pig farm biosecurity measures for the control of Salmonella on European farms – a case control study	submitted	Yes	TBC	TBC
Detection of HEV RNA by one-step real-time RT-PCR in far-row-to-finish pig farms in Bulgaria	submitted	Yes	TBC	TBC
Slaughterhouse biosecurity measures for Salmonella control with quantified effectiveness: a review	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Review of the implementation of effective biosecurity practices, related to Salmonella and hepatitis E virus control, in a selection of European pig slaughterhouses	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
A quantitative microbiological risk assessment for transmission of HEV in the pork production chain.	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Surveillance of Hepatitis E virus circulation in Italian pig farms	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Sequence diversity of Hepatitis E virus from European pig farms	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Protective Biosecurity Measures to reduce hepatitis E virus in European pig farms	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Biosecurity measures reducing Salmonella spp., hepatitis E virus and pathogenic Escherichia coli	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
prevalence in pig farms: A systematic review and meta-analysis.				

Additional output

Posters

- Jones, H., Smith, R.P., Burow, E., on behalf of the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of Salmonella in European pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Alborali G., Guadagno F., Delibato E., Treglia I., De Sabato L., Monini M., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Molecular tracing of dissemination routes of Salmonella spp, Hepatitis E virus and other viruses as fecal indicators in pigs at slaughterhouse. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6646338>
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Aprea G., Romantini R., Alborali G., D'Angelantonio D., Garofolo G., Scattolini S., De Sabato L., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Presence of Salmonella spp. And Hepatitis E virus in Italian pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6638970>
- Meester M., Tobias T., Meulenbroek C., Hakze-van der Honing R., van Oort S., Bouwknecht M., Stegeman A., van der Poel W.H.M. (2022). Prevalence of HEV in finishing pigs: cross-sectional exploration of farm specific patterns and evaluation of sampling. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6566927>
- Kozyra, I., Zając, M., Żmudzki, J., Dors, A., Skrzypiec, E., Wasyl, D., Rzeżutka, A. (2022). Epidemiological significance of Salmonella and hepatitis E virus (HEV) occurrence in fattening pigs in Poland. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6673709>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2021). Multi-levels Hepatitis E Virus Spread In Various Epidemiological Contexts: Combining Complex Network Analysis & Disease Transmission Model. Poster at the 8th International Conference on Infectious Disease Dynamics (Epidemics 8), online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5786494>
- Huber, N., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu, E. L., Prigge, C., Käsbohrer, A., Andraud, M., D'Angelantonio, D., Viltrop, A., Niine, T., Hammami, P., Żmudzki, J., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for farms and linked processing operations. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Smith, R., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). Salmonella presence on European pig farms. I3S International Symposium Salmonella & Salmonellosis 20.-22.06.2022. Saint-Malo. <https://zenodo.org/record/7054296>
- Dors, A., Wasyl, D., Rzeżutka, A., Karbowski, P., Szalkowski, W., Żmudzki, J. (2022). A survey on external biosecurity in selected commercial Polish pig farms. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Burow, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Tobias, T., Sassu, E. L., Galpó, E., Prigge, C., Smith, R. P., Sjölund, M. (2022). Expert opinion on biosecurity measures for controlling Salmonella and hepatitis E virus in pig farming - findings of the OHEJP BIOPIGEE project. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). The best biosecurity practices in European abattoirs in regards to Salmonella and hepatitis E virus. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online. <https://zenodo.org/record/7032155>

- Jones, H., Smith, R. P., Burow, E. (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of *Salmonella* in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Biosecurity practices to reduce risk of hepatitis E virus in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Sensitivity and specificity of pen-level sampling methods for hepatitis E virus detection in fattening pigs. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Osland, A.M, Oastler, C. Brook, E. Gosling, B. Arvand, M. Richter, A.M, Konrat, K. Asal, B. Vestby. L.K. (2022). Effect of Glutaraldehyde on biofilm-associated wild type *Salmonella*. Poster will be presented at Eurobiofilms 2022. 31.8.22-3.9.22, Mallorca, Spain
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Multi-levels hepatitis E virus spread in various epidemiological contexts: combining complex network analysis & disease transmission model. Poster at the Epidemics conference. <https://zenodo.org/record/5786494>
- Hammami, P (2021). Live animal movement - Understnad trade partners choices to predict cahins of contact. SVEPM 2021.
- McCarthy, C. (2021). BIOPIGEE: Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures. OHEJP ASM 2021.
- Bester, C. (2022). Development of an economic model to assess the cost-effectiveness of biosecurity measures to reduce the burden of *Salmonella* and Hepatitis E virus in the pork production chain. ISAH 2022.

Oral presentations

- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Biosecurity measures in European slaughterhouses to prevent the contamination of pig carcasses with *Salmonella*. Konverentsi "terve loom ja tervislik toit 2022" artiklikogumik (Estonian conference), 157–160. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6355316>
- Viltrop, A. (2022). Biosecurity of *Salmonella* from Estonian pig farms perspective. Estonian Officials Veterinarian Training day.
- Burow, E. (presentation), Zoche-Golob, V. (abstract), Aprea, G., Sjölund, M., for the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Biosecurity measures reducing Hepatitis E Virus in pig herds – findings of the OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. Oral presentation at German conference 22. Fachtagung für Fleisch- und Geflügelfleischhygiene, 1.-2. March 2022, Berlin, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6524126>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Spread of hepatitis E virus from pens to the national industry: complex network analysis and modelling. 54th Journées de la Recherche Porcine (JRP), 2nd February 2022, online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6091598>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière : analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation. Talk at the Junior Researcher Programme conference <https://zenodo.org/record/6091598>

- Burow, E., N. Huber, E. Galipó, R. Smith (2022). Effective and prioritised biosecurity practice to control Salmonella in pig farming - findings from the BIOPIGEE project. Oral presentation at HealthyLivestock conference, 16.06.2022, hybrid
- Burow, E., Schulze-Horsel, T., Harlizius, J., Rostalski, A., Smith, R., Zoche-Golob, V., Galipó, E., Waller, E., Jones, H., Sjölund, M., Käsbohrer, A. (2022). Biosicherheitsmaßnahmen zur Kontrolle von Salmonellen und Hepatitis E Viren in der europäischen Schweinehaltung - OHEJP Projekt BIOPIGEE. Biosecurity measures for controlling Salmonella and hepatitis E virus in European pig farming - OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. DACH Epidemiologietagung 2022, 31.08.-02.09.2022, Oldenburg.
- Galipó, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu E. L., Prigge, C., Sjölund, M., Tobias, T., Rzezutka, A., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Pig farm biosecurity for control of Salmonella and hepatitis E virus infections – a survey of European experts. Oral presentation at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.
- Hammami, P. (2021). Complex network analysis and Exponential Random Graph Models: Epidemiological implications of network structures. Modah 2021.
- Hammami, P. (2021). Multi-level Hepatitis E Virus Spread in various epidemiological contexts: combining complex network analysis & disease transmission models. CCS 2021.
- Wilkins, N. (2022). A farm-to-consumption quantitative microbiological risk assessment for hepatitis E in pigs. Presented at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

In WP6, additional outcomes like support tool for e.g. farmers, information/education material for farming pupils, website information and two more workshops (in September 2022) for the exchange of ideas with stakeholders were planned. The workshops took place with broad international audience. The education material and website presentations is in work.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Outcomes of the project have been discussed at the following institutes of the project consortium:

At work group level at APHA, SVA and BfR.

At department level at APHA and BfR

At institute level at BfR.

A representative of EFSA was present at the final project meeting of BIOPIGEE in order to discuss the outcomes.

Furthermore results of the project are going to be presented and discussed at the UK Pig Health and Welfare Council (PHWC).

2.10.7 One Health impact

The OHEJP BIOPIGEE project aimed at identifying effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control hepatitis E virus (HEV) and Salmonella occurrence in European pig farming. These two pathogens represent important zoonotic organisms.

Correspondingly the comprehensive literature reviews, field and experimental studies, expert opinion surveys and risk modelling which had been done provide a valuable knowledge base for international stakeholders involved in the domain of zoonoses. The outcomes include guidance for farmers, veterinarians, consultants and slaughterhouses in European countries in form of illustrative flyers and web content to inform stakeholders, incl. collaborating farm education centres. The material should provide reliable and cost-efficient guidance on the reduction of Salmonella and HEV spread in animals and humans (through occupational exposure) which add important information for monitoring and regulation in order to advance One Health.

Regional and national authorities could pick up the material produced, translate them into their regional language(s) and use them. It is also possible to develop the material further or adapt it to the local needs.

During the process we reached out to academics and practitioners in the field particularly in the three workshops organized by BIOPIGEE. But we also presented and discussed our results at various national events. Namely at a 2-days-hybrid event of the North Rhine-Westphalian Pig Health Service which took place at the Chamber of Agriculture in Bad Sassendorf, Germany where we engaged with the participants of veterinarians, representatives of agriculture and the pig industry as well as laboratory staff and researchers. During the event, a contact was made with an advisory service on biosecurity practices in pig production in Baden-Wuerttemberg, and in a subsequent telephone meeting information was exchanged in more detail on measure effectiveness and the interest and use of farmers to implement knowledge. Another network was established with the agricultural education centre of the North Rhine-Westphalian Chamber of Agriculture and a web meeting was arranged after the conference to discuss how best to disseminate project results to agricultural students. Further exchange was agreed.

Then we went to the annual conference of the Institute of the Veterinary Medicine and Animal Sciences of the Estonian University of Life Sciences which was attended by farmers, food industry representatives, and state officials of the field. There results of the BIOPIGEE research were presented and discussed in two presentations in two sections of the event.

Also in Estonia we presented our work in a seminar which took place for the animal health officials from the headquarter and regional offices of the Agriculture and Food Board. The seminar was organized by the Estonian Veterinary and Food Laboratory (VFL).

The information about biosecurity with respect to Salmonella might help to inform scientist and risk managers who study AMR in pig production to mitigate resistant versions of Salmonella along the pig production chain.

2.10.8 Data Management Plan

<https://zenodo.org/record/7429754>

2.10.9 Future dissemination activities

Main stakeholders are farmers and vets. The main materials produced during the project are support tools like checklists, guidance documents and a cost-benefit model. The PMT and Communication

Team can help in providing easy to access storage of above mentioned materials and help dissemination by featuring these materials at events with agricultural stakeholders as well or in publications in farmers magazines.

2.11 JRP22-R2-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES

2.11.1 Consortium composition

Project Leader: Pikka Jokelainen (SSI, Denmark) PIJO@ssi.dk

Deputy Project Leader: Joke van der Giessen (RIVM, the Netherlands)

Work Package Leaders and Co-Leaders:

WP1: Pikka Jokelainen (SSI, Denmark), Joke van der Giessen (RIVM, the Netherlands)

WP2: Marieke Opsteegh (RIVM, the Netherlands), Sara Monteiro Pires (DTU-FOOD, Denmark)

WP3: Marco Lalle (ISS, Italy), Anne Mayer-Scholl (BfR, Germany)

WP4: Furio Spano (ISS, Italy), Frank Seeber (RKI, Germany)

WP5: Gereon Schares (FLI, Germany), Simone Cacciò (ISS, Italy)

Gender balance: 50%/50%.

TOXOSOURCES Joint Research Project consortium comprised 20 One Health EJP (OHEJP) partner institutes at the start of the project, and 21 at the end of the project: Anses, SZU, VRI, BfR, FLI, RKI, DTU, SSI (Project Leader), UCM, UoS, ISS, RIVM, WbVR, FHI, NVI, PIWET, INIAV, INSA, SLV, SVA, and BIOR (originally involved as external partner, joined OHEJP in 2021). In addition, the work included collaboration with several external research groups that participated with their own funding.

TOXOSOURCES consortium proved highly motivated and resourceful, and there was a very good atmosphere for the cross-sectoral, interdisciplinary One Health collaboration. Despite need to adapt to challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic, TOXOSOURCES reached its objectives – both the ambitious scientific objectives and the integrative objectives. Looking at the short CVs in the proposal and current career stage of key researchers in the consortium, it is clear that TOXOSOURCES had positive impact on career development of both early career researchers and experienced researchers involved in the work. The multidisciplinary collaboration structure enabled focusing on specific expertise areas that each contributed to addressing the common research question. This approach was globally identified as inspirational and to have potential for expanding and export.

TOXOSOURCES was successful beyond expectations – a sustainable international, cross-sectoral, multidisciplinary One Health collaboration became established. Despite the lack of direct continuation of funding, the consortium has decided to continue collaboration and being inclusive, welcoming further experts to join.

Figure 1. Kick-off Meeting of TOXOSOURCES, February 2020, at Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark, and a screenshot from a monthly online meeting of TOXOSOURCES work package (WP)-Leaders and WP-Co-Leaders.

2.11.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

TOXOSOURCES, a three-year Joint Research Project (2020-2022) within the One Health EJP, focused on *Toxoplasma gondii* at the interfaces between humans, animals, food, and the environment. The zoonotic parasite causes a high disease burden in humans, also in Europe. Moreover, it can cause clinical disease in numerous animal species, and it has an environmentally resistant form. The infection can be acquired by ingesting oocysts (environmental pathway) or tissue cysts (meatborne pathway). The relative importance of the two major pathways as well as the specific sources within these pathways has been unknown, partly due to a lack of appropriate methods. In particular, environmental contamination with *T. gondii* oocysts has been understudied and underestimated.

TOXOSOURCES investigated the relative contributions of the different transmission routes and sources of *T. gondii* infection using multidisciplinary approaches. The project developed new methods, yielded new knowledge, and moved the state-of-the-art to a new level.

The TOXOSOURCES consortium collected data for a multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii*. A multi-country quantitative exposure survey was conducted, and systematic literature reviews yielded estimates of prevalence and risk factors in humans and a high number of animal host species, and in fresh produce and the environment. After an extensive literature review to support the selection of the most suitable method to detect *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce, a Standard Operating Procedure was developed, implemented and validated, and applied in a multicentre study on ready-to-eat salads. The project explored promising new antigens and critically assessed previously identified ones for serology for detecting *T. gondii* infections caused by oocysts, and developed a workflow for assay development from a One Health perspective. An unprecedented effort of whole genome sequencing of *T. gondii* isolates was used to identify polymorphic marker regions for the establishment of a new typing method to detect within-genotype variation. The project organised ring trials as part of validation of the method to detect *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce and to harmonise the current state-of-the-art genotyping.

TOXOSOURCES yielded quantitative and comparable estimates of the contribution of different sources to *T. gondii* infections across Europe. The project filled relevant data and knowledge gaps, confirmed previously known sources, and yielded data on new possible sources, such as contaminated ready-to-eat salads. The exposure survey data will be useful also for other multi-country foodborne risk-assessments. The extensive work on source-attributing serology concluded that there is currently no antigen identified, by TOXOSOURCES nor other groups, that allows robust estimates of the proportion of infections acquired from oocysts by serology. The new NGS-based typing tool is a major methodological advancement to identify outbreaks and trace sources, and was successfully applied on various sample matrices in pilot studies that increased our knowledge on molecular epidemiology of the zoonotic parasite.

TOXOSOURCES consortium has become globally known as an example of successful international cross-sectoral One Health collaboration. The Consortium comprised 21 One Health EJP partners and several external collaborators. TOXOSOURCES delivered exceeding the expectations: all Milestones were reached and all Deliverables were submitted by their deadlines, and the project succeeded in its ambitious aims and developed new methods, advanced science, and established a sustainable cross-sectoral multidisciplinary collaboration. Dissemination of outcomes was very active and included a high number of scientific publications and presentations at conferences and science-policy interfaces, and collaborations with other projects and networks were established. The harmonised methods are now in use in several laboratories across Europe, and the consortium has decided to continue collaboration also after the One Health EJP funding period ends.

2.11.3 Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

Progress made in TOXOSOURCES followed the planned timeline throughout the project lifetime. All (100%) Milestones were reached and all (100%) Deliverables were delivered and made publicly available by their deadlines.

Due to the COVID-19-pandemic, there was a need to adapt internal timelines, in particular those related to laboratory work due to lockdowns. TOXOSOURCES applied for a 6-month extension until the end of the year 2022, to ensure 1) that the project could fully achieve all the planned aims; 2) that all partners had the opportunity to benefit from implementation of the new methods and knowledge; 3) that the studies were able to cover all the aspects planned; 4) that the outputs were of high quality and there was time for efficient dissemination; and as a result of all the previous points: 5) that TOXOSOURCES would have the full impact it had the potential to have. COVID-19 pandemic was the sole reason for the extension request.

The work was organized into five work packages (WPs) with tasks (T) and subtasks (sT). The project spun over three Annual Periods of OHEJP (Y3-Y5, 2020-2022). All outputs are publicly available via the project homepage under OHEJP website: <https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-toxosources/> and via Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22TOXOSOURCES%22>.

WP1 Coordination and impact

TOXOSOURCES-WP1 managed the project and was responsible for its progress, and integrated the results of the project to achieve the common goals. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 ensured the project adhered to H2020 rules and was responsible for the Data Management Plan. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 coordinated the compiling of deliverables and reports and their timely submission, as well as the organization of project meetings and communication. Science-to-policy translation, collaboration with industry, and efficient dissemination were emphasized to maximize the impact. Several collaborations with other projects and networks were established and strengthened. Of specific note is DISH-collaboration (Figure 2) with a cluster of other projects outside the OHEJP, established under Horizon Results Booster (HRB) services.

The main aim of TOXOSOURCES-WP1 was ensuring project progress as planned and organizing the Annual Meetings. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 integrated the results of the project to make them useful, in particular to contribute to developing interventions. These aims were fully reached.

JRP22-WP1-T1- Management, coordination and communication

The established key structures for management of the project included monthly online meeting with TOXOSOURCES WP-Leaders and Co-Leaders, consortium emails, use of an online group for sharing and storage of relevant documents, and WP-level meetings. The Kick-off Meeting was held February 3–4, 2020, at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark (hybrid). Consortium meetings were held on October 20, 2020 (Annual Meeting 2020, online), on June 8, 2021 (Annual Meeting 2021, Part I, online), on November 15, 2021 (Annual Meeting 2021, Part II, online), at ICOPA 2022 in August 2022 (hybrid), and on November 29, 2022 (Final Meeting, online).

The Data Management Plan (DMP) was updated regularly, and the Project Leader participated in the work of the OHEJP DMP Committee. All Milestones were reached and all Deliverables were submitted by their deadlines throughout the timeline of the project, which is exceptional taken the challenges caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The careful risks-and-dependencies planning proved useful, and the consortium was resourceful and highly motivated to work together through the challenging times. At the Final Meeting, the consortium decided to continue collaboration also after the OHEJP funding period ends.

JRP22-WP1-T2 Integration of all results to contribute to developing interventions, dissemination

The outcomes from different work packages all contributed to addressing the research question – What are the relative contributions of the different sources of T. gondii infection? – and were timely provided from one team to another during the project. The outcomes and outputs were made efficiently available following FAIR principle, and all data will be made available by the end of the OHEJP in September 2023. Very active dissemination of the outcomes included a high number of scientific publications and presentations to relevant audiences at conferences and webinars. Early-career colleagues involved in the work were particularly encouraged to present the results. Efficient dissemination and science-to-policy activities at national, European and global levels included facilitating the use of the new knowledge, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, and advocating multidisciplinary approaches - integration of results using a One Health approach. The TOXOSOURCES-approach, international multidisciplinary collaboration, was presented in Europe and beyond - including in events in India (virtually), USA and Colombia – and became acknowledged by global peers as an exemplary approach with export potential.

TOXOSOURCES established collaborations with projects within and outside OHEJP. TOXOSOURCES was invited to join a HRB project group “DISH - Towards healthy and safe diet” that included at first SafeConsume, Stance4Health, EAT2beNICE and FOODSAFETY4EU. A factsheet and video about the DISH collaboration were produced, and two lunch webinars were organised (on April 6, 2022 and on October 12, 2022). DISH became a sustainable collaboration that has continued actively since the HRB service period ended. Based on suggestion by TOXOSOURCES, a OHEJP Cogwheel Workshop with SafeConsume was organised on November 25, 2020. SafeConsume invited TOXOSOURCES to give a presentation and participate in round table at their International Conference in Bucharest, Romania, on June 27-28, 2022. The two projects were also a part of collaboration to organize a Breakfast Session ‘Co-creating better food systems in Europe’ at European Health Forum Gastein, on September 27, 2022. FOODSAFETY4EU invited TOXOSOURCES to present at Pre-Forum ‘Towards EU Food Safety Forum: The new sustainability regulation: how to integrate it into food safety?’ in December 2022.

TOXOSOURCES was very active also within the One Health EJP, and collaborated e.g. with MEmE and PARADISE projects. TOXOSOURCES presented at Annual Scientific Meetings 2020 (online), 2021 (Copenhagen, Denmark) and 2022 (Orvieto, Italy). The project was invited to present at the Stakeholders Committee Meeting of OHEJP in Copenhagen, Denmark, in June 2021, at online ESAB meeting and Review meeting in May 2022, and at the joint POC-PMC meeting in Stockholm, Sweden, in November 2022. Moreover, TOXOSOURCES was highlighted in a OHEJP Thematic Report focusing on environmental aspects of One Health, presented the novel typing approach at a OHEJP Dissemination Workshop, and presented its sustainability approach at the OHEJP Final School 2022.

**Welcome to the DISH table
towards healthy and safe
diets**

Figure 2. A page from factsheet produced for cross-project collaboration DISH, and a social media (Twitter) post about a DISH workshop.

WP2 Multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii* infections

TOXOSOURCES-WP2 provided major contributions towards quantifying the relative contributions of sources of *T. gondii* infection, including meat products, fresh produce and environmental pathways, in Europe, by quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA). TOXOSOURCES-WP2 developed and optimised a QMRA model for *T. gondii* infection via tissue cysts (meat), and models for oocysts (with focus on contaminated vegetables and soil) progressed to the final stages of development. TOXOSOURCES applied the meatborne infection model in the first multi-country QMRA-study across Europe. Collection and validation of input data for the QMRA was achieved with contributions and support from all TOXOSOURCES partners and TOXOSOURCES-WP3 and WP4.

The work built on previous work and models, and focused on sustainability: by making all the databases and models publicly available in connection to deliverables and publications, new data can be used to update and reduce uncertainty in the model outputs in a transparent manner. The exposure data and framework of the QMRA model will be useful also for initiatives on other pathogens with complex transmission routes. Recommendations for future studies and their reporting were formulated in the publications. The work included synergies and close collaboration with OHEJP PhD Project ToxSauQMRA and included short term visits across partner institutes.

The results of WP2 work will have substantial positive health impact – and One Health impact – at national, European and global levels. They can inform actions that will improve food safety throughout the food chain: infection control at farm level to lower prevalence in animals, processing of meat into various products, and preparing meat in homes and restaurants. These actions will improve not only human health, but also health and welfare of the animals raised for meat production or fed meat as part of their diet, as the infection can cause clinical signs also in animal hosts.

JRP22-WP2-T1 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections

The work built on national experiences from the Netherlands, and achieved its ambitious aims in regard to input data, model improvements, and application in a multi-country study in nine countries across Europe. All input data (prevalence in animals, anatomical distribution of the parasites in the hosts, consumption data, meat processing data), as well as submodels (inactivation by heating, salting, freezing and a dose-response model) were combined in the final framework of the QMRA model to obtain country-specific outputs for a wide range of food-products (Figure 3).

The developed model takes into account uncertainty in fitted model parameters (e.g. inactivation efficiency, consumption rates) and natural variation. The processing of the products was based on gathered information (WP2-T4) and modelled using inactivation models. The model output is at regional level, with country-specific consumption patterns (WP2-T3) and infection prevalence in animals (WP2-T2). Since infection with *T. gondii* is assumed to persist lifelong, 'age at first infection' and associated variables like the product, animal species, and processing steps, were chosen as outcomes for the exposure assessment: Source attribution was performed by comparing the contributions of different products to the modelled first infections. Using the age at first infection has the additional benefit that direct comparison with human seroprevalence data is possible (WP2-T5).

We present the most interesting results of the QMRA in Table 1. Across all countries, unheated salted products attribute the most. This is partly due to the high consumption, but also because in our inactivation model salting was found to be less effective than anticipated. We recommend deeper investigation into the efficacy of salting. Products that fit this preparation pattern are spreads, cured products, and dry-fermented sausages (e.g. Mettwurst, ham, salami). Second in the ranking are products with no processing or heating at all, even though they are rarely eaten. The results confirm that sufficient heat treatment almost completely eliminates the risk.

Figure 3. QMRA model structure, indicating the flow of the model steps and at what level the steps operate. The column to right specifies the data and/or sub-models used.

For each country, the distribution of age of first infection, possibly stratified by product/animal, or other properties

Attribution of infection											
Number of consumptions per person per year in brackets											
Processing			Country								
Salting	Consumer cooking	Heating at production	Czech Republic	Germany	Spain	France	The Netherlands	Poland	Denmark	Norway	Portugal
n	Medium	n	0%	0%	10% (303)	3% (66)	1% (52)	3% (119)	2% (76)	1% (106)	9% (210)
n	Rare	n	2% (5)	9% (8)	16% (39)	13% (45)	6% (7)	10% (27)	8% (15)	1% (5)	6% (11)
n	Raw	n	37% (14)	23% (3)	8% (3)	14% (7)	3% (1)	25% (6)	14% (3)	1% (1)	11% (3)
n	Well done	n	0%	1% (241)	0%	0%	3% (384)	0%	1% (386)	0%	0%
y	no cooking	n	54% (254)	65% (262)	51% (336)	55% (209)	77% (213)	59% (177)	67% (135)	36% (245)	72% (156)
y	no cooking	y	5% (42)	0%	13% (20)	8% (13)	7% (11)	2% (5)	5% (472)	61% (1693)	0%
y	Raw	n	2% (1)	0%	1% (0)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
y/n	no cooking	n	0%	2% (6)	1% (6)	7% (7)	3% (7)	1% (8)	3% (8)	0%	2% (5)

Table 2. Attribution of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection risk to different meat processing and preparation. The percentages indicate the proportion of infections attributable to a certain combination of preparation approaches (i.e. a measure of risk). Columns add up to 100%. The numbers in brackets indicate the number of consumptions per person per year (i.e. a measure of exposure).

JRP22-WP2-T2 Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* infection in animals

An extensive systematic literature review on *T. gondii* prevalence in animals across Europe, covering more than 50 animal species and including animals raised or hunted for human consumption as well as felids, was conducted. The work built on previous experiences from systematic reviews performed for EFSA and in the Baltic-Nordic region; a search strategy was developed, the retrieved records were screened, and data extracted and checked. The data were analysed using a Bayesian hierarchical model to obtain age-dependent estimates of seroprevalence by animal species in five regions, separate for indoor and outdoor husbandry, which served as key input to the QMRA. Prevalence estimates varied between species, regions, indoor/outdoor rearing, and types of detection methods applied. Prevalence data based on direct detection methods were scarce. Overall, *T. gondii* seroprevalence estimates were highest in Eastern Europe and lowest in Northern Europe.

This task included collaboration with early-career colleagues, and cross-project collaboration with OHEJP PhD project ToxSauQMRA. Related to this task, TOXOSOURCES members are also participating in another review together with the OHEJP-ORION project, focusing on risk factors for *T. gondii* infections in animals. While that information is not directly needed for the QMRA, together with the prevalence estimates it will provide important input for planning interventions at farm-level.

JRP22-WP2-T3 Quantitative exposure survey

An exposure questionnaire was developed by expanding an existing questionnaire and taking into account experiences from the Dutch National Food Consumption Survey, risk factor information from a prospective case-control study in the Netherlands, and applying categorisation of the EFSA FoodEx system, which enables comparison with other surveys. The questions were adapted to the different countries by including country/region-specific products, and sample sizes were determined (2000 or 3000 respondents per country). The questionnaires were distributed via a market research agency to collect harmonised data on food consumption and handling and exposure to oocysts from nine countries. Bayesian statistics was employed to derive probability distributions for frequency of consumption or parameters regarding preparation (e.g. cooking), which served as input data to the QMRA. The survey and its results will be useful for other pathogens with complex transmission routes. The results indicate important regional differences in consumption, and exposure, across Europe.

JRP22-WP2-T4 Overview of processing parameters for relevant meat products

Information on food consumption was collected from the EFSA FoodEx2 database, and on country/region-specific relevant products and their processing from consortium members and external experts, including in collaboration with industry. The list of products and product-specific processing parameters informed exposure survey questions. The data from the survey informed which meat products were included in the QMRA model, and the product-specific parameter values for freezing, salting and heating (e.g. time, temperature, concentration) served as key input to the model.

JRP22-WP2-T5 Review of prevalence and risk factors for human *T. gondii* infection

The experiences from TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T2, earlier work under COST-action Euro-FBP and the collaborative review with OHEJP-ORION were incorporated in the planning of this task, exemplifying One Health synergies. A total of 1822 publications were retrieved and 142 articles met the inclusion criteria. Twenty-two articles described risk factors of *T. gondii* infection, and 91 articles reported seroprevalence data. Overall seroprevalences reported in the articles varied between 9.1% and 87.6%. The results of this work addressed a specific knowledge gap expressed by ECDC, and served to validate QMRA model output, including both country-level incidence estimates and the identified main sources. The scientific manuscript is scheduled for submission in 2023.

WP3 Multicentre survey to fill the key existing gap: role of fresh produce (i.e. Ready-to-Eat salads)

TOXOSOURCES-WP3 contributed to filling the knowledge gap concerning the relevance of fresh produce contamination by *T. gondii* oocysts as an infection source for humans. TOXOSOURCES-WP3 selected the most suitable method for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce using a literature review, expert experiences, experimental evaluation and inter-laboratory comparison by ring trial. Harmonised detection was implemented among the partners. TOXOSOURCES-WP3 collected existing data on *T. gondii* oocyst prevalence in fresh produce and the environment, together with information on fresh produce (e.g. ready-to-eat (RTE) production, trading and consumption) in Europe. The data were used to design a risk-based sampling strategy for a multicentre study on *T. gondii* in fresh produce, applying the standard operating procedure (SOP) that was developed and validated (Figure 4). The multicentre study, spanning all four European regions, is the largest conducted and delivered valuable input to TOXOSOURCES-WP2 and future QMRAs, and to developing interventions.

JRP22-WP3-T1 Selection, evaluation and implementation of detection procedure for *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce

An extensive literature review and multi-attribute assessment of the different steps in molecular detection of *T. gondii* (oocyst recovery, DNA extraction and DNA amplification) was performed and complemented by a survey of expert opinions, current practices and experiences, to select the most suitable molecular method for *T. gondii* oocyst detection in fresh produce. The Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.1 summarizes this process, which provided a good starting point for developing the SOP for the multicentre study of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce. The results were published as a scientific article in early 2021.

The comparative experimental work, consisting of a parallel SOP evaluation between two partners, VRI and ISS, was completed in 2020, and instead of the planned physical technical workshops, video tutorials were produced. The work towards the SOP was reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2 and presented to relevant audiences in 2021. Following full SOP implementation by nine partners, the SOP was further validated during a ring trial conducted in 2021. The ring trial timeline was adjusted to allow all interested laboratories (higher number of laboratories than originally planned) to implement the method, and thus this task was adapted to continue some months longer than originally planned. The deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.3 describes the organisation of the ring trial. Outcomes of the work were presented at several scientific congresses and events.

JRP22-WP3-T2 Design of a risk-based sampling strategy

An extensive review of peer-reviewed literature on the prevalence of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was performed, as well as a review of the literature on *T. gondii* prevalence in the environment (soil and water) and bivalves. These were complemented by an online questionnaire to consortium partners to collate grey literature on the topic. A data summary on literature-based prevalence of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was provided to TOXOSOURCES-WP2, and the results were published as scientific publication in early 2022. The key aspects of the work and results from grey literature search were reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.4, and key results were presented at several scientific events.

The work to design of a risk-based sampling strategy for the multicentre study of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce included an online questionnaire to gather relevant information on trade and consumption of ready-to-eat salads from local and international industry. In addition, a request for information was distributed via the EFSA focal point network, and a survey on RTE salads sold locally at supermarkets across Europe was conducted. Data from the literature review and these approaches were combined to design a sampling plan, taking into account sample size calculations, feasibility and costs. The milestone of finalizing the sampling strategy was reached on time, and the final sampling

strategy was presented to the consortium at the Annual Meeting 2021, Part I. The strategy, described in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.5, was applied in WP3-T3.

JRP22-WP3-T3 Multicentre pilot survey on *T. gondii* in fresh produce in Europe

A multicentre pilot survey on the molecular detection of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce in Europe was successfully conducted. Samples were collected over one year (from October 2021 to September 2022) in ten countries representative of the four European regions according to the strategy developed in WP3-T2. Fresh produce samples were obtained from local supermarkets and analysed using the SOP defined in WP3-T1. One partner (INIAV) performed only the oocyst recovery step of the SOP, stored the processed samples frozen and delivered them to two other partners (BfR and UCM) for the molecular testing. This approach provided flexibility that supported increasing the overall number of tested samples. The final number of samples analysed was almost 3000 samples (93% of the aimed sample size), making the study the largest conducted worldwide. In addition to the original plan, qPCR positive samples were analysed by an independent nested PCR assay and sequencing to further confirm the results. Moreover, there was collaboration with TOXOSOURCES-WP5 regarding exploring suitability of these samples for genotyping using the new typing tool developed. Work of this task was reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.5 and full results are being prepared for a scientific publication scheduled for 2023. The gathered experiences and considerations are highly important for planning further studies as well as possible interventions. The results call for attention and action: In a small but non-negligible proportion of the samples, *T. gondii* DNA was detected, indicating contamination of RTE-products with the parasite, and calling for more attention to this product group as possible sources for *T. gondii* infections. It would be recommendable to establish routine testing for foodborne parasites in the RTE-salad food chain.

Figure 4. An illustration of the steps of the developed and validated method for molecular detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* contamination in fresh produce. Spiking of salads and spiked sediment samples were used to evaluate the performance across the different steps of the method in the ring trial.

WP4 Serology method based on novel antigens to discriminate *T. gondii* infections acquired from oocysts

TOXOSOURCES-WP4 explored source-attributing serology and developed and applied a framework and workflow for protein screening and development of a serological test, and reported it in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1, in an international scientific publication and in presentations at conferences. New promising antigens as well as antigens reported in previous literature to be suitable to detect oocyst-driven infections were critically evaluated, and development work of a source-attributing serological assay was conducted. The conclusion is that here is no suitable antigen identified, by TOXOSOURCES or others, that would be ready for the final assay validation steps and application to estimate the proportion of oocyst-driven infections in humans and animals.

JRP22-WP4-T1 Identification and production of *T. gondii* stage-specific antigens for source attribution

The predicted proteome of the *T. gondii* oocyst/sporozoite was analysed bioinformatically to identify the best stage-specific and antigenically relevant protein candidates. A list of 96 proteins with source-attributing potential was defined (Figure 5), including hypothetical proteins (n=45), putative oocyst wall constituents (n=24), LCCL domain-containing proteins (n=7), PAN domain-containing proteins (n=7), validated or putative microneme proteins (n=6), and SAG-related surface antigens (n=4). For this, numerous sources were used: annotated proteins and proteomes in ToxoDB-database; published parasite proteomes and transcriptomes not yet present in ToxoDB; and algorithms not implemented in ToxoDB for predicting biochemical and biophysical protein properties, like surface accessibility, hydrophilicity and solubility, and antigenicity. The main selection criteria were exclusive expression in oocysts and evidence of secretion, and prioritisation was done based on protein/transcript abundance and a high score in linear epitope prediction by two algorithms, Epidope and BepiPred2.

Cloning of genes of interest (GOIs) was attempted by PCR amplification from either a cDNA library derived from oocyst RNA, or genomic DNA where possible. As expression vectors we used plasmids that had been used previously successfully and which allowed the affinity purification of N- or C-terminally 6His-tagged proteins of interest (POIs). In some cases where no or minimal expression of soluble protein was detectable, N-terminal fusion with solubility-enhancing maltose-binding protein (MBP) was attempted. Not surprisingly with such a shot-in-the-dark approach, some were not clonable, or proved insoluble or instable. A total of 53 proteins could be amplified and cloned, of which 35 could be expressed and purified in sufficient amounts at purity suitable for the subsequent assays. In addition, three proteins described in the literature as oocyst-specific antigens, TgERP, CCp5A and OWP8, were successfully expressed to evaluate their usefulness, specificity and sensitivity.

Figure 5. TOXOSOURCES-WP4 identified (A) and cloned, expressed and purified (B) potentially oocyst/sporozoite-specific antigens of *T. gondii* that could have source-attributing potential, and explored serology to discriminate between oocyst- versus tissue cyst-driven infections by serology.

JRP22-WP4-T2 Development of a novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections;

JRP22-WP4-T2-sT1 Standardization of a POI-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and/or bradyzoite driven *T. gondii* infections using reference pig sera;

JRP22-WP4-T2-sT2 Validation of a novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA to diagnose oocysts-and/or bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections using reference sera from several relevant host species including humans

A workflow was established, published and followed for the screening of the POIs with potential for source-attributing serology. First, four panels of sera from experimentally infected pigs (one experimental infection in pigs inoculated with either oocysts or cysts, two experimental infections with pigs inoculated with oocysts) and one panel of sera from sheep experimentally inoculated with oocysts were characterized by employing a wide battery of conventional tests (ELISAs, immunofluorescence assay and western blot). The panels were provided by three partners of the consortium from unrelated studies. Two panels of pig sera and one panel of sheep sera were selected for the screening of POIs.

In the first screening step, we used a few pig sera that were analyzed by POI-based western blots. The POIs selection criteria were: i) the detection of seroconversion after the infection; ii) ability to differentiate between oocyst- vs. tissue cyst-driven infections, and ii) concordance of results regardless of the panel of pig sera analysed. After a preliminary selection of POIs, the whole panels of sera were analysed by POI based-WB and newly developed POI-based ELISAs. In addition, proteins from previous literature were analyzed by POIs-based WBs using the panels of sera.

After the first screening step, most POIs were discarded. Only the sporozoite specific proteins CCp5A, TgERP (LEA850) and SR1 (fragments SR1-central and SR1-LH2-Nterm) passed the screening and were used for the development and standardization of novel POIs-based ELISA methods. When all samples from both sera panels were analysed by the POIs-based WBs and ELISAs, some pig sera recognized the selected POIs prior to infection and just a few animals showed seroconversion. Moreover, neither CCp5A nor TgERP could discriminate between oocyst- and tissue cyst-driven infections. An increase in anti-SR1 and anti-SR1-LH2 specific IgGs was observed in pigs infected with tissue cysts, but no significant differences among groups were detected due to high individual variability. Finally, none of the POIs passed the screening with the sheep sera panel.

Additional testing was conducted to confirm the TgERP results, with focus on protein purification protocols, protein batches from different years, protein concentration per well, ELISA plate systems (including NTA-Ni based protocols) and blocking solutions, among others. Further work is needed with both SR1 protein fragments, SR1 and SR-LH2, to clarify their suitability as tissue cyst markers for animals and humans. Moreover, IgA response against the antigens deserves further research.

JRP22-WP4-T3 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-derived *T. gondii* infections in animals and in humans;

JRP22-WP4-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory validation of the POI-based ELISA; JRP22-WP4-T3-sT2 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in domestic animals (pigs, small ruminants) and wildlife (wild-boar, wild ungulates) used for human consumption;

JRP22-WP4-T3-sT3 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in humans

The pipeline designed and followed for development of a source-attributing serological tool including assessment of possible antigens did not identify a suitable antigen that would be ready for final assay validation steps. This task successfully produced concrete plans for those steps, including for interlaboratory ring trial and evaluation of diagnostic performance using field samples. The concrete plans made are ready to be taken to use. The consortium gathered experience in designing and conducting ring trials (two were conducted, in WP3 and WP5), has access to suitable sera from across

Europe and the world for exploring the relative prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in several animal species, and established new collaborations with colleagues in Serbia as well as in South-America, where several waterborne toxoplasmosis outbreaks have occurred, for access to human samples. As sending samples from human subjects is challenging, the future collaboration might focus on transfer of methodology.

WP5 Novel *T. gondii* typing method to detect within-genotype variation

By Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS), TOXOSOURCES-WP5 successfully identified highly polymorphic regions in genomes of very closely related *T. gondii* strains across Europe and established a novel typing method tailored to European needs. The work included an unprecedented effort of collecting isolates and producing and collecting WGS-data. Moreover, a ring trial focusing on the current state-of-the-art-genotyping method was organised, supporting obtaining comparable results. Progress and results were reported in Deliverables, presented to relevant scientific audiences, as well as to national and international stakeholders at a OHEJP Dissemination Workshop focusing on preparedness. The work included collaboration with early-career researchers and collaboration with OHEJP PARADISE project.

JRP22-WP5-T1 Retrieval of relevant *T. gondii* isolates or NGS-quality DNAs for NGS and NGS-MST

Toxoplasma gondii isolates, WGS-quality DNAs or WGS-data on isolates were collected from across Europe. Isolates were expanded *in vitro*, and DNA was extracted for WGS. The focus was on *T. gondii* Type II isolates, while other isolates i.e. Type I, Type III and recombinant type isolates were included as well. This retrieval of key *T. gondii* isolates or DNAs was highly successful and a total of 91 isolates were collected, markedly more than the original target. Isolates from northern and eastern European regions were first underrepresented on the list, but further efforts were successful in gathering more isolates from these regions. All DNAs were also characterised based on polymorphism of fewer markers using existing standard techniques, i.e. PCR-RFLP and microsatellite (MS) typing.

JRP22-WP5-T2 Novel, standardized high-throughput direct NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method;

WP5-T2-sT1 Whole genome sequencing (WGS) of key *T. gondii* isolates and WGS-quality DNAs;

WP5-T2-sT2 Establishment, validation and refinement of a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method

Based on sequence information obtained by WP5-T1, a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST genotyping method was successfully established and validated to distinguish between closely related *T. gondii* strains. The Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1 summarized the key steps of the establishment of the NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method.

A large number of whole genome sequences were generated and collated. In addition to WGS of 76 key *T. gondii* isolates, WGS of further isolates were obtained by collecting from public databases (n=9) and by collaboration with external partners (n=17), resulting in a total number of 102 WGS sequenced isolates. Based on the sequences, highly polymorphic marker regions (partially focusing on introns and/or particular gene regions of e.g. virulence associated genes) were identified and evaluated for suitability for the establishment of a new typing method. The higher number of sequences than originally planned proved highly beneficial for the work. For validation, the novel NGS-MLST results were compared with results of other state-of-the-art techniques (PCR-RFLP, MS typing).

A standardized workflow for the collection and analysis of NGS-MLST data on *T. gondii* was established. The novel NGS-MLST technique was applied to different types of samples, including DNA from in-vitro cultivated parasites, tissue/organ samples, paraffin-embedded material from various intermediate host species, and feline fecal samples. These samples were assessed by real time PCR to determine the specific DNA levels and typing sensitivity was correlated to DNA quantification results.

JRP22-WP5-T3 Inter-laboratory comparison and NGS-MLST pilot studies;

JRP22- WP5-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory comparison on the novel NGS-MLST method;

JRP22- -WP5-T3-sT2 Pilot studies using novel NGS-MLST method

This task designed and conducted the first international multi-laboratory ring-trial for genotyping *T. gondii*. A panel of three sets of reference samples was prepared, each addressing key aspects of genotyping.

Only one partner indicated interest to participate in a ring trial using the novel NGS-MLST genotyping method. Full-scale inter-laboratory ring-trial using the new method was therefore not reasoned at this point. Instead, the setup was used for a ring trial on the current typing standard, i.e. microsatellite typing. Five laboratories across Europe participated, three of them belonging to TOXOSOURCES consortium (UCM, SSI, FLI) and two were external partners (University of Limoges, Moredun Research Institute). This ring trial increased understanding of the MS-method and genotyping, and the outcomes support obtaining harmonised results across laboratories; the results are being finalised for publication, which will include a practical guideline. The ready, tested plan for an inter-laboratory comparison of genotyping can be used in the future for the novel NGS-MLST genotyping method and for comparing results obtained by different methods.

The established novel NGS-MLST genotyping method was applied to *T. gondii* positive samples from the field, including samples from definitive hosts, intermediate animal hosts, humans, and environment. Three specified pilot studies were conducted, based on availability of suitable isolates/DNA/samples. One study assessed *T. gondii* in cat fecal samples collected all over Germany and samples of cases of toxoplasmosis in various hosts from Eastern, Western and Southern parts of Germany. A second study focused on toxoplasmosis in squirrels in The Netherlands, and a third study on *T. gondii* in cats from various parts of Denmark. Additionally, 1396 samples (paraffin embedded materials, native tissues, oocysts and extracted DNAs) from across Europe were tested. Of these samples, 215 yielded complete typing profiles using MS-typing. The vast majority was typed as type II or type II-like (n=210); n=5 were type III *T. gondii*, and a representative sample was tested with the new NGS-MLST typing tool. Result will be published in 2023.

Figure 6. The new TOXOSOURCES NGS-based typing tool successfully separates European Toxoplasma gondii Type I, II and III, identifies exotic and recombinant strains, fingerprints T. gondii Type II, and identifies point source outbreaks by their identical typing patterns. This is a major methodological advancement, with particular importance in the European setting. The outbreaks shown were outbreaks in sheep flocks, which are of both animal health and public health importance.

2.11.4 Project self-assessment

The TOXOSOURCES consortium considers TOXOSOURCES a great success. The consortium succeeded in reaching the ambitious aims and objectives and delivering all the expected results listed in the call text, and in integrating the scientific results and advancements into important, substantial and concrete contributions to address the research question and to inform design of interventions.

- ✓ Quantitative estimates of the sources and transmission routes of *T. gondii*, as well as of the geographical differences, to inform risk management.
- ✓ Novel and improved source attribution models and methods to trace the sources and transmission routes of *T. gondii*. Baseline knowledge resources, systematic collation of the scattered available data, and improved preparedness.
- ✓ Outcomes providing an excellent basis for the development of innovative and effective interventions at national, regional, European and global levels.

The scientific level of the work was very high at global standards, and the scientific results yielded are robust and have moved the state-of-the-art of the field. The dissemination activities ensured impact at national, European and global levels. The integrative activities succeeded in making TOXOSOURCES a sustainable network that will continue beyond the funding period under OHEJP.

The track record of all (100%) Deliverables and Milestones reached by their deadlines demonstrates the efficient management of the project. The deviations of the original project plan were minor, and they were decided after careful consideration and justification:

- The 6-month extension request was reasoned and solely due to COVID-19-related challenges that affected the timelines of some of the laboratory work. The extension and related minor adjustments in internal timelines provided additional time to enhance dissemination activities for those parts of the work that were less affected by the pandemic-related challenges, which was in line with the originally planned focus on dissemination and supported the project aims.
- The meeting frequency among WP-leaders and WP-co-leaders was increased to a monthly meeting. The Annual Meeting in 2021 was divided into two parts to better align the input needs from the consortium, discussed at the meetings, with the timeline of Deliverables.
- External partners participated in selected activities that were not crucial for the project, according to their funding situation, some more and others less than originally planned. One of the originally external partner institutes, BIOR, was welcomed to the consortium as a full OHEJP partner, when the institute joined the OHEJP following an enlargement campaign. This exemplifies TOXOSOURCES as attractive, collaborative and inclusive consortium. The collaborations with colleagues outside Europe yielded a separate national funding application for source attribution of *T. gondii* in China, plans for future sample and methodology collaborations with colleagues in South America, and a successful Symposium at International Congress of Parasitology with invited speakers from overseas, sharing important experiences e.g. on ocular toxoplasmosis.
- Collection of information on production, trading and consumption of RTE-salads required additional approaches to those originally planned. The additional efforts extended the connections of the consortium to wider networks, including networks of EFSA and the industry, which was beneficial for building trust and collaboration with the industry.
- Due to COVID-19-related restrictions and considerations, some planned physical meetings had to be changed to online meetings. The kick-off meeting of TOXOSOURCES was a hybrid meeting, and the final meeting was an online meeting. Instead of the planned physical

workshops, video tutorials were produced in WP3, and a series of online meetings to discuss consensus guidelines for MS-typing were organised in WP5.

- The extensive work on source-attributing serology concluded that currently, there is no antigen identified, by TOXOSOURCES nor other groups, that allows robust estimates of the proportion of infections acquired from oocysts by serology. Thus, no pilot studies on field samples were taken to the final conduction phase. The pipeline for such studies and availability of suitable samples were successfully achieved, ready to be taken to use.
- The higher number of isolates and WGS than planned proved highly useful for the work. There was no need to test the novel typing method with spiked sample matrices because we were successful in gathering more preferred real samples in their own matrices, including oocysts in feces and paraffin-embedded and native tissues from various intermediate hosts. The ring-trial on typing was not conducted on the novel NGS-based typing tool as only one partner expressed interest, whereas the ring trial on the current state-of-the-art method, MS-typing, attracted two external laboratories in addition to consortium partners and served to test the ring trial design. The MS-typing ring trial collaboration yielded important consensus guidelines and a scientific article manuscript that is scheduled for submission for publication in 2023.

TOXOSOURCES became much more than research – integrative activities were an integrated part of the work. Together, the consortium members developed harmonised protocols, conducted large multicentre studies, collected samples and collated data. Methods were implemented at several laboratories, across sectors, and their usefulness was demonstrated by yielding comparable data. The work improved collaboration across laboratories, and substantially contributed to increasing their One Health capabilities and capacities. For example, the new typing method improved preparedness of the laboratories to detect outbreaks and emerging new strains. TOXOSOURCES contributed to training of next generations of One Health scientist by involvement of several early career colleagues in the work, and everyone in the consortium learned a lot during the project. TOXOSOURCES produced SOPs and guidelines, and formulated recommendations to different target audiences.

The international, cross-sectoral and multi-disciplinary consortium proved excellent to address all the identified gaps and to successfully deliver the work at very high scientific level. One Health approach was applied in all activities, from collaborating across sectors to developing laboratory methods suitable for samples from humans, animals and environment. TOXOSOURCES consortium attracted one new partner during the three years and the collaboration is sustainable – the consortium decided to continue the collaboration also after the OHEJP funding period, and discusses options for opening up for wider participation. Collaborations with research groups focusing on other pathogens, in particular other apicomplexan parasites, and wider aspects of food safety, such as DISH collaboration, were fruitful and supported the aims of TOXOSOURCES.

TOXOSOURCES consortium is **an example of a sustainable multidisciplinary cross-sectoral scientific One Health collaboration** established as a project with support from EU co-funding. TOXOSOURCES results are of **top scientific level at global standards** and **fully aligned with the original project objectives**. **The implementation was efficient and of high quality**, as demonstrated by the impeccable track record of all Milestones and Deliverables reached by their deadlines, and the high number of scientific outputs. **Integrative aspects** included harmonizing methods and capacity building across sectors. The harmonized methods are implemented in several laboratories across Europe, exemplifying both immediate **impact and sustainability**. TOXOSOURCES will have long-term scientific, policy and societal impact, as it improved knowledge on sources and transmission of *T. gondii* and yielded results that can directly inform design of interventions. More efficient prevention of *T. gondii* infections and toxoplasmosis across the food chain in a One Health approach will improve health, quality of life, trade and economy.

2.11.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

All (100%) Deliverables were submitted and published on Zenodo by their deadlines.

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1.1	Data Management Plan	M30	M30	Public. 10.5281/zenodo.3924450 OHEJP: available Additionally, the final DMP was published M60: https://zenodo.org/record/7497365#.Y_HnkGmZOUk	8
22	D-JRPTOXOSOURCESWP1.2	Final reports	M60	M60	Public. Final report and final DMP. https://zenodo.org/record/7497365#.Y--qlmmZOUk OHEJP: available	3
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.1	Report on prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> infection in animals	M40	M40	Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730705	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential , the Zenodo reference, other comments	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		for human consumption and cats within Europe			OHEJP: available	
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.2	Report on quantitative exposure data from survey of WP2	M48	M48	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812060#.YdVbAWjMKUk OHEJP: available	3
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.3	Report on regional variation of prevalence and risk factors of human <i>T. gondii</i> infection within Europe	M59	M59	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/7383011#.Y--rGWmZOUk OHEJP: available	5
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.4	Report on relative contribution of different sources and routes of exposure by country/region	M59	M59	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/7384280#.Y--q_WmZOUk OHEJP: available	4
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.1	Report on available analytical procedures for detection of <i>T. gondii</i> in fresh produce and list of promising analytical procedures	M28	M28	Public. 10.5281/zenodo.3778719 OHEJP: available	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2	SOP on detection of <i>T. gondii</i> in selected fresh produce matrix	M36	M36	Public. 10.5281/zenodo.4405242 OHEJP: available	2
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.3	Report on the ring trial of WP3	M40	M40	Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730717 OHEJP: available	2
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.4	Report on literature review on the prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> oocysts in fresh produce and environment	M48	M48	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812067#.YdVaomjMKUk OHEJP: available	5
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.5	Report on occurrence of <i>T. gondii</i> in selected fresh produce in different regions in Europe	M59	M59	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/7382981#.Y--rMGmZOUk OHEJP: available	4
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1 [numbering corrected, this is 4.1]	SOP for a novel source-attributing serological method	M48	M48	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812071#.YdVay2jMKUk	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
					OHEJP: available	
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.2	Report on the prevalence of oocyst-derived infections in humans and animals	M59	M59	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/7384299#.Y--qt2mZOUk OHEJP: available	2
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1	SOP for a novel NGS-MLST genotyping method of WP5	M48	M48	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812077#.YdVa22jMKUk OHEJP: available	2
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.3 [original number kept, there is no 5.2]	Report on the inter-laboratory comparison and the pilot studies of WP5	M59	M59	Public. https://zenodo.org/record/7382853#.Y--rRGmZOUk OHEJP: available	2

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

All (100%) Milestones were reached by their deadlines.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-01	Kick-off Meeting held by WP1	M26	Yes, M26	Kick-off Meeting held on 3.-4.2.2020 at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark, with possibility to attend online. Milestone reached by M26 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-02	Bioinformatic selection of oocyst/sporozoite-specific antigens completed in WP4	M28	Yes, M28	Selection done. Milestone reached by M28 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOXOURCES-03	Key isolates summarized in WP5	M30	Yes, M28	Summary list of key isolates compiled. Milestone reached by M28 (ahead of timeline).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-04	List of meat products or dishes that need to be included in exposure survey is provided by WP2-T4 to WP2-T3	M34	Yes, M34	List provided. Milestone reached by M34 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-05	Experimental selection of the appropriate methods for samples analysis in WP3	M36	Yes, M36	Experimental selection done. Milestone reached by M36 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-06	Delivery of data summary on literature-based prevalence	M36	Yes, M36	Data summary delivered.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		of <i>T. gondii</i> oocysts in fresh produce from WP3 to WP2			Milestone reached by M36 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-07	Production of the first sets of purified soluble recombinant proteins (up to 100) for WP4-T2 serological assays	M36	Yes, M36	Production started. Milestone reached by M36 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-08	Evaluation of the source attributing ability of the first sets of stage-specific antigens produced in WP4-T1	M36	Yes, M36	Evaluation started. Milestone reached by M36 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-09	Finalization of risk-based sampling strategy of WP3	M38	Yes, M38	Strategy ready by the deadline of the milestone. The sampling plan was presented to the consortium at Annual Meeting 2021, Part I. Milestone reached by M38 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-10	Country-specific estimates of prevalence in animals provided as input for QMRA	M38	Yes, M38	Input data provided. Milestone reached by M38 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-11	Questionnaires for exposure survey ready to be rolled out by WP2	M38	Yes, M38	Questionnaires finalised. Milestone reached by M38 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-12	List of meat products for which processing parameters	M40	Yes, M40	Information provided, with focus on local products included in the survey.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
		need to be collected is provided to WP2-T4			Milestone reached by M40 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-13	Exposure data from survey are provided as input for QMRA	M43	Yes, M41	Data available in M41. Milestone reached by M41 (ahead of timeline).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-14	Processing parameters for relevant meat products are provided as input for QMRA	M45	Yes, M45	Reaching this milestone was supported by the work done to identify relevant local products (synergy), and included discussions with industry. Milestone reached by M45 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-15	Country-specific estimates for prevalence of human <i>T. gondii</i> infection provided as input data for QMRA	M45	Yes, M45	Inclusion of papers in systematic review. Milestone reached by M45 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES- 16	Delivery of data summary on fresh produce consumption in EU from WP3 to WP2	M45	Yes, M45	Data delivered. Milestone reached by M45 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-17	Delivery of data summary on literature-based prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> oocysts in environment from WP3 to WP2	M45	Yes, M45	Data delivered. Milestone reached by M45 (on time).

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-18	Antigens for serological assays	M48	Yes, M48	The key antigens were delivered in batches. Milestone reached by M48 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-19	Annual Meeting held by WP1	M48	Yes, M47	Annual Meeting Part I held in M42, part II in M47. Milestone reached by M47 (ahead of timeline).
22	M-JRPTOXOSOURCES-20	Final Meeting held by WP1	M60	Yes, M59	Final meeting held in M59. Milestone reached by M59 (ahead of timeline).

2.11.6 Publications and additional outputs

All TOXOSOURCES publications are uploaded to Zenodo and made available also via TOXOSOURCES project website. Those listed below that lack a Zenodo link at the time of this report in December 2022 will be uploaded to Zenodo in the next upload batch in 2023, after the final version of the article is available.

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Contamination of Soil, Water, Fresh Produce, and Bivalve Mollusks with <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts: A Systematic Review. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10030517 https://zenodo.org/record/6351110#.YnkeCehBxwQ	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
A real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction for the specific detection of <i>Hammondia hammondi</i> and its differentiation from <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04571-8 https://zenodo.org/record/4647866#.YGNbWK8zaUk	Published	YES	NO	YES, 2190 €
Expanding the Known Repertoire of C-Type Lectin Receptors Binding to <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts Using a Modified High-Resolution Immunofluorescence Assay https://doi.org/10.1128/mSphere.01341-20 https://zenodo.org/record/4657064#.YGXUY68zaUk	Published	YES	NO	YES, 2130 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Expression of in vivo biotinylated recombinant antigens SAG1 and SAG2A from <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> for improved seroepidemiological bead-based multiplex assays https://doi.org/10.1186/s12896-020-00646-7 https://zenodo.org/record/4129949#.X6Ldr4hKjcc	Published	YES	NO	YES, 1.890 €
Fluorescent bead-based serological detection of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> infection in chickens https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04244-6 https://zenodo.org/record/3974390#.X6PV0WhKjcc	Published	YES	NO	YES, 1990 €
Infection prevention and control practices of ambulatory veterinarians: A questionnaire study in Finland https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.464 https://zenodo.org/record/4647937#.YGNfea8zaUk	Published	YES	NO	YES, 0 €
Isolation and genetic characterization of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in Spanish sheep flocks https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04275-z https://zenodo.org/record/3974417#.X6PWsWhKjcc	Published	YES	NO	YES, 1990 €
Molecular Methods for the Detection of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts in Fresh Produce: An Extensive Review	Published	YES	NO	YES, 738.89 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010167 https://zenodo.org/record/4647840#.YGNQk68zaUk				
<p>Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed <i>Besnoitia</i> species</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YHg5Z-gzaUk</p>	Published	YES	NO	YES, 2190 € Open Access funding enabled and organized by project DEAL.
<p>Isolation, Genotyping, and Mouse Virulence Characterization of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> From Free Ranging Iberian Pigs</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.604782 https://zenodo.org/record/5516873#.YUg5qOxxe70</p>	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
<p>In vivo and in vitro models show unexpected degrees of virulence among <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> type II and III isolates from sheep</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00953-7 https://zenodo.org/record/5516897#.YnkflehBxwQ</p>	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
<p>Comparison of Direct and Indirect <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Detection and Genotyping in Game: Relationship and Challenges</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9081663 https://zenodo.org/record/5516907#.YUg8qOxxe70</p>	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Zoonotic pathogens in wild muskoxen (<i>Ovibos moschatus</i>) and domestic sheep (<i>Ovis aries</i>) from Greenland https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.599 https://zenodo.org/record/5516925#.YUhCMexxe70	Published	YES	NO	YES, 1600 €
A longitudinal study of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> seroconversion on four large Danish sow farms. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109460 https://zenodo.org/record/5516957#.YUhCDexxe70	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
The disease burden of ocular toxoplasmosis in Denmark in 2019: Estimates based on laboratory testing of ocular samples and on publicly available register data https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parepi.2021.e00229 https://zenodo.org/record/5595613#.YXZegxpBy70	Published	YES	NO	YES, 1580 €
Identification of Oocyst-Driven <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Infections in Humans and Animals through Stage-Specific Serology—Current Status and Future Perspectives https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9112346 https://zenodo.org/record/5821931#.YdXABWCZOUk	Published	YES	NO	YES, 1647 €
Changes in serum biomarkers of inflammation in bovine besnoitiosis	Published	YES	NO	YES, 1555 €, covered from other funding

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04991-0 https://zenodo.org/record/5812119#.YdVZe2jMKUk				
Identification of molecular biomarkers associated with disease progression in the testis of bulls infected with <i>Besnoitia besnoiti</i> https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00974-2 https://zenodo.org/record/5812116#.YdVZo2jMKUk	Published	YES	NO	YES, 2245 €, covered from other funding
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> genetic diversity in Mediterranean dolphins https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11080909	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
Unifying virulence evaluation in <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> : a timely task https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2022.868727	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> genotyping: a closer look into Europe https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2022.842595	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
Comparative performance of five recombinant and chimeric antigens in a time-resolved fluorescence immunoassay for detection of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> infection in cats https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2022.109703	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Detection of anti- <i>Neospora caninum</i> antibodies in sheep's full-cream milk by a time-resolved fluorescence immunoassay https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109641	Published	YES	NO	YES, ND
Veterinarians as a risk group for zoonoses: exposure, knowledge and protective practices in Finland https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2021.10.008	Published	YES	NO	YES, 0€
Prevalence and molecular characterization of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in different types of poultry in Greece, associated risk factors and co-existence with <i>Eimeria</i> spp https://rdcu.be/cYyoU	E-pub ahead	YES	NO	YES, covered from project DEAL
Advances towards the complete in vitro life cycle of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	In press	YES	NO	YES, 0€
Systematic review and modelling of age-dependent prevalence of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in livestock, wildlife and felids in Europe	Submitted	YES	NO	YES, ND
Tropism and persistence of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> : from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham	Submitted	YES	NO	YES, ND

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Assessing welfare risks in unowned unsocialised domestic cats in Denmark based on associations with low body condition score	Submitted	YES	NO	YES, ND

Twenty-five scientific publications were published, several are submitted, and more are scheduled for submission in 2023. Total number of scientific publications from TOXOSOURCES will be well over 30, realistic expectation is closer to 50. This is a substantial contribution to the total scientific output of OHEJP as a whole.

All TOXOSOURCES publications are Gold Open Access, publicly available and made easily findable via the project homepage: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/jrp-toxosources/> and via Zenodo with keyword 'TOXOSOURCES': <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22TOXOSOURCES%22>. These will be updated at least three times during 2023.

Publishing scientific results from TOXOSOURCES continues until the end of the OHEJP i.e. September 2023, and budget is secured for Gold Open Access publication fees during this time to ensure FAIRness. At the end of OHEJP, list of key TOXOSOURCES publications will be compiled into summaries by topic and published on Zenodo, to further support FAIRness, in particular findability, across sectors and to specific target audiences.

Additional output

TOXOSOURCES yielded a high number of outputs, and dissemination was very active during the project implementation phase, as demonstrated by a high number of scientific publications and numerous presentations to relevant target groups including scientific audiences, reference laboratories and science-policy audiences. Further dissemination activities are scheduled for 2023, and all data will be published and made publicly available by the end of OHEJP, so that they can be used by others.

Contributions to additional scientific publications for wider scientific impact

Examples of external publications where TOXOSOURCES has collaborated, but in a role that using TOXOSOURCES funding for Gold Open Access publishing fee was not applicable. In these situations, TOXOSOURCES has advocated for and ensured that the dissemination is as FAIR as possible, e.g. by publishing key metadata on Zenodo:

Experimental infection with *Toxoplasma gondii* in broiler chickens (*Gallus domesticus*): seroconversion, tissue cyst distribution, and prophylaxis

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-020-06984-x>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4647895#.YGNbDT9JGUl>

Seroprevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* in outdoor dogs and cats in Bangkok, Thailand

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0031182021000421>
<https://zenodo.org/record/5812133#.YdVZOGjMKUk>

Molecular survey of *Besnoitia* spp. (Apicomplexa) in faeces from European wild mesocarnivores in Spain

<https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14206>
<https://zenodo.org/record/5812123#.YdVZXWjMKUk>

Development and validation of a time-resolved fluorescence immunoassay for the detection of anti-*Toxoplasma gondii* antibodies in goats

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109432>
<https://zenodo.org/record/5812135#.YdVYmmjMKUk>

A high number of invited talks, oral presentations and poster presentations to key scientific and science-policy audiences across Europe and the world

Mandagsmøde, Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology & Prevention, SSI, 2.3.2020

How and why to prevent *Toxoplasma gondii* infections

Pikka Jokelainen

Invited talk

Presentations at OHEJPASM2020, May 27-29, 2020

Source attribution for *Toxoplasma gondii* infections in Europe

Marieke Opsteegh, Hannah Morgan, Huifang Deng, Gereon Schares, Sandra Stelzer, Sara Monteiro Pires, Helga Waap, Jacek Sroka, Heidi Enemark, Jelena Srbljanovic, Olgica Djurkovic Djakovic, Chiara Trevisan, Agnetha Hofhuis, Lasse S. Vestergaard, Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van

der Giessen, Euro-FBP (COST Action FA1408), TOXOSOURCES Consortium.
Oral presentation

TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen, Marieke Opsteegh, Marco Lalle, Furio Spano, Gereon Schares, Sara Monteiro Pires, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Frank Seeber, Simone M. Cacciò, Joke van der Giessen, TOXOSOURCES Consortium

Poster, available: https://zenodo.org/record/3924468#.Y_EPrmmZOU

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham, a quantitative risk assessment

Filip DAMEK, Bastien FREMAUX, Dominique AUBERT, Marieke OPSTEEGH, Sandra VUILLERMET, Pikka JOKELAINEN, Joke VAN DER GIESSEN, Pascal BOIREAU, Isabelle VILLENA, Radu BLAGA

Poster and talk at 3-Minute-Thesis competition

OHEJP Cogwheel workshop with JPIAMR, April 28, 2020

#TOXOSOURCES *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen

Short oral presentation

Webinar '*Toxoplasma gondii* e toxoplasmosis in una prorspettiva One Health' organized by Italian Society of Parasitology (SOIPA), June 30, 2020

TOXOSOURCES – *TOXO*plasma *gondii* SOURCES quantified

P JOKELAINEN, M OPSTEEGH, M LALLE, F SPANO, G SCHARES, S MONTEIRO PIRES, A MAYER SCHOLL, F SEEBER, S M CACCIÒ, J VAN DER GIESSEN, TOXOSOURCES CONSORTIUM

Poster and short oral presentation

OHEJP Summer School August 17-28, 2020

Parasites in the food chain: global One Health risks

Wildlife and Public Health

Joke van der Giessen

Lectures

PhDay, UCM, October 14, 2020

Desarrollo de un nuevo ELISA para la detección de anticuerpos frente a *Toxoplasma gondii* en el ganado porcino

Nadia María López Ureña

Oral presentation

International One Health Webinar Series of School of Public Health and Zoonoses, Guru Angad Dev Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, India, November 5, 2020

Relative contributions of the different sources of *Toxoplasma gondii*, a globally important pathogen of major public health concern

Pikka Jokelainen

Invited talk

International Pathology Day, November 11, 2020

Endemic pathogens and international research projects during a pandemic: *Toxoplasma gondii* and international research project TOXOSOURCES as an example

Pikka Jokelainen and Martha Betson

Oral presentation

Round table: Why international knowledge sharing is a winner

Pikka Jokelainen
Roundtable panellist

ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, November 12, 2020

Toxoplasma gondii in Spanish farm animals: opening new avenues from genotype to phenotype
Mercedes Fernández-Escobar
Oral presentation

OHEJP Cogwheel workshop with SafeConsume, November 25, 2020

TOXOSOURCES - *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified
Pikka Jokelainen
Short oral presentation

15th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites, December 15, 2020

#TOXOSOURCES *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified
Pikka Jokelainen
Short oral presentation

TOXO-21 webinar, 2021

Phenotypic Characterization of *Toxoplasma gondii*: Needs for Normalization
Rafael Calero-Bernal
Oral presentation

Relative contributions of different sources of *Toxoplasma gondii*, globally important pathogen of major One Health concern

Pikka Jokelainen
Oral presentation

ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, February 18, 2021

Selection, validation and SOP development of a molecular detection method for identification of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables
Iva Slana, Nadja Bier, Borbara Bartosova, Gianluca Marucci, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Pikka Jokelainen, Marco Lalle
Oral presentation

A comparative study of the most widely used serological tests in the diagnosis of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in small ruminants

López-Ureña, Nadia María; Calero-Bernal, Rafael; Pazmiño-Bonilla, Elvis Daniel; Vázquez-Calvo, Ángela; Sánchez-Sánchez, Roberto; Ortega-Mora, Luis Miguel; Álvarez-García, Gema
Oral presentation

RSU conference, virtual/Riga, Latvia, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen
Invited oral presentation

Conference of Scandinavian-Baltic Society for Parasitology, virtual/Vilnius, Lithuania, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen
Poster presentation

OHEJP at SSI, 4.5.2021 and 3.11.2021

Pikka Jokelainen
Short oral presentations

OHEJPASM 2021, June 9-11, 2021

Lights and shades in genotyping: European *Toxoplasma gondii* needs a closer look using harmonised approaches.

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Maksimov P.; Joeres, M.; Álvarez-García, G.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Calero-Bernal, R.
Poster.

Unprecedented Whole Genome Sequencing effort reveals highly polymorphic regions in the genome of European *Toxoplasma gondii* strains.

Joeres, M.; Maksimov, P.; Tuschy, M.; Bärwald, A.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Cacciò, S.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G. Poster.

Development of a Next-Generation Sequencing-based typing method for *Toxoplasma gondii* for European needs.

Maksimov, P.; Cacciò, S.; Joeres, M.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G.
Oral presentation.

Molecular method for detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables: method selection, validation and SOP development.

Iva Slana, Nadja Bier, Borbara Bartosova, Gianluca Marucci, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Pikka Jokelainen, Marco Lalle.
Oral presentation

***Toxoplasma gondii* prevalence in animals in Europe: a systematic review.**

Filip Dámek, Helga Waap, Marieke Opsteegh, Pikka Jokelainen, Delphine Le Roux, Gunita Deksne, Huifang Deng, Gereon Schares, Arno Swart, Anna Lundén, Gema Álvarez-García, Martha Betson⁹, Rebecca Davidson, Adriana Gyorke, Sanne Stokman, Daniela Antolová, Zuzana Hurníková, Henk J. Wisselink, Jacek Sroka, Siv Klevar, Rob van Spronsen, Radu Blaga.
Poster.

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage.

Filip Dámek, Bastien Fremaux, Dominique Aubert, Marieke Opsteegh, Sandra Thoumire, Sandra Vuillermet, Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen, Pascal Boireau, Isabelle Villena, Radu Blaga.
Poster.

Conference 'Responsible Use of Antibiotics in Animals', 2021

Infection prevention and control practices among ambulatory livestock and equine veterinarians

Marie Verkola, Terhi Järvelä, Asko Järvinen, Pikka Jokelainen, Anna-Maija Virtala, Paula M. Kinnunen, Annamari Heikinheimo
Poster

ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, June 24, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen
Keynote presentation

Environmental contamination with *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts: a systematic review

López-Ureña, Nadia María‡; Chaudhry, Umer‡; Calero-Bernal, Rafael; Messina, Davide; Evangelista, Francisco; Betson, Martha; Lalle, Marco; Jokelainen, Pikka; Ortega-Mora, Luis Miguel; Álvarez-García, Gema

Oral presentation

Annual conference of the German Veterinary Medical Society, section “Parasitology and Parasitic Diseases”, 28th to 30th June 2021

Development of a next-generation sequencing-based typing method to detect within-genotype variation in *Toxoplasma gondii*

M. Joeres, P. Maksimov, M. Tuschy, A. Bärwald, F. J. Conraths, B. Koudela, R. Blaga, S. Caccio, M. Fernández-Escobar, R. Calero-Bernal, L. M. Ortega-Mora, P. Jokelainen, G. Schares

Poster

WAAVP, Dublin, Ireland, July 2021

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to dry sausage

Filip Dámek, Bastien Fremaux, Dominique Aubert, Marieke Opsteegh, Sandra Thoumire, Sandra Vuillermet, Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen, Pascal Boireau, Isabelle Villena, Radu Blaga

Poster

***Toxoplasma gondii* prevalence in animals in Europe: a systematic review**

Filip Dámek, Helga Waap, Marieke Opsteegh, Pikka Jokelainen, Delphine Le Roux, Gunita Deksné, Huifang Deng, Gereon Schares, Arno Swart, Anna Lundén, Gema Álvarez-García, Martha Betson, Rebecca Davidson, Adriana Gyorke, Sanne Stokman, Daniela Antolová, Zuzana Hurníková, Henk Wisselink, Jacek Sroka, Siv Klevar, Rob van Spronsen, Radu Blaga

Poster

Endoparasites of feral cats in Denmark

Stine Thorsø Nielsen, Ida Sofie Thuesen, Søren Saxmose Nielsen, Peter Sandøe, Pikka Jokelainen, Christen Rune Stensvold, Michelle Bitsch Hardy, Nikoline Johansson, Heidi Huus Petersen, Stig Milan Thamsborg, Helena Mejer

Poster

International workshop on molecular methods for *T. gondii* during summer 2021

Several teachers and participants from TOXOSOURCES.

One Health session of Project Review Module of ECDC’s EPIET and EUPHEM programmes, August 25, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen. Project presentation, chairing, participation in round table.

Zoonoses 2021 – International Symposium on Zoonoses Research “From Disease Ecology to SARS-CoV-2; Berlin, October 13-15, 2021

Identification of oocyst-driven *Toxoplasma gondii* infections through stage-specific serology – concepts and challenges

Gema Álvarez García; Rebecca Davidson; Siv Klevar; Pikka Jokelainen; Luis Miguel Ortega Mora; Furio Spano; Frank Seeber

Poster

13th European Multicollloquium of Parasitology EMOP2020. Belgrade, Serbia, 12-16.10.2021

Wildlife as sentinels and indicators for transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii*

Pikka Jokelainen
Invited talk (duo talk with Dr. Shapiro)

Risk ranking and evaluation of surveillance systems for foodborne parasites in Europe.
Joke van der Giessen

Public Health impact of foodborne parasite in a One Health approach
Joke van der Giessen

TOXOSOURCES: *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified
Pikka Jokelainen

***Toxoplasma gondii* seroprevalence in European wildlife: a systematic review**

Filip DÁMEK, Helga WAAP, Marieke OPSTEEGH, Arno SWART, Pikka JOKELAINEN, Delphine LE ROUX, Gunita DEKSNE, Huifang DENG, Gereon SCHARES, Anna LUNDÉN, Gema ÁLVAREZ-GARCÍA, Martha BETSON, Rebecca DAVIDSON, Adriana GYÖRKE, Sanne STOKMAN, Daniela ANTOLOVÁ, Zuzana HURNÍKOVÁ, Henk J. WISSELINK, Jacek SROKA, Siv KLEVAR, Rob van SPRONSEN, Radu BLAGA

Tropism of *Toxoplasma gondii* in the tissues of experimentally infected pigs

Filip Dámek, Břetislav Koudela, Sandra Thoumire, Anaëlle da Silva, Josef Kameník, Radu Blaga

Environmental contamination with *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts: a systematic review

Nadia María LÓPEZ UREÑA[‡], Umer CHAUDHRY[‡], Rafael CALERO BERNAL, Davide MESSINA, Francisco EVANGELISTA, Martha BETSON, Marco LALLE, Pikka JOKELAINEN, Luis Miguel ORTEGA MORA, Gema ÁLVAREZ GARCÍA

Comparative study of the serological tests used for the diagnosis of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in domestic pigs

Nadia María LÓPEZ UREÑA[‡], Rafael CALERO BERNAL, Ángela VÁZQUEZ CALVO, Patricia VÁZQUEZ ARBAIZAR, Nuria GONZÁLEZ FERNÁNDEZ, Radu BLAGA, Břetislav KOUDELA, Luis Miguel ORTEGA MORA, Gema ÁLVAREZ GARCÍA

Genome-wide single nucleotide variation in *Toxoplasma gondii* type II isolates from Europe. Maksimov, P.; Caccio, S.; Joeres, M.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G.
Oral presentation

Molecular method for detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables: method selection, validation and SOP development.

Gianluca MARUCCI, Iva SLANA, Nadja BIER, Barbora BARTOSOVA, Anne MAYER-SCHOLL, Pikka JOKELAINEN, Marco LALLE.
Oral presentation

DISCONTTOOLS seminar 20.10.2021

DISCONTTOOLS expert group on zoonotic toxoplasmosis: many gaps identified, new diagnostics developments and vaccines are necessary for effective intervention
G. Schares, L. Ortega-Mora, F. Katzer, A. Heckerroth, H. Sager, J. Gutierrez, P. Jokelainen, P. Deplazes, L. H. Kramer

V SIMBRATOX -Brazilian Symposium of Toxoplasmosis and II SINTOX -International Symposium of Toxoplasmosis. Universidade Federal Rural de Rio de Janeiro. November, 2021

Calero-Bernal, R. Invited speech: Methodologies for the study of *Toxoplasma gondii* genetic population structure: future perspectives.

16th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites, 24.11.2021 (online)

Multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii* infections in Europe
Marieke Opsteegh

Serology method based on stage-specific antigens to discriminate *T. gondii* infections acquired from oocysts

Furio Spano

A novel NGS-MLST typing method to detect *T. gondii* within-genotype variation at the European level

G. Schares, M. Joeres, P. Maksimov, M. Tuschy, A. Bärwald, F. J. Conraths, D. Höper, S. Calvelage, B. Koudela, R. Blaga, M. Fernández-Escobar, R. Calero-Bernal, L. M. Ortega-Mora, S. Caccio, P. Jokelainen

SFP-SFMM October 28-29, 2021, Lyon, France

Toxoplasma gondii seroprevalence in selected animal species in Europe: a systematic review
Filip DÁMEK, Helga WAAP, Marieke OPSTEEGH, Arno SWART, Pikka JOKELAINEN, Delphine LE ROUX, Gunita DEKSNE, Huifang DENG, Gereon SCHARÉS, Anna LUNDÉN, Gema ÁLVAREZ-GARCÍA, Martha BETSON, Rebecca DAVIDSON, Adriana GYÖRKE, Sanne STOKMAN, Daniela ANTOLOVÁ, Zuzana HURNÍKOVÁ, Henk WISSELINK, Jacek SROKA, Siv KLEVAR, Rob van SPRONSEN, Radu BLAGA and Pascal BOIREAU

Journée Sciences de la Vie, February 16, 2022, Créteil, France

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to dry sausage
Filip Dámek, Bastien Fremaux, Dominique Aubert, Marieke Opsteegh, Sandra Thoumire, Sandra Vuillermet, Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen, Pascal Boireau, Isabelle Villena, Radu Blaga

Poster presentation and talk at 3-Minute-Thesis competition

OHEJPASM2021, Orvieto, Italy, 11-13 April 2022

A European exposure survey to assess the risk of toxoplasmosis TOXOSOURCES-WP2

Marieke Opsteegh

Oral presentation

Modelling of the age-dependent prevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* in livestock, wildlife and felines

Filip DÁMEK (ANSES, FR), Marieke OPSTEEGH (RIVM, NL), Helga WAAP (INIAV, PT), Pikka JOKELAINEN (SSI, DK), Delphine LE ROUX (ANSES, FR), Gunita DEKSNE (BIOR, LV), Huifang DENG (RIVM, NL), Gereon SCHARÉS (FLI, DE), Anna LUNDÉN (SVA, SE), Gema ÁLVAREZ-GARCÍA (UCM, ES), Martha BETSON (UNIS, UK), Rebecca DAVIDSON (NVI, NO), Adriana GYÖRKE (USAMVCN, RO), Daniela ANTOLOVÁ (SAV, SK), Zuzana HURNÍKOVÁ (SAV, SK), Henk J. WISSELINK (WBVR, NL), Jacek SROKA (NVRI, PL), Siv KLEVAR (NVI, NO), Rob van SPRONSEN (RIVM, NL), Radu BLAGA (ANSES, FR), Arno SWART (RIVM, NL)

Poster

Molecular method for detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables: inter-laboratory SOP validation and field application

Gianluca Marucci, Nadja Bier, Martha Betson, Rafael Calero-Bernal, Gema Alvarez-Garcia, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Pikka Jokelainen, TOXOSOURCES Ring Trial and Survey participants, Marco Lalle.

Poster

Contamination of soil, water, fresh produce and bivalve mollusks with *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts: a systematic review

López-Ureña, N.M.; Chaudhry, U.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Cano-Alsua, S.; Messina, D.; Evangelista, F.; Betson, M.; Lalle, M.; Jokelainen, P.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Álvarez-García, G.

Microbiology Society Annual Conference 2022, Belfast, 4-7.4.2022

Toxoplasma gondii, a globally important parasite of One Health concern

Pikka Jokelainen

Invited keynote talk

VIII VETINDOC PhDay Faculty of Veterinary Sciences, Complutense University of Madrid, 2022

Avances en el desarrollo de métodos serológicos con potencial para diferenciar entre infecciones inducidas por ooquistes o quistes tisulares de *Toxoplasma gondii*

Nadia María López Ureña

Oral presentation, that was awarded the second award of the best oral communication

Parasitology Symposium, 18.5.2022

Quantitative microbial risk assessment for *Toxoplasma gondii* infections

Marieke Opsteegh

German Veterinary Medical Society, section “Parasitology and Parasitic Diseases” 23. - 25.05.2022, Berlin, Germany

A novel Ion AmpliSeq-based typing method of *Toxoplasma gondii* reveals an excellent typing resolution among European type II strains

M. Joeres, P. Maksimov, D. Höper, S. Calvelage, R. Calero-Bernal, Fernández-Escobar, B. Koudela, R. Blaga, M. Globokar Vrhovec, K. Stollberg, N. Bier, S. Sotiraki, J. Sroka, W. Piotrowska, P. Kodym, W. Basso, F. J. Conraths, M. L. Darde, F. Spano, S. Caccio, L. M. Ortega-Mora, P. Jokelainen, G. Schares

Oral presentation

A ring trial to harmonize *Toxoplasma gondii* microsatellite typing provides the basis for a comparative analysis of results obtained in five European research laboratories

M. Joeres, G. Cardron, K. Passebosc-Faure, N. Plault, M. Fernández-Escobar, C. Hamilton, L. O’Brien-Anderson, R. Calero-Bernal, P. Maksimov, F. J. Conraths, M. L. Darde, H. Vedel Nielsen, L. M. Ortega-Mora, P. Jokelainen, A. Mercier, G. Schares

Poster

XVI International Congress on Toxoplasmosis and *Toxoplasma gondii* Research. Riverside, California, USA, 2022

Advancing source attributing *Toxoplasma gondii* serology.

López-Ureña, N.M.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.; Koudela, B.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Jokelainen, P.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Álvarez-García, G.

Oral presentation

Quantifying sources of *Toxoplasma gondii* exposure in Europe

Pikka Jokelainen
Oral presentation

The 2nd International Workshop on Environmental Toxoplasmosis 2022, USA

Quantifying sources of *Toxoplasma gondii* exposure in Europe
Pikka Jokelainen
Invited talk

Advancing source attributing *Toxoplasma gondii* serology.

López-Ureña, N.M.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.; Koudela, B.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Jokelainen, P.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Álvarez-García, G.
Oral presentation

OHEJP research seminar at DTU-FOOD, 15.6.2022

Presentation of OHEJP parasitology projects
Pikka Jokelainen
Oral presentation

ONE2022 Health, Environment, Society EFSA Conference. Brussels, Belgium. 21-24.6.2022

Consumer habits in nine European countries captured to assess the risk of foodborne infections
Marieke Opsteegh (RIVM), Arno Swart (RIVM), Nadja Bier (BfR), Anne Mayer-Scholl (BfR), Gereon Schares (FLI), Solveig Jore (FHI), Rebecca Davidson (NVI), Helga Waap (INIAV), Rafael Calero Bernal (UCM), Gema Alvarez Garcia (UCM), Radu Blaga (ANSES), Filip Damek (ANSES), Sara Monteiro Pires (DTU), Christen Rune Stensvold (SSI), Jacek Sroka (NVRI), Mirosław Rozycki (NVRI), Břetislav Koudela (VRI), Jurgen Chardon (RIVM), Elisa Benincà (RIVM), Mattijs de Haas (RIVM), Marco Lalle (ISS), Jakob Ottoson (SLV), Joke van der Giessen (RIVM), Pikka Jokelainen (SSI)
Poster. Available: [Poster Gallery | ONE Conference 2022 \(one2022.eu\)](#)

International Conference of SafeConsume 27-28.6.2022

Toxoplasma gondii sources
Pikka Jokelainen
Invited oral presentation and round table discussion about DISH

15th International Congress of Parasitology, ICOPA2022, Copenhagen, Denmark, August 2022

Symposium organised by TOXOSOURCES: TOXOSOURCES.
TOXOSOURCES project
WP leaders and co-leaders.
Short oral presentations. Video on demand.

Symposium organised by TOXOSOURCES: One Health EJP parasitology projects.

TOXOSOURCES
Pikka Jokelainen and Joke van der Giessen.
Oral presentation. Video on demand.

Symposium organised by TOXOSOURCES: From genotype to phenotype: importance of genotyping to understand virulence and infection epidemiology of *Toxoplasma gondii*.

Needs on the implementation of harmonised procedures to better evaluate *Toxoplasma gondii* virulence.

Calero-Bernal, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Katzer, F.; Su, C.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.
Oral presentation.

Genotyping *Toxoplasma*: whole genome sequences of isolates across Europe reveal more diversity within European type II than expected

Maksimov, P.; Angulo-Lara, P.; Galal, L.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Mercier, A.; Lorenzi, H.; Joeres, M.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Globokar-Vorhovec, M.; Stollberg, K.; Bier, N.; Sotiraki, S.; Sroka, J.; Piotrowska, W.; Kodym, P.; Basso, W.; Conraths, F.J.; Dardé, M.L.; Spano, F.; Vatta, P.; Cacciò, S.; Jokelainen, P.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Schares, G.

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND MODELLING OF AGE-DEPENDENT PREVALENCE OF *TOXOPLASMA GONDII* IN LIVESTOCK, WILDLIFE AND FELIDS IN EUROPE

Filip DÁMEK (ANSES, FR), Marieke OPSTEEGH (RIVM, NL), Helga WAAP (INIAP, PT), Pikka JOKELAINEN (SSI, DK), Delphine LE ROUX (ANSES, FR), Gunita DEKSNE (BIOR, LV), Huifang DENG (RIVM, NL), Gereon SCHARÉS (FLI, DE), Anna LUNDÉN (SVA, SE), Gema ÁLVAREZ-GARCÍA (UCM, ES), Martha BETSON (UNIS, UK), Rebecca DAVIDSON (NVI, NO), Adriana GYÖRKE (USAMVCN, RO), Daniela ANTOLOVÁ (SAV, SK), Zuzana HURNÍKOVÁ (SAV, SK), Henk J. WISSELINK (WBVR, NL), Jacek SROKA (NVRI, PL), Siv KLEVAR (NVI, NO), Rob van SPRONSEN (RIVM, NL), Radu BLAGA (ANSES, FR), Arno SWART (RIVM, NL)

Oral presentation

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to dry sausage

Filip Dámek, Bastien Fremaux, Dominique Aubert, Marieke Opsteegh, Sandra Thoumire, Maxime Delsart, Sandra Vuillermet, Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen, Pascal Boireau, Isabelle Villena, Radu Blaga

Oral presentation

Detailed anatomical distribution of *Toxoplasma gondii* in tissues of experimentally infected pigs

Filip Dámek, Bastien Fremaux, Dominique Aubert, Sandra Thoumire, Sandra Vuillermet, Isabelle Villena, Radu Blaga

Oral presentation

Molecular method for detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables: inter-laboratory SOP validation and multicentre field application.

Gianluca Marucci, Nadja Bier, Alessia Possenti, Martha Betson, Rafael Calero-Bernal, Nadia María López Ureña, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Pikka Jokelainen, Marco Lalle

Oral presentation

A novel ion amplicon-based typing method of *Toxoplasma gondii* reveals an excellent typing resolution among type II strains

Joeres, M.; Maksimov, P.; Höper, D.; Calvelage, S.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Globokar-Vrhovec, M.; Stollberg, K.; Bier, N.; Sotiraki, S.; Sroka, J.; Piotrowska, W.; Kodym, P.; Basso, W.; Conraths, F.J.; Dardé, M.L.; Spano, F.; Cacciò, S.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G.

Poster

Progress on the development of a source-attributing diagnostic tool of *Toxoplasma gondii* infections

López-Ureña, N.M.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.; Koudela, B.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Jokelainen, P.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Álvarez-García, G.

Poster

EHFG2022 European Health Forum Gastein 27.9.2022

Co-creating better food systems in Europe.

Pikka Jokelainen

Video available: [Co-creating better food systems in Europe - YouTube](#)

DISH lunches, online workshop series (April 6, 2022, October 12, 2022)

Pikka Jokelainen

Co-organiser, panellist

Meeting of the Dutch clinical parasitology working group (NVP-WVP) and the working group medical microbiology (WAMM), 20 September 2022

One-health in parasitology at RIVM: *Toxoplasma* epidemiology and source attribution as example

Titia Kortbeek and Marieke Opsteegh

Future Self-Care in Europe – Copenhagen Meeting organized by SCiE, 19-20.9.2022

Round table discussion on empowerment and health literacy with focus on AMR and One Health

Pikka Jokelainen

Food Quality and Safety Summit, CII, India, 23.9.2022

Foodborne parasites as One Health challenges

Pikka Jokelainen

Oral presentation

6th International Meeting on Apicomplexa in Farm Animals: Apicowplexa, 5-7 October 2022, Bern, Switzerland

Toxoplasma gondii genotypes in Europe—a lot we know—a lot we do not know

Schares, G.; Joeres, M.; Cardron, G.; Maksimov, P.; Angulo-Lara, P.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Koudela, B.; Vatta, P.; Cacciò, S.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P. Keynote presentation

In vitro and in vivo models for the evaluation of *Toxoplasma gondii* strain virulence

Calero-Bernal, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Katzer, F.; Su, C.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.

Keynote presentation

Systematic review and modelling of the age-dependent prevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* in livestock, wild-life and felids in Europe

Filip DÁMEK (ANSES, FR), Marieke OPSTEEGH (RIVM, NL), Helga WAAP (INIAV, PT), Pikka JOKELAINEN (SSI, DK), Delphine LE ROUX (ANSES, FR), Gunita DEKSNE (BIOR, LV), Huifang DENG (RIVM, NL), Gereon SCHARES (FLI, DE), Anna LUNDÉN (SVA, SE), Gema ÁLVAREZ-GARCÍA (UCM, ES), Martha BETSON (UNIS, UK), Rebecca DAVIDSON (NVI, NO), Adriana GYÖRKE (USAMVCN, RO), Daniela ANTOLOVÁ (SAV, SK), Zuzana HURNÍKOVÁ (SAV, SK), Henk J. WISSELINK (WBVR, NL), Jacek SROKA (NVRI, PL), Siv KLEVAR (NVI, NO), Rob van SPRONSEN (RIVM, NL), Radu BLAGA (ANSES, FR), Arno SWART (RIVM, NL)

Oral presentation

In search of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocyst-specific proteins with source-attributing usefulness: key steps and limitations

López-Ureña, N.M.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.; Koudela, B.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Jokelainen, P.; Regidor-Cerrillo, J.; Diezma-Diaz, C.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Álvarez-García, G.

Oral presentation

In vitro assay to determine inactivation of *Toxoplasma gondii* in meat samples

Marieke Opsteegh

Oral presentation

Genetic diversity of *Toxoplasma gondii* in the endangered Iberian lynx (*Lynx pardinus*)

Calero-Bernal, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Salas, M.; Nájera, F.; Crespo, E.; García-Talens, A.; Grande-Gómez, R.; Peña, J.; Palacios, M.J.; González-Barrio, D.; Habela, M.Á.; Caballero-Gómez, J.; Zorrilla, I.; Fernández-Verón, I.; López, G.; Salcedo, J.; García-Bocanegra, I.; Álvarez-García, G.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.

Poster

Anti-*Toxoplasma gondii* antibodies in European residents within the last 20 years: A systematic review and meta-analysis

Calero-Bernal, R.; Gennari, S.M.; Cano-Alsua, S.; Ríos, A.; Álvarez-García, G.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.

Poster

Development, inter-laboratory SOP evaluation and application of a molecular method for detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in ready-to-eat leafy-green salads in a multicentre study in Europe

Barbora Zalewska

Poster

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to dry sausage

Filip Dámek, Bastien Fremaux, Dominique Aubert, Marieke Opsteegh, Sandra Thoumire, Delphine Le Roux, Sandra Vuillermet, Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen, Pascal Boireau, Maxime Delsart, Isabelle Villena, Radu Blaga

Poster

Meat processing as part of a quantitative microbial risk assessment for *Toxoplasma gondii* infections in Europe

Marieke Opsteegh

Poster

Detailed anatomical distribution of *Toxoplasma gondii* in tissues of infected pigs

Filip Dámek, Bastien Fremaux, Dominique Aubert, Sandra Thoumire, Delphine Le Roux, Sandra Vuillermet, Maxime Delsart, Isabelle Villena, Radu Blaga

Poster

Comparison of *Toxoplasma gondii* distribution in tissues of experimentally infected pigs

Filip Dámek, Břetislav Koudela, Sandra Thoumire, Anaëlle Da Silva, Josef Kameník, Radu Blaga

Poster

Genotyping *Toxoplasma gondii*: whole genome sequences of isolates across Europe reveal diversity within European type II strains

Pavlo Maksimov

Poster

Typing of European *Toxoplasma gondii* type II strains by a novel Ion AmpliSeq-based technique

Maike Joeres

Poster

Meat processing as part of a quantitative microbial risk assessment for *Toxoplasma gondii* infections in Europe

Arno Swart, Filip Dámek, Elisa Benincà, Axel Bonačić Marinović, Jakob Ottoson, Jurgen Chardon, Radu Blaga, Helga Waap, Břetislav Koudela, Jacek Sroka, Nadja Bier, Gereon Schares, Solveig Jore, Rebecca Davidson, Rafael Calero-Bernal, Gema Alvarez Garcia, Christen Rune Stensvold, Mirosław Rozyck, Sara Monteiro Pires, Joke van der Giessen, Pikka Jokelainen, Marieke Opsteegh

Poster

DEVELOPMENT, INTER-LABORATORY SOP EVALUATION AND APPLICATION OF A MOLECULAR METHOD FOR DETECTION OF *TOXOPLASMA GONDII* OOCYSTS IN READY-TO-EAT LEAFY-GREEN SALADS IN A MULTICENTRE STUDY IN EUROPE

Nadja S. Bier, Rebecca D. Berg, Rafael Calero-Bernal, Martha Betson, Umer Chaudhry, Filip Damek, Rebecca Davidson, Gema Alvarez-Garcia, Gro Johannessen, Pikka Jokelainen, Nadia María López-Ureña, Gianluca Marucci, Anne Mayer-Scholl, Weronika Piotrowska, Alessia Possenti, Jacek Sroka, Helga Waap, Barbora Zalewska, Marco Lalle

Poster

European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites 17th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites, Rome, Italy, 15-16 September 2022

European multicenter survey of *Toxoplasma gondii* contamination in ready-to-eat salads

Marco Lalle

Oral presentation

Journée Sciences de la Vie, October 19, 2022, Paris-Bercy, France

MODELLING OF THE AGE-DEPENDENT PREVALENCE OF *TOXOPLASMA GONDII* IN LIVESTOCK, WILDLIFE AND FELINES

Filip Dámek, Marieke Opsteegh, Helga Waap, Pikka Jokelainen, Delphine Le Roux, Gunita Deksné, Huifang Deng, Gereon Schares, Radu Blaga, Arno Swart, on behalf of the OH EJP TOXOSOURCES consortium

Poster

XVIII Congreso Colombiano de Parasitología e Medicina Tropical, 30.11.-3.12.2022, Bogota, Colombia

Pikka Jokelainen

Invited plenary talk. (Figure 7)

Figure 7. TOXOSOURCES Project Leader Pikka Jokelainen, invited plenary talk at XVIII Congreso Colombiano de Parasitología e Medicina Tropical, Bogota, Colombia, December 2022.

OHEJP Final School 5-7 December 2022

Sustainability in One Health – experiences from multidisciplinary TOXOSOURCES project

Pikka Jokelainen

Invited talk

FoodSafety4EU Pre-forum: Towards the EU Food Safety Forum. The new sustainability regulation: how to integrate it into food safety. Brussels 15.12.2023

Pikka Jokelainen

Short oral presentation and discussion

Article published: ["Towards the EU Food Safety Forum: shaping together the new collaborative platform" FoodSafety4EU PRE-FORUM 2022 "The new sustainability regulation: how to integrate it into food safety?" | Zenodo](#)

Artistic collaboration for innovative dissemination to general public

Pikka Jokelainen, scientific support to artwork about *Toxoplasma gondii*:

Anni Puolakka: From the Heart (2021)

Single channel video, duration 14:14

The work was commissioned by Jyväskylä Art Museum (Jyväskylä, Finland), and has been also shown at Tampere Film Festival (Tampere, Finland), Baltic Triennial (Vilnius, Lithuania), and HAM gallery/Helsinki Art Museum (Helsinki, Finland).

<http://annipuolakka.com/fromtheheart/>

Examples of other activities for visibility and dissemination

#TOXOSOURCES has been used on social media:

<https://twitter.com/hashtag/toxosources?f=live>

Participation in #WomenInScience tweet of OHEJP 11.2.2021

Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen

Interviewed to Pathologist-journal

Pikka Jokelainen

Interview for article in Finnish Cat Association on feline toxoplasmosis
Pikka Jokelainen

Contribution to Danish zoonosis report 2022
Pikka Jokelainen, Henrik Vedel Nielsen

Examples of communication by TOXOSOURCES partner institutes, including in local languages

<https://www.ssi.dk/aktuelt/nyhedsbreve/epi-nyt/2020/uge-4---2020>

https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Forsch/EJP_OH2020.html

<https://www.sva.se/forskning/internationellt-samarbete/europeisk-samverkan-kring-livsmedelsburna-smittor/toxosources-ett-one-health-ejp-projekt/>

https://www.bfr.bund.de/en/toxoplasma_gondii_sources_quantified_ejp_toxosource_-_249310.html

<https://www.iss.it/en/web/iss-en/-/news-1>

Highlights of contributions to training the next generations of One Health researchers

TOXOSOURCES created an inspiring scientific collaboration where early career researchers were welcomed as part of the team. Particularly the following four colleagues had major roles and contributed substantially to the work and dissemination activities:

PhD candidate: Filip Dámek (ANSES) – part of OHEJP PhD programme

Title: ToxSauQMRA: Study of the tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham, a quantitative microbiological risk assessment

PhD candidate: Nadia María López Ureña (UCM)

Title: *Toxoplasma gondii* detection in fresh produce and development of novel serological tools for source attribution.

PhD defended in 2021: Mercedes Fernández Escobar (UCM)

Title: Genetic and phenotypic characterization of *Toxoplasma gondii* isolates obtained from sheep and Iberian pigs in Spain

PhD candidate: Maike Joeres (FLI)

Title: Development and application of a next-generation sequencing-based typing method to detect within-genotype variation in *Toxoplasma gondii*

TOXOSOURCES consortium has been mentioned by others as **exemplary in being productive and disseminating its outputs and outcomes**. A particularly highlighted aspect has been that details of the different steps of the work, including scientific reasoning for the decisions made, have been transparently published as public Deliverables during the work. The high number of scientific publications and the high number of presentations to scientific and science-policy audiences ensure scientific, policy and societal impact.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc. Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, WOA, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

TOXOSOURCES answered its research question and the key outcomes are **the estimates of contribution of different sources to human *T. gondii* infections**. These are of high interest to various stakeholders at national, European and global levels. Moreover, key outcomes and outputs of interest to various audiences include data and fitted distributions from exposure survey, meat processing data, Bayesian hierarchical model for age-dependent seroprevalence, quantitative risk assessment model, SOPs of new methods, guidelines, and whole genome sequences of high number of *T. gondii* strains across Europe. Several outcomes from the transparent step-by-step approaches have also proven to be of interest to different audiences. For example, the databases of systematic reviews of WP2-T2 and WP2-T5 were shared with Julius Kühn-Institut to develop a machine learning-based tool that can support screening process within CADIMA-software.

Major target audience which has been efficiently reached is the scientific community, but TOXOSOURCES has also targeted the general public in its communication, also using new approaches. An example of innovative approaches was provision of scientific support to the production of a short film about *T. gondii*, which has been shown at museums and film festivals. DISH collaboration has supported widening the scope of interested audiences to include various stakeholders involved in shaping future food safety in Europe and globally, including e.g. NGOs, social scientists, and national and European organisations. TOXOSOURCES results are important also for occupational health specialists, as some professions, such as veterinarians, can be exposed in their work.

The developed and validated method for detection of *T. gondii* in fresh produce is now fully implemented in several laboratories across Europe. Harmonising and improving genotyping across laboratories improved preparedness of the laboratories to trace sources in outbreaks and to detect newly emerging strains. TOXOSOURCES partners include the European reference laboratory (EURL) for parasites, and the network of national reference laboratories was efficiently used for dissemination.

Outcomes of TOXOSOURCES an excellent basis for the development of innovative and effective interventions at national, regional, European and global levels, and there has been interest among stakeholders of all levels. Of particular relevance are the following key points from each WP:

- TOXOSOURCES consortium is an example of a sustainable multidisciplinary cross-sectoral scientific One Health collaboration established with support from EU co-funding.
- Quantitative estimates of the sources and transmission routes of *T. gondii*, as well as of the geographical differences, can efficiently inform risk management and improve food safety and health. Across all countries, unheated salted meat products attribute the most to *T. gondii* infections. This is partly due to the high consumption, but also because in the inactivation model salting was found to be less effective than anticipated. We recommend deeper investigation into the efficacy of salting. Second in the ranking are products with no processing or heating at all, even though they are rarely eaten. The results confirm that sufficient heat treatment almost completely eliminates all risk.
- Considering the robust and cost-effective SOP for *T. gondii* detection in fresh produce that TOXOSOURCES developed and the demonstration of the parasite's DNA in RTE salads, indicating a risk for consumers, it would be recommendable to establish routine testing for foodborne parasites in the RTE-salad food chain. Such testing is in place for bacterial

pathogens, but currently not for parasites. TOXOSOURCES outcomes on this matter are directly usable for efficient science to regulatory policy translation.

- TOXOSOURCES substantially advanced science in the field of source-attributing serology. Future efforts exploring source-attributing serology should consider high-throughput cloning strategies and/or synthetic genes followed by in situ expression methods, which require substantial budget but could circumvent several of the encountered challenges.
- Major contribution to the scientific community was the unprecedented whole genome sequencing effort conducted. The MS-typing ring-trial and guideline will support more laboratories to start genotyping, and complemented with the novel method the work in TOXOSOURCES improved preparedness for tracing sources in outbreaks and for detecting emerging strains.

2.11.7 One Health impact

TOXOSOURCES consortium is a uniquely strong example of what a One Health consortium with complementary expertise can achieve. One Health approach was used in all activities, which was a very positive learning experience for everyone involved, across seniority levels. TOXOSOURCES contributed substantially to training of the next generations of One Health researchers.

The results of TOXOSOURCES are of relevance to national, European and international stakeholders. The results have been discussed at Stakeholder Committee meeting, Dissemination Workshop and POC/PMC meeting targeting national stakeholders. There are several examples of impact at national level. For example, a risk profile of foodborne parasites was compiled by the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration. In the Netherlands, the results were communicated with the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport which provided co-funding for TOXOSOURCES as well as to the preceding QMRA work. An example of impact at global level is that TOXOSOURCES project leader was invited to contribute to FAO Guidelines for surveillance of *Toxoplasma gondii*/toxoplasmosis in livestock. The developed and harmonized methods were applied to samples from humans, animals, and environment, and are implemented in laboratories across sectors, across Europe.

TOXOSOURCES consortium established fruitful collaborations with other projects, including projects within OHEJP (ToxSauQMRA, MEmE, PARADISE), and many outside OHEJP. Impactful collaborations include the DISH project cluster (policy and societal impact, shaping future food safety), collaborations with research groups focusing on other apicomplexan parasites (scientific impact via collaborations and synergies), and collaborations with groups focusing on risk assessment (improved approaches), disease burden estimation (baseline data and expertise) and occupational health of specific groups (e.g. veterinarians).

Collaborations with food industry (Interest Group and different networks) were active across relevant food types. The consortium reached out to industry contacts to obtain information for designing the multicentre study on RTE salads. For validating the meat processing data, TOXOSOURCES collaborated with industry representatives via the Liaison Centre for the Meat Processing Industry in the European Union (CLITRAVI). Moreover, in the Netherlands a Private-Public-Partnership project with the aim to study inactivation of *T. gondii* by salt is ongoing. These data will be implemented in the QMRA model developed within TOXOSOURCES, and the results can inform new risk mitigation strategies, in balance with policies to reduce overall salt intake and aiming for healthy, safe and sustainable diets. DISH collaboration can be useful for disseminating these outcomes to relevant audiences at European level.

The results of TOXOSOURCES will have substantial positive One Health impact at national, European and global levels. The results can inform actions that will improve food safety throughout the food chain: from improving infection prevention and control at farm level to lower prevalence in animals to

risk mitigation in the production and processing of fresh produce, processing of meat into various products and preparing food in homes and restaurants. The evidence-based actions will improve not only human health, but also health and welfare of the animals raised for meat production or fed meat as part of their diets, as the infection can cause clinical disease also in animal hosts.

2.11.8 Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan (DMP) of TOXOSOURCES is available on Zenodo and via TOXOSOURCES website. TOXOSOURCES project leader participates in DMP committee of OHEJP.

[Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1.1 Data Management Plan FINAL VERSION | Zenodo](#)

2.11.9 Future dissemination activities

Several scientific publications are scheduled for 2023, and budget has been moved from Y5 budget to Y6 budget for the Open Access publication fees. At the end of OHEJP in September 2023, list of key TOXOSOURCES publications will be compiled into summaries by topic and published on Zenodo, to further support their FAIRness, in particular findability, across sectors. DISH collaboration continues. TOXOSOURCES colleagues are involved in the organization of the 17th International Congress on Toxoplasmosis which will be held in Berlin, Germany, in May 2024.

It has been very useful for TOXOSOURCES to be part of OHEJP, and the consortium will take benefit of the support to dissemination provided by the OHEJP also during 2023. Specifically, updates to the project website have been agreed with the OHEJP Communications Team, and a presentation will be prepared to the Stakeholders Conference of OHEJP.

TOXOSOURCES consortium will continue the collaboration, and dissemination of its outputs and outcomes, for several years. Hopefully further funding will be found to ensure efficient longer-term continuation and widening of the collaboration. Acknowledgement to the original TOXOSOURCES under OHEJP will be always highlighted. The project period under OHEJP 2020-2022 was when the zoonotic parasite *T. gondii* was addressed by an international cross-sectoral multidisciplinary One Health approach – now known as TOXOSOURCES approach – for the first time in the world.

TOXOSOURCES implementation period was from January 2020 to December 2022. The consortium continues collaboration, and has already identified possible opportunities for future funding.

Further dissemination activities are scheduled for 2023, including scientific publications, invited talks, scientific presentations, and making all data publicly available by the end of OHEJP.

2.12 JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS

2.12.1 Consortium composition

Projectleader: Eelco Franz (RIVM) / Dariusz Wasyl (Piwet)

WP2 lead / co-lead: Marianne Chemaly (ANSES) / Julio Alvarez (VISAVET)

WP3 lead / co-lead: Roan Pijnacker (RIVM) / Nina van Goethem (Sciensano)

WP4 lead / co-lead: Eva Litrup (SSI) / Maria Pardos de la Gandara (Int. Pasteur)

WP5 lead/ co-lead: Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM) / Nina van Goethem (Sciensano)

2.12.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The objective of the ADONIS project was to identify determinants underlying the stagnation/reversal of the decreasing trend in Salmonella Enteritidis incidence in humans and poultry in the EU. This will deliver stakeholders and policy makers with anchor points to at least prevent a continued stagnation or even a re-establishment a decreasing trend in Salmonella incidence in humans and poultry.

On the primary production it was concluded that there are some variations both in the way National Control Programs (NCPs) are implemented as well as on the underlying poultry populations tested that could influence the performance of the surveillance activities. Even though implementation of NCPs and their auditing by the EU have improved over the 12 years, room for improvement in both areas was also identified, including sampling, laboratory testing, reporting, restrictions and measures taken along the food chain, as well as evaluation of NSCPs progress.

On the epidemiology level it was shown that in the Netherlands and Belgium the incidence of S. Enteritidis shows an upward trend from 2015 onwards. Statistical modelling also showed that the increased occurrence of potential outbreaks and invasive infections since 2015 might only partially explain the observed reversal of the trend. In addition, on the EU level we noticed a significant increase in number of outbreaks between 2015 and 2019, which was mainly caused by an increase in Eastern Europe related to S. Enteritidis (and eggs). Finally, neither changes in surveillance in systems of human salmonellosis or changes in human exposure to Salmonella Enteritidis through the consumption of eggs are likely to explain the observed changes in the S. Enteritidis epidemiology.

On the pathogen level the genomic clustering revealed the split of the European Enteritidis into roughly two major clades with little structuring by collection date, source, or country of isolation. No strong evidence of a split between populations of S. Enteritidis before and after the stagnating trend in Europe. Comparative genomic of S. Enteritidis revealed the wide-spread presence of a large international group of plasmids carrying β -lactam resistance genes in humans, animals and food. We also detected prophages specific for some genetic clusters, although their impact on the phenotype/virulence is not clear yet. In-vivo virulence assays showed an emergence in recent years of more virulent strains of Enteritidis in Europe. These could be a contributing factor in explaining the stagnation on the decreasing trend in human salmonellosis due to Enteritidis, however these more virulent strains appear randomly in otherwise closely related genomic clusters, and can therefore not be responsible for the major change in the Enteritidis decline observed.

Finally, a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) showed the rankings of the potential determinants and options for intervention for the stagnating SE trend in Europe pointed consistently to the level of poultry health and production. Salmonella control activities in poultry are harmonised across the EU for many years, but our results suggest that further improvements may be necessary for some countries.

In summary, we conclude that more efforts should be undertaken to control Salmonella in the EU in order to re-establish a decrease in incidence. We determined that the most relevant anchor points for the rankings of the potential determinants and options for intervention for the stagnating SE trend in Europe consistently pointed to the level of poultry health and production.

2.12.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Project coordination and administration

WP1-T1 coordination and project management

The project was coordinated by the RIVM; which took care of overall project leadership, overall project financials, and reporting of year reports and deliverables. Regular meetings with WP leaders were organized throughout the duration of the project. During this meetings the list of milestones and deliverables (incl. the timelines) were systematically discussed.

WP1-T2 Organisation consortium meetings

On January 15 and 16 (2020) the kickoff meeting of the EJP JRP ADONIS was held at RIVM (Bilthoven, The Netherlands). The meeting was generally perceived as very pleasant and constructive. After short introductions of people and institutes short presentations were given on the project management and the individual WPs (according to the project plan). The afternoon and the next day were used to fine-tune the plans per WP and to make agreements. This was done in break-out sessions where so-called X-matrices were constructed. These matrices consists of 4 quadrants (long-term objectives, tasks belonging to these objectives, milestones/deliverables relate to these, and actual actions to be taken in order to reach those). This way clear working plans per WP were made. These matrices help to get an overview of tasks, milestones/deliverables/ and actions per WP and serve as direct input for every meeting.

Final meeting was organised in hybrid mode in Pulawy, Poland (1st/2nd Dec. 2022). Altogether, over 40 participants contributed to the meeting, both on-site and on-line. Besides partner institutions delegates, invited representants of stakeholders' agencies (EFSA and ECDC) actively participated in the discussion on outcomes on the project and further dissemination steps.

WP1-T3 Reporting

RIVM lead the on-time delivery of 9 months and 12 months reports the OHEJP consortium. All progress reports have been delivered.

WP2 Salmonella controls at the primary production level

WP2-T1 Comparative analysis of Salmonella controls and management levels at MSs level

The objective of this task was to characterise the way National Control Programs (NCPs) are implemented on the primary production in Europe and to identify potential factors associated with an increased probability of detection that would help to understand the trends in detection in poultry in Europe. A survey describing the implementation of NCP in laying hen flocks conducted in collaboration with official veterinary services in France, the Netherlands, Poland, Spain and United Kingdom revealed different dynamics in the populations subjected to the program (increase in number of animals/flocks, changes in predominant production types with a decrease in the relative importance of caged flocks in all countries, etc.), although program measures implemented were largely homogeneous. Still, several data gaps such as availability of different types of data on controls performed by food business operators and information on vaccination status were also identified. These factors could have a limited but hard to quantify effect on the performance of the NCPs. The evaluation of the reports from

audits conducted by the European Commission on the NCPs revealed the existence of a wide range of possible (generally minor) deficiencies in the implementation of these programs in most countries, with recommendations more often being directed towards issues observed at the poultry farm level, although a positive overall trend in the way programs were implemented was observed.

Finally, the detailed analysis of NCP data from two EU countries (Spain and France) for multiple years revealed that several characteristics of the farm, the flock and the sampling were associated with the sampling outcome. In Spain the location of the farm, the production type of the flock (caged vs. non-caged), the age of the animals and who collected the samples (national authorities vs. food business operators), which samples were collected (faeces vs. boot swabs and dust samples) and when they were collected (time of the year) were associated with the probability of finding Salmonella in laying hen flocks, although a clear trend over time was not observed, with risk of positivity remaining at similar levels over the 2016-2020 period. Altogether the sampler (CA vs. FBOp) had the strongest influence on the outcome of the sampling conducted even after the effect of other possible confounders was taken into consideration, pointing at factors not considered explicitly in the model. A similar analysis to the Spanish study was carried out on results of the Salmonella national control plan (SNCP) in France. The study was carried out using data from 130,026 sampling events (designated as 'control') taking place in 6,778 laying hen houses in France from 01/01/2013 to 31/12/2021. Results were reported at poultry house level with no further information on poultry flock (size, age, vaccination status). The outcome of interest was the detection of a Salmonella target serovar STS (SE, ST and its monophasic variants) on at least one of the samples obtained during a control performed in a poultry house. Over 130,026 controls, 977 controls led to the detection of STS (0.75%). The frequency of positive controls increased steadily over the studied period from 0.51% in 2013 to 1.02% in 2020. The probability of obtaining a positive control was modelled using a multivariate mixed logistic regression model taking into account repeated controls in the poultry houses. Explanatory variables were related to the poultry house (localisation, type of housing system) and to the control (date of sampling, sampling operator, number and types of samples). The risk of a positive control was related to the poultry house localisation, with a higher risk in Eastern and South-eastern regions in relation to Western regions. Similarly, a higher risk of positivity was observed for samplings conducted in caged housing system compared to floor/free-range/organic production types. At the control level, the odds of detecting Salmonella were much higher when samplings were conducted by the competent authorities (CA), when more than 5 samples were taken and in the later months of the year (Jul-December). Certain years were marked by a higher risk of STS detection as in 2016, 2020 and 2021. The sensitivity of the final model was $Se=0.97$ and the specificity $Sp=0.77$. This study is the first one to analyse the results of the SNCP in laying hen flocks since the EU regulation came into force in France in 2011. We observed an impact of sampling conditions (sampler, number of samples) on the risk of Salmonella detection but also the effect of the housing system, caged system being more at risk than the on-floor, free-ranged and organic systems. These results are of interest to improve preventive measures implemented in the frame of the Salmonella national control plan.

This work is described in two deliverables focused on the survey on NCPs implemented in different Member States (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6107543>) and on the analysis of NCP data from Spain (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6811500>).

Part of this work has been submitted for publication

In addition to the above activities, the 38 country audit reports available at https://ec.europa.eu/food/audits-analysis/audit_reports/index.cfm (as of 4th 2020) were blindly (country/year hidden) and subjectively analysed for key messages (both positive and negative) and audit recommendations. The overall audit conclusion is that NSCPs were implemented and improved during 2008 – 2019 due to the MSs' efforts and allocated resources. The intensity of auditing declined over the study period (55% audits 1st half-period (2008 – 2013), 45% in 2nd, only 2 countries visited yearly over the last 4 years; four countries never visited). Not all audits targeted all 5 poultry production sectors covered by the EU legislation. The decreasing number of audit recommendations

(63% in 1st half-period, 37% in 2nd) shows the improvement of NSCPs. On the other hand, only 7 (18,4%) reports include a positive adjective (i.e. “correctly” or “well”) in the overall conclusions and just 2 reports do not contain a negative message.

Of nearly 250 recommendations given, less than half (47%) is based on the EU legislation directly referring to NSCPs, particularly sampling, testing, or control measures. The others address official controls at the national level (20%) or Salmonella controls in general (16%). More than half (55%) of recommendations address issues observed at the farm level (NSCP implementation, sampling, biosecurity, and control measures). The other issues are related to official controls and NSCP implementation (18%), diagnostic problems at the laboratory level (9%), and incongruent legislation (8%). The quality and in-depth of the recommendations differ considerably (i.e. refers to specific paragraphs in a specific piece of legislation versus ambiguous and unspecific ones). Since 2015 the reports relate recommendations with specific findings and conclusions (good practice). Some audits cumulate several regulations into a single recommendation whereas other reports multiply the same issue into several recommendations based on a separate legal base.

It is concluded that both the implementation of NSCP and the auditing process have improved over the 12 years, although there is still room for improvement in both areas. A clear definition of the legal basis (the list of EU legislation) and areas (i.e. check-list for MS’ self-evaluation and auditor guidance) would enhance the efficacy and harmonisation of Salmonella controls in poultry. The observed stagnation of the downward trend in Salmonella human infections provides the rationale to increase the intensity of auditing. An algorithm accounting for the size of national poultry production, and the performance of NSCPs (i.e. meeting the community targets and the frequency of Salmonella spp detection in foods) might be useful to indicate the frequency of audits in a specific country. Moreover, all Member States should be enrolled in the process due to the fact that even a small infection source on top of the poultry production pyramid and poultry products for a limited regional market might contribute to the overall human salmonellosis epidemiology.

WP2-T2 Comparative analysis of Salmonella controls and management levels at farm level

Within the WP2 of the project, we completed a literature review on available data on sampling protocols for Salmonella in laying hens. The review aimed to gain insight in the performance of different sampling procedures for detection of Salmonella in laying hens, based on results reported in literature. This can either be experimental infections, or field data. We aimed to identify the most reliable procedures using qualitative and quantitative information, that can be recommended for their standardised application within monitoring programmes. In total 924 abstracts were screened, resulting in selection of 87 and 18 publications for a qualitative and quantitative analysis respectively.

Results of the qualitative analysis revealed heterogeneity in the execution of sampling both the laying hens and environmental samples as described in the reviewed research publications. The most frequent environmental matrices were faeces and dust, however their sample sizes and sampling locations were highly variable and often poorly described. The quantitative analysis aimed initially to compare the detection ability of different environmental sampling procedures, relative to prevalence of infection in the flock. However, high variability in both the samples taken at animals level (this limits quantification of prevalence) and the environmental sampling matrices impeded the analysis. As a result a relative comparison of environmental sampling matrices between each other was performed, which included the available information on hens prevalence as a covariate in the applied mixed effect model. The results revealed that in caged flocks the probability of detection was higher when using dust samples than faeces (OR=1.3, p=0.002). In non-cage housing system however, dust had lower probability of detection than faeces (Interaction Dust : System OR=0.54, p<0.001). Overall, detection of Salmonella increased with an increase in the prevalence in hens irrespective of the sampling method using environmental matrices (OR=1.01, p<0.001).

While revising the publications it was found that the culture method was often incompletely described. Not all publications followed or at least described execution of ISO 6579 completely. Because detection

of Salmonella is not only affected by the sampling procedure, but also by the culture method we added such data extraction to our review. Our results revealed that different steps of culture methods as described in ISO 6579 have been widely applied, however variation from this ISO method was common. It is difficult to say to what extent these variations affected the final result for detection of Salmonella, but the estimate is that it had a limited impact in comparison to the sampling strategy.

The ultimate aim of this review was to identify the most reliable procedures that can be recommended for their standardised application within monitoring programmes. Unfortunately, data were very limited because the methods used were often insufficiently described, and when available there was a wide variation in both quantities of matrices and locations sampled. As a result based on extracted data from the literature it is difficult to advice on the best method to sample laying hens.

[A manuscript from this study is under preparation for publication in a scientific journal.](#)

WP2-T3 On farm surveys

The obtained data give a picture of the laying hens in Poland over the last two years (Fig. 1). Based on data received from breeders of laying hens running farms in the territory of the Republic of Poland (wielkopolskie, małopolskie, dolnośląskie, łódzkie and mazowieckie Voivodships).The survey was conducted on 31 laying hen farms in the country. These areas currently have the largest number of such farms in Poland, therefore they were taken into account in the survey. Based on the data obtained from the herds participating in the survey, we can estimate that almost 70.8% of the surveyed herds are herds kept in the rearing cage type. The next place is mulch farming with the number of about 17% of the surveyed flocks. Laying hens kept in the free-range rearing system in Poland account for about 6%. On the other hand, flocks of laying hens included in organic production/ecological production are by far the least numerous group - only 3.1% of such flocks were recorded in the survey.

Fig. 1 Types of commercial laying hen farms in Poland

The results regarding the epidemiological situation in Poland provided by the General Veterinary Inspectorate do not show which herds were vaccinated. However, the data obtained during the survey in flocks of laying hens in the country (PL) show that all flocks for which the survey was conducted were subject to prophylactic vaccination against Salmonella. Laying hen flocks in the study ranged from 2,400 to 5,200 per flock. There was no positive Salmonella infection in the data obtained from the survey, all flocks surveyed were free of infection. The laying hen farms participating in the survey showed strong biosecurity at the farm level (disinfection of poultry buildings and all transport equipment), and monitoring of farms at each stage of poultry production in the production cycle. The Republic of Poland national programs of eradication of certain Salmonella serotypes in breeding flocks of Gallus gallus have been implemented since 2007. Salmonella infection control programs are in place at all farms participating in the survey. On farms surveyed, synbiotic products (prebiotics/probiotics) colonizing the digestive tract with beneficial bacterial flora were often used. Synbiotic preparations containing probiotics, prebiotics, vitamins and microelements as well as herbal extracts, essential oils and garlic extracts were used. These farms also used substances such as acidifying the contents of the digestive tract. The surveyed farms have implemented and respected quality systems such as: Good

Hygienic Practice (GHP), Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point (HACCP).

WP2-T4 Synthesis of regulation and surveillance practices

The work performed within the different tasks of WP2 on the analysis of NSCP at the Member State (MS) level of participating partners (Spain, France, Poland, United Kingdom and the Netherlands) led to conclusions and recommendations that can be formulated based on the findings listed below:

Several characteristics of the farms and flocks included in the monitoring activities performed in the NSCP as well as of the samplings themselves were associated with an increased probability of finding a positive result in the two countries for which data were available (Spain and France). This suggests that these characteristics should be carefully considered when interpreting the results from NSCPs and, in particular, when assessing temporal trends, since according to the survey conducted in all MS where WP2 partners were located the prevalence of some of these potential risk factors (for detection and/or *Salmonella* infection) is changing in the poultry population in the countries subjected to the studies conducted in WP2 (such as the increasing proportion of non-caged flocks observed in the last years for all countries assessed). Among these, the following are particularly relevant:

- Cage systems had a higher probability of yielding positive results for *Salmonella* compared with other categories (floor, free-range and organic) in samplings conducted in Spain and France, which is also in agreement with the baseline study conducted in France in 2005.
- Samplings conducted by the competent authorities (CA) in laying hen flocks were also more often positive than those conducted by food business operators (FBOp), in agreement with results found in NSCP conducted in broilers and turkeys. This result held even when accounting for other possible confounders (such as previous results in the flock, housing system of the flocks, age of the birds or sample types), suggesting the existence of other non-controlled factors that should be further investigated. This is of great importance since NSCP largely rely on samplings conducted by FBOp (every 15 weeks) since they represent a large proportion of all samplings conducted in laying hens, which means that if they fail to detect *Salmonella* infection could lead to an underestimation of the true prevalence in laying hen flocks.
- Other risk factors associated with increased probability of positive results (age of the birds, number of samples collected, type of sample) have been previously described, but their effect highlight the importance of taking them into consideration when assessing changes in the epidemiological situation over the years.
- The close relationship between some of these risk factors (such as e.g. sample type and housing type, with certain types of samples being preferentially collected in certain type of systems) makes difficult the assessment of their impact on the sensitivity of the samplings conducted. Nevertheless, results obtained suggest that the evaluation of the sensitivity of the sampling strategies conducted in the frame of NSCPs should take into account the housing systems. Based on a relative comparison of results obtained in France, in non-cage housing systems, faeces seem to be superior to dust samples. For caged systems, dust showed better results. However, since the EU plans to phase out caged animal farming, this may be less relevant in the future.
- Vaccination was identified as a key measure in the decrease observed in the prevalence of *Salmonella* infection in laying hen flocks in the last decades. However, there was a paucity of good quality data regarding the coverage and specific vaccination protocols used in laying hens in MS for which information was collected, what should be addressed in order to fully understand the impact that this practice may still have in the trends observed in poultry production.

- Faeces and dust were the most frequently environmental matrices described in the literature. The definition of these matrices was variably interpreted (differences in type and size of the samples). Sampling methods to detect *Salmonella* in laying hens are often insufficiently described in the literature.

There is room for improvement regarding reporting of the methods used in control programs, through a thorough assessment of good quality data on the results obtained in the samplings conducted. A prerequisite for this is that data should be collected in a consistent manner (ideally across MS) and include several farms, flocks and sampling characteristics identified in this WP. This will help to improve *Salmonella* detection from sampling to laboratory analysis by considering these factors supported by collecting data to fill the gaps identified (i.e. sample size, sample type, housing type, entity in charge of the sampling (CA vs. FBOp)). Altogether, this will help to assess whether there is an underestimation of the prevalence of infection in poultry flocks that could explain the different rates of positivity depending on factors such as the sampler.

Auditing of SCP implementation confirms Member States' efforts and resource allocation on *Salmonella* controls on the primary production stage. Although over a decade-long experience in the implementation of SCPs show steady improvement, only few audits confirm full congruence with the legal requirements. The room for improvement includes sampling, laboratory testing, reporting, restrictions and measures taken along the food chain (including outbreak analyses), as well as evaluation of NSCPs progress. The above is in agreement with the recommendations listed above.

Similar to the SCPs implementation, also the auditing process evolved over the years. The recent reports link the observed deficiencies with legal requirements. Nevertheless, the auditing might be intensified and improved with clear criteria for MS selection linked with the national scale of poultry production, meeting of community targets, and clear legal criteria for audited areas (i.e. self-evaluation checklist).

This has been published in the Deliverable D-JRP26-WP2.3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7431578>)

WP3 Surveillance, epidemiology and exposure

WP3-T1 Evaluation of surveillance systems

The objective of this task was to describe and evaluate Member States (MS) national surveillance systems for *Salmonella* Enteritidis in humans, using an adapted version of the 2014 ECDC evaluation framework of public health surveillance systems, to assess whether the recent plateau of *S. Enteritidis* cases could be related to changes in the performance of the human surveillance systems and/or diagnostic standards that are in place. Evaluations of surveillance systems (although time consuming and often difficult) in recurrent cycles is highly recommended in order to correctly interpret incidence over time and conduct comparisons between countries. Surveillance systems of The Netherlands and Belgium were described and evaluated for two time periods (2008-2013 and 2014-2019), before and after the levelling of the decreasing trend, to identify whether changes in the surveillance systems could explain the observed *S. Enteritidis* trend. The key elements that were described included surveillance objectives, surveillance type (e.g. event-based, monitoring), surveillance characteristics (e.g. passive *versus* active, compulsory *versus* voluntary), data source(s), data flow, population under surveillance, geographic resolution, period and frequency of data collection, case definition(s), and diagnostic tests used. Key attributes that were evaluated were internal validity (e.g. coding errors), internal completeness (e.g. missing information), external completeness / sensitivity (i.e. percentage of cases captured by the surveillance system), and representativeness (e.g. geographical area covered). Overall, there was no indication that the levelling off of the decreasing *S. Enteritidis* trend in the Netherlands and Belgium could be due to changes in the *Salmonella* surveillance system.

This work is described in a joint deliverable combining D-JRPFZ-4-WP3.1 and D-JRPFZ-4-WP3.3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6226393>)

The evaluation of the Belgian surveillance system has been published as: Nina Van Goethem et al. Coverage of the national surveillance system for human Salmonella infections, Belgium, 2016-2020. PLOS ONE: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820>

WP3-T2 Assessment of changes in the epidemiology of human *S. Enteritidis* infections

Incidence of salmonellosis. With this task we aimed at describing temporal changes in the incidence of SE human infection between 2006 and 2019, and to determine whether the trend would change if corrected for changes in e.g. age distribution of the underlying population or the proportion of travel-related cases. Data on culture-confirmed SE human infections from national surveillance registries in the Netherlands and Belgium between 2006 and 2019, and Spain between 2007 and 2017, were analysed using multivariable negative-binomial regression models with restricted cubic splines. SE incidence was significantly higher in summer and autumn than winter, in persons aged 0–4 years and 5–14 years than in persons ≥ 60 years, and increased with increasing proportions of travel-related and resistant SE infections. SE incidence decreased significantly in both countries until 2015, followed by an increasing trend, which was particularly pronounced in the Netherlands (fig. 2). Potential SE outbreaks in both countries and invasive infections in the Netherlands also increased after 2015. Although an increase in invasive infections and potential outbreaks may play a role in the reversal of the SE incidence, they cannot fully explain it. Interestingly, for Spain, a different trend was observed, with the SE incidence stabilizing around 2010 to 2014, but decreasing before and after that time period. The SE trend from Spain as reported in the ECDC Surveillance Atlas of Infectious Disease has a different trend than the SE data used in these analyses. Since 2013/2014, the SE incidence has increased according to the ECDC report, similar to what was observed for the Netherlands and Belgium. However, here we describe a decrease in the same time period. The most likely reason is that human salmonellosis became a notifiable disease in 2015 in Spain, leading to an increase in the number of laboratories reporting SE cases since 2015. For our analyses, we therefore only used data from laboratories that reported throughout the study period. This would be particularly important to investigate for countries contributing most SE cases to the total number of cases in the EU/EEA. These include for example Czechia, reporting around 25% of all SE cases in the EU/EEA, and Poland, which only started reporting SE cases since 2017, accounting for almost 20% of SE cases since then.

The European Union One Health Zoonoses Reports for 2020 and 2021 show the lesson learned from COVID-19 pandemic. The 2020 lockdowns, intense sanitations and disinfections, followed by relaxations of restrictions in 2021 resulted in the decrease of general public exposure to foodborne pathogens, including Salmonella, and its subsequent increase. This real-life and drastic experience provides opportunities to study factors underlying the Salmonella epidemiology leading to reduced exposure (incl. consumers' awareness and education).

This work is described in a joint deliverable combining -JRP26-WP3.2 and D-JRP26-WP3.4: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7082442>

This work is published in: Chanamé Pinedo Linda, Franz Eelco, van den Beld Maaïke, Van Goethem Nina, Mattheus Wesley, Veldman Kees, Bosch Thijs, Mughini-Gras Lapo, Pijnacker Roan. Changing epidemiology of Salmonella Enteritidis human infections in the Netherlands and Belgium, 2006 to 2019: a registry-based population study. Euro Surveill. 2022;27(38). <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.38.2101174>

Fig. 2. Changes over time in the incidence of *Salmonella Enteritidis* (SE) human infection, with 2006 as reference year, in the Netherlands and Belgium, 2006–2019

Source attribution at

EU level using outbreak data [in collaboration with the OHEJP research project DISCOVER]. To prioritize interventions, it is important to keep abreast of the sources and trends of salmonellosis outbreaks. The objective of this study was to determine the main food sources and recent trends of *Salmonella* outbreaks in Europe. *Salmonella* outbreak data from 34 European countries in 2015–2019 were obtained from the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). For the source attribution analysis, implicated foods were categorized according to EFSA's zoonosis catalogue classification scheme. An established probabilistic source attribution model was applied using the information on the implicated foods, overall and by region and serotype. To assess significant trends in outbreak occurrence, overall and by region and serotype, mixed-effects Poisson models were used. Overall, the most important food source of salmonellosis outbreaks was eggs (33 %, 95 % Uncertainty Interval [UI]: 31–36 %), followed by pork (7 %, 95 % UI: 6–8 %), and (general) meat products (6 %, 95 % UI: 5–8 %) (Fig. 3). While eggs were the most important food source in all regions, pork was the second most common food source in Northern and Western Europe, and (general) meat products in Eastern and Southern Europe. Outbreaks caused by *S. Enteritidis* (SE) and other known serotypes (other than SE and *S. Typhimurium* and its monophasic variant [STM]) were mostly attributed to eggs (37 %, 95 % UI: 34–41 % and 17 %, 95 % UI: 11–25 %, respectively), whereas outbreaks caused by STM were mainly attributed to pork (34 %, 95 % UI: 27–42 %). Overall, there was a significant increase in the number of outbreaks reported between 2015 and 2019, by 5 % on average per year (Incidence Rate Ratio [IRR]: 1.05, 95 % Confidence Interval [CI]: 1.01–1.09). This was driven by a significantly increased number of outbreaks in Eastern Europe, particularly those caused by SE (IRR: 1.15, 95 % CI: 1.09–1.22), whereas in Northern and Southern Europe, outbreaks caused by SE decreased significantly from 2015 to 2019 (IRR: 0.72, 95 % CI: 0.61–0.85; IRR: 0.70, 95 % CI: 0.62–0.79, respectively) (Fig. 4). Regional, temporal and serotype-associated differences in the relative contributions of the different sources were also observed.

Fig 3. Proportions of human salmonellosis outbreaks attributed to simple and unknown (including complex) food sources by year with their respective 95 % uncertainty intervals in Europe, 2015–2019.

Fig 4. Annual trends of human salmonellosis outbreaks by serotype per each European region based on the mixed-effects Poisson regression model with a three-way interaction term between year, European region, and serotype (2015–2019).

This work is published in: Chanamé Pinedo Linda, Lapo Mughini Gras, Eelco Franz, Tine Hald, Sara Pires. 2022. Sources and trends of human salmonellosis in Europe, 2015–2019: An analysis of outbreak data. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* Volume 379, 16 October 2022, 109850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2022.109850>

WP3-T3 Reservoir output load exposure assessment

In this task, the association between human exposure to Salmonella Enteritidis (SE) through chicken eggs and the number of human salmonellosis cases was explored. The rationale was that changes in human exposure to SE could potentially explain the levelling off of the decreasing trend of human SE cases in Europe. For the exposure assessment, a simplified approach of the pre-treatment load was used, which was calculated as the product of egg SE prevalence and egg consumption rate. Due to the limited availability of egg SE prevalence data, we also investigated the suitability of laying hen flock level SE prevalence as a proxy for egg SE prevalence. However, the correlation between the two was limited, and flock level SE prevalence was therefore not included in further analysis.

Annual data on egg SE prevalence could only be obtained from Spain. Pooled sample egg SE prevalence's from Spain were first transformed to annual egg SE prevalence's. Next, annual egg SE prevalence was compared with the annual incidence rate of salmonellosis in Spain. We found a weak correlation between the pre-treatment SE load and the number of human SE cases, which indicates that changes in human exposure to SE through consumption of chicken eggs cannot explain the

stagnating SE incidence in humans. However, several other factors could be at play that we could not take into account, such as: the obtained dataset on egg SE prevalence in Spain is not representative for the true egg SE prevalence in Spain; egg SE prevalence was measured on the shell of the egg and not for the content, which might not fully represent the true human SE exposure; humans might be exposed to SE via other transmission routes than chicken eggs. This study also looked at the importance of SE exposure from imported eggs, but that seemed to be negligible for Spain as eggs mainly originated from in-land.

We found no indication that the changing trend in human salmonellosis incidence is related to changes human exposure to SE from chicken eggs. However, data availability was limited, and analyses could only be performed for Spain, of which it is unknown whether results are generalizable to other countries. Therefore, based on results in this study, we could not fully determine whether the EU-wide reversal of the decreasing SE trend in humans could be due to changes in exposure to SE through eggs

This work is described in deliverable D-JRPFZ-4-WP3.5: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7082418>

WP4 Salmonella genomics

WP4-T1 Collection overview

All partners are involved in WP4, especially in the collection of sequences. An inventory was created to get an overview of the available strains and sequences at each partner institution. The inventories were collated and presented at a meeting, where a decision was made on the final selection of strains to be sequenced for the genomic analyses. The need of a MTA for sharing the sequences in order to analyse them in different partner laboratories, has significantly delayed the completion of the sequence sharing. All sequences were available for all partners medio 2021. The dataset collected for the project comprised 1867 genomes. Of these, 1814 have passed the quality control. The seven loci MLST typing indicated the presence of several sequence types, but 1769 genomes were ST11. The genomes of ST11 was used in the following analyses. The distribution of the isolates per source and country of isolation indicated a good coverage of the participating countries for the animal, environmental, food and human isolates (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Distribution of isolates according to country and source of isolation.

WP4-T2 Population structure and comparative genomics

The single-linkage hierarchical agglomerative clustering based on cgMLST revealed the split of the European Enteritidis into roughly two major clades with little structuring by collection date, source, or country of isolation (Fig. 6). A few small clusters were detected that were specific to a certain country or host or time-period.

cgMLST silhc

Figure 6: Single linkage hierarchical clustering tree, annotated with the country, source and year of isolation.

All samples were then screened for phages using ProphET on all samples and for further identification also PHASTER. Comparative analysis performed on the collection detected two prophages that were specific for the two major clades respectively. Some smaller clusters were also detected that contained prophages particular to these clusters. Among these was a cluster consisting of 86 isolates of human and poultry origin from several countries. Some strains containing these clade and cluster specific prophages were selected to be investigated in WP4-T4.

Plasmids in the collection were also investigated. Even though Enteritidis is usually pansusceptible, resistance to certain antimicrobial classes has been reported recently. Plasmids are an important mechanism contributing to resistance development, mainly due to their potential for being transmitted horizontally. We characterized the plasmid profile and carriage of resistances genes in this dataset. Sequenced genomes were assembled and for identification of plasmid replicons and resistance genes, PlasmidFinder and ResFinder were used. Plasmid identities were further confirmed using MOB-Suite and the location of the genes in putative plasmid contigs confirmed using blast. For those strains containing IncX1 plasmid replicons and AMR genes in the same contig (n=45), sequence similarity was evaluated using blast. A phylogeny was built using a hybrid reference (created from three different plasmid sequences) to confirm identified clusters (Figure 7). In 98 strains both plasmid replicon and AMR genes were detected. In 80 of these both targets were present in the same putative plasmid sequence (82 plasmid sequences with AMR genes and plasmid replicons). Most common plasmid replicons among the 82 sequences were IncX1 (54.32%), Col(pHAD28 (14.81%) and Inc11 (13.58%). After evaluation of sequence similarity of IncX1 sequences six clusters were identified. Two groups (n=19 and n=9) was formed by plasmid sequences of isolates from different countries and

different sources (animal, food and human). All those sequences presented IncX1-IncX3 replicons and a blaTEM-1B. Two other groups presented four animal Spanish strains each. One group presented sequences with IncX1 and blaTEM-1, the other with IncX1 and a MDR genes (aadA1, sul1, dfraA1, tet(A), qacE).

Figure 7. Phylogenetic analysis of plasmid sequences with mapping of AMR genes.

Our comparative genomic analysis revealed the existence of a big international group of plasmid sequences (belonging to IncX1-IncX3 groups and carrying β -lactam resistance genes) in epidemiologically unrelated Enteritidis strains present in humans, animals and food. In addition, three smaller plasmid groups were observed in strains from Spanish animal sources. This suggests the sustained circulation of different IncX1 plasmid variants in Enteritidis.

Source attribution of *Salmonella* Enteritidis using genomic data

Two source attribution models were applied to perform probabilistic assignment of human isolates to a source, a Random Forest Machine Learning (RFML) model which used wgMLST loci (3255 core and 5303 accessory loci) as model features and a Bayesian STRUCTURE model based on cgMLST (3002 core loci) on a dataset comprising 1275 /1102 animal or food strains and 495/511 human strains, respectively. The overall model accuracy for source attribution with RFML after feature reduction was 0.758 (95% CI: 0.730, 0.785) and a kappa value of 0.684 for the training set, and 0.495 (95% CI: 0.439, 0.551) and a kappa value of 0.333 for the test set. Poor accuracy values produced by RFML for the training and in particular the test set stem from the fact that model was not able to distinguish isolates originating from the broiler and the layer primary source classes. The majority of human isolates were attributed by the model to layers (50.7%) followed by 20.6% to broilers, 14.5% to eggs, 10.5% to chicken meat, 3.4% to other sources (mostly turkeys) and 0.2% to poultry isolates of unspecified source. Self-attribution rates were also low or very low for all sources except chicken meat source using STRUCTURE model where majority of the human isolates were attributed to the chicken meat source. The low level accuracy for both models, which operate based on an assumption that each population/source is characterized by a specific set of alleles (RFML)/allele frequencies (STRUCTURE), was most likely due to the inter-source mixing and inability of the models to discriminate isolates from different 'known' populations/sources, mainly due to the genetic similarity of isolates obtained from different sources in this dataset. This was especially true for the isolates originating from broilers and

layers which comprised vast majority of the animal isolate dataset. Using other genetic markers (such as kmers or host adaptation markers) and obtaining a more balanced dataset may improve the prediction power of the future *S. Enteritidis* source attribution models.

WP4-T3 Phylodynamics and phylogeography

Several hypotheses have been made to explain the current non-declining trend of SE. These can be allocated at three main levels: poultry health and production; epidemiology and public health (infra) structure; and pathogen evolution. While the reasons for the changes in SE incidence are likely to be multifactorial and interrelated in nature, the determinants of the recent plateau might be in part explained by the genetic variation of SE. This includes emergence or clonal expansion of specific strains with increased fitness, i.e.: increased bacterial division, increased virulence or antibiotic resistance. In order to elucidate the stagnated SE trend in Europe at the pathogen evolution level, we provide a general overview of the population structure of SE strains to identify major SE lineages. Furthermore, we assessed the long and short-term evolution and the emergence of different SE clones over time, with the aim to identify potential clonal or demographic expansion among ten European countries before and after the SE incidence change in Europe. We detected a small temporal signal within the two clades (figure 8). Which enabled us to do a coalescent skyline model. This confirmed that there had been an increase in the effective bacterial population size prior to 2007 and then a decrease, as expected, however there is no visible plateau (figure 9).

Figure 8 Root to tip divergence for clade 1 (top) and clade 2 (bottom)

Figure 9 Coalescent skyline model showing the increase in effective bacterial population size until around 2007 and then a decrease.

Figure 10. Top two, genetic differentiation between sources. Bottom two genetic divergence between countries. Both calculated by the F_{st} index using the cgMLST profiles. The higher number, the more diverged/differentiated.

There is no large differentiation between sources (figure not shown). There is more differentiation between countries (figure 10). In clade 1 the highest genetic differentiation is between Spain and both Poland and Belgium, followed by France and the United Kingdom. Overall France has the highest divergence. For clade 2 the highest genetic differentiation is between France and especially Poland, but actually all other countries. France is by far the most diverged, followed by the Netherlands. This is also clear to the phylogenetic tree where there are clusters with only French samples, as there are some with only Dutch samples and a few clusters of other country origins.

WP4-T4 Mutant creation and Testing — including GWAS studies

Prophages has been shown to impact evolution of bacteria. In our dataset we detected prophages which are specific for some genetic clusters. The two large clades contained an ST64B-like prophage and an RE2010 prophage. We also detected a smaller cluster closely related to one of the two major clades which contained a Gifsy2-like prophage. In order to determine the impact of these prophages not only on creation of clusters and clades, but also on the fitness of the strains in these clades/clusters, we will knock out the prophages and test the mutants. Work is ongoing in the laboratory to create knock-out mutants of strains containing the three specific prophages and these mutants will be tested in assays regarding growth and stress (pH, salt, bile, minimal nutrient requirements, temperature, oxygen, hydrogen peroxide). Further phenotypic assays will be conducted within the allowed time of the project.

Work performed by associated partner ISZLER

The way *Salmonella enterica* invades and replicates inside the epithelial cells strongly influence gut pathogenesis. It has been observed that phenotypic differences in cells invasion and replication among Enteritidis strains lead to differences in virulence obtained through in-vivo experiments (e.g. in terms of organ invasiveness in chickens). The emergence in recent years of more virulent strains of Enteritidis in Europe could be a contributing factor in explaining the stagnation on the decreasing trend in human salmonellosis due to Enteritidis. In order to test whether there are different virulence phenotypes in the Enteritidis population in Europe, we performed cell culture infection assays with strains belonging to different ST11 clades (i.e. global epidemic and outlier clades). We observed significant differences in invasion and replication both between and within the clades suggesting that phenotypic differences in virulence may frequently emerge within the population (and also within sub-populations and small clusters). In order to further test this observation, we performed a phenotypic assay by infecting epithelial cells with different isolates belonging to the same genomic cluster (corresponding to HC5 = 60189 cluster in Enterobase) from the outlier clade. The cluster was chosen since isolates belonging to HC5 = 60189 was responsible for a large outbreak from Laying Hens in central Italy. Specifically, we performed infection of epithelial cells with isolates which distinguishes between cytosolic and vacuolar bacteria by differential expression. We developed a specific image analysis pipeline to quantify invasion, vacuolar load and cytosolic replication with single cell resolution. The single cell resolution assays showed significant differences in the tested virulence phenotypes within isolates belonging to HC5 = 129197 confirming that strains with different virulence profiles may frequently emerge within the Enteritidis population even in very closely related genetic isolates. Work is ongoing in the laboratory to create single-SNP mutants of strains displaying different virulence profiles to understand the genetic features responsible for the observed phenotypes.

WP5 MCDA model to support priority setting

WP5-T1 Framework building + WP5-T2 MCDA modelling

After years of significant decline, the incidence of *Salmonella enterica* serotype Enteritidis (SE) human infections in Europe has started stagnating in recent years. The reasons for this stagnation remain largely unclear and are possibly multifactorial and interconnected in nature. We assessed and ranked several potential determinants of the stagnating SE trend in Europe, as well as different options for intervention at the level of poultry health and production, public health (infra)structure, and pathogen biology.

A Multi-Criteria Decision-Analysis (MCDA) approach based on the Analytical Hierarchy Process was used. Through two separate surveys, a European panel of Salmonella experts first provided weights for several pre-defined criteria and subsequently scored different potential determinants and options for intervention (i.e. alternatives) against the criteria, during 2020-21 (Fig. 11). The weighting and scoring were based on Saaty's pairwise comparisons. The final ranking of the alternatives was derived from the summation of the products of each criterion weight with the score of the corresponding alternative. Sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the impact of different methodological choices, including European regions, and domains of expertise on the ranking of the determinants and options for intervention.

The first and second-ranked determinants of the stagnated trend in human SE infections were related to poultry health and production, namely “inadequacies of sampling programmes” and “premature relaxation of control measures” (Fig. 12). This ranking agreed with the ranking of the options for intervention, which was also those at the poultry health and production level, specifically “stricter biosecurity”, “improving sampling”, and “better/increased vaccination”. Differences in rankings were observed among European regions and domains of expertise.

The rankings of the potential determinants and options for intervention for the stagnating SE trend in Europe pointed to the level of poultry health and production. Salmonella control activities in poultry in Europe are harmonized across countries for many years, but the results of this study suggest that further improvements may be necessary for some European countries. Yet, a multidisciplinary collaboration among veterinarians, public health professionals, and microbiologists is needed to further understand the origins of the stagnating SE trend and to identify effective interventions in order to reverse it, contextually in a given country.

Fig. 12 Ranking of the determinants (A) and options for intervention (B) of the stagnating trend

This work is described in deliverable D-JRP26FBZ-4-WP5.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7111538>

This work has been submitted as a publication to BMC Public Health as: Linda Chanamé Pinedo, Nina Van Goethem, Panagiotis Mallioris, Ewa Pacholewicz, Roan Pijnacker, Eelco Franz, Lapo Mughini-Gras ; Assessing potential determinants of the stagnating trend in Salmonella Enteritidis human infections in Europe and options for intervention: a multi-criteria decision analysis

2.12.4 Project self-assessment

Both EFSA and ECDC expressed their concerns regarding the fact that the declining trend of salmonellosis cases in the EU has levelled off. Both agencies highlighted the need to “investigate the reasons behind the increase”. In response, the ADONIS project was launched with the main objective to identify determinants underlying the stagnation/reversal of the decreasing trend in Salmonella Enteritidis incidence in the EU. This will provide stakeholders and policy makers with anchor points to at least prevent a continued stagnation or even re-establish a decreasing trend in Salmonella incidence. A diverse group of international experts in epidemiology, microbiology, and genomics from the human as well as the veterinary domain were brought together in the ADONIS consortium. As planned we applied a cross-sectorial approach in which we investigate possible explanatory factors at the levels of primary production, human epidemiology/exposure, and the pathogen itself. No major deviations from the original plan took place. However, the COVID19 pandemic caused some serious delays due to shifting priorities at the participating institutes, leaving the ADONIS project on a lower priority regarding capacity. Nonetheless, the ADONIS project delivered some major new insight in Salmonella epidemiology/microbiology.

Major results: At the epidemiology level we confirmed that the incidence of S. Enteritidis infections is no longer decreasing and even increasing in The Netherlands and Belgium, even after correcting for factors such as changes in age distribution, the proportion of travel-related cases etc.. On an EU scale the number of S. Enteritidis outbreaks are increasing, particularly in Eastern Europe and associated with laying hens / eggs. Neither changes in surveillance systems or changes in human exposure to S. Enteritidis were found likely to explain the observed changes in the S. Enteritidis epidemiology. At the primary production level we identified that, since several farm management approaches differ considerably between locations, much can be gained by optimising sampling strategies to maximise sensitivity in detecting Salmonella. At the pathogen level no strong evidence of a split between populations of S. Enteritidis before and after the stagnating trend in Europe was found. Although

unclear what the implications for epidemiology are, we detected sustained circulation of different IncX1 plasmid (incl. AMR genes) variants in *S. Enteritidis* across Europe. We also identified an emergence in recent years of more virulent strains of *S. Enteritidis* in Europe which could be a contributing factor in explaining the stagnation on the decreasing trend in human salmonellosis due to *Enteritidis*. Finally, based on expert elicitation we determined that the rankings of the potential determinants and options for intervention for the stagnating SE trend in Europe consistently pointed to the level of poultry health and production.

Major recommendations:

- Salmonella control activities in poultry in Europe are harmonized across countries for many years, but the results of this project suggest that further improvements may be necessary for some European countries including stricter biosecurity, improved/optimised sampling, better/increased vaccination, and regular auditing of control programs performance. Regarding the latter, this encompasses defining clear criteria for auditing, including the list of legislation and check-list for country self-evaluation, increased audit intensity and coverage based on a clear transparent algorithm.
- Because of the increase in the incidence of *Salmonella Enteritidis* and the number of outbreaks, as well as potential changes in the pathogen population (e.g. emergence of a more virulent strain), is it of major importance to maintain and improve high quality *Salmonella* surveillance system with state-of-the-art typing methods such as whole-genome-sequencing.
- Both for improving *Salmonella* control, surveillance and outbreak investigation it is of high importance that collaboration is continued in a multidisciplinary and international One Health setting.

2.12.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
23	D-JRP23-WP1.1	Detailed work plan developed (Kick-off meeting minutes)	28	April 20, 2020	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6107451	10
23	D-JRP#-1.2	Y3 report delivered	M39	M39		
23	D-JRP23-WP1.3	Y4 report delivered	M60	M60		
23	D-JRP23-WP1.4	Result dissemination plan developed	M60		Not achieved. Part of this final report and to performed when all results are concise.	
23	D-JRP#-2.1	Report on the evaluation of the questionnaires	M30	M47	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6107543	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
23	D-JRP26-WP2.2	MS's specific analysis of temporal trend of Salmonella in poultry flocks	M42	M52	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6811500	
23	D-JRP26-WP2.3	Recommendations for improving Salmonella surveillance in poultry flocks	M60	M60	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7431578	
23	D-JRP#-3.1	Description of surveillance systems regarding their key elements	M50	M50	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6226393	
23	D-JRP#-3.2	Description of basic epidemiological characteristics of human S. Enteritidis cases and other relevant serovars	M50	M50	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7082442	
23	D-JRP26-WP3.3	Report on the evaluation of the surveillance systems' attributes	M50	M50	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6226393	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
23	D-JRP#-3.4	Extended the report on epidemiological characteristics with results from the rarefaction analysis the refined source attribution models, but also with data on food consumption patterns	M50	M50	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7082442	
23	D-JRP#-3.5	Report on human S. enteritidis exposure in different countries and time periods	M50	M50	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7082418	
23	D-JRP23-WP4.1	Sequence inventory report	M33	M39	Public: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6107789	
23	D-JRP23-WP4.2	List of genetic determinants associated with the change in Salmonella incidence in Europe	M59	M60	Public: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436581	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
23	D-JRP#-5.1	Final assessment frameworks of MCDA	M48	M48	Public: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7111538	
23	D-JRP23 WP5.2	Experts elicitation results for the assessment of weights	M50	M50	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6325485	
23	D-JRP23 WP5.3	Outcomes of the MCDA analysis.	M52	M56	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6786081	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify)

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
23	M-JRP26-1	Kick-off meeting organised	M26	Y	
23	M-JRP26-2	Communication partners mapped	M28	Y	
23	M-JRP26-3	Inventory of documents available for the comparative analyses	M30	Y	
23	M-JRP26-4	Farm survey planed and questionnaires developed		Y	
23	M-JRP26-5	Selection of three countries of which their national S. Enteritidis surveillance systems will be evaluated	M27	Y	
23	M-JRP26-6	Obtained national surveillance data on S. Enteritidis and other relevant serovars	M30	Y	
23	M-JRP26-7	Sequence collection to be shared amongst partners	M38	Y	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
23	M-JRP26-8	Phylogenetic trees describing the sequence collection (D-JRP#-WP4.1)	M60	Y	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.
23	M-JRP26-9	Inventory of MCDA methods suited to the data being collected.	M30	Y	
23	M-JRP26-10	Annual meeting organised	M40	Y	
23	M-JRP26-11	Outline of the assessment framework (transmission chain)	M42	Y	
23	M-JRP26-12	Meeting on aligning epidemiological and QMRA approach	M45	Y	
23	M-JRP26-13	List of candidate strains for phenotype testing	M60		
23	M-JRP26-14	Identification of the experts to participate in the weighting exercise of the MCDA	M42	Y	

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
23	M-JRP26-15	Data finalized for manuscript on Population of Salmonella collection	M48	Y	
23	M-JRP23-16	Final meeting organised	M60	Y	
23	M-JRP23-17	Data finalized for manuscript on Phylodynamics and Phylogeography	M60	Y	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.
23	M-JRP23-18	Data finalized for manuscript on phenotypes	M60	Y	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.
23	M-JRP23-19	Publication of sequence collection on European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)	M60/61	Y	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.

2.12.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Mughini Gras et al 2021, Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human salmonellosis in the Netherlands; <i>Epidemiology & Infection</i> , DOI: 10.1017/S0950268821002557 https://zenodo.org/record/6090653	Published	Yes		Yes (2500 euros)
Nina Van Goethem, An Van Den Bossche, Pieter-Jan Ceyskens, Adrien Lajot, Wim Coucke, Kris Vernelen, Nancy H. C. Roosens, Sigrid C. J. De Keersmaecker, Dieter Van Cauteren, Wesley Mattheus. Coverage of the national surveillance system for human <i>Salmonella</i> infections, Belgium, 2016-2020. <i>PLOS ONE</i> : https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820 https://zenodo.org/record/6090759	Published	Yes		Yes
Samper-Cativiela C., Dieguez-Roda B., Trigo da Roza F., Ugarte-Ruiz M., Elnekave E., Lim S., Hernandez M., Abad D., Collado S., Saez J.L., de Frutos C., Agüero M., Moreno M.A., Escudero J.A., Alvarez J. Genomic	Published	Yes		Yes (1500 GBP)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
characterization of multi drug resistant of Salmonella serovar Kentucky ST198 isolated in poultry flocks in Spain (2011-2017). Microbial Genomics 8(3) doi: 10.1099/mgen.0.000773 https://zenodo.org/record/7082555				
Chanamé Pinedo Linda, Franz Eelco, van den Beld Maaïke, Van Goethem Nina, Mattheus Wesley, Veldman Kees, Bosch Thijs, Mughini-Gras Lapo, Pijnacker Roan. Changing epidemiology of Salmonella Enteritidis human infections in the Netherlands and Belgium, 2006 to 2019: a registry-based population study. Euro Surveill. 2022;27(38). https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.38.2101174 https://zenodo.org/record/7303720	Published	Yes		Yes
Chanamé Pinedo Linda, Lapo Mughini Gras, Eelco Franz, Tine Hald, Sara Pires. 2022. Sources and trends of human salmonellosis in Europe, 2015–2019: An analysis of outbreak data. International Journal of Food Microbiology Volume 379, 16 October 2022,	Published	Yes		Yes

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
109850. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2022.109850 https://zenodo.org/record/7303730				
Linda Chanamé Pinedo, Nina Van Goethem, Panagiotis Mallioris, Ewa Pacholewicz, Roan Pijnacker, Eelco Franz, Lapo Mughini-Gras ; Assessing potential determinants of the stagnating trend in Salmonella Enteritidis human infections in Europe and options for intervention: a multi-criteria decision analysis	Submitted to BMC Public Health	Yes		
Clara Samper-Cativiela, Maria Esther Prieto, Soledad Collado, Cristina de Frutos, Adam Branscum, Jose Luis Saez, Julio Alvarez. Identification of risk factors associated with an increased probability of Salmonella detection in commercial layer flocks in Spain	Submitted	Yes		
Trends of human salmonellosis in Portugal, 2015-2022: increase of S. Enteritidis in the last years	In preparation	yes		

Additional output

Additional output next to scientific publications is listed in section 11 (list of dissemination and communication activities; including for example proceedings and posters)

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

The major outcome of this project is the conclusion that, since we showed increasing incidence in some countries and increased number of outbreaks at the EU level, more efforts should be undertaken to control Salmonella in the EU. Subsequently, we determined that the most relevant anchor points to achieve this point to the level of poultry health and production. More specifically, we recommend to improve the full congruence of audits with the legal requirements, with room for improvement regarding sampling, laboratory testing, reporting, restrictions and measures taken along the food chain (including outbreak analyses), as well as evaluation of NSCPs progress. The auditing might be intensified and improved with clear criteria for MS selection linked with the national scale of poultry production, meeting of community targets, and clear legal criteria for audited areas (i.e. self-evaluation checklist). It would be beneficial to EFSA to take note of these conclusions.

In addition, we highlighted the importance of maintaining and improving a good functioning Salmonella surveillance system at the public health level with state-of-the-art (WGS) typing of isolates in order to efficiently detected clusters/outbreaks. The sharing of this typing data internationally and in a One Health setting is of the utmost importance to tackle cross-border events and to identify (potential) sources as quick as possible in order to prevent outgrowth of clusters/outbreaks. It would be beneficial to ECDC to take note of these conclusions.

Currently, much effort is placed in infectious diseases control preparedness with national and international programs to improve One Health surveillance. It appears that the focus is often not per se on foodborne zoonoses here while this is typically where One Health surveillance is already more developed and where the advantages already have been shown. We recommend to place more focus on foodborne zoonoses in One Health surveillance programs.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Some of the outcomes of this project are taken up by follow-up projects.

- The recommendation to maintain a high quality Salmonella surveillance in adopted by a RIVM initiative to nominate salmonellosis as a notifiable disease in NL.
- The recommendation for One health surveillance with cross-domain data-sharing is followed-up in the DG-Sante funded Joint Action “UNITED4surveillance” with improvements in data sharing within the Netherlands, and with pilot activities in other countries.

2.12.7 One Health impact

The major outcome of this project is the conclusion that, since we showed increasing incidence in some countries and increased number of outbreaks at the EU level, more efforts should be undertaken to control Salmonella in the EU. Subsequently, we determined that the most relevant anchor points to achieve this point to the level of poultry health and production. This makes the problem of Salmonella

a true One Health issue. Lowering the incidence and reducing the number of outbreaks can only be achieved by a joint effort between public health, veterinary health, and food safety domains.

On the public health side we highlighted the importance of maintaining and improving a good functioning Salmonella surveillance system at the public health level with state-of-the-art (WGS) typing of isolates in order to efficiently detect clusters/outbreaks. The sharing of this typing data internationally and in a One Health setting is of the utmost importance to tackle cross-border events and to identify (potential) sources as quick as possible in order to prevent outgrowth of clusters/outbreaks. Data-sharing between public health, veterinary health and food safety domains should be more common than currently is the situation. We strongly urge to move beyond legal hurdles and search solutions for the possibility of data-sharing (which has been shown it is possible in for example The Netherlands).

On the veterinary side there is much room for improvements regarding the execution of national control programs, which is of crucial importance to adequately monitor trends in prevalence at primary production level. More specifically, we recommend to improve the full congruence of audits with the legal requirements, with room for improvement regarding sampling, laboratory testing, and reporting. This will also deliver higher quality data that can be analysed for risk factors regarding Salmonella prevalence. In addition, the auditing might be intensified and improved with clear criteria for MS selection linked with the national scale of poultry production, meeting of community targets, and clear legal criteria for audited areas (i.e. self-evaluation checklist).

In summary, the re-establishment of a decreasing trend in salmonellosis in the EU can only be established by a One Health approach with combined efforts from public health, veterinary health and food safety stakeholders at the national and international level. We especially highlight the importance of finding solutions for data-sharing that will greatly improve the understanding of sources and transmission pathways.

2.12.8 Data Management Plan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436727>

2.12.9 Future dissemination activities

The results of ADONIS (as well as other OHEJP projects) are brought in new projects to be launched in 2023. One of these is the Joint Action Integrated Surveillance where 24 EU member states take part with their public health institutes, supplemented with 11 veterinary institutes. One of the core work packages is One Health surveillance. ECDC is strongly involved in this JA and there is connection to the EFSA mandated initiative on One Health surveillance.

2.13 JRP24-R2-FBZSH9-BeONE

2.13.1 Consortium composition

Project leaders: Sofie Holtsmark Nielsen and Katrine Grimstrup Joensen. Previously Kristoffer Kiil and Claudia Coipan.

WP1 lead Vítor Borges, co-leads Katrine Grimstrup Joensen, Karin Lagesen, Claudia Coipan

WP2 lead Claudia Coipan, co-leads Vítor Borges, Katrine Grimstrup Joensen

WP3 lead Simon Tausch/(Holger Brendebach), co-leads Sofie Holtsmark Nielsen, Adriano Di Pasquale

WP4 lead Sofie Holtsmark Nielsen, co-leads Simon Tausch/(Holger Brendebach), Rolf Sommer Kaas

WP5 lead Katrine Grimstrup Joensen, co-leads Claudia Coipan

WP6 lead Sofie Holtsmark Nielsen, co-leads Vítor Borges, Claudia Coipan, Holger Brendebach

2.13.2 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The ultimate goal of the BeONE project has been to develop integrative solutions, where molecular and epidemiological data for foodborne pathogens can be interactively analysed, visualised and interpreted by experts across disciplines and sectors, thus contributing to a sustainable and more efficient routine surveillance following a One Health approach.

In order to facilitate and enhance the connection between EU laboratories enrolled in the Food and Waterborne Disease (FWD) genomic surveillance, a digital structure for genomic and epidemiological data exchange was developed within BeONE. This structure relies on a harmonised data model that facilitates the bi- or multilateral automated data exchange under legal and GDPR considerations. This is in agreement with the EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) ontology for encoding BeONE epidemiological data and aims at cross-sector harmonisation with the ECDC. The BeONE data model is open to hold additional, non-harmonized information for further exploration. This structure promotes multi-country and intersectoral collaborations towards a One Health approach. To accommodate this structure, the BeONE Datahub has also been developed. This is a server-based web application that can work directly on the database of shared samples and metadata, and that launches ReporTree, a novel surveillance-oriented tool that strengthens the linkage between genomic and epidemiological data by rapidly identifying genetic clusters at any (or all) sample distance thresholds (e.g., for outbreak detection) and generating surveillance-oriented reports for the derived clusters. Noteworthy, besides the proof-of-concept that this tool can be smoothly integrated in other surveillance-oriented workflows, enhancing evidence-informed public-health decision making, ReporTree is also playing a central-role in the BeONE multi-country and inter-sectoral assessment of cluster congruence between the different genomic surveillance pipelines by facilitating and speeding-up the cluster detection and pipeline comparability. Furthermore, a BeONE algorithm to support outbreak detection was modelled and tested on *Listeria* (evaluation still ongoing for the remaining target pathogens).

In interconnection with the Datahub, epidata can be viewed and filtered in tables and geographically placed on a map and phylogenetic trees (with clustering data) can be visualised in the developed BeONE dashboard. Being provided as a standalone desktop tool and independent of a specific backend, the BeONE Dashboard can therefore be used to visualise data from multiple pipelines. The input format builds on the JSON format. .

BeONE might open for the possibility of different European laboratories exchanging data and interactively visualising the derived genetic clusters integrated with epidemiological and geographical data in the BeONE dashboard in compliance with the “lab-to-lab” data transfer agreements. Fully aligned with the One Health concept, BeONE may ultimately promote an enhanced interoperability at multi-country and intersectoral levels towards an evidence-informed public health policy- and decision-making.

2.13.3 Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Typing comparability and nomenclature

WP1-T1 Establishment of state of the art

WP1-T1 aimed to create a hands-on-oriented handbook with the current state-of-the-art within genomics methods for Whole-Genome Sequencing (WGS) typing of the BeONE target species: *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli* and *Campylobacter jejuni*. This task was developed in collaboration with the [ORION](#) project. The final output is the “[One Health Sequencing for Surveillance HandBook](#)”, covering the main technical and practical aspects associated with the application of WGS for foodborne diseases surveillance ([Deliverable 1.1](#)). By following a simple and straightforward writing and structure, this document can be easily understandable by laboratory staff starting in the field, helping national and local laboratories to build capacity and competence on the usage of genomics methods for surveillance purposes.

WP1-T2 Dataset selection and curation

Sub-Task: WP1-T2-ST1 Dataset selection and collection

WP1-T2-ST1 aimed to compile a “BeONE dataset” capturing a wide genomic diversity for the above-mentioned foodborne pathogens, including samples from human, food and veterinary sources, and sets of epidemiologically verified outbreak isolates. NVI’s SAGA server was set-up for data upload, storage and analysis. Guidelines for data upload were provided, including instructions to fill a metadata submission form elaborated using EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) for Controlled Vocabularies (collaboration with WP3). BeONE partners shared sequencing data and metadata for 4,438 isolates, in compliance with a signed Material Transfer Agreement (MTA). Data was anonymized by renaming and shuffling the sequencing reads and files. As this dataset did not cover the expected genetic diversity [assessed in terms of sequence type (ST) or serotype], a complementary dataset (“public dataset”) with 9,740 samples was created to capture the genetic diversity present in public databases.

Sub-Task: WP1-T2-ST2 Quality check and assurance, and genome assembly

Dataset curation involved quality control/filtering of the sequencing reads, confirmation of species identification (and contamination checking), genome assembly and *in silico* typing. From the 4,438 samples shared within BeONE, 3,884 passed the curation step. Their anonymized sequencing reads and genome assemblies were publicly released at ENA and Zenodo, respectively [1,426 *L. monocytogenes* ([PRJEB57166](#) and [7267486](#)); 1,540 *S. enterica* ([PRJEB57179](#) and [7267785](#)); 308 *E. coli* ([PRJEB57098](#) and [7267844](#)); 610 *C. jejuni* ([PRJEB57119](#) and [7267879](#))]. From the 9,740 samples retrieved from public databases, 8,383 passed the curation step and had their genome assemblies publicly released in Zenodo [1,874 *L. monocytogenes* ([7116878](#)); 1,434 *S. enterica* ([7119735](#)), 1,999 *E. coli* ([7120057](#)); 3,076 *C. jejuni* ([7120166](#))]. The combination of the two complementary datasets of each species potentiates the genetic diversity necessary for further tasks ([Deliverable 1.2](#)). Besides their utility for the accomplishment of BeONE tasks, these datasets are expected to represent a useful asset in future surveillance- and research-oriented studies.

WP1-T3 Clustering congruence and thresholds

WP1-T3 aims to i) evaluate the behavior of different surveillance-oriented genomics pipelines in the definition of genetic clusters, through the identification of threshold ranges with high resolution for outbreak detection or stable threshold ranges for nomenclature design (useful for longitudinal surveillance); ii) determine the congruence with traditional typing nomenclatures, such as ST or serovar; iii) identify congruent resolution levels between pipelines, as a way to facilitate international data sharing and cooperation; and, iv) assess the similarities and discrepancies between pipelines in the identification of outbreak-related isolates.

Sub-Task: WP1-T3-ST1 Selection of WGS-based typing methods to be evaluated

All partners confirmed availability to include their routine genomics-surveillance pipeline for foodborne pathogens in the WP1-T3 analysis. Based on provided details for each pipeline, we established a strategy to avoid pipeline redundancy and increase the analysis efficiency. Each partner was responsible to install and run its pipeline on the datasets generated in WP1-T2, with full support of the WP1 team. This exercise counted with a wide variety of pipelines, from multiple countries and sectors (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Summary of the different countries and sectors involved in the BeONE assessment of cluster congruence with indication of the pipeline diversity per country/sector and species.

Sub-Task: WP1-T3-ST2 Assessing clustering congruence between different methods at different hierarchical levels and

Sub-Task: WP1-T3-ST3 Correlating clustering congruence with existing nomenclature schemes

Cluster congruence analysis required clustering information at all possible distance thresholds for each pipeline. However, some pipelines do not reach this resolution level, instead ending-up in intermediate outputs (e.g., allele/SNP or distance matrices) that are explored with non-automated approaches for cluster identification, such as the visual exploration of (large) dendrograms resulting from hierarchical clustering (HC) or Minimum-Spanning Trees (MST) provided by [GrapeTree](#). To facilitate, speed-up and automate this workflow, we developed [ReporTree](#) ([10.21203/rs.3.rs-1404655/v2](#)), a flexible tool that allows diving into the complexity of pathogen diversity to rapidly identify genetic clusters at any (or all) distance threshold(s) and to generate surveillance-oriented reports based on the available metadata. Besides its direct contribution to enhance current surveillance workflows, ReporTree was tailored to answer specific WP1-T3 needs:

Deal with output heterogeneity: ReporTree deals with multiple file formats (SNP/allele or distance matrices, trees/dendrograms, multiple-sequence alignments or VCFs), being able to process the different WP1-T3-ST1 outputs. Noteworthy, ReporTree integrated [vcf2mst](#) to deal with VCF files as result of the collaboration with [COVRIN](#).

Obtain clustering at all possible thresholds: ReporTree automatically determines genetic clusters at all possible distance thresholds using several methods without the need of dendrogram/tree visualization. For instance, we shaped GrapeTree open-source code so that ReporTree can obtain cluster information directly from MSTs (modified version available at [GitHub](#)).

Determine cluster congruence and stability regions: ReporTree assesses several metrics that can be used to compare clustering information at consecutive thresholds of a pipeline (determining regions of stability) or at all thresholds of two methods (determining pipeline comparability). For this, we modified the code of [Comparing Partitions tool](#) (modified version available at [GitHub](#)).

ReporTree benchmarking with the four “public datasets” compiled in WP1-T2 showed that it can be smoothly implemented in routine surveillance workflows, with negligible computational and time costs. Complying with the FAIR principles, ReporTree is freely available in [GitHub](#) under a GPL-3.0 license and at [Docker hub](#). Besides its incorporation in the BeONE datahub (WP4), ReporTree is also integrated in the [COHESIVE](#) platform.

The massive cluster congruence analysis targeting the above-mentioned objectives is still ongoing for the four foodborne bacterial species. Preliminary results show the existence of low stability (*i.e.*, low congruence in cluster composition between subsequent distance thresholds) in the highest resolution region (spanning the “outbreak level”) in each pipeline (Figure 2), followed by “plateau” regions of high stability (*i.e.*, yielding similar cluster composition at distant thresholds), likely reflecting the pathogen population structure. At least for *L. monocytogenes* (ongoing analysis for the remaining species), there is a good concordance between the first large “plateau” of stability and MLST nomenclature in all pipelines. Importantly, the highest concordance between the different thresholds of two pipelines follows a linear tendency, which allows the identification of inter-pipeline correspondence points (*i.e.*, threshold levels/regions with similar clustering). Based on these observations, we anticipate that this study will provide important information regarding the behavior of each pipeline and facilitate the direct comparability of their results. Moreover, as the code used to generate these outputs will be publicly available, it will open the possibility for other institutes to analyze their own methods and assess how they compare to others. This outcome potentiates the impact of this task beyond the BeONE partners, while providing valuable knowledge to facilitate and promote (international) data sharing, cooperation and communication during routine surveillance and outbreak investigation ([Deliverable 1.3](#)).

Figure 2. Example of the comparability of two pipelines using the *L. monocytogenes* dataset. A) Cluster congruence between two allele-based pipelines, with high resolution level (including outbreak region) highlighted in orange (and zoom-in in panel B); C) Dendrogram of allele1 pipeline, with dashed lines connecting the distance to the stability regions observed in A; D) Cluster congruence in the first 200 distance thresholds of six pipelines, with stability regions marked in gray and the highest congruence with ST marked in orange.

WP2: Joining molecular and epidemiological methods

WP2-T1: Conceptualization of epidemiological and biological factors impacting on fine resolution clustering and outbreak detection

A conceptual model of the factors impacting fine resolution clustering and outbreak detection has been made and explained in detail in a draft manuscript which is now undergoing the last revision round with the co-authors. The abstract hereof was submitted as deliverable to Zenodo and the OHEJP online platform (10.5281/zenodo.4476394).

WP2-T2: Integrating genomics with epidemiology

Cluster detection based on WGS often assumes that the various isolates come from a common source and that the source is clonal in nature i.e. the population of the bacterial pathogen at the source is genetically homogeneous. Thus, all the isolates pertaining to a cluster can be traced back to a most recent common ancestor, which, in epidemiological terms, means that patients that share highly similar strains are likely to have contracted these from a common source. Challenges still remain regarding the epidemiological interpretation of WGS. A major point of uncertainty is the definition of clusters. To this end we have developed a multitier algorithm that incorporates concepts of evolutionary biology. For compatibility with the currently used molecular typing system – cgMLST, Hamming distance, and single-linkage hierarchical clustering (sl) – the first step follows this procedure. The use of single linkage combined with a variable number of missing loci for each isolate allows, however, for allelic distances within a cluster much exceeding the predefined threshold of allelic dissimilarities. Furthermore, the structural unit of DNA is not the gene but the nucleotide, which means that allelic distances may be in fact an underestimation of the dissimilarity among isolates. We thus use a second step involving SNP-calling, pairwise Hamming distances, and Gaussian mixture models to split potential multimodal distributions of pairwise dissimilarities, which are often indicative of multiple clusters. Additionally, in a third step we calculate the expected SNP distances between any two or n (multiple coalescent) isolates based on Kingman's coalescent model of shared ancestry. In a fourth step, the comparison of the distribution of observed dissimilarities with the expected one is expressed as the probability that the two or n selected isolates come from a common ancestor in a given timespan. The summarised WP2-T2 deliverable (D2.2) (<https://zenodo.org/record/6375255#.YjmYpjXcCU>). The testing of the algorithm is still ongoing. A final version of the manuscript (D2.4) describing the algorithm and its testing together with broader considerations on the process of clustering is intended for 2023 (the draft can be found on Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.7457825).

WP2-T2-ST1 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates

The 1027 BeONE dataset sequences belonging to four sequence types, are being used for validation.

WP2-T2-ST2 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the Shiga toxin producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) isolates

A total of 863 BeONE dataset sequences are being used for validation.

WP2-T2-ST3 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the *Salmonella enterica* isolates

The 1739 BeONE dataset sequences belonging to three serovars are being used for validation.

WP2-T2-ST4 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the *Listeria monocytogenes* isolates

The 1600 BeONE dataset sequences belonging to five sequence types are being used for validation.

Additionally, we have applied the above mentioned algorithm to a dataset of *Listeria monocytogenes* CC6, containing isolates epidemiologically validated as part of an outbreak in The Netherlands. In our example, the cluster defined with the broad threshold of ten alleles dissimilarity (often used in practice) is subsetting in the second step to a cluster corresponding to seven alleles and in a third step to one corresponding to four alleles difference. Additionally, our analyses indicate that inclusion of WG sequences from other sectors (i.e. food safety) is highly desirable if not mandatory for accurate cluster identification.

WP2-T3: Definition of guidelines for cluster investigation

In developing the algorithm at WP2-T2 (D2.2) (<https://zenodo.org/record/6375255#.YjmYpjXcCUI>) we have used various data sources (e.g. cgMLST and SNP) and methods (e.g. hierarchical clustering, maximum likelihood), and have identified strengths and weaknesses of their usage in daily practice. A comparison of the respective methods as well as prospective improvements to cluster detection are being compiled into a document intended to be finalised in 2023 (draft available on Zenodo 10.5281/zenodo.7457814).

WP3: Storage, management, and sharing for meta- and molecular data

WP3-T1: Evaluate national level data sharing

As discussed at the KOM and described in Task BeONE-WP1-T1 Establishment of state of the art, we decided to base the output of this task on existing literature and bilateral communication. The key hurdles described by project partners at the KOM focused on both technical restrictions and data privacy concerns.

A preliminary state of the art has been taken by the questionnaire conducted in COHESIVE: “Questionnaire on available databases and Information Systems for WGS DATA MANAGEMENT”.

The COHESIVE deliverable D-4.1.2 and D-4.1.3 provides the status of the feasibility studies for sharing, integrating and harmonising WGS data and related epi/metadatas between human and veterinary organisations at member state level. The involved member states are Italy, the Netherlands and Norway.

WP3-T2: Metadata acquisition and standardisation

Subtask: WP3-T2-ST1 Metadata acquisition

The metadata acquisition form was distributed among data submitters for WP1-T2-ST1. The data extraction from the returning forms was automated and information is casted into JSON data structures that are ready for import into the BeONE database via an API (see WP3-T3-ST2). For each sample-related information, where data collection is restricted to controlled vocabularies from the EFSA Data Collection Framework, the superordinate hierarchy of each term is complemented, thus allowing information queries in a non-uniform dataset with varying levels of information provided by data submitters without the need to process Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues.

Subtask: WP3-T2-ST2 Standardization using ontologies

Epidemiological metadata fields are structured using predefined fields. To allow interoperability between institutions, a selection of suitable EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues is used. The included hierarchical connections between terms suffice to use the vocabulary as an ontology system for the purposes of the BeONE system.

The ontology system has been tested when collecting the metadata from WP1-T2-ST1 using the epidemiological metadata collection excel sheet. This concludes Milestone 3.8.

WP3-T3: Database design and implementation

Subtask: WP3-T3-ST1 Determine and implement data structure for database

Database structures have been established for WGS data. Mandatory fields narrow down to cgMLST profile allele hashes, species names, country of origin and year of sampling. Additionally, it is strongly advised to fill a number of optional data fields, including results from Quality Control, computational steps and epidata at a higher spatiotemporal resolution within the limits of an MTA. Database design regarding Epidata has also been finalised. The epidata structure is based on the EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues using preselected fields (see JRP24-WP3-T2-ST2). The metadata implementation allows to combine the hierarchical terms of the DCF catalogues in a tag-like fashion to improve their joint descriptive accuracy. Each hierarchical term is stored as a term lineage within the data model including hierarchical level information to improve automated filtering and annotation of phylogenetic models. The BeONE data model has been incorporated into the SSI Bifrost database structure to benefit from Bifrosts MongoDB metadata handlers. Nevertheless, the BeONE module is independent of other Bifrosts modules tailored to the requirements of SSI, e.g. WGS data computation. A documentation of the database setup is available at the BeONE API repository (https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone).

Subtask: WP3-T3-ST2 Implement API for import of data

Due to personnel changes at SSI, where the API was to be developed as part of the Bifrost system, we redesigned the data import structure, as also mentioned in JRP24- WP4-T3. As a proof-of-concept, data from local partners will be transformed into JSON files following the data structure determined in JRP24- WP3-T3-ST1. Data will then be exported, symmetrically encrypted, sent to partners and then decrypted on their end to add it to their local database.

In detail, the BeONE API repository (https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone) provides scripts to import from and export to the BeONE JSON format. These scripts serve as a bridge between the BeONE MongoDB and the BeONE dashboard until live database queries are established (see JRP24-WP3-T3-ST6).

Data in transit as well as in public databases may be encrypted in a field- and detail-specific manner to preserve privacy and to control the information exchange between partners. Bilateral data sharing agreements determine the level of detail that can be decrypted and used for epidemiological analyses. For epidata described by terms of the EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues, each hierarchical level is paired with a cryptographic key to allow a fine-grained control over shared information. Scripts for en-/decryption, keyring generation and field filtering are available and documented in the BeONE API repository.

Data exchange between distributed BeONE MongoDBs is facilitated by automated repeated execution of synchronisation scripts to allow surveillance with a minimum of lag time. An implementation of this system was presented to BeONE partners during the BeONE workshop held at the SSI in June 2022.

Subtask: WP3-T3-ST3 Data porting from an existing pipeline

The WGS assembly and quality control pipeline AQUAMIS (<https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12050644>) as well as the cgMLST-based clustering pipeline chewieSnake (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.649517>) were adapted to output analysis results in a BeONE compatible JSON data structure. The outputs from these pipelines can be imported into the BeONE MongoDB database without further changes.

Subtask: WP3-T3-ST4 Data porting from further pipelines

The BeONE data model was designed with compatibility to a number of different pipelines in mind. The highest congruency in harmonisation was achieved with the EFSA WGS data model. Its development coincided with the finalisation of the BeONE data model and yielded reciprocal

refinement. This cooperation is still ongoing until finalisation of the EFSA WGS data model. As a second compatible example pipeline, the outputs of SSI's Bifrost Pipeline will be ported into the BeONE system. Development of this latter bridge has started.

Subtask: WP3-T3-ST5 Expansion of the API for referencing/exporting of entries in other reference databases

Due to both time and trouble with the ENA API we have chosen to cancel this task. It will be moved to sustainability.

Subtask: WP3-T3-ST6 Expansion of the API for queries from the dashboard WP4

The BeONE Datahub (WP4-T4) contains its own API for communicating with the MongoDB database.

WP3-T4: National data sharing pilot

Along with the development of the BeONE data exchange system, the national data sharing pilot was preferred and slightly readjusted. In collaboration with FLI, isolates of *Salmonella enterica* serotype Dublin were exchanged between the BfR and the FLI, responsible for Food Safety and Animal Health respectively. Data was clustered using cgMLST based on ChewieSnake and cgSNPs. Cluster congruence was determined. A publication on this work is planned. Additionally, German federal state public health agents were trained in the usage of a WGS surveillance platform that featured data collection in the BeONE data model format via the BfR pipelines AQUAMIS and ChewieSnake. In this workshop, held at the LGL Oberschleißheim in May 2022, the BeONE MongoDB was presented as an automated information exchange system while emphasising the ease of data submission to superordinate agencies for surveillance on the national and European level.

WP4: Development of a user-oriented interface (dashboard) for analysis and sharing of epi and molecular data

Web-based user interface for analysis and sharing of epi and molecular data.

BeONE Dashboard is 'Just a dashboard'. It works as a standalone desktop application that can open and view files in the BeONE JSON format provided by WP3. It is easy to install and use, but depends on a pipeline that can generate files in the appropriate JSON format (plus a tree in Newick format).

BeONE Datahub is a full web application which can read a MongoDB database (structured in the BeONE MongoDB schema provided by WP3). BeONE Datahub is a multi-user tool and provides more functionality than BeONE Dashboard. As a server-based application it takes some time and technical skills to get it up and running; however, it offers a more automated workflow than the BeONE Dashboard, and provides automatic identification of clusters, taking advantage of ReporTree functionality (WP1-T3).

WP4-T1 Dashboard

The dashboard was developed as a standalone application that can be downloaded and installed on the user's own computer. This means that the software is 'backend-agnostic' and can be utilised with different backend systems. This standalone application supports Windows, MacOS, and Linux computers and all major web browsers in recent versions. The source code for the BeONE Dashboard is available under the Apache open source licence version 2.0 and is published on GitHub: <https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard>

The dashboard visualises sample metadata in a table and a map. A phylogenetic tree (in Newick format) can also be visualised. Furthermore, it is possible to filter the metadata of the samples.

Subtask: WP4-T1-ST1 Core display components

These core display components have been developed:

Data Sources view: This component enables the user to load BeONE JSON data files into the dashboard.

Field Editor: This component makes it possible to search for data within the loaded BeONE JSON files and pick interesting data for showing in the dashboard. All data in the JSON files can be picked this way allowing the user to determine the data of interest. Furthermore, the Field Editor can impose basic filtering on the selected data fields for further narrowing down interesting parts of a data set.

Table View: This component shows the selected data set in a tabular fashion and features selecting/deselecting individual samples. It also has a feature for selecting all samples in the current filtering (or all samples in the dataset if no filtering is applied).

Tree View: A Newick file containing a phylogenetic tree with the same sample ID's as the JSON files is required for this component. If such a file is loaded into the dashboard, it will show the samples in a tree view. Selecting and deselecting individual samples can be done here as well as in the Table View, and the selection state is shared between the two components.

Geographic View: This component plots the samples in a geographic map based on latitude/longitude metadata.

Subtask: WP4-T1-ST2 Component integration

Much effort has been put into creating a structure that makes the components interoperate with each other. More specifically, this means that:

The components share a common data structure

The components share a common state for which samples are selected – i. e., you can select or deselect a sample in any of the components and the selection state will be shared by all components.

WP4-T2 Back end analysis implementation

With the software architecture that was chosen for the BeONE project and the feature set that was chosen for WP4, it was generally not relevant to integrate back-end analysis tools as part of WP4 (as most of the analysis back-end is independent of WP4). The only exception is ReporTree, which is described below.

WP4-T3 Cluster analysis and collaboration tool

At the technical workshop at SSI in June 2022, it was decided to incorporate ReporTree in the Datahub. This integration allows the rapid identification of genetic clusters at any (or all) distance thresholds and the generation of surveillance-oriented reports, while providing all the files (trees, metadata with clusters) necessary for Dashboard visualization.

WP4-T4 Data sharing front end

The data sharing front-end has now been dubbed 'BeONE Datahub'. With this web application, which has to be installed locally for each institute.

With the BeONE datahub it is possible to:

View sample metadata for both own samples and samples imported from other institutes using the data exchange tools produced by WP3.

Run the integrated analysis tool (ReporTree) on both own and external samples (and combinations thereof).

View cluster analysis results and other results provided by the analysis tool.

The source code for BeONE Datahub is available under the Apache open source licence version 2.0 and is published on GitHub on this url: <https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-datahub>.

Subtask: WP4-T4-ST1 Web-based input system

Besides the JSON import, described above, a data import utility has been made for BeONE Datahub that imports allele profiles and metadata from TSV files of types that are normally users within the genomic analysis domain. This utility broadens the scope of the data sharing front end so it can be used even without having pipelines that produce data directly in the BeONE JSON format.

Subtask: WP4-T4-ST2 Import/Export front end for reference databases

Due to time, personnel and the chosen software architecture this had to be cancelled.

Subtask: WP4-T4-ST3 BeONE data exchange system

Due to time, personnel and the chosen software architecture this had to be cancelled.

WP5: Dissemination, Testing, Evaluation and Sustainability

WP5-T1 Dissemination

Detailed instruction manuals and guidelines are made available for data input and output, as well as guidelines for data interpretation, sharing etc. Much of this is output provided by the respective WPs. With these guidelines and instructions a straightforward interpretation of molecular and epidemiological data by the users (spanning different sectors and countries) will be possible using the dashboard. As there are many separate steps, various instruction manuals are provided covering the overall development achieved in the BeONE project. Instructions are provided for each part considering both data input to the system, data output and data interpretation.

Instructions related to the BeOne dashboard:

These instructions are available at <https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard> where all the dashboard documentation is collected in a wiki including a step-wise guide to install the dashboard (D.5.1):

<https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard/wiki/Installing-BeONE-Dashboard>.

Furthermore, an installation (youtube) tutorial was also prepared as part of the instructions used for the participant testing of the dashboard and the hands-on exercise held at the workshop in June 2022. This tutorial is part of (D.5.3) and available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eEaD9donwIO>

Two additional youtube tutorials (D.5.3) are available on how to import data to the dashboard (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QKynHd-Sx5c>) and how to filter the data using the dashboard (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6IsRdFSC0js>).

Instructions related to the BeOne data hub:

At the datahub sample metadata can be viewed, samples from other institutes imported and the integrated ReporTree can be run from which clustering results etc. can be viewed allowing comparison of phylogenetic relations between isolates (across institutions, countries etc.)

All documentation for the datahub is available here: <https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-datahub> and for ReporTree here: <https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>

Documentation related to the BeOne analysis pipelines and database:

All necessary documentation for the BeOne database design is available at the BfR gitlab (https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone), including database structure and the API

repository providing scripts for importing/exporting to the BeONE JSON format, which is the format bridging the BeONE MongoDB and the BeONE dashboard. The decentralised database setup and instructions for installation on public servers is available at the repository wiki pages (https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone/-/wikis/home). The manuals were tested by the participants of the hands-on exercise held at the workshop in June 2022.

The documentation for the adaptation of the WGS assembly and quality control pipeline AQUAMIS and the cgMLST-based clustering pipeline chewieSnake to the BeONE compatible JSON data structure is available from:

- AQUAMIS: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/AQUAMIS
- chewieSnake: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/chewieSnake

Furthermore, the metadata parsing is available from https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/beone-metadata-parsing

WP5-T2 Continuous Testing and Feedback

Extensive testing, feedback and evaluation has been performed during the project period to ensure a final dashboard which is user-friendly and thus employable by users from different sections that have different requirements for specific features for data analysis and interpretation. The development was guided towards a tool meeting the specific needs of both the public health side and the food/vet side to allow for a tool useful in surveillance and outbreak detection.

Internal testing of all developed components was performed extensively before proceeding with the user testing. This includes features of the dashboard, datahub, data sharing and analysis tools that are incorporated into the BeONE workflow.

Subtask: WP4-T2-ST1 Development of a detailed test framework

The entire BeONE consortium served as test framework, and the dashboard was tested both during technical meetings as well as by the partners individually using the generated surveys.

Subtask: WP4-T2-ST1 Continuous Testing of the platform

The user testing was coordinated between SSI and RIVM. Surveys were made in Google forms and sent to all BeONE participants.

The first survey aimed at obtaining feedback on the dashboard installation and additionally on user-friendliness of instructions, administrative rights restrictions, suggestions of Operating Systems platforms, and dependency packages errors. The installation survey is located here:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe30Zv_9smtY4kscJvQ1WXIpbktvGGq6j7v12Bn9HZJHg4Mw/viewform

The form contained instructions to find the program and install it, as well as a link to the video tutorial for installation: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eEaD9donwI0>

The second survey aimed at obtaining feedback on the filtering features of the dashboard, in particular insights on how to make relevant sample and metadata filtering were obtained. For testing, a testset consisting of ten samples in JSON format, one tree file in newick format, and two additional JSON files used to illustrate how the dashboard would report errors (such as samples with missing metadata).

The filtering survey is located at:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScloFgW4xmzI-nbex6VNV5n6-ecnma11BhUC0XleOx-V_DkGA/viewform

The form contained link to the two tutorials for testing:

- How to load the dashboard again <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QKynHd-Sx5c>
- How to filter data <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6lsRdFSC0js>

WP5-T3 Final evaluation

The final evaluation was postponed to autumn 2022, as the project was extended. The Final evaluation will be performed as part of the Final Meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark on december 13th -14th. Here a final workshop with a hands-on exercise using the system developed in BeOne will be tested and evaluated. The conclusions from this final testing will be delivered in the Final evaluation report (D5.4)

WP5-T4 Sustainability

Key requirements for sustainability of the dashboard and analysis system have been identified during the project as good documentation of the system, and an open source organisation around the system to carry on the collaborative work after the project ends.

At the end of the project a final sustainability document will be created, describing the possibilities.

WP6: Management

WP6-T1 Management

Virtual monthly meetings for all partners and in a shorter period the last year also biweekly technical meetings to discuss such details more thoroughly.

WP6-T2 Communication

Subtask: WP6-T2-ST1 Kickoff meeting

Kickoff meeting was held at RIVM the 16-17 January 2020.

Subtask: WP6-T2-ST2 2nd Annual Meeting

2. Annual meeting was held virtually, due to corona restrictions, 28th of October 2021.

Subtask: WP6-T2-ST3 3rd Annual Meeting

The third annual meeting will be held 13-14 December 2022 at SSI.

Subtask: WP6-T2-ST4 Development hackathon

A technical workshop hosted at SSI the 27th-28th of June 2022. Representatives from each WP presented their work and BfR did their final handover as well as a workshop to test it (as BfR will not be an active partner for the extension of BeONE).

WP6-T3 Data Management

We have used google docs for sharing documents and presentations. Zenodo for deliverables and the NVI server SAGA for sharing sequencing data.

2.13.4 Project self-assessment

A large part of the initial project objectives were met, however some with modifications. Many deliverables were delayed during the project due to the COVID-19 pandemics. As intended, integrated surveillance tools were developed for interactive analysis of molecular and epidemiological data for selected foodborne pathogens, tailoring their functionality and applicability to different disciplines and sectors. By having researchers involved that were part of the JIP ORION, the BeONE project was able to build on the knowledge and recommendations obtained from this former project.

The initial plan was to implement algorithms for integration of genomic and epidemiological data as well as integrate existing components of bioinformatic tools within a dashboard. However, this had to be solved in a different way due to a change of staff which made it impossible to implement as planned. Instead the dashboard was constructed to make use of already generated data by importing it as a JSON format developed in WP3 and visualise and interpret in the developed backend independent dashboard and datahub - a web based server with an API to the database that also integrates ReportTree.

The front-end features provided by the BeONE dashboard can facilitate comparisons of the various and commonly used WGS-typing outputs such as MLST, serotype, AMR markers etc. Furthermore, the dashboard can visualise phylogenetic relations by importing newick files enabling the use of either SNP or cgMLST analysis for establishing phylogenetic relations. The end result is a well-functioning dashboard that is less restricted in analysis setup, but does require a certain format of import data.

According to the objectives, cluster agreement between different WGS-based typing approaches was assessed as part of the project, providing valuable knowledge to facilitate and promote (international) data sharing, cooperation and communication during routine surveillance and outbreak investigation.

During the development the BeONE consortium concluded that the fact that the dashboard is independent of the backend is actually advantageous in the way that the users are not restricted to a specific backend that will very likely change within a short time frame (few years), thus potentially making the system able to function without major modifications for a longer time.

Originally the cross-sectoral collaboration at the local, national and international level enabling sharing of data in a flexible way i.e. allowing for confidentiality of certain data when needed was intended to be possible through the dashboard. This is obtained with the BeONE data format developed in WP3 and integrated in the Datahub.

The lesson learned from this part is that an ambitious, overarching project like BeOne has taken more time than estimated, and that the specific skill set of the participating developers will somewhat dictate the development process. Thus it has been essential to be adaptive and change plans on the go. Making it all fit together has proven a huge task, and for future projects like this it would be a great advantage to build on already established pipelines, structures etc. and thoroughly researching other possibilities, pros and cons, and reaching out to other institutes who use it.

2.13.5 Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
24	D-BeONE.1.1	Report on the state-of-art	M30	M39	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5155570 Scope changed to avoid duplication of work with ORION, and mitigate delays due to COVID-19.	4
24	D-BeONE.1.2	Finalized BeONE dataset	M48	M48	Public https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5808832	3
24	D-BeONE.1.3	Report with clustering congruence results	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7445805	4
24	D-BeONE.2.1	Draft manuscript on the conceptual model	M34	M36	Public (D-BeONE.2.1 Draft conceptual model of factors impacting genomic clustering Zenodo) https://zenodo.org/record/4476394#.YUC8MThDtM2	4
24	D-BeONE.2.2	Final Outbreak detection algorithm	M48	M50	https://zenodo.org/record/6375255#.YjmYpjXcCU	4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
24	D-BeONE.2.3	Final Guidelines	M60	M60	https://zenodo.org/record/7457814#.Y6Bs8OTMKUK	4
24	D-BeONE.2.4	Draft manuscript on outbreak detection algorithm and guidelines	M60	M60	https://zenodo.org/record/7457825#.Y6BsXOTMKUK	4
24	D-BeONE.3.1	Report on national data sharing pilot	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7458008	5
24	D-BeONE.4.1	Back-end analysis pipeline	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://zenodo.org/deposit/7457034	4
24	D-BeONE.4.2	Web input system	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://zenodo.org/deposit/7457043	4
24	D-BeONE.4.3	Final BeONE system	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://zenodo.org/deposit/7457064	4
24	D-BeONE.5.1	Instruction for local installation of dashboard	M60	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7380271#.Y4cmisuZM2w	4
24	D-BeONE.5.2	Software list	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://zenodo.org/deposit/7438688	4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
24	D-BeONE.5.3	Tutorial	M60	M60	Public https://zenodo.org/record/7380300#.Y4coMcuZM2w	4
24	D-BeONE.5.4	Final evaluation report	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://zenodo.org/deposit/7438727	4
24	D-BeONE.5.5	Final sustainability document	M60	M60	Will be deposited here before end of the year: https://zenodo.org/deposit/7438745	4
24	D-BeONE.6.1	Initial data management plan	M30	M33	Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497853#.YToRjxlxdaQ	8, management

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JI P Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
24	M-BeONE.1.1	State-of-the-art completed	M30	yes	
24	M-BeONE.1.2	Collected dataset	M30	yes	
24	M-BeONE.1.3	Curated WGS dataset completed	M51	yes	
24	M-BeONE.1.4	Agreement on the methods/solutions to evaluate	M30	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.1.5	Clustering congruence analysis completed	M60	yes	
24	M-BeONE.2.1	The critical factors for outbreak detection have been identified	M32	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.2.2	Outbreak detection algorithm -provisional version	M42	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.2.3	Guideline proposal	M60	yes	

JRP/JI P Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
24	M-BeONE.3.1	Agreement on minimal and optimal set of metadata	M28	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.2	Finalized evaluation of data sharing experiences	M34	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.3	Implementation of data structure	M52	yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.4	Finished implementation of controlled data entry	M36	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.5	Plan for ontology implementation	M36	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.6	Implementation of API for import of data	M52	yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.7	Data porting from an existing pipeline	M42	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.8	Application of the selected ontology system(s)	M54	yes	
24	M-BeONE.3.9	Data porting from at least one further pipeline	M42	yes	

JRP/JI P Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
24	M-BeONE.3.10	Expansion of the API for export functionality	M54	-	Cancelled due to changed structure of data collection (no raw data provided). No other tasks are affected.
24	M-BeONE.3.11	Expansion of the API for queries from the dashboard	M60	yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.1	Initial requirement list from workshop at kick-off meeting	M26	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.2	Implementation plan	M28	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.3	Prototype dashboard	M53	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.4	Plan for data sharing system	M34	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.5	Basic system for display component integration	M40	yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.6	Cluster analysis and collaboration tool ready for testing	M58	yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.7	Import/Export front end for reference databases implemented	M58	-	Change of plans for dashboard construction

JRP/JI P Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
24	M-BeONE.4.8	Dashboard in workable condition for Final Evaluation workshop	M58	yes	
24	M-BeONE.4.9	BeONE data exchange system implemented	M60	-	Change of plans for dashboard construction
24	M-BeONE.5.1	Simulated international outbreak at 3rd annual meeting	M60	yes	Reduced to a smaller exercise that tested both the datahub and the dashboard
24	M-BeONE.5.2	Yearly sustainability document	M60	yes	
24	M-BeONE.5.3	Initial test plan	M28	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.5.4	Overall evaluation at 2nd annual meeting (workshop)	M40	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.6.1	2nd annual meeting	M40	Yes	
24	M-BeONE.6.2	3rd annual meeting	M60	yes	

2.13.6 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Prediction of antimicrobial resistance in clinical <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> isolates from whole-genome sequencing data 10.1007/s10096-020-04043-y https://zenodo.org/record/4249355#.X6UnVWhKjcc		Yes		3825
ReporTree: a surveillance-oriented tool to strengthen the linkage between pathogen genetic clusters and epidemiological data (INSA and IZSAM)	Submitted	Yes		?
Multi-country and intersectoral assessment of cluster congruence between different genomic surveillance pipelines (ALL BEONE PARTNERS AS AUTHORS)	Under preparation	Yes		~1200
Pathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> spp. and <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. in Two natural Conservation Centers of Wildlife in Portugal: Genotypic and Phenotypic Characterization (INSA in collaboration with EJP DISCOVER project) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7341097	Published	Yes		Yes (but publication fee was not paid by BeONE)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>Clonal relation between Salmonella enterica subspecies enterica serovar Dublin strains of bovine and food origin in Germany.</p> <p>Jörg Linde¹, Istvan Szabo², Simon H. Tausch², Carlus Deneke², Ulrich Methner^{1*}</p> <p>¹Institute of Bacterial Infections and Zoonoses, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institute, Jena, Germany</p> <p>²German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, Berlin, Germany</p>	To be submitted	Yes		~600
Use of whole genome sequencing in epidemiological surveillance – why do we do the things that we do	Under preparation	Yes		1500
Conceptual model of clustering for outbreak detection – back to the basics	Under preparation	Yes		1500
New perspective from retrospective analysis of outbreaks	Under preparation	Yes		1500

Additional output

Pre-print publications:

1. Mixão V, Pinto M, Sobral D, Di Pasquale A, Gomes JP, Borges V (2022) ReporTree: a surveillance-oriented tool to strengthen the linkage between pathogen genetic clusters and epidemiological data. Research Square. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1404655/v2>

Poster presentations:

1. Mixão V, Pinto M, Sobral D, Di Pasquale A, Gomes JP, Borges V (2022) ReporTree: a surveillance-oriented tool to strengthen the linkage between pathogen genetic clusters and epidemiological data. 3º Dia Jovem Investigador INSA (08/11/2022). Lisboa, Portugal

2. Mixão V, Pinto M, Gomes JP, Borges V. ReporTree: a surveillance-oriented tool to strengthen the linkage between pathogen genetic clusters and epidemiological data. 32nd ECCMID (23-26/04/2022). Lisboa, Portugal

Tools:

<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>

<https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard> for the installation of the dashboard as well as the following youtube tutorials:

- How to install the dashboard (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eEaD9donwI0>
- How to load the dashboard again (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QKynHd-Sx5c>
- How to filter data (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6IsRdFSCOjs>

- Available documentation for the WP3 pipelines for analysis:
- BfR Gitlab: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone
- Metadata parsing: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/beone-metadata-parsing
- AQUAMIS: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/AQUAMIS/-/tree/hb_json_schema
- chewieSnake: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/chewieSnake/-/tree/jsonexport

Wiki:

<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree/wiki>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Tools:

ReporTree: <https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>

An automated and flexible pipeline that can be used for multiple pathogens for the automatic detection of genetic clusters and their linkage to epidemiological data, in a concept aligned with “One

Health” perspectives. For instance, this tool can facilitate the identification of main circulating lineages and rapidly characterize them with any data of interest, such as antimicrobial resistance data. Furthermore, its flexibility can contribute to speed-up genomics-informed surveillance, facilitating and accelerating the production of surveillance-oriented reports. ReporTree benchmarking demonstrated that this tool can be smoothly implemented in routine surveillance bioinformatics workflows, with negligible computational and time costs. ReporTree resource can easily be integrated in start-to-end platforms for genomics/epidemiological analysis (for instance, it is integrated in the COHESIVE Information System and the BeONE dashboard), thus contributing to a sustainable and efficient genomics-informed pathogen surveillance in the fields of public health and food safety.

<https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard> for the installation of the dashboard as well as the following youtube tutorials:

How to install the dashboard (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eEaD9donwI0>

How to load the dashboard again (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QKynHd-Sx5c>

How to filter data (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6IsRdFSCOjs>

Available documentation for the WP3 pipelines for analysis:

- Decentralised DBs - setup and data exchange: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone
- Metadata parsing: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/beone-metadata-parsing
- AQUAMIS: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/AQUAMIS
- chewieSnake: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/chewieSnake

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

ReporTree: <https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>

ReporTree has already been implemented in the routine surveillance of multiple pathogens at INSA, including bacterial and viral pathogens. For instance, it is implemented in the workflow for genomic surveillance of *L. monocytogenes*, being routinely applied to identify potential listeriosis outbreaks, and is currently being tested for application in the genomics surveillance of other important bacterial pathogens (*Neisseria* spp. and *Mycobacterium* spp.). Furthermore, it was integrated in SARS-CoV-2 surveillance to accelerate and automatize the assessment of the frequency of multiple sub-lineages per week and it is being applied to identify mutations and clusters of interest during the ongoing Monkeypox outbreak investigation. Although ReporTree is currently available as a command line tool, proof-of-concept was generated showing that this resource can easily be integrated in start-to-end pipelines/platforms for genomics/epidemiological analysis. Besides its integration in the BeONE Datahub/Dashboard, it is already integrated in the [COHESIVE](https://onehealth.jp/jip-cohesive/) (<https://onehealth.jp/jip-cohesive/>) Information System.

2.13.7 One Health impact

The BeONE project has helped to build a network of experts spanning different sectors to discuss different ways of doing surveillance and how to share data between different institutes. The different pipelines for WGS-based surveillance have furthermore been compared in the BeONE project to

highlight the comparability of results between different institutes (WP1). The outcome of the pipeline comparison and differences in surveillance setup is important knowledge that can be advantageous for other future developments with One-Health surveillance setups.

Additionally, ReporTree was developed as part of BeONE to facilitate the detection of genetic clusters and their linkage to epidemiological data, in a concept aligned with “One Health” perspectives. This tool can be useful for other parties, not only for routine phylogenetic analysis through distinct WGS-based surveillance systems, but also to promote/accelerate the direct comparability of their results. These outcomes are potentiated by ReporTree standalone open sourced release, as well as by its current integration in the BeONE Datahub/Dashboard and in the [COHESIVE](#) Information System, solutions that can facilitate and promote (international) data analysis and sharing, cooperation and communication during routine surveillance and outbreak investigation at multi-country and inter-sectoral levels..

A conceptual model of the clustering and a simulation-based algorithm for bacterial evolution have been built (WP2). These emphasise the need for flexible thresholds in clustering used to detect outbreaks. Furthermore, they emphasise the need for increased cooperation among the OneHealth sectors and experimental studies to broaden the understanding of bacterial population dynamics in various niches and food-processing chains.

An ontology system with predefined epidemiological metadata fields has been created for the BeONE system, which is interoperable with the EFSA Data Collection Framework catalogues (WP3). The samples and metadata are shared via encrypted JSON files and not dependent on a specific backend, it is therefore possible for many different institutes or the like to create these files for sharing in the BeONE data format.

A backend-independent dashboard has been developed for visualising both sample metadata and a phylogenetic tree. As it is backend-independent all can use it as long as they can convert their data into the JSON format needed or have tsv files (WP4).

A datahub has also been developed where it is possible to choose from the shared samples and make a distance matrix and phylogenetic tree based on these samples and visualised in the dashboard (WP4).

BeONE enables faster and easier data sharing between different institutes, animal or human. Though decisions on cgMLST scheme and harmonisation is needed. As well as a means to get the correct JSON format.

BfR and FLI already have had a national pilot for data sharing (WP3-T4) and they will continue with the data sharing after BeONE ends. Components from BeONE will also be incorporated into the Danish project SOFI (data sharing between SSI and the Danish food authorities).

In summary, the BeONE project resulted in tools and outputs that are expected to i) contribute to the capacitation of EU laboratories to carry out routine surveillance integrating both genomic and epidemiological data, ii) launch new research lines to improve FWD (food and waterborne diseases) genomic epidemiology, and iii) facilitate data sharing and comparability among EU countries, international organisations, and/or other stakeholders involved in FWD prevention and control. Fully aligned with the One Health concept, BeONE may ultimately promote an enhanced interoperability at multi-country and intersectoral levels towards an evidence-informed public health policy- and decision-making.

[2.13.8 Data Management Plan](#)

<https://zenodo.org/record/7457598#.Y8EpOnbMJvg>

2.13.9 Future dissemination activities

The stakeholders for the BeONE project outputs are primarily the institutions performing typing and surveillance of foodborne pathogens; either on a national level such as the specific partner countries, or institutions with a more international interest such as ECDC and EFSA. Some outputs of the project, primarily specific tools, will also be relevant for stakeholders working with genomic data in other settings; for instance university researchers.

In BeONE the dissemination has primarily been focused on making everything that was developed open source and available in different github/gitlabs to ensure interested parties could get access (also in the future). Outputs have also been disseminated through a few conferences and the POC/PMC meeting. Furthermore, the harmonization of ontologies has been developed through close contact with EFSA.

In 2023, the expected dissemination from the BeONE consortium will be a number of scientific publications that will provide some visibility of the project outcomes. Furthermore, parts of the project will live on as integrations into active surveillance systems (national data sharing in Germany and Denmark) and as part of other projects (COHESIVE). Otherwise no major dissemination activities have been planned from the BeONE consortium.